

XX ISA World Congress of Sociology

Melbourne, Australia | June 25-July 1, 2023

Melbourne Convention and Exhibition Centre

Resurgent Authoritarianism: *Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics, and Economies*

World Congress
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- Dr Sylvia Ang, *Contesting Chineseness. Nationality, Class, Gender and New Chinese Migrants*, Amsterdam University Press (2022).
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Acknowledgement of Country

The place known as Australia comprises the traditional estates of over 250 First Nations language groups. For nearly 50 years now, Australians have increasingly formally recognised the importance of Country and First Nations peoples' relationships and protocols for conducting business in Country. Acknowledging Country shows respect for the Country, and the First Nations' continuing connections to Country.

TASA and the ISA 2023 World Congress, too, wish the cultural protocols to be known to all and observed. The Country we meet on for this World Congress is called Narrm. It is the home of the Kulin Nation Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung people. We acknowledge their sovereignty and pay our respects to their elders and ancestors. To learn more, please visit www.aiatsis.gov.au.

Welcome

Welcome Address by the President of the International Sociological Association

Sari Hanafi

We are finally meeting in person. Once we eventually decided to change the date of this XX ISA World Congress of Sociology many questions remained: Should it be online, hybrid, or in-person? Who could not make it? Who would still be fearful of coming too close to others? After almost three years of online meetings due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this major in-person event appears as a historic moment.

It is a great pleasure for me to welcome you, sociologists from all over the world, to our XX ISA World Congress of Sociology. This twentieth anniversary is unique for our international community to celebrate.

It is unique for two reasons: First, 81 years after our first Congress, which started with a limited number of participants and Research Committees, it now gathers thousands of sociologists from all over the globe and keeps striving to ensure better diversity and inclusivity (in terms of region, career stage and gender). The regularity of these congresses demonstrates the capacity of the ISA to build a bridge between different scientific communities, even during the Cold War. Part of my presidential project during these five years has been to work on the specificity of this twentieth edition: the Global Mapping of Sociologists, along with all ISA past Congresses and Forums' abstracts of sessions and their presenters' details are available online. Two reports were also commissioned to study plenaries at past congresses and examine the development of some Research Committees, their changing forms and contents in terms of topics, theories and methodologies, publications, as well as the nature of National Associations' participation in congresses. Additionally, our Academic Writing Workshops are here to enhance the participation of young researchers from the Global South, not only in our congresses but also in ISA publications.

This XX Congress is also unique for being our first hybrid one, setting forward new rules for reducing our carbon footprint in a digital, post-COVID, sustainability-oriented age. We envisaged different scenarios, but the outcome has been most encouraging, with more than 6,400 accepted abstracts. The Program Coordinators did a great job assessing the submissions.

When we chose the theme for this Congress, *Resurgent Authoritarianism: Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics, and Economies*, authoritarianism was not

as widespread as it is now, including in the Global North. Its growth has been facilitated by the gradual “symbolic thickening” of public culture through combinations of extreme nationalist and religious fervor, notably when a national conservative project replaces the liberal political project, and public reason becomes incapable of dealing with either a unified conception of justice or different conceptions of the good in society. With more hierarchical polarization in society, we live in a time when reasonable public debate is often impossible. These are demagogical times animated by the vertiginous rise of populism and many levels of misunderstanding between the religious and the secular, in our scholarship and media, and in their relationship to politics, economy, and culture. Religiosity is increasing in many regions, and secularism has become, in

some countries, a civic religion against other religions, particularly those of populations originating from migration.

The Congress program has been the subject of many meetings of the Program Committee. The Local Organizing Committee, headed by Dan Woodman, has shouldered tremendous logistic work. I want to thank them all. After long deliberations by the Program Coordinators and ISA Executive Committee members and thanks to the terrific work of our Executive Secretary Izabela Barlinska and her team, we have ended up with a wonderful program, with most speakers present.

Sari Hanafi
President, International Sociological Association

Discours de bienvenue du Président de l'Association internationale de Sociologie

Nous voilà enfin réunis en personne. Une fois la décision prise de changer la date de ce XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'ISA, de nombreuses questions étaient restées en suspens : Fallait-il organiser un congrès virtuel, hybride ou présentiel ? Qui ne pourrait pas venir ? Qui restait réticent à s'approcher trop près des autres ? Après près de trois années de réunions en ligne en raison de la pandémie de Covid-19, cet important rendez-vous en présentiel apparaît comme un moment historique.

Je suis très heureux de vous accueillir, vous qui êtes des sociologues venus du monde entier, à notre XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'ISA. Ce vingtième anniversaire est remarquable, et ce pour deux raisons.

D'abord parce que, 81 ans après son premier congrès, qui avait rassemblé un nombre limité de participants et de comités de recherche, l'ISA réunit aujourd'hui pour cette XX^e édition des milliers de sociologues du monde entier, avec toujours le souci d'assurer une plus grande diversité et une meilleure inclusion du point de vue géographique, de l'étape de la carrière et du genre. La régularité des congrès de l'ISA démontre la capacité de l'Association à jeter un pont entre les différentes communautés scientifiques, et ce même pendant la guerre froide. Une partie de mon projet présidentiel au cours de ces cinq années a consisté à travailler dans ce sens, avec d'une part le *Global Mapping of Sociologists*, une « cartographie mondiale des sociologues », et d'autre part la mise en ligne des résumés de tous les Congrès et Forums passés de l'ISA. Deux rapports ont par ailleurs été commandés pour étudier les plénières des congrès passés et analyser l'évolution, tant au niveau de la forme que des contenus, des sujets, des théories, des méthodologies et des publications de certains comités de recherche, ainsi que la nature de la participation des associations nationales aux congrès. Des ateliers d'écriture

académique sont également proposés pour favoriser la participation des jeunes chercheurs des pays du Sud global, non seulement aux congrès de l'ISA mais aussi à ses publications.

Ce XX^e congrès est également remarquable car c'est notre premier congrès hybride, établissant de nouvelles règles pour réduire notre empreinte carbone pour une ère numérique post-Covid orientée vers la durabilité. Nous avons envisagé différents scénarios, mais les résultats ont été très encourageants, avec plus de 6400 résumés acceptés. Les coordinateurs du programme ont fait un excellent travail d'évaluation des soumissions.

Lorsque nous avons choisi le thème de ce Congrès, *Résurgence de l'autoritarisme : Sociologie des nouveaux enchevêtrements entre religions, politique et économie*, l'autoritarisme n'était pas aussi répandu qu'aujourd'hui, y compris dans les pays du Nord global. Sa progression a été facilitée par « l'épaississement symbolique » progressif de la culture publique produit par des combinaisons de ferveur extrême à la fois nationaliste et religieuse – notamment lorsqu'un projet national conservateur vient remplacer le projet politique libéral, et que la raison publique devient incapable d'envisager une conception unifiée de la justice ou différentes conceptions du bien dans la société. Dans un contexte de plus forte polarisation hiérarchique de la société, nous vivons une époque où un débat public raisonnable est souvent impossible. L'heure est à la démagogie, encouragée par la montée vertigineuse du populisme et par les multiples niveaux d'incompréhension entre religieux et laïcs, à travers nos travaux et à travers les médias, et dans la relation qu'ils entretiennent avec la politique, l'économie et la culture. La religiosité augmente dans de nombreuses régions du monde, tandis que la laïcité est devenue, dans certains pays, une religion civique

dressée contre les autres religions, notamment celles des populations issues de l'immigration.

Le programme du Congrès a fait l'objet de nombreuses réunions du Comité de Programme. Le Comité local d'Organisation, dirigé par Dan Woodman, a réalisé un énorme travail logistique. Je tiens à tous les remercier. Après de longues délibérations des coordinateurs du programme et des membres du Comité exécutif de l'ISA, et grâce à

l'excellent travail de notre secrétaire exécutive Izabela Barlinska et de son équipe, nous avons mis sur pied un formidable programme et pouvons compter sur la présence ici à Melbourne de la plupart des intervenants.

Sari Hanafi,
Président de l'Association internationale de Sociologie

Discurso de bienvenida del Presidente de la Asociación Internacional de Sociología

Por fin nos encontramos en persona. Cuando finalmente decidimos cambiar la fecha de este XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la ISA, muchas preguntas quedaron por responder: ¿Debería ser en línea, híbrido o presencial? ¿Quién no podría venir? ¿Quién seguiría teniendo miedo de acercarse demasiado a los demás? Después de casi tres años de reuniones en línea debido a la pandemia de COVID-19, este gran evento presencial aparece como un momento histórico.

Es un gran placer para mí darles la bienvenida a nuestro XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la ISA. Este vigésimo aniversario es notable para nuestra comunidad internacional de sociólogos y sociólogas, por dos razones.

En primer lugar, 81 años después de su primer Congreso, que reunió un número limitado de participantes y Comités de Investigación, la ISA reúne ahora en esta vigésima edición a miles de sociólogos y sociólogas de todo el mundo, siempre con el objetivo de lograr una mayor diversidad e inclusión desde el punto de vista geográfico, de la etapa profesional y del género. La regularidad de estos congresos demuestra la capacidad de la ISA para tender puentes entre diferentes comunidades científicas, incluso durante la Guerra Fría. Parte de mi proyecto presidencial durante estos cinco años ha sido trabajar en esta dirección, con el *Global Mapping of Sociologists*, una "cartografía mundial de sociólogos", y la publicación de los resúmenes de todos los Congresos y Foros anteriores de la ISA.

También se han encargado dos informes para analizar las sesiones plenarias de congresos pasados y la evolución, tanto en forma como en contenido, de los temas, teorías, metodologías y publicaciones de algunos Comités de Investigación, así como la naturaleza de la participación de las Asociaciones Nacionales en los congresos. También se ofrecen talleres de escritura académica para fomentar la participación de jóvenes investigadores del Sur Global, no sólo en los congresos de la ISA sino también en sus publicaciones.

Este XX Congreso también es notable por ser nuestro primer congreso híbrido, que establece nuevas reglas para reducir nuestra huella de carbono en una era digital, post-COVID y orientada a la sostenibilidad. Preveíamos

diferentes escenarios, pero el resultado ha sido de lo más alentador, con más de 6.400 resúmenes aceptados. Los coordinadores del programa han hecho un gran trabajo evaluando las propuestas.

Cuando elegimos el tema de este Congreso, *Autoritarismo resurgente: sociología de las nuevas interrelaciones entre religión, política y economía*, el autoritarismo no estaba tan extendido como ahora, incluso en el Norte Global. Su progresión se ha visto facilitada por el "engrosamiento simbólico" gradual de la cultura pública a través de combinaciones de fervor nacionalista y religioso extremo, especialmente cuando un proyecto conservador nacional sustituye al proyecto político liberal y que la razón pública se vuelve incapaz de lidiar con una concepción unificada de la justicia o diferentes concepciones del bien en la sociedad. En un contexto de mayor polarización jerárquica en la sociedad, vivimos en una época en la que un debate público razonable es a menudo imposible. Estos son tiempos demagógicos, favorecidos por el vertiginoso auge del populismo y los múltiples niveles de incomprensión entre religiosos y laicos, en nuestra academia y medios de comunicación, y en su relación con la política, la economía y la cultura. La religiosidad está aumentando en muchas regiones del mundo, y el laicismo se ha convertido, en algunos países, en una religión cívica contrapuesta a otras religiones, especialmente las de las poblaciones de origen inmigrante.

El programa del Congreso ha sido objeto de muchas reuniones del Comité de Programa. El Comité Organizador Local, encabezado por Dan Woodman, ha realizado un enorme trabajo logístico. Quiero darles las gracias a todos ellos. Tras largas deliberaciones de los Coordinadores del Programa y los miembros del Comité Ejecutivo de la ISA, y gracias al valioso trabajo de nuestra Secretaria Ejecutiva Izabela Barlinska y su equipo, hemos logrado un programa fantástico, que cuenta con la presencia de la mayoría de los ponentes aquí en Melbourne.

Sari Hanafi,
Presidente de la Asociación Internacional de Sociología

Alpha Possamai-Inesedy

Welcome Address by the President of The Australian Sociological Association

Welcome to the XX International Sociological Association's (ISA) World Congress of Sociology hosted by The Australian Sociological Association (TASA) in the vibrant city of Narrm/Melbourne, Australia! We are honoured to welcome you to this beautiful city and to acknowledge that the Congress will be on the unceded lands of the Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung people of the Kulin Nation. TASA acknowledges their living culture and their unique role in the spiritual, social, economic, and environmental well-being of this land. We pay our respect to Elders, past, present and emerging and extend that respect to all First Nations peoples taking part in the Congress.

We are delighted to gather sociologists from all corners of the globe, in person and virtually, to engage in thought-provoking discussions, share insights, and contribute to the theme of this year's conference *Resurgent Authoritarianism: Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics, and Economies*. As we embark on this journey, we are proud to be hosting the Congress in a country that is currently undergoing an important democratic process – the Voice Referendum.

The Voice Referendum in Australia is a significant step towards achieving constitutional recognition and advancing the rights of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. This referendum seeks to provide a formal mechanism for their voices to be heard and to empower them in shaping decisions that affect their lives and communities. It is an opportunity to address historical injustices and work towards a more inclusive and equitable society.

As participants in this Congress, we have the privilege of gathering at a time when Australia is actively engaging in this transformative process. We encourage you to reflect on the importance of constitutional recognition and its implications for social research, policy development, and community engagement.

The ISA World Congress of Sociology provides a unique platform for the work of Australian sociology. The almost 800 members of TASA belong to 26 thematic groups that demonstrate our commitment to interdisciplinary collaboration, critical analysis, applied research, and social justice. Australian sociology makes important contributions to understanding and addressing complex social issues both domestically and globally. TASA's official journal – the *Journal of Sociology* – showcases this scholarship in all its forms.

While you engage in critical discussions and explore the research presented here, we also invite you to take the time to learn about and reflect upon the historical and contemporary experiences of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in Australia. Narrm/Melbourne, known as the cultural capital, offers numerous opportunities to engage with Indigenous cultures, artworks, and stories.

We hope that this Congress will be a catalyst for new ideas, collaborations, and transformative actions. Through conversations and the sharing of knowledge, we aim to foster meaningful connections and inspire positive change both within academia and in the wider society.

Welcome to Narrm/Melbourne and welcome to the XX ISA World Congress of Sociology – we are excited to host you.

***Alpha Possamai-Inesedy
President, The Australian Sociological Association
Professor of Sociology, Pro Vice Chancellor Engagement and Advancement,
Western Sydney University***

Message de bienvenue de la Présidente de l'Association australienne de Sociologie

Bienvenue au XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'Association internationale de Sociologie (ISA) organisé par l'Association australienne de Sociologie (TASA) dans la ville dynamique de Narrm/Melbourne, en Australie ! C'est pour nous un honneur de vous accueillir dans cette belle ville et de rappeler que le Congrès se déroulera sur les terres non cédées du peuple Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung de la nation Kulin. TASA reconnaît la culture vivante et le rôle unique de ce peuple dans le bien-être spirituel, social, économique et environnemental de cette terre. Nous rendons hommage aux anciens, d'hier, d'aujourd'hui et de demain, et étendons ces marques de respect à toutes les personnes des Premières Nations qui participeront au Congrès.

Nous nous réjouissons de réunir des sociologues des quatre coins du monde, en personne et virtuellement, pour participer à des discussions stimulantes, partager leurs idées et contribuer au thème de la conférence de cette année, *Résurgence de l'autoritarisme : Sociologie des nouveaux enchevêtrements entre religions, politique et économie*. Nous sommes également fiers d'accueillir ce Congrès dans un pays qui connaît actuellement un important processus démocratique, le *Voice Referendum*.

Ce référendum sur la voix autochtone marque en Australie une avancée majeure sur la voie de la reconnaissance constitutionnelle et la défense des droits des peuples aborigènes et insulaires du détroit de Torres. Ce référendum vise à mettre en place un mécanisme formel permettant aux Aborigènes et aux insulaires du détroit de Torres de faire entendre leur voix et de prendre part aux décisions qui affectent leur vie et leur communauté. C'est l'occasion de remédier à des injustices historiques et d'œuvrer en faveur d'une société plus inclusive et plus juste.

Les participants à ce Congrès ont ainsi le privilège d'être réunis à un moment où l'Australie s'engage activement dans ce processus de transformation. Nous vous encourageons à réfléchir à l'importance de la reconnaissance constitutionnelle et à ses implications pour la recherche sociale, l'élaboration de politiques et l'engagement communautaire.

Le Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'ISA constitue une plateforme unique pour le travail des sociologues australiens. TASA compte près de 800 membres actifs dans 26 groupes thématiques, témoignant de notre engagement en faveur de la collaboration interdisciplinaire, de l'analyse critique, de la recherche appliquée et de la justice sociale. La sociologie australienne contribue de façon importante à la compréhension et à la résolution de problèmes sociaux complexes, tant au niveau national que mondial, et le journal officiel de TASA, *Journal of Sociology*, reflète bien sa diversité.

Vous allez avoir ici l'occasion de participer à des échanges critiques et de découvrir les recherches présentées. Mais nous vous invitons également à prendre le temps d'en savoir plus et de réfléchir sur les expériences historiques et contemporaines des Aborigènes et des insulaires du Détroit de Torres en Australie. Narrm/Melbourne, connue comme la capitale culturelle du pays, offre de nombreuses occasions d'entrer en contact avec les cultures, les œuvres d'art et les histoires autochtones.

Nous espérons que ce Congrès servira de catalyseur à de nouvelles idées, collaborations et actions transformatrices. À travers les conversations et le partage des connaissances, nous cherchons à favoriser des liens qui comptent et à inspirer des changements positifs, dans le monde universitaire aussi bien que dans la société en général.

Bienvenue à Narrm/Melbourne et au XX^e Congrès mondial de sociologie de l'ISA. Nous sommes ravis de vous accueillir.

Alpha Possamai-Inesedy
Présidente de l'Association australienne de Sociologie (TASA)
Professeure de sociologie, Présidente responsable de l'engagement de la promotion, Western Sydney University

Discurso de bienvenida de la Presidenta de la Asociación Australiana de Sociología

Bienvenidos y bienvenidas al XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la Asociación Internacional de Sociología (ISA), organizado por la Asociación Australiana de Sociología (TASA) en la vibrante ciudad de Narrm/Melbourne, Australia. Es un honor darles la bienvenida a esta hermosa ciudad y reconocer que el Congreso se celebrará en las tierras no cedidas del pueblo Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung de la nación Kulin. TASA reconoce su cultura viva y su papel único en el bienestar espiritual, social, económico y medioambiental de esta tierra. Expresamos nuestro respeto a los Ancianos, pasados, presentes y por venir así como a todas las personas de las Primeras Naciones que participan al Congreso.

Estamos encantados de reunir a sociólogos y sociólogas de todos los rincones del mundo, presencialmente y virtualmente, para entablar debates que inviten a la reflexión, compartir ideas y contribuir al tema de la conferencia de este año, *Autoritarismo resurgente: sociología de las nuevas interrelaciones entre religión, política y economía*. También quiero destacar que nos enorgullece acoger el Congreso en un país que está actualmente viviendo un importante proceso democrático, el Voice Referendum.

Este referéndum para dar voz a la población indígena de Australia supone un gran paso adelante hacia el reconocimiento constitucional y la defensa de los derechos de los pueblos aborígenes e isleños del Estrecho de Torres. Busca proporcionar un mecanismo formal para que los aborígenes e isleños del Estrecho de Torres hagan oír su voz y participen en las decisiones que afectan a sus vidas y comunidades. Es una oportunidad para abordar injusticias históricas y obrar por una sociedad más inclusiva y justa.

Los participantes en este Congreso tienen el privilegio de reunirse en un momento en el que Australia está activamente comprometida en este proceso de transformación. Les animamos a reflexionar sobre la importancia del reconocimiento constitucional y sus implicaciones para la investigación social, el desarrollo de políticas y el compromiso comunitario.

El Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la ISA ofrece una plataforma única para el trabajo de los sociólogos australianos. Los casi 800 miembros de TASA pertenecen a 26 grupos temáticos que demuestran nuestro compromiso con la colaboración interdisciplinar, el análisis crítico, la investigación aplicada y la justicia social. La sociología australiana contribuye de manera importante a comprender y abordar cuestiones sociales complejas tanto a nivel nacional como mundial, y la revista oficial de TASA, *Journal of Sociology*, pone de relieve su diversidad.

Mientras participan en debates críticos y descubren la investigación que aquí se presenta, también les invitamos a que dediquen tiempo a conocer y reflexionar sobre las experiencias históricas y contemporáneas de los pueblos aborígenes e isleños del Estrecho de Torres en Australia. Narrm/Melbourne, conocida como la capital cultural, ofrece numerosas oportunidades para relacionarse con las culturas, obras de arte e historias indígenas.

Esperamos que este Congreso sea un catalizador de nuevas ideas, colaboraciones y acciones transformadoras. A través de conversaciones y del intercambio de conocimientos, pretendemos fomentar conexiones significativas e inspirar cambios positivos tanto en el mundo académico como en la sociedad en general.

Les deseamos a todos y a todas la bienvenida a Narrm/Melbourne y al XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la ISA: estamos encantados de recibirles.

Alphia Possamai-Inesedy
Presidenta de la Asociación Australiana de Sociología
Catedrática de Sociología, Vicerrectora de Participación y Promoción, Western Sydney University

Dan Woodman

Jo Lindsay

Welcome from the Congress Local Organising Committee Co-Conveners

It is wonderful to have you join us for the XX ISA World Congress of Sociology. Melbourne is called Narm in the local First Nations language and our meeting place is on the unceded lands of the Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung people of the Kulin Nation. First Nations people have been coming together to discuss ideas on the land on which we meet for over 40,000 years. We pay our respect to the Elders, past and present, of the Kulin nation and to all First Nations elders and people taking part in the Congress.

The Australian Sociological Association (TASA) was awarded hosting rights in mid-2016, and much has happened in the intervening seven years. During the Covid-19 pandemic we questioned whether we would be able to share our remarkable city with you and the Congress was delayed by a year. So, if you are joining us in-person, we are delighted to finally welcome you to Melbourne!

The heart of this Congress will be the many intellectual contributions made in the hundreds of sessions and thousands of papers being delivered across the week. The great variety of topics is held together by our prescient Congress theme, chosen by ISA President Sari Hanafi, of *Resurgent Authoritarianism: The Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics, and Economies*. We hope you get to see some of your favourite scholars present and discover the early career sociologist who will become one of your new favourites. We wish you luck choosing what to attend among the many options and do encourage you to attend the four Australian Thematic Sessions and other sessions featuring Australian sociologists during the Congress.

It is our pleasure to thank the key people who played a role in making the Congress a reality. Joining us on the Local Organising Committee were Netta Bromdal, Brendan Churchill, Catherine Hastings, Kim Humphrey, Sonia Martin, Theresa Petray, Alpha Possamai-Inesedy, Brady Robards, and Georgia Van Toorn. Anna Halafoff, Shanthi Robertson, and Katie Hughes were also members of the committee at earlier points. In particular, we want to acknowledge Katie's leadership in TASA's bid to host the Congress. TASA's Indigenous Portfolio leader Joann Schmitter also offered the LOC invaluable advice on numerous occasions. Thank you also to Sari Hanafi, and the Congress Program Committee, the ISA Executive Committee, ISA's Council of National Associations and Research Council and TASA's Executive Committee. Planning this Congress in the context of the pandemic involved difficult decisions for the ISA and TASA and the members of these decision-making groups approached these challenges with empathy, professionalism, and a level head.

Thank you to the teams at Confex and Arinex who provided the professional support needed to put on an event this size. Thank you also to the team at the Melbourne Convention Bureau who supported our bid to host the Congress and to our sponsors, particularly the State Government of Victoria for their generous support. Finally, we are sincerely grateful to Izabela Barlinska and the team in the ISA office, and to our esteemed colleague Sally Daly, the Executive Officer at TASA, for the incredible effort, professionalism and patience.

Social connection is a crucial part of ISA events, and particularly so as we come together both in-person and virtually, for many of us in our first meeting with colleagues in many years. Our city is famous for its laneways, covered in street art, its cultural life and cultural diversity along with its great food and coffee. For those attending in person, we hope you get to experience some of our wonderful city during your time with us in Narm/Melbourne.

***Dan Woodman and Jo Lindsay
Co-Conveners, XX World Congress of Sociology Local Organising Committee***

Message de bienvenue des co-présidents du Comité local d'Organisation du Congrès

WELCOME

Message de bienvenue des co-présidents du Comité local d'Organisation du Congrès

Nous nous réjouissons de pouvoir vous compter parmi nous à l'occasion de ce XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'ISA. Melbourne s'appelle Narm dans la langue locale des Premières Nations, et notre lieu de rencontre se trouve sur les terres non cédées du peuple Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung de la nation Kulin. Cela fait plus de 40.000 ans que les membres des Premières Nations se retrouvent pour échanger des idées sur les terres sur lesquelles nous nous trouvons aujourd'hui réunis. Nous souhaitons rendre hommage aux Anciens, d'hier et d'aujourd'hui, de la nation Kulin, et à tous les anciens et membres des Premières Nations venus participer à ce Congrès.

L'Association australienne de Sociologie (TASA) s'est vu confier l'organisation du Congrès au milieu de l'année 2016, or il s'est passé beaucoup de choses depuis. Pendant la pandémie de Covid-19, nous nous sommes demandé si nous serions en mesure de vous accueillir dans notre merveilleuse ville, et le Congrès a finalement été reporté d'un an. Si vous y assistez en personne, nous sommes donc ravis de pouvoir enfin vous accueillir ici à Melbourne !

Le cœur de ce Congrès sera constitué par toutes les contributions intellectuelles apportées au cours des centaines de sessions et des milliers de communications qui seront présentées tout au long de la semaine. Les divers sujets abordés s'articulent autour du thème prémonitoire du Congrès, choisi par le Président de l'ISA, Sari Hanafi, *Résurgence de l'autoritarisme: Sociologie des nouveaux enchevêtrements entre religions, politique et économie*. Nous espérons que vous aurez l'occasion de rencontrer en personne certains des chercheurs qui vous intéressent le plus et que vous en découvrirez de nouveaux parmi la jeune génération de sociologues. Nous vous souhaitons de bien choisir vos activités parmi les nombreuses options disponibles et vous encourageons à assister aux quatre sessions australiennes thématiques et aux autres sessions auxquelles participeront des sociologues australiens tout au long du Congrès.

Nous souhaitons remercier les principales personnes qui ont contribué à ce que ce Congrès devienne réalité. Netta Bromdal, Brendan Churchill, Catherine Hastings, Kim Humphrey, Sonia Martin, Theresa Petray, Alpha Possamai-Inesedy, Brady Robards et Georgia Van Toorn ont pris part au travail du Comité local d'Organisation. Anna Halafoff, Shanthi Robertson et Katie Hughes ont également été membres du Comité à des étapes précédentes. Nous tenons en particulier à souligner le

rôle de premier plan joué par Katie dans la candidature de TASA pour accueillir ce Congrès. Joann Schmider, responsable des affaires indigènes de TASA, a également offert au Comité local d'Organisation de précieux conseils à de nombreuses reprises. Merci également à Sari Hanafi, au Comité de Programme du Congrès, au Comité Exécutif de l'ISA, au Conseil des Associations Nationales et au Conseil de la Recherche de l'ISA, ainsi qu'au Comité Exécutif de TASA. Pour les deux associations, la planification de ce congrès dans le contexte de la pandémie a impliqué des décisions difficiles, qui ont été abordées avec empathie, professionnalisme et sérénité par leurs organes de décision.

Merci aux équipes de Confex et d'Arinex qui ont apporté le soutien professionnel nécessaire à l'organisation d'un événement de cette envergure. Merci également à l'équipe du *Melbourne Convention Bureau* qui a soutenu notre candidature pour accueillir le Congrès, et à nos partenaires, en particulier le gouvernement de l'État de Victoria pour son généreux soutien. Enfin, nous sommes sincèrement reconnaissants à Izabela Barlinska et à l'équipe du secrétariat de l'ISA, ainsi qu'à notre chère collègue Sally Daly, responsable exécutive de TASA, pour leur extraordinaire travail, leur professionnalisme et leur patience.

Le lien social est un élément essentiel des rendez-vous de l'ISA, a fortiori lorsque nous nous réunissons avec des collègues à la fois en personne et virtuellement, pour beaucoup d'entre nous pour la première fois depuis des années. Notre ville est célèbre pour ses ruelles investies par le street art, sa vie culturelle et sa diversité culturelle, ainsi que pour sa gastronomie et son café. Nous espérons que ceux d'entre vous qui êtes venus assister au Congrès en personne auront l'occasion de connaître un peu notre merveilleuse ville de Narm/Melbourne.

Dan Woodman et Jo Lindsay
Co-présidents du Comité local d'Organisation du XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie

Bienvenida de los coordinadores del Comité Organizador Local del Congreso

Es maravilloso tenerles con nosotros en el XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la ISA. Melbourne se llama Narrm en la lengua local de las Primeras Naciones y nuestro lugar de reunión está en las tierras no cedidas del pueblo Wurundjeri Woi Wurrung de la Nación Kulin. Los pueblos de las Primeras Naciones llevan más de 40.000 años reuniéndose para debatir ideas en las tierras en las que estamos ahora reunidos. Presentamos nuestros respetos a los ancianos, pasados y presentes, de la nación Kulin y a todos los ancianos y miembros de las Primeras Naciones que participan en el Congreso.

La Asociación Australiana de Sociología (TASA) fue seleccionada a mediados de 2016 para organizar este Congreso, y han pasado muchas cosas desde entonces. Durante la pandemia de COVID-19 nos preguntamos si seríamos capaces de acogerles en nuestra maravillosa ciudad, y el Congreso quedó finalmente aplazado un año. Así que, si nos acompaña hoy en persona, ¡estamos encantados de darles por fin la bienvenida a Melbourne!

El corazón de este Congreso serán las numerosas contribuciones intelectuales realizadas en los cientos de sesiones y miles de ponencias que se presentarán a lo largo de la semana. La gran variedad de cuestiones que se tratarán se mantiene unida por el tema premonitorio del Congreso, elegido por el Presidente de la ISA, Sari Hanafi, *Autoritarismo resurgente: sociología de las nuevas interrelaciones entre religión, política y economía*. Esperamos que tengan la oportunidad de conocer en persona a algunos de los investigadores que más les interesan y que descubran otros nuevos entre la generación más joven de sociólogos. Les deseamos suerte a la hora de elegir a qué asistir entre las muchas opciones disponibles y les animamos a asistir a las cuatro Sesiones Temáticas Australianas y a otras sesiones en las que participen sociólogos australianos durante el Congreso.

Queremos dar las gracias a las principales personas que han contribuido a hacer realidad este Congreso. Se unieron a nosotros en el Comité Organizador Local Netta Bromdal, Brendan Churchill, Catherine Hastings, Kim Humphrey, Sonia Martin, Theresa Petray, Alpha Possamai-Inesedy, Brady Robards y Georgia Van Toorn. Anna Halafoff, Shanthi Robertson y Katie

Hughes también formaron parte del Comité en etapas anteriores. Nos gustaría agradecer especialmente el liderazgo de Katie para impulsar la candidatura de TASA para acoger el Congreso. Joann Schmider, responsable de los asuntos indígenas de TASA, también ofreció al Comité Organizador Local su valiosísimo asesoramiento en numerosas ocasiones. Gracias también a Sari Hanafi, al Comité del Programa del Congreso, al Comité Ejecutivo de la ISA, al Consejo de Asociaciones Nacionales y al Consejo de Investigación de la ISA, y al Comité Ejecutivo de TASA. Para ambas asociaciones, la planificación de este Congreso en el contexto de la pandemia supuso decisiones difíciles, que sus órganos de decisión supieron abordar con empatía, profesionalidad y sensatez.

Gracias a los equipos de Confex y Arinex, que nos han proporcionado el apoyo profesional necesario para organizar un evento de esta envergadura. Gracias también al equipo del *Melbourne Convention Bureau*, que apoyó nuestra candidatura para albergar el Congreso, y a nuestros patrocinadores, en particular al Gobierno del Estado de Victoria, por su generoso apoyo. Por último, estamos realmente agradecidos a Izabela Barlinska y al equipo del secretariado de la ISA, y a nuestra estimada colega Sally Daly, Directora Ejecutiva de TASA, por su increíble esfuerzo, profesionalidad y paciencia.

La interacción social es una parte crucial de los eventos de la ISA, y más aún cuando nos reunimos, tanto en persona como virtualmente, para muchos de nosotros por primer vez en años. Nuestra ciudad es famosa por sus callejuelas, su arte callejero, su vida cultural y su diversidad cultural, y también por su estupenda gastronomía y café. Esperamos que los que han venido a asistir al Congreso en persona tengan la oportunidad de conocer un poco nuestra maravillosa ciudad de Narrm/ Melbourne.

***Dan Woodman y Jo Lindsay
Coordinadores del Comité Organizador Local del XX
Congreso Mundial de Sociología***

Message from the Lord Mayor of Melbourne

Sally Capp

The City of Melbourne is honoured to welcome you to the XX International Sociological Association World Congress of Sociology, hosted by the Australian Sociological Association.

You couldn't have picked a better destination for a week of inspired discussion and debate.

Melbourne is proud to be a knowledge city – we've worked hard to cultivate a thirst for connection, collaboration and innovation, and we're home to two of the world's top 100 universities.

As a city we are constantly evolving, which makes this the perfect arena to unleash your big, bold and brave ideas.

We know humanities, arts and social sciences – politics, philosophy and more – are what propels our society forward, and it is a privilege to host professionals of your standing.

We cannot wait to welcome you to our city for the official programming, and to see you indulge in Melbourne's world-renowned food, fashion, events, arts and music scene while you're here with us.

I hope you come away from the experience feeling invigorated.,

Sally Capp
Lord Mayor, City of Melbourne

Message de la maire de Melbourne

C'est un honneur pour la ville de Melbourne de vous accueillir au XX^e Congrès Mondial de Sociologie de l'Association internationale de Sociologie, organisé par l'Association australienne de Sociologie.

Vous n'auriez pas pu choisir de meilleure destination pour une semaine de discussions et de débats inspirés.

Melbourne est fière d'être une ville propice à la connaissance : nous avons beaucoup œuvré pour cultiver la soif de connexion, de collaboration et d'innovation, et abritons deux des 100 universités les mieux classées du monde.

Notre ville est en constante évolution, ce qui en fait un lieu idéal pour donner libre cours à vos grandes, audacieuses et courageuses idées.

Nous savons que les sciences humaines, les arts et les sciences sociales – la science politique, la philosophie et bien d'autres domaines encore – sont ce qui fait avancer notre société, et c'est un privilège d'accueillir des spécialistes de votre niveau.

Nous sommes impatients de vous accueillir dans notre ville pour la programmation officielle de ce Congrès et de vous voir profiter pendant votre séjour parmi nous de sa gastronomie, sa mode, ses activités et sa scène artistique de renommée mondiale.

J'espère que vous ressortirez ressourcés de cette expérience.

Sally Capp
Maire de la Ville de Melbourne

Mensaje de la Alcaldesa de Melbourne

Es un honor para la ciudad de Melbourne darles la bienvenida al XX Congreso Mundial de Sociología de la Asociación Internacional de Sociología, organizado por la Asociación Australiana de Sociología.

No podrían haber elegido un destino mejor para una semana de inspiradas discusiones y debates.

Melbourne se enorgullece de ser una ciudad del conocimiento: hemos trabajado duro para cultivar la sed de conexión, colaboración e innovación, y tenemos dos de las 100 mejores universidades del mundo.

Nuestra ciudad está en constante evolución, lo que la convierte en el escenario perfecto para dar rienda suelta a sus grandes ideas audaces y valientes.

Sabemos que las humanidades, las artes y las ciencias sociales – la ciencia política, la filosofía y demás – son las que impulsan nuestra sociedad hacia adelante, y es un privilegio acoger a especialistas de su categoría.

Estamos impacientes por recibirles en nuestra ciudad para la programación oficial del Congreso, y por verles disfrutar mientras estén aquí con nosotros de la gastronomía, la moda, los eventos, las artes y la música de renombre internacional de nuestra ciudad.

Espero que salgan de esta experiencia con energías renovadas.

Sally Capp

Alcaldesa de la Ciudad de Melbourne

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ISA
International
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Association

Current Sociology is a fully peer-reviewed, international journal that publishes original research and innovative critical commentary both on current debates within sociology as a developing discipline, and the contribution that sociologists can make to understanding and influencing current issues arising in the development of modern societies in a globalizing world.

An official journal of the International Sociological Association since 1952, Current Sociology is one of the oldest and most widely cited sociology journals in the world.

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International Sociology

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ISA
International
Sociological
Association

Established in 1986 by the International Sociological Association (ISA), *International Sociology* was one of the first sociological journals to reflect the research interests and voice of the international community of sociologists. This highly ranked peer-reviewed journal publishes contributions from diverse areas of sociology, with a focus on international and comparative approaches. The journal presents innovative theory and empirical approaches, with attention to insights into the sociological imagination that deserve worldwide attention. New ways of interpreting the social world and sociology from an international perspective provide innovative insights into key sociological issues.

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Elections for the ISA Executive Committee

Executive Committee Elections

Election of the ISA officers for the period July 2023 – July 2027

Elections of the ISA Executive Committee's members for the period July 2023 – July 2027 will be held at the XX ISA World Congress of Sociology in Melbourne, Australia.

- **June 26, 2023 Monday** *Venue: MCEC, Plenary 1 (Ground Floor) 21:00-23:00*
Election speeches by the candidates for President and Vice-Presidents *Open meeting for all Congress participants*
- **June 28, 2023 Wednesday** *Venue: MCEC, 104 (Level 1) 21:00-23:00*
Assembly of Councils: Business Meeting and Election of the ISA President and 4 Vice-Presidents
- **June 29, 2023 Thursday** *Venue: MCEC, 216 (Level 2) 17:30-19:30*
Council of National Associations: Election of 8 members of the ISA Executive Committee
- **June 29, 2023 Thursday** *Venue: MCEC, 216 (Level 2) 21:00-23:00*
Research Council: Election of 8 members of the ISA Executive Committee

List of all Nominees

The curriculum vitae and, for the candidates for the President and Vice-Presidents their priorities if elected to a post, can be found at <https://www.isa-sociology.org/uploads/imagen/1522-isa-elections-2023-2027.pdf>

Nominees for President

Geoffrey PLEYERS, Belgium
Elisa REIS, Brazil

Nominees for Vice-President of Research Council

Allison LOCONTO, France
Emma E. PORIO, Philippines

Nominees for Vice-President of National Associations

Abdie KAZEMIPUR, Canada
Bandana PURKAYASTHA, USA

Nominees for Vice-President of Publications

Chaime MARCUELLO-SERVÓS, Spain
Karim MURJI, United Kingdom
Marta SOLER GALLART, Spain

Nominees for Vice-President of Finance and Membership

Dilek CINDOGLU, Turkey
Elina OINAS, Finland

Nominees for the Executive Committee

A. Elections by the Council of National Associations

Svitlana BABENKO, Ukraine
 Mabrouk BOUTAGOUGA, Algeria
 Chih-Jou Jay CHEN, Taiwan
 Stéphane DUFOIX, France
 Tom DWYER, Brazil
 Petya ILIEVA-TRICHKOVA, Bulgaria
 Shaikh Mohammad KAIS, Bangladesh
 Tselmegsaikhan LKHAGVA, Mongolia
 Rima MAJED, Lebanon
 Emiko OCHIAI, Japan
 Michael Perry OKYEREF, Ghana
 Ana RIVOIR, Uruguay
 Borut RONCEVIC, Slovenia
 Seyed Hossein SERAJZADEH, Iran
 Cécile VAN DE VELDE, Canada
 Dan WOODMAN, Australia

B. Elections by the Research Council

Talja BLOKLAND, Germany
 Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, Greece
 Isabel DA COSTA, France
 Debra DAVIDSON, Canada
 Manisha DESAI, USA
 Sandra FACHELLI, Spain
 Carles FEIXA-PAMPOLS, Spain
 Jan Marie FRITZ, USA
 Mar GRIERA LLONCH, Spain
 Anna ODROWAZ-COATES, Poland
 Aaron PITLUCK, USA
 Rhoda REDDOCK, Trinidad & Tobago
 Hermilio SANTOS, Brazil
 Markus S. SCHULZ, Germany
 Nazanin SHAHROKNI, USA
 Tina UYS, South Africa

Nominations from the floor

Further nominations may also be made from the floor for all elections, if supported by five members of the relevant Council and made with the consent of the candidate.

1. All candidates must have been ISA individual members in good standing since the previous World Congress and must still be so at the time of elections.
2. All proposers must be delegates to the Research Council or to the Council of National Associations from an association in good standing.
3. A duly signed nomination form should be received at the ISA stand at the Congress registration area at least two days before the scheduled election.

XX ISA World Congress Organization

International Sociological Association

Executive Committee 2018-2023

PRESIDENT

Sari Hanafi
American University of Beirut, Lebanon

VICE-PRESIDENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Geoffrey Pleyer
Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium

VICE-PRESIDENT NATIONAL ASSOCIATIONS

Filomin Gutierrez
University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines

VICE-PRESIDENT PUBLICATIONS

Eloísa Martín
United Arab Emirates University, UAE

VICE-PRESIDENT FINANCE AND MEMBERSHIP

Sawako Shirahase
University of Tokyo, Japan

Members of the Executive Committee

Tova Benski, *College of Management Studies, Israel*

Chih-Jou Jay Chen, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

Jan Fritz, *University of Cincinnati, USA*

Koichi Hasegawa, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan*

Hiroshi Ishida, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Grace Khunou (resigned April 2022), *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Allison Loconto, *Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement, France*

Susan McDaniel, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Elina Oinas, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Laura Oso Casas, *Universidade da Coruña, Spain*

Bandana Purkayastha, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Rhoda Reddock, *University of the West Indies, Trinidad & Tobago*

Borut Rončević (April 2022-July 2023), *School of Advanced Social Studies, Slovenia*

Mounir Saidani, *Centre d'études et de recherches économiques et sociales, Tunisia*

Ayse Saktanber, *Middle East Technical University, Turkey*

Celi Scalón, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Nazanin Shahrokni, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*

Program Committee

ISA PRESIDENT AND CHAIR

Sari Hanafi, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

ISA VICE-PRESIDENTS

Filomin Gutierrez, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*

Eloísa Martín, *United Arab Emirates University, UAE*

Geoffrey Pleyers, *Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium*

Sawako Shirahase, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

MEMBERS OF THE RESEARCH COORDINATING COMMITTEE

Hiroshi Ishida, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Allison Loconto, *Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement, France*

Susan McDaniel, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Nazanin Shahrokni, *Syracuse University, USA*

MEMBERS OF THE NATIONAL ASSOCIATIONS LIAISON COMMITTEE

Grace Khunou, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Elna Oinas, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Bandana Purkayastha, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Celi Scalon, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

INVITED ISA MEMBER

Armando Salvatore, *McGill University, Canada*

Local Organizing Committee

Dan Woodman, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

ISA SECRETARIAT

Izabela Barlinska, *Executive Secretary*

Lola Busuttil, *Publications Offic*

Juan Lejárraga, *Membership Offic*

Program and Registration Management

The Conference Exchange

www.confex.com

Australian Local Organizing Committee

VICE-CONVENERS

Dan Woodman, *University of Melbourne, LOC Chair*

Jo Lindsay, *Monash University*

TASA EXECUTIVE REPRESENTATIVE

Alphia Possamai-Inesedy, *Western Sydney University, President of The Australian Sociological Association (TASA)*

MEMBERS

Netta Bromdal, *University of Southern Queensland*

Brendan Churchill, *University of Melbourne*

Anna Halafoff, *Deakin University*

Catherine Hastings, *Macquarie University*

Kim Humphery, *Charles Darwin University*

Sonia Martin, *Australian Catholic University*

Theresa Petray, *James Cook University*

Brady Robards, *Monash University*

Georgia Van Toorn, *University of New South Wales*

PCO

Arinex, Australia

General Information

Registration, Venue and Local Information

Registration Information

Registration: Sunday, June 25 – Saturday, July 1, 2023

The registration desk is located just inside the main entrance of the Melbourne Convention and Exhibition Centre on 1 Convention Centre Place. The registration desk is located in the Foyer of the Convention Centre, opposite doors 7 and 8.

On-site registration begins Sunday, June 25. The registration desk will be open as follows:

Sunday June 25	11:00 – 20:00
Monday, June 26 and Tuesday, June 27	7:00 – 18:00
Wednesday, June 28	8:00 – 18:00
Thursday, June 29 and Friday, June 30	8:00 – 17:00
Saturday, July 1	8:00 – 15:00

Name Badge

Each delegate will receive a name badge upon registration. For security reasons, all participants are required to wear their name badge during activities related to the XX ISA World Congress of Sociology. Admission to sessions, the exhibition, and social functions including the Opening Ceremony and Reception will not be granted without the relevant name badges.

Opening Ceremony and Reception

The Opening Ceremony will take place on Sunday, 25 June 2023: 17:30 – 20:15, MCEC, Plenary 2. The Welcome Reception will follow in the MCEC Foyer from 20:30 – 22:30.

The event will open with a Welcome to Country by Djirri Djirri elder Mandy Nicholson. There will also be a smoking ceremony and dancing by the *Djirri Djirri Dancers*, who are a Wurundjeri female dance group and also Traditional Custodians of Narrm (Melbourne). Djirri Djirri means Willy Wagtail in Woiwurrung, the language of Wurundjeri people, the Traditional Custodians of Narrm and surrounds. The Willy Wagtail the Spirit Bird, gave them dance. Many of their group have danced since they were young children, while others have learnt as adults. You will hear Elder Mandy Nicholson singing in Woiwurrung, the language of the Wurundjeri people and watch the language come to life through dance.

Farewell Party: Friday, June 30, 2023

The Farewell Party hosted by The Australian Sociological Association will be held in The Crown – Conference Hall 1 (Level 2) from 21:00 – 23:00.

Tickets are required and must be purchased on-line prior to June 16, 2023. No tickets will be sold on-site.

Exhibition

The Exhibition, Publishers Lounge and Scholars Hub Event Series will be located in on the ground floor foyer of the Convention Centre, adjacent to the registration area.

Sunday, June 25	14:00 – 17:30
Monday, June 26 to Friday, June 30	08:00 – 17:00
Saturday, July 1	08:00 – 15:30

Venue Information

Venue

The XX ISA World Congress sessions and events will take place in both the Melbourne Convention and Exhibition Centre (MCEC) and the Crown Hotel.

The main entrance into MCEC is via 1 Convention Centre Place. There are also entrances on Orrs Walk.

The main entrance into Crown Hotel is via 8 Whiteman Street (see signs for “Crown Conference Centre”).

Information Booths:

Delegates can visit the information booths located in the MCEC, Foyer ground floor.

Tourist Information

Drop by the Melbourne Visitor Desk in the MCEC. Foyer ground floor, and get local advice on things to do and see during your stay in Melbourne.

Lost and Found

If you find something, or lose something, please see the staff at the registration desk at MCEC, Foyer ground floor.

Volunteers

Assistance will be available throughout both venues from our helpful volunteers who will be wearing white XX ISA World Congress T-shirts.

Internet Access

Free Wi-Fi is available at the MCEC and the Crown Hotel in all public areas.

Business Centre

Copying and printing services as well as items for purchase will be available from the Business Centre.

Hours: Mondays to Fridays 9:00 – 17:00

Medical Services

This service will be available to delegates in the MCEC and The Crown for urgent medical issues requiring first aid-immediate assistance. International delegates are responsible for arranging their own medical insurance, for any additional medical needs. Please speak to a staff member at the registration/information desk located at both MCEC and The Crown for assistance with medical issues requiring first-aid.

Special purpose rooms

The special purpose rooms are located in the MCEC.

Opening hours 8:00-21:00 except for the childcare room where it will be open based on the hours booked by the parents.

Childcare Room - Green Room A (Lower Ground Floor) pre-booked only

Family Room - Green Room B (Lower Ground Floor)

Faith Room - located behind Plenary 2 (Ground Floor)

First Nations Room - Clarendon Room G (ground floor)

Press and Media Room – located behind Plenary 2 (Ground Floor)

Work Room - Clarendon Room C (level 1)

Quiet Room - Clarendon Room F (level 1)

Luggage storage - Cloak room located behind Plenary 1 (Ground Floor)

Accessibility

Information has been compiled for those with accessibility concerns. Please speak to a staff member at the registration desk for assistance.

Technical Information for Presenters

Presenters were requested to upload presentation slides to the Congress system in the Speaker Center by 12 June 2023 (it will not be possible to present from your own computer). If you missed the deadline for uploading your presentation or need to make changes to your slides, you must bring a new copy of your presentation with you to upload onsite in the Speaker Ready Room the day before your presentation session.

All in-person oral presenters should visit the Speaker Ready Room before their session to preview their presentation using the Congress software and confirm there are no technical issues. If uploading your presentation slides onsite, you must visit the Speaker Ready Room in the same venue (i.e. MCEC or The Crown) in which your presentation will be held.

Speaker Ready Room Locations:

- For presentations in The Crown: M7 (Level 1)
- For presentations in the MCEC: SP101 (Level 1) or SP201 (Level 2)

Opening hours:

Sunday, June 25	14:00 – 17:00
Monday–Thursday June 26-29	07:30 – 19:00
Friday June 30	07:30 – 17:00
Saturday July 1	07:30 – 15:00

Sage Studies in International Sociology

The *SAGE Studies in International Sociology (SSIS)* was founded in 1974 and is published in connection with the **International Sociological Association**. The books in this series are intended to encourage debates of international significance and map out future trends of sociological importance.

Visit the Journal website:

<https://au.sagepub.com/en-gb/oc/sage-studies-in-international-sociology>

Program Structure

Timetable of Sessions and Meetings

Melbourne 2023	08:30-10:20	10:30-12:20	12:30-13:50	14:00-15:20	15:30-17:20	17:30-19:20	19:30-20:50	21:00-23:00
Sunday 25 June		Research Council Business Meeting (delegates only) 10:30-12:30		Council of National Associations Business Meeting (delegates only) 14:00-16:00		Opening Ceremony, Presidential Address, Prize Giving and Reception		
Monday 26 June	Presidential Plenary I	RC, WG, TG	Integrative Sessions	Semi-Plenaries & Australian Thematic Sessions	RC, WG, TG Associations Sessions	RC, WG, TG Ad Hoc Author Meets Critics	RC, WG, TG Professional Development Sessions	ISA Officers Election speeches (open meeting)
Tuesday 27 June	RC, WG, TG	RC, WG, TG	Integrative Sessions Spotlight Sessions	Semi-Plenaries & Australian Thematic Sessions	RC, WG, TG Associations Sessions	RC, WG, TG Ad Hoc Author Meets Critics	RC, WG, TG Professional Development Sessions	
Wednesday 28 June	RC, WG, TG	RC, WG, TG	Integrative Sessions	Semi-Plenaries & Australian Thematic Sessions	RC, WG, TG Associations Sessions Past Presidents Session	RC, WG, TG Ad Hoc Author Meets Critics	RC, WG, TG Professional Development Sessions	Assembly of Councils Business Meeting President & Vice-Presidents Elections (delegates only)
Thursday 29 June	RC, WG, TG	RC, WG, TG	Integrative Sessions Spotlight Sessions	Semi-Plenaries & Australian Thematic Sessions	RC, WG, TG Associations Sessions	RC, WG, TG Ad Hoc Training Session RC officers	RC, WG, TG Professional Development Sessions	Research Council Elections (delegates only)
						Council of National Associations Elections (delegates only) 17:30-19:30		
RC, WG, TG = Research Committees, Working Groups, Thematic Groups sessions								

Timetable of Sessions and Meetings

Program Structure

Melbourne 2023	08:30-10:20	10:30-12:20	12:30-13:50	14:00-15:20	15:30-17:20	17:30-19:20	19:30-20:50	21:00-23:00
Friday 30 June	RC, WG, TG	RC, WG, TG	Integrative Sessions	Presidential Session II & Installation of New President	RC, WG, TG Associations Sessions	RC, WG, TG Ad Hoc Training Session RC officers		Farewell Party 21:00-23:00
Saturday 1 July	RC, WG, TG	RC, WG, TG New EC Meeting (members only)	RC, WG, TG 12:30-14:00 Induction session new EC officers 12:30-14:00	RC, WG, TG 14:30-16:20	Spotlight Session		The out-going & new Executive Committee Dinner (members only)	
RC, WG, TG = Research Committees, Working Groups, Thematic Groups sessions								
Melbourne 2023"	9:00	10:30	12:30	14:00	15:30	17:30	19:30	21:00
Friday 23 June	Publications and Finance and Membership Committees till 13:00			Research Coordinating and National Associations Liaison Committees 14:30-18:30				
Saturday 24 June	Executive Committee (members only) till 13:00			Executive Committee (members only) 14:30 - 18:30				
Sunday 25 June		Research Council Business Meeting (delegates only)		Council of National Associations Business Meeting (delegates only) 14:00-16:00				
Monday 26 June								ISA Officers Election speeches (open meeting) 21:00-23:00
Tuesday 27 June								
Wednesday 28 June								Assembly of Councils Business Meeting President & Vice-Presidents Elections (delegates only) 21:00-23:00
Thursday 29 June							Council of National Associations Elections (delegates only) 17:30-19:30	Research Council Elections (delegates only) 21:00-23:00
Friday 30 June						RC, WG, TG Training Session (delegates only)		
Saturday 1 July		New Executive Committee Meeting (members only)	Induction session of newly elected EC officers				The out-going & new Executive Committee Dinner (members only)	
Melbourne 2023	9:00	10:30	12:30	14:00	15:30	17:30	19:30	21:00

Timetable of Sessions and Meetings

TIMETABLE

Timetable Day by Day

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
Friday 23 June			
<i>09:00 - 18:30</i>			
ISA Administrative Meetings	885	ISA Executive Committee Meeting. Part I	<i>(University of Melbourne)</i>
Saturday 24 June			
<i>09:30 - 18:30</i>			
ISA Administrative Meetings	886	ISA Executive Committee Meeting. Part II	<i>(University of Melbourne)</i>
Sunday 25 June			
<i>10:30 - 12:30</i>			
ISA Administrative Meetings	887	Research Council. Business Meeting	<i>M12 (Crown)</i>
<i>14:00 - 16:00</i>			
ISA Administrative Meetings	888	Council of National Associations. Business Meeting	<i>M12 (Crown)</i>
<i>17:30 - 20:15</i>			
Presidential Sessions	1	Opening Ceremony and Presidential Address	<i>Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
<i>20:15 - 22:30</i>			
Social Events	896	Welcome Reception	<i>Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
Monday 26 June			
<i>08:30 - 10:20</i>			
Presidential Sessions	2	Liberalism, the Other and Religion	<i>Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
<i>10:30 - 12:20</i>			
RC52, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-1	COVID-19 Pandemic and Global Health Workforce Policies and Governance: Challenges and Issues at the Forefront	<i>203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
WG08, RC38 Joint Sessions	JS-2	Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part I	<i>CCH2 (Crown)</i>
RC02, RC07, RC24, RC47, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-3	Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies	<i>105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
RC46, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-4	Return Migration during a Pandemic: Challenges and Interventions	<i>CCH1 (Crown)</i>
RC01, RC04 Joint Sessions	JS-5	The Soldier-Scholar: Postsecondary Education of Future Military Officers	<i>P1 (Crown)</i>
RC06, RC34, TG10 Joint Sessions	JS-6	To Grant or Not to Grant? Use and Timing of Media Tools in Families with Teen and Pre-Teen Ager	<i>106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
RC02 Economy and Society	38	Developing Socio-Economic Theory with Empirical Cases	<i>213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	84	Indigenous Data Sovereignty	<i>207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)</i>

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	152	Participation and Resurgent Authoritarianism: African and International Perspectives and Experiences	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	163	Health, Harm, and Social Disadvantage	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	178	Meaning-Making, Emotion and Legal Change	M13 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	202	The Presentation of Self: Fads and Fades of the Contemporary Social Link	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	216	Pharmaceuticalisation of Society: Current Debates and Empirical Contributions	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	235	Theorizing the Social World in the Digital Age. Part I	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	251	More Than a Buzzword: Wellbeing in Organizations	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	263	Security Policies and Their Effects: Repression, Securitization and Precarity // Fluctuations of Political Capital in Authoritarian Contexts	M11 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	290	VET Around the World. Comparing Vocational Education and Training Systems and Outcomes Globally	M3 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	320	Decolonising Studies of Religions in Oceania: South-South Flows of Diverse Worldviews across the Indian and Pacific Oceans	CCH3 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	354	Confronting the dragons of destruction: Environmental confrontations with capitalism and colonialism.	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	372	Language, Religion, and Linguistic Rights in Times of Crisis	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	390	Sport and Media	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	399	Comparative Analysis of Social Inequalities between Early and Late Industrialized Countries	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	434	The Frontiers of Work and in Work.	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	449	Migration in Asia – Integration and Cultural Diversity	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	466	Home Is Not so Sweet Home: Shadow Pandemic from COVID 19	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	503	Marginalised Youth, Street Cultures and Mediation	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	522	Phenomenology and Critical Theory	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	532	Globalization, Alienation and the Cultural Patterns of Right-Wing Extremism	M8 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	564	Decolonizing Disasters Studies in the Global South: First-Hand Research Experiences	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	582	Food and Social Change	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	592	Addressing Population Change through Social, Health and Other Public Policies	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	618	Learning from the Past: Historical Approaches to Labour Strategy and Their Contemporary Applications	M2 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	653	RC47 Opening Session: Global Dialogues in Social Movement Studies	P3 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	665	Social Movements, Socio-Ecological Practices and Climate Change	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC55 Social Indicators	739	Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of the 2020-2022 Pandemic on Quality of Life and Well-Being. Part I: Social Relations, Happiness, and Mental Well-being	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	760	Building and Integrating Cross-Disciplinary Perspectives of Visual Research	M16 (Crown)
WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations	767	The Upheavals in the Global Order and Their Ramifications for Democracy	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG05 Famine and Society	770	Environmental Crisis/Justice, Global Frameworks and Local Actions: An Agenda for Sustainable Development (Technical Session & Panel Discussion)	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	781	Institutional Ethnography in Educational Settings	M15 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	817	Risks, Catastrophes and Emancipation: Decolonizing Risk Sociology	M6 (Crown)
TG07 Senses and Society	828	The Political Life of Sensation	M5 (Crown)
TG11 Violence and Society	850	Violence in the Contemporary Public Realm	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 13:50			
Integrative Sessions	19	Care, Care work and Migration in Light of the Pandemic and Global Conflicts	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	20	Postcolonial and Southern Perspectives in Digitalization	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:00 – 15:20			
Plenary Sessions	4	PLI.1 Postsecularity or Multiple Secularities?	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Plenary Sessions	5	PLII.1 Inequalities Created in Neoliberal Economies	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Australian Thematic Sessions	15	The Sociology of Refugees, Asylum and Border Control in Australia	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
15:30 – 17:20			
RC34, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-7	Climate Crisis, Mental Health and Youth Resistance	CCH1 (Crown)
RC38, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-8	Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part II	CCH2 (Crown)
RC31, RC06 Joint Sessions	JS-9	Navigating Aging, Social Well-Being, and Cultural Expectations Among Migrant and Transnational Families	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46, RC26 Joint Sessions	JS-10	Panel Discussion: Accrediting Your Undergraduate or Graduate Program in Sociological Practice: A Workshop on Process, Benefits, and Outcomes By the Commission on the Accreditation of Programs in Applied and Clinical Sociology (CAPACS)	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-11	Religious Actors and Social Movements in Contemporary World	P1 (Crown)
RC10, WG05 Joint Sessions	JS-12	Resurgent Authoritarianism in the Context of SDG 1 on No Poverty, SDG2 on Zero Hunger and SDG 17 on Partnerships for the Goals: Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies	P3 (Crown)
RC18, RC09, RC19, RC20, RC56, TG03 Joint Sessions	JS-13	Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC36, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-14	The Rise and Fall of Authoritarian Populisms (Hopefully)	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11, RC54 Joint Sessions	JS-15	Violence & Body: Reflecting Our Own Limits and Beyond	M13 (Crown)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	29	Conscription and Retention	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	39	Varieties of Care Work: Exploring National Differences	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	56	Nuevas Políticas Urbanas En Iberoamérica. Avances Hacia La Nueva Agenda Urbana	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	65	Re-Thinking the Role of Sociology of Education in Tackling the Global Rise of Authoritarianism, Populism, Xenophobia, and Racism.	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	85	Covid, Racism and Indigeneity: tensions and responses	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	119	Constructing Future 'New Normals' after Pandemics and Other Crises	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	164	How Sociological Is the Sociology of Ageing?	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	179	Lay Participation in Justice	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	190	Leisure during the Period of Pandemic and Resurgent Authoritarianism, Presidential Session	M15 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	203	TV Series in the Era of Digitalization, Globalization and Resurgent Authoritarianism	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	217	National Health Systems and the State: The Experience of Practitioners and Patients	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	236	Antipodean Social Theory	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	302	Leisure in the City. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	321	The Experiences of Secularity in Muslim-Majority Contexts	CCH3 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	355	Environmental Sociology Roundtables	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC24 Environment and Society	356	New research in environmental attitudes, values, behaviours and practices.	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	400	Stratification in Early Childhood and Achievements in the Life Course	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	435	Work and Employment Key Issues in Australia and Oceania	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	450	Smartphones As Micro-Homes, Away from Home? Comparing Forms of Portable and Digital Homemaking Among Migrants and Displaced Young People	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	467	Decolonizing the Sociology of Gender and Sexualities	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	489	Recent Developments and Current Approaches to the Analysis of Panel Data	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	541	Societal representations in the arts	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	619	Organising in the Platform Economy	M2 (Crown)
RC45 Rational Choice	634	Computational Social Science and Rational Choice	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	666	Social Movements and Transitional Justice 'from below': Exploring Grassroots Activism in Armed Conflicts and Post-Conflict Contexts	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	691	Paradoxes of Mobilities	M8 (Crown)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	701	Citizen-Science: Systemic Perspectives on Group, Community Empowerment and Co-Decision	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	710	Professions, Politics, and the State	M12 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	724	The Intersection between Spatial and Generational Orders for Understanding Childhood	M4 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	740	Volunteerism in the Midst of the Pandemic	M9 (Crown)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	834	Decolonising the Curriculum: Teaching and Pedagogical Interventions in Sociology	M5 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	840	Media Usage and Intimacies in the Next Generation	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Associations of Sociology	857	Health and Well-being of Individuals in East Asia: Changes from 2010 through 2021	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
17:30 – 19:20			
RC18, RC07, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-16	Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part I	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC53, RC34 Joint Sessions	JS-17	Children and Youth Navigating Gender	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG03, RC03 Joint Sessions	JS-18	Collaborative Research I: Critical Reflections on Research Ethics and Methodological Practices	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG10, RC11 Joint Sessions	JS-19	Connected Seniors: Technology across the Life Course	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30, RC02, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-20	International Migration and Economic Informalization : A Denationalized Perspective - Part I	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41, RC55 Joint Sessions	JS-21	Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part I	CCH2 (Crown)
RC24, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-22	Materialist Sociology: Biometabolism, Technometabolism, Technoaddiction	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	66	Contemporary Issues in Sociology of Education I	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	67	COVID Winners and Losers in Education: How the Pandemic Has Exacerbated but Also Improved Current and Future Social Inequalities	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	86	Citizenship, Nationalism and Racism	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	98	Digital Family Practices	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	141	Development Processes on Geographical Frontiers II	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	153	Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility Under Conditions of International Globalization and Growing Nationalism As Driver of Wars	M14 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	218	Where Next for Sociological Alcohol Research?	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	252	Meta-Organizations, Meta-Organizing and Grand Challenges (Part 1)	M4 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	291	Current Research in Comparative Sociology	M3 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	303	Leisure in the City. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	322	Religious Change in Europe	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	341	Quantification and Power: Values, Normative Agendas and Policy Paradigms behind Numbers. Part II	M10 (Crown)
RC25 Language and Society	373	Language As a Tool for Oppression and Resistance within Institutional Practices	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	382	The Socio-Political Dimension of Gender Relations in Times of Crisis and of Resurgent Authoritarianism	M5 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	401	Cutting-Edge Research in Social Stratification	Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	402	Stratification and Inequality in Diverse Societies	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	451	Conceptualising Transnational Youth Mobilities and Transitions amidst Social Challenges	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	468	Feminist Pedagogies, Positionality and Situatedness	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	504	Becoming Adults As Children of Immigrants	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	523	Social Cohesion: Political Discourse and Sociological Conceptualization I	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	533	Irrational Rationality: Informational and Knowledge-Based Alienation	M8 (Crown)
RC38 Biography and Society	553	New Developments in Biographical Research	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	565	Overcoming Siloization Practices to Achieve All-of-Society-Based Inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction: Case Studies, Surveys and Theories	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	583	Food System Shocks and Food Security Vulnerabilities: Moving Beyond Business As Usual I	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	620	Migrant and Precarious Labour in Logistics: Mapping Employment Regimes and Reconnecting Workers Solidarities Along the Global Supply Chain	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	641	RC46 Business Meeting	P3 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	654	Food for Justice	P1 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	667	Social Movements, State and Civil Society: Perspectives from the Global South. Part I	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	711	Professions, the State, and Regulation	M12 (Crown)
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	733	Embodiment and Ground Theory. David Le Breton and His Contribution to the Sociology of the Body, a Commemorative Session	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC56 Historical Sociology	752	Historicising Power Relations and Habitus Formation. Part I	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	761	RC57 Business Meeting	M16 (Crown)
WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations	768	WG01 Business Meeting	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
WG05 Famine and Society	771	Panel Discussion on Covid Pandemic, Rising Authoritarianism, Food Insecurity and Emerging Cultural, Social, Economic, Political and Democratic Challenges	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	782	Different Perspectives on the Sociology of Knowledge	M15 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	793	The Imperial Passion of Race: The Case of Max Weber. Invited Speaker	M1 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	818	Theorizing Risk and Uncertainty. Part I	M6 (Crown)
TG11 Violence and Society	851	Lethal Violence: Sociological Approaches to Homicide and Femicide/ Feminicide	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Author Meets Critics	875	Critical Engagement with Public Sociology: A Perspective from the Global South edited by Andries Bezuidenhout, Sonwabile Mswana, Karl Von Holdt	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Author Meets Critics	876	The Gift Paradigm: A Short Introduction to the Anti-Utilitarian Movement in the Social Sciences by Alain Caillé	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Ad Hoc Sessions	881	Atmospheres of the infra-ordinary	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

19:30 – 20:50

RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	87	RC05 Business Meeting	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	165	RC11 Business Meeting	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	204	RC14 Business Meeting	M1 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	292	Comparative Sociology: Research and Methods	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	304	RC21 Business Meeting	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	391	Sport, Economies and Mega-Events	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	469	RC32 Business Meeting	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	490	RC33 Business Meeting	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	542	Theatres and Public Sphere	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	668	Social Movements, State and Civil Society: Perspectives from the Global South. Part II	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG10 Digital Sociology	841	TG10 Business Meeting	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11 Violence and Society	852	TG11 Business Meeting	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	863	Getting Active with the United Nations	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	864	Turning Research into Publications in Sociology Journals	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
21:00 – 23:00			
ISA Administrative Meetings	889	Candidates election speeches	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30 - 10:20

RC07, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-23	Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part II	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC23, RC14 Joint Sessions	JS-24	Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part IV	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC53, TG10 Joint Sessions	JS-25	Digital Mediation of Children's Learning and the Changing Ecology of Home-School-World Connectivity	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG03, RC24 Joint Sessions	JS-26	Human Dimensions of Development and Sustainable Development Goals	CCH1 (Crown)
RC55, RC41 Joint Sessions	JS-27	Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part II	CCH2 (Crown)
RC47, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-28	Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Public Sphere	P1 (Crown)
RC52, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-29	Working Abroad: The Experience of Mobile Professionals in Foreign Labour Markets	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34, RC48, RC04 Joint Sessions	JS-30	Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (1)	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	30	Sociology of War	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	40	The Social Economy of Migrant Labour -- Improving Social Protections to End Exploitation	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	68	Sociological Perspectives on Social Innovation in Education	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	88	Global Islamophobia: Policies and Practices	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	99	The Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Family Life: Risks and Opportunities	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	131	RC08 Business Meeting	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	142	New Theories and Findings in Development Sociology	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	166	Civic Engagement in Later Life: Expanding the Social Gerontological Imagination	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	180	Rights, Experts and Access to Justice	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	191	Leisure and Global Housing Crises	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	219	Cross-Country Comparative Sociological Analyses of Covid-19 Patient Experiences: Insights from the Dipex International Collaboration	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	253	The Recombinant Strengths of Organisations Employing New Technologies	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	264	Preferences for Redistribution in the Global South	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	277	Wealth, Welfare and the Asset Economy. Part I	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	305	Civil Society, Public Institutions and Governance	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	323	Measuring Religiosity in East Asia	CCH3 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC24 Environment and Society	357	Re-conceptualizing Socio Ecological Systems in an Era of Climate Change	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	374	Discourse Analysis Methodology and the Role of Written Narratives in Sociological Research	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	383	Social Economy's Transformative Power, Creative Sectors and the Art of Local Resilient Recovery	M5 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	403	Experiences and Consciousness of Inequality	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	436	Work Precarities in the Global South, Part I.	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	452	Tackling East Asian Migration Regimes: Challenges and Opportunities for East Asian Democracies	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	470	Roundtable 1	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	566	Women Practitioners in Emergencies	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	603	Invited Session: Dr. Cecilia Ridgeway	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	621	Repertoires of Action	M2 (Crown)
RC45 Rational Choice	635	Dynamics of Capitals and Social Inequality from the Rational Choice Perspective	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	642	The History of Clinical Sociology in Different Regions of the World	M12 (Crown)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	682	Mental health and the community	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	692	Open Forum: Envisioning a Future of Sociology in Tourism Studies	M8 (Crown)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	702	4P and Cognitive Policy Making in Health: A Sociocybernetic Approach	M3 (Crown)
RC56 Historical Sociology	753	Historicising Power Relations and Habitus Formation. Part II	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	772	Religious Diversity: Dialogue and Integration	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG08 Society and Emotions	794	Feeling States	M13 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	819	Mixed Themes: Methods/Methodologies - (voluntary) Risk-Taking	M6 (Crown)
10:30 – 12:20			
RC37, RC36 Joint Sessions	JS-31	Art and Alienation	M2 (Crown)
RC02, RC23 Joint Sessions	JS-32	International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Labour-Capital Relations	CCH1 (Crown)
RC24, RC03 Joint Sessions	JS-33	Marine Justice, Ocean Studies, and Coastal Communities	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-34	Religious Actors and Social movements: Gender and Sexual Diversity	P1 (Crown)
RC21, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-35	The Collaboration and Solidarity of Local and Ethnic Residents in Global Cities	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26, RC10 Joint Sessions	JS-36	Transformative Research, Education and World Social Forum	M10 (Crown)
RC34, RC04, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-37	Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (2)	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	31	The Military and Politics in 21st Century	M14 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC02 Economy and Society	41	Power, Politics, Beliefs & Values in the Economy	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	69	Rethinking Questions and Issues of Social Justice in Education	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	89	Race, Racism and Anti-Racism in Australia: Knowledge for Action Beyond Epistemological Divisions	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	100	Childbearing Intentions and Behaviors in Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	120	RC07 Business Meeting	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	205	The Political Communication of Russia-Ukraine War: Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies. La Communication Politique De La Guerre d'Ukraine : Pour Une Sociologie d'Un Emmêlement Politique, Économique Et Culturel.	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	220	The Response of Health Professions to Complementary and Alternative Medicine	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	237	Theorising Elites	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18 Political Sociology	265	Globalisation at a Crossroads: Current Perspectives and Future Assessments	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	278	Advanced democracies.	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	404	Youth, Young Adults and Stratification	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	437	Estudios Del Trabajo En América Latina. Algunos Ejes Temáticos En Un Cambio De Época	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	453	Social and Spatial Mobility: New Entanglements of Class and Migration	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	471	In the Shadow of the Pandemic: The Impact of Authoritarian Trends and Tendencies on Gender and Sexual Politics.	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	491	Relational Data and Geo-Data: Research Strategies of Analysis and Visualization	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	524	Conviviality/Convivialisme Studies and the Renewal of Sociology	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC38 Biography and Society	554	Biographical Research – Contemporary Methodological and Ethical Concerns	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	567	Women, Men and Lgbtiqa+ People in Disasters	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	584	Agri-Food Sustainability in a Post-COVID World	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	611	Housing Affordability and Inequality during the COVID19 pandemic	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	643	Certified Clinical Sociologists: In and out of the Academy	M12 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	669	Social Movements Challenges in a Post-Pandemic World: New Agendas, New Dynamics	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	693	Mobilities after Covid 19 – Social and Wellbeing Perspectives on Tourism in Unsettling Times	M8 (Crown)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	703	Evolution of Meaning: Toward a Synthesis between Systems Theory and the Sociology of Knowledge	M3 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	725	Opening Session of RC53 Sociology of Childhood	M4 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	734	Bodies and Emotions in the Present Time	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC55 Social Indicators	741	The Advantages of Analysing Longitudinal Data for Understanding Changes in Levels of Life Satisfaction	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	762	Visual and Multimodal Studies of the City. Part I	M16 (Crown)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	783	Doing Institutional Ethnography: Issues and Innovations I	M15 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	804	Marginalization, Wellbeing, and Justice	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	835	Teaching then and Now: Transitions in Sociological Pedagogy	M5 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	842	Digital Rights and Internet Freedom in the Big Data Era - Is It a Lost Battle?	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11 Violence and Society	853	The Consequences of Violence	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 13:50			
Spotlight Sessions	12	Racism and Islamophobia	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	21	Prosumption in Post-COVID-19 societies	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	22	Understanding the Criminalization of Struggles for Rights: Resurgent Authoritarianism or Deliberalization of Democracies?	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:00 – 15:20			
Plenary Sessions	6	PLI.2 Toward Broader Horizons of Secularity	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Plenary Sessions	7	PLII.2 Individual vs. Collective Rights to Life under Neoliberalism	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Australian Thematic Sessions	16	The Social and Political Implications of Climate Change	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
15:30 – 17:20			
RC38, RC56 Joint Sessions	JS-38	Collective Memories of Violence: Remembering in Families and Local Communities	CCH2 (Crown)
RC14, RC07, RC10, RC23, TG10 Joint Sessions	JS-39	Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25, RC05 Joint Sessions	JS-40	Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part I	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48, RC24 Joint Sessions	JS-41	Globalization-Induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, Identity and Ecological issues). Part I	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30, RC02, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-42	International Migration and Economic Informalization: A Denationalized Perspective - Part II	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-43	Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Ecological Turn	P1 (Crown)
RC19, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-44	Variiegated Intersections of Social Policy and Finance	CCH1 (Crown)
RC03 Community Research	57	Updating Community Research: Past, Present, Future	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	70	Student Trajectories and Interlevel Transitions: Impacts of the Pandemic on Educational Inequalities	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC06 Family Research	101	Balancing Work and Family: Gender Roles and Caregiving	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	143	Development Processes on Geographical Frontiers I	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	167	Migration and Migrancy As Points of Departure for Research on Aging and Old Age	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	181	Sociology of Complaints and Complaint Bodies	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	192	Happiness in Post Pandemic Era: A Global Perspective	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	221	The Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Persons with Disabilities: Call for a Sociological Reflexivity	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	238	Social Imaginaries and Political Forms. Part I	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	254	Meta-Organizations, Meta-Organizing and Grand Challenges (Part 2)	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	266	Analyzing the Links between Authoritarian Political Practices and Reactionary Ideas	M11 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	293	Values in Transition and Development: New Findings from the World Values Survey	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	306	Workspace Conflicts, Urban Lives and Livelihoods: Emerging Politics, Planning and Practice across the Global North and South. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC24 Environment and Society	358	Revitalizing participatory democracy to address climate and environmental disruptions	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	392	Sport, Health and Wellbeing	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	405	Global Trends in Education and Stratification	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	454	How Does Migration Scholarship Contribute to Public Discourse?	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	472	The “New Right” War on Gender and Intersectional Feminist Responses II	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	492	Integrating Survey Data from Different Sources: Comparability, Quality, and Applications	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	505	Presidential Session: The Sociology of Youth Today	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	534	Alienation in the 21st Century: Revisiting, Reevaluating, Recentering. Part I	M8 (Crown)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	543	Art and War	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	568	Volunteers and Aid in Disaster Contexts	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	585	Sociology of Agriculture and Food Roundtables	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	593	Behavioural Perspectives of Control and Elimination of Communicable Diseases	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	622	Labour Politics in East Asia	M2 (Crown)
RC45 Rational Choice	636	Evolution of Social Norms and Cooperation	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	644	Community Resilience Innovations in Food Security and Health: Towards Resilient Recovery from the COVID-19 Pandemic	P3 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	712	Interprofessional Teamwork in Healthcare. Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemics	M12 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	742	Social Mechanisms of Wellbeing in Comparative Perspectives	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	773	Panel Discussion on Religious Diversity, Marginalization of Minorities and Marginalised and Deepening Crises in the World	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG08 Society and Emotions	795	Images and Emotions	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	805	Gender, Sexuality, and Social Justice	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	820	Inequality, Power, and Intersectional Perspectives on Risk I	M6 (Crown)
TG07 Senses and Society	829	Excursions in Sensory Studies: Teaching, Doing, Writing	M5 (Crown)
Associations of Sociology	858	Looking Back to Move Forward: European Sociological Legacy Revisited	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

16:00 – 17:15

Other Activities		Commemorative Event: Margaret S. Archer (1943-2023)	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
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17:30 – 19:20

RC25, RC05 Joint Sessions	JS-45	Everyday Practices of ‘Othering’: Ongoing Developments. Part II	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31, RC32 Joint Sessions	JS-46	Gender in Skilled Migration: Beyond Western Perspectives	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC56, RC17 Joint Sessions	JS-47	Historical Sociology of Organizations. Part I	M11 (Crown)
WG01, RC26 Joint Sessions	JS-48	Integrative and Disintegrative Processes in Europe and Eurasia: Public Opinion, State Politics and Media Discourse.	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44, RC48, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-49	Labor Unrest, Social Revolts and Revolutions, 1851-2020: Findings from the Global Social Protest Database	CCH1 (Crown)
RC04, RC30 Joint Sessions	JS-50	Navigating the Other Side of the Classroom: Exploring Teachers’ Experiences at Work	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18, RC10 Joint Sessions	JS-51	Political Socialization in Changing Times: Generations and Agents.	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-52	Understanding the Sociological Interplay of Emotions	CCH2 (Crown)
RC03, RC37 Joint Sessions	JS-53	Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development	M2 (Crown)
RC04, RC57 Joint Sessions	JS-54	Why Do We Need the Visual? Understanding Educational Practices Using Visual Data and Methods.	P1 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	42	Digitalized Economic Interactions in the Global South: In Search of a New Research Agenda	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	102	Gender, Family, and Work. Part I	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	121	Futures Research: Open Themes Part III	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	168	Mapping Age: Spaces, Places and Environments of Aging	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	182	Authoritarian and Conservative Rules in Contemporary Societies: The Battlefield of Women’s Rights and Freedom. Part I	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	193	Assessing Leisure and Tourism in Post Pandemic Era	M15 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	206	Crisis Discourse, Propaganda Technologies and Information Warfare in the New War's Era: Challenges and Solutions	M1 (Crown)
RC16 Sociological Theory	239	RC16 Business Meeting	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	307	Workspace Conflicts, Urban Lives and Livelihoods: Emerging Politics, Planning and Practice across the Global North and South. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	324	RC22 Presidential Session I Henrietta Nyamnjoh "Stoking the Flames of Faith: The Challenge of Keeping Religiosity Activated in COVID and Post-COVID Times"	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	342	Digital Innovation in the Innovation Society: Sociological Perspectives	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	359	Climate change vulnerability and adaptation across the North and South	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	406	Effects of Disruptive Events	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	455	Migrant Activisms	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	473	Building Feminist Academia: Research Experiences from the Social Sciences	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	493	Innovation in Data Collection	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	506	Conservatism, Authoritarianism, and Chauvinism within Youth Culture Around the World	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	507	The Experiences of Rural Youths in the Context of the Covid 19 Pandemic	Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	525	Social Cohesion: Political Discourse and Sociological Conceptualization II	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	535	Existential Perspectives on Alienation	M8 (Crown)
RC38 Biography and Society	555	Biographical Methods in Applied Social Research	M13 (Crown)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	586	Food System Shocks and Food Security Vulnerabilities: Moving Beyond Business As Usual II	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	594	Child and Youth Indicators and Their Well-Being: Vital Statistics for Planning and Development	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	604	Lecturing Diversity – Lessons from the Classroom.	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	655	Intersectional Gender Politics on the Right, Antifeminist Backlash, and Feminist Politics of Resistance	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	670	Social Movements, environment and social justice	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	683	Victimization and Experiences of Violence Among Mental Health Service Users	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	704	Sociocybernetic Perspectives on Power	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	713	Going Beyond Organisational Professionalism. Exploring the Role of Work Settings for Professionals in the Digitalised Era:Session II - Organisation & Professions	M12 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	726	Intersectionality and Cultural Politics of Childhood	M4 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC55 Social Indicators	743	Pandemic Crisis, War, and Resurgent Authoritarianism: Challenges for the Future of Social Indicators Research	M9 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	821	Inequality, Power, and Intersectional Perspectives on Risk II	M6 (Crown)
Author Meets Critics	877	Diaspora as Translation and Decolonisation by Ipek Demir	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
19:30 – 20:50			
RC04 Sociology of Education	71	RC04 Business Meeting	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	103	Gender, Family, and Work. Part II	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	122	War and Global Realignments: Geopolitical Prospects	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	132	Past, Present and Future: Learning from 'Old' Sociological Research	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	144	Why Societies Collapse ?	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC15 Sociology of Health	222	RC15 Business Meeting	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	255	RC17 Business Meeting	M4 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	325	RC22 Business Meeting	CCH3 (Crown)
RC25 Language and Society	375	RC25 Business Meeting	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	384	RC26 Business Meeting	M5 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	407	RC28 Business Meeting	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	456	RC31 Business Meeting	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	508	RC34 Business Meeting	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	569	RC39 Business Meeting	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	694	RC50 Business Meeting	M8 (Crown)
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	735	Sea-Ing through Bodies, Health, and Sustainability	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG08 Society and Emotions	796	WG08 Business Meeting	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	806	TG03 Business Meeting	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	865	How to get into the international publication game if you are a scholar from the Global South	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	866	In Conversation with Senior Sociologists: Making Connections, Bridging Generations	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	867	Public Sociology: Writing for Publics	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
Wednesday 28 June			
<i>08:30 - 10:20</i>			
RC40, RC07 Joint Sessions	JS-55	Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics I	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC53, RC51 Joint Sessions	JS-56	Childhoods and Systemic Inequalities	CCH2 (Crown)
RC31, RC32 Joint Sessions	JS-57	Gender-Based Violence and Migration: Global Perspectives	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18, RC05 Joint Sessions	JS-58	Is Nationalism Democratic or Authoritarian?	P1 (Crown)
RC30, RC25 Joint Sessions	JS-59	Language and Work: The Post-Pandemic Evolutions of Categorizations Toward (Un)Employment and Working Conditions	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC24, TG04 Joint Sessions	JS-60	Materiality, Brutality and Risk: Decolonial Readings of the Twin Climate and Energy Crisis	CCH1 (Crown)
RC34, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-61	When Students Protest about the Climate Crisis: Realities, Reactions and Results	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	32	Rethinking the Old, New and Future Roles of Armed Forces	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	43	Economic Sociology of Craftsmanship	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	72	Social and Political Underpinnings of Teacher Recruitment and Certification	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	104	Caring Fathers in the Global Context. Part I	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	133	Theories and Methods in Undertaking Histories of Sociology	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	145	RC09 Business Meeting	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	169	Reimagining Active Ageing for New Times	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	207	Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part II	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	223	Sociology of Vaccines. Part I	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	240	Ulrich Beck and COVID-19 Pandemics	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	256	How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 1)	M4 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	279	Wealth, Welfare and the Asset Economy. Part II	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	294	The Comparative Political Sociology of Public Opinion, Policy and Social Inequality	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	308	Climate urbanism and the subaltern	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	326	Religious Change in Latin America	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	343	Bringing Intersectionality to Science: How Equity Diversity and Inclusion Impacts Scientific Policies and Practices. Part I	M10 (Crown)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	393	Sport and Politics	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	408	Integrated Data on People, Time, and Places in Research on Social Stratification and Mobility	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	424	Criminal Organizations, Drugs and the Youth	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	457	Forced Migration and Trafficking in Persons in the Contemporary World: The Variables of Gender, Human Rights and Covid-19 Pandemic	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	474	Theorizing Gender in Populist Times: Understanding the Challenge to Critical Social Sciences	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	494	New Trends in Digital Social Research	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	536	Flexible Employment and Alienation	M8 (Crown)
RC38 Biography and Society	556	Conceptual Challenges in Biographical Research	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	570	Business Community Resilience, Protecting Livelihoods and Safeguarding Services	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	595	Contemporary Demographic Transitions	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	645	Mythical Thinking, Religion and Politics. What about Democracy Today?	M12 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	656	Social Movements Democratic Practices	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	671	The construction of dissent: strategies and collective identities	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	684	Social Relationships and Mental Health and Illness	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC56 Historical Sociology	754	Sociology in Somber Times: Opening Windows into the Future	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	763	Visual and Multimodal Studies of the City. Part II	M16 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	774	Potential of Big Data in Poverty Assessment	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	784	Using Institutional Ethnography to Understand Justice and Power	M15 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	807	Human Dimensions of Sustainable Development	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	836	Addressing Rising Authoritarianism through Sociological Teaching	M5 (Crown)
10:30 – 12:20			
RC41, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-62	Demographic Change, Economic Outcomes and Religious Belief	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21, RC04 Joint Sessions	JS-63	Housing and School Choices in the Unequal City: Uneasy Trade-Offs, New Combinations and Socio-Spatial Consequences	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14, RC57 Joint Sessions	JS-64	Reconstructing Knowledge: Digital Humanities and Visual Culture	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC23, RC24 Joint Sessions	JS-65	Sociology and the Climate Science-Politics Gap	CCH1 (Crown)
RC31, RC32 Joint Sessions	JS-66	The Covid-19 Crisis, Gender, and the Price of Migrants' Invisibility	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48, RC10 Joint Sessions	JS-67	Urban Collective Action	P1 (Crown)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	33	Civil-Military Collaboration and Research Perspectives	M14 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC02 Economy and Society	44	Indebted Subjectivities: Juggling with Consumer Credit	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	58	Community Mobilization in Urban and Rural Context	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	90	Navigating the ECR- stage: a panel on negotiating research and publishing in today's academic climate.	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	105	Caring Fathers in the Global Context. Part II	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	106	Gender, Family, and Work. Part III	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	123	Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part II	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	146	RC09 Poster Session	Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	194	Leisure Time Activities, It's Changing Patterns and Development.	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	224	Sociology of Vaccines. Part II	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	241	Social Theory in China, Social Theory of China	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18 Political Sociology	267	New Theories of Political Sociology: Power, Social Psychology, and Macro-Bargaining	M11 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	295	Comparative Sociology: Theory and Methods	M3 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	327	Exploring changes in religiosity: new patterns and trends	CCH3 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	360	Energy Consumption Patterns and Behaviors	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	376	The Interplay of Language, Migration and Mobility: Policy and Practice	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	385	Legal and Educational Instruments to Contrast Gender-Based Violence	M5 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	409	Multi-Generational Perspective in Social Stratification Research	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	438	Implications of Authoritarian Policies on Workers and Labor Precariousness	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	458	Gender, Migration, and Agency: Marriage Migration to Emerging Destinations	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	475	Presidential Session: Masculinities in Authoritarian Times	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	509	Young People's Experiences and Relationships in the Global Pandemic (1)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	526	Elusive Concepts of the Social. Simultaneous Analysis from Different Socio-Cultural Contexts.	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	544	Arts and Democracy	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	571	Compound Disasters, Extreme Weather, and the Impact of Livelihoods	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	587	Food and Social Change II	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	605	Perceptions and Preferences about Inequality, Meritocracy and Redistribution	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	612	Housing Inequality in China	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	623	Labour Internationalisms from Above and Below	M2 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	657	Capitalism and Class in Contemporary Social Movements	P3 (Crown)
RC50 International Tourism	695	Silenced and Unheard Voices: Human Rights in Tourism	M8 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	714	Professional Work. Part I	M12 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	727	Institutional, Political and Cultural Challenges in the Studies of Childhood	M4 (Crown)
RC56 Historical Sociology	755	Historical Sociology As Relational Memory. Part I	M9 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	797	Emotions, Senses and Artifacts Related to Physical Distance during the COVID-19 Pandemic/Emociones, Sentidos y Artefactos Relacionados Con La Distancia Física Durante La Pandemia De Covid19	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	808	Status, Discourse, and Authoritarianism	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	822	The Democratization of Risk and Prevention in a Sociological Perspective	M6 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	843	Swipe Right or Swipe Left? Sociological Perspectives of Digital Sexual Spaces	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 13:50			
Integrative Sessions	23	(Dis)Entangling Religion(s) and Politics in fighting for Freedom and Dignity. Cross approaches from Algeria, Palestine, and Tunisia	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	24	COVID 19 in Brics Countries: Comparative Sociological Perspectives	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:00 – 15:20			
Plenary Sessions	8	PLIII.1 Populism: Local Forms of a Global Phenomenon	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Plenary Sessions	9	PLIV.1 Brutalizing Authoritarianism	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Australian Thematic Sessions	17	Indigenous Sociology in Australia	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
15:30 – 17:20			
Other Activities		AISOC Asociación Iberoamericana de Investigación en Sociología de las Organizaciones y Comunicación	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17, RC24, RC40, TG04 Joint Sessions	JS-68	Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part I	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-69	Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part I	P1 (Crown)
RC54, TG11 Joint Sessions	JS-70	Diversities Bodies, Violence and Human Rights in the 21st Century: The Gender and Racism Issues	M16 (Crown)
RC34, RC18 Joint Sessions	JS-71	Doing Research on Young People with Young People: Co-Productions, Co-Authoring and Collaborations	CCH1 (Crown)
RC05, RC25 Joint Sessions	JS-72	Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part III	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-73	Femmes Migrantes Sur Le Marché Du Travail Subalterne/Migrant Women in the Subaltern Labor Market	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
WG05, RC10 Joint Sessions	JS-74	People-Centric Governance, Society, and Sustainable Development	P3 (Crown)
TG10, RC57 Joint Sessions	JS-75	The Algorithmic Turn in Visual Studies	M6 (Crown)
RC47, RC12 Joint Sessions	JS-76	The Criminalization of Struggles for Rights, Democratic Regression, and Legal Mobilisation. Part I	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	34	Retention in the Armed Forces	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	45	Finance As a Verb: Local Practices of Global Finance	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	73	How Reading Performance Is Related to Cultural Capital	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	107	Linked Lives: Intergenerational Relationships and Wellbeing	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	134	The Genesis of Sociology and the Relationship to Its Sibling Disciplines	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	147	State and Development	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	170	Methods of Ageing Research - Innovative Methodological Pathways	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	208	Formation of Assertive Identities: New entanglements of Politics and Religion (studies occasioned by the Bahun culture)	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	225	Digital Health Futures	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	280	Social Protection in Africa and Asia: Challenges and Innovations	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	309	Trying to Connect: Examining Social and Infrastructural Inequalities. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	328	Religion in Oceania	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	344	Biopolitics, Culture and Digital Control in the Context of Technology Assessment. Part I	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	361	New Directions in Environmental Sociology	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	394	Sport and Development	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	410	Social Mobility Using Historical Data	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	425	Policing and Punishment in Global Perspective	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	459	Is This Home? Return Migration and the (mis)Appropriation of the Ancestral Place of Origin	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	476	Southern Theories, Connell, and Other Sociological Reflections on Lives during Times of Crises.	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	495	Methods of Social Network Analysis	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	537	Alienation in the 21st Century: Revisiting, Reevaluating, Recentering. Part II	M8 (Crown)
RC38 Biography and Society	557	Same Interview, Different Perspectives – Invited Session	M13 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	572	Displacement, Migration, and Relocation	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	624	Global and Regional Trade Unions and the Future of Work Regulation	M2 (Crown)
RC45 Rational Choice	637	What makes sociology credible?	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	672	Violent Extremism and Authoritarianism: Which Relation with Social Movements?	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	685	Models of Mental Health Problems	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	705	RC51 Business Meeting	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	715	Professional Work. Part II	M12 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	728	Hearing the Voices of Children Revisited? Silencing and the Generational Order	M4 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	744	Socioeconomic Inequalities in Times of Change: Indicators for Assessing Them in a Global World	M9 (Crown)
WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations	769	Post-Globalization Challenging Democracies	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	785	Various Approaches to Ethnography/Institutional Ethnography	M15 (Crown)
TG07 Senses and Society	830	The Sense of Data and the Data of Sense: Bodies, Technologies, Spaces	M5 (Crown)
Associations of Sociology	859	Pacific Indigenous Sociology	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
ISA Former Presidents	880	Former ISA Presidents Session: History of ISA and its twenty World Congresses of Sociology	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
17:30 – 19:20			
TG04, RC17, RC24, RC40 Joint Sessions	JS-77	Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part II	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC54, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-78	Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part I	M6 (Crown)
RC35, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-79	Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part II	P1 (Crown)
RC25, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-80	Language and Immigrant Generations: New Entanglements.	CCH1 (Crown)
RC14, RC37, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-81	Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part I	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC52, RC19 Joint Sessions	JS-82	Professional Transformations in Public Sector/Social Services Management: Trends and Challenges – between Managerial ‘Governmentality’ and Authoritarian Governance?	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC02 Economy and Society	46	Postcolonial Ethnographies of Racial Capitalism: A View in/from Africa	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	74	Neoliberalism, Human Capital Discourse and Education Practice	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	91	Policing and the Construction of Racialized Groups and Social Control in the Americas	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	108	Generational Relations in Times of Intersecting Crises	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	135	Social Research, Funding Sources and Social Prognostication in the History of Sociology	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	148	Migration, Innovation and Entrepreneurship in the Contemporary World	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	154	Digital Futures between Domination and Participation Part III: Digital Discourse and Democracy	M14 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	195	Well-Being and Leisure Activities during COVID-19 Pandemic	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	226	Fertility and the Family	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18 Political Sociology	268	Invited Session : Authoritarianisms and Democracies through the Intermediaries of Public Action	M11 (Crown)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	296	RC20 Business Meeting	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	310	Trying to Connect: Examining Social and Infrastructural Inequalities. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	329	Religious Change in the Middle East and North Africa	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	345	Microbial Knowledge in Biopolitical Times	M10 (Crown)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	386	Political Leadership between Pandemic and Post-Pandemic Times	M5 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	411	Schools and Inequality	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	426	Comparative Juvenile Correctional Education: Toward the Transcendence of Globalized Penal Populism	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	439	Workers, Precarity and Exploitation of the “Post-Work” Era in Africa	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	460	Street Level Bureaucracies and Their Impact on Migrant in/Exclusion	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	477	Global Perspectives on the Struggle for Reproductive Justice	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	478	Roundtable 2	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	496	Doing Qualitative Research in Turbulent Times	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	510	The Challenges and Affordances of Longitudinal Youth Research	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC38 Biography and Society	558	The Social Construction of Migrants: Contested (Hi-)Stories of Migration from the Perspective of Biographical Research	M13 (Crown)
RC42 Social Psychology	606	Women and Children with Disability : Their Psycho-Social Susceptibility in the Modern Society.	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	613	Housing Inequality in Australia and New Zealand	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	625	RC44 Business Meeting	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	646	Addressing the Opportunities, Challenges and Lessons of Paid Domestic Work	M12 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	658	Social Movements, Decolonial Perspectives and Struggles Against Coloniality of Power	P3 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	686	The Social Genesis of Cognitive Difficulties	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	696	Tourism Paradoxes: Contradictions, Controversies, and Challenges	M8 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	729	Critical Perspectives on Children's Rights	M4 (Crown)
RC56 Historical Sociology	756	Historical Sociology As Relational Memory. Part II	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	764	Future Visions of Society: Visual Data and Ethics	M16 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	775	Urbanization in Himalayas: Emerging Crises and Civil Society	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Author Meets Critics	878	Aesthetico-Cultural Cosmopolitanism and French Youth: The Taste of the World by Vincenzo	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Author Meets Critics	879	Refuge beyond Reach: How Rich Democracies Repel Asylum Seekers by David Scott FitzGerald	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Ad Hoc Sessions	882	Neighbour Culture Around the World: Challenges and Opportunities	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Other Activities		Book launch: The Routledge International Handbook of Femicide and Femicide. Edited by Myrna Dawson and Saide Mobayed Vega	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
17:50 – 20:50			
Other Activities		BRICS Sociology Business Meeting	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
19:30 – 20:50			
RC03 Community Research	59	Local Welfare Regimes: A Comparative Analysis	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	183	RC12 Business Meeting	M16 (Crown)
RC16 Sociological Theory	242	Charisma, Populism, or Charismatic Populism?	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	281	RC19 Business Meeting	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC24 Environment and Society	362	RC24 Business Meeting	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	440	RC30 Business Meeting	P2 (Crown)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	527	RC35 Business Meeting	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	538	RC36 Business Meeting	M8 (Crown)
RC38 Biography and Society	559	RC38 Business Meeting	M13 (Crown)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	588	RC40 Business Meeting	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	596	RC41 Business Meeting	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	607	Securing Full Citizenship: Social Psychological Perspectives on Building Inclusive Communities	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC45 Rational Choice	638	RC45 Business Meeting	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	659	RC47 Business Meeting	P3 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	730	RC53 Business Meeting	M4 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC56 Historical Sociology	757	RC56 Business Meeting	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	776	Panel Discussion on Famine, Poverty, Energy Poverty, Climate Change and Climate Justice	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	786	WG06 Business Meeting	M15 (Crown)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	837	TG09 Business Meeting	M5 (Crown)
Professional Development	868	Principles Supporting Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in the ISA	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	869	The backstage of Journal Editing and How to be a good reviewer	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	870	What Editors Look for In a Book Manuscript and How to Prepare Your Proposal	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

21:00 – 23:00

ISA Administrative Meetings	890	Assembly of Councils. Elections	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
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Thursday 29 June**08:30 - 10:20**

RC16, RC35 Joint Sessions	JS-83	Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part III	P1 (Crown)
RC05, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-84	Citizenship and Inequality	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17, RC18 Joint Sessions	JS-85	Crisis and State Capacities 1: Crises and Challenges	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47, RC21 Joint Sessions	JS-86	New Urban Mobilizations and Solidarities - Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives	CCH1 (Crown)
WG05, RC24 Joint Sessions	JS-87	Transforming Traditional Knowledge System of Mountains: A Threat to Sustainability	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32, RC30 Joint Sessions	JS-88	Women in an Occupational Gender Segregation Global Labor Market	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC02 Economy and Society	47	Lifeworld of Precarious Work and Subjectivities	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	75	Contemporary Issues in Sociology of Education II	Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	109	Flight from Marriage and Parenthood in Asia	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	124	Futures Research: Open Themes Part II	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	149	Innovations in the Study of Innovation in Development	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	171	Ageing with Limited Family Ties	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	196	Authority and Leisure: A Symbiotic Dichotomy ?	M15 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	209	Contemporary Communication Issues. "Modernity" and "Traditions"	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	227	Enhancing the Dialogue between Science and Society: The Challenges of e-Health Care	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	282	Sensibilities, Pandemic and Social Policies	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	311	Governing Urban Marginality in the Post-Covid City. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	330	Keynote Session: Tom Smith "Spirituality and Religion: Trends and Cross-National Comparisons"	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	346	Bringing Intersectionality to Science: How Equity Diversity and Inclusion Impacts Scientific Policies and Practices. Part II	M10 (Crown)
RC25 Language and Society	377	Media, Social Exclusion and Audience Empowerment	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	412	Racial and Ethnic Inequality	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	427	Prision, Penitentiary Studies and Human Rights	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	461	Exploring International Migration from the Sending Country Perspective: The Case of the Philippines	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	479	COVID-19: Intersectional Perspectives on Patriarchy and the Pandemic	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	511	Youth Work and Authoritarianism: Responses to Social Conditions	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	545	Literature, Conflict and Social Relations	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	573	Research and Best Practices for Disasters Yet to Come: Preparedness and Mitigation amid Global Disasters	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	589	Exploring the emerging landscape of agtech innovation: venture capital, intermediaries, and the limits of "green capitalism"	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	614	Pathways into Sharing: From Space-Commoning to Collaborative Housing Practices	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	626	Rethinking Unionism	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	647	Womxn Navigating Academic Exclusion	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	673	Gezi in Retrospect: Recalling Mass Protests and Reclaiming Alternative Political Imaginations	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	687	Covid-19 and Mental Illness: A Syndemic & Structural Perspective	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	697	Decolonising Asian Tourism in the New Entanglements of International Tourism	M8 (Crown)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	706	Female Biocapital, Technology and the Market: A Multilevel Research Field. Part One	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	716	Opressors or Saviours? The Role of Professions in a Changing World	M12 (Crown)
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	736	Understanding Rising Authoritarianism: Affects, Emotions and Resonance in the Neoliberal Politics of the Body	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC55 Social Indicators	745	Measuring and analyzing the impact of the 2020-2022 pandemic on quality of life and wellbeing. Part II: basic public services and public policy	M9 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	798	Quantitative (Sociological) Research on Emotions: Challenges and Possibilities	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	809	Global Human Rights and Children	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	823	Emotions, Trust, Hope and Other Approaches of Managing Uncertainty and Non-Knowledge. Part I	M6 (Crown)
TG07 Senses and Society	831	Translating Sensory Experience	M5 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	844	Sociological Perspectives on Digital Methodologies	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
10:30 – 12:20			
RC53, RC39 Joint Sessions	JS-89	Childhoods at the Crossection of Disasters	CCH2 (Crown)
RC40, TG10 Joint Sessions	JS-90	Extending Critical Approaches to Agtech and Foodtech: Dialoguing Insights from the Insides and Outsides of Technology Design Projects	CCH3 (Crown)
RC06, RC28 Joint Sessions	JS-91	Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part I	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31, RC05 Joint Sessions	JS-92	Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48, RC07 Joint Sessions	JS-93	La Lucha Contra Los Extractivismos En América Latina y El Futuro De La Región Struggle Against Extractivism in Latin America and the Future of the Region	CCH1 (Crown)
RC23, RC22 Joint Sessions	JS-94	Religion and Science	P1 (Crown)
RC47, RC40 Joint Sessions	JS-95	The Potential of Food Movements and Intersectional Food Inequalities	P3 (Crown)
RC24, RC03 Joint Sessions	JS-96	Traditional Water Cultures and the Modern Life	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	35	Islamic Violent Movements in Contemporary Africa	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	48	Seeing Precarity through a Comparative Analysis of Labor in Various Economies	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	76	Intersectional Approach and Inequality of Educational Opportunity	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	136	Comparative National Histories of Sociology	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	172	Adult Children's Life Transitions, Intergenerational Support and Older Parent's Wellbeing	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	184	Judicialization of Social Problems and Governance of Security in Comparative Perspectives	M16 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	210	Contemporary Communication Issues: Technology and Surveillance	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	228	The Entanglements of Religions, Health, and Political-Economy in Africa	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	243	The New Trinity: Simmel. Tarde. Mead	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	257	Author Meets Critics: Richard Badham & Brenda Santiago - Ironies of Organizational Change	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	269	Crisis and State Capacities 2: Shifting State Capacities	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	283	Reconsidering Concepts and Ideas in Current Welfare State Policies	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	297	Values, Social Structures and Social Interactions: The Consequences and Challenges of the Pandemic	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	312	Governing Urban Marginality in the Post-Covid City. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	387	Social-Technical Dynamics, Cultural Issues and Artificial Intelligences in Smart Cities: Info-Communication Policy and Society	M5 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC27 Sociology of Sport	395	Sport, Bodies and Identities	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	413	Studying Educational Inequality with Big Data and Computational Methods	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	441	Uncertainty and Inequality: The Long-Term Effects of the Pandemic on Workers Careers and Experiences	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	462	Recent Developing Immigration and Integration Policies	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	480	Authors Meets Critics	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	497	Participatory Visual Research. Disentangling Power Dynamics Using Collaborative Techniques	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	512	Youth in the Global South: Opportunities, Challenges and Articulations	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	528	Critical Theories Revisited: Immanent Critique and Coloniality	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	539	New/Old Forms of Alienation and Resistance Under Advanced Neoliberalism	M8 (Crown)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	546	Arts in Cultural Diplomacy	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	597	COVID-19 and the World Population	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	627	Strikes: Past, Present and Futures	M2 (Crown)
RC45 Rational Choice	639	RC45 Open Oral Session on Advances in Rational Choice Research	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	648	Strengthening Democracy through Participation in Local Governance	M12 (Crown)
RC56 Historical Sociology	758	RC56 Open Session 1	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	777	Women in Developing and Least Developed Countries: Emerging Issues and Alternatives	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	787	Using Institutional Ethnography in Socio-Legal Studies	M15 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	824	Emotions, Trust, Hope and Other Approaches of Managing Uncertainty and Non-Knowledge. Part II	M6 (Crown)
TG11 Violence and Society	854	Violence, Culture and Traumatic Memory	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 13:50			
Spotlight Sessions	13	Whither the Arab-Israel Conflict?	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	25	Constructing the foundations for Asian sociology: A case of family and gender studies	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	26	De-Centering Global Sociology: The 'Peripheral Turn' in Social Theory and Research	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:00 – 15:20			
Plenary Sessions	10	PLIII.2 Populism and its "Others": An Intersectional Approach to the Construction of the "People"	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
Plenary Sessions	11	PLIV.2 Knowledge, Authority and Post-factual Era	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Australian Thematic Sessions	18	The Reshaping of Inequality in Australia	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
15:30 – 17:20			
RC40, RC07 Joint Sessions	JS-97	Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics II	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11, RC55 Joint Sessions	JS-98	Challenges and Opportunities in Measuring Violence	M12 (Crown)
RC05, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-99	Crossing Borders – Shifting Orders? Intersectional Perspectives on the Ukrainian War and the Reorganization of European Border Spaces	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06, RC28 Joint Sessions	JS-100	Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part II	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-101	Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part I	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG08, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-102	Mobilizing Emotions by Social Movements and in Contemporary Humanitarian Effort	CCH1 (Crown)
RC03, RC16 Joint Sessions	JS-103	Theories of Practice: New Perspectives in Urban Theory and Research	P1 (Crown)
RC46, RC17 Joint Sessions	JS-104	Whistleblowing and Social Justice	CCH2 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	49	Racial Capitalisms: Race, Caste, Ethnicity, and Indigeneity in Economic Life	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	77	The Challenge to Remain Relevant: Public Higher Education Versus Private Higher Education	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	137	Transnational Histories of Sociology	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	150	Local Politics between Resurgent Authoritarianism and Resilient Democratisation	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	155	Challenges and International Perspectives of Participatory Democracy at Work in the Era of Resurgent Authoritarianism	M14 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	197	Leisurement during the Period of COVID-19 Pandemic and Resurgent Authoritarianism	M15 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	211	Contemporary Communication Issues. Digital Futures	M1 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	270	Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited . Part III	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	284	RC19 Open Session Global South emerging economies	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	298	Trust and Social Capital in Cross-Cultural Perspective: Examining the Key Indicators and Newest Trends	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	313	Emotions and Social Experiences in the Cities Today. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	331	Keynote Speech Session - Jörg Stolz "Is the Secular Transition a Global Phenomenon? New Evidence and Problems"	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	347	Theoretical Models, Challenges, and Prospects for the Sociological Studies of Artificial Intelligence and Human-Machine Interactions in the Age of Online Culture	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	363	Environmental Inequalities	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	388	Life after and Beyond the City: Challenging Alternatives to Disturbing Urbanization	M5 (Crown)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	428	Policing, Violence and Public Security in a Global Perspective	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	442	The Grey Areas of Vulnerabilities in the World of Work	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	481	Gender and Queer Formations Under Authoritarianism in the Global South	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	498	Big Data Analysis for Social Sciences I	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	513	Youth Transitions in a Post-Pandemic World: Challenges and Opportunities for Youth and Young Adults in the Sphere of Work (1)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	547	Art and Theory	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC38 Biography and Society	560	Biographical Research in Extreme Places and Difficult to Reach Areas: Challenges and Strategies	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	574	The Rise of the Professional: Emergency Management and Community Responses to Disasters and Crises	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	598	Demography and Religion	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	608	RC42 Business Meeting	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	615	Social Design. from Theory to Practice in Building Inclusive Society.	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	628	Gendered Workplace Violence: What Role for the Labour Movement?	M2 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	660	Collaborative Research with Social Movements	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	674	Gender Mobilizations in Times of Rising Authoritarianism	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	688	Social and Emotional Well-Being of Adolescents and Young Adults Living in Rapidly Changing Real and Virtually Constructed Worlds	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	698	Politics and Borders	M8 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	731	COVID-19: Deepening Inequalities for the Marginalized Children	M4 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	810	Justice Systems, Reform, and Human Rights	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG10 Digital Sociology	845	Digitalization, Democracy and Trust	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Associations of Sociology	860	The Restoration of Justice and Human Rights	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Associations of Sociology	861	The Toolkit of Emerging Autocrats. Part I	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
17:30 – 19:20			
RC46, RC18 Joint Sessions	JS-105	Building Local Participatory Democracies in the Era of Threatened National Democracies and Resurgent Authoritarianism.	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG05, TG03 Joint Sessions	JS-106	Climate Change, Poverty and Inequality in Globalizing World: Changing Socio-Economic, Environmental Fabric of Human Settlements, Neglect of Human Rights and Marginalization of the Poor	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-107	Education, Solidarity and Engagement: The Study of Morals and Emotions in Altruistic Educational Experiences	CCH1 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC11, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-108	Migration and Ageing	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40, RC17 Joint Sessions	JS-109	Organizing through Standards and Value Hierarchies	CCH2 (Crown)
RC38, RC21 Joint Sessions	JS-110	Spatial Scales and the Analysis of Biographies and Family (Hi)Stories	P1 (Crown)
TG04, RC25 Joint Sessions	JS-111	The Language of Risk. Part I	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10, RC34, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-112	To Participate or Not to Participate? Social Movements 4.0 and the Return of Dichotomies	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03, RC37 Joint Sessions	JS-113	Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development II	M2 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	50	Economy and Culture	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	92	Racism, Nationalism and the Impact on Intermarriage and Mixed Families	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	110	RC06 Business Meeting	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	125	Futures Research: Open Themes. Part I	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	138	Reflecting upon Translation in the History of Sociology	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	185	RC12 WG on Civil Justice and Dispute Resolution	M16 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	229	Social Dimensions of Public Health Activism: Global, National and Local Perspectives	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	244	Cultural Sociology: Hermeneutics, Semiotics, Dialectics	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	285	Eco-Social Policies: Is a Consensus between the Ecological, Social and Economic Possible?	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	314	Emotions and Social Experiences in the Cities Today. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	332	Nonreligion: Meaning, Practice, and Consequences across the Life Course, Part 1	CCH3 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	333	Religion Poster Session	Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	348	The Robert K. Merton Award for Distinguished Contribution to the Sociology of Science and Technology	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	364	Gendering the Sociology of Climate Change	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	414	Advancing Research on Gender Inequalities: A Life Course Perspective	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	443	Current Theoretic and Methodologic Challenges in Sociology of Work	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	482	Empowerment of Women in India and Abroad	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	499	Data Quality of Cross-National Surveys	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	514	Youth Transitions in a Post-Pandemic World: Challenges and Opportunities for Youth and Young Adults in the Sphere of Work (2)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	529	The Peripheral Turn in Sociology: Rethinking Sociology As Nonexclusionary and Inclusive. Part I	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	575	Examining the Illusion of Control: Single Truths, Complexity and Disaster Resilience	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC45 Rational Choice	640	Rational Choice and Unintended Consequences amid Social Crisis	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	661	Social Movements, Solidarity Economy and Common Goods	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	675	RC48 Business Meeting	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	707	Female Biocapital, Technology and the Market: A Multilevel Research Field. Part Two	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	717	Professions and Inequalities	M12 (Crown)
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	737	Body throughout Time: The Role of Women in Theoretical and Social Movements	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC55 Social Indicators	746	Indicators to Compare Social Stratification and Inequalities Among Countries	M9 (Crown)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	788	Exploring Intersections: Institutional Ethnography, Environment, and Development	M15 (Crown)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	838	Global Reach for Your Teaching Research and Artifacts: How to Publish in the ISA's 'Sociological Teaching' Online Platforms	M5 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	846	Sociological Theory for a Digital Society	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11 Violence and Society	855	Durkheim, Violence and Society	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Ad Hoc Sessions	883	Teaching the Sociology of Climate Change across the Sociology Curriculum	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
ISA Administrative Meetings	891	Council of National Associations. Elections	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
19:30 – 20:50			
RC02 Economy and Society	51	RC02 Business Meeting	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	156	RC10 Business Meeting	M14 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	198	RC13 Business Meeting	M15 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	271	RC18 Business Meeting	M11 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	349	RC23 Business Meeting	M10 (Crown)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	429	RC29 Business Meeting	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	616	RC43 Business Meeting	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	629	Collective and Connective Action: Workers and Social Media	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	649	Marginalized Communities As Agents of Social Change	P3 (Crown)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	689	RC49 Business Meeting	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	718	RC52 Business Meeting	M12 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	747	RC55 Business Meeting	M9 (Crown)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	825	TG04 Business Meeting	M6 (Crown)
TG07 Senses and Society	832	TG07 Business Meeting	M5 (Crown)
Professional Development	871	Doing Sociology Writing Workshop	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	872	How to Write a Book Review and Why It Is Important for Early-Career Scholars	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

21:00 – 23:00

ISA Administrative Meetings	892	Research Council. Elections	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
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Friday 30 June

08:30 - 10:20

RC47, RC38 Joint Sessions	JS-114	Black Lives and the New Wave of Antiracist Mobilization within and across World Regions	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01, RC39 Joint Sessions	JS-115	COVID-19: Patterns in Domestic Military Operations	CCH2 (Crown)
RC04, RC03 Joint Sessions	JS-116	Inclusive Education, Knowledge Co-Production, Social Justice and Human Rights	P1 (Crown)
RC02, RC23 Joint Sessions	JS-117	International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Sovereignty and Infrastructural Power	CCH1 (Crown)
RC25, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-118	Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part II	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11, RC32 Joint Sessions	JS-119	Persistence and Change: Collaborative, Conceptual and Contextual Global Understandings of Gender-Based and Intersectional Violence	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC02 Economy and Society	52	Elements for an Emancipatory Sociology: An Appraisal of the Work of István Mészáros	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	93	African Diaspora Settlement: Opportunities and Challenges	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	111	International Comparative Perspectives on Family Goals and Values	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	157	Networking, Collaborative Dialogue, Shared Governance: Practical Cases for Sustaining Participatory Democracy in Education	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	173	Formal and Informal Care in Later Life	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	186	Sociology of Hate Speech Laws. 1	M16 (Crown)
RC16 Sociological Theory	245	Configuration and Codes and Sustainability Part I	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	286	Intersectionalities - Race, Gender and Social Class Discrimination, Religion and Political Identification.	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	299	Comparative Analysis of Transnational Migration Communities and the Formation of New Urban Ethnicity in the Global Cities in the Age of Artificial Intelligence and Online Culture	M3 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	315	Knowledge and Power Contestation in Transforming Urban Spaces in India	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC22 Sociology of Religion	334	Remembering the Contributions of Deceased Scholars Including James Beckford, Gary Bouma & Roland Robertson	CCH3 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	365	Sustainable Energy Transitions I: Frameworks, Drivers and Barriers	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	396	Sport, Exclusion and Inequities	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	415	Session on New Developments of Intra- and Intergenerational Social Mobility	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	430	Social Violence, Urban Studies and Cybercrime	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	444	Conflicts and Normative Transactions in Multicultural Work Contexts	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	483	Female Migration, Poverty and Inequality	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	500	From Interviewing to Diaries: Data Quality in Quantitative and Qualitative Social Research	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	515	Global South Youth Studies: The RC34 Oxford University Press Handbook Presidential Project	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	530	New Horizon for the Memory Studies	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	548	Museos Inclusivos, Polifónicos y Participativos: Desafíos Para Las Instituciones Museales En El Siglo XXI	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	590	Food and Social Change III	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	599	Demography and War	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC43 Housing and Built Environment	617	Housing Policies and Practices: Authoritarian Means to Dispossess the Urban Poor or the Tolerance of Neglected Citizens?	214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	630	Labour Relations and Strategic Industries in Brazil	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	650	Citizen Involvement and Co-Production of Care in Vulnerable Communities	M12 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	676	Globalization-Induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, Identity and Ecological issues). Part II	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	699	New Digital/Social Entanglements in Tourism: Implications for Sustainability, Industry and Communities.	M8 (Crown)
RC53 Sociology of Childhood	732	Slow Violence, Crises of Care, and Possible Futures	M4 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	748	Youth Wellbeing and Changes of Social Institutions	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	778	Interrogating Famine	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	789	The Politics of Institutional Ethnography: Representation, Reflexivity, and Method	M15 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	799	Intersectional Perspectives on Love	M13 (Crown)
10:30 – 12:20			
RC54, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-120	Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part II	M6 (Crown)
RC19, RC18 Joint Sessions	JS-121	Combating Homelessness in Welfare State Regimes: A New Paradigm Shift in Local Social Policy?	P1 (Crown)
RC03, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-122	Community Influences on Lifestyles and Health	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC04, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-123	Educational Migration in the Post-Pandemic World: Exploring Continuities and Discontinuities	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05, RC20 Joint Sessions	JS-124	Indigenous Sociology, Indigenous Lifeworlds	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC53, RC11 Joint Sessions	JS-125	Linking Ages - Pathways to Cross-Fertilizing the Fields of Age and Childhood Studies	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC49, TG04 Joint Sessions	JS-126	Mental Health and Risk	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-127	Thinking through and Beyond Capitalism after the Great Reset	CCH2 (Crown)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	36	RC01 Business Meeting	M14 (Crown)
RC06 Family Research	112	Marriage Equality Around the World	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	126	Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part III	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC08 History of Sociology	139	Sociology and Sociologists in Latin America. Institutions, Biographies, Networks, and Comparative Perspectives.	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development	151	Visual Representations of Development: Practices and Possibilities	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	212	Creación De Espacios De Participación Y Libertad Informativa. Propuestas Desde La Comunicación Responsable Y La Sociología	Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	258	Organizational Networks: Innovation and Learning in Response of Organizational Challenges	M4 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	316	Political Contestations Along the Urbanization Continuum	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	335	Spirituality, Wellbeing and Risks	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	350	Collaborative Robots: New Socio-Technical Constellations and Dominant Narratives	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	366	Sustainable Energy Transitions II: Frameworks, Drivers and Barriers.	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	378	Discursive Discourses of Political Violence	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	416	Child Development and Educational Inequalities	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	417	Stratification and Inequality in Education - the Role of Context	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	431	Insecurities, Violence and Democracy in the Global South	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	445	Transformation of Industrial Relations and Emerging Organization: Digital, Rationalization and Storage Industry.	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	484	Gender-Based Violence and Inequalities of Social Class and Race/Ethnicity	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	516	Youth in Latin America and the Caribbean: Pandemic Impacts on Inequalities from an Intersectional Perspective	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC36 Alienation Theory and Research	540	The Covid-19 Pandemic and Alienation	M8 (Crown)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	549	Solidarity in Arts and Culture	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC38 Biography and Society	561	Biographical Perspectives in the Research Field of Political Participation	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	576	Cultural Heritage and Disaster	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	609	Social Alienation	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	631	Labour and the Green Transition	M2 (Crown)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	662	Far-Right Movements, Authoritarianism and Pandemic	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	677	Assessing the Trajectories of People's Movements in South Asia	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	708	Understanding Political Crises in the 2020s - a Sociocybernetics Approach	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	719	Challenges of Professional Groups and Professionalism in Latin America in a Context of Disputes between Authoritarianism and Democracy	M12 (Crown)
RC56 Historical Sociology	759	RC56 Open Session 2	M9 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	765	The Social Manifestations' Synthesis As Image	M16 (Crown)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	790	The Legacy of Dorothy E. Smith: What is the Future of IE?	M15 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	811	Locating Human Rights in Globalized World	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG07 Senses and Society	833	Experiencing Silence and Expanded Time; Other Sensory Pathways and Knowledge	M5 (Crown)
TG10 Digital Sociology	847	Responsible Digitalization	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG11 Violence and Society	856	The Precarity of (Social) Life: Mapping the Impact of the Global Pandemic on Violence(s) Against Women	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 13:50			
Integrative Sessions	27	Social movements under varieties of authoritarian threats	Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Integrative Sessions	28	The Good University: Addressing Growing Stratification and Gender Discrimination in the University Workforce	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:00 – 16:00			
Presidential Sessions	3	Building a Just Post-COVID-19 World	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
15:30 – 17:20			
WG01, RC34 Joint Sessions	JS-128	Approaching Planetary Youth Research	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC02, RC35 Joint Sessions	JS-129	Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Innovation and Dynamism	P1 (Crown)
RC51, RC18, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-130	Complexity in the Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe (II)	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47, WG08 Joint Sessions	JS-131	Emotions and Environmental Activism	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC09, RC48 Joint Sessions	JS-132	The Prospects of a Pluriversal Transition to a Post-Capitalist, Post-Carbon Future	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC21, RC43, RC39 Joint Sessions	JS-133	Understanding the Entanglements of Urban Disasters	CCH1 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC02 Economy and Society	53	Rising Corporate Concentration and the Monopolistic Milieu	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	60	Can Place-Based Policies Enhance Community Life and Democracy: On Neighbourhood Governance, Participation and Institutional Trust.	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	78	When Global Meets Local: the Dialectics between Indigenous Knowledge and Global Competition	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	94	Challenges in Comparative Research between Europe and Colonized Countries	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	113	Single-Parent Families and Institutions in the Global South and North	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	127	Horizons of Future and Everyday Life	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	158	Organizing Against Authoritarianism in the Platform and on-Demand Economy	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	174	Ageing, Care and Technology	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	187	Sociology of Hate Speech Laws. 2	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	199	Socio-Political Scenario of Drugs and Leisure in Global Era	M15 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	213	New Communication Technologies and Changing Patterns of Social Stratification in Globalizing World	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	230	Patients Participation and Transformation of Society	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	246	Social Imaginaries and Political Forms. Part II	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	259	How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 2)	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	272	Conservative Mobilizations of Local Organizations : Power Relations and Tensions Around Democracy	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	287	RC19 Keynote Address: Social Safety Nets in OECD Countries: Tracing Three Decades of Change	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	300	Happiness, Well-Being and Life Quality in Comparative Perspective	M3 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	336	Religion and Wellbeing in Asia in Times of Crisis	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	351	Quantification and Power: Values, Normative Agendas and Policy Paradigms behind Numbers. Part I	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	367	Bringing nature in: Human-wildlife interactions.	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	379	Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part III	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	418	Regionally Different? the Relevance of Geo-Spatial Inequalities for Labour Market Outcomes	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	432	Drugs, Organized Crime and Illicit Markets	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	446	Traditional and New Mechanisms of Social Protection of Workers	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	485	Gendering Nationalism in 21st Century China 1	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC34 Sociology of Youth	517	Young People's Experiences and Relationships in the Global Pandemic (2)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	550	Analyzing Films and Series As a Way to Social Knowledge	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC38 Biography and Society	562	Biography and Disaster: From Methodological Perspectives	M13 (Crown)
RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food	591	Good Farm Animal Welfare in Sustainable Food Systems	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	600	Disease Progression and Mortality in Prospective Studies	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	651	Clinical Sociologists in Poverty Eradication Efforts	M12 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	678	Generational Creativity in Contemporary Youth Activism	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences	738	RC54 Business Meeting	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC55 Social Indicators	749	Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of the 2020-2022 Pandemic on Quality of Life and Well-Being. Part III: Children and young people	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	779	Fostering Federalism, Decentralization and People Participation to Cope with Resurgent Authoritarianism and Strengthen and Sustain Democracies, Development and Good Governance	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	812	Pluriversal Approaches to Human Rights and Sdg's	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	826	Theorizing Risk and Uncertainty. Part II	M6 (Crown)
TG09 Sociological Teaching	839	Strategies for Making Sociology Locally and Globally Relevant for Students	M5 (Crown)
Associations of Sociology	862	Recovery, Resilience, and Regeneration beyond Disasters	209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Associations of Sociology	898	The Toolkit of Emerging Autocrats. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

17:30 – 19:20

RC03, RC21 Joint Sessions	JS-134	(Re)Turning to Urban (new) Normality	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-135	Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Relational and Cultural Analysis	P1 (Crown)
RC09, RC15 Joint Sessions	JS-136	Knowledge Co-Production, Communities, Social Justice and Human Rights	CCH1 (Crown)
RC31, RC18, RC51 Joint Sessions	JS-137	The Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution	37	Beyond the Greedy Institution	M14 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	54	Reconstructing the Global Economy – Production Chains, Knowledge Chains, & Value Chains	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	79	Education for Sustainable Development	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	95	The Normalisation of the Global Far Right: From Global Financial Crisis to Covid Pandemic	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	114	New Tales of the Golden Family. Actors, Narratives and Contestation across Resurgent Authoritarianism	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	128	Post-Pandemic Futures: Affect, Responsibility and Materiality.	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC08 History of Sociology	140	South-South Intellectual Exchanges : Networks, Actors, Theories, Impact	102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	214	The Expansion of Social Media and the Emergence of Global Communication System: Theoretical, Methodological and Empirical Concerns	M1 (Crown)
RC16 Sociological Theory	247	Configuration, Code and Sustainability Part II	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	260	How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 3)	M4 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	288	Beyond the Extremely Poor: Social Policies and Individual Strategies in the Global South	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC20 Comparative Sociology	301	Comparative Sociology of Public Opinion	M3 (Crown)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	337	Nonreligion: Meaning, Practice, and Consequences across the Life Course, Part 2	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	352	Digital Neoliberalism and Surveillance Capitalism: Technology Induced Monopoly	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	368	Immaterialities: Norms, Culture and Religion in environmental politics and practice.	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	397	Global Sport Practices	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	419	Income Inequality, Class and Consumption	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	447	Understanding Care Work in a Context of Crisis: Health, Risks and Labour Conflicts	P2 (Crown)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	486	Secular Authoritarianism and Gender Inequalities in Plural Societies	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	501	Big Data Analysis for Social Sciences II	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	518	Across Youth Emotions and Aspirations: Educational Institutions, Inner Entrepreneurship and Social Imaginaries	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	551	Place and the Sociology of Art	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	577	A Dialogue on Community Engagement and Disaster Research	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	632	Labour and Climate Change	M2 (Crown)
RC46 Clinical Sociology	652	Springer's Clinical Sociology Book Series: Celebrating the New Books and Submitting Your Proposal	P3 (Crown)
RC49 Mental Health and Illness	690	Social Inclusion of Mentally Ill Persons	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	720	Professionalization and Counter-Professionalization in Early-Childhood Education and Care	M12 (Crown)
RC57 Visual Sociology	766	Social Visualities: Palgrave Book Series Launch.	M16 (Crown)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	791	Institutional Ethnography (IE) in Healthcare and Healthcare Education	M15 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	800	Social Justice and Emotions	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	813	Rising Authoritarianism and Perspectives on Democracy in Globalized World	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG10 Digital Sociology	848	Society and Algorithms	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
Ad Hoc Sessions	884	What Makes a Global Intellectual? The Joyful Seriousness of Robert Bellah	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
ISA Administrative Meetings	893	Training session RC/WG/TG officers	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
19:30 – 20:50			
Professional Development	873	Managing Everyday Life as a Research-Focused Academic	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
Professional Development	874	Practicing Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in ISA Research Committees, Working Groups, and Thematic Groups	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
21:00 – 23:00			
Social Events	897	Farewell Party	Conference Hall 1 (Crown, Level 2)

Saturday 1 July

08:30 - 10:20

RC35, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-138	Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Societal Variation, Entrepreneurship	P1 (Crown)
RC05, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-139	Racial Capitalisms, Spatial Productions	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	61	Cultural Institutions and Community	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	80	Rethinking the Modern Educational Model: East Asian Perspectives	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	115	Work-Family Interface and Parental and Child Wellbeing in Challenging Times	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	159	Action-Research for Participation and Empowerment	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	175	Ageing Better By Design - Activation, Co-Production and Social Inclusion of Older People	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	188	Migration and Gendered Labour	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	200	Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Leisure: Adaptation of New Lifestyle during Lockdown	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	231	Reproduction in the Current World: Focusing on Prenatal Testing and Abortion	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	261	(Meta)Theorizing in Organizational Sociology	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	273	Meritocracy and Refinement of Authoritarianism in Growing Inequality	M11 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	317	Urban Art between Community and Artwashing	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	338	Religion As an Instrument of Rooting for the Liquid Identity of Migrants Part 1	CCH3 (Crown)
RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology	353	State Role in the Post-Pandemic Market of Ideas	M10 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	369	Expertise for Transformative Change	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	380	Intersections of Gender, Sexuality, and Age (Youth) Looking at Language	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice	389	Conspiracy Theories, Populism and Crisis in the Global World	M5 (Crown)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC28 Social Stratification	420	Impact of the Covid Pandemic for Gender Inequality in Work and Family	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC29 Deviance and Social Control	433	Gender Violence: Atrocities on Women and Other Vulnerable Groups in the Covid Era	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30 Sociology of Work	448	Post-Pandemic Possibilities for Workplace Change	P2 (Crown)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	463	Indian Migrants in India and Abroad	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	487	The Future of Global Gender Inequality and Intersectionalities	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	519	Digital Citizenship and Digital Skills of Young People (1)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC37 Sociology of Arts	552	RC37 Business Meeting	206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC38 Biography and Society	563	Indigenous People's Experiences amid Socio-Historical Power Struggles	M13 (Crown)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	578	Disasters and Crime	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	601	New Family Structures	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC42 Social Psychology	610	Social Psychology in the Age of COVID	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	679	Nature vs Culture: emerging conflicts and citizens' rights	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC50 International Tourism	700	Tourism As Geopolitical Strategy: State Action, Soft Power and Ordinary Practices and Repertoires in International and Domestic Tourism	M8 (Crown)
RC51 Sociocybernetics	709	Understanding Digital and Surveillance Capitalism from Sociocybernetic Perspectives	M3 (Crown)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	721	RC52 Open Session I: Professionalism, Ethics and Social Change	M12 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	750	Gender Equality Measurement. Part I	M9 (Crown)
WG05 Famine and Society	780	WG05 Business Meeting	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	814	Perspectives on Mass Migration, Refugees, and Prisoners of War	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty	827	Risk and Space: Risk Perception and Risk Normalization	M6 (Crown)
10:30 – 12:20			
TG10, RC21 Joint Sessions	JS-140	Digital Urbanism	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC48, RC07, RC47 Joint Sessions	JS-141	Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part I	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC11, RC30 Joint Sessions	JS-142	Participation Chances, Inequality and Risks of Exclusion in Prolonged Working Lives in Europe	CCH1 (Crown)
RC02, RC12 Joint Sessions	JS-143	Tax Policies and Tax Optimization Practices	P1 (Crown)
RC09, RC02 Joint Sessions	JS-144	Women Entrepreneurs on the African Continent and Beyond	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	62	Comunidades Resilientes: Capacidades Colectivas De Resistencia y Transformación Ante Las Nuevas Adversidades	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	81	Edtech and the Post-Pandemic University: Understandings and Interventions	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	96	Racialization, Migration and Covid	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	116	Politics, Family, and Familial Relationships	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	160	Democratic Participation and Self-Management Vs Authoritarianism: Theoretical Reflections and Propositions	M14 (Crown)
RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture	215	Socio-Digital Challenges and Vulnerability of Organizations. Communicative Approaches	M1 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	232	Inequalities in Health, Mental Health, and Discrimination. Part I	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	248	Classical Social Theory and Emotions Revisited	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17 Sociology of Organization	262	Organizations and Digital Innovation	M4 (Crown)
RC18 Political Sociology	274	Toward a New Political Sociology of Health	M11 (Crown)
RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy	289	Global Social Policy in Times of Crisis: Covid-19 and the Role of International Organizations	217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	339	Religion and Health. Intersections and (Dis)Agreements in Contemporary Societies.	CCH3 (Crown)
RC24 Environment and Society	370	Roles and Impacts of Non-State Actors for Climate Change Mitigation	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC25 Language and Society	381	The Functional Perspective of the Regional Languages in the Modern World	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC27 Sociology of Sport	398	RC27 Business Meeting	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	421	Innovation in Sociological Research of Gender and Socio-Economic Policies	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	464	Religions and Migrations: The Experience of the Boundaries and Borders	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32 Women, Gender and Society	488	Gendering Nationalism in 21st Century China 2	109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	520	Digital Citizenship and Digital Skills of Young People (2)	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis	531	The Peripheral Turn in Sociology: Rethinking Sociology As Nonexclusionary and Inclusive. Part II	107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	579	Toward a Critical Disaster Studies in Japan and Beyond: Issues in Theory and Research	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC41 Sociology of Population	602	General Population Issues	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC44 Labor Movements	633	Authoritarian Innovations in Labour Governance	M2 (Crown)
RC55 Social Indicators	751	Gender Equality Measurement. Part II	M9 (Crown)
WG06 Institutional Ethnography	792	Doing Institutional Ethnography: Issues and Innovations II	M15 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	801	Emotions, Subjectivities, and Sociodynamics of Inequalities Emociones, Subjetividades y Sociodinámicas De Las Desigualdades	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	815	Precarious Workers, Precarious Residents and Authoritarian Politics	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
ISA Administrative Meetings	894	New Executive Committee meeting	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
12:30 – 14:00			
ISA Administrative Meetings	895	Induction session new EC officers	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30, RC24 Joint Sessions	JS-145	Environment and Work: Links and Threats	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC32, RC38 Joint Sessions	JS-146	Gendered Intergenerational Experiences of Social Mobility in Migration	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC56, RC17 Joint Sessions	JS-147	Historical Sociology of Organizations. Part II	M4 (Crown)
RC25, RC34 Joint Sessions	JS-148	Language on/of Youth Under COVID-19 Pandemic	P1 (Crown)
RC02, TG11 Joint Sessions	JS-149	Political Economy and Violence: The Implications of Taking Violence Seriously for Theories of Hegemonic and Counter-Hegemonic Forces	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	63	Comunidades Resilientes: Capacidades Colectivas De Resistencia y Transformación Ante Las Nuevas Adversidades II	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	82	The Possibilities and Challenges of Decoloniality in Education and Research	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity	97	Exploring the New Configurations of Whiteness	207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	117	The 'empty Nest' in Times of Change: An International Comparative Perspective on Family Recompositions and Adult Children and Parents' Relationships	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	129	Hope, Future and Social Theory	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	161	Civic Participation and the Process of Local Community Revitalization. Multinational Perspective and Experience	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	176	Ageing, Autonomy and Connectedness	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC12 Sociology of Law	189	Social System and Legal Systems	M16 (Crown)
RC13 Sociology of Leisure	201	Changing Nature of Leisure Activities during Resurgent Authoritarianism	M15 (Crown)
RC15 Sociology of Health	233	Inequality in Health Care - Empirical Studies about Health Care Professions	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	249	Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part IV	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18 Political Sociology	275	The State and Society Relationship in East Asian Countries Under COVID-19 Pandemic	M11 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	318	Contesting Urban Governance. New Forms of Citizenship and the Power of Protest across Institutional Contexts. Part I	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC22 Sociology of Religion	340	Religious Diversity in Australia	CCH3 (Crown)
RC28 Social Stratification	422	Immigration, Integration, and Attitudes Toward Immigrants	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC31 Sociology of Migration	465	Precarious Legal Status Trajectories	204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC33 Logic and Methodology in Sociology	502	Using Social Media for Social Research: Theoretical and Methodological Challenges	111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	580	The Intersection of Health and Disasters	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	663	Social Movements and the State	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	680	Agrarian and Rural Movements : Changing Dynamics and New Alliances	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	722	RC52 Open Session II: Corporatism, Bureaucratization and Their Implications for Professionalism	M12 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	802	Hatred Also Loves: Gender and Emotions in Today's Political Landscape	M13 (Crown)
TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice	816	Rising Authoritarianism and Challenges before Marginalized Communities in Globalized World	218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG10 Digital Sociology	849	Do We Need a Sociology of the Digital?	205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
14:30 – 16:20			
RC32, RC20 Joint Sessions	JS-150	Female Employment, Gender Equality and Women Empowerment across the Globe	105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC17, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-151	Organising Precarity and Inequality in the Gig Economy	CCH1 (Crown)
RC22, RC31 Joint Sessions	JS-152	Religion As an Instrument of Rooting for the Liquid Identity of Migrants Part 2	106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
TG04, RC25 Joint Sessions	JS-153	The Language of Risk. Part II	203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC30, RC44 Joint Sessions	JS-154	Trade Unions Under Authoritarianism in the Global South	P1 (Crown)
RC02 Economy and Society	55	Global Inequalities and Pandemic Diseases--Recent and Historical Impacts of Contagious Diseases on within- and between-Country Inequalities	213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC03 Community Research	64	RC03 Business Meeting	108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC04 Sociology of Education	83	Caste, Social Psyche and Humiliation at Higher Education	212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC06 Family Research	118	Parenting and Child and Adolescent Socioemotional Development in Chinese Families	220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC07 Futures Research	130	Disinformation in the Technomediatic Public Sphere	112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management	162	Latin American Social Movements, Collective Actions and Democracy	M14 (Crown)
RC11 Sociology of Aging	177	Retirement in the 21st Century	216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC15 Sociology of Health	234	Inequalities in Health, Mental Health, and Discrimination. Part II	208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC16 Sociological Theory	250	Theorizing Desires: Sexualizing Sociological Theories	210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC18 Political Sociology	276	Social Constraint and Self-Control in Times of Pandemic Crisis	M11 (Crown)
RC21 Regional and Urban Development	319	Contesting Urban Governance. New Forms of Citizenship and the Power of Protest across Institutional Contexts. Part II	104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC24 Environment and Society	371	Social Dynamics of Climate Change Policy-Making and Political Action	219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC28 Social Stratification	423	Social Stratification Research in the Aging Population	110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC34 Sociology of Youth	521	Young People, the 'crisis of Democracy' and Political Transformation	103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Program	No.	Session Title	Room
RC39 Sociology of Disasters	581	Technology and Disasters	101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements	664	Religious and Social Movements	P3 (Crown)
RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change	681	Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part II	211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups	723	The Changing Paradigm of Professions and Professional Groups in the Era of Globalization	M12 (Crown)
WG08 Society and Emotions	803	Emotions in Poverty Contexts	M13 (Crown)
15:30 – 17:20			
Spotlight Sessions	14	War in Ukraine: a Sociological Perspective	Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)
16:30 – 18:30			
Other Activities		Social Love and Solidarity Group	215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Timetable of Administrative Meetings

No.	Session Title	Room
Friday 23 June		
<i>09:00 - 13:00</i>		
885	Publications Committee	University of Melbourne
885	Finance and Membership Committee	University of Melbourne
<i>14:30 - 18:30</i>		
885	Research Coordinating Committee	University of Melbourne
885	National Associations Liaison Committee	University of Melbourne
Saturday 24 June		
<i>09:00 - 18:30</i>		
886	Executive Committee	218 (Melbourne Convention Center)
Sunday 25 June		
<i>10:30 - 12:30</i>		
887	Research Council Business Meeting	M12 (Crown)
<i>14:00 - 16:00</i>		
888	Council of National Associations Business Meeting	M12 (Crown)
Monday 26 June		
<i>21:00 - 23:00</i>		
889	Election Speeches by the Candidates	Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Center)
Wednesday 28 June		
<i>21:00 - 23:00</i>		
890	Assembly of Councils: Election of the President and Four Vice-Presidents	104 (Melbourne Convention Center)
Thursday 29 June		
<i>17:30 - 19:30</i>		
891	Council of National Associations Elections	216 (Melbourne Convention Center)
<i>21:00 - 23:00</i>		
892	Research Council Elections	216 (Melbourne Convention Center)
Friday 30 June		
<i>17:30 - 19:20</i>		
893	Training session RC/WG/TG Officer	104 (Melbourne Convention Center)
Saturday 1 July		
<i>10:30 - 12:20</i>		
894	New Executive Committee meeting	216 (Melbourne Convention Center)
<i>12:30 - 14:00</i>		
895	Induction session new EC office	103 (Melbourne Convention Center)

Presidential Sessions

Sunday 25 June

17:30 - 20:15

1 Opening Ceremony and Presidential Address

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

Welcome to Country

Welcome by Sari Hanafi, President of the International Sociological Association

Welcome by Dan Woodman, Chair of the Australian Local Organizing Committee

Welcome by Alphia Possamai-Inesedy, President of the Australian Sociological Association

ISA Award for Excellence in Research and Practice presented by Sari Hanafi, ISA President

Speech of the awardee. Raewyn Connell

ISA Worldwide Competition for Junior Sociologists. Winners' presentation by Ayse Saktanber, Coordinator, Member of the ISA Executive Committee

XXI ISA World Congress of Sociology 2027. Presented by Jun HAN, Vice-Chair of the Local Organizing Committee

Presidential Address Sari Hanafi, President of the International Sociological Association

Discussion

Monday 26 June

08:30 - 10:20

2 Liberalism, the Other and Religion

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

Chair: Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

2.1 Cécile LABORDE, *Nuffield College, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*
Minimal Secularism: A Defense

2.2 Azmi BISHARA, *Arab center for research and policy studies, Qatar*
Should Liberals in Authoritarian States Stand for Comprehensive or Just for Minimal "Political Liberalism"?

2.3 Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
First principles: A Declaration of Interdependence

2.4 Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia*
Religious Nationalism and Anti-Cosmopolitan Terror

Friday 30 June

14:00 - 16:00

3 Building a Just Post-COVID-19 World

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

Chair: Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

3.1 Guangjin CHEN, *Institute of Sociology, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, Beijing, China*
The Present Situation, Challenges and Way ahead of Social Development and Justice in China in Post-Covid Period from Sociological Perspective

3.2 Didier FASSIN, *Collège de France, Institute for Advanced Study, France*
Unlearned Lessons of the Pandemic

3.3 Eva ILLOUZ, *Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales-Paris, France*

Fear, the Anti-Democratic Emotion

3.4 Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*
The global politicization and religionization of COVID-19 pandemic – the future of the past or the past of the future?

Plenary Sessions

Monday 26 June

14:00 - 15:20

4 PLI.1 Postsecularity or Multiple Secularities?

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Geoffrey PLEYERS, *FNRS-CriDIS/ UCLouvain & CEMondiales, Belgium* and Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

- 4.1** Armando SALVATORE, *McGill University, Canada*
Reinventing Secularity As Civility? Islamic Articulations Linking Past and Present
- 4.2** Anindita CHAKRABARTI, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Post-Secularity, Multiple Secularities and Post-Coloniality: Investigating the Indian Conundrum
- 4.3** Monika WOHLRAB-SAHR, *Universität Leipzig, Germany*
Post-Secularity or Multiple Secularities – What Is behind New Interpretations of the Religious Situation?

5 PLII.1 Inequalities Created in Neoliberal Economies

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Allison LOCONTO, *Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA), France* and Dan WOODMAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

- 5.1** Michele LAMONT, *Harvard University, USA*
Seeing Others: Redefining Worth in our Divided World
- 5.2** Lisa ADKINS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Inequalities in the Asset Economy: Some Questions for Sociology

5.3 Soo Yeon KIM, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Global Trade, the Neoliberal Political Economy, and Inequality

5.4 Matthew WYNYARD, *Massey University, New Zealand*
Happy ever after in the marketplace? Neoliberalism and Māori in Aotearoa New Zealand.

Tuesday 27 June

14:00 - 15:20

6 PLI.2 Toward Broader Horizons of Secularity

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Bandana PURKAYASTHA, *University of Connecticut, USA* and Armando SALVATORE, *McGill University, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

- 6.1** Lutfi SUNAR, *Istanbul Medeniyet Üniversitesi, Turkey*
New Forms of Secularities: Values and Latent Secularism in Everyday Life in Turkey
- 6.2** Kalpana KANNABIRAN
Beyond Hubris, Triumphal Pageantry and Whataboutery: Re-Notating the Secular for Our Times
- 6.3** Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Beyond multiple modernities and secularization as normativity: how to (sociologically) deal with charismatic leaders in times of resurgent authoritarianism.
- 6.4** Roberto CIPRIANI, *University Roma Tre, Italy*
Beyond Secularization: New Perspectives

7 PLII.2 Individual vs. Collective Rights to Life under Neoliberalism

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Susan MCDANIEL, *University of Victoria, Canada* and Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

7.1 Neha VORA, *Lafayette University, USA*
Neoliberal Authoritarianism? Knowledge Economy, Nativism, and National Branding in Qatar

7.2 Imed MELLITI, *University of Tunis El-Manar, Tunisia*
Emploi Et Travail Des Jeunes En Contexte Néolibéral. L'Exemple De La Tunisie Postrévolutionnaire; Youth Employment and Work in a Neoliberal Context. the Example of Post-Revolutionary Tunisia

7.3 Verónica GAGO, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Conceptualizing Neoliberalism after the Feminist Struggles

7.4 Peggy LEVITT, *Wellesley College, USA*
Transnational Social Protection: Changing Social Welfare in a World on the Move

Wednesday 28 June

14:00 - 15:20

8 PLIII.1 Populism: Local Forms of a Global Phenomenon

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan* and Nazanin SHAHROKNI, *The London School of Economics, United Kingdom*

Chair: Nazanin SHAHROKNI, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

8.1 Zakiya LUNA, *Washington University, Saint Louis, USA*
Populism and Popularity: Which Women Count in the 'New' Mobilizations?

8.2 Teresa R. MELGAR, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
Populism and Its Implications to Citizenship: Insights from the Developing World

8.3 Geoffrey PLEYERS, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium*
Religion, Social Movements and Politics in Brazil: From Liberation Theology to Bolsonaro

8.4 Mikhail CHERNYSH, *Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*
Populism As a Political Phenomenon in a Changing Society

9 PLIV.1 Brutalizing Authoritarianism

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Celi SCALON, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Celi SCALON, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

9.1 Housamedden DARWISH, *Leipzig University, Germany*
Authoritarianism in the Contemporary Arab Secular/Religious Debates on the Question of the State: Missed Issue

9.2 Siri HETTIGE, *University of Colombo, Sri Lanka*
Inclusive Development, Sustainability and Democracy: Illusive Goals in the Context of Neo-Liberalism, Populism and Resurgent Authoritarianism in Sri Lanka

9.3 Wiebke KEIM, *CNRS, Germany*
On Authoritarian Intellectuals

Thursday 29 June

14:00 - 15:20

10 PLIII.2 Populism and its "Others": An Intersectional Approach to the Construction of the "People"

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Filomin GUTIERREZ, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines* and Nazanin SHAHROKNI, *The London School of Economics, United Kingdom*

Chair: Filomin GUTIERREZ, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

10.1 Maria Esperanza CASULLO, *Universidad Nacional de Río Negro, Argentina*
The Body Speaks before It Even Talks: Populism, Identification and Bodily Performance

10.2 Bandana PURKAYASTHA, *University of Connecticut, USA*
On "the People" and Their "Others": Reflections on Populism through an Intersectional Lens

10.4 Ov Cristian NOROCEL, *Lund University, Sweden*
The Illiberal Radical-Right Populist "People": From Politics of Fear to Anti-Gender Politics

11 PLIV.2 Knowledge, Authority and Post-factual Era

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Chair: Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

11.1 Ghassan HAGE, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Profession: Academic

11.2 Stephanie ALENDA, *Universidad Andres Bello, Chile*
Constitution-Making in Chile: The Tortuous Quest for a New Socio-Political Order

11.3 Stephane DUFOIX, *University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France*
Who Needs to be Decolonized?

11.4 Paula Irene VILLA BRASLAVSKY, *LMU Munich, Germany*
„German Angst? Authoritarian Mobilizations and Rhetorics Surrounding Gender“

Spotlight Sessions

Tuesday 27 June

12:30 - 13:50

12 Racism and Islamophobia

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sari HANAFAI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

12.1 Nacira GUENIF, *University Paris 8, France*
Beneath Integration Lie Racism and Islamophobia: A French Situated Account

12.2 François BURGAT, *Institut de recherches et d'études sur le monde arabe et musulman (CNRS-IREMAM), France*
History and Politics: The Roots of European Islamophobia

12.3 Farid HAFEZ, *International Studies at Williams College, USA*
Islamophobia in Muslim Majority Societies: Global Entanglements in a Postcolonial World

12.4 Randa ABDEL-FATTAH, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Neo-Liberalism, Anti-Islamophobia Advocacy and the Betrayal of Palestinian Advocacy

Thursday 29 June

12:30 - 13:50

13 Whither the Arab-Israel Conflict?

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Rhoda REDDOCK, *The University of the West Indies, Trinidad and Tobago*

Chair: Rhoda REDDOCK, *The University of the West Indies, Trinidad and Tobago*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

13.1 Areej SABBAGH-KHOURY, *Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel*
Decolonizing Epistemology: A Sociology of Persisting Crisis in Palestine/Israel

13.2 Ian S. LUSTICK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*
The Future of Israel-Palestine: Solutionism and the One-State Reality

13.3 Lev GRINBERG, *Ben Gurion University, Israel*
From Military Occupation to upgraded Apartheid, a path dependent eventful sociology of the Dynamic Zionist Colonizing Project

13.4 Mohammed BAMYEH, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*
Death to Realism! Toward a Social Psychology of Palestinian Resistance

Saturday 1 July

15:30 - 17:20

14 War in Ukraine: a Sociological Perspective

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Borut RONCEVIC, *School of Advanced Social Studies, Slovenia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

14.1 Angelos GIANNAKOPOULOS, *University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Germany*
The Russian Heim-Ins-Reich Policy: Historical Revisionism and Conquest War

14.2 Nikolai GENOV, *Free University Berlin, Germany*
Individualization in Collectivist War

14.3 Olga KUTSENKO, *National Taras Shevchenko University, Ukraine*
Power of Freedom and Activism: Ukrainian Alternative to Militant Authoritarianism

14.4 Larissa TITARENKO, *Belarusian State University, Belarus*
Consequence of the War in Ukraine on Global Sociology

14.5 Tamara MARTSENYUK, *Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine*
Women's Participation in Defending Ukraine in Russia's War: Gender Sociology Perspective

Australian Thematic Sessions

Monday 26 June

14:00 - 15:20

15 The Sociology of Refugees, Asylum and Border Control in Australia

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia* and Ashleigh HAW, *Deakin University, Australia*

Chair: Farida FOZDAR, *Curtin University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

15.1 Sal CLARK, *Swinburne University of Technology, Australia*
The Waiting Room: Indonesia As the Forgotten Lynchpin in Australia's Architecture of Exclusion

15.2 Claire LOUGHNAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
'The unlawful': the power to name

15.3 Behrouz BOOCHANI, *University of Canterbury, New Zealand*
White saviour culture and the Australian detention industry

Tuesday 27 June

14:00 - 15:20

16 The Social and Political Implications of Climate Change

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jo LINDSAY, *Monash University, Australia* and Kim HUMPHERY, *Charles Darwin University, Australia*

Chair: Kim HUMPHERY, *Charles Darwin University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

16.1 Kristen LYONS, *School of Social Science, University of Queensland, Australia*
Carbon Offset Markets and the Contested Space of Human Rights

16.2 Bruce TRANTER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Attitudes on Climate Change in Australia

16.3 Stewart LOCKIE, *James Cook University, Australia*
From Conservation to Assisted Ecosystem Adaptation: The Social and Political Implications

16.4 Yolande STRENGERS, *Monash University, Australia*
Everyday Imaginaries for Future Life in a Climate Constrained World

Wednesday 28 June

14:00 - 15:20

17 Indigenous Sociology in Australia

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Theresa PETRAY, *James Cook University, Australia* and Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia*

Chair: Theresa PETRAY, *James Cook University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

17.1 Sara MOTTA, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Decolonising Critical Social(ogical) Theory: Enfleshing Post-Covid Futurities

17.2 Daryle RIGNEY, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Indigenous Australian Nation Building – Voice, Treaty, Truth

17.3 Yin PARADIES, *Deakin University, Australia*
Indigenous Perspectives on Decolonial Societies

17.4 Kathleen BUTLER, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Exploring Guardianship-Informed Urban Governance for Aboriginal Peoples

Thursday 29 June

14:00 - 15:20

18 The Reshaping of Inequality in Australia

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Annette BROMDAL, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*; Sonia MARTIN, *Australian Catholic University, Australia* and Brady ROBARDS, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Brady ROBARDS, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

18.1 Bronwyn CARLSON, *Macquarie University, Australia*
The uncomfortable truth of inequality in so called Australia

18.2 Steven ROBERTS, *Monash University, Australia*
Sort of in Everything, Everywhere All at Once: Reflections on Australia's Contemporary Class Inequalities, from the Macro to the Micro

18.3 Karen SOLDATIC, *PO Box 11, Australia*
Sociologies of Inequality and Community Wellbeing: Why Positioning Disability at the Centre of the Narrative Enables New Understandings of Inequality in Australia

18.4 Mary Lou RASMUSSEN, *The Australian National University, Australia*
Australian Young People, Reproduction, Inequality and Climate

Integrative Sessions

Monday 26 June

12:30 - 13:50

19 Care, Care work and Migration in Light of the Pandemic and Global Conflicts

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*; Ito PENG, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

Chair: Ito PENG, *University of Toronto, Canada*

Co-Chair: Anju PAUL, *New York University Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

19.1 Isabel SHUTES, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*
Mobility Regimes and Care Workers Pre and Post Pandemic

19.2 Sabrina MARCHETTI, *Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Italy*
Ukrainian Migrant Caregivers in Italy at the Convergence of Pandemic, War and Populist Crisis

19.3 Nicola PIPER, *Queen Mary University of London, United Kingdom*; Anita GHIMIRE, *Nepal Institute for Social and Environmental Research, Nepal* and Katharine JONES, *Coventry University, United Kingdom*
Managing Health Care through Foreign Nurse Recruitment: Bilateral Labour Agreements As Tools of Governance in Times of Crisis

19.4 Ito PENG, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Zhe YAN, *University of Würzburg, Germany*
Immobility within Mobility: Migrant Long-Term Care Workers and COVID-19 in China

20 Postcolonial and Southern Perspectives in Digitalization

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*; Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2, France*; Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates* and Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

20.1 Jenny CHAN, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*
Independent Contractors, Migrant Households, and Cost Competitiveness in e-Commerce Logistics Chains in China

20.2 Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2 LiRIS EA 7481, France* and Seydi Ababacar DIENG, *Université Cheikh Anta Diop, Dakar, Senegal*
New It Business Opportunities in Senegal: Policy Measures and Current Entrepreneurship Models

20.3 Habibul KHONDKER, *Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*
Contesting Postcoloniality: Sociology in the Twenty-First Century

Tuesday 27 June

12:30 - 13:50

21 Presumption in Post-COVID-19 societies

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Davide ARCIDIACONO, *University of Catania, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

21.1 Davide ARCIDIACONO, *University of Catania, Italy*; Allison LOCONTO, *Université Gustave Eiffel, France* and Antonello PODDA, *University of Cagliari, Italy*
Introducing Prosumption As an Analytical Tool for Innovation: From Systematic Review to an Integrative Research Agenda

21.2 Tommaso GRAVANTE, *Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, Mexico*
From Prosumer to Activism: The Politicization of the Everyday in Latin American Pandemic Times

21.3 Lara MAESTRIPIERI, *DASTU/Politecnico di Milano, Italy*
Prosumption in the Early Childhood Education and Care

21.4 Piergiorgio DEGLI ESPOSTI, *University of Bologna, Italy* and Jillet SAM, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Emerging Platform Society: Analysing Prosumption and Digital Payments

21.5 Henrike RAU, *Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Germany*; Eoin GREALIS, *Ludwigs-Maximilian-Universität (LMU), Germany* and Lukas EMRICH, *Department of Geography, LMU Munich, Munich Germany, Germany*
Going Full Circle? the Potential Role of Prosumerism in a Circular Society

22 Understanding the Criminalization of Struggles for Rights: Resurgent Authoritarianism or Deliberalization of Democracies?

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Ricardo PENAFIEL, *Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada*

Discussant: Judith BESSANT, *RMIT University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

22.1 Rodrigo AZEVEDO, *Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Penal Reforms, Patrimonialism and Criminalization of Corruption in Brazil – Balance and Perspectives

22.2 Marie-Christine DORAN, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
Unveiling the Resurgence of Authoritarian Legacies in Latin American Democracies: The Case of Politico-Sexual Violence (PSV) in Recent Social Mobilizations

22.3 Rob WATTS, *RMIT University, Australia*
Why Are Liberal Democracies Scared of Dissent? Examples from Australia, Canada, UK and USA

22.4 Jennifer EARL, *University of Arizona, USA*
Understanding Layered and Legalized Repression

Wednesday 28 June

12:30 - 13:50

23 (Dis)Entangling Religion(s) and Politics in fighting for Freedom and Dignity. Cross approaches from Algeria, Palestine, and Tunisia

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Abaher EL-SAKKA, *Birzeit University, Palestine*; Mabrouk BOUTAGOUGA, *University of Batna 1, Algeria* and Mounir SAIDANI, *Centre d'Études et de Recherches Économiques et Sociales, Tunisia*

Panelist: Mona ALGHURAIBI, *King Saud University, Saudi Arabia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

23.1 Mabrouk BOUTAGOUGA, *University of Batna 1, Algeria*
Religion and Politics in Algeria: From Clash to Domestication

23.2 Mounir SAIDANI, *outdated, Tunisia*
Who is mobilising religious sensibilities of on the Tunisian political scene? (Dis)entangling religion and politics in postrevolutionary Tunisia

24 COVID 19 in Brics Countries: Comparative Sociological Perspectives

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tom DWYER, *University of Campinas, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

24.1 Soraya CORTES, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Public Policies and the COVID-19 Pandemic: Brazilian Government Responses, What Explains Them and the Effect of Policies

24.2 Mikhail CHERNYSH, *Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*
The Social Consequences of COVID-19

24.3 Abha CHAUHAN, *Indian sociological Society, India*
Policies, Governance and Society Interface: Assessing COVID-19 Pandemic Crisis in India

24.4 Guangjin CHEN, *Institute of Sociology, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, Beijing, China*
The Impacts of COVID-19 on Social Mentality in China —a Sociological Analysis Based on Two Surveys Conducted in 2020

24.5 Jayanathan GOVENDER, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*
South Africa'S Double Failure: State and COVID-19

24.6 Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, USA*
Comments on COVID-19 in Brics Countries

Thursday 29 June

12:30 - 13:50

25 Constructing the foundations for Asian sociology: A case of family and gender studies

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Emiko OCHIAI, *Kyoto University, Japan*; Minh Huu NGUYEN, *Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Institute for Family and Gender Studies, Vietnam* and Susan MCDANIEL, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Chair: Kimio ITO, *Kyoto Sangyo University, Japan*

Co-Chair: Ki-Soo EUN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*

Discussant: Susan MCDANIEL, *University of Victoria, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

25.1 Emiko OCHIAI, *Kyoto University, Japan*
Multilayered Diversity in Global Family and Gender Studies: A New Vista from Asian Insider Perspectives

25.2 Patricia UBEROI, *Institute of Chinese Studies, India*
Gender and Sexuality in Asian Societies: Issues of Comparison and Interpretation

25.3 Heiwa DATE, *Shiga University, Japan*
Similarities and Differences in Patriarchal Value and Filial Piety in Asian Societies: Results from the Cafs Project

25.4 Minh Huu NGUYEN, *Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Vietnam*
Son Preference in the Family in the East and Southeast Asian Contexts

26 De-Centering Global Sociology: The 'Peripheral Turn' in Social Theory and Research

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany*; Marcel FOURNIER, *Université de Montréal, Canada*; Craig BROWNE, *University of Sydney, Australia* and David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

26.1 Arthur BUENO, *University of Frankfurt, Germany*; Mariana TEIXEIRA, *CEBRAP (Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning), Brazil* and David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*
The Peripheral Turn: Conceptualizing Global Sociology (introductory remarks)

26.2 Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany*
Creolizing the Modern: Transylvania As Periphery across Empires

26.3 Sujata PATEL, *Indian Institute of Advanced Studies, India*
Class from a Peripheral Perspective: Informality, Work, Labour and Migration

26.4 Xiaoying QI, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Sociology-Making Against Its Conventions: Drawing on Concepts from Peripheral Formations

26.5 Raewyn CONNELL, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Beyond Marginality: How We Can Build a New Mainstream World Sociology and What It Might Look like

Friday 30 June

12:30 - 13:50

27 Social movements under varieties of authoritarian threats

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Breno BRINGEL, *State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Angelica CUELLAR VAZQUEZ, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*; Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

27.1 Michael GILLAN, *M261 35 Stirling Highway, Australia*
Authoritarian Innovations and Labour Governance in Myanmar's Reform Era

27.2 Lauren LANGMAN, *Loyola University of Chicago, USA*
Star Trek or Matrix: Wither Humanity?

27.3
Thoughts after Prison: Social Movement Research, High-Risk Activism and Democracy

28 The Good University: Addressing Growing Stratification and Gender Discrimination in the University Workforce

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Alpha POSSAMAI-INESEDY, *Western Sydney University, Australia*; Marcel FOURNIER, *Université de Montréal, Canada*; Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany* and Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

Chair: Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

28.1 Mary ROMERO, *Arizona State University, USA*
Corporatization of Knowledge in the New American University

28.2 Raewyn CONNELL, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Response By Raewyn Connell: Making Good Universities

28.3 Bandana PURKAYASTHA, *University of Connecticut, USA*
"so Much Data, Such Few Socially-Just Solutions": Some Thoughts on Raewyn Connell's Research on Universities and Where We Continue to be Positioned Today.

28.4 Rhacel PARRENAS, *University of Southern California, USA*
Decolonizing the Study of Global Migration

Research Committees

RC01

Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution

Program Coordinator: Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-5 The Soldier-Scholar: Postsecondary Education of Future Military Officers

Committees: RC01 *Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution (Host)*; RC04 *Sociology of Education*

See Joint Session Details for JS-5.

15:30-17:20

29 Conscription and Retention

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Tibor SZVIRCSEV TRESCH, *Swiss Military Academy at the ETH Zurich, Switzerland* and Johan OSTERBERG, *Swedish Defense University, Sweden*

Chair: Emanuela RIZZO, *Military Academy (MILAC) At ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

Panelist: Luke GAHAN, *Australian Institute of Family Studies, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

29.1 Thomas FERST, *Swiss Military Academy, Switzerland* and Tibor SZVIRCSEV TRESCH, *Swiss Military Academy at the ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

Abstract: *Conscription in Switzerland: An Important Element in the Swiss Society*

29.2 Thomas FERST, *Swiss Military Academy, Switzerland* and Tibor SZVIRCSEV TRESCH, *Swiss Military Academy at the ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

Abstract: *Attitudes of Swiss Recruits Toward Conscription*

29.3 Slawomir NOWOTNY, *Chancellery of the Prime Minister, Poland*

Old War Threat and New Generations

29.5 Gen NOGAMI, *Waseda University, Japan*

Ambiguous Attitude and Modest Organization: Pursuing the Postmodern Military

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

30 Sociology of War

Language: English, French

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Oleh IVANOV, *National-University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine*

Chair: Cornelis KOONINGS, *University of Utrecht, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

30.1 Anton OLEINIK, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada* and Vladimir PANIOTTO, *Kyiv International Institute of Sociology, Ukraine*

Assessing Propaganda Effectiveness: The Case of Russia's War in Ukraine

30.2 Teija SEDERHOLM, *Finnish National Defence University, Finland*; Milla ALARAATIKKA, *Finnish National Defence University, Finland*; Pekka KOISTINEN, *Finnish National Defence University, Finland*; Miina KAARKOSKI, *Finnish National Defence University, Finland* and Aki-Mauri HUHTINEN, *Finnish National Defence University, Finland*

The Role of Situational Awareness in Countering Disinformation at the Information Battlefield

30.3 Miguel OLIVA, *Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero, Argentina*

War, Social Sciences, and the Apocalypse

30.4 Maja GARB, *Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia*

Professional Military Education in Slovenia: Painful Processes and Civil-Military Gap

30.5 Bahare ARVIN, *Tarbiyat Modares University, Iran*
A Comparative Study of the State Power Structure in the Middle East with a Focus on the Recent State Power Structure in Iran

30.6 Violette LARRIEU, *ENSTA Bretagne, France* and Jean FRANCES, *ENSTA Bretagne, France*
Innovate to Win: Is That Easy?

10:30-12:20

31 The Military and Politics in 21st Century

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil* and Abu BAH, *Northern Illinois University, USA*

Chair: Rene MOELKER, *Netherlands Defence Academy, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

31.1 Cornelis KOONINGS, *University of Utrecht, Netherlands*
Civil-Military Politics and the New Illiberalism in Latin America

31.2 Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*
Military and Politics in Contemporary Brazil

31.3 Abu BAH, *Northern Illinois University, USA*
Military Regimes and Human Security in West Africa: A Critique of Democratic Failures in Mali and Guinea

31.4 Temitope ORIOLA, *Dept of Sociology, Canada*
The Military and National Politics: The Civilian-Military Leadership Interest Convergence

31.5 Unsal SIGRI, *OSTİM Technical University, Ankara, USA* and Taha KALAYCI, *Çukurova University, Turkey*
Prestige Seeking and International Commitments: Turkey's Involvement in the Nagorno-Karabakh War

31.6 Marek ROHR-GARZTECKI, *Collegium Civitas, Poland*
Easternisation of the Atlantic Alliance

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

32 Rethinking the Old, New and Future Roles of Armed Forces

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Lindy HEINECKEN, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*

Chair: Gen NOGAMI, *Waseda University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

32.1 Soili PAANANEN, *National Defence University, Finland*
How Peacekeepers As Leaders Embrace Dynamic Tensions?

32.2 Darrell IRWIN, *University of Connecticut, USA*
'Assertive' Foreign Policy Narratives in South China Seas Disputes

32.3 Rene MOELKER, *Netherlands Defence Academy, Netherlands*
The Construction of Reality through Inclusion Wars. Inclusion and Culture in an Organization on the Periphery

32.4 Anne OBLING, *The Royal Danish Defence College, Denmark*
Some Integration Issues in NATO's Collaborative Workforce: A Study of Multi-National Military Headquarters

10:30-12:20

33 Civil-Military Collaboration and Research Perspectives

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Irina GOLDENBERG, *Department of National Defence Canada, Canada*

Chair: Rene MOELKER, *Netherlands Defence Academy, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

33.1 Irina GOLDENBERG, *Military Personnel Command, Canada* and William DENOMME, *Department of National Defence, Canada*
Defence Civilians: Integration in the Total Defence Workforce

33.2 Erik HEDLUND, *Drottning Kristinas Vag 37, Sweden*
From What to How Building up Civil-Military Collaboration Skills through Training and Practice

33.3 Josh WENGER, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan, Taiwan* and Paul JOBIN, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Blurring Civil-Military Boundaries? the Rise of Civil Defence Organizations in Taiwan's Civil Society

33.4 Dana GROSSWIRTH KACHTAN, *Open University of Israel, Israel*
Why Quality Matters? Researching the Military from Bottom to Top

33.5 James CONNOR, *University of New South Wales, Australia* and Ben WADHAM, *Flinders University, Australia*
A Typology of Administrative Violence in the Australian Defence Force

15:30-17:20

34 Retention in the Armed Forces

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Irina GOLDENBERG, *Military Personnel Command, Canada*; Johan OSTERBERG, *Swedish Defense University, Sweden* and Tibor SZVIRCSEV TRESCH, *Swiss Military Academy at the ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

Chair: Tibor SZVIRCSEV TRESCH, *Swiss Military Academy at the ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

34.1 Bradley WEST, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Cultural Recognition, Pride in Service, and 'Civilianization' in the Armed Forces: Retention Challenges and the Civilian Employability of Military Personnel

34.2 Emanuela RIZZO, *Military Academy (MILAC) At ETH Zurich, Switzerland*
Swiss Military Families: Facticity, Challenges and Implications for Employee Retention.

34.3 Stefano DE ROSA, *Swiss Military Academy, Switzerland*
Large-Scale Analysis on the Relationship between Commensality and Unit Cohesion

34.4 Ionel SAVA, *University of Bucharest, Romania*
Retention and Reform of the All Volunteer Force in East Central European Countries

34.5 Vida CESNUIITYTE, *General Jonas Zemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania, Lithuania*
Conscription in Lithuania: Motivation, Attitudes and Contribution into Defence Forces

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

35 Islamic Violent Movements in Contemporary Africa

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Alemayehu KUMSA, *Charles University, Faculty of Humanity, Czech Republic*

Chair: Jiri SUBRT, *Charles University, Czech Republic*

Panelist: Jiri SUBRT, *Charles University, Czech Republic*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

35.1 Ikem UJENE, *University of Ibadan, Nigeria*
'Shared Spaces or Shared Bushes?': Land-Use and Economic Implications of Terrorists' Reintegration in Northeast Nigeria

35.2 Wisdom FAFI, *University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria*
The Dynamics of Security Management of Boko Haram Terrorism in Nigeria

35.3 Leonid ISSAEV, *HSE University, Russian Federation* and Alisa SHISHKINA, *HSE University, Russian Federation*
Terrorist Activity in the Sahel Countries: The Impact of the Arab Spring and the Experience of Deradicalization

35.4 Olayinka AJALA, *Leeds Beckett University, United Kingdom*
Terrorism in the Lake Chad Basin: Understanding the Economic Dimensions and Role of Vigilantes in Counter-Terrorism

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-115 COVID-19: Patterns in Domestic Military Operations

Committees: RC01 *Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution (Host)*; RC39 *Sociology of Disasters*

See Joint Session Details for JS-115.

10:30-12:20

36 RC01 Business Meeting

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*

Chair: Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*

17:30-19:20

37 Beyond the Greedy Institution

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Rene MOELKER, *Netherlands Defence Academy, Netherlands*

Chair: Soili PAANANEN, *National Defence University, Finland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

37.1 Rene MOELKER, *Netherlands Defence Academy, Netherlands*
Beyond the Greedy Family

37.2 Janja VUGA BERSNAK, *University of Ljubljana, Slovenia*; Gasper FERME, *University of Ljubljana, Slovenia* and Maja ŠKAFAR, *Ljubljana, Slovenia*
The Sources of Support within the Slovenian Military Family's Ecosystem

37.3 Olufiayo AJALA, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*
"Beyond the Greedy Institution: Nigerian Military Families and the War Against Boko Haram"

37.4 Baris ATES, *Turkish National Defence University, Turkey*
Towards Turkish Military Sociology: Challenges and Opportunities

RC02

Economy and Society

Program Coordinator: Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC07 Futures Research RC24 Environment and Society RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-3.

38 Developing Socio-Economic Theory with Empirical Cases

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Karen SHIRE, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

Chair: Karen SHIRE, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

38.1 Xinyue SHEN, *Fudan University, China*
Relational Duality and the Backup Meaning: Money and Love in the Chinese Idol Industry

38.2 Anette STENSLUND, *Southern University Denmark, Denmark*
We Know We've Been Innovative When We Don't Win Competitions

38.3 Erdem KAYSERILIOGLU, *PhD, Koc University, Turkey*
Humanitarian Aid As an Economic Action: A Gift Perspective

38.4 Ms LEENA, *Indian Institute of Foreign Trade, India* and Saroj RATH, *University of Delhi, India*
The Inroad of Retail Investors into the Indian Equity Markets: Tapping the so Far Untapped Potential

Discussion

15:30-17:20

39 Varieties of Care Work: Exploring National Differences

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Nadya GUIMARAES, *University of Sao Paulo, Brazil* and Heidi GOTTFRIED, *Wayne State University, USA*

Chair: Heidi GOTTFRIED, *Wayne State University, USA*

Discussant: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

39.1 Anju PAUL, *New York University Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates*; Sophia QIU, *Yale-NUS College, Singapore* and Cynthia CHEN, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
A Comparison of Domestic Worker Protections Around the World

39.2 Nadya GUIMARAES, *University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*; Javier PINEDA, *Universidad de Los Andes, Colombia*; Simone WAJNMAN, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil* and Suelen CASTIBLANCO, *Universidad de La Salle, Colombia*
Pandemic, Labor Market and Gender in Brazil and Colombia

39.3 Helena HIRATA, *GTM/CRESPPA, CNRS, France*; Aurelie DAMAMME, *University Paris 8/CNRS CRESPPA, France* and Michelle REDONDO, *Paris 8/CNRS CRESPPA, France*
Actions and Visions of Care in a Post-Pandemic World?

39.4 Ruth MILKMAN, *CUNY Graduate Center, USA*
Continuity or Change? the Impact of the Pandemic on U.S. in-Home Careworkers

39.5 Ito PENG, *University of Toronto, Canada*
The COVID-19 Its Impacts on Working Parents with Small Children: Korea-Canada Comparison

39.6 Guita Grin DEBERT, *Campinas State University, Brazil* and Jorge FELIX, *University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*
The Care of Older Adults in the Brazilian Covid-19 Context

Discussion

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

39.7 David DU TOIT, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Outsourced Maternalism: A Consequence of Outsourcing Domestic Work to Household Cleaning Service Firms

17:30-19:20

JS-20 International Migration and Economic Informalization : A Denationalized Perspective - Part I

Committees: RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC02 Economy and Society and RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-20.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

40 The Social Economy of Migrant Labour -- Improving Social Protections to End Exploitation

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Karen SHIRE, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

Chair: Sandhya AS, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

40.1 Manashi RAY, *West Virginia State University, USA*
To Flee or Not to Flee? Im/Mobility Among Ukrainian Glass Artists and Entrepreneurs

40.2 Heidi GOTTFRIED, *Wayne State University, USA*
Beyond Old Divides: Care Migration in Regional Perspective

40.3 Karen SHIRE, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany* and Sylvia WALBY, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom*
The Political Economy of Human Trafficking -- How Neo-Liberalization Enables Crime

40.4 Alinaya Sybilla FABROS, *University of California Berkeley, USA*
The Left-Beyond: Failed Patriarchs, Empowered Women and the Labor Earmarking of Older Migrant Workers amid Elusive Retirement

Discussion

10:30-12:20

JS-32 International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Labour-Capital Relations

Committees: *RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-32.

41 Power, Politics, Beliefs & Values in the Economy

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Miguel Angel VITE PEREZ, *Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, Mexico*

Chair: Dana KORNBERG, *UC-Santa Barbara, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

41.1 David COBURN, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Elaine COBURN, *Glendon Campus, York University, Canada*
Economy and Society, Economy in Society? the World Bank World Development Reports, 1978-2022

41.2 Ayca ZAYIM, *Mount Holyoke College, USA*
The Politics of Swap Lines and the Hierarchy of the International Financial System

41.3 Rachel AALDERS, *Australian National University, Australia*
Empowering Finance: Understanding the Beliefs and Values Embedded in Consumer Fintech

41.4 Xiaomin CAI, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Working on the Market Frontier: Selling Prohibited Assisted Reproductive Technologies in Pronatalist China

41.5 Riona BASU, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Understanding Inequalities: The Concept of Wealth Elites in Sociology

Discussion

15:30-17:20

JS-44 Variegated Intersections of Social Policy and Finance

Committees: *RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy (Host); RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-44.

JS-42 International Migration and Economic Informalization: A Denationalized Perspective - Part II

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC02 Economy and Society and RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-42.

17:30-19:20

JS-49 Labor Unrest, Social Revolts and Revolutions, 1851-2020: Findings from the Global Social Protest Database

Committees: *RC44 Labor Movements (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change and RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-49.

42 Digitalized Economic Interactions in the Global South: In Search of a New Research Agenda

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Michelle Fei-yu HSIEH, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

Chair: Michelle Fei-yu HSIEH, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

42.1 Sana AHMAD, *WZB Social Science Center Berlin, Germany*
Automated Content Moderation: A Site of Social and Economic Inequalities in India

42.2 Heesun CHOI, *Chung-Ang University, Republic of Korea*
Crowd Work without Crowd: A Study on the Dual Labor Market in Crowd Labor Market in Korea

42.3 Vladimir PACHECO, *Aarhus University, Denmark* and Chiara BRESCIANI, *Aarhus University, Denmark*
A Wallet on Your Phone: Preliminary Findings on the Salvadorean Bitcoin Bet

42.4 Mayumi TABATA, *Senshu University, Japan*
The Role of Stock Trading Apps and SNS in Generational Justice: The Case of Youth Financial Civic Movements in Taiwan and Japan

42.5 Anson AU, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*
Cryptocurrencies and the Promise of Individual Economic Sovereignty in an Age of Digitalization: A Critical Appraisal

Discussion

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

43 Economic Sociology of Craftsmanship

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Andrey SGORLA, *University of Siena, Italy*

Chair: Andrey SGORLA, *University of Siena, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

43.1 Susan LUCKMAN, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Michelle PHILLIPOV, *University of Adelaide, Australia*
Artisanal Making, Cultural Inclusion, and the Limits of Media Representation

43.2 Emanuela NACLERIO, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*
In Search of Sustainable Work: Micro-Entrepreneurs' Narratives and Practices of Craft

43.3 Pauline DELPERDANGE, *Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium*
The Heterogeneity of Authenticity Arguments in a New Craft Market Sector : The Case of Microbrewery in Belgium

43.4 Judit BODNAR, *Central European University, Hungary*
Craft-Producing Locality in the Sharing Economy

43.5 Belinda ZAKRZEWSKA, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom*; Michael B BEVERLAND, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom* and Stephan MANNING, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom*
Recipes for Crafting Authenticity and Coloniality

43.6
Discussion

10:30-12:20

44 Indebted Subjectivities: Juggling with Consumer Credit

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: M. Fatih KARAKAYA, *Istanbul University, Turkey*

Chair: Dustin STOLTZ, *Lehigh University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

44.1 Tobias DAVIDSSON, *Department of Social Work, University of Gothenburg, Sweden* and Erik ERIKSSON, *School of Social Work, Lund University, Sweden*
Young and Overindebted. Time out of Rhythm

44.2 M. Fatih KARAKAYA, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
"Restructuring" the Consumer Credit: A Frame Analysis of Non-Performing Loan Market in Turkey

44.3 Fernanda GOBBI, *Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil*
Money and Violence in Informal-Illegal Loans in the Popular Strata of São Paulo-Brazil

44.4 Pheeraya WONGSARANUCHIT, *Meajo University, Thailand*; Pusanisa THECHATAKERNG, *Meajo University, Thailand*; Sutawan SATJASOMBOON, *Meajo University, Thailand* and Sirikul TULASOMBAT, *Meajo University, Thailand*
Stairway to Purchase: New Customer Journey Mapping on Low-Rise Condo in Thailand

Discussion

15:30-17:20

45 Finance As a Verb: Local Practices of Global Finance

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA*

Chair: Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

45.1 Alicia GIRON, *Instituto de Investigaciones Económicas-UNAM, Mexico*
China Railway Construction, Chinese Finance Capital

45.2 Yu-hsiang CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*
Credit Rating As a Tool of Communication and Negotiation: SME Lending in Taiwanese Banks

45.3 Rajorshi RAY, *IIT Kanpur, India*
Financial Actors in Context: An Ethnographic Study on Financial Intermediation and Its Role in Platform Dependent Entrepreneurship in India

45.4 Anirudh RAGHAVAN, *Ashoka University, India*
The Moral Investor : Equity Markets, Speculation and Retail Investing Boom in India

45.5 Abhiram H, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India, India* and Jillet Sarah SAM, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India, India*
Understanding Cryptocurrencies from the Perspective of Social Institutions

Discussion

17:30-19:20

46 Postcolonial Ethnographies of Racial Capitalism: A View in/from Africa

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jordanna MATLON, *American University, USA*

Chair: Lynette SPILLMAN, *University of Notre Dame, USA*

Discussant: Michael BURAWOY, *University of California, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

46.1 Jordanna MATLON, *American University, USA*
The Crisis of Black Masculinity in Racial Capitalism

46.2 Marcel PARET, *University of Utah, USA*
Passive Revolution through Racial Inclusion in South Africa

46.3 Zachary LEVENSON, *University of North Carolina, Greensboro, USA*
Reversing Apartheid Under Racial Capitalism: Notes from Land Occupations in Cape Town

46.4 Jessie LUNA, *Colorado State University, USA*
White Gold, Black Debt: Racial Capitalism and Agricultural Modernization in Burkina Faso

46.5 Michael BURAWOY, *University of California, USA*
Discussant

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

47 Lifeworld of Precarious Work and Subjectivities

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sandeepan TRIPATHY, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Sandeepan TRIPATHY, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

47.1 Andrei POPOV, *Vologda Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences (VolRC RAS), Russian Federation*
The Meanings of Precarity in the World of Work: Generational Approach

47.2 David FARRUGIA, *Deakin University, Australia*; Julia COFFEY, *University of Newcastle, Australia, Australia* and Steven THREADGOLD, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Solidarity, Belonging and Precarious Work in the Hospitality Industry

47.3 Pamela CARO MOLINA, *Universidad Santo Tomás, Chile*
Precariousness(es) of the Productive and Reproductive Work of Seasonal Fruit Growers in the Central Valley of Chile: An Empirical Study

47.4 Shruti GUPTA, *National University of Singapore, India*
Migrant Experiences, Gender Relations, and 'Negotiated Agency': Conceptualising Precarity through and Beyond Labour

Discussion

10:30-12:20

48 Seeing Precarity through a Comparative Analysis of Labor in Various Economies

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sandeepan TRIPATHY, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Sandeepan TRIPATHY, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

48.1 Shiyun TANG, *Renmin university of china, China*
The Power Structure Analysis of the Precarious Labor Situation and Production Relations of Ride-Hailing Drivers

48.2 Muhammed ALAKITAN, *University of Ibadan, Nigeria*
Bans, Gender, Unpaid Labour and Surveillance: Precarities of Nigerian Twitter Influencer Entrepreneurship

48.3 Ludovic BAKEBEK, *Department of social and cultural Anthropology University of Liège, Belgium*
Thinking Urban Labor and Social Mobility Beyond the Precarity Discourse: A View from the Construction Sector in Douala, Cameroon

48.4 Neha GUPTA, *National Institute of Technology Silchar, India* and Anushree GUPTA, *Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad, India*
Heat Resistance: A Case Study of Platform Workers' 'AC Strike' in Kolkata and Hyderabad

Discussion

15:30-17:20

49 Racial Capitalisms: Race, Caste, Ethnicity, and Indigeneity in Economic Life

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dana KORNBERG, *UC-Santa Barbara, USA*

Chair: Dana KORNBERG, *UC-Santa Barbara, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

49.1 Tomislav RIMAC, *ESCI, Pompeu Fabra University, Spain*
Communion and Generative Social Change: A Study of Intra-Organizational Processes Enabling Individual and Collective Agency

49.2 Cassi CLAYTOR, *Case Western Reserve University, USA*
Markets, Racial Capitalism, and Racial Exclusion on the Retail Sales Floor

49.3 Nioshi SHAH, *UCSB, USA*
Reinforcing Caste Boundaries in Everyday Social Interactions: A Critical Analysis of Upper Class Bania Women in India

49.4 Deepa EBENEZER, *Azim Premji University, India*
Multi-National Corporations and Caste: Experiences of Sanitation Workers from Chennai

49.5 Sanjeev ROURAY, *Assistant Professor, Brunei Darussalam*
'Almost like Engineers!' Material and Symbolic Practices of Plumbers in Delhi

Discussion

17:30-19:20

50 Economy and Culture

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Lynette SPILLMAN, *University of Notre Dame, USA*

Chair: Jeffrey ALEXANDER, *Yale University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

50.1 Paromita SANYAL, *Florida State University, USA*
Life and Debt: Household Financialization & the Changing Culture of Credit

50.2 Simone POLILLO, *University of Virginia, USA*
Planning and Econometric Models in Post-World-War-II Italy: A Sociology of Performative Regimes

50.3 Alex PREDA, *Kings College London, United Kingdom*; Julie VALK, *Kings Business School, United Kingdom* and Ruowen XU, *Kings Business School, United Kingdom*
The Blockchain Prophecies: Social Imaginaries of the Cryptoeconomy

50.4 Lynette SPILLMAN, *University of Notre Dame, USA*
Theorizing Economic Culture

Discussion

19:30-20:50

51 RC02 Business Meeting

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-117 International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Sovereignty and Infrastructural Power

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology

See Joint Session Details for JS-117.

52 Elements for an Emancipatory Sociology: An Appraisal of the Work of István Mészáros

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ricardo DELLO BUONO, *Manhattan College, USA*

Chair: David FASENFEST, *Wayne State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

52.1 Ricardo DELLO BUONO, *Manhattan College, USA*
Moving Beyond Leviathan: Mészáros on the Role of the State

52.2 Ricardo ANTUNES, *University of Campinas, Brazil*
Una Apuesta Al Futuro y La Urgência De La Alternativa Socialista: La Contribución De István Mészáros

52.3 Andres PIQUERAS, *Universidad Jaume I, Spain*
Degenerative Phase of Capitalism. Terminal Capitalism?

52.4 Adrian SOTELO VALENCIA, *UNAM, Mexico*
La Superexplotación Del Trabajo En Las Mediaciones De Segundo Orden De István Mészáros. the Super-Exploitation of Labor in the Second-Order Mediations of István Mészáros.

52.5 Carlos Eduardo MARTINS, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
The Structural Crisis of Capitalism, US Imperialism and Alternatives for the XXI Century

52.6 Murillo VAN DER LAAN, *University of Campinas, Brazil*
The Question of Natural Limits in the Work of István Mészáros

52.7 Caio ANTUNES, *Federal University of Goiás - UFG, Brazil*
Education in Mészáros

10:30-12:20

JS-127 Thinking through and Beyond Capitalism after the Great Reset

Committees: RC16 Sociological Theory (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-127.

15:30-17:20

JS-129 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Innovation and Dynamism

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis

See Joint Session Details for JS-129.

53 Rising Corporate Concentration and the Monopolistic Milieu

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Siddharamesh HIREMATH, *Bangalore Central University, India*

Chair: Somashekher CHINNAPPA, *Bangalore University, India*

Co-Chair: Jayashree KULKARNI, *JSW Steel Limited, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

53.1 Hiroko INOUE, *University of California, Riverside, USA*
Political and Economic Power: Foreign Investment Dependence

53.2 Abdul Gaffar KHAN, *Gulbarga University, India*
Corollaries of Corporate Invasion: Colonization of Healthcare Sector in India

53.3 Miguel Angel VITE PEREZ, *UAM, Mexico*
Extractivism As an Interpretative Concept of Urban Development in the Global South

53.4 Subhaschandra NATIKAR, *Karnatak University, India*
Medical Corporatism: Commodification of Healthcare

53.5 Vasudha M C, *Jyoti Nivas College Autonomous, India*
Spate of Mergers and Acquisitions in Indian Edtech Industry: Waves of Predatory Consolidation

53.6 Raghavendra GUDAGUNTI, *Near Gopalswamy Temple, India*
Big Pharma Corporatism and Vaccine Monopoly: Indian Struggle through the Pandemic

Discussion

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

53.7 Anjanappa BADADA HANUMAPPA, *Kuvempu University, India*
Monopolistic Consolidation in Pharmaceutical Sector: Implications for Medication and Innovation

17:30-19:20

JS-135 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Relational and Cultural Analysis

Committees: RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-135.

54 Reconstructing the Global Economy – Production Chains, Knowledge Chains, & Value Chains

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dennis MCNAMARA, 3700 O St NW, USA

Chair: Mailys GANTOIS-MALDAGUE, Université Paris 1 - Panthéon Sorbonne, France

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

54.1 Dennis MCNAMARA, 3700 O St NW, USA
China's Challenge - Managing Cross-Strait Connectivity

54.2 Bronwyn LEE, Binghamton University, USA
Suriname's Bauxite Industrialization: How a Specialized Commodity Exporter Reconstructed Global Aluminum Production Chains By Asserting Local Priorities

54.3 Svetlana KIRDINA-CHANDLER, Institute of Economics, Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation
From Global Economy to Bipolar Economy

54.4 Joongkoo LEE, Hanyang University, Republic of Korea
What the Netflix-Korean Wave Nexus Teaches Us about Global Cultural Value Chains

54.5 Amogh ARAKALI, Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India
Locals within Globals: Theorising for Local Environmental Factors in Global Manufacturing Chains Using Case Studies from India

54.6 Diego MAGGI, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Knowledge Management and Division of Labor in the Global Automotive Industry: Considerations on the Brazilian Case

Discussion

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

JS-138 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Societal Variation, Entrepreneurship

Committees: RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-138.

JS-139 Racial Capitalisms, Spatial Productions

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-139.

10:30-12:20

JS-143 Tax Policies and Tax Optimization Practices

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC12 Sociology of Law

See Joint Session Details for JS-143.

JS-144 Women Entrepreneurs on the African Continent and Beyond

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-144.

12:30-14:20

JS-149 Political Economy and Violence: The Implications of Taking Violence Seriously for Theories of Hegemonic and Counter-Hegemonic Forces

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); TG11 Violence and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-149.

14:30-16:20

55 Global Inequalities and Pandemic Diseases--Recent and Historical Impacts of Contagious Diseases on within- and between-Country Inequalities

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Christopher CHASE-DUNN, University of California-Riverside, USA; Yoshimichi SATO, Kyoto University of Advanced Science, Japan and Hiroko INOUE, University of California, Riverside, USA

Chair: Christopher CHASE-DUNN, University of California-Riverside, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

55.1 Michael LEE, CUNY-Hunter College, USA
From Flea to Shining Flea: Pandemics in the Modern World-System, 1600-2022

55.2 Anthony ROBERTS, Colorado State University, USA
The Covid-19 Pandemic and Contemporary & Future Income Inequality in the United States: A Machine Learning Approach

55.3 Vitalina BUTKALIUK, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine
The Pandemic of Inequality: The Social Lessons of the Pandemic for Humanity

Discussion

RC03

Community Research

Program Coordinators: Marta KLEKOTKO, Jagiellonian University, Poland; Cristina MATEOS MORA, University Pablo Olavide, Sevilla, Spain; Johan ZAAIMAN, North-West University, South Africa and Angel ZAPATA MOYA, Pablo de Olavide University, Spain

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

56 Nuevas Políticas Urbanas En Iberoamérica. Avances Hacia La Nueva Agenda Urbana

Language: Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maria Jose GUERRERO-MAYO, UNIVERSIDAD PABLO DE OLAVIDE, Spain and Maria Jose DORADO RUBIN, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain

Chair: Maria Jose GUERRERO-MAYO, UNIVERSIDAD PABLO DE OLAVIDE, Spain

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

56.1 Alicia DOMINGUEZ-GONZALEZ, Pablo de Olavide University, Spain
El Impacto De La Política De Cohesión De La Unión Europea Sobre Las Condiciones De Vida a Escala Local En España.

56.2 Francesca DonATI, Università degli Studi Milano-Bicocca, Italy
La Perspectiva de Género en las Iniciativas Urbanas Integral de La Unión Europea: El Caso Español (1994-2020)

56.3 Maria del mar LLOPIS ORREGO, Universidad Pablo de Olavide (Sevilla), Spain; Maria Jose DORADO RUBIN, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain; Juan MURCIANO ROSADO, Universidad de Sevilla, Spain and Alberto SANTIESTEBAN, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain
Movilidad Urbana Sostenible Y Género

56.4 Cristina GONZALEZ - BENITEZ, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain and Cristina MATEOS MORA, Pablo de Olavide University, Spain
¿Influye La Escena Cultural En El Impacto De Políticas Locales? Una Exploración a Partir De Proyectos De Regeneración Urbana En España

56.5 Macarena IBARRA, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile
La Experiencia De La Dictadura y Los Avances De La Nueva Política Urbana En Chile

17:30-19:20

JS-18 Collaborative Research I: Critical Reflections on Research Ethics and Methodological Practices

Committees: TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice (Host); RC03 Community Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-18.

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

JS-33 Marine Justice, Ocean Studies, and Coastal Communities

Committees: RC24 Environment and Society (Host); RC03 Community Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-33.

15:30-17:20

57 Updating Community Research: Past, Present, Future

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Terry Nichols CLARK, University of Chicago, USA and Rachel HARVEY, Columbia University, USA

Chair: Hyesun JEONG, University of Cincinnati, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

57.1 Clemente J. NAVARRO, Pablo de Olavide University, Spain
Institutions and Communities Life: Towards CROSS-National Comparative Analysis of Urban Scenes

57.2 Terry Nichols CLARK, University of Chicago, USA
From Community Research to Scenes Analysis: Past, Present and Future of the RC03

57.3 Marta KLEKOTKO, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Updating Community Research: Community As Social Practice

17:30-19:20

JS-53 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development

Committees: RC03 Community Research (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts

See Joint Session Details for JS-53.

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

58 Community Mobilization in Urban and Rural Context

Language: Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Daniel GUTIERREZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Maria-Rosa HERRERA-GUTIERREZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*

Chair: Daniel GUTIERREZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

58.1 Timothy GENTLES, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
The Curation of Affective Experiences of Nature- the Case of Two Far Right Groups

58.2 Pavel POSPECH, *Masaryk university, Czech Republic*
Rurality, Anti-Urbanism and “Real Life”

58.3 Nohelia PASAPERA, *Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú, Peru*
Resignificación Del Derecho a La Ciudad: Inclusión De Una Agenda Feminista En Dos Ediciones Del Foro Mundial De La Bicicleta (Lima, 2018 y Quito, 2019)

58.4 Patricia SCHETTINI, *Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina*
Dinámica De La Contienda En La Organización Del Movimiento De Cartoneros En La Ciudad De La Plata, Argentina

19:30-20:50

59 Local Welfare Regimes: A Comparative Analysis

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maria Jesus RODRIGUEZ GARCIA, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Emma MITCHELL, *Institute for Culture and Society, Western Sydney University, Australia*

Chair: Emma MITCHELL, *Institute for Culture and Society, Western Sydney University, Australia*

Discussants: Maria Jesus RODRIGUEZ GARCIA, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Emma MITCHELL, *Institute for Culture and Society, Western Sydney University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

59.1 Espen DAHL, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway*; Åsmund HERMANSEN, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway* and Thomas LORENTZEN, *University of Bergen, Norway*
Welfare-Work Trajectories Among Social Assistance Recipients in a Local Perspective

59.2 Francesca DONATI, *Università degli Studi Milano-Bicocca, Italy*; Maria Jesus RODRIGUEZ GARCIA, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Patricia DOMINGUEZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Urban Governance Lab, Spain*
The Governance of Care. Legislative Frameworks, Challenges and Opportunities Created By Municipal Policies

59.3 Manuel GARCIA, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain*
¿Afectan Las Políticas Urbanas a La Estabilidad Residencial? Evidencia Para España

59.4 Alicia DOMINGUEZ-GONZALEZ, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain* and Clemente J. NAVARRO, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*
How Do Local Welfare Systems Influence Perceptions of Local Services and Quality of Life? an Analysis of Major European Cities.

59.5 María del Carmen NAVARRO SOLANO, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*; Maria Jesus RODRIGUEZ GARCIA, *Centre for Urban Political Sociology and Policies Pablo de Olavide University, Spain* and Angel ZAPATA MOYA, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*
Social Policies in Times of Austerity: The Influence of Women’s Representation on Public Welfare Effort at Local Level.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

59.6 Jose BETANZOS-MARTIN, *Autonomía Sur, S.Coop.And, Spain* and Maria Jose GUERRERO-MAYO, *UNIVERSIDAD PABLO DE OLAVIDE, Spain*
Una Política Municipal De Vivienda En Cesión De Uso y Las Finanzas Éticas. El Caso De Barcelona y La Aportación De Coop57

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

JS-96 Traditional Water Cultures and the Modern Life

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society (Host)*; RC03 *Community Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-96.

15:30-17:20

JS-103 Theories of Practice: New Perspectives in Urban Theory and Research

Committees: RC03 *Community Research (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-103.

17:30-19:20

JS-113 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development II

Committees: RC03 *Community Research (Host)*; RC37 *Sociology of Arts*

See Joint Session Details for JS-113.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-116 Inclusive Education, Knowledge Co-Production, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: RC04 *Sociology of Education (Host)*; RC03 *Community Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-116.

10:30-12:20

JS-122 Community Influences on Lifestyles and Health

Committees: RC03 Community Research (Host); RC15 Sociology of Health

See Joint Session Details for JS-122.

15:30-17:20

60 Can Place-Based Policies Enhance Community Life and Democracy: On Neighbourhood Governance, Participation and Institutional Trust.**Location:** 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Clemente J. NAVARRO, *Center for Sociology and Local Policies - Pablo de Olavide University, Spain***Chair:** Clemente J. NAVARRO, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****60.1** Marina PERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Yunailis SALAZAR, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain***The Embeddedness of the Citizen Assets Programme in Barcelona: Reminding the Role of Trust****60.2** Rotchel AMIGO, *Bukidnon State University, Philippines* and Cheryl AMIGO, *Bukidnon State University, Philippines*
The Role of Social Capital on Organizational Resiliency: The Case of Migrant Community**60.3** Reinhold SACKMANN, *Martin-Luther-University, Germany* and Ina MAYER, *University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
The Effects of Social Cohesion on Local Societies

17:30-19:20

JS-134 (Re)Turning to Urban (new) Normality

Committees: RC03 Community Research (Host); RC21 Regional and Urban Development

See Joint Session Details for JS-134.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

61 Cultural Institutions and Community**Location:** 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada***Chair:** Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****61.1** Tracy Xavia KARNER, *University of Houston, USA*
Museums, Festivals, and Scenes: Building Community Around Photography**61.2** Clara CIRDAN, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*
Cultural Democracy in Museums**61.3** Raisa AKIFEVA, *The University of Western Australia, Australia***Russian-Speaking Communities in Spain and Australia: Cultural Production Dilemmas and Power Relations.****61.4** Sudeep KAUR, *Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, India*
The Impact of Social Media on the Dynamics of Ethnic Community in Rajasthan

10:30-12:20

62 Comunidades Resilientes: Capacidades Colectivas De Resistencia y Transformación Ante Las Nuevas Adversidades**Language:** Spanish**Location:** 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Maria-Rosa HERRERA-GUTIERREZ, *CENTRO DE SOCIOLOGÍA Y POLÍTICAS LOCALES, Spain* and Maria de las Olas PALMA GARCIA, *Universidad de Málaga, Saipan***Chair:** Cristina MATEOS MORA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****62.1** Saul CURLO-LOPEZ, *Universidad del País Vasco - Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Spain* and Luis Migule UHARTE POZAS, *Universidad del País Vasco - Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Spain***Errekaleor Barrio Libre: ¿De La Resistencia a La Construcción ó La Resistencia Como Construcción?****62.2** Ana LOPEZ CARLASSARE, *University of Málaga, Spain*
Resiliencia Comunitaria En Zonas Despobladas: Aproximación Desde Profesionales De La Acción Social**62.3** Mercedes CUENCA SILVESTRE, *Universidad Ramon Llull, Spain* and Enrique PASTOR SELLER, *Universidad de Murcia, Spain*
La Articulación Entre Los Principios Éticos y Las Prácticas Comunitarias Resilientes**62.4** Elena RUIZ-ANGEL, *Universidad de Huelva, Spain*
Resilience Capacity of Women Victims of Gender Violence in Spain.**62.5** Elena FERRI, *University of Huelva, Spain*; Fernando RELINQUE, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*; Octavio VÁZQUEZ, *University of Huelva, Spain* and Aleix MORILLA, *University of Huelva, Spain*
Evaluación DEL Impacto Y La Gestión De LOS Riesgos EN LOS Servicios Sociales. Validación DEL Modelo a Través DEL Método Delphi

12:30-14:20

63 Comunidades Resilientes: Capacidades Colectivas De Resistencia y Transformación Ante Las Nuevas Adversidades II

Language: Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maria-Rosa HERRERA-GUTIERREZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Maria de las Olas PALMA GARCIA, *Universidad de Malaga, Saipan*

Chair: Angel ZAPATA MOYA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

63.1 Daniel GUTIERREZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*
De La Trinchera AL Bienestar: Redes De Apoyo Mutuo Durante La COVID-19

63.2 Ines ROUQUAUD, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Argentina*
Servicio Social De Andalucía: Cambios e Innovaciones En La Gestión Durante COVID-19. Perspectiva De Abajo Hacia Arriba.

63.3 Patricia SCHETTINI, *Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina*; Daniela TORILLO, *Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina* and María Cecilia NOGUEIRA, *Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina*
Resistencia y Colectivización Frente a Los Desafíos De La Cuarentena En Sectores Vulnerables De Argentina. La Situación Particular De Un Comedor Comunitario De Un Barrio Periférico De La Ciudad De La Plata, Provincia De Buenos Aires, República Argentina

63.4 Maria Eugenia SANCHEZ DIAZ, *Universidad Iberoamericana Puebla, Mexico*
Los Desgarramientos Civilizatorios: Una Perspectiva

14:30-16:20

64 RC03 Business Meeting

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

RC04

Sociology of Education

Program Coordinators: Marios VRYONIDES, *European University of Cyprus, Cyprus* and Shaheeda ESSACK, *Department of Higher Education and Training, South Africa*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-5 The Soldier-Scholar: Postsecondary Education of Future Military Officers

Committees: RC01 *Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution (Host)*; RC04 *Sociology of Education*

See Joint Session Details for JS-5.

15:30-17:20

65 Re-Thinking the Role of Sociology of Education in Tackling the Global Rise of Authoritarianism, Populism, Xenophobia, and Racism.

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maria CHALARI, *European University Cyprus, Cyprus* and Marios VRYONIDES, *European University of Cyprus, Cyprus*

Chair: Maria CHALARI, *European University Cyprus, Cyprus*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

65.1 Tien-Hui CHIANG, *Anhui Normal University, China*; Allen THURSTON, *School of Social Science, Education and Social Work, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom* and Alison MACKENZIE, *School of Social Science, Education and Social Work, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom*
Gearing the Relation from Self-Monitoring to Collective Surveillance through Cultural Therapeutics in the Regime of Neoliberal Governmentality

65.2 Halleli PINSON, *Ben-Gurion University, Israel*
Neo Zionist Right-Wing Populist Discourse and Activism in the Israel Education System Background and Conceptual Framework

65.3 Simina DRAGOS, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom* and Taylor HUGHSON, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Nascent Authoritarianism and the Populist "Free Speech Crisis" in the UK: The Importance of the Sociology of Education

65.4 Joanne DILLABOUGH, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom* and Sagarika BOSE, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Hungarianisation, Horrorism and a 'Funeral for Higher Education': Populist Knowledge-Making and Political Legitimacy in Pre and Post War Hungary

65.5 Mirjam WEIBERG, *German Centre for Integration and Migration Research, Germany* and Olaf KLEIST, *German Centre for Integration and Migration Research, Germany*
New Modes and Forms of Civic Education in Time of Populism, Xenophobia, and Racism

65.6 Lawrence SAHA, *The Australian National University, Australia*
Populist Extremism and the Education Connection: Some "New" Sociological Perspectives

65.7 Trevor MAKHETHA, *University of the Western Cape, South Africa*
Reimagining Sociology of Education in South Africa: Toward a Radical Praxis

65.8 Yuli ASTIANA, *The University of Adelaide, Australia*
Educating Against Radicalisation and Violent Extremism: A Study of Peace Pedagogical Practices in Indonesia

17:30-19:20

67 COVID Winners and Losers in Education: How the Pandemic Has Exacerbated but Also Improved Current and Future Social Inequalities

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Joanna SIKORA, *Australian National University, Australia* and Lawrence SAHA, *Australian National University, Australia*

Chair: Joanna SIKORA, *Australian National University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

67.1 Mareike RUSSMANN, *German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW), Germany*; Nicolai NETZ, *DZHW, Germany* and Markus LÖRZ, *HIS Institut für Hochschulentwicklung, Germany*
Dropout Intentions of Students with Disabilities

67.2 Wei-yun CHUNG, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
Navigating the Unknown Waters of Home-Schooling during Taiwan's COVID Lockdown

67.3 Antoaneta GETOVA, *Sofia University, Bulgaria*
Three Years of Online Learning in the Universities in Bulgaria: Effects and Perspectives for the Future

67.4 Sebastian FUENTES, *CONICET/FLACSO-UNTREF, Argentina*
Educational Inequalities and Teaching during the Pandemic at Secondary Level: An Analysis of "Innovative" Practices and the Construction of Inequalities in Argentina

67.5 P Nikhil KUMAR, *University of Hyderabad, India* and Vamsi SURAPOGU, *University of Hyderabad, India*
Digital Alienation of Dalit Students during the Pandemic: A Case Study of University of Hyderabad

67.6 Bruna COELHO, *UFRJ, Brazil*; Ana beatriz DE JESUS, *UFRJ, Brazil* and Renata DE MIRANDA, *UERJ, Brazil*
The Impacts and Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Educational Practices and Teaching Work in Brazil

67.7 Alessandra DECATALDO, *University of Milan Bicocca, Italy* and Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*
Being Insecure and Overload Among University Lecturers: The Effects of Technostress on Their Working Life and Work-Family Balance

67.8 Jiwei LU, *East China Normal University, China*
"Camera on, Please, Let'be Together": A Case Study of High School Students' Experience Towards Online Class in China during the COVID-19 Pandemic

67.9 Josué GUTIÉRREZ BARROSO, *Universidad de La Laguna, Spain*; Ana PADRON, *Universidad de La Laguna, Spain* and Juan Vianney TRUJILLO-GONZÁLEZ, *Universidad de La Laguna, Spain*
Post-Pandemic University Access in Tenerife: Gender Inequalities

67.10 Maria Cecília Martins Ferreira da SILVA, *ULHT_Lisbon, Portugal* and Vítor Duarte TEODORO, *NOVA School of Science and Technology, New University of Lisbon, Portugal*
Título: Opportunities in Portuguese Curriculum and Assessment Followed Covid-19

66 Contemporary Issues in Sociology of Education I

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Marios VRYONIDES, *European University of Cyprus, Cyprus*

ROUNDTABLES:

RC04 Roundtable 1

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

66.1 Duru ARUN KUMAR, *NSUT, India*
Marketization of Higher Education in India - Role of Accreditation

66.2 Joao SEBASTIAO, *Iscte Instituto Universitario de Lisboa, Portugal*
Political Context Matters: A Reflexion about the Impact of Politics on Inclusive Education

66.3 Cihan ERDAL, *Carleton University, Canada* and Jacqueline KENNELLY, *Carleton University, Canada*
The Disorientation of Democracy and Public Life: (Neo) Liberal Democratic Citizenship Education in the Twenty-First Century

66.4 Djordje STEFANOVIC, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia*; Nathan MANNING, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia*; Eleanor RIDINGS, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia* and Thomas WOOD, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia*
Could University Education Make Populism Unpopular Again?

66.5 Fatemeh YAZDANI, *Lund University, Sweden*
The Policy Discourse of the Desirable Education System: A Case Study of Post-Revolutionary Iran

RC04 Roundtable 2

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

66.6 Jacqueline KENNELLY, *Carleton University, Canada* and Cihan ERDAL, *Carleton University, Canada*
Probing School Bullying Practices As Classification Struggles: Challenges and Possibilities for Youth Social Justice

66.7 Karen DOOLEY, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Megan KIMBER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Elizabeth BRIANT, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Mary FINCH, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Rebecca ENGLISH, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
Problem or Solution? (In)Justices and Government-Sponsored Programs of Shadow Education in Literacy

66.8 Megha WADHWA, *Free University of Berlin, Germany*
Looking at My Field without and with the Camera: Filming As a Method for Migration Studies

RC04 Roundtable 3

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

66.9 Alberto PIERDANT RODRÍGUEZ, *Universidad Autonoma Metropolitana-Xochimilco, Mexico*; Jesús RODRÍGUEZ, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana - Xochimilco, Mexico*; Alberto Isaac PIERDANT CASTELLANOS, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana - Xochimilco, Mexico*; Nelly MOLINA, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana - Xochimilco, Mexico*; Elba Cristina RODRÍGUEZ, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana - Xochimilco, Mexico* and Ana Elena NARRO, *Universidad Autonoma Metropolitana - Xochimilco, Mexico*
Remote Teaching-Learning of University Mathematics in Mexico. An Educational Model That Accentuated Existing Social Inequalities

66.10 Anirban MUKHERJEE, *Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Petroleum Technology, India*
Tribal Education in India: Deconstructing the Acculturation Hypothesis

66.11 Glen Christian TACASA, *University of the Philippines Los Banos, Philippines*
A Pedagogy of Ambiguities and Silences: Analyses of the Philippine History Education on Marcos' Authoritarian Regime

66.12 Shushwi KE, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*
Rising Authoritarianism and Devaluation of Liberal Education: A Sociological Reflection

66.13 Imraan BUCCUS, *DUT and SIT, South Africa*
In the Trenches': South African Vice-Chancellors Leading transformation in Times of Change

RC04 Roundtable 4

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

66.14 Chun-wen LIN, *National Chiayi University, Taiwan*
Does It Matter or Is It Necessary and Possible to Talk about Social Class with Middle School Students?

66.15 Kitty TE RIELE, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Emily RUDLING, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Sherridan EMERY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Becky SHELLEY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Jessica WOODROFFE, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Natalie BROWN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Educational Equity in Times of Crisis

66.16 Shinichi HAMAMOTO, *Nihon University, Japan*
How Is Inequality Accumulating?: Decomposing Differences in Educational Attainment By Categorical Variables into Each Educational Transition in Japan

66.17 Louie Benedict IGNACIO, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*
Social Capital in Cross-Cultural Settings: Case of International Students in the Philippines

RC04 Roundtable 5**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

66.18 Yasukiyo SUGIMOTO, *University of Miami, USA*
Pedagogy of Life: Reexamining and Eliminating Fundamental Social Inequalities

66.19 Walter ALLEN, *UCLA, USA*; Denise ORTIZ, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*; Azeb TADESSE, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*; Chantal JONES, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA* and Gadise REGASSA, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*
"be the Change You Seek" Faculty of Color, Organizational Change and Campus Racial Climate

66.20 Darina LEPADATU, *Kennesaw State University, USA* and Kathleen KIRK, *Kennesaw State University, USA*
Campus Hate Crimes during the Trump Era: University Responses to Violent White Supremacist Movements in the US

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

68.5 Anna Maria LEONORA, *University of Catania, Italy*
Educational Disobedience As Innovative Educational Practice. Insights from a Mediterranean Case Study

68.6 Chandrika KB, *Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, 591156 Karnataka, India, India* and Shamalabai B. DASOG, *Dept of Sociology, M.Ms Arts, Commerce, Science and Home- Science College, India*
New Education Policy-2020: An Innovative Initiation in Karnataka State, India

68.7 Tatiana SEMENOVA, *Sociologist, Russian Federation*
The Re-Thinking Experience of Collaboration between the Sociological Faculty of University and Potential Employers for the Future Sociological Education

68.8 Hugo CLAROS, *Independent, Peru*
Monitoring and Evaluation for Educational Innovation in Perú: Both a Potential Community Tool and a Required Bureaucratic Language

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-30 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (1)

Committees: *RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change and RC04 Sociology of Education*

See Joint Session Details for JS-30.

68 Sociological Perspectives on Social Innovation in Education

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Karina MALDONADO-MARISCAL, *Technical University Dortmund, Germany*

Chair: Carol REID, *Western Sydney University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

68.1 Karina MALDONADO-MARISCAL, *Technical University Dortmund, Germany* and Antonius SCHRÖDER, *Technical University Dortmund, Germany*
Social Innovation in Education

68.2 Juha TUUNAINEN, *University of Oulu, Finland* and Kari KANTASALMI, *University of Oulu, Finland*
Processing Societal Expectations: Decision-Making on Entrepreneurial Education in a Research University

68.3 Analia MEO, *CONICET, Argentina*; Ana Inés HERAS, *CEDESI-UNSAM- CONICET, Argentina* and Mariano CHERVIN, *University of Buenos Aires (UBA) - Research Institute Gino Germani, Argentina*
Educational Policies, Innovations, and Actor Network Theory

68.4 Ho-dae CHONG, *Duksung Women's University, Republic of Korea* and Jong-kil KIM, *Department of Sociology, Duksung Women's University, Republic of Korea*
Innovating the Innovation By Competition and Cooperation in Higher Education: The Case of the Social Sciences Korea(SSK) Program As a Natural Experiment

10:30-12:20

JS-37 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (2)

Committees: *RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC04 Sociology of Education and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-37.

69 Rethinking Questions and Issues of Social Justice in Education

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hernan CUERVO, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Karina MALDONADO-MARISCAL, *Technical University Dortmund, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

69.1 Pepka BOYADJIEVA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, BAS, Bulgaria* and Petya ILIEVA-TRICHKOVA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, BAS, Bulgaria*
A Multidimensional and Comparative Social Justice Perspective Towards Inequalities in Access to Higher Education

69.2 Hernan CUERVO, *5/100 Leicester St, Australia*
The Struggles for Recognition and Distribution: A Theoretical Approach to Rural Teaching Recruitment

69.3 Kitty TE RIELE, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Tim CORCORAN, *Deakin University, Australia*; Alison BAKER, *Victoria University, Australia* and Julie WHITE, *Victoria University, Australia*
Social Justice in Youth Justice: Participation in Education By Incarcerated Young People

69.4 Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*; Mauricio SALGADO, *Universidad Andrés Bello, Chile* and Kevin CARRASCO, *COES - Center for Social Conflict and Cohesion Studies, Chile*
Meritocracy, Redistributive Preferences and Political Socialization at School

69.5 Quentin MAIRE, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Social Justice and the Subject-Based Curriculum: Socio-Academic Distribution and Status Hierarchy in the Making of Curriculum Inequality

69.6 Ilana FINEFETER-ROSENBLUH, *Monash University, Australia* and Jane WILKINSON, *Monash University, Australia*
"It's Expensive...Not Everyone Can Afford It...It's Unpleasant": Students' (un)Ethical Ideas of Marketised-Privatised Faith-Based Schooling in Australia

69.7 Gonzalo SARA VÍ, *CIESAS, Mexico*
School Belonging and Social (In)Justice in Mexico

69.8 Manuela MENDOZA HORVITZ, *University of O'Higgins, Chile* and Gabriel GUTIÉRREZ, *Universidad Diego Portales/ Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
The Ubiquity of Inclusion: Institutional Discourses and Features Shaping Socioeconomic Diversity in Schools

69.9 Tebeje MOLLA, *Deakin University, Australia* and Trevor GALE, *University of Glasgow, Scotland*
Educational Dis/Advantage: Expanding the Spaces of Assessment

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

69.10 Cecilia ADROGUE, *CONICET - Universidad de San Andrés, Argentina* and Eugenia ORLICKI, *Argentinos por la Educación - CEDH UdeSA, Argentina*
The Value and Distributive Effect of Public Education Expenditure in Argentina

15:30-17:20

70 Student Trajectories and Interlevel Transitions: Impacts of the Pandemic on Educational Inequalities

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina* and Emilia DI PIERO, *CONICET- UNLP, Argentina*

Chair: Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/ Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

70.1 Joanna SIKORA, *Australian National University, Australia*
An Unusual Dynamic? How Diverse Student Groups Transitioned from Secondary to Tertiary Education Pre- and during the Pandemic in Australia

70.2 Charlotte BRANCHU, *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom* and Vikki BOLIVER, *Durham University, United Kingdom*
Mapping Social Networks of Possibilities: Landscapes of Trajectories into Higher Education

70.3 Agustina CORICA, *FLACSO, Argentina*
Trayectorias Escolares y Pandemia En La Educación Secundaria Desde Un Abordaje Regional En Argentina

70.4 Jennifer GLICK, *Pennsylvania State University, USA*; Scott YABIKU, *Pennsylvania State University, USA*; Arinala RANDRIANASOLO, *Pennsylvania State University, USA* and Melissa ALCARAZ, *Brigham Young University, USA*
School Closures, Household Livelihood Loss and the Retreat from Educational Engagement

70.5 Emilia DI PIERO, *CONICET- UNLP, Argentina*; Santiago GARRIGA OLMO, *IdIHCS-CONICET/UNLP, Argentina* and Ana Laura MARCHEL, *FaHCE/UNLP, Argentina*
Expectativas Estudiantiles y Políticas De Articulación Interniveles En La Educación Secundaria Bonaerense Argentina En La Pandemia

70.6 Liang-Wen LIN-JANUSZEWSKI, *Paderborn University, Germany*
First-Year University Transition Experiences of German Students in the Global Pandemic

70.7 Valeria DABENIGNO, *University of Buenos Aires, Argentina* and Analia MEO, *CONICET, Argentina*
Perspectivas Docentes Sobre Vínculos Sociales y Pedagógicos Con Sus Estudiantes Durante La Pandemia. Variaciones, Desigualdades y Cambios En El Pasaje De La Educación Remota a La Bimodalidad.

17:30-19:20

JS-54 Why Do We Need the Visual? Understanding Educational Practices Using Visual Data and Methods.

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); RC57 Visual Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-54.

JS-50 Navigating the Other Side of the Classroom: Exploring Teachers' Experiences at Work

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); RC30 Sociology of Work

See Joint Session Details for JS-50.

19:30-20:50

71 RC04 Business Meeting

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

72 Social and Political Underpinnings of Teacher Recruitment and Certification

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Iasonas LAMPRIANOU, *University of Cyprus, Cyprus*

Chair: Elspeth MCINNES, *University of South Australia, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

72.1 Pranaya SWAIN, *Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai, India, India* and Biswajit APAT, *National Institute of Science Education and Research Bhubaneswar, India*
Prearity of Contract Teachers: A Qualitative Analysis of Lived Experiences

72.2 Taylor HUGHSON, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*

Producing New Kinds of Teachers in England 2008-2020: Tracing Knowledge Production and Elite Actor Networks in the Reform of Teacher Certification

72.3 Chien-Lung WANG, *Department of Education, National Taitung University, Taiwan* and Juhui CHANG, *National Taitung University, Taiwan*

The Strategic Development of Advanced Indigenous Language Proficiency of Student Teachers Specialized in the Initiative Teacher Program for Indigenous Language and Literacy Domain for Secondary Schools in Taiwan

72.4 Jurate LITVINAITE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
The Emergence of the Third Space in Teachers' Professional Practices

72.5 Silvia ANNEN, *University of Bamberg, Germany*; Xavier ST-DENIS, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada* and Julia HUFNAGL, *University of Bamberg, Germany*
Relations between Family Background and Persistence in Overqualification – Comparative Results from UK and Germany

72.6 Carla TAPIA, *School of Education and Professional Studies, Australia*; Parlo SINGH, *School of Education and Professional Studies, Australia*; Susan WHATMAN, *School of Education and Professional Studies, Australia* and Debbie BARGALLIE, *Griffith Institute of Educational Research, Australia*
Teacher Activism: Struggles over Public Education in Chile

10:30-12:20

JS-63 Housing and School Choices in the Unequal City: Uneasy Trade-Offs, New Combinations and Socio-Spatial Consequences

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC04 Sociology of Education

See Joint Session Details for JS-63.

15:30-17:20

73 How Reading Performance Is Related to Cultural Capital

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Chun-wen LIN, *National Chiayi University, Taiwan* and Jason Chien-chen CHANG, *Chinese Culture University, Taiwan*

Chair: Kent Sheng Yao CHENG, *National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

73.1 Ying-jie JHENG, *National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*; Chun-wen LIN, *National Chiayi University, Taiwan* and Yuen-kuang LIAO, *Chinese Culture University, Taiwan*
Does Cultural Capital Still Matter?: A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Cultural Capital on Reading Performance

73.2 Elspeth MCINNES, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Pauline HARRIS, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Alexandra DIAMOND, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Bec NEILL, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Cynthia BROCK, *University of Wyoming, USA* and Ufemia CAMAITOGA, *University of the South Pacific, TAFE Lautoka, Fiji*
Involving Families in Integrating Embodied and Objective Community Language Capital in Reading Resources for Preschool Aged Children Entering Monolingual Education Systems

73.3 Shu-min CHEN, *Tatung University, Taiwan* and Ying-jie JHENG, *National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*
Effects of the New Immigrants' Cultural Capital on Child-Rearing Process: Perspectives from Multi-Ethnic Relationship

73.4 Chiaying WU, *Department of Education, Chinese Culture University, Taiwan*
The Study of Junior High School Students' Reading Literacy: The Cases of Taiwan in PISA 2018

73.5 Maria CHALARI, *European University Cyprus, Cyprus* and Marios VRYONIDES, *European University Cyprus, Cyprus*
Adolescents' Reading Habits during COVID-19: Are They Still a Mechanism for Cultural Reproduction?

17:30-19:20

74 Neoliberalism, Human Capital Discourse and Education Practice

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tien-Hui CHIANG, *National University of Tainan, China*

Chair: Tien-Hui CHIANG, *National University of Tainan, China*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

74.1 Anthony DWORKIN, *University of Houston, USA* and Lawrence SAHA, *Australian National University, Australia*
The Effects of Neoliberal Assumptions, Policies, and Practices on School Culture and Trust in School

74.2 Weihe XIE, *Institute of Education, Tsinghua University, China* and Wen WEN, *Institute of Education, Tsinghua University, China*
The Imbalance between Knowledge in Modern Educational System: Humanities Vs. Natural Sciences

74.3 Atsuko SHIMBO, *Waseda University, Japan* and Mutsuko TENDO, *Miyagi Gakuin Women's University, Japan*
Human Capital Discourse and Cultural Resources: A Case Study of Family Education in Japan

74.4 Chunping WANG, *National Taipei University of Education, Taiwan*; Po-han LIN, *National Taipei University of Education, Taiwan* and Bo-Ruey HUANG, *Chinese Culture University, Taiwan*
Global Citizenship Competencies, New Immigrant Youths' Hybrid Identity, and Social Justice- Taiwan Observation Under the Globalization Condition

74.5 Kent Sheng Yao CHENG, *National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*
When Global Meets Local: the Dialectics between Indigenous Knowledge and Global Competition

74.6 Zhaoxi ZHENG, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Learning to Become Neoliberal Subjects: Discursive Tensions between Australian Higher Education Policies and Research Student Experiences

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

75 Contemporary Issues in Sociology of Education II

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Shaheeda ESSACK, *Department of Higher Education and Training, South Africa*

ROUNDTABLES:

RC04 Roundtable 1

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

75.1 Adam RAJCAN, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Edgar BURNS, *Waikato University, New Zealand*
What Do We Know about Australian and New Zealand Sociology PhDs in the Latest Decade (2010-19)?

75.2 Atinder KAUR, *Punjab Agricultural University Ludhiana, India*
Covid 19 Crisis and Online Education System: Narratives from Rural Households (India)

75.3 Donatella POLIANDRI, *INVALSI (Italian National Institute of Educational Evaluation), Italy*; Grazia GRAZIOSI, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*; Beba MOLINARI, *Univeristy of Catanzaro 'Magna Graecia', Italy* and Graziana EPIFANI, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*
School-to-Work Program during Pandemic: First Evidence from Italy.

RC04 Roundtable 2

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

75.4 Roman SMIRNOV, *Free University of Berlin, Germany*
International PhD-Students during the Pandemic: Transformation of Migrant Strategies and Career Planning

75.5 Sharmila RAMA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa* and Ruth HOSKINS, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*
Reflecting on the Teaching and Learning Experiences and Lived Realities of the Students in the Bachelor of Social Science Extended Curriculum Degree at the University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa during the COVID-19 Pandemic

75.6 Leonie BUSCHKAMP, *Leibniz University Hannover (LCSS - Leibniz Center for Science and Society), Germany* and Tim SEIDENSCHNUR, *University of Kassel (INCHER - International Center for Higher Education Research), Germany*
Windows of Opportunities. How the Pandemic Changed Education in Different Disciplines at Universities.

RC04 Roundtable 3

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

75.7 Liang-Wen LIN-JANUSZEWSKI, *Paderborn University, Germany*
International Students' First-Semester Transition Experiences after the Pandemic in Germany

75.8 Deepak KUMAR, *University of Delhi, India*
Embedded Disposessions: The Gendered Self in the Classroom

75.9 John Rey CODILLA, *Davao Oriental State University, Philippines* and Mona LAYA, *University of Immaculate Conception, Philippines*
Encounters and Ordeals on Violent Incidents and School Safety: Their Status and Relationship

RC04 Roundtable 4

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

75.10 Abu MAZUMDER, *HSTU, Bangladesh* and Khadiza Tul KUBRA, *HSTU, Bangladesh*
Voluntary Supplementary Education and Academic Performance of Underprivileged Children: 'Hstu Mojar Ischool' Model

75.11 Mariusz ZEMLO, *University of Bialystok, Poland*
The School Normative System a Key Element in Determining the Quality of the School Environment

75.12 Gisela REDONDO-SAMA, *Rovira i Virgili University, Spain* and Teresa SORDE-MARTI, *Univ Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Dialogic Leadership for Social Justice

75.13 Mohammed Illias SHEIKH, *International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai, India* and Kailash DAS, *International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai, India*
Effectiveness of E-Counselling Session during COVID-19 Pandemic in Open Distance Learning Programme: A Cross-Sectional Study in India

10:30-12:20

76 Intersectional Approach and Inequality of Educational Opportunity

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Aigul ALIEVA, *Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research, Luxembourg*; Jekatyerina DUNAJEVA, *Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Centre for Social Sciences, Hungary* and Hanna SIAROVA, *Public Policy and Management Institute, Lithuania*

Chair: Shaheeda ESSACK, *Department of Higher Education and Training, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

76.1 Hanna SIAROVA, *Public Policy and Management Institute, Lithuania* and Jekatyerina DUNAJEVA, *Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Centre for Social Sciences, Hungary*
Intersectionality in Education Policy Documents: Comparative Analysis of Nine European Countries

76.2 Celia BOUCHET, *Sciences Po (CRIS-LIEPP), France*
Disability-Related Educational Gaps By Socioeconomic Background, Migration and Gender: Insights from a Mixed Methods Study in France

76.3 Ineke PIT-TEN CATE, *Luxembourg Centre for Educational Testing (LUCET), University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg* and Sabine GLOCK, *Institute for Educational Research, School of Education, Bergische Universität Wuppertal, Germany*
Combined Effects of Students' Gender and Ethnicity on Teachers' Stereotype-Based Expectations: A Systematic Review

76.4 Cecilia ADROGUE, *CONICET - Universidad de San Andrés, Argentina*; Victoria ANAUATI, *CEDH - Universidad de San Andrés, Argentina* and Mariano TOMMASI, *CEDH - Universidad de San Andrés, Argentina*
Educational Inequalities in Argentina: Mechanisms, Dynamics and Evidence

76.5 Peter ROBERT, TARKI Social Research Institute, Hungary
How Do Unhappiness and Marginalisation at School Undermine Academic Performance?

76.6 Angharad BUTLER - REES, University of Warwick, United Kingdom
Disentangling Educational Pathways and Work Outcomes for Disabled Young People in England

76.7 Ineke PIT-TEN CATE, Luxembourg Centre for Educational Testing (LUCET), University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg; Martha OTTENBACHER, Luxembourg Centre for Educational Testing (LUCET), Faculty of Humanities, Education and Social Sciences, University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg; Aigul ALIEVA, Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research, Luxembourg; Taylor KROEZEN, Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research (LISER), Luxembourg; Andreas HADJAR, University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg; Juliette TORABIAN, Department of Social sciences, Faculty of Humanities, Education and Social Sciences, University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg and Frederick DE MOLL, Department of Social sciences, Faculty of Humanities, Education and Social Sciences, University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg
The Longitudinal Impact of Student Characteristics, School Composition and Track Placement on Mathematics Performance: Inter- and Cross Level Intersectionality

76.8 Sarvendra YADAV, Dr. Harisingh Gour Central University Sagar, India
Intersectionality in Course Choices: A Cross-Sectional Study of Educational Inequalities in India

15:30-17:20

77 The Challenge to Remain Relevant: Public Higher Education Versus Private Higher Education

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Shaheeda ESSACK, Department of Higher Education and Training/University of Johannesburg, South Africa

Chair: Shaheeda ESSACK, Department of Higher Education and Training, South Africa

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

77.1 Su-ming KHOO, National University of Ireland, Ireland
Connecting the Challenges of Quality and Equality in Higher Education in Ireland and South Africa – Learning from a Collective Intelligence Based Research Project.

77.2 Reyhaneh JAVADI, University of Alberta, Canada and Zohreh BAYATRIZI, University of Alberta, Canada
Private Sociology: The Origins and Impacts of for-Profit Courses Outside Academia in Iran

77.3 Yuki HONDA, Graduate School of Education, The University of Tokyo, Japan
The Impact of College Education in the Humanities and Social Sciences on Job Skills and Social Attitudes after Graduation: The Case of Japan

77.4 Fidel AREVALO, Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala, Guatemala
The Challenge of Public Universities to be Able to Respond to the Needs of Inclusion, Equity and Development, in Unfavorable Contexts.

77.5 Yuxuan WANG, IOE University College London, United Kingdom
Development of Undergraduate Student Research Capability in Social Sciences: A Comparative Study between China, UK and the US

77.6 Dhaneswar BHOI, University of Edinburgh UK, Social and Political Science, United Kingdom and Neelima LAKRA, London School of Management Education, United Kingdom
Public and Private Higher Education in Laissez-Faire Economy: Echoes of Marginal Section Students of India

77.7 Sebastian FUENTES, CONICET/FLACSO-UNTREF, Argentina
Challenges for University Systems in the Southern Cone: Public and Private Institutions Facing Diverging Social Expectations

17:30-19:20

JS-107 Education, Solidarity and Engagement: The Study of Morals and Emotions in Altruistic Educational Experiences

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions

See Joint Session Details for JS-107.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-116 Inclusive Education, Knowledge Co-Production, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); RC03 Community Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-116.

10:30-12:20

JS-123 Educational Migration in the Post-Pandemic World: Exploring Continuities and Discontinuities

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-123.

15:30-17:20

78 When Global Meets Local: the Dialectics between Indigenous Knowledge and Global Competition

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Kent Sheng Yao CHENG, National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan

Chair: Kent Sheng Yao CHENG, National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

78.1 Ai-hsuan MA, National Chengchi University, Taiwan
Internationalization at Home in Taiwan's Higher Education: Domestic Students' Perspectives

78.2 Ruomeng LIU, East China Normal University, China and Zhiying WU, University of Queensland, Australia
Walking on the Road of Educational Discontinuous: A Study on the Cross-Cultural Growth of Young Chinese Students Abroad

78.3 Lucia Ratih KUSUMADEWI, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*

Multicultural Education As a Social Movement

78.4 Aditya RAJ, *Indian Institute of Technology Patna, India*
Promises of India's New Education Policy 2020

78.5 Beatrice LAM, *Hong Kong Metropolitan University, Hong Kong* and Hei-hang Hayes TANG, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Problematising the Global North/ South Binaries: A Critical Review of the Sociological Literature of Education of Ethnic Minority Students in Hong Kong

78.6 Mei-Ling LIN, *National Open University, Taiwan*
Globalisation and Implications for Education: Local Pedagogies

78.7 Juhui CHANG, *National Taitung University, Taiwan* and Chien-Lung WANG, *Department of Education, National Taitung University, Taiwan*

When the Majority Becomes the Minority: Non-Indigenous Teachers' Cultural Competence Development in an Indigenous School in Taiwan

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

78.8 Satyanarayana GATTU, *Osmania University, India*
Higher Education in India and Emerging Trends (A Sociological Study)

17:30-19:20

79 Education for Sustainable Development

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Anita Cecilia HIRSCH ADLER, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Anita Cecilia HIRSCH ADLER, *Colonia Letran Valle, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

79.1 Judith PEREZ-CASTRO, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico* and Guadalupe PALMEROS Y AVILA, *Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, Mexico*
Education for Sustainability in Higher Education Students

79.2 Jesus GARCIA REYES, *UNAM, Mexico* and Alejandro MARQUEZ, *UNAM, Mexico*
Factors That Affect the Perception of Citizenship and Community Partition of Young People Aged 15 to 17 in Mexico

79.3 Claire WAGNER, *University of Pretoria, South Africa* and Jeremy GIBBERD, *Nelson Mandela University, South Africa*
Pedagogical Insights from a Course on Reducing University Students' Ecological Footprints

79.4 Tunghsing HSIUNG, *National Taitung University, Taiwan*
Indigenous Student-Teacher and Learning for Sustainability: Cultural Diversity and Educational Equity

79.5 Jesus GARCIA REYES, *UNAM, Mexico*
Formación Profesional y Ética En Post Pandemia En Estudiantes De Pueblos Originarios De Educación Superior

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

80 Rethinking the Modern Educational Model: East Asian Perspectives

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Shinichi AIZAWA, *Sophia University, Japan*

Chair: Shinichi AIZAWA, *Sophia University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

80.1 Anita KOO, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
The Emergence of Vocational/Professional Training in Expanded Higher Education Systems in East Asia

80.2 Fumiaki OJIMA, *Doshisha University, Japan*
Changes in Socio-Economic Inequality of Educational Opportunity: How Competition to Higher Education Entry Influenced Its Effect?

80.3 Masayuki FUJINE, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan*
Challenging and Conformity to the Dominant Education System: A Case of Alternative Education Movements in Japan

80.4 Ichiro OKANO, *Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Japan*
The Politics of Linguistic Relativity in Japanese English Education

80.5 Josiane MARTIN-O'BRIEN, *International University of Monaco (IUM), Monaco*
Institutionalization of Western Management Education in India: A Tale of Three Histories

80.6 Jhaverbhai PATEL, *School of Social Sciences, India*
Rethinking on Gandhiji's Nai Talim Education System

10:30-12:20

81 Edtech and the Post-Pandemic University: Understandings and Interventions

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Claire POLSTER, *University of Regina, Canada* and Janice NEWSON, *York University, Canada*

Chair: Josiane MARTIN-O'BRIEN, *International University of Monaco (IUM), Monaco*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

81.1 Judith PEREZ-CASTRO, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico* and Jesus GARCIA REYES, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Digital Exclusion and Educational Inequality in Indigenous University Students

81.2 Edmondo GRASSI, *Roma Tre University, Italy*
Technology and University: The Perception of the Student Population in Roma Tre

81.3 Elsa ESTRELA, *Lusofona University/ CeiED, Portugal* and Carla GALEGO, *Lusofona University/ CeiED, Portugal*
Academic Professionalism in the XXI Century: Processes of Change in Teachers' Practice

81.4 Luke MCCRONE, *Imperial College London, United Kingdom* and Julianne VIOLA, *Imperial College London, United Kingdom*
The Hybrid Learning Dilemma: Exploring the Learning Choices of Disadvantaged Students during the COVID-19 Era

81.5 Anita Cecilia HIRSCH ADLER, *Colonia Letran Valle, Mexico*
Postgraduate Academics from a Mexican University and Their Vision of the Covid-19 Pandemic

12:30-14:20

82 The Possibilities and Challenges of Decoloniality in Education and Research

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Melanie BAAK, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Joel WINDLE, *University of South Australia, Australia*

Co-chairs: Melanie BAAK, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Joel WINDLE, *University of South Australia, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

82.1 Terry WOTHERSPOON, *University of Saskatchewan, Canada* and Emily MILNE, *MacEwan University, Canada*
The Role of Cultural Supports for Indigenous Students: Spaces for and Impediments to Decolonizing Education

82.2 Julian KUSABS, *The University of Adelaide, Australia*
Indigenous Historical Writings and Decolonial Futures of Education

82.3 Nomkhosi XULU-GAMA, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*; Aisha LORGAT, *Chris Hani Institute, South Africa* and Bianca TAME, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Decolonising Sociology: The South African Sociological Association As a Decolonial Catalyst?

82.4 Vanessa BAROLSKY, *Deakin University, Australia* and Laura RODRIGUEZ CASTRO, *Southern Cross University, Australia*
Reflecting on Global Dialogues on Decolonising Truth-Telling: Challenges and Possibilities

82.5 Kim MCLEOD, *The University of Tasmania, Australia*
Attending to the Particular to Enact Decolonial Theory in Teaching Practice

82.6 Marie BRENNAN, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Lew ZIPIN, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Reparative Activism Towards Decolonising Australian Teacher Education

82.7 Sophie RUDOLPH, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Jessica GERRARD, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Understanding the Material, Epistemic and Affective Dimensions of Racial Domination

82.8 Sarah MCDONALD, *University of South Australia, Australia*
A Review of Approved Texts and Text Choice for Subject English Teachers through a Decolonial Lens: Current and Future Options

14:30-16:20

83 Caste, Social Psyche and Humiliation at Higher Education

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Dhaneswar BHOI, *University of Edinburgh UK, Social and Political Science, United Kingdom* and Neelima LAKRA, *London School of Management Education, United Kingdom*

Chair: Dhaneswar BHOI, *University of Edinburgh UK, Social and Political Science, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

83.1 Rama DEVI, *KREA University, India*
Negotiating Caste in Educational Spaces: Trials of Dalit Youths in Higher Education in Delhi

83.2 Deep CHAND, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*
Resistance Against Caste Norms in Higher Education: A Perspective from below

83.3 Saraswati SUNA, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Caste Capital, Social Psyche and Humiliation: An Examination of Dalit Women Experiences in Higher Educational Institution in Eastern India

83.4 Deepak KUMAR, *University of Delhi, India*
Linguicism in Indian Higher Education: A Case Study of University of Delhi

83.5 Bagesh KUMAR, *National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration, New Delhi, India*
Understanding Humiliation in Indian Higher Education: A Perspective from Dalit and Adivasi Students

RC05

Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity

Program Coordinators: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*; Andrew SPORLE, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Rochelle COTE, *Memorial University, Canada* and Claudia TAZREITER, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

84 Indigenous Data Sovereignty

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Andrew SPORLE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Chair: Tori DIAMOND, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

84.1 Margaret WALTER, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Jacob PREHN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Social Research and the Operationalisation of Indigenous Data Sovereignty in Australia

84.2 Cassandra PRICE, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Bobby MAHER, *Australian National University, Australia* and Ray LOVETT, *Australian National University, Australia*
Operationalising the Indigenous Data Sovereignty Principles in Australia

84.3 Jacqueline QUINLESS, *University of Victoria, Canada*
Decolonizing Data: Unsettling Conversations about Social Research Methods

84.4 Lara GREAVES, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Cinnamon Jo LINDSAY, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Emerald MURIWAI, *Ngā Pou Mana Tangata Whenua Allied Health, New Zealand*; Charlotte MOORE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Eileen LI, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Andrew SPORLE, *iNZight Analytics, New Zealand* and Terryann CLARK, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Māori and the Integrated Data Infrastructure: A Critical Review of the Literature and Suggestions to Realise Māori Data Aspirations

84.5 Andrew SPORLE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Contested Data: Government Resistance to an Indigenous Data Sovereignty-Informed Response to the Epidemic

84.6 Desi SMALL-RODRIGUEZ, *University of California-Los Angeles, USA*
Decolonizing Demographic Data for Tribal Peoples

15:30-17:20

85 Covid, Racism and Indigeneity: tensions and responses

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Claudia TAZREITER, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Chair: Tori DIAMOND, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

85.1 Lara GREAVES, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
The Māori Electorates: Exploring Māori Electoral Roll Choices in Our Own Words

85.2 Vesa PUURONEN, *University of Oulu, Finland*
Local Politics As Perpetuator of Colonisation

85.3 Mokong Simon MAPADIMENG, *University of Limpopo, South Africa*
Social Cohesion in South Africa in the Aftermath of Apartheid – Advocating for the Indigenous Afro-Sensed and Ubuntu/Botho Anchored Approach.

85.4 Ray LOVETT, *Australian National University, Australia* and Makayla-may BRINCKLEY, *Australian National University, Australia*
Race, Racism, and Wellbeing Impacts on Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples in Australia

85.5 Ashleigh HAW, *Deakin University, Australia*
A Rationale for Community-Driven Antiracist Initiatives during Global Health Crises: Lessons from COVID-19

17:30-19:20

86 Citizenship, Nationalism and Racism

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Umut EREL, *Open University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Umut EREL, *PO Box 252, Walton Hall, United Kingdom*

Co-Chair: Ling TANG, *Academy of Film, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

86.1 Shobba HAMAL-GURUNG, *South Utah University, USA*
Bhutanese Refugees of Nepali Origin: Navigating Nationality and Citizenship in an Unequal World

86.2 Catharina PEECK-HO, *Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany*
Vulnerability, Inequality and Citizenship: The Example of Sanctuary Cities in the United States

86.3 Georgia STORM, *James Cook University, Australia*
Meeting in the White Space: The Discourse of First Nations Client and Legal Practitioner Relations.

86.4 Anya HOMMADOVA, *Sam Houston State University, USA*
The Struggle between Pro and Anti-Immigration Sentiment in the U.S. during the 2020 U.S. Election

86.5 Aitor JIMENEZ, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Ainhoa DOUHAIBI, *Universtat Ouberta de Catalunya, Spain*
The Islamophobic Consensus: Datafying Racism in Catalonia

86.6 Sanjeev ROUTRAY, *Assistant Professor, Brunei Darussalam*

Migration Narratives: Delhi As an Imagined Space of Belonging and Citizenship

86.7 Ragi BASHONGA, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

My Mother Was My First Country: A Micro-Level Exploration of Identity and Xenophobic Sentiment

19:30-20:50

87 RC05 Business Meeting

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

88 Global Islamophobia: Policies and Practices

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Shila KHAYAMBASHI, *York University, Canada* and Shirin KHAYAMBASHI, *Brandon University, Canada*

Chair: Shila KHAYAMBASHI, *York University, Canada*

Co-Chair: Shirin KHAYAMBASHI, *Brandon University, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

88.1 Anilesh KUMAR, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*

Prime Time Hate: A Political Economy Approach to Investigate Communal Narratives on TV Debates in India

88.2 Ali KASSEM, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Islamophobia, Racism, and the Modern Condition: West Asia North Africa, Modern Nation-States, and Anti-Racism

88.3 Berta ALVAREZ-MIRANDA, *Complutense University Madrid, Spain* and Cecilia ESEVERRI, *Complutense University Madrid, Spain*

From Moors to Muslims: Categories, Controversies and Critical Events in Spain

88.4 Shirin KHAYAMBASHI, *Brandon University, Canada*
Violence, Gender, and Religion in Greater Toronto Area and York Region: The Experience of Iranian Muslim Women

10:30-12:20

89 Race, Racism and Anti-Racism in Australia: Knowledge for Action Beyond Epistemological Divisions

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Karen FARQUHARSON, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia* and Karen BLOCK, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Karen FARQUHARSON, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

89.1 Melanie BAAK, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Joel WINDLE, *Federal University of Ouro Preto, Brazil*

Affective Burden and the Performance of Anti-Racist Education from the Margins

89.2 Franka VAUGHAN, *Victoria University, Australia*; Mario PEUCKER, *Victoria University, Australia*; Jo DOLEY, *Victoria University, Australia* and Tom CLARK, *Victoria University, Australia*

Reporting Racism: Empowerment to Speak out or a New Civic Duty for Those Facing Racism?

89.3 Jessie LIU, *Australian National University, Australia*
Thinking through Race & Settler Colonialism with Asian Australian Studies

89.4 Anthony MORAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Australian Rules Football, Discourses of Race and Racism, and Challenges for Anti-Racism

89.5 Julius MOK, *Asia Institute, University of Melbourne, Australia*

Multiculturalism in Refocus: An Institutional Strengthening of Australia's Multicultural Compact

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

89.6 Callum STEWART, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Race, Nation, and Age: Theorising White Settler Futurism

15:30-17:20

JS-40 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part I

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society (Host)*; RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-40.

17:30-19:20

JS-45 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part II

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society (Host)*; RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-45.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-58 Is Nationalism Democratic or Authoritarian?

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-58.

10:30-12:20

90 Navigating the ECR- stage: a panel on negotiating research and publishing in today's academic climate.**Location:** 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia***Chair:** Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia***Co-Chair:** Andrew SPORLE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand***Panelists:** Virginia MAPEDZAHAMA, *Diversity Council Australia, Australia* and Kristine AQUINO, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

- 90.1** Kristine AQUINO, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Navigating the Ecr Stage

15:30-17:20

JS-72 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part III**Committees:** RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host)*; RC25 *Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-72.

17:30-19:20

91 Policing and the Construction of Racialized Groups and Social Control in the Americas**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Natalie BYFIELD, *St. John's University, USA* and Leticia SIMOES GOMES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil***Chair:** Natalie BYFIELD, *St. John's University, USA***Co-Chair:** Leticia SIMOES GOMES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil***Discussants:** Natalie BYFIELD, *St. John's University, USA* and Leticia SIMOES GOMES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

- 91.1** David CUNNINGHAM, *Washington University in St Louis, USA*
Anti-Civil Rights Enforcement Networks: A Cascading Comparative Field-Based Approach to Understanding Racialized Control Systems
- 91.2** Michiru ITO, *Otsuma Women's University, Japan*
Survival of the Privileged White Minority in the Black Majority Caribbean: How Whiteness Is Reinforced and Enforced
- 91.3** David MCCALLUM, *Victoria University, Australia*
Law, Justice and Indigenous Intergenerational Trauma - a History of the Present in Australia

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-84 Citizenship and Inequality**Committees:** RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-84.

10:30-12:20

JS-92 Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations**Committees:** RC31 *Sociology of Migration (Host)*; RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-92.

15:30-17:20

JS-99 Crossing Borders – Shifting Orders? Intersectional Perspectives on the Ukrainian War and the Reorganization or European Border Spaces**Committees:** RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-99.

17:30-19:20

92 Racism, Nationalism and the Impact on Inter-marriage and Mixed Families**Location:** 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Erica CHITO CHILDS, *City University of New York-Hunter College, USA***Chair:** Erica CHITO CHILDS, *City University of New York-Hunter College, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

- 92.1** Francesco CERCHIARO, *KU Leuven, Belgium*
"Marrying the Other" Social Reactions to "Christian-Muslim" Couples in Italy, France and Belgium
- 92.2** Helen FORBES-MEWETT, *Faculty of Arts, Australia*; Dharma ARUNACHALAM, *Monash University, Australia* and Andrew MARKUS, *Monash University, Australia*
Inter-Ethnic Partnering and Integration in Australia: A Qualitative Study
- 92.3** Ayla DENIZ, *Ankara University, Turkey*
Navigating Racial Boundaries with Intersecting Identities: Lived Experiences of Mixed-Race Families in Turkey
- 92.4** Yuna SATO, *University of South Australia, Japan* and Yu-Anis ARUGA, *Tokyo University, Japan*
Choices of Lifestyles and Identity Construction By Multiracial Youth in Japan
- 92.5** Gwendolyn GILLIERON, *LinCS, Université de Strasbourg, Morocco*
Searching for Belonging. How Mixed Individuals Navigate Racism in Morocco and Switzerland.

92.6 Vasily BUBLIKOV, *Independent Scholar, Russian Federation*
The Population of Russia with Dual Russian-Ukrainian Ethnicity Under the Conditions of an Authoritarian, Nationalist Regime in Russia

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

93 African Diaspora Settlement: Opportunities and Challenges

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Farida FOZDAR, *Curtin University, Australia*

Chair: Farida FOZDAR, *Curtin University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

93.1 Rachel AYRTON, *University of Birmingham, United Kingdom*
Searching for Home: Conflict, Deterritorialisation, and National Belonging Among the South Sudanese Diaspora in the UK

93.2 Claire MORAN, *Action Lab, Monash University, Australia*
African Kids Can: Using Social Media to (re)Claim the African Youth Narrative in Australia

93.3 Melissa KELLY, *Toronto Metropolitan University, Canada*
Intersectional Identities: Highly Educated Zimbabweans Negotiate Race, Class, and Ethnic Hierarchies in a South African City

93.4 Byron WILLIAMS, *The University of Waikato, New Zealand*
Understanding Housing Discrimination through African Storytelling: Exploring Experiences of Racism Amongst African Renters in Wellington, New Zealand.

93.5 Gisele ISHIMWE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Unsettling Integration Experiences of African Refugee Youth in Perth, WA.

93.6 Claire MORAN, *Action Lab, Monash University, Australia* and Virginia MAPEDZAHAMA, *Diversity Council Australia, Australia*
Afrocentric Digital Belonging: Theorising the Social Media Practises and Experiences of Black African Young People in Australia

10:30-12:20

JS-124 Indigenous Sociology, Indigenous Lifeworlds

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC20 Comparative Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-124.

15:30-17:20

94 Challenges in Comparative Research between Europe and Colonized Countries

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Cristina GOMES, *FLACSO Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Andrew SPORLE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

94.1 Nikolay ZAKHAROV, *Södertörn University, Sweden*
Futures of Anti-Racism: Comparative Perspectives

94.2 Binu VARGHESE, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*
Decolonization or De-Brahmanization: Revisiting Hindutva As a Decolonial Praxis in India

94.3 Tika GAUTAM, *Tribhuvan University, Nepal* and Hari Prasad ACHARYA, *Tribhuvan University, Nepal*
Ethnicity, Social Transformation and Changing Dalithood in Nepal

94.4 Roluah PUIA, *Indian Insitute of Technology Roorkee, India*
Who(se) Decolonisation and Decolonial Theory: A Reflection from India with Special Reference to Northeast India

94.5 Andrea DE LA HIDALGA, *Universidad Iberoamericana Puebla, Mexico* and Maria Eugenia SANCHEZ DIAZ, *Universidad Iberoamericana Puebla, Mexico*
Whiteness, Racialization and Citizenship in Mexico

17:30-19:20

95 The Normalisation of the Global Far Right: From Global Financial Crisis to Covid Pandemic

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ulrike M VIETEN, *Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom* and Scott POYNTING, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

Chair: Ulrike M VIETEN, *Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom*

Co-Chair: Scott POYNTING, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

95.1 Jennifer SNOOK, *Grinnell College, USA* and Ross HAENFLER, *Grinnell College, USA*
Defending the "Folk": Heathenry and the Micro-Foundations of the Far-Right

95.2 Joshua ROOSE, *Deakin University, Australia*; Pam NILAN, *University of Newcastle, Australia* and Bryan TURNER, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Masculinities, Citizenship and Right-Wing Populism in Australia

95.3 Natalie-Anne HALL, *Loughborough University, United Kingdom*
Taking Back Control: Brexit As a Vehicle for Transnational Far-Right Mainstreaming Online

95.4 Viola DOMBROWSKI, *Universität Koblenz-Landau, Germany*
Modes of Demarcation: Gendered and Sexualized Mechanisms of in- and Exclusion in German Right-Wing Populism

95.5 Nathan MANNING, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia* and Djordje STEFANOVIĆ, *School of Social Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia*
Beyond Angry White Men: Progressive Sociological Imagination As an Alternative to Aggrieved Entitlement

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

JS-139 Racial Capitalisms, Spatial Productions

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-139.

10:30-12:20

96 Racialization, Migration and Covid

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Umut EREL, *PO Box 252, Walton Hall, United Kingdom*

Chair: Rochelle COTE, *Memorial University, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

96.1 Lori WILKINSON, *Migration Futures, Canada*; Jeremy PATZER, *University of Manitoba, Canada* and Kiera LADNER, *University of Manitoba, Canada*
Pandemic-Induced Racism Against Indigenous Peoples, Newcomers and Racialized Persons: Canada, USA and Mexico Compared

96.2 Rebekah JAUNG, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Lynne PARK, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Joohyun Justine PARK, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*; David MAYEDA, *University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Changzuo SONG, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Asian New Zealanders' Experiences of Racism during the COVID-19 Pandemic and Its Association with Life Satisfaction

96.3 Chungse JUNG, *SUNY Cortland, USA*
Ethnonationalism or Asian Panethnicity: Koreans and Korean Americans Responses to Anti-Asian Violence during the COVID-19 Pandemic

96.4 Umut EREL, *PO Box 252, Walton Hall, United Kingdom*; Eirini KAPTANI, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*; Margaret O'NEILL, *University College Cork, Ireland* and Tracey REYNOLDS, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*
Participatory Artsbased Research Online - Addressing Social Isolation with Migrant Women during the Covid19 Pandemic

96.5 Ann KIM, *York University, Canada*
Discrimination during the Covid-19 Pandemic and Future Plans Among International Students from Asia in Canada

96.6 Glenda BALLANTYNE, *Swinburne University, Australia*
The Impact of Covid-19 Related Racism on Asian Australians' Feelings of Belonging

96.7 Mateusz KAROLAK, *University of Wrocław, Poland* and Konul JAFAROVA, *University of Wrocław, Poland*
Being Essential but Foreign. the Lived Experiences and Coping Strategies of Migrants Working in Poland during the COVID-19 Pandemic.

12:30-14:20

97 Exploring the New Configurations of Whiteness

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ipek DEMIR, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom* and Karim MURJI, *University of West London, United Kingdom*

Chair: Ipek DEMIR, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*

Co-Chair: Karim MURJI, *University of West London, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

97.1 Dominika BLACHNICKA-CIACEK, *SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities, Warsaw, Poland* and Irma BUDGINAITE-MACKINE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
The Ambiguous Lives of 'the Other Whites': Class and Racialisation of Eastern European Migrants in the UK

97.2 Morgan CARMELLINI, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*
The Whiteness of São Paulo's Military Police: Thinking Police As a Site of Racial Socialisation

97.3 Macarena BONHOMME, *Universidad Autónoma de Chile, Chile*
Making Whiteness in the Context of South-South Migration in Chile

97.4 Catherine MARTIN, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
White with 'Native' Blood: The Formative Role of Anglo-Indians' in the Colonial Creation of the White Race

97.5 Viola DOMBROWSKI, *Universität Koblenz-Landau, Germany*
Constructing the Collective – Antagonisms and Ambivalences in the Alternative for Germany's Configuration of the People

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

97.6 Jiyoung KIM, *IDHE.S-Nanterre, France*
Gentrifying Otherness: Diversity and Whiteness in the Restaurants of Canal Saint-Martin Neighborhood in Paris

RC06

Family Research

Program Coordinators: Lukasz CZARNECKI, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico* and Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-6 To Grant or Not to Grant? Use and Timing of Media Tools in Families with Teen and Pre-Teen Ager

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-6.

15:30-17:20

JS-9 Navigating Aging, Social Well-Being, and Cultural Expectations Among Migrant and Transnational Families

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC06 Family Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-9.

17:30-19:20

98 Digital Family Practices

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Randi WAERDAHL, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway*

Chair: Randi WAERDAHL, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

98.1 Nora KOTTMANN, *German Institute for Japanese Studies, Tokyo, Japan*
Proximity at Distance? Digital Family Practices through the Lens of Gender and Privilege

98.2 Kaidong GUO, *UCL, United Kingdom*
Home on the Virtual and Physical Space: Negotiating Family Relationships at a Distance in a Triangular Structure

98.3 Monika PALMBERGER, *Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology, Austria*
Digital Media in the Lives of Young Adult Refugees: Taking on New Responsibilities and New Family Roles

98.4 Shiva CHANDRA, *Western Sydney University, Australia* and Benjamin HANCKEL, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Examining Lgbtqia+ Young People's Social Media Practices As 'Doing' Family

98.5 Mellissa GORDON, *University of Delaware, USA* and Christine OHANNESSIAN, *University of Connecticut, USA*
Social Media Use and Early Adolescents' Internalizing Symptoms: The Moderating Role of Family Functioning

98.6 Oxana MIKHAILOVA, *HSE University, Russian Federation* and Elena MAKSYUTA, *HSE University, Russian Federation*
Parenting Practices Representation in Russian-Languaged Podcasts: Scientifically Informed Motherhood and Marginalized Fatherhood

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

99 The Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Family Life: Risks and Opportunities

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ismet KOC, *Hacettepe University, Turkey*

Chair: Ismet KOC, *Hacettepe University, Turkey*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

99.1 Barbara SONZOGNI, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*; Gabriella D'AMBROSIO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy* and Dario GERMANI, *IRCrES (CNR), Italy*
The Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Daily Life: Do Social and Individual Features Affect the Family Atmosphere and the Views on the Future?

99.2 Monica SANTORO, *University of Milan, Italy*
The Effects of Lockdown Covid-19 on Children and Families: The Italian Case

99.3 Anna KUROWSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Agnieszka KASPERSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Gayle KAUFMAN, *Davidson College, USA*
Working from Home and Perception of Change in Work-Life Balance Among Parents with Dependent Children in Six Countries during the Covid-19 Pandemic

99.4 Dahye KIM, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*; Bussarawan TEERAWICHITCHAINAN, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Christine HO, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Transition of Social Support and Income Security Among Older Adults during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Implications for Childlessness and Social Integration

99.5 Ruby LAI, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*
Intersectional Marginalization and Family Strategies: Family Lives in Cubicle Homes Under Covid-19

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

99.6 Excellent EJIOGU, *Department of Sociology and Anthropology University of Uyo, Nigeria*; Dorothy ONONOKPONO, *Department of Sociology and Anthropology University of Uyo, Nigeria* and Justina A. OGODO, *Curriculum & Instruction/Science Education Baylor University, Waco, TX, USA*
The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Family Life in Asaba, Southern Nigeria

99.7 Ilyar HEYDARI BARARDEHI, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Anna KUROWSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Dual-Earner Parents' Synchronized Working Arrangement during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Recurrent Event Analysis

99.8 Surbhi DAYAL, *Indian Institute of Management Indore, India*
Household Division of Labour: A Case Study from India

99.9 Marc GRAU I GRAU, *Sobreatic, Spain* and Montserrat GAS AIXENDRI, *Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Spain*
Understanding Family Resilience during COVID-19: The Role of Spirituality and Religiosity

99.10 Catherine BERHEIDE, *Skidmore College, USA*; Megan CARPENTER, *St. Lawrence University, USA* and David COTTER, *Union College, USA*

Being a Parent, Scholar, and Parent-Teacher: The Relationship of Gender and Parenthood to the Division of Labor and Work-Life Balance Among Academic Staff in the United States during the COVID-19 Pandemic

10:30-12:20

100 Childbearing Intentions and Behaviors in Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Yu-Hua CHEN, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*

Chair: Pei-Chun KO, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

100.1 Anna KUROWSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Beata OSIEWALSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Working from Home and Change in Fertility Intentions during Covid-19 Pandemic in Two Contrasting Gender Cultures: The Comparison of Sweden and Poland

100.2 Svetlana SIVOPLYASOVA, *Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Russian Federation* and Evgenia SIGAREVA, *Institute for Demographic Research – Branch of the Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences (IDR FCTAS RAS), Russian Federation*

The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Reproductive Behavior of the Russian Population: Statistical and Sociological Analysis

100.3 Chi CHIAO, *National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University, Taiwan* and Yu-Hua CHEN, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
COVID-19 Pandemic, Neighborhood Characteristics and Pregnancy Intention Among Married Women in India

100.4 Kayo SAWADA, *Nara Women's University, Japan*
Low Fertility and the Caring Fathers: The Case of Japan

100.5 Weiyi HU, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Confessions of the 'leftover Women': An Analysis of Family Life in Contemporary China

15:30-17:20

101 Balancing Work and Family: Gender Roles and Caregiving

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

101.1 Manuela NALDINI, *University of Turin, Italy* and Arianna SANTERO, *University of Turin, Italy*
Money, Love and (co)Parenting. Post-Separation Parents' Negotiations about Economic and Care Responsibilities Towards the Children

101.2 Xiaowan CANG, *University of Oxford, China*
How Do Middle-Class Women See Ideal Motherhood in Three-Child China?

101.3 Celia BOUCHET, *Sciences Po (CRIS-LIEPP), France*
Disability As a Status Revealer and Material Mitigator of the Gender Division of Labor: Insights from a Mixed Methods Study in France

101.4 Juliane ACHATZ, *IAB Institute for Employment Research, Germany*; Brigitte SCHELS, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany* and Cordula ZABEL, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany*

Integrated into Working Life, but Stressed. Effects of Subsidized Employment for Long-Term Unemployed Men and Women Under Consideration of Unpaid Work at Home

101.5 Sheree GREGORY, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Rethinking the Role of Gender, Care and Work: A Case Study of Screen Industry Directors, Gender Equality Policy and Pathways Toward Change

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

101.6 Yulin YANG, *Renmin University of China, China*
Education As Bargaining Power or Egalitarian Gender Ideology? Educational Assortative Mating and the Division of Housework within Married Couples in China

101.7 Jayeeta BASU, *Maharani Kasiswari College, India*
Competent Women Lawyers of Eastern India Juggling between the Maternal Wall and Breaking the GLASS Ceiling: A Sociological Study

101.9 Izabela SLEZAK, *University of Lodz, Poland*
"It's Complicated": Sex Work and Relations in the Family of Origin

101.10 Pragati DUBEY, *IIT BOMBAY MONASH RESEARCH ACADEMY, India*; Dharma ARUNACHALAM, *Monash University, Australia* and D. PARTHASARATHY, *Indian Institute of Technology, India*
Gender and Child Malnutrition in Rural West Bengal (India): A Qualitative Analysis

17:30-19:20

102 Gender, Family, and Work. Part I

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA*

Chair: Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

102.1 Pedro ROMERO-BALSAS, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain*; Gerardo MEIL, *universidad autónoma de madrid, Spain* and Jesus ROGERO-GARCIA, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain*
Parental Leave's Use By Latin-American Fathers in Spain

102.2 Daisuke ITO, *Center for Sustainable Development Studies, Toyo University, Japan*; Chino YABUNAGA, *Toyo University, Japan*; Akie YADA, *Center for Sustainable Development Studies, Toyo University, Japan* and Hiroya TAKAMATSU, *Musashino University, Japan*
Wives As Teachers and Husbands As Students: Japanese Couples' Transitions to Parenthood

102.3 Steven ROBERTS, *Monash University, Australia*; Karla ELLIOTT, *Monash University, Australia* and Riikka PRATTES, *Monash University, Australia*
Exploring the Drivers and Impacts of Men's Participation in Front Line, 'low Level', Paid Care Work: Insights from Australia

102.4 Junko NISHIMURA, *Ochanomizu University, Japan*
Women's Time in Domestic Work over the Life Course: Evidence from Women Born in the Late 1960s through Early 1980s

102.5 Chia-Ling YANG, *National Kaohsiung Normal University, Taiwan*
Bordercrossing Grandparenting and Work-Family Balance in Taiwanese Migrant Families

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

102.6 Petteri EEROLA, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland*; Armi MUSTOSMÄKI, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland* and Henna PIRSKANEN, *University of Lapland, Finland*
The Parental Night Shift: Gendered Inequalities in Night-Time Care in the Accounts of Finnish Parents.

102.7 Chisato ATOBE, *Rikkyo university, Japan* and Mai IGARASHI, *University of Niigata Prefecture, Japan*
Gender Studies Pertaining to Work-Family Balance Among HIV-Positive Gay Men in Japan

102.8 Yifei HUANG, *Peking University, China*
Division of Household Labor and Married Couple's Subjective Well-Being in China

19:30-20:50

103 Gender, Family, and Work. Part II

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA*

Chair: Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

103.1 Montserrat SIMO-SOLSONA, *University of Barcelona (Gran Via Corts Catalanes, 585, 08007 Barcelona), Spain*; Andres COCO-PRIETO, *University of Barcelona, Spain*; Teresa BARTUAL FIGUERAS, *University of Barcelona, Spain* and Joaquin TURMO GARUZ, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Labour Participation of Same-Sex Couples: An Empirical Study from the Spanish Labour Force Survey (EPA)

103.2 Anne LAMBERT, *French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED), France*; Mariona SEGÚ, *French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED), France* and Chhavi TIWARI, *French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED), France*
Becoming Parent: The Impact of Nonstandard Work Schedules on Childbearing in France

103.3 Shu-Yung WANG, *Chung Cheng University, Taiwan* and You-syue LIOU, *National Chung-Cheng University, Taiwan*
Why the Gendered Gap between Entitlement and Usage in Parental Leave?

103.4 Hachiro IWAI, *Kyoto University, Japan*
Long-Term Transformation of Women's Life Course in Japan: Findings of Quantitative Sociological Research

103.5 Aida VILLANUEVA, *University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA*
Mothers' Employment in Times of COVID-19: Assessing the Impact of Employment History in a High Mortality Context

103.6 Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA*
Couples' Gender Ideology, Work Hours, and Marital Quality

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

103.7 Gerlinde MAUERER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Social Inequalities in Claiming Parental Leave and Childcare Benefits. Empirical Evidence from Austria.

103.8 Alberto DEL REY, *University of Salamanca, Spain*; Jesus GARCIA-GOMEZ, *University of Salamanca, Spain* and Guillermo ORFAO, *University of Salamanca, Spain*
Work-Family Balance in a Gender Perspective. an Analysis of the Transition to Motherhood / Fatherhood By Employment Status in a Country with Very Low and Late Fertility (Spain).

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

104 Caring Fathers in the Global Context. Part I

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Petteri EEROLA, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland*; Henna PIRSKANEN, *University of Lapland, Finland*; Pedro ROMERO-BALSAS, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain* and Katherine TWAMLEY, *University College London, United Kingdom*

Chair: Pedro ROMERO-BALSAS, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

104.1 Amy RAUB, *WORLD Policy Analysis Center, University of California Los Angeles, USA*
Mapping Barriers and Supports for Caring Fatherhood: An Analysis of Laws in 193 Countries

104.2 Ekaterina IVANOVA, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Caring after Separation: Russian Fathers Doing Shared Parenting

104.3 Lucille NGAN, *Hang Seng University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Anita Kit-wa CHAN, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Gender Equality or Just More Involved Fathering? a Critical Examination of the Division of Childcare in Hong Kong's Professional Middle-Class Families

104.4 Youngcho LEE, *London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE), United Kingdom*
It Takes a Village to Raise a Child Free from Gender Stereotypes: A Qualitative Study of Leave-Taking Fathers' Gendered Parenting Experiences in South Korea

104.5 Mengyao WU, *University of Salamanca, Spain*
Reconstruction of Fatherhood in a Strange Land: Exploring Fathering Practices of Chinese Migrants in Spain

104.6 Casey SCHEIBLING, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Jillian SUNDERLAND, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Compromising Care or Masculinity? How Canadian Fathers Negotiate Competing Gender Expectations for Work and Family

104.7 Nazeema ISAACS, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
Men and Care Work: Insights from Co-Resident Fathers in Dual Income Households in the Western Cape

10:30-12:20

105 Caring Fathers in the Global Context. Part II**Location:** 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Petteri EEROLA, *University of Tampere, Finland*; Henna PIRSKANEN, *University of Lapland, Finland*; Pedro ROMERO-BALSAS, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain* and Katherine TWAMLEY, *University College London, United Kingdom***Chair:** Petteri EEROLA, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland***Co-Chair:** Henna PIRSKANEN, *University of Lapland, Finland***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****105.1** Imad ALATAS, *University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, USA***"I Get to See My Kids Grow up": The Lived Experiences of Muslim Househusbands in Malaysia.****105.2** Justine VAN DE BEEK, *Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management, Netherlands*; Femke HILVERDA, *Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management, Netherlands*; Violet PETIT-STEEGHS, *Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management, Netherlands* and Anna Petra NIEBOER, *Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management, Netherlands*
Vulnerability and Resilience in Young Men Who Unintentionally Become Fathers**105.3** Tebogo LOBAKA, *Social Development, South Africa*
Non-Resident Not Absent: The Caregiving Role Non-Resident Fathers Play in Raising Their Children**105.4** Ashlee BORGKVIST, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Marc GRAU I GRAU, *Sobreactic, Spain*
Complicit Masculinity: A Theoretical Framework of Fathers "in between" in the Organizations**105.5** Roger PATULNY, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
Who Are Fathers Caring for Emotionally? Results from an Australian Survey of Interpersonal Emotion Management**105.6** Katarzyna WOJNICKA, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*
Protective Masculinity: Theorizing "Masculine Care"**106 Gender, Family, and Work. Part III****Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Deniz YUCEL, *William Paterson University of New Jersey, USA***Chair:** Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia***ROUNDTABLES:****Roundtable A****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****106.1** Kathryn MCGARRY, *Maynooth University, Ireland* and Irma KONDRATAITE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Resisting Silence and Stigma: Mothering and Sex Work**106.2** Yoko MAKI, *Sophia University, Japan*
The Price of Care: A Reflection on Work in Childcare and Elderly Care in France**106.3** Eva BERMÚDEZ-FIGUEROA, *Universidad de Cádiz, Spain*
Re-Organizing Care and Work: Spanish Skilled Migrant Families in Europe**106.4** Ben SCULLY, *University of Witwatersrand, South Africa*; Akua BRITWUM, *University of Cape Coast, Ghana* and Abigail APPIAH, *University of the Cape Coast, Ghana*
Social Reproduction Theory and the Informal Economy: Informal Women Workers and Childcare in Ghana**106.5** Kazuko SANO, *Osaka University of Commerce, Japan*
Japanese Mothers' Careers in Transition: Who Choose to Work and Why?**Roundtable B****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****106.6** Gabriel CALUZZI, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Maree PATSOURAS, *Centre for Alcohol Policy Research, La Trobe University, Australia*; Cassandra WRIGHT, *Menzies School of Health Research, Australia*; Emmanuel KUNTSCHE, *Centre for Alcohol Policy Research, La Trobe University, Australia* and Sandra KUNTSCHE, *Centre for Alcohol Policy Research, La Trobe University, Australia*
Beyond "Wine Mums": Better Understanding the Structural and Social Factors Shaping Drinking Practices Among Working Mothers**106.7** Elizabeth COOK, *City, University of London, United Kingdom* and Rachel CONDRY, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*
Neoliberal Responsibilization and the Family: State Regulation of Families of Those Subject to Criminal Justice in the UK**106.8** Karina PINHAO, *Center for Social Studies, Brazil*
Denied Motherhood: The Struggle of Guarani-Kaiowá Mothers for Future Generations of the Guarani-Kaiowá**106.9** Zhilan FANG, *Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Gabriel LIU, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom* and Liling ZHU, *Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Doing Gendered "Exit": Work, Care and the Moral Practices of Disabled Identities**106.10** Dorinda 'T HART, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
Gendered Expectations of Motherhood in Abortion Narratives**106.11** Egle SUMSKIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*; Violeta GEVORGIANIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania* and Ciara BRADLEY, *Maynooth University, Ireland*
A Glimpse into the Invisible Life of Working Mothers with Disabilities**Roundtable C****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****106.12** Shuang QIU, *Keele University, United Kingdom*
Gender and Family Practices: Living Apart Together Relationships in China**106.13** Naa Adjeley ALAKIJA SEKYI, *University of Cape Coast, Ghana*
The Dilemma of Existing Marital Relationships in Ghana: Experiences and Perspectives of Abused Women in the CAPE COAST Metropolis**106.14** Mega Ayu Rahma MD, *Wajo District - Statistics Indonesia, Indonesia* and Titik HARSANTI, *Politeknik Statistika STIS, Indonesia*
The Problem of Unmet Need for Family Planning in Eastern Indonesia: The Importance of Husband's Role

106.15 Priyanka MITTAL, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India*
Outside Paid Work and Women's Intra Household Agency: Insights from Case Studies of Upper Class Elite Women in Delhi

106.16 Lingxi CHEN, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Gender Policy Mismatch: Why Do Women Not Using Facilities Designed to Help Them Balance Mothering and Work?

106.17 Nicole DE WET, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*
Adolescent Mothers and Their Children in South Africa: What Are the Socioeconomic Determinants of Living Arrangements?

Roundtable D

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

106.18 Maila MERTENS, *University of Zurich, Switzerland*; Larissa FRITSCH, *University of Zurich, Switzerland* and Joerg ROESSEL, *University of Zurich, Switzerland*
New Reproduction Technologies, Gender, and Careers

106.19 Valeria INSARAUTO, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland* and Danilo BOLANO, *Bocconi University, Italy*
A Matter of (In)Congruence: Attitudes Toward Women's Voluntary Childlessness and Their Relation to Occupational Sex Segregation

106.20 Saori MIYASHITA, *Nagoya City University, Japan*
Gendered Formalization through Social Security and Tax Inclusion: The Case of Women Family Workers in Japan

106.21 Anna BAGIROVA, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation*; Natalia BLEDNOVA, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation* and Aleksandr NESHATAEV, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation*
Family Design of Parental Leave in Russia: From Actual to Desirable

106.22 Jennifer AYTON, *College of Health and Medicine, University of Tasmania, Australia*; Sue PEARSON, *College of Health and Medicine, University of Tasmania, Australia*; Alison GRAHAM, *Tasmanian Department of Health, Tasmania, Australia*; Gemma KITSOS, *College of Health and Medicine, University of Tasmania, Australia* and Emily HANSEN, *College of Arts, Law and Education, University of Tasmania, Australia*
Clandestine Labour: Australian Parents' Accounts of Returning to Work and Breastfeeding

15:30-17:20

107 Linked Lives: Intergenerational Relationships and Wellbeing

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Pei-Chun KO, *Monash University, Australia*; Zheng MU, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Shu HU, *Singapore University of Social Sciences, Singapore*

Chair: Shu HU, *Singapore University of Social Sciences, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

107.1 Anis BEN BRIK, *Hamad Bin Khalifa University College of Public Policy, Qatar*; Natalie WILLIAMS, *Institute for Rehabilitation Science and Engineering, USA* and Sarah SARAH BARKER LADD, *College of Education and Human Sciences, University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*

Family Satisfaction, Relationship Satisfaction, and Beliefs about Resilience: Understanding Parent Stress in the COVID19 Pandemic Using the Double ABCX Model

107.2 Pei-Chun KO, *Monash University, Australia*; Shu HU, *Singapore University of Social Sciences, Singapore* and Zheng MU, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Linked Lives: Effects of Assortative Mating By Hukou and Education on Older Parents' Subjective Wellbeing in China

107.3 Karen OKIGBO, *University of Chicago, USA*
The Immigrant Bargain in Marital Decision Making Among Nigerian Immigrants in the United States

107.5 Andreja ZIVODER, *Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia*; Alenka SVAB, *Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia* and Janja VUGA BERSNAK, *Faculty of Social Sciences University of Ljubljana, Slovenia*
Growing up in Military Families: Coping with Prolonged and Repeated Parental Absence

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

107.6 Takeshi HAMANO, *University of Kitakyushu, Japan*
Does Divorce Deprive Fathers from Caring after Their Child? Shared Parenting of Separated Family and Fatherhood in Contemporary Japan

107.7 Izabela JANSSEN-WNOROWSKA, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Seemingly Perfect Circumstances for Caring Fathers: Austrian Parental Leave System Showing What Is Missing in Caring Masculinities

107.8 Radoslaw KOSSAKOWSKI, *University of Gdansk, Poland*; Magdalena ZADKOWSKA, *University of Gdansk, Poland*; Sophie DAVID-GORETTA, *Université de Paris, France* and Natasza KOSAKOWSKA-BEREZECKA, *University of Gdansk, Poland*
Struggling with Limitations, Creating New Possibilities – the Identity of Men in the Empty Nest Stage

17:30-19:20

108 Generational Relations in Times of Intersecting Crises

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Susan MCDANIEL, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Chair: Susan MCDANIEL, *University of Victoria, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

108.1 Xiaorong GU, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*; Doris BUEHLER-NIEDERBERGER, *University of Wuppertal, Germany*; Jessica SCHWITTEK, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany* and Elena KIM, *American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan*
The Young Generation As Blessing, Bridge, and Burden Bearer: Intergenerational Relations amidst Social Challenges-- Lessons from Asia

108.2 Paula PUSTULKA, *SWPS University, Poland*; Justyna SARNOWSKA, *SWPS University, Poland* and Agnieszka KWIATKOWSKA, *Uniwersytet SWPS, Poland*
An Intergenerational Perspective on Transitions-to-Adulthood in a Polycrisis Era

108.3 Charlotte BECKER, *University of Cologne, Germany*
Attitudes Toward Immigrants in the Family Context

108.4 Gülçin CON WRIGHT, *TED University, Turkey*; Asya FILIZ, *TED University, Turkey* and Selenay KAŞKAYA, *TED University, Turkey*
Within-Family Differences in Downward Support Flows to Adult Children in Turkey during COVID-19 Pandemic and Economic Crisis

108.5 Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Instituto Campechano, Mexico* and Luis Fernando GÓNGORA CARLO, *Instituto Campechano, Mexico*
Life Satisfaction of Indigenous Groups in Mexico. the Case of Mayan Speaking Families in Campeche.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

109 Flight from Marriage and Parenthood in Asia

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Lake LUI, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*; Zheng MU, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Adam CHEUNG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*

Chair: Adam CHEUNG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

109.1 Lake LUI, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan* and Zheng MU, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Are Children Still Important for Asian Families? a Comparative Study of the Lowest-Low Fertility Societies

109.2 Minhye KIM, *Changwon National University, Republic of Korea* and Dong-Kyun IM, *Department of Sociology, Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Attitudes Towards Children and Subjective Well-Being: A Comparison between East and Southeast Asia

109.3 Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA*
Modernization, Filial Piety, and the Decreasing Appeal of Marriage and Parenthood in China

109.4 Chia-Ling WU, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
Singlehood, Egg Economy and Stratified Reproduction

109.5 Meera CHOI, *Yale University, USA*
Gender Ideology and Changes in Desires for Heterosexual Love: A Study on Cultural Narratives of Young Women Opting out of Sex, Dating, Marriage, and Childbearing in South Korea

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

109.6 Naoki IGUCHI, *Mejiro University, Japan*
What Factors Decrease Satisfaction with Romantic Relationships: Focusing on Mismatch Related to Gender Roles in Japan

10:30-12:20

JS-91 Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part I

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC28 Social Stratification

See Joint Session Details for JS-91.

15:30-17:20

JS-100 Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part II

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC28 Social Stratification

See Joint Session Details for JS-100.

17:30-19:20

110 RC06 Business Meeting

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

111 International Comparative Perspectives on Family Goals and Values

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Wei-Jun Jean YEUNG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Wei-Jun Jean YEUNG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Discussant: Zheng MU, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

111.1 Souleymane SANOGO, *University of Geneva, Switzerland*; Clémentine ROSSIER, *University of Geneva, Switzerland* and Marlène SAPIN, *FORS Lausanne, Switzerland*
Family Solidarity Norms and the Salience of Family Relationships for Individual Social Support in a Comparative Perspective

111.2 Arnstein AASSVE, *Bocconi University, Italy*; Samuel PLACH, *Bocconi University, Italy*; Chen PENG, *Bocconi University, Italy*; Alicia ADSERÀ, *Princeton University, USA*; Letizia MENCARINI, *Bocconi University, Italy*; James RAYMO, *Princeton University, USA* and Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*
Family Ideals across Cultures

111.3 Pooja PAUL, *Umea University, Sweden*
Gender Equality As Attitude or Context: What Matters for Fertility?

111.4 Vaida TRETJAKOVA, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania* and Daumantas STUMBRYŠ, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*
Societal Attitudes Towards Male Childlessness in Europe

111.6 Raisa AKIFEVA, *The University of Western Australia, Australia*
Child-Rearing Styles, Practices, and Values of Russian-Speaking Migrants in Spain and Australia: National Habitus and "Parenting Paradox"

10:30-12:20

112 Marriage Equality Around the World**Location:** 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Gayle KAUFMAN, *Davidson College, USA* and D’Lane COMPTON, *University of New Orleans, USA***Chair:** Gayle KAUFMAN, *Davidson College, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

112.1 Susanne CHOI, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Relationships without a Future: Gay and Lesbian Intimacies in China

112.2 Hiroyuki KUBOTA, *Nihon University, Japan*
“Friendship Marriage” between Non-Heterosexuals: Circumventing Amatonormativity in Marriage in Japan.

112.3 Saori KAMANO, *National Institute of Population and Social Security Research, Japan*; Diana KHOR, *Hosei University, Japan* and Yusuke KAMIYA, *Chuo University, Japan*
Who Are More Equal? a Comparison of Legally Married Heterosexual Couples, Cohabiting Heterosexual Couples, and Cohabiting Same-Gender Couples in Japan

112.4 Riva ZIV, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
Role Division in Same-Sex Couples

15:30-17:20

113 Single-Parent Families and Institutions in the Global South and North**Location:** 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Morena TARTARI, *University of Padua, Italy***Chair:** Gayle KAUFMAN, *Davidson College, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

113.1 Katarzyna WOJNICKA, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*
From Fathers’ Rights Movement to Single Parents’ Advocacy: The Case of the Platform for European Fathers

113.2 Karabo MOHAPANELE, *Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC), South Africa*
The Impact of the Socio-Economic Status of Female Single Parent Families on Street Children Phenomenon

113.3 Vanessa CARREIRA, *Universidade de Évora, Portugal* and Rosalina COSTA, *Universidade de Évora & CICS.NOVA. UÉvora Universidade Nova de Lisboa - NOVA FCSH Av. de Berna 26-C 1069-061 Lisboa, Portugal*
Lonely Parents, Lonely Children? a Sociological Look at the Perspectives of Young Adults Socialized in Single-Parent Families

113.4 Lovemore NDLOVU, *United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Zimbabwe*
Role of Sociological Theory in Deconstructing Sociological Phenomena in Africa – the Social Exchange Theory and the Small House in Zimbabwe

113.5 Deepali DATTA, *Department of Sociology, Delhi School of Economics, University of Delhi, India*
Understanding Families of Choice and Practices of Kinning through Adoptive Families in India

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

113.6 Lina SUMSKAITE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Family without Children? Women’s Perspectives in a Qualitative Study in Lithuania

17:30-19:20

114 New Tales of the Golden Family. Actors, Narratives and Contestation across Resurgent Authoritarianism**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Rosalina COSTA, *Universidade de Évora & CICS.NOVA.UÉvora Universidade Nova de Lisboa - NOVA FCSH Av. de Berna 26-C 1069-061 Lisboa, Portugal***Chair:** Rosalina COSTA, *Universidade de Évora & CICS.NOVA. UÉvora Universidade Nova de Lisboa - NOVA FCSH Av. de Berna 26-C 1069-061 Lisboa, Portugal***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

114.1 Sheyla MORONI, *Università degli Studi di Firenze, Italy* and Erika CELLINI, *University of Florence, Italy, Italy*
Modern Family Through the Eyes of Giorgia Meloni and Those of Pope Francis

114.2 Paulo ISENBERG LIMA, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
Differences in Environmental Attitudes: Generational Conflict or Culture War?

114.3 Esther SEROK, *Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel*
Perspectives of Family Authoritarianism in a Post Covid-19 Era Causing Entanglement of Family Governance and Challenges of Virtual Learning. Can Diverse Families Function As Their Children’s Educators in a Virtual Learning Reality?

114.4 Nicola CARROLL, *University of York, United Kingdom*; Katherine TWAMLEY, *University College London, United Kingdom* and Charlotte FAIRCLOTH, *University College London, United Kingdom*
‘Familiation of Risk’ and Intensification of Inequalities during COVID-19

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

114.5 Empar AGUADO, *Universitat de València, Spain*
RE-Conciliation and Teleworking: OPEN Dilemmas in Times of Pandemic

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

115 Work-Family Interface and Parental and Child Wellbeing in Challenging Times**Location:** 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Jianghong LI, *WZB Berlin Social Science Center, Germany* and Wen-Jui HAN, *New York University, USA***Chair:** Wen-Jui HAN, *New York University, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

115.1 Jianghong LI, *WZB Berlin Social Science Center, Germany*; Chia LIU, *University of St. Andrews, United Kingdom* and Till KAISER, *Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany*
Maternal Non-Standard Work Schedules and Children’s Socio-Emotional Development: Evidence from the UK

115.2 Anne LAMBERT, *French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED), France* and Chhavi TIWARI, *French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED), France*
Mental Health Among Nonstandard Schedule Employees: The Gendered Role of Family and Work Resources

115.3 Inga LASS, *Federal Institute for Population Research, Germany*; Esperanza VERA-TOSCANO, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Mark WOODEN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Working from Home, COVID-19 and Job Satisfaction Among Parents: Evidence from Australian Panel Data

115.4 Ingela NAUMANN, *The University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom*; Eloi RIBE, *University of St Andrews, United Kingdom* and Joanna SAKALI, *University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom*
Care, Work and Family Wellbeing in Times of Crisis: COVID-Lessons on Access Inequalities to Childcare for Families in Britain.

115.5 Viorela ducu CSETRI, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania*; Mihaela HARAGUS, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania* and Aron TELEGDİ-CSETRI, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania*
Ukrainian and Moldovan Transnational Families' Registers of Co-Presence in Relation to Work

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

115.6 Peiwei GU, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
The Anxious Middle-Class Parents? the Role of Parental Style and Children's Academic Performance on Chinese Parents' Mental Health

115.7 Dinithi Padmasiri MAMPE KANKANAMALAGE, *University of New South Wales Canberra, Australia*
Work-Family Conflict (WFC) and Working From Home (WFH) during the COVID-19 pandemic: Information Technology (IT) managers in the Sri Lankan IT industry

115.8 Mariko TATSUMI, *Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*
Can Caring Masculinities Achieve to the Gender Equality? : Child-Caring of Japanese Fathers and Masculinities of Ikumen

10:30-12:20

116 Politics, Family, and Familial Relationships

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Veronica GREGORIO, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*; Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA* and Clarence BATAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*

Chair: Veronica GREGORIO, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Co-chairs: Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA* and Clarence BATAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

116.1 Louie Benedict IGNACIO, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*; Mark David DERAYUNAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*; Paola mari JAMOLA, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines* and Quinito GONZALES, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*
Uncovering the Dark Side: Social Capital and Political Beliefs in Filipino Families

116.2 Ruby LAI, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*
Deliberative Harmony?: Negotiating Family Conflicts during High-Risk Social Movements

116.3 Felix ROSSMEISSL, *Institute for Social Research Frankfurt, Germany*
'Doing Family' in Western Jihadist Subculture and Its Effects on Radical Careers

116.4 Owen ABBOTT, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*
Forgiveness and Reconciliation in Families after Political Conflict

116.5 Maximiliano MARENTES, *Universidad Nacional de San Martín (UNSAM), Argentina*
A Multi-Families Album: Politics of Visibility of an Argentinean LGBTQ+ Family Association

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

116.6 Adam CHEUNG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
How Does within-Couple Political Disagreements Affect Marital Quality in Time of Political Polarization? Evidence from Hong Kong

116.7 Adam CARTER, *The University of Sheffield, United Kingdom* and Katherine DAVIES, *The University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
Living through Brexit: Families, Relationships and Everyday Life in 'Brexit Britain'

12:30-14:20

117 The 'empty Nest' in Times of Change: An International Comparative Perspective on Family Recompositions and Adult Children and Parents' Relationships

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Magdalena ZADKOWSKA, *University of Gdansk, Poland*; Marta SKOWRONSKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*; Christophe GIRAUD, *Université Paris Cité, Faculty of Social Sciences, CERLIS, France* and Rita GOUVEIA, *University of Lisbon, Portugal*

Chair: Marta SKOWRONSKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

117.1 Julia SAUTER, *NOVA - OsloMet, Norway*
Is Blood Thicker Than Water? Family Values in Step- and Biological Families at the Empty-Nest Stage in Norway

117.2 Yusuke HAYASHI, *Musashi University, Japan* and Misaki MATANO, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
Influence of Children's Leaving Home on Parental Attitudes: The Case of Japan

117.3 Justyna KAJTA, *SWPS University, Poland* and Paula PUSTULKA, *SWPS University, Poland*
Between Nesting and Autonomy: Young People and Housing Transitions during Social Crises

117.4 Emmanuelle MAUNAYE, *Université Rennes1, France*; Virginie MUNIGLIA, *EHESP. Département SHS / Arènes, France*; Emilie POTIN, *Université Rennes 2 / LIRIS, France* and Céline ROTHE, *EHESP, France*
Back in the Nest: How Family Reconciliation Questions Forms of Child Support and Family Solidarity

117.5 Sandra GAVIRIA, *Université Le Havre Normandie, France*
Returning to the Nest in a Time of Pandemic

117.6 Magdalena ZADKOWSKA, *University of Gdansk, Poland*
**Family Mission Accomplished? Couple in Empty Nest and
Recomposition of Gender Roles.**

14:30-16:20

**118 Parenting and Child and Adolescent
Socioemotional Development in Chinese
Families**

Location: 220 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Yan XIA, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln,
USA*

Chair: Yan XIA, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*

Panelists: Dan WANG, *The University of Oklahoma, USA*;
Yunqi WANG, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*; Weiman XU,
University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA; Zhenqiao YANG, *University of
Nebraska-Lincoln, USA* and Zheng WANG, *Henan University, China*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

118.1 Zhenqiao YANG, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*
and Weiman XU, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*
**Understanding Parenting Identity Construction in Chinese
Parents: A Narrative Study**

118.2 Zheng WANG, *Henan University, China* and Yingying
HUANG, *Baiyuni school, Shangqiu, Henan province, China*
**Investigation on 3-6 YEARS Old Children'S Autonomy of
RURAL Area MULTI-Children Families — Based on an XX
Area of Henan Province, P.R.China**

118.3 Dan WANG, *The University of Oklahoma, USA* and
Yunqi WANG, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*
**The Associations between Individual Characteristics,
Family, School, and Familism and Chinese Adolescent Social
Initiative**

118.4 Jin JIANG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong* and
Chunni ZHANG, *Peking University, China*
**Trajectories of Leaving the Parental Home: Traditional
Values, Individualistic Attitudes, and Youth Transitions of
Chinese Young People**

118.5 Yunqi WANG, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA* and
Dan WANG, *The University of Oklahoma, USA*
**Adolescents' Family Relationship Dynamics and Their
Internet Use in China: A National Sample**

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

118.6 Weiman XU, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA* and
Zhenqiao YANG, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*
**Home Environment and Children's Academic Performance
across Time: The Mediator Role of Children's
Conscientiousness**

118.7 Tran MINH THI, *Vietnam Journal of Family and Gender
Studies, Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Vietnam*
**Changes in Marriage Patterns in East and Southeast Asia in
Recent Two Decades**

RC07

Futures Research

Program Coordinator: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC24 *Environment and Society* RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements* and RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-3.

15:30-17:20

119 Constructing Future 'New Normals' after Pandemics and Other Crises

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Julia ROZANOVA, *Yale University, USA*

Chair: Julia ROZANOVA, *Yale University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

119.1 Branko ANCIC, *Institute for Social Research in Zagreb, Croatia*; Mladen DOMAZET, *Institute for Political Ecology, Croatia*; Jelena PUĐAK, *Institute for Social Sciences Ivo Pilar, Croatia* and Tomislav CIK, *Institute for Social Research in Zagreb, Croatia*

Collapses Ahead of Us, Pandemics Ahead of Us – Exploring Resilience of Societies and Health Regimes Performance

119.2 Iryna ZAVIRIUKHA, *European Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Tetiana KIRIAZOVA, *Ukrainian Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Oleksandr ZEZIULIN, *Ukrainian Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Sheela SHENOI, *Yale School of Medicine, USA* and Julia ROZANOVA, *Yale University, USA*

The Willingness of Older People with HIV to Live and Clinicians to Work When a "Normal Life" Is Stopped.

119.3 Iryna ZAVIRIUKHA, *European Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Tetiana KIRIAZOVA, *Ukrainian Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Oleksandr ZEZIULIN, *Ukrainian Institute of Public Health Policy, Ukraine*; Sheela SHENOI, *Yale School of Medicine, USA*; Komal GULATI, *Lewis Katz School of Medicine at Temple University, USA* and Julia ROZANOVA, *Yale University, USA*

How Covid-19 Pandemic Has Tempered Ukrainians to Effectively Conduct Sociological Health Research in the Context of War and Any Future Crises

119.4 Natalya SHUMSKAYA, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan*; Ainura KURMANALIEVA, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan*; Ainurayim OPOBEKOVA, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan*; Margarita SABIROVA, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan*; Evgeni YULDASHEV, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan* and Yuri MALYSHEV, *AIDS Foundation East-West Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan*

Resilient Future Options Following Covid-19 Pandemic Among at-Risk Prisoners with Injection Drug Use History: Insights from Kyrgyzstan

17:30-19:20

JS-16 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part I

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* and RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-16.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-23 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part II

Committees: RC07 *Futures Research (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-23.

10:30-12:20

120 RC07 Business Meeting

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

15:30-17:20

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I

Committees: RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC10 *Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management* RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology* and TG10 *Digital Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-39.

17:30-19:20

121 Futures Research: Open Themes Part III

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa*

Chair: Emil Albert SOBOTTKA, *Rua Prof. Fitzgerald 192, Brazil*

Panelist: Emil Albert SOBOTTKA, *Rua Prof. Fitzgerald 192, Brazil*

ROUNDTABLES:

Roundtable A

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

121.1 Peter ROGERS, *Macquarie University, Australia*
New Concepts of Liberty

Roundtable B

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

121.2 Theang TERON, *PhD, Norway*
The Phenomenon of New Karbi Politico-Religious Reformation Movements: Interventions, Associations and Continuity

121.3 Ke-hsien HUANG, *National Taiwan University, Sociology Department, Taiwan*
Transnational Religion and Limited Party-Statehood: Reexamining the State-Church Relationship of the Presbyterian Church through Surveillance Documents

121.4 Nikolay ZAKHAROV, *Södertörn University, Sweden*
Religion in Authoritarian Belarus: Protest Mobilisations Against Election Fraud and Against War in Ukraine

121.5 Patria Gwen BORCENA, *Greenresearch Environmental Research Group, Inc., Philippines* and Resurreccion MANALO, *ESCR - Asia, Inc., Philippines*
The Philippine Religious Groups in the Public Square amidst the President's War on Drugs

19:30-20:50

122 War and Global Realignments: Geopolitical Prospects

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jan P. NEDERVEEN PIETERSE, *University of California at Santa Barbara, USA* and Kim SCIPES, *Purdue University Northwest, USA*

Chair: Jan P. NEDERVEEN PIETERSE, *University of California at Santa Barbara, USA*

Co-Chair: Kim SCIPES, *Purdue University Northwest, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

122.1 Yohanes MARIANTA, *STFT Widya Sasana, Indonesia*
Rowing between Two Reefs: A Study of Indonesia's Hedging Strategy in the Face of US-China Rivalry

122.2 Jan P. NEDERVEEN PIETERSE, *University of California at Santa Barbara, USA*
Ukraine War, Clash of Authoritarianisms, Global Resets

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-55 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics I

Committees: RC40 *Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-55.

10:30-12:20

123 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part II

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*

Chair: Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, IDHES, ENS Paris-Saclay, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

123.1 Nitsan CHOREV, *Brown University, USA*
The Virus and the Vessel, or: How We Learned to Stop Worrying and Love Surveillance

123.2 Tin-yuet TING, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*
Unequal Pathways to Vlogging: How Social Class Shapes the Career Aspirations and Professional Routines of Youtubers

123.3 Glen BERMAN, *Australian National University, Australia* and Kate WILLIAMS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
'Hybridity' and the Construction of Digital Futures

123.4 Amy MOWLE, *Victoria University, Australia*
Tracing the Tensions of Networked Feminism on Reddit's r/TwoXchromosomes

123.5 Maitrayee MULLICK, *Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India* and Archana PATNAIK, *Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India*
Networked Ecologies, Marginalized Citizens, and Participatory Governance: Case of Smart City Bhubaneswar, India

123.6 Vinay BRANDON, *Delhi School of Economics, University of Delhi, India*
The World According to Crypto: Debugging Monetary Trust for a Digital Society

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

124 Futures Research: Open Themes Part II

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa*

Chair: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa*

Co-Chair: Rovashni CHETTY, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

124.1 Jianghong LI, *WZB Berlin Social Science Center, Germany*
Unequal Electoral Participation: The Negative Effects of Long Work Hours and Unsociable Work Schedules in Europe

124.2 Yuri NAKAJIMA, *Nagasaki University, Japan*
Cultural Barriers to Leaving Their Places of Origin: Thinking of "Place Attachment" in the Japanese Context

124.3 Tania GARCIA-RAMOS, *University of Puerto Rico, PR*
Care Work in Puerto Rico: Relevant Contributions and Proposals for Future Research

124.4 Sean MCNELIS, *Centre for Urban Transitions, Swinburne University of Technology, Australia*

Functional Collaboration: Transitioning to World Care

124.5 Jo HAYNES, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom* and Ian WOODWARD, *Syddansk Universitet, Denmark*
'Looking Good, Being Good, and Doing Good'. Moral Governance and the New Responsibilised Music Festival.

124.6 Mariana MOTTA VIVIAN, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Crises of Democracy, Authoritarianism, and Aspirations for the Future in Contemporary Brazilian Sociology

10:30-12:20

JS-93 La Lucha Contra Los Extractivismos En América Latina y El Futuro De La Región | Struggle Against Extractivism in Latin America and the Future of the Region

Committees: *RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC07 Futures Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-93.

15:30-17:20

JS-97 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics II

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); RC07 Futures Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-97.

17:30-19:20

125 Futures Research: Open Themes. Part I

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa*

Chair: Radhamany SOORYAMOORTHY, *University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

125.1 Guillermina JASSO, *Two Washington Square Village, USA*

From Fairness and Loss Aversion to the Golden Number: Signals for Futures Research?

125.2 Mokong Simon MAPADIMENG, *University of South Africa, South Africa*

Africanising Educational Curriculum through Indigenous Knowledges – Challenges, Constraints and Possibilities.

125.3 Rovashni CHETTY, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa* and Hema HARGOVAN, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Visible Yet Invisible: The 'lived' Experiences of Persons with Albinism at Selected Institutions of Higher Education in Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa

125.4 Roger CAMPDEPADROS, *Universitat de Girona, Spain* and Lena DE BOTTON, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Contextual and Relational Variables Associated to Taking a Stance in Favor of Gender Violence Victims

125.5 Ingrid KOFLER, *Free University of Bolzano, Italy* and Maximilian WALDER, *Eurac Research, Italy*

Craftspeople and Their Imaginary: How the Technological Development Shapes the Future of the Craft Sector

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

126 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part III

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tin-yuet TING, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*

Chair: Tin-yuet TING, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

126.1 Magdalena KAROLAK, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*

Citizen Participation and Online Environments after a Crisis of Democracy: Lessons from Iceland

126.2 Masato TANIGUCHI, *Keio University, Japan*
Changing the Way We Think about Change

126.4 Alexandre MARTINS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Dynamics of Social Imagination and Political Strategies: Sexual and Gender Dissidents' Politics in Contemporary Argentina and Colombia

126.5 Doo Hyeong LEE, *Université Lumière Lyon 2, France*
From Ideologists to Programmers: Activists' Roles in Contemporary South Korean Social Movements

15:30-17:20

127 Horizons of Future and Everyday Life

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Emilia ARAUJO, *University of Minho, Portugal* and Paula URZE, *NOVA University, CIUCHT, Portugal*

Chair: Mokong Simon MAPADIMENG, *University of Limpopo, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

127.1 Giacomo BAZZANI, *University of Florence, Italy*
Futures in Action: Expectations, Imaginaries and Narratives of the Future

127.2 Fareed KAVIANI, *Monash University, Australia*; Hannah KORSMEYER, *Monash University, Australia*; Kari DAHLGREN, *Monash University, Australia*; Yolande STRENGERS, *Monash University, Australia* and Sarah PINK, *Monash University, Australia*
People and Everyday Life with Future Energy Systems: Integrating Qualitative Foresights into Industry Scenarios

127.3 Radhika CHAKRABORTY, *National University of Singapore, India*
Futures Past, Present, and Elsewhere: Hindu Sindhi Diaspora in Hong Kong

17:30-19:20

128 Post-Pandemic Futures: Affect, Responsibility and Materiality.**Location:** 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Julia COOK, *University of Newcastle, Australia* and Giuliana MANDICH, *University of Cagliari, Italy***Chair:** Julia COOK, *University of Newcastle, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

128.1 Peter KELLY, *Deakin University, Australia*; Seth BROWN, *RMIT University, Australia* and James GORING, *School of Education, Deakin University, Australia*
COVID-19 and Young People's 'Future Presents': Scenario Planning, Hopes and Anxieties in the Anthropocene

128.2 Manuel SCHULZ, *University of Jena, Germany*
The Existential Veil of Ignorance - Principles of a Neo-Phenomenological Theory of Justice for the 21th Century

128.3 Ash WATSON, *UNSW Sydney, Australia*
Feeling the Future with Fiction: Storytelling and Sociological Imagination

128.4 Cicek USUMEZGEZER, *Kirkclareli University, Turkey*
Promises of Horror Cinema for Sociological Imagination in Troubled Futures

128.5 Raffaele GUETTO, *University of Florence, Italy*; Giacomo BAZZANI, *University of Florence, Italy* and Daniele VIGNOLI, *University of Florence, Italy*
Narratives of the Future and Fertility Decision-Making in Uncertain Times. an Application to the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

JS-141 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part I

Committees: RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research and RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements*

See Joint Session Details for JS-141.

12:30-14:20

129 Hope, Future and Social Theory**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina***Chair:** Silvia CATALDI, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy***Co-Chair:** Gennaro IORIO, *University of Salerno, Italy*

Panelists: Paulo Henrique MARTINS ALBUQUERQUE, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil* and William CALVO-QUIROS, *American Culture and Latina/o Studies | University of Michigan, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

129.1 Gennaro IORIO, *University of Salerno, Italy*
Different and Together: The Hope of Social Love.

129.2 Paulo Henrique MARTINS ALBUQUERQUE, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil*
Hope and the Right to Dream As Political Practice in the Transition from Capitalism

129.3 William CALVO-QUIROS, *American Culture and Latina/o Studies | University of Michigan, USA*
Hope and Liberty: Challenging the Gerrymandering of Freedom

129.4 Silvia CATALDI, *sapienza university of rome, Italy*
Research Practices and Hope: Notes for a New Engagement of Social Sciences

14:30-16:20

130 Disinformation in the Technomediatic Public Sphere**Location:** 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Richard MISKOLCI, *Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP), Brazil***Chair:** Mokong Simon MAPADIMENG, *University of Limpopo, South Africa***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

130.1 Vern SMITH, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
Individualised and Collectivised Cyber-Deviance

130.2 Emil Albert SOBOTTKA, *Rua Prof. Fitzgerald 192, Brazil*
Platform Capitalism and Democracy: Crisis of the Public Sphere in Brazil

RC08

History of Sociology

Program Coordinator: Natalia MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, *University of Sydney, Australia*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

131 RC08 Business Meeting

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Fran COLLYER, *University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Fran COLLYER, *University of Sydney, Australia*

19:30-20:50

132 Past, Present and Future: Learning from 'Old' Sociological Research

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Laurie PARSONS, *University of Leicester, United Kingdom*

Chair: Wiebke KEIM, *CNRS, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

132.1 Rosalind EDWARDS, *University of Southampton, United Kingdom* and Val GILLIES, *University of Westminster, United Kingdom*
Wives' Role in Pioneering Classic British Community Studies: The Bethnal Green and Salford Diaries

132.2 Gay MOKWENA, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
Revisiting "Native Life in South Africa": Excavating Sol Plaatje As a Public Sociologist

132.3 Geoffrey MEAD, *Monash University, Australia*
Behind the Collective Memory: Maurice Halbwachs As Empirical Sociologist

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

132.4 Victor LIDZ, *Drexel University College of Medicine, USA*
The Development of Four Function Macrosociology

132.5 Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*
A Sociology of Itinerancy: Donald Pierson and Its Importance for Studies of the Body in Brazil

132.6 Mitsuhiro TADA, *Kumamoto University, Japan*
Talcott Parsons' Monolingualism and the Age of the National Society

132.7 Hedvig EKERWALD, *University of Uppsala, Sweden*
A Comeback for the 'American Soldier'?

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

133 Theories and Methods in Undertaking Histories of Sociology

Language: English, French

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Marcel FOURNIER, *Université de Montréal, Canada*

Chair: Natalia MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

133.1 Romulo LELIS, *Brazilian Center of Analysis and Planning, Brazil*
Against Revelation: Hubert and Mauss' Shaping of Durkheim's Late Sociology of Religion

133.2 Josef GINNERSKOV, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Revisiting Popular Theories of Sociology with an Interpretative Take on Computational Methods

133.3 Eleanor TOWNSLEY, *Mount Holyoke College, USA* and Ben GEBRE-MEDHIN, *Mount Holyoke College, USA*
Speaking for Sociology (and the social sciences): Computational Text Analysis of a Century of Presidential Addresses to the Disciplines

133.4 Ayako OZEKI, *Wakayama University, Japan*
La Loi De La Nature Et La Loi De La Société Chez Durkheim Et Bergson

133.5 Marcel FOURNIER, *Université de Montréal, Canada*
Theories and Methods in History of Francophone Sociology 2000-2020

133.6 Diego PEREYRA, *Gino Germani Research Institute / Universidad Nacional de Lanús, Argentina*
Society in Numbers. Forms of Legitimation of Empirical Sociology in Argentina from Academic Journals and the Press (1940-1975).

133.7 Fran COLLYER, *University of Sydney, Australia*
What Happens to Sociological Knowledge in a Democratic Context?

15:30-17:20

134 The Genesis of Sociology and the Relationship to Its Sibling Disciplines

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hedvig EKERWALD, *University of Uppsala, Sweden*

Chair: Natalia MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

134.1 Manish THAKUR, *Indian Institute of Management Calcutta, India*
Sociology and Social Sciences in India: Connections and Closures

134.2 Alberto CORDEIRO DE FARIAS, *Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ), Brazil*

What Is a “Systematic History” of Sociology? Presentation of the Problem and Some Hypotheses.

134.3 Seyda TUNCBILEK, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
The French Sociologist-Anthropologists or Anthropologist-Sociologists: Durkheim, Mauss, and Lévi-Strauss

134.4 Linda LUIZ, *St. Teresa’s College, Ernakulam, India*
Sociology and Its Siblings: The Case of Kerala from the 1930s

134.5 Jo KASAGI, *The Open university of Japan, Japan*
Social Logic in Gabriel Tarde: An Intersection of Sociology and Philosophy

134.6 John Eustice O’BRIEN, *Portland State University (ret.), Monaco*
Durkheim’s Rediscovered Lessons from 1892: Institutional Sociology from Study of Crime?

134.7 Jakub MOTRENKO, *Uniwersytet Warszawski/University of Warsaw, Poland*
The Metamorphosis of Interdisciplinarity: From Unity of Method to the Search for Deeper Insight

134.8 Marek SKOVAJSA, *Charles University, Czech Republic*
Two Early Careers in Sociology: Masaryk and Jerusalem

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

134.9 Frederico AGOAS, *Interdisciplinary Centre of Social Sciences, NOVA University Lisbon (CICS.NOVA), Portugal*
Towards an Integrated Historical Sociology of Colonial and Metropolitan Social Research

134.10 Rajesh MISRA, *University of Lucknow, India*
Integration of Economics, Sociology and Anthropology: Practice of Sociology at Lucknow (India)

17:30-19:20

135 Social Research, Funding Sources and Social Prognostication in the History of Sociology

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Paolo PARRA SAIANI, *University of Genoa - Department of International and Political Sciences, Italy*

Chair: Paolo PARRA SAIANI, *University of Genoa - Department of International and Political Sciences, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

135.1 Liutauras KRANIAUSKAS, *Klaipeda University, Lithuania*
Who Won a Million? Analysing Competition of S.S.H for Grants in Lithuania

135.2 Michiel VAN DAM, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
Early Experiments in the Creation of Sociological Belief: Louis De Bonald and the Christian-Sociological Culture of Prediction

135.3 Matteo BORTOLINI, *University of Padua, Italy, Italy*
“Putting Italy on the Map. ‘il Caso Italiano’ the Role of Experts in Predicting the Coming Crisis of the 1970s”

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

136 Comparative National Histories of Sociology

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Fran COLLYER, *University of Karlstad, Sweden* and Matthias DULLER, *Central European University, Austria*

Chair: Fran COLLYER, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

136.1 Sayana MITUPOVA, *Russian Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Russian Federation*
Sociology in Totalitarian Societies of Soviet Russia and Imperial Japan

136.2 Muhammed Fazil BAS, *Yildiz Technical University, Turkey*
National Identity and Sociology: A Comparison of the Institutionalization of Sociology As an Academic Discipline in Germany and Turkey

136.3 Kohei YOSHIDA, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*
Nationalized and Denationalized Sociologies: The Studying How Borders Were Created between Émigré and American Scholars during the WWII

15:30-17:20

137 Transnational Histories of Sociology

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Barbara HOENIG, *University of Graz, Austria*; Marcia CONSOLIM, *Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil* and Wiebke KEIM, *CNRS, Germany*

Chair: Wiebke KEIM, *CNRS, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

137.1 Meta CRAMER, *University of Freiburg, Germany, Germany*
Institutionalizing and Decolonizing Anglophone Caribbean Social Sciences 1950-1990: Four Generations of Transnational Knowledge Production

137.2 Joao Marcelo EHLERT MAIA, *14th Floor, Brazil*
A Tale from the Cold War: Ilari and the Social Sciences in Latin America (1966-1972)

137.3 Laurent AFRESNE, *University of Paris Nanterre, France*
Circulation and Reception Studies As a Way to Enact a Transnational History of Sociology

137.4 Stephane DUFOIX, *University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France*
How (Latin)American Is the Decolonial Perspective in the Social Sciences ?

137.5 Clara RUVITUSO, *Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut, Berlin, Germany*
A Transnational Trajectory between Consultancy, Academia and Care Work: The Pioneering Sociological Lens of Cynthia Hewitt De Alcántara

17:30-19:20

138 Reflecting upon Translation in the History of Sociology**Language:** English, French**Location:** 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Rafael SCHOEGLER, *University of Graz, Austria***Chair:** Jaroslaw KILIAS, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

138.1 Stefan FORNOS KLEIN, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil* and Carolina NASCIMENTO, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil*
Peripheral Internationalization at a Crossroads: Trajectories and Agendas in the Brazilian Context

138.2 Marcia CONSOLIM, *Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil*
Intellectual Figures in the New World: Practices and Representations of Professors of Sociology in Brazil (1930-1945)

138.3 Jaroslaw KILIAS, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Translations in the Making of Polish Sociology 1956-1989

138.4 Rafael SCHOEGLER, *University of Graz, Austria*
Translation: Circulating and Transforming Sociological Thinking

139.3 Claudio RAMOS ZINCKE, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile* and Alexis CORTES MORALES, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile*
Pensamiento Crítico y Sociología. El Caso De Chile

139.4 Gina ZABLUDOVSKY, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
La Institucionalización De La Sociología En México (1930 1965)

139.5 Juan Jesús MORALES, *Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez, Chile* and Justino GÓMEZ DE BENITO, *Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez, Chile*
Trajectory De La Sociología En Chile. De Su Temprana Institucionalización a Una Sociología Plural Para Una Sociedad Diversa.

17:30-19:20

140 South-South Intellectual Exchanges : Networks, Actors, Theories, Impact**Location:** 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Stephane DUFOIX, *University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France* and Leandro RODRIGUEZ MEDINA, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana at Azcapotzalco, Mexico***Chair:** Stephane DUFOIX, *University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

140.1 Meta CRAMER, *University of Freiburg, Germany, Germany*
Epistemic Sovereignty in the West Indies: The New World Group in the 1960s

140.2 Anaheed AL-HARDAN, *Howard University, USA*
African-Asian Anti-Colonialism in 1960s Cairo

140.3 Estevão BOSCO, *Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO), Brazil* and Lidiane RODRIGUES, *Federal University of ABC, Brazil*
From 'Adaptive Realism' to Critical Intercultural Hermeneutics: A Dialogue between Brazilian Sociology and Post/Decolonial Scholarship on Eurocentrism

140.4 Linda LUIZ, *St. Teresa's College, Ernakulam, India*
Its Not Sociology! Restraints and Possibilities for the History of Sociology in India

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

139 Sociology and Sociologists in Latin America. Institutions, Biographies, Networks, and Comparative Perspectives.**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Joao Marcelo EHLERT MAIA, *Getulio Vargas Foundation, Brazil***Chair:** Diego PEREYRA, *Gino Germani Research Institute / Universidad Nacional de Lanús, Argentina***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

139.1 Seyda TUNCBILEK, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
Un Sociólogo Rebelde: Los Años Brasileños De Claude Lévi-Strauss (1935-1939)

139.2 Philipp ALTMANN, *Universidad Central del Ecuador, Ecuador*
A Particular Tradition - Sociology in Ecuador in the Latin American Context

RC09

Social Transformations and Sociology of Development

Program Coordinators: Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2, France* and Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy RC20 Comparative Sociology RC56 Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

17:30-19:20

141 Development Processes on Geographical Frontiers II

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*

Chair: Brian DILL, *University of Illinois, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

141.1 Jennifer KEAHEY, *Arizona State University, USA*
Agrarian Transformation and Resistance in Post-Authoritarian Environments

141.2 Debasish HAZARIKA, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, INDIA, India*
Place-Making, Conflicts, and Borderland Lives in Northeast India

141.3 Carles FEIXA, *University Pompeu Fabra, Spain* and Montserrat INIESTA, *University Pompeu Fabra, Spain*
"SHE (OR HE) Wasn't Single". Hydroelectric Exploitation in Spain from a Gender Perspective

141.4 Anna KASTEN, *Ernst-Abbe-University of Applied Sciences Jena, Germany*
Authoritarianism in the Context of Humanitarian Aid for Refugees on the Polish-Belarusian Border

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

142 New Theories and Findings in Development Sociology

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA*

Chair: Jennifer KEAHEY, *Arizona State University, USA*

Discussant: Jennifer KEAHEY, *Arizona State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

142.1 Jhoner PERDOMO, *Central University of Venezuela. Institute of Economic and Social Research, Venezuela*
Sustainable Wellbeing Index for Monitoring the Capabilities, Freedoms, and Opportunities of Individuals Against the Rise of Global Authoritarianism.

142.2 Ananda KURITI, *Institute for Development Studies Andhra Pradesh, India* and Satish DEEPATI, *Institute for Development Studies Andhra Pradesh (IDSAP), Visakhapatnam, India*
Youth and Environmental Change in India: A Theoretical Perspective

142.3 Kokichi SHOJI, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
A Historical Way to Integrate Human Bodies and Our Planet into a Social and Ecological System

142.4 Su-ming KHOO, *National University of Ireland, Ireland*
Sustaining Ignorance amidst Planetary Omnicrisis

15:30-17:20

143 Development Processes on Geographical Frontiers I

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA*

Chair: Uddhab P PYAKUREL, *Kathmandu University, Nepal*

Discussants: Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates* and Sirojuddin ARIF, *Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia, Indonesia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

143.1 Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA*
Frontier Development: Groceries or Blood?

143.2 Saowalak CHAYTAWEEP, *Maejo university, Thailand*
Community Governance, Trust State and Drivers of Conflict ; Reflections on Conflict in Northern Thailand

143.3 Thomas MALSOM, *North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong, India*; Romita REANG, *North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong, India* and Biswaranjan TRIPURA, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai, India*
Community Experiences of Extractivism in Tripura, Northeast India

143.4 Vishnu VAIRAGAD, *Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India*
Indian Villages: An Authoritarian Caste-Ruled Re-Publics

143.5 Ligaya LINDIO MCGOVERN, *Indiana Univeristy, USA*
Neoliberalism, Global Capitalism, Extractivism and the Politics of Resistance in the Philippine Context

19:30-20:50

144 Why Societies Collapse ?**Location:** 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Samuel COHN, *Texas A and M University, USA* and Joshua DUBROW, *Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland***Chair:** Saowalak CHAYTAWEAP, *Maejo university, Thailand***Discussant:** Saowalak CHAYTAWEAP, *Maejo university, Thailand***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****144.1** Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA*
What Doesn't KILL You Makes You Stronger: Societal Death Processes and Economic Growth**144.2** Sizhe XIE, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
From Fetching to Governing: A Global Survey of Women's Political Empowerment and Water Access**144.3** Jems BAG, *University of Hyderabad, India*
Capitalist Mode of Development and Community Rehabilitation: A Critical Analysis of Industrial Project in Odisha, India**Wednesday 28 June**

08:30-10:20

145 RC09 Business Meeting**Location:** 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Chair:** Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2, France*

10:30-12:20

146 RC09 Poster Session**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Antje DANIEL, *University of Vienna, Austria*; Petra DANNECKER, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Eva GERHARZ, *Fulda University of Applied Sciences, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****146.1** Susanne GUSTAFSSON, *Dalarna University, Sweden*
Jan's Life-History: Changing Faces of Managerial Masculinities and Consequences for Health**146.2** Josephine DIONISIO, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*; Kidd Alonzo Juwan PALANCA, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines* and Ferdinand SANCHEZ II, *Centre for Deliberative Democracy and Global Governance, University of Canberra, Australia*
Social Networks of Care in Times of COVID-19

15:30-17:20

147 State and Development**Location:** 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Dorina ROSCA, *The American University of Moldova, Moldova***Chair:** Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA***Discussant:** Dorina ROSCA, *The American University of Moldova, Moldova***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****147.1** Nobuyuki YAMADA, *Komazawa University, Japan*
Where Is "Reciprocity" in Capitalism?: An Approach from the Neo-Polanyian Perspective**147.2** Dieter NEUBERT, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*
Development Sociology Under Scrutiny. Challenges of Post-Colonial Critique**147.3** Sirojuddin ARIF, *Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia, Indonesia*
Power Resources, Social Ties, and Inequality: Rural Threats and the Distributional Outcomes of Rural Development in Indonesia and Malaysia**147.4** Silvia MALACARNE, *Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Italy*
Mutual Learning Is Possible? Practical Evidence of a More Equal International Development Cooperation**147.5** Yunjeong YANG, *Hankuk University of Foreign Studies, Republic of Korea*; Moamen GOUDA, *Hankuk University of Foreign Studies, Republic of Korea*; Adriana KEATING, *International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Australia*; Chantra SOURN, *Habitat for Humanity Cambodia, Cambodia* and Phoeun OUM, *Habitat for Humanity Cambodia, Cambodia*
Towards Resilient Community Development: Time-Series Findings, Practical Challenges and Reflections on a CCA Action Research Project to Build Disaster Resilience in Rural Cambodian Communities**147.6** Matthew SABBI, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*
Critical Arena of the Authoritarian Public Sphere? Imihigo-Induced Governance Forums in Rwanda

17:30-19:20

148 Migration, Innovation and Entrepreneurship in the Contemporary World**Language:** English, French**Location:** 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Dorina ROSCA, *Ladyss, UMR 7533 CNRS, France***Chair:** Dorina ROSCA, *Ladyss, UMR 7533 CNRS, France***Discussant:** Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2, France***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****148.1** Tika GAUTAM, *Tribhuvan University, Nepal* and Hari Prasad ACHARYA, *Tribhuvan University, Nepal*
Capitalism, Migration and Entrepreneurship in Nepal**148.2** Xinwei ZHANG, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Low-Tech Immigration Living in Modernity: The Ongoing of East-Asian Bubble Tea Entrepreneur in Finland**148.3** Ji LI, *Kobe University, Japan* and Masaya NAKATSUKA, *Kobe University, Japan*
The Structure and Role of Support Networks for Migrant Entrepreneurs in Rural Japan

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

149 Innovations in the Study of Innovation in Development

Language: French, English

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2 LIRIS EA 7481, France*

Chair: Samuel COHN, *Texas A&M University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

149.1 Yukimi SHIMODA, *Waseda University, Japan*
Considering Intersections of Development Issues and Social Entrepreneurs

149.2 Abdul-Aziz DEMBELE, *Université Rennes 2, France*
Mobile Phone and Rural Development. Case Study in Côte D'ivoire

149.3 Brian DILL, *University of Illinois, USA* and Hany ZAYED, *University of Illinois - Urbana Champaign, USA*
Egypt 2.0: The Rise of a Digital Developmental State

149.4 Line LINDGAARD ANDERSEN, *School of Social Science, University of Tasmania, Hobart, Tasmania, 7005, Australia*
Regional Innovation: An Cross-Industry Exploration of Innovation Practices in the Cradle Coast Region of Tasmania

15:30-17:20

150 Local Politics between Resurgent Authoritarianism and Resilient Democratisation

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Dieter NEUBERT, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*; Matthew SABBI, *University of Bayreuth, Germany* and Alexander STROH, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*

Chair: Dieter NEUBERT, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

150.1 Uddhab P PYAKUREL, *Kathmandu University, Nepal*; Matti KOHONEN, *Financial Transparency, United Kingdom* and UPP SERASINGHE, *University of Colombo, Sri Lanka*
Tracking COVID-19 People's Recovery Fund in the Global South Countries

150.2 Emmanuelle BAROZET, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*; Vicente ESPINOZA, *Universidad Santiago de Chile, Chile* and Emilio MOYA, *Universidad Católica de Temuco, Chile*
Disputes in the Normative and Political Order in Chile Today: The Case of Patronage in Local Governments

150.3 Gabriele BECKMANN, *Fachhochschule für Interkulturelle Theologie Hermannsburg, Germany* and Moira ZUAZO, *FU Berlin, Germany*
Decentralisation and Local Governments in Bolivia – Do They Rather Serve to Democratisation or to Strengthen a “Democracy with Adjectives”?

150.4 Matthew SABBI, *University of Bayreuth, Germany* and Alexander STROH, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*
The Paradox of Local Autonomy: An Inverse Relationship between the National State of Democracy and Space for Autonomous Decision-Making of Local Councils?

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

151 Visual Representations of Development: Practices and Possibilities

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Rukmini SEN, *Dr B R Ambedkar University Delhi, India* and Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*

Chair: Uddhab P PYAKUREL, *Kathmandu University, Nepal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

151.1 Aarshi JAHAN, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Delhi, India*
The Epistemological Function of Visuals- Questioning the Visual Representation of Dalit Community in Development Discourse

151.2 Lukasz ROGOWSKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland*
Visual Representations of Rural Development. Challenges of Using Visual Research Methods in Studying Rural Areas.

15:30-17:20

JS-132 The Prospects of a Pluriversal Transition to a Post-Capitalist, Post-Carbon Future

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-132.

17:30-19:20

JS-136 Knowledge Co-Production, Communities, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host); RC15 Sociology of Health

See Joint Session Details for JS-136.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

JS-144 Women Entrepreneurs on the African Continent and Beyond

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-144.

RC10

Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

Program Coordinators: Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa*; Michela FREDDANO, *INVALSI, Italy* and Sheetal BHOOLA, *The University of Zululand, South Africa, South Africa*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

152 Participation and Resurgent Authoritarianism: African and International Perspectives and Experiences

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa* and Sheetal BHOOLA, *The University of Zululand, South Africa, South Africa*

Chair: Sheetal BHOOLA, *The University of Zululand, South Africa, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

152.1 Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa*
An Uninvited Space for Public Participation in South Africa: The Events of July 2021 in Durban.

152.2 Pawel STAROSTA, *University of Lodz, Poland*
Patterns of Public Participation Versus Authoritarian and Democratic Attitudes in European Countries

152.3 Uddhab P PYAKUREL, *Kathmandu University, Nepal*
New Democracy and Public Opinion Research: A Study of Survey of Nepali People, 2022

15:30-17:20

JS-12 Resurgent Authoritarianism in the Context of SDG 1 on No Poverty, SDG2 on Zero Hunger and SDG 17 on Partnerships for the Goals: Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management (Host); WG05 Famine and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-12.

17:30-19:20

153 Corporate Governance and Corporate Social Responsibility Under Conditions of International Globalization and Growing Nationalism As Driver of Wars

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Volkmar KREISSIG, *Taita Taveta University Kenya/University Wuppertal, Kenya* and Sheetal BHOOLA, *The University of Zululand, South Africa, South Africa*

Chair: Eleni NINA-PAZARZI, 8, *Voutsina Street, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

153.1 Maria SANTOS, *SOCIUS / Lisbon School of Economics and Management, Portugal*
Global Supply Chains and Work Practices: The Case of Inditex

153.2 Abilio ZACARIAS, *ISEG-University of Lisbon, Portugal*
The Characteristics of Board Chair for More Effective Recruitment Process in Times of Financial Crisis.

153.3 Simangele CELE, *The University of Zululand, South Africa* and Joy MDINISO, *The University of Zululand, South Africa*
Small and Medium Businesses in Kwazulu- Natal, South Africa and Their Approach to Corporate Social Responsibility Programs.

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

JS-36 Transformative Research, Education and World Social Forum

Committees: RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-36.

15:30-17:20

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC07 Futures Research RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-39.

17:30-19:20

JS-51 Political Socialization in Changing Times: Generations and Agents.

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-51.

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

JS-67 Urban Collective Action

Committees: *RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management*

See Joint Session Details for JS-67.

15:30-17:20

JS-74 People-Centric Governance, Society, and Sustainable Development

Committees: *WG05 Famine and Society (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management*

See Joint Session Details for JS-74.

17:30-19:20

154 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation Part III: Digital Discourse and Democracy

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Stefan LUCKING, *Hans-Boeckler-Stiftung, Germany*

Chair: Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

154.1 Gabriela VILLEN M. SCUTARI, *State University of Campinas, Brazil* and Leda GITAHY, *State University of Campinas, Brazil*
The Unmaking of the Public University in Brazil: From the Ministry of Education to the Police Pages

154.2 Marina FONTOLAN, *Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil*; Nicole DE MARCH, *Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil*; Giselle Soares Menezes SILVA, *Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil* and Maycon Poli BARBOSA, *Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil*
Brazil, Democracy, and Deepfakes: Overseeing the 2022 Elections

154.3 Zhifan LUO, *Concordia University, Canada*
Adapting the Conceptual Tool to the Digital Future: A Two-Dimensional Framework of Censorship

Thursday 29 June

15:30-17:20

155 Challenges and International Perspectives of Participatory Democracy at Work in the Era of Resurgent Authoritarianism

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa* and Eleni NINA-PAZARZI, *8, Voutsina Street, Greece*

Chair: Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

155.1 Maria FREGIDOU-MALAMA, *Faculty of Education and Business Studies, Sweden* and Michelle RYDBACK, *Department of Business and Economic Studies, Faculty of Education and Business Studies, University of Gävle, Sweden*
From Successful to Unsuccessful Social Enterprise: Unitis a Social Cooperative in Sweden

155.2 Georgios KARALIS, *Greek Bar Association, Greece* and Eleni NINA-PAZARZI, *University of Piraeus, Greece*
Does Participation in Modern Day Work Unions Improve Job Equality and Democracy?

155.3 Vera VRATUSA, *University of Belgrade, Serbia*
Globalization of Democratic Participation Self-Governance Versus Globalization of Oligopolistic Markets Totalitarianism

155.4 Rodrigo RAMIS MOYANO, *Instituto de Estudios Sociales Avanzados (IESA-CSIC), Spain*
Does Ideology Matter? a Systematic Review of Participatory Institutions Implementation By Political Parties

155.5 Michela FREDDANO, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of Educational System of Instruction and Training), Italy*
PAR to Train Teachers in Monitoring for School Self-Evaluation: The Research Experience at the Galileo Technical and Professional Pole

17:30-19:20

JS-112 To Participate or Not to Participate? Social Movements 4.0 and the Return of Dichotomies

Committees: *RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-112.

19:30-20:50

156 RC10 Business Meeting

Location: M14 (Crown)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

157 Networking, Collaborative Dialogue, Shared Governance: Practical Cases for Sustaining Participatory Democracy in Education

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Donatella POLIANDRI, *INVALSI (Italian National Institute of Educational Evaluation), Italy* and Letizia GIAMPIETRO, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of Educational Instruction and Training), Italy*

Chair: Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

157.1 Letizia GIAMPIETRO, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of Educational Instruction and Training), Italy*; Angela LITTERI, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System), Italy* and Enrico NERLI BALLATI, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System), Italy*

What Shared Governance to School Development? the Value for Schools' Case Study

157.2 Giuseppe DE LUCA PICIONE, *University of Naples 'Federico II', Italy* and Lucia FORTINI, *University of Naples 'Federico II', Italy*

The Networks of Adult Education As Learning Communities to Support Participatory Democracy

157.3 Maurizio MERICO, *University of Salerno, Italy*; Anna Fausta SCARDIGNO, *University of Bari, Italy*; Daniele MORCIANO, *UNIVERSITY OF BARI, Italy* and Nadia CRESCENZO, *University of Salerno, Italy*

Enhancing the Learning Continuum. Toward a Renewed Integration between School and out-of-School Contexts in Italy

157.4 Claudio TORRIGIANI, *Università degli Studi di Genova Disfor Tax ID 00754150100, Italy*; Paola GIANNONI, *Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy*; Elena ZINI, *Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy*; Valeria PANDOLFINI, *Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy* and Mauro PALUMBO, *Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy*

The governance of school-work alternance in Italy: salient features and ways of improvement

157.5 Antonello SCIALDONE, *INAPP-NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR PUBLIC POLICY ANALYSIS, Italy*

Some Remarks about Collaborative Governance and CO-Creation of Shared Administration

15:30-17:20

158 Organizing Against Authoritarianism in the Platform and on-Demand Economy

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Stefan LUCKING, *Hans-Böckler-Stiftung, Germany* and Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, France*

Chair: Stefan LUCKING, *Hans-Boeckler-Stiftung, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

158.1 Chris TILLY, *University of California Los Angeles, USA*
Digital Technology in US Store-Based Retail: Toward Job Upgrading or Degradation?

158.2 Athina AVAGIANOU, *University of the Aegean, Greece*; Georgios CHATZICHRISTOS, *Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece* and Stelios GIALIS, *University of the Aegean, Greece*
Delivering Labour Precariousness? Grounding a Socio-Spatially Sensitive Theory for Platform Food Delivery Workers

158.3 Nuno BOAVIDA, *NOVA University of Lisbon, Portugal*; Pablo SANZ DE MIGUEL, *NOTUS asr, Universidad Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*; Antonio MONIZ, *Universidade Nova de Lisboa, FCT-UNL, CICS.NOVA, Portugal* and Juan ARASANZ, *NOTUS asr, Spain*

How Do Different Platform Workers Organise to Achieve Bargaining Power in Platform Work? Examples from Iberian Countries

158.4 Cong PENG, *Communication University of China, China*
Freelancers' power over Time in the Perspective of Sociology of Time

158.5 Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, IDHES, ENS Paris-Saclay, France*

Platform Workers in the US and the EU: Independent Contractors or Employees?

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

159 Action-Research for Participation and Empowerment

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Azril BACAL ROIJ, *Uppsala University, Sweden*; Erik LINDHULT, *Mälardalen University, Sweden* and Michela FREDDANO, *INVALSI, Italy*

Chair: Azril BACAL ROIJ, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

159.1 Amy MOWLE, *Victoria University, Australia*; Therese RILEY, *Victoria University, Australia*; Bojana KLEPAC, *Victoria University, Australia*; Téa O'DRISCOLL, *Victoria University, Australia*; Annette GRAHAM, *Victoria University, Australia* and Melinda CRAIKE, *Victoria University, Australia*
"It's Not a Linear Process": Designing Systemic Interventions with Communities

159.2 Gabriele MORELLI, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*
Transformative or Market-Driven Solutions to Social Challenges? the Social and Solidarity Economy and Its Impact on Southern European Cities: The Case of Bologna.

159.3 Julia KURZ, *Technical University of Dortmund, Germany*
Disempowering for Participation.

159.4 Erik LINDHULT, *Mälardalen University, Sweden*; Marianne ERICSSON, *ABF/Workers' Educational Association, Sweden*; Åsa STENLUND-BJÖRK, *ABF/Workers' Educational Association, Sweden*; Leif EDVARDSSON, *ABF/Workers' Educational Association, Sweden*; Ann-Mari SCHWARTZ, *Runö Folk High School, Sweden* and Anna BERGKVIST, *ABF/Workers' Educational Association, Sweden*
Research Circles and Swedish Folk Bildung As Approach to Democratized Research and Learning in Revitalizing the Ideas and Practices of Its Own Tradition

159.5 Michela FREDDANO, *INVALSI (National Institute for the Evaluation of Educational System of Instruction and Training), Italy*
School Self-Evaluation Report (RAV) As a Tool of Action-Research: The Experience of an Italian Primary and Middle School for Improve the Educational Continuity

10:30-12:20

160 Democratic Participation and Self-Management Vs Authoritarianism: Theoretical Reflections and Propositions

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Catherine CASEY, *Loughborough University, United Kingdom*; Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, France* and Stefan LUCKING, *Hans-Boeckler-Stiftung, Germany*

Chair: Stefan LUCKING, *Hans-Boeckler-Stiftung, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

160.1 Isabel DA COSTA, CNRS, France
Theoretical Reflections on Power, Authority, and Democratic Participation in Employment Relations

160.2 Laura LOEZA REYES, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico
Las Estrategias De Las Organizaciones Civiles Mexicanas Para Defender Los Derechos Humanos En Un Contexto De Autocratización: 2018 - 2023

160.3 Charlize TOMASELLI, University of Cape Town, South Africa
Policy, Participation and Empowerment: A Case Study of Community Resistance Against Authoritarian Neoliberal Policy.

160.4 Mourad MHENNI, Sousse university, Diraset Etude Maghrebine laboratory., Tunisia
L'Institution Syndicale Et Les Régimes Politiques Autoritaires En Tunisie : Approche Socio-Historique

160.5 Thomas HAIPETER, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany; Sophie ROSENBOHM, University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute for Work, Skills and Training, Germany and Christine ÜYÜK, University-of Duisburg-Essen, Institute for Work, Skills and Training, Germany
Transnational Networks, World Works Councils and Global Framework Agreements: Interdependencies and Dynamics of Action for Transnational Labour Regulation in Multinational Companies

12:30-14:20

161 Civic Participation and the Process of Local Community Revitalization. Multinational Perspective and Experience

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Pawel STAROSTA, University of Lodz, Poland

Chair: Pawel STAROSTA, University of Lodz, Poland

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

161.1 Roganda Sadani Ukur SOLIN, Magister of Sociology, Indonesia and Ida RUWAIDA, University of Indonesia, Indonesia
Children's Participation in the Prevention of Violence Against : Fulfillment of Children Right to Participation

161.2 Niccolo MORELLI, University of Genova, Italy
Urban Collective Action in the Field of Security: Empirical Comparative Research on Neighbourhood Watch Groups in Modena.

161.3 Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development, India
Participatory Revitalisation of Urban Environmental Infrastructure in North-Western India: Some Evidence from Recent Studies

161.4 Nagender TADEPALLY, VILLAGES IN PARTNERSHIP (VIP), India
Participatory Democracy for Sustainable Development - FIELD Experiment to Understand and Identify the Process.

161.5 Subhendu RAJ, PGDAV E COLLEGE, India
Assessing COVID-19 Challenges to Public Health in India

14:30-16:20

162 Latin American Social Movements, Collective Actions and Democracy

Language: Spanish, English

Location: M14 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Maria da Gloria GOHN, University of Campinas, Brazil

Chair: Karina MALDONADO-MARISCAL, Technical University Dortmund, Germany

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

162.1 Camila MACEDO PONTE, Université de Genève, Switzerland
Democracy and Youth Participation in the Brazilian Semiarid: The Experiences of the Youth Consortium of Bahia

162.2 Claudio PENTEADO, Federal University of ABC, Brazil; Lucca TORI, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil; Paulo Roberto SOUZA, Universidade Federal do ABC, Brazil and Luana HOMMA, Universidade Federal do ABC, Brazil
Colectivos y Tecnologías De La Información y Comunicación: Un Análisis De Colectivos Culturales En São Paulo

162.3 Maria da Gloria GOHN, CNPq- National Research Council, Brazil
Activism in Brazil Today: In Defense of Rights and Democracy

162.4 Jose Javier MANYAS NAVARRO, Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain and Iker JIMENO, Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain
Self-Management As a Tool of Local Movements to Fight Corruption and Loss of Social Welfare in the Paraná Region (Brazil)

RC11

Sociology of Aging

Program Coordinators: Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

163 Health, Harm, and Social Disadvantage

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sandra TORRES, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

Chair: Milena FELDMANN, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

163.1 Lucía R. HERNES, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*; Ana LARA-MERCHAN, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*; Elisa RAMIREZ-MUÑOZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*; Rafael GRANDE, *Universidad de Málaga, Spain* and Juan Manuel GARCIA GONZALEZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*

Loneliness, Social Support and Mental Health Among Older Adults without Cognitive Impairment Living in Nursing Homes: A Cross-Sectional Survey Study

163.2 Lucie VIDOVICOVA, *Masaryk University, Czech Republic*
Elder Abuse and Neglect Phenomena in Czechia: First National Prevalence Study

163.3 Jaroslava MARHANKOVA, *Charles University, Smetanovo nabr. 6, 110 01 Praha 1, Czech Republic*
Older Adults' Representations of Dementia: A Qualitative Exploration

163.4 Jeanne HOEJGAARD-BOEYTLER, *Social work, Sweden*
Harm Reduction As Care? Providing Eldercare for People with Substance Abuse and Complex Needs

163.5 Esteban CALVO, *Society and Health Research Center, Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Artes, Universidad Mayor, Chile*; Cynthia CORDOVA, *Society and Health Research Center, Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Artes, Universidad Mayor, Chile*; Robin SHURA, *Department of Sociology, Kent State University at Stark, USA*; Kasim ALLEL, *College of Medicine and Health, University of Exeter, United Kingdom*; Alvaro CASTILLO-CARNIGLIA, *Society and Health Research Center, Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Artes, Universidad Mayor, Chile*; Jose MEDINA, *Society and Health Research Center, Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Artes, Universidad Mayor, Chile* and Silvia S. MARTINS, *Department of Epidemiology, Mailman School of Public Health, Columbia University, USA*

Global Pain and Aging: A Cross-Sectional Study on Age Differences in the Intensity of Chronic Pain Among Middle-Aged and Older Adults in 20 Countries

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

163.6 Tirth BHATTA, *University of Nevada, Las Vegas, USA*
Childhood Disadvantage and Later-Life Health: Situating Intersectionality in a Sociohistorical Context

163.7 Takashi IGUCHI, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
The Logic of Dementia Prevention in Contemporary Japanese Society and Its Rise and Fall

15:30-17:20

164 How Sociological Is the Sociology of Ageing?

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Chris GILLEARD, *University College London, United Kingdom*

Chair: Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

164.1 Paul HIGGS, *University College London, United Kingdom*
Sociological Theorising in the Sociology of Ageing;

164.2 Chris GILLEARD, *UCL Division of Psychiatry, United Kingdom*
Rethinking the Social Construction of Old Age

164.3 Martin HYDE, *Swansea University, United Kingdom*
Ageing in a Global Context: New Spatial Dynamics of Later Life

164.4 Anagha TENDULKAR - PATIL, *Sophia College for Women, India*
Sociology of Ageing: Potential and Fallacies

17:30-19:20

JS-19 Connected Seniors: Technology across the Life Course

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC11 Sociology of Ageing

See Joint Session Details for JS-19.

19:30-20:50

165 RC11 Business Meeting

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

166 Civic Engagement in Later Life: Expanding the Social Gerontological Imagination

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Rodrigo SERRAT, *University of Barcelona, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

166.1 Marina NASMAN, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland*; Fredrica NYQVIST, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland*; Mikael NYGÅRD, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland* and Toon VERCAUTEREN, *Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium*
Multidimensional Civic Engagement Among Older Adults in Europe: Individual and Country Level Variations and Drivers

166.2 Daniel BLANCHE-TARRAGÓ, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC), Spain*
Life Histories of Older Adults' Activism(s): Experiences, Practices, and Meanings

166.3 Inma PEIRO-MILIAN, *Universitat de Barcelona (UB), Spain*; Pernilla ÅGÅRD, *Uppsala University, Sweden*; Karima CHACUR-KISS, *Universitat de Barcelona (UB), Spain*; Bas DIKMANS, *Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium* and Sandra TORRES, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Older Migrants and Older People Living in Socially Disadvantaged Communities' Perspectives on Barriers and Enablers to Civic Engagement

166.4 Joonmo SON, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
The Reciprocal Relationship between Social Engagement and Cognitive Function Among Older Adults in South Korea

166.5 Yoshinori KASAI, *Keio University, Japan*
Older Adults' Civic Engagement in Various Way: Based on Their Life Histories and Local Newsletters

15:30-17:20

167 Migration and Migrancy As Points of Departure for Research on Aging and Old Age

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Kyriakos MARKIDES, *University of Texas Medical Branch, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

167.1 Tuen yi CHIU, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*
Mobile Ageing: Transborder Mobilities, Agency and the Well-Being of Older Adults in Hong Kong

167.2 Daniel DOHAN, *University of California San Francisco, USA*; Alma HERNANDEZ, *University of California San Francisco, USA*; Melissa MA, *University of California San Francisco, USA* and Stephen ZAMARRIPA, *University of California San Francisco, USA*
Aging and Migration: Structural, Institutional, and Cultural Dynamics

167.3 Jeehun KIM, *Dept. of Social Studies Education, Inha University, Republic of Korea* and Judith TREAS, *University of California, Irvine, USA*
Harder to Retire in Singapore or Korea? Korean Older Adults in Singapore on Linked Lives and Ageing in Place

167.4 Giovanni MATERA, *Harvard University, Weatherhead Center for International Affairs, USA*
The Role of Mental Health Care in the Mitigation of Recognition Gaps Affecting Elderly Forcibly Displaced Ukrainian Migrants.

167.5 Johanna ZULUETA, *Toyo University, Japan*
Ageing Migrants and Social Well-Being: The Case of Filipino Women in Rural Japan

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

167.6 Youumi LEE, *Syracuse University, USA* and Adrienne ATTERBERRY, *State University of New York (SUNY) at New Paltz, USA*
International Migration, Acculturation, and Care Work: Unpacking the Experiences of Korean Grandparent Caregivers in the USA

167.7 Jayakumar MADHAVAN SARASAMMA, *University of Kerala, India*
Back to Square One: Livelihood of Elderly Return Emigrants in Kerala, India

17:30-19:20

168 Mapping Age: Spaces, Places and Environments of Aging

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Karla WAZINSKI, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

168.1 Max TRAVERS, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Peta COOK, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Keith JACOBS, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Caroline OSBORNE, *synergy urban consulting, Australia*; Fatemeh AMINPOUR, *UNSW, Australia* and Zack DWYER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Community and Conflict in Retirement Villages

168.2 Marie ERIKSSON, *Linnaeus University, Sweden* and Clary KREKULA, *Linnaeus University, Sweden*
Older Residents in the Shadow of Welfare Policy: An Analysis of Swedish Housing Allowance from a Historical and Age Critical Perspective

168.3 Wendy MARTIN, *Brunel University London, United Kingdom*; Kirsten ELLISON, *Trent University, Canada*; Barbara MARSHALL, *Trent University, Canada* and Isabel PEDERSEN, *Ontario Tech University, Canada*
Visualizing the Datasphere: Representations of Old Bodies and Their Data in Promotional Images of Smart Sensor Technologies for Ageing at Home

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

168.4 Wing sun CHAN, *Caritas Institute of Higher Education, Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Ka yi FUNG, *Caritas Institute of Higher Education, Hong Kong*
Informalising Social Service of Carers' Café in Hong Kong: A Qualitative Social Network Analysis

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

169 Reimagining Active Ageing for New Times

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Virpi TIMONEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Chair: Virpi TIMONEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

169.1 Sigita DOBLYTE, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain* and Roberto GIOSA, *University of Oviedo, Spain*
Why People Work Past Retirement Age: A Meta-Ethnography of Meanings and Motivations in Later-Life Working

169.2 Nathan WIDJAJA, *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*
Barriers and Facilitators to Singaporean Minority Older Adults' Participation in Active Ageing Centres

169.3 Jan Marie FRITZ, *Univ. of Cincinnati and Univ. of Johannesburg, USA*
Addressing the Mandatory Retirement of Older Adults

169.4 Beatrice LAM, *Hong Kong Metropolitan University, Hong Kong*; Cheuk Ki FUNG, *Hong Kong Metropolitan University, Hong Kong* and Cheong Yu, Stephen CHAN, *Caritas Institute of Higher Education, Hong Kong*
Intergenerational Relations and Reimaginings of 'Active Ageing': Observations of Higher Education Students' Understandings of 'Old Age' Under the Covid-19 Pandemic in Hong Kong

15:30-17:20

170 Methods of Ageing Research - Innovative Methodological Pathways

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

170.1 Francisca ORTIZ, *Millennium Institute for Care Research (MICARE), Chile*
Recovering Ego's Memories: Some Reflections from Collecting Personal Networks of Older People

170.2 Christine MAIR, *University of Maryland Baltimore County, USA*
Measuring Contextual Variation in Older Adults' Quality-of-Life Cross-Nationally: Challenges and Opportunities

170.3 Corina ILINCA, *Faculty of Sociology and Social Work, Romania*
On How We Can Measure Intersectional Disadvantage at Old Age

170.4 Anna URBANIAK, *NUI Galway, Ireland* and Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*
Doing Research Together: The Role of Reflexivity in Increasing Inclusivity of Participatory Approaches with Older Adults

170.5 Anna ANDREENKOVA, *Institute for comparative social research CESSI, Russian Federation*
Comparative Longitudinal Surveys of Older Generation As the Method to Study Ageing – Methodological Challenges in Case of Russia

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

171 Ageing with Limited Family Ties

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Bussarawan TEERAWICHITCHAINAN, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Christine MAIR, *University of Maryland Baltimore County, USA*

Chair: Bussarawan TEERAWICHITCHAINAN, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Co-Chair: Christine MAIR, *University of Maryland Baltimore County, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

171.1 Wiraporn POTHISIRI, *College of Population Studies, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand*
Childlessness and the Unmet Need for Long-Term Care: Insights from a Mixed-Methods Approach

171.2 Dan TANG, *Renmin University of China, China*
The Social Networks and Mental Health of Chinese Older Adults Who Have the Only Child

171.3 Tran MINH THI, *Vietnam Journal of Family and Gender Studies, Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Vietnam*
Involvement of Vietnamese Elder in Economic Activities in the Lens of Family Ties, Low Institutional Coverage, and Gender Identity

171.4 Pildoo SUNG, *Duke-NUS Medical School, Singapore*
Change in Social Network Types Among Older Adults before and during the COVID-19 Pandemic

171.5 Jinfeng LI, *Institute of Developmental Psychology, Beijing Normal University, China* and Dahua WANG, *Institute of Developmental Psychology, Beijing Normal University, China*
Public Attitudes As the Macro-System of the Parents Who Lost Their Only Child: Ethical Imputation, Predicament Awareness, and Help Willingness

171.6 Phuong DANG, *Institute of Sociology, VASS, Vietnam* and Katsumi SHIMANE, *Senshu University, Japan*
Living Alone in a Children-Oriented Space: The Well-Being of Vietnamese Elderly

10:30-12:20

172 Adult Children's Life Transitions, Intergenerational Support and Older Parent's Wellbeing

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Pei-Chun KO, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Karla WAZINSKI, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

172.1 Fengxian QIU, *Anhui Normal University, China*; Heying ZHAN, *Georgia State University, USA* and Anna THOMAS, *Anhui Normal University, China*
Adaptive Cultural Solidarity: Understanding the Livelihood of Older Adults in Rural China — a Case Study of Lee Village

172.2 Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Elizabeth ADAMSON, *Social Policy Research Centre, UNSW, Australia*; Lyn CRAIG, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Alison WILLIAMS, *Sydney University, Australia* and Virpi TIMONEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Work and Care Decision Making across Genders and Generations: The Case of Grandparent Childcare

172.3 Xue BAI, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*; Chang LIU, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*; Shuai ZHOU, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*; Chi-Ko LEE, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong* and Xiaogang WU, *New York University Shanghai, Hong Kong*
A Mixed-Method Study of Intergenerational Care Planning in Ageing Families: The Roles of Economic and Social Capital

172.4 Gülçin CON WRIGHT, *TED University, Turkey*; Selenay KAŞKAYA, *TED University, Turkey* and Asya FILIZ, *TED University, Turkey*
Adult Children's Transition in or out of Marriage and Older Parents' Wellbeing in Turkish Families

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

172.5 Xue BAI, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*; Joanne LUK, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*; Ranran HE, *Purdue University, USA*; Tongling XU, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong* and Daniel LAI, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Intergenerationally Tied Relocation and Care Circulation in Ageing Families

172.6 Emilia KRAMKOWSKA, *University of Białystok, Poland*
Who Should Take Care of a Dependent Elderly Person? the Perspective of Representatives of Different Generations

17:30-19:20

JS-108 Migration and Ageing

Committees: *RC11 Sociology of Aging (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-108.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

173 Formal and Informal Care in Later Life

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

173.1 Monika PALMBERGER, *Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology, Austria* and Barbara GOETSCH, *Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology, University of Vienna, Austria*
Ageing in Times of the Pandemic: Experiencing the COVID-19 Pandemic in Care Institutions

173.2 Elisa RAMIREZ-MUÑOZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*; Ana LARA-MERCHAN, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain* and Juan Manuel GARCIA GONZALEZ, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain*
"Thank You for Asking Us and for Listening to Us": Experiences of Loneliness and Emotional Health Among Older Adults Living in Long-Term Care Facilities

173.3 Ayushi DUBE, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India* and Anindita CHAKRABARTI, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Elderly Caregiving, Family, and Inheritance: Narratives from the District Court of Ayodhya (India)

173.4 Asmita AASAAVARI, *University of Connecticut, USA*
Aging, Family Ties and Cultures of Caregiving

173.5 Adam MURSAL, *University of Waterloo, Canada* and Weizhen DONG, *University of Waterloo, Canada*
Eldercare Staffing Issues & Personal Support Workers' (PSW) Job Quality

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

173.6 Heidi GAUTUN, *Norwegian Social Research Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway* and Christopher BRATT, *Department of Psychology, Inland Norway University of Applied Sciences, Lillehammer, Norway*
Employees As Caregivers for Older Parents

173.7 Gigi LAM, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*
Pilot Scheme on Community Care Service Voucher for the Elderly in Hong Kong: Implications for Long-Term Care Policy

173.8 Emilia KRAMKOWSKA, *University of Białystok, Poland*
Who Should Take Care of a Dependent Elderly Person? the Perspective of Representatives of Different Generations

10:30-12:20

JS-125 Linking Ages - Pathways to Cross-Fertilizing the Fields of Age and Childhood Studies

Committees: *RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); RC11 Sociology of Aging*

See Joint Session Details for JS-125.

15:30-17:20

174 Ageing, Care and Technology

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Matthew LARIVIERE, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*

Chair: Milena FELDMANN, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

174.1 Jenny WAYCOTT, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Ryan M. KELLY, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Steven BAKER, *Griffith University, Australia* and Wei ZHAO, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Technology for Personalised Enrichment in Aged Care: A Care Ethics Perspective

174.2 Marcus PERSSON, *Linköping University, Sweden*; David REDMALM, *Uppsala University, Sweden*; Clara IVERSEN, *Uppsala University, Sweden* and Lisa FERM, *Linköpings University, Sweden*
Caregivers' Practical, Social, and Ethical Competence When Using Robotic Animals.

174.3 Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*
Virtual Visits Home: Belonging and Home-Making in and across Place in Residential Care

174.4 Matthew LARIVIERE, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
The Digital Care Promissory: Unresolved Contemporary Care Problems and Imagined Techno-Futures

174.5 Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Jenny WAYCOTT, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia*; Evonne MILLER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Jacqueline JOHNSTON, *Rural Northwest Health, Australia*; Tabitha PORTER, *Benetas, Australia* and Wendy JAMES, *Rural Northwest Health, Australia*
Virtual Reality in Aged Care: A Relational Analysis of a Technological Innovation

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

174.6 Louise MCCABE, *University of Stirling, United Kingdom*; Veronica MONTES DE OCA ZAVALA, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*; Nereide CURRERI, *University of Stirling, United Kingdom*; Marissa VIVALDO, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico* and M. Concepcion ARROYO, *Universidad Juarez del Estado de Durango, Mexico*
The Social Lives of Older People Living in Mexico and Scotland during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Reflections on Rights, Resources and Technology

174.7 Grzegorz GAWRON, *University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland*
Co-Production Practices in Public Social Services during the COVID-19 Lockdown Period. the Example from Centers for Seniors Organized Under the Polish Government's Multiannual Program "Senior+".

174.8 Niccolo MORELLI, *University of Genova, Italy*
What Role for Digital Health in an Ageing World? Patterns of (in)Disposition

175.3 Jolanta PEREK-BIALAS, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*; Natalia KRYGOWSKA-NOWAK, *Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland*; Anna SZCZUCKA, *Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland* and Joanna KWINTA-ODRZYWOLEK, *Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland*
Co-Creation As Innovative Way to Include Older Persons in Age-Friendly Environment

10:30-12:20

JS-142 Participation Chances, Inequality and Risks of Exclusion in Prolonged Working Lives in Europe

Committees: RC11 *Sociology of Aging (Host)*; RC30 *Sociology of Work*

See Joint Session Details for JS-142.

12:30-14:20

176 Ageing, Autonomy and Connectedness

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sandra TORRES, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

Chair: Sandra TORRES, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

176.1 Satu HEIKKINEN, *Karlstad university, Sweden* and Andreas HENRIKSSON, *Karlstad University, Sweden*
Dancing for Intimacy – Transformation of Relationships in Old Age

176.2 Cecile CARRA, *LEM - CNRS - UMR 9221, France* and Julie VARLET, *Université d'Artois- LEM - CNRS - UMR 9221, France*
Empowerment and Older People: Characteristics of French-Language Research

176.3 Laura HURD, *The University of British Columbia, Canada* and Lynda LI, *School of Kinesiology, The University of British Columbia, Canada*
LGBTQ+ Older Adults' Perceptions and Experiences of Aging

176.4 Peta COOK, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Contextualising Age-Friendly Communities: Moving Beyond the World Health Organization

14:30-16:20

177 Retirement in the 21st Century

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Anna URBANIAK, *NUI Galway, Austria*

Chair: Anna URBANIAK, *NUI Galway, Austria*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

177.1 Danuta ZYCZYNSKA-CIOLEK, *Instytut Filozofii i Socjologii PAN, Poland*; Ewa POTEPA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland* and Piotr DRYGAS, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Social Justice Perceptions Among Recipients of the Lowest Pensions in Poland

177.2 Daisuke WATANABE, *3-3-1 Kichijoji-kitamachi, Japan*
An Analysis of Career and Retirement Pattern in Old Age

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

175 Ageing Better By Design - Activation, Co-Production and Social Inclusion of Older People

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Grzegorz GAWRON, *University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland* and Paulina ROJEK-ADAMEK, *Pedagogical University of Kraków, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

175.1 Letizia CARRERA, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy* and Paolo CONTINI, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy*
The Role of Urban Policies in Countering the Relational Loneliness of Older Citizens: Public Spaces and Cohousing

175.2 Andrzej KLIMCZUK, *Warsaw School of Economics, Poland*
Design and Co-Design in the Concept and Policy of Building a Future Society for All Ages

177.3 Carolina NORDLINDER, *Univerity of Gavle, Sweden*;
Peter ÖBERG, *University of Gavle, Sweden*; Pär GRELL,
University of Gavle, Sweden; Gunnar BERGSTROM, *University
of Gavle, Sweden* and Pia THAM, *University of Gavle, Sweden*
***What Predicts Retirement Intentions of Older Workers (45+)
in Long-Term-Care? a Systematic Review***

177.4 Reema SEN, *Case Western Reserve University, USA*
Midlife Retirement Priorities of Professionals in India

RC12

Sociology of Law

Program Coordinators: Lisa WEBLEY, *University of Birmingham, United Kingdom* and Robyn HOLDER, *Griffith University, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

178 Meaning-Making, Emotion and Legal Change

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Sharyn ROACH ANLEU, *Flinders University, Australia*

Chair: Meredith ROSSNER, *The Australian National University, Australia*

Discussant: Sharyn ROACH ANLEU, *Flinders University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

178.1 Sharyn ROACH ANLEU, *Flinders University, Australia* and Kathy MACK, *College of Business, Government & Law, Australia*
The Challenges of Emotion and Judging

178.2 Adriana ROMERO SANCHEZ, *University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA*
'Justice Orthopedics': Meanings and Sensibilities and Penal Change in Colombia

178.3 Elena LLORCA ASENSI, *University of Alicante, Spain*; Alexander SÁNCHEZ DÍAZ, *University of Alicante, Spain*; Maria Elena FABREGAT CABRERA, *University of Alicante, Spain* and Raul RUIZ CALLADO, *University of Alicante, Spain*
"Why Can't We?" Disinformation and Right to Self-Determination. the Catalan Conflict on Twitter

15:30-17:20

179 Lay Participation in Justice

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Robyn HOLDER, *Griffith University, Australia*

Chair: Robyn HOLDER, *Griffith University, Australia*

Discussant: Meredith ROSSNER, *The Australian National University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

179.1 Meredith EDELMAN, *Monash Business School, Australia*
Rethinking Responses to Corporate Wrongdoing

179.2 John TAGGART, *Queen's University, Belfast, United Kingdom*
Intermediaries As Facilitators of Lay Participation in the Criminal Justice System

179.3 Theodora PUTRI, *School of Regulation and Global Governance (RegNet), The Australian National University, Australia*
Csos' Participation in Creating Indonesia's Gender Responsive Criminal Justice System

179.4 Meredith ROSSNER, *The Australian National University, Australia*; Martha MCCURDY, *UNISG, Switzerland* and David TAIT, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Active or Passive Participants? How Higher Levels of Involvement By Lay Participants Impacts on Their Experience of Justice.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

180 Rights, Experts and Access to Justice

Language: French, Spanish, English

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Dani RUDNICKI, *Universidade La Salle - Brazil, Brazil*

Chair: John TAGGART, *Queen's University, Belfast, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

180.1 Elina SAGNE-OLLIKAINEN, *Abo akademi, Finland*
Understanding the Work of Public Actors in the Human Rights Field in Finland

180.2 Montserrat GAS AIXENDRI, *Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Spain*
Cómo Avanzar Hacia Una Aplicación Global y Multicultural Del Sistema De Derechos Humanos: El Paradigma De La Libertad Religiosa y La Igualdad De Género

180.3 Masatoshi KATO, *Ritsumeikan University, Japan*
Merits and Limits of the Judicial System As a Conflict Resolution Mechanism in Japan: The Case of the Social Conflict in Isahaya City

180.4 Emily SCHINDELER, *Griffith University, Australia*
The Problematic Nature of Experts and Expertise in the Justice System

15:30-17:20

181 Sociology of Complaints and Complaint Bodies

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Julia DAHLVIK, *University of Applied Sciences FH Campus Wien, Austria*

Chair: Julia DAHLVIK, *University of Applied Sciences FH Campus Wien, Austria*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

181.1 Sarah MOORE, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*
Crisis Diverted: The Handling of Public Crises in the Twenty-First Century

181.2 David PLATER, *South Australian Law Reform Institute, Australia*; Robyn HOLDER, *Griffith University, Australia* and Mary ILIADIS, *Deakin University, Australia*
Judicial Review and Prosecution Accountability, England and Wales

181.3 Guinea ADAMASTOS, *PhD Scholar, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi, India*
Burden of Legal Access: Extrajudicial Grievance Redressal By Victims of Sexual Harassment in Indian Legal Profession

181.4 Anita STUHMCKE, *University of Technology of Sydney, Australia* and Matthew GROVES, *Deakin University, Australia*
What can be learned from Ombudsman mistakes?

17:30-19:20

182 Authoritarian and Conservative Rules in Contemporary Societies: The Battlefield of Women's Rights and Freedom. Part I**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Barbara BELLO, *University of Milano, Italy* and Letizia MANCINI, *University of Milan, Italy***Chair:** Meredith EDELMAN, *Monash Business School, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****182.1** Giovanna TRUDA, *University of Salerno, Italy*
*The Society of "Women's Rights": Socio-Economic Dynamics and Political Dimension***182.2** Tamara KUENNEN, *University of Denver, USA*
*Institutional and Cultural "Power and Control": Uncovering the History of the Power and Control Wheel***182.3** Mirabelle CHI EPSE OKEZIE, *Tasmania University, Australia*
*Harm Perpetrated with Good Intentions: Breast Ironing in Cameroon***182.4** Cynthia BOWMAN, *Cornell Law School, USA*
*Socialist Feminism (By Some Name) Is the Only Effective Antidote to Authoritarianism***182.5** Tracy TURNER, *Associate Dean for Learning Outcomes, Southwestern Law School, Los Angeles, California USA, USA*
*Binary Sports As a Cage for Women and Gender Minorities***Wednesday 28 June**

15:30-17:20

JS-76 The Criminalization of Struggles for Rights, Democratic Regression, and Legal Mobilisation. Part I**Committees:** RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC12 Sociology of Law*

See Joint Session Details for JS-76.

19:30-20:50

183 RC12 Business Meeting**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Thursday 29 June**

10:30-12:20

184 Judicialization of Social Problems and Governance of Security in Comparative Perspectives**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada***Chair:** Masayuki MURAYAMA, *Meiji University, Japan***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****184.1** George PAVLICH, *University of Alberta, Canada*
*A Sociology of Accusation: Social Lore, Law, and the Criminally Accused***184.2** Lindy HEINECKEN, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa* and Wilhelm JANSE VAN RENSBURG, *SIGLA, Stellenbosch University, South Africa*
*Military Deployment during Covid-19: Implications for Security Sector Governance and Civil Oversight***184.3** Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia*
*Legal Need in Australia: Towards a Shared Definition and Conceptual Understanding***184.4** Georgia STORM, *James Cook University, Australia*
*Indigenous Justice Inequity and Solicitor Conduct: Judicializing Indigenous Cultural Security in Legal Practitioner-Client Relations***DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:****184.5** Apei SONG, *University of New South Wales (UNSW), Australia*
Multiple Logic, Multi-Governance, and Legal Consciousness: A Legal Sociological Analysis of Urban Drug Management in China

17:30-19:20

185 RC12 WG on Civil Justice and Dispute Resolution**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Masayuki MURAYAMA, *Meiji University, Japan* and Luigi COMINELLI, *University of Milan, Italy***Chair:** Robyn HOLDER, *Griffith University, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****185.1** Takayuki II, *Senshu University, Japan*
*Japanese Lawyers from 2010 to 2020: In Comparison to Chicago Lawyers***185.2** Alysia BLACKHAM, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
*Enabling Access to Justice? Conciliation and Dispute Resolution in Equality Law***185.3** Masayuki MURAYAMA, *Meiji University, Japan*
*How Do Consumers Choose Lawyers? Findings of a Japanese Survey***185.4** Jean DE MUNCK, *Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium*
*Mediation and Human Rights As Legal Supports of the Constitutionalization of Western Family Systems***185.5** Luz CARDONA ACUNA, *Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila, Mexico* and Juan Camilo PORTELA, *Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila, Mexico*
Interaction, Process, and Moral Dispute: An Interactionist and Processual Approach to the Study of Legal Change

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

186 Sociology of Hate Speech Laws. 1

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Monireh MOHAMMADI, York University, Canada

Chair: Arunita DAS, York University, Canada

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

186.1 Monireh MOHAMMADI, York University, Canada
Free Speech and Its Limit

186.2 Ayako HATANO, University of Oxford, Japan
Hate Speech and Internalisation of International Human Rights: A Case Study of the Social Movement Against Racism and Anti-Hate Speech Law in Japan

186.3 Harshita SWAMI, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India
The Ideals of Justice and Equality Vis-à-Vis Indian Legal System: Assessing Requirement of Special Hate Crime Laws in India

15:30-17:20

187 Sociology of Hate Speech Laws. 2

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Monireh MOHAMMADI, York University, Canada

Chair: Monireh MOHAMMADI, York University, Canada

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

187.1 Anuradha SINGH, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India
Hurt Sentiments and the Law in Independent India: Liberal Rights, Caste- Hate Speech and Redressal

187.2 Ephraim BARRERA, University of Ottawa - Centre for Law, Technology and Society, Canada
Online Speech Laws in Modern Democracies: Understanding Social Effects on Democratic Participation and the Rational Agency of Citizens

187.3 Valerie JENNESS, University of California, USA and Stefan VOGLER, NORC, USA
Policing the Rainbow: An Empirical Examination of LGBTQ+ People's Perceptions of Police As Friend or Foe in the Context of "Trust in Government"

187.4 Arunita DAS, York University, Canada
Hate Speech and Social Media: Understanding the Changing Nature of Far-Right Extremism in Canada

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

188 Migration and Gendered Labour

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Rashmi JAIN, Rajasthan University, India

Chair: Ayako HATANO, University of Oxford, Japan

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

188.1 Rashmi JAIN, Rajasthan University, India
Introspecting Gendered Migration: A Cross Cultural Perspective

188.2 Hideki TARUMOTO, Waseda University, Japan
Migration, Citizenship, and Gender in East Asia

188.3 Manish YADAV, Department of Sociology, University of Rajasthan, India
Global Migration: Sexuality, Law and Class-Based Mobility Capital of Indian Gay Men

188.4 Yashasvi SURANA, University of Rajasthan, India; Naveen SINGH, UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN, India; Mahesh CHOUDHARY, university of rajasthan, India and Mohita SHARMA, Kanoria PG Mahila Mahavidalaya, India
Effects of Migration and HIV Status of Bridge Groups on Their Families in India.

188.5 Achalie KUMARAGE, School of Regulation and Global Governance, Australian National University, Australia
Re-Thinking Collective Bargaining: Legal and Normative Pluralism As an Instrument in Labour Rights Negotiations

10:30-12:20

JS-143 Tax Policies and Tax Optimization Practices

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC12 Sociology of Law

See Joint Session Details for JS-143.

12:30-14:20

189 Social System and Legal Systems

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Germano SCHWARTZ, UniRitter, Brazil

Chair: Emily SCHINDELER, Griffith University, Australia

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

189.1 Germano SCHWARTZ, UniRitter, Brazil and Renata COSTA, Unilasalle, Brazil
Algonormative Expectations

189.2 Monjurul AHSAN, Center for Climate Justice-Bangladesh (CCJ-B), Bangladesh
Historical Injustice and Displacement of Indigenous Community from Their Ancestral Land and Territory: A Case Study in Munda Community of Bangladesh

189.3 Stefania Adriana BEVILACQUA, Alma Mater Studiorum Bologna, Italy
A Sociological Perspective on European LAW

RC13

Sociology of Leisure

Program Coordinator: Sukant CHAUDHURY,
University of Lucknow, India

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

190 Leisure during the Period of Pandemic and Resurgent Authoritarianism, Presidential Session

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Sukant CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*

Chair: Prem Sagar VIVEK, *University of Mumbai, India*

Co-Chair: Rasul MOWATT, *North Carolina State University, USA*

Panelists: Rashmi JAIN, *Rajasthan University, India*; Pranjal SARMA, *Dibrugarh University, India* and Sukant CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

191 Leisure and Global Housing Crises

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Alan LAW, *Trent University, Canada*

Chair: Prem Sagar VIVEK, *University of Mumbai, India*

Co-Chair: Sandip CHAUDHARI, *SBES College of Art and Commerce, Aurangabad-431001(India), India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

191.1 Smita CHAKRABORTY, *Jhargram Raj College, Girls' Wing, India* and Dr. Ruby SAIN, *Adamas University, India*
Slums, Space and Seat of Power: A Study of Slum Sustainability in Kolkata

191.2 Pekka RASANEN, *University of Turku, Finland*; Atte OKSANEN, *Tampere University, Finland*; Markus KAAKINEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*; James HAWDON, *Virginia Tech, USA* and Donna SEDGWICK, *Virginia Tech, USA*
Exposure to Online Fake News on Covid-19 and Consumption Preferences. a Comparison of the United States and Finland

191.3 Xianfei XU, *Zhejiang Daily Press Group, China*
How to Build a Community Life Linked By Leisure Activities

15:30-17:20

192 Happiness in Post Pandemic Era: A Global Perspective

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Rashmi JAIN, *Rajasthan University, India*

Chair: Kali JHA, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar, MP, India*

Co-Chair: Dilip KHAIRNAR, *Deogiri College, Aurangabad, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

192.1 M. M. Abdullah SONY, *University of Debrecen, Hungary*; Tuhin ROY, *Sociology Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh* and Ruby SAIN, *Adamas University, India*
Recreation Scenario of Bangladeshi Transgender People amid New Normal Era

192.2 Nidhi BANSAL, *Malaviya National Institute of Technology, India* and Jagatpal SINGH, *Malaviya National Institute of Technology Jaipur, India*
Relation between Leisure and Social Activities (LSA) Participation and Perceived Life Satisfaction Among the Elderly: Evidences from Longitudinal Ageing Study in India, Wave-1

192.3 Qingyue WU, *Zhejiang University, China* and Huimei LIU, *Zhejiang University, China*
Resonance in Digital Leisure in the Post-Covid 19 Era -- a Case of the App Red in China

192.4 Anuja JAIN, *University of Rajasthan jaipur, India*
Reinvigorating Happiness of Leisure in Covid Times

192.5 Smita CHAKRABORTY, *Jhargram Raj College, Girls' Wing, India* and Dr. Ruby SAIN, *Adamas University, India*
Pleasure of Piety: Post-Pandemic Spiritual Well-Being Among Santhal Youths in Jhargram

192.6 Pradeep KUMAR, *I.N.M.P.G College, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India, India* and Deepti KAUSHIK, *Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India*
To be a Tourist or Not : After Effects of Covid on Tourism

17:30-19:20

193 Assessing Leisure and Tourism in Post Pandemic Era

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Misri Lal VERMA, *Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University (CSJMU), India*

Chair: Jhaverbhai PATEL, *School of Social Sciences, India*

Co-Chair: Machhindra SAKATE, *MRJM College, Umbraj, Karad, India, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

193.1 Manavjeet KAUR, *Panjab University Chandigarh, India*
Leisure As Drug Abuse Among Youth

193.2 Lan WEI, *South China Normal University, China*
A Study of the Optimized Path of Leisure Lifestyle in the Post-COVID-19 Era—Based on the Ecological View of Marxism

193.3 Ibrahim ABRAHAM, *Federation University Australia, Australia*
Serious Leisure and Leisure Time in Postsecular Perspective

193.4 Gobind SINGH, *HEMVATI NANDAN BAHUGUNA GARHWAL UNIVERSITY, SRINAGAR, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA, India* and Onima SHARMA, *D.A.V. (PG) College, Dehradun; Uttarakhand, India*
Sustainable ECO-Tourism in Post Pandemic Era: A Study of Uttarakhand Himalayan Region

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

194 Leisure Time Activities, It's Changing Patterns and Development.

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Smita AWACHAR, *Tantradhyna nagar, India*

Chair: Ma HUIDI, *Chinese National Academy of Arts, China*

Co-Chair: Onima SHARMA, *Adhohiwala-II, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

194.1 Jarmo KALLUNKI, *Tampere University, Finland*; Ossi SIRKKA, *Tampere University, Finland*; Riie HEIKKILÄ, *Tampere University, Finland* and Semi PURHONEN, *Tampere University, Finland*

Highbrow, Popular and Mundane Leisure Participation, 1981–2017: The Meltdown Scenario, Omnivores and Snobs Re-Visited

194.2 Kenneth ROBERTS, *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom*

Time Use, Work and Leisure in the UK before, during, between and Following the COVID-19 Lockdowns

194.3 Pranjal SARMA, *Dibrugarh University, India*
Leisure Activities and Development of Tourism in Leh, India

194.4 Shiyi LUO, *Beijing Sport University, China* and Hui TIAN, *Beijing Sport University, China*

Understanding Leisure Constraints of Chinese College Students: A Comparison of Participants and Non-Participants

194.5 Machhindra SAKATE, *MRJM College, Umbraj, Karad, India, India*
Challenges to Tamasha - a Folk Art : A Case Study in Satara and Sangli District of Maharashtra, India.

194.6 Anju BENIWAL, *Government Meera Girls College, Udaipur (Rajasthan), India*
Women's Leisure and Constraints to Leisure Participation: Indian Perspectives

194.7 Rahul HAJARE, *DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY ASC COLLEGE BADNAPUR INDIA, India*
Revival of Family and Personal Relations with Free Time during Imposed Lockdown: A Study Conducted in Metro City

194.8 Sandip CHAUDHARI, *SBES College of Artst and Commerce, Aurangabad-431001(India), India*
Leisure Activities of Youth in Metropolitan City: A Sociological Analysis

17:30-19:20

195 Well-Being and Leisure Activities during COVID-19 Pandemic

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Anju BENIWAL, *Government Meera Girls College, Udaipur, India*

Chair: Kenneth ROBERTS, *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom*

Co-Chair: Rashmi JAIN, *Rajasthan University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

195.1 Ma HUIDI, *Chinese National Academy of Arts, China*
How Leisure Is Being Swallowed up By Authoritarianism

195.2 Pratap PINJANI, *NCPSL, Education Ministry, Govt. Of India, New Delhi, India*
Revaluating Leisure and Its Role in Combating COVID-19

195.3 Ka yi FUNG, *Caritas Institute of Higher Education, Hong Kong* and Gina LAI, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Mutual Support and the Influences of Playing Pokemon Go on Older People amid the COVID-19 Pandemic in Hong Kong

195.4 Onima SHARMA, *Adhohiwala-II, India* and Gobind SINGH, *HEMVATI NANDAN BAHUGUNA GARHWAL UNIVERSITY, SRINAGAR, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA, India*
Leisure Activities and Mental Well Being of Youth in India during COVID-19 Pandemic Lockdown

195.5 Anju BENIWAL, *Government Meera Girls College, Udaipur (Rajasthan), India*
Leisure and Well-Being of Indian Youth during COVID-19 Pandemic

195.6 Kali JHA, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar, MP, India*
COVID: Emerging Pattern of Leisure and Women in India

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

196 Authority and Leisure: A Symbiotic Dichotomy ?

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Bhavna SOOD, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India, India*

Chair: Ibrahim ABRAHAM, *Federation University Australia, Australia*

Co-Chair: Pranoti CHIRMULEY, *St Xavier's College Mumbai, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

196.1 Rasul MOWATT, *North Carolina State University, USA*
The White Nationalist Animation of Public Space

196.2 Alberto DE MASCELLIS, *Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*
Power and Play in Nerd Subculture: The "Most Efficient Tactics Available"

196.3 Alan LAW, *Trent University, Canada*
Leisure As Resistance

196.4 Shuyang DA, *Westlake University, China* and Huimei LIU, *Zhejiang University, China*
Leisure As Political Discourse: Leisure and the National Development of Contemporary China

196.5 Sanjay TEWARI, *LN Mithila University, India*
Measuring Leisure Practices and Sports through the Lenses of Their Contribution to Education

196.6 Jhaverbhai PATEL, *Gujarat university Ahmedabad India., India* and Subhashchandra PANDAR, *Gujarat Vidyapith, India*
M.a. Student's Activities in Leisure Time-a Sociological Inquiry.

196.7 Dilip KHAIRNAR, *Deogiri College, Aurangabad, India* and Kulkarni KULKARNI MANJITA, *st.Mira's College for Girls, Pune India, India*
Utilization of Leisure Time By the Ageing through the Various Platform of Social Media: A Sociological Study with Indian Context

15:30-17:20

197 Leisurement during the Period of COVID-19 Pandemic and Resurgent Authoritarianism

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Prem Sagar VIVEK, *University of Mumbai, India*

Chair: Smita AWACHAR, *Tantradhyna nagar, India*

Co-Chair: Bhavna SOOD, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

197.1 Sukant CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*
Leisure in Indian Society during the Period of COVID-19: Some Issues

197.2 Kali JHA, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar, MP, India*
COVID: Leisure and Women in India: A Sociological Study

197.3 Priya GARG, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar, M.P., India*
Leisure and Tourism in India: A Study of Housewives of Marwar Region during COVID-19

197.4 Pranoti CHIRMULEY, *St Xavier's College Mumbai, India*
Leisure As a Joke and As a Survival Kit.

19:30-20:50

198 RC13 Business Meeting

Location: M15 (Crown)

Friday 30 June

15:30-17:20

199 Socio-Political Scenario of Drugs and Leisure in Global Era

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Pranjal SARMA, *Dibrugarh University, India*

Chair: Sukant CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*

Co-Chair: Alan LAW, *Trent University, Canada*

Panelist: Anju BENIWAL, *Government Meera Girls College, Udaipur, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

199.1 Pranjal SARMA, *Dibrugarh University, India*
Drugs, Leisure and Society in Assam, India : A Sociological Study

199.2 Smita AWACHAR, *Tantradhyna nagar, India*
Role of Social Organisation in Shaping Leisure Activities in India

199.3 Sandhya CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*
ISSUE of Drug and Leisure: Qualitative Analysis of CASES from Lucknow, India

199.4 Rajni BALA, *Baring Union Christian College, Batala, India*
Experiencing Stigma and Discrimination: A Study of Women Drug Abusers of Punjab

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

200 Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Leisure: Adaptation of New Lifestyle during Lockdown

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Pratima VERMA, *CSJM University, India*

Chair: Smita CHAKRABORTY, *Jhargram Raj College, Girls' Wing, India*

Co-Chair: Sanjay TEWARI, *LN Mithila University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

200.1 Rui GOMES, *University of Coimbra, Centre for Social Studies, Portugal*
Confined Leisures

200.2 Jack MELTON, *School of Social and Political Sciences, Australia*
A Lot's Gonna Change: Researching Fan Perceptions of Live Music Cancellations Due to the COVID-19 Pandemic

200.3 Kexin YU, *International Christian University, Japan*
How People Cope With Their Life Under the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Role of Watching YouTube Consumer-Generated Advertising (CGA) Videos as a Leisure Activity

200.4 Prashant ANAND, *University of Lucknow, India*
Leisure during COVID-19 Pandemic Among Undergrad Students: A Study of Lucknow City, India

200.5 Samprikta CHATTERJEE, *BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY, India*
Gender Inequality and Leisure: A Study of Women in the Traditional Family Setup of Varanasi

12:30-14:20

201 Changing Nature of Leisure Activities during Resurgent Authoritarianism

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Sukant CHAUDHURY, *University of Lucknow, India*

Chair: Alan LAW, *Trent University, Canada*

Co-Chair: Smita AWACHAR, *Tantradhyna nagar, India*

Panelists: Kenneth ROBERTS, *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom* and Ma HUIDI, *Leisure Studies, Center of Chinese National Academy of Arts., China*

RC14

Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture

Program Coordinator: Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, *Panteion University, Greece*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

202 The Presentation of Self: Fads and Fades of the Contemporary Social Link

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, *Panteion University, Greece*

Chair: Laurence LAROCHELLE, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

202.1 Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, *Panteion University, Greece*
Relations of Non-Commitment: Analyzing the Contemporary Sociality

202.2 Huanqi WANG, *individual, China*
How Has Social Media Made the Distinction between 'Online' and 'Offline' Identity Increasingly Irrelevant?

202.3 Yui-fung YIP, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Online Rumors As a Participatory Theatre: The Case of Covid-19 Pandemic in Hong Kong

202.4 Bruno Marco Cuer DOS SANTOS, *Universidade Federal de São Paulo, Brazil*
The Case of "Intellectuals" and "Digital Influence" in Brazil

202.5 Sagar SINGH, *Central University of Rajasthan, India*
Constituting and De-Constituting the Discursive Social Links in Youtube Comments Thread

202.6 Dauda BUSARI, *University of Ibadan, Nigeria*
Toxicity of Cancel Culture and Performance of Radicalism Among Young People in Nigeria

15:30-17:20

203 TV Series in the Era of Digitalization, Globalization and Resurgent Authoritarianism

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Laurence LAROCHELLE, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*

Chair: Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, *Panteion University, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

203.1 Laurence LAROCHELLE, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*
From Television to Netflix: Overcoming Political Authoritarianism

203.2 Yassine AKHIATE, *Mohammed V University of Rabat, Morocco* and Mohamed BENDAHAN, *Mohammed V, University of Rabat, Kingdom Of Morocco, Morocco*
The Impact of Turkish and Korean Series on the Production and Consumption of Television Content in the Maghreb Country

203.3 Virendra P. SINGH, *Chairman, GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), Raj Nagar Extension Ghaziabad-201017, India, India*
The Power of Social Media and the Crisis in the Indian Cine Industry

203.4 Alex, lih-shing CHAN, *Soka University, Hong Kong*
Streaming Reality Show and Japan's Soft Power

203.5 Usha RANA, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya Central Univ., India*
Reflections of Psycho-Sociological Impacts of OTT Platforms: A Study from Central India

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

203.6 Tulio ROSSI, *Universidade Federal de Uberlandia, Brazil*
Contributions of the Sociology of Cinema for Analysing Streaming TV Shows

203.7 Ying LAI, *Beijing Normal University, China*
Digital Miracle and Reality Undercurrents: The Globalization of Original Streaming Films and Series for Regional Industries

19:30-20:50

204 RC14 Business Meeting

Location: M1 (Crown)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-24 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part IV

Committees: RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology (Host)*; RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture*

See Joint Session Details for JS-24.

10:30-12:20

205 The Political Communication of Russia-Ukraine War: Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies. La Communication Politique De La Guerre d'Ukraine : Pour Une Sociologie d'Un Emmêlement Politique, Économique Et Culturel.

Language: French, English

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, Panteion University, Greece

Chair: Laurence LAROCHELLE, Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

205.1 Christiana CONSTANTOPOULOU, Panteion University, Greece
Les Frontières De l'Europe : « Reportant » La Guerre d'Ukraine

205.2 Francesca GRECO, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy; Gevisa LA ROCCA, University Kore of Enna, Italy and Giovanni BOCCIA ARTIERI, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy
Evolution De L'opinion Publique Occidentale Sur Le Conflit Russo-Ukrainien Dans La Twittersphère

205.3 Oksana LYCHKOVSKA-NEBOT, Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Ukraine
Les Stratégies De La Guerre Informationnelle Comme Les Éléments Cruciaux De La Guerre Contemporaine : Le Cas De La Guerre En Ukraine

15:30-17:20

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC07 Futures Research RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-39.

17:30-19:20

206 Crisis Discourse, Propaganda Technologies and Information Warfare in the New War's Era: Challenges and Solutions

Language: English, French

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Oksana LYCHKOVSKA-NEBOT, Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Ukraine

Chair: Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, Universidad Complutense, Spain

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

206.1 Yuliia SOROKA, N.V. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine
Voiceless People in the Field of (information) War

206.2 Valeria DONATO, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy
Visibility and Propaganda in TikTok: #Ukraine and #Russia

206.3 Sharon AVITAL, Tel Aviv University, Israel
The Rhetoric of Crisis during the Vaccination Campaign- Truth, Lies and Hate

206.4 Muyang LI, York University, Canada
Digital Diplomacy As Authoritarian Practices: A Case-Study of China's Wolf Warrior Diplomacy

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

207 Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part II

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Musa YUSUPOV, Chechen State University, Russian Federation

Chair: Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India

Panelist: Terbi LOYI, Savitribai Phule Pune University, India

Discussant: Timothy MALACARNE, Nevada State College, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

207.1 Terbi LOYI, Savitribai Phule Pune University, India
Music and Everyday Life Perspective

207.2 Timothy MALACARNE, Nevada State College, USA
Tipping Hats, Riding Coattails: Intertextual Reference Networks in American Country Music

207.3 Lide MA, School of Journalism and Communication, Beijing Normal University, China; Xiuli ZHAO, School of Journalism and Communication, Beijing Normal University, China; Beijia REN, School of Journalism and Communication, Hebei University, China and Yuan HE, School of Journalism and Communication, Hebei University, China
The Cross-Genre Dissemination of Platformized Cultural Contents: Computing How Algorithm Erode Cultural Boundaries in China

207.4 Irem ELBIR, Atılım University, Turkey
Raise Your Dissent: Turkish Rap Music within the Popular Culture

207.5 Yubai LI, Department of Sociology, Tsinghua University, China
Ambivalent Resistance: Indie Music, Mobilization and Hong Kong's Localist Movement

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

207.6 Ana SANTOS, Instituto Federal de São Paulo, Brazil
Mass Music and the Meanings of the Feminine: Brazilian Country Music and "Popular Feminism"

207.7 Huanqi WANG, individual, China
Cultural Globalisation, Heavy Metal Music and Chinese Society

10:30-12:20

JS-64 Reconstructing Knowledge: Digital Humanities and Visual Culture

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC57 Visual Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-64.

15:30-17:20

208 Formation of Assertive Identities: New entanglements of Politics and Religion (studies occasioned by the Bahujan culture)**Location:** M1 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Bhup SINGH, DGC Gurugram, India and Alok MEENA, Sanatan Dharam Govt. College, Beawar (Ajmer), India**Chair:** Arvinder A. ANSARI, Jamia Millia Islamia, India**Co-Chair:** Deepti KAUSHIK, Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India**Panelist:** Anju BENIWAL, Government Meera Girls College, Udaipur, India**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

208.1 Durgesh TRIPATHI, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGSIPU), India and Surbhi TANDON, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGSIPU), Sector 16-C, Dwarka, New Delhi-110078., India
Digital Dalits Constructing Subaltern Public Sphere with Their Political Engagement

208.2 Musa YUSUPOV, Chechen State University, Law Faculty, Russian Federation
Ethical Culture and Religion As a Factor of Assertive Identity Formation in Chechnya and the North Caucasus

208.3 Naresh KUMAR, Central University of Gujarat, India
Understanding Dalit Diaspora and Transnational Network across Globe: A Perspectives of Dalit Diasporic Organizations.

208.4 Kajal KALSI, Department of Sociology, University of Jammu, India
Manifestation of Dalit Consciousness through Ravidas Bhakti: A Phenomenological Study from Jammu and Kashmir

208.5 Binoyjyoti DAS, SSS/CSSS, JNU New Delhi, India
Ambedkarite Buddhism and Its Role in Socio-Cultural Transformation of Dalits

17:30-19:20

JS-81 Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part I

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-81.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

209 Contemporary Communication Issues. "Modernity" and "Traditions"**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M1 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, Universidad Complutense, Spain**Chair:** Yassine AKHIATE, Mohammed V University of Rabat, Morocco**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

209.1 Pilar RODRIGUEZ MARTINEZ, University of Almeria, Spain
Social Networks, Extremism and Pro-Violence Attitudes

209.2 Edmondo GRASSI, San Raffaele University, Italy
Artificial Intelligence and Ethical Changes

209.3 Mohammad MOZUMDER, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies, Bangladesh
Virtuous Obsession or Hyperbole: Mobile(phone) Munchies

10:30-12:20

210 Contemporary Communication Issues: Technology and Surveillance**Location:** M1 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India**Chair:** Virendra P. SINGH, Chairman, GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), Raj Nagar Extension Ghaziabad-201017, India, India**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

210.1 Gavin John SMITH, Australian National University, Australia; Mark ANDREJEVIC, Monash University, Australia; Pat O'MALLEY, Australian National University, Australia; Neil SELWYN, Monash University, Australia; Xin GU, Monash University, Australia and Chris O'NEILL, Monash University, Australia
The Elephant in the Gaming Room: The Case of Facial Recognition Technology and Gaming Culture in Australia

210.2 Sahr MALALLA, University of Victoria, Canada
Settler Colonial Surveillance in Canada's Federal Prisons: Engendering Erasures through the Use of Actuarial Instruments in the Security Classification Procedure

210.3 Rasel HUSSAIN, Lingnan University, Hong Kong
Rumours(Gujob) and Misinformation in the Era of Information Society: A Case of Bangladesh Society

210.4 Tyler BRANSTON, University of Victoria, Canada
Ascetic Surveillance and Artificial General Intelligence.

15:30-17:20

211 Contemporary Communication Issues. Digital Futures**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M1 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Oksana LYCHKOVSKA-NEBOT, Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Ukraine**Chair:** Oksana LYCHKOVSKA-NEBOT, Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Ukraine**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

211.1 Sreyasi CHATTERJEE, Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, India
Beyond Binaries: Exploring How New-Media Technology in India Promotes Inclusion of Transgender Persons.

211.2 Marian ADOLF, University of Applied Sciences Vienna, Austria
Strategies Against Epistemological Disorder: Updating Insights into the Connection of Communication, Knowledge, and Identity

211.3 Felipe GARCIA, *Cultural Studies, University of São Paulo, Brazil* and Marcio MORETTO, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Counterpublics and Cancel Culture

211.4 Rima ZILINSKAITE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Prosumption As a Mode of Acting on Web 2.0: Typology

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

212 Creación De Espacios De Participación Y Libertad Informativa. Propuestas Desde La Comunicación Responsable Y La Sociología

Language: Spanish

Location: Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Leticia PORTO PEDROSA, *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain*

Chair: Victoria SANAGUSTIN-FONS, *University of Zaragoza, Spain*

Panelist: Alberto ZUART GARDUNO, *Universidad Autónoma de Chiapas, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

212.1 Maria SANZ-HERNANDEZ, *University of Zaragoza, Spain*; Xaquín PÉREZ-SINDÍN, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Angel ALONSO DOMINGEZ, *University of Oviedo, Spain* and Rosario MARCOS SANTIAGO, *University of León, Spain*
Los Medios De Comunicación Ante La Transición Energética Justa. Discursos y Coaliciones En Territorios Afectados Por La Salida Del Carbón

212.2 Leticia PORTO PEDROSA, *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain*; Luis Manuel MARTÍNEZ DOMÍNGUEZ, *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain* and Marta CARRIÓN SÁNCHEZ, *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain*
Infancia y Relaciones De Amistad Sostenible En Un Mundo Empantallado

212.3 Diana del Consuelo CALDERA GONZÁLEZ, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*; Miguel Agustín ORTEGA CARRILLO, *Universidad de la Salle Bajío A.C., Mexico* and María Guadalupe ARREDONDO HIDALGO, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*
Avatares De La Libertad De Expresión En México

212.4 Kenia DEL ORBE AYALA, *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain* and Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, *Universidad Complutense, Spain*
Regulación DEL Voto Desde EL Extranjero EN LOS Países Americanos. Justificación, Evolución Y Particularidades

212.5 Alberto ZUART GARDUNO, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain* and Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, *Universidad Complutense of Madrid, Spain*
EL Comienzo De UN Intento De Comprensión a La Crisis De Satisfacción De La Democracia Española Desde La Comunicación Responsable.

212.6 María Guadalupe HIDALGO, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*; Diana del Consuelo CALDERA GONZÁLEZ, *Universidad de Guanajuato (UGU450325KY2), Mexico* and Miguel Agustín ORTEGA CARRILLO, *Universidad de la Salle Bajío A.C., Mexico*
La Industria Creativa Como Una Alternativa Para Las Representaciones Culturales, Colectivas e Inclusivas.

15:30-17:20

213 New Communication Technologies and Changing Patterns of Social Stratification in Globalizing World

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India* and Pankaj Kumar SINGH, *Maharana Pratap Govt. PG College, Dept of Sociology 243633 Bilsi (Budaun) - India, India*

Chair: Virendra P. SINGH, *Chairman, GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), Raj Nagar Extension Ghaziabad-201017, India, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

213.1 Christina SCHACHTNER, *Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt, Austria*
Transnational Spaces and Scopic Media. Sociality in Change

213.2 Achla TANDON, *Hindu college, Department of Sociology, India*
Intercultural Competencies and Role of MEDIA

213.3 Madhu SISODIA, *Dav Pg College (BHU), India*
Nature and Types of Cyber Crime in a Town of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

213.4 Natxo SOROLLA, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain* and Amado ALARCON ALARCON, *University of Texas at El Paso, USA*
Literacies of XXI Century: Socially Hidden Factors behind Language Skills and STEM Skills. the Predominant Role of Language in Social Stratification

17:30-19:20

214 The Expansion of Social Media and the Emergence of Global Communication System: Theoretical, Methodological and Empirical Concerns

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Virendra P. SINGH, *Chairman, GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), Raj Nagar Extension Ghaziabad-201017, India, India* and Sarvesh TRIPATHI, *GGSIIP University New Delhi, India*

Chair: Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

214.1 Piya PONGSAPITAKSANTI, *Kyoto Sangyo University, Japan*
Gender Roles in Television Commercials in ASIA: A Comparison of Japan, China, Korea, Taiwan, Thailand, and Singapore

214.2 Madhu SISODIA, *Dav Pg College (BHU), India*
Social Media and Women Empowerment in India

214.3 Yu HOU, *Zhongnan University of Economics and Law, China* and Peng XU, *Zhongnan University of Economics and Law, China*
Intergroup Communication, Identity and Transcultural Construction of Fan Community -- Empirical Research Based on the Fan Community of Dimash

214.4 Sachin BHARTI, *Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, India* and Manisha PANCHAL, *Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi, India*
Films in the Era of Global Communication: A Study on Contemporary Indian Films in View of Social Media

214.5 Runping ZHU, Lanzhou University, China and Xinlei GE, Lanzhou University, China
India through Chinese Generation Z's Eyes: The Link between News Media Consumption and Youth's Perceptions of India

214.6 Gea DUCCI, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy and Camilla FOLENA, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy, Italy
The Public Sector Communication on Covid-19 in the Hybrid Media Ecosystem: A National Survey on the Italian Citizens' Perception.

215.4 Amparo COIDURAS, University of San Jorge, Spain
Data Mining Responsibility in the Design Process of Smart Products and Services. a Current Challenge for Organisations.

215.5 Julianna Paola RAMIREZ LOZANO, CENTRUM Catholic Graduate Business School. Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú, Perú., Peru
Challenges and Opportunities of Virtual Education for Business Training for Entrepreneurs in the Latin American Context

215.6 Edgar VAZQUEZ GONZALEZ, Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico and Cecilia RAMOS, Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico
Labor Reform in Mexico 2019: Lessons and Learnings.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

215.7 Mariano Agustin GONZALEZ CHOUCINO, Universidad de Alicante. Domicilio: Crta. San Vicente, s/n; 03690 San Vicente (Alicante), Spain and Raul RUIZ CALLADO, Universidad de Alicante, Spain
Las Desigualdades Digitales En Los Procesos De Socialización. Análisis Desde Una Perspectiva Generacional y Figuracionista

215.8 Nicolas DEMANGE, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain
Digital Communication and Lifestyles in Online Social Networks: A Systematic Review of the Literature on the Impact on the Mental Health of Digital Users.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

215 Socio-Digital Challenges and Vulnerability of Organizations. Communicative Approaches

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Sergio Alberto LLANO ARISTIZÁBAL, Universidad del Norte, Colombia; Alejandro PISCITELLI, UNIVERSIDAD CATOLICA ARGENTINA, Argentina and Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, Universidad Complutense, Spain

Chair: Diana del Consuelo CALDERA GONZÁLEZ, Universidad de Guanajuato (UGU450325KY2), Mexico

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

215.1 Seppo POUTANEN, University of Turku, Finland
"but the Feelings Were like an Explosion Would Have Happened in the Office, and in a Sense It Had" - Analysing the Virtual Communication Efforts of European Doctoral Researchers in the Pandemic Era

215.2 Shila KHAYAMBASHI, York University, Canada
Cyber Communication and Culture of Violence

215.3 Victoria SANAGUSTIN-FONS, University of Zaragoza, Spain
Social Sustainability and Social Economy Organizations: A Way of Overcome Vulnerabilities through Intergenerational Dialogue

RC15

Sociology of Health

Program Coordinators: Nelson BARROS, *University of Campinas, Brazil*; Farah PURWANINGRUM, *Taman Chryasant, Indonesia* and Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-1 COVID-19 Pandemic and Global Health Workforce Policies and Governance: Challenges and Issues at the Forefront

Committees: RC52 *Sociology of Professional Groups (Host)*; RC15 *Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-1.

216 Pharmaceuticalisation of Society: Current Debates and Empirical Contributions

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jonathan GABE, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom* and Paul MARTIN, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*

Chair: Jonathan GABE, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

216.1 Brian C. KELLY, *Purdue University, USA* and Mark PAWSON, *Purdue University, USA*

Co-Opted Pharmaceuticalization: Reconsidering Polydrug Use with Prescription Medications Among Young Adults in Nightlife

216.2 Fan-tzu TSENG, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Psychostimulants, Gender Norms, and Transformative Self: The Medication Practices for Young Adults with ADHD in Taiwan

216.3 Sigita DOBLYTE, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain*
Less Than Perfect Brain: Pharmaceuticalisation in the Workplace

216.4 Shlomo GUZMEN-CARMELI, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel* and David RIER, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel*
Getting Undone Science Done to Make New Treatments Available: Entrepreneurial Organizers and Citizen Scientists

216.5 Marcela GONZALEZ-AGUERO, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
A reflection on citizenship and therapeutic markets: Chileans with rare diseases and their journeys to access orphan drugs

15:30-17:20

JS-7 Climate Crisis, Mental Health and Youth Resistance

Committees: RC34 *Sociology of Youth (Host)*; RC15 *Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-7.

217 National Health Systems and the State: The Experience of Practitioners and Patients

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom* and Guido GIARELLI, *UNIVERSITY MAGNA GRAECIA, Italy*

Chair: Guido GIARELLI, *UNIVERSITY MAGNA GRAECIA, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

217.1 Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*
Medical Practitioners, Social Closure and the State: Variations across National Health Systems and Their Implications for Patients

217.2 Mike DENT, *Staffordshire University, United Kingdom*
The Medical-Industrial Complex: Implications for the European National Health Services

217.3 Mauro SERAPIONI, *Centre for Social Studies, Portugal*
Public Participation in the National Health Services of Three European Macro-Regions

217.4 Hiroshi YAMANAKA, *Osaka University, Japan* and Natsuko NOJIMA, *Ishinomaki Senshu University, Japan*
National Health System in Japan and the Experiences of People with Rare Disease

217.5 Heqing HUANG, *Gonville & Caius College, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Organisational Structure of a Chinese Hospital: Microcosm of a Hybrid Polity

217.6 Angela GENOVA, *University of Urbino, Italy* and Simone LOMBARDINI, *University of Genova, Italy, Italy*
General Practitioners in Front of Covid-19: Italy in European Comparative Perspective.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

217.7 Nuzulul PUTRI, *Health Policy and Administration Department, Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Airlangga, Kampus C Mulyorejo Surabaya Indonesia, Indonesia*; Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Hasbullah THABRANY, *ThinkWell, Indonesia*
An Integrative Review on the Theory-Practice Gap of Capitation Payment Model in the Indonesian National Health Insurance

217.8 Jaconiah Shelumiel MANALAYSAY, *University of the Philippines-Diliman, Philippines*
Challenges and Advances in Universal Health Care Implementation: A Case Study of Selected Healthcare Practitioners in a Tertiary Hospital in the Philippines

17:30-19:20

218 Where Next for Sociological Alcohol Research?

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sarah MACLEAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Gabriel CALUZZI, *La Trobe University, Australia* and Amy PENNAY, *La Trobe University, Australia*

Chair: Sarah MACLEAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

218.1 Hau PHAM, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Alcohol, Addiction, and Subjugated Knowledge: Reimagining Alcohol Experiences and Subjectivity in Viet Nam through Ma Men

218.2 Airi-Alina ALLASTE, *Tallinn University, Estonia*
Meaning, Motives, Contexts and Risks of High-Intensity Drinking in Estonia

218.3 Kristen FOLEY, *Torrens University Australia, Australia*
A Hermeneutic Exploration of the Alcohol Marketplace and Lived Histories of Australian Midlife Women

218.4 Emily NICHOLLS, *University of York, United Kingdom*
'Nice Little Life-Hack'? No and Low Alcohol Drinks and New (non)Drinking Practices

218.5 Tristan DUNCAN, *Monash University, Australia* and Michael SAVIC, *Turning Point, Australia*
Disaster in Alcohol Research: Composing New Directions for Thought and Action

218.6 Michala KOWALSKI, *Drug Policy Modelling Program, SPRC, UNSW Sydney, Australia*
What's the Problem with the Night-Time Economy: Examining the Problematisations in New South Wales' Late-Night Alcohol and Night-Time Economy Policies

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

218.7 Peta STRAGALINOS, *Turning Point, Australia*; Michael SAVIC, *Turning Point, Australia* and Tina LAM, *Monash Addiction Research Centre, Australia*
Knock-Offs, Lock-Ins and Kick-Ons: Assembling after Work Drinks in Hospitality

218.8 Brittany RALPH, *Monash University, Australia*
The Complex Role of Alcohol and Autonomy in Men's Lives

219.2 Lorraine SMITH, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Kate JOHNSTON-ATAATA, *Social and Global Studies Centre, School of Global, Urban and Social Studies, RMIT University, Australia* and Anna URBANOWICZ, *School of Health and Social Development, Faculty of Health, Deakin University, Australia*
Establishing a Cross-National Study on Experiences of COVID-19 - Methods, Processes, Challenges: The Australian Experience

219.3 Cervantee WILD, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Sasha LEWIS-JACKSON, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Maria Ines CONCEIÇÃO, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*; Alicia Navarro Dias DE SOUZA, *Hospital Universitário Clementino Fraga Filho, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Vinita Mahtani CHUGANI, *Universidad de La Laguna, Spain*; Miho IWAKUMA, *Kyoto University, Japan* and Rie TOYOMOTO, *Kyoto University, Japan*
Government Guidance and Citizen Responses during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Cross-Country Analysis

219.4 Anna DOWRICK, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Kate HUNT, *Institute for Social Marketing and Health, University of Stirling, United Kingdom*; Alice MACLEAN, *Institute for Social Marketing and Health, University of Stirling, United Kingdom*; Jane EVERED, *University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA*; Michelle MARCINOW, *Institute for Better Health, Trillium Health Partners, Canada*; Anna URBANOWICZ, *School of Health and Social Development, Faculty of Health, Deakin University, Australia* and Nienke VERHEIJ, *University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of Health Sciences, Applied Health Research, Netherlands*
Negotiation of Collective and Individual Candidacy for Long Covid Healthcare in the Early Phases of the Covid-19 Pandemic: Heard, Diverted and Rejected Candidacy

219.5 Marcelo CASTELLANOS, *Collective Health Institute, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil*; Jane EVERED, *University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA*; Rachel GROB, *University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA*; Tanvi RAI, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Ana Carmago Goncalves GERMANI, *The Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*; Annelieke DRIESSEN, *The London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, United Kingdom* and Alicia Navarro Dias DE SOUZA, *Hospital Universitário Clementino Fraga Filho, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Coming to Terms in an International Collaboration: Situated Researchers and Situating Data

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

219 Cross-Country Comparative Sociological Analyses of Covid-19 Patient Experiences: Insights from the Dipex International Collaboration**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Rika Sakuma SATO, *DIPEX-Japan, Japan***Chair:** Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Panelists: Lorraine SMITH, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Anna DOWRICK, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Cervantee WILD, *Medical Sociology and Health Experiences Research Group, Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences, University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Marcelo CASTELLANOS, *Collective Health Institute, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil* and Rika Sakuma SATO, *DIPEX-Japan, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

219.1 Rika Sakuma SATO, *DIPEX-Japan, Japan*
Message from the Frontiers of Cross-Country Comparative Qualitative Research

10:30-12:20

220 The Response of Health Professions to Complementary and Alternative Medicine**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom* and Nelson BARROS, *University of Campinas, Brazil***Chair:** Nelson BARROS, *University of Campinas, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

220.1 Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*
Professionalization and the Relationship between Orthodox and Unorthodox Medicine in Britain: Sympathy for the Devil?

220.2 Ayse POLAT, *Assistant Professor, Turkey*; Huseyin KUCUKALI, *Istanbul Medipol University, Turkey* and Zubeyde DEMIRCIOGLU, *Istanbul Medeniyet University, Turkey*
Orchestrating Modern and Alternative Medicine: Challenges for the Practitioners of CAM in Turkey

220.3 Joana ALMEIDA, *University of Bedfordshire, United Kingdom*; Kavi SHARMA, *Brighton & Sussex Medical School, University of Sussex, United Kingdom*; Jonathan GABE, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom*; John ANDERSON, *Brighton & Sussex Medical School, University of Sussex, United Kingdom* and Dr. Richard SIMCOCK, *Brighton & Sussex Medical School, University of Sussex, United Kingdom*
Perceptions of Use of Complementary and Alternative Therapies in Women with Breast Cancer

220.4 Paula FEDER-BUBIS, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*
How Physical Therapy's Professional Boundaries Are Contested Following the Enactment of the Medical Professions Regulation Act in Israel?

15:30-17:20

221 The Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Persons with Disabilities: Call for a Sociological Reflexivity

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Angela GENOVA, *university of Urbino, Italy*; Alice SCAVARDA, *Università degli Studi di Torino, Italy* and Maria SWIATKIEWICZ MOSNY, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*

Chair: Angela GENOVA, *university of Urbino, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

221.1 Pariz Pikul GOGOI, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Covid 19 Pandemic and the Persons with Intellectual Disabilities in Assam

221.2 Tracey LAPIERRE, *University of Kansas, USA*; Carrie WENDEL-HUMMELL, *University of Kansas, USA*; Jennifer BABITZKE, *University of Kansas, USA*; Darcy SULLIVAN, *University of Kansas, USA*; Lora SWARTZENDRUBER, *University of Kansas, USA* and Danielle OLDS, *Saint Lukes Hospital, USA*
Politicization of COVID-19 and Experiences of Care and Disability in the United States: The Case of Home Care in Kansas

221.3 Kathy ANDERSON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Long COVID, ME/CFS and the 'long Haul': Histories of Contested Chronic Illness in Australia

19:30-20:50

222 RC15 Business Meeting

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

223 Sociology of Vaccines. Part I

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Co-chairs: Hannah TAYLOR-ABDULAI, *University of Cape Coast, Ghana* and Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

223.1 Alessandra SANNELLA, *University of Cassino, Italy*; Maurizio ESPOSITO, *university of cassino and lazio meridionale, Italy*; Maria FERRARA, *Università degli Studi di Cassino, Italy*; Lia LOMBARDI, *Università di Cassino, Italy*; Sara SBARAGLI, *Università degli Studi di Cassino, Italy*; Giuseppina LO MORO, *università di torino, Italy* and Elisabetta DE VITO, *Università degli Studi di Cassino, Italy*

Roadmap for Proposals for Interventions with Healthcare Professionals: Knowing and Counteracting Vaccine Hesitation. First Results from Vax-Trust European Project (Project: 965280)

223.2 Idalina ODZIEMCZYK STAWARZ, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*

Social Representations of Vaccination in the Context of Family Experiences – Insights for Behavioural Interventions

223.3 Eric VOGELSANG, *Cal State-San Bernardino, USA* and Andrea POLONIJO, *University of California-Merced, USA*
Scarier Than the Flu Shot? the Social Determinants of Shingles and Influenza Vaccinations Among U.S. Older Adults

223.4 Mohammad Mainul ISLAM, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*; MD Yeasir YUNUS, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*; Muhammad Saifullah AKIB, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*; Md. Rakibul IQBAL, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh* and Mohona KHAN, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*
Prevalence of COVID-19 Vaccine Hesitancy in South Asia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

223.5 Judy SIU, *Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong* and Anita KOO, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
COVID-19 Non-Vaccination Among the People of Hong Kong: Resistance to Biomedical Hegemony As a Barrier

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

223.6 Fabio LUCCHINI, *eCampus University, Italy* and Michele MARZULLI, *Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Italy*
The Debate on Covid-19 Vaccines and the Image of Science: A New Political Cleavage in Europe?

10:30-12:20

224 Sociology of Vaccines. Part II

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Co-chairs: Anita KOO, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong* and Judy SIU, *Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

224.1 Hannah TAYLOR-ABDULAI, *University of Cape Coast, Cape Coast, Ghana, Ghana*
We Do Not Have COVID-19 Here: Community Understanding of the Causes, Signs and Symptoms and Management of COVID-19: Implication for Vaccine Acceptance

224.2 Aleksandra WAGNER, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*; Tadeusz RUDEK, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*; Maria SWIATKIEWICZ MOSNY, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland* and Paulina POLAK, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*
Co-Producing Vaccine Hesitancy in the Pre- and Covid Discourses on Immunization: A Comparative Study.

224.3 Yelena MEJOVA, *ISI Foundation, Italy*; Giuseppe CRUPI, *ISI Foundation, Italy*; Jacopo LENTI, *ISI Foundation, Italy*; Michele TIZZANI, *ISI Foundation, Italy*; Kyriaki KALIMERI, *ISI Foundation, Italy*; Daniela PAOLOTTI, *ISI Foundation, Italy* and André PANISSON, *CENTAI, Italy*
Echo Chambers of Vaccination Hesitancy Discussion on Social Media during COVID-19 Pandemic

224.4 Ana Patricia HILARIO, *Instituto de Ciências Sociais, Universidade de Lisboa (ref: 5122300242), Portugal*; Alice SCAVARDA, *Università degli Studi di Torino, Italy*; Dino NUMERATO, *Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic*; Mario CARDANO, *University of Turin, Italy*; Esther LERMYTTE, *Gent University, Belgium*; Pia VUOLANTO, *Tampere University, Finland* and Pru HOBSON-WEST, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*
Seven Sampling Strategies for Seven Countries: Successful Flexibility in an International Study on Vaccine Hesitancy during the Covid-19 Pandemic

224.5 Hiroshi KOJIMA, *Waseda University, Japan*
Correlates of Vaccine Non-Uptake Among Younger Muslims in Britain during COVID-19 Pandemic

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

224.6 Michael MARANDA, *Western Michigan University The Evaluation Center, USA* and Sanjay MARWAH, *Independent Consultant, USA*
Vaccine Hesitancy—the Hydra of Public Health?

224.7 Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Images of the Body in Vaccine Science – an Ethnographic Study on a Nordic-West African Vaccine Trial

224.8 Taiwo Olabode KOLAWOLE, *Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria* and Timilehin Peter OWOEYE, *Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria*
COVID-19 Vaccine: Nigeria Scenerio

15:30-17:20

225 Digital Health Futures**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Benjamin MARENT, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom***Chair:** Benjamin MARENT, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

225.1 Rowena FORSYTH, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Krestina AMON, *Cyberpsychology Research Group, Biomedical Informatics and Digital Health Theme, School of Medical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health, University of Sydney, New South Wales, Australia*; Brad RIDOUT, *Cyberpsychology Research Group, Biomedical Informatics and Digital Health Theme, School of Medical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health, University of Sydney, New South Wales, Australia* and Andrew CAMPBELL, *Cyberpsychology Research Group, Biomedical Informatics and Digital Health Theme, School of Medical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health, University of Sydney, New South Wales, Australia*
Communication, Connectedness and Collegiality in Health Professionals' Use of Online Communities for Peer Interaction.

225.2 Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*
Digitizing Peer Support Activities of People with Illnesses and/or Disabilities

225.3 Anna DOMARADZKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Mikolaj BIESAGA, *Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland*; Magdalena KOŁODZIEJCZYK, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Ewa DOMARADZKA, *WSB University, Poland*
Digital Right to a Healthy City

225.4 Eun kyong SHIN, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*
Sociomarkers and Connectomes: Neuro-Developmental Imprints in Adolescent Brains

225.5 Monica MURERO, *University Unina, Italy*
Innovating Fragile Patients Care during COVID-19: A "mixed" future for Digital Health?

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

225.6 Taoyi YANG, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Revisiting Digital Health: "Feeling Better" and Digital Treatment in Public Health Governance

225.7 Juhyun LEE, *CERMES3, France*
Ambivalence of Screens: Appropriation of Screens By Korean Young Adults with Problematic Internet Use

225.8 Caterina FILARETI, *University of Salento, Italy*
Digital Technologies Applied to Oncology

225.9 Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Natalie ARAUJO, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Tonya STEBBINS, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Jessica VELASQUEZ URRIBARRI, *La Trobe University, Australia*; Emma KOSTER, *Our Good Hood, Australia* and Linda WHITBY, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Communicating in a Crisis: Digital Solutions for Alerting Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Communities in an Emergency

17:30-19:20

226 Fertility and the Family**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia***Chair:** Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

226.1 Limor GONEN, *Ariel University, Israel*
Valuing the Invaluable: Do Emotional Experiences during Fertility Treatments Affect the Willingness to Pay for Them?

226.2 Limor GONEN, *Ariel University, Israel*
Satisfaction with in Vitro Fertilization Treatment: Patients' Experiences and Professionals' Perceptions

226.3 Sabrina ZEGHICHE, *Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada* and Isabel COTE, *Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada*
Constructing Insemination Fraud As a Social Problem: A Qualitative Study

226.4 Alessandra DECATALDO, *University of Milan Bicocca, Italy* and Concetta RUSSO, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*
Voicing Preterm Parents' Experiences. Patienthood and Participation in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

226.5 Eric VOGELSANG, *Cal State-San Bernardino, USA*
Gender, Social Lives, and Older-Adult Alcohol Abuse: A Comparison between USA and Ireland.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

227 **Enhancing the Dialogue between Science and Society: The Challenges of e-Health Care**

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Alessandra DECATALDO, *University of Milan Bicocca, Italy*; Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*; Concetta RUSSO, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy* and Noemi NOVELLO, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

Chair: Guido GIARELLI, *UNIVERSITY MAGNA GRAECIA, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

227.1 Pui Yan Flora LAU, *Department of Sociology, Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*
Healing through Social Media: Experiences of Ethnic Minority Cancer Patients and Survivors in Hong Kong

227.2 Benjamin MARENT, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom* and Flis HENWOOD, *University of Brighton, United Kingdom*
Digital Transformations of HIV Care: A Sociomaterial Inquiry

227.3 Mahua PATRA, *Maulana Azad College, Kolkata, India*; Palash DAS, *Rampurhat Govt. Medical College and Hospital, India* and Debasish SINHA, *Rampurhat Government Medical College and Hospital, India*
Patients' Experiences with Telemedicine Treatment System: An In-Depth Study in Rural West Bengal, India

227.4 Noemi NOVELLO, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy* and Concetta RUSSO, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*
Reconnecting the Social with the Medical Experience in the NICU: The Role of s Digital Technology

227.5 Cornelius SCHUBERT, *TU Dortmund University, Germany*
Patient Generated Data As "Grey Data"

227.6 Victoria DUDINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation*
Patient Activism Strategies in Digital Space in the Light of New Epidemic Risks

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

227.7 Sofia KORZHUK, *Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Russian Federation*
Accessible or Not That Much? Urban Mobility Conditions for People with Disabilities through the Prism of Russian Youtube Users Reactions

10:30-12:20

228 **The Entanglements of Religions, Health, and Political-Economy in Africa**

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Alex ASAKITIKPI, *The Independent Institute of Education, South Africa*

Chair: Emeka OBIOHA, *Walter Sisulu University, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

228.1 Alex ASAKITIKPI, *The Independent Institute of Education, South Africa*
The Intersection of Radical Pentecostalism and Health Implications in South Africa

228.2 Amithy JASROTIA, *University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, India*; Mohita SHARMA, *University of Rajasthan, India*; Mamta KUMARI, *University of Rajasthan, India* and Rolly SINHA, *University of Rajasthan, India*
Care Models of PLHA: A Comparative Assessment of Africa, India & USA

15:30-17:20

JS-101 **Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part I**

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society (Host)*; RC15 *Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-101.

17:30-19:20

229 **Social Dimensions of Public Health Activism: Global, National and Local Perspectives**

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Victoria DUDINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation*; Olga BORODKINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation* and Elizabeth J. KING, *University of Michigan, USA*

Chair: Victoria DUDINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation*

Co-Chair: Olga BORODKINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

229.1 Belinda JOHNSON, *RMIT University, Australia*; Pieta SHAKES, *James Cook University, Australia* and Chris MAYLEA, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Public Health Activism to Address the Psychosocial Impacts of Unexpected Fetal Findings in Pregnancy

229.2 Mahua PATRA, *Maulana Azad College, Kolkata, India* and Achintya DEY, *Retired from Centre for disease Control, USA*
Health Social Movement to Access Required Primary Care: A Case Study in a Rural Primary Health Centre, India

229.3 Gaku OSHIMA, *Meiji University, Japan*
"Words" That Communicate: Queer Performances As Public Health Activism

229.4 Natalie JOVANOVSKI, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Tess JAEGER, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Embodying the 'anti-Diet' Movement: The Lived and Learned Experiences of Health Professionals in the Broad Anti-Diet Community

229.5 Daniel LA PARRA-CASADO, *University of Alicante, Spain*; Anna-Britt COE, *Umeå University, Sweden*; Carmen VIVES-CASES, *University of Alicante, Spain* and Mariano SALAZAR, *Karolinska Institutet, Sweden*
Addressing Masculinities to Stop Intimate Partner Violence: How Are Social Innovations Being Created in Different Types of Organizations in Spain and Sweden?

229.6 Mauro SERAPIONI, *Centre for Social Studies, Portugal* and José Patrício BISPO JÚNIOR, *Federal University of Bahia - Multidisciplinary Institute of Health (IMS-UFBA), Brazil*
Representativeness and Effectiveness: Two Critical Dimensions of Participation in Health Systems. a Literature Review

230.3 Claudia ALCAYAGA-ROJAS, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Advancing in the understanding of the assembly of health care for people with chronic diseases in the social scaffolding built in Primary Health Care centres in Chile

230.4 Eleonora COCCO, *University of Cagliari, Italy* and Aide ESU, *University of Cagliari, Italy*
Approaching Multiple Sclerosis Integrating Expert Systems and Narrative Medicine

17:30-19:20

JS-136 Knowledge Co-Production, Communities, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: *RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host)*; *RC15 Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-136.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

231 Reproduction in the Current World: Focusing on Prenatal Testing and Abortion

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Chiaki SHIRAI, *Shizuoka University, Japan*

Chair: Kentaro ISHIJIMA, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

231.1 Chiaki SHIRAI, *Shizuoka University, Japan*
Prenatal Testing and Views of Disability in East Asia, South-East Asia and South Asia

231.2 Keisuke SAITO, *Okayama University, Japan*
Assisted Reproductive Technologies Prompt Male Subjectivity in Reproduction: Issues and Controversies Surrounding Elective Abortion

231.3 Atsuko SANO, *Tokyo University, Japan*
How Do the ICT Affect to the Discourse on Reproductive Health Rights: A Case Study of Germany and Japan

231.4 Setsuko SUGANO, *Saitama University, Japan*
Attitudes of Obstetricians and Gynecologist Towards Prenatal Testing and Abortion in Japan

231.5 Yuko NIKAIDO, *National Museum of Ethnology, Japan*
How Ireland Attempted to Avoid Stigma on Disability through the Legalization of Abortion

231.6 Dorinda 'T HART, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
Visualising Relational Autonomy in Abortion Decision-Making

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-118 Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part II

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host)*; *RC15 Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-118.

10:30-12:20

JS-122 Community Influences on Lifestyles and Health

Committees: *RC03 Community Research (Host)*; *RC15 Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-122.

15:30-17:20

230 Patients Participation and Transformation of Society

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*

Chair: Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

230.1 Elisa ROSSI, *University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy*
Patient's Participation in Medical Consultation

230.2 Zhengwei HUANG, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, Hong Kong*; Tianwei LONG, *Illness Challenging Foundation, China*; Ling TAO, *Shenzhen Research Institute, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, China*; Yin DOU, *Department of Sociology, Tsinghua University, China* and Jun JIN, *Department of Sociology, Tsinghua University, China*
Analysis of Rare Disease Patient Organizations (RDPOs) in China and Influencing Factors of Fundraising Amount: An Organizational Cross-Sectional Study

10:30-12:20

232 Inequalities in Health, Mental Health, and Discrimination. Part I**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Cristina GOMES, *FLACSO Mexico, Mexico***Chair:** Cristina GOMES, *FLACSO Mexico, Mexico***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

232.1 Verna KEITH, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*; Ryon COBB, *Rutgers University, USA*; Whitney PIRTLE, *University of California Merced, USA* and Dawne MOUZON, *Rutgers University, USA*

Black-White Paradox in Mental Health: The Significance of Racial Classification Vs. Self-Assessed, Other Assessed, and Incongruent Skin Tone

232.2 Elodie EDWARDS-GROSSI, *IRISSO, Universite Paris Dauphine-PSL, France*

Race in the Clinic: On Antiracist Medicine and Psychiatry in the US Today

232.3 Brian C. KELLY, *Purdue University, USA* and Michael VUOLO, *The Ohio State University, USA*

The Rise and Decline of Racial Stratification of Prescribing and Overdose Mortality: Reconsidering Fundamental Causes in a Drug Crisis

232.4 Merih ATES, *DeZIM-Institute, Germany* and Tae KIM, *DeZIM-Institute, Germany*

Racial Discrimination and Health Consequences – Evidence from Germany

232.5 Christy ERVING, *The University of Texas at Austin, USA* and Tiffany WILLIAMS, *Tennessee State University, USA*

Anticipatory Race-Related Stress & Depressive Symptoms Among U.S. Black Women: Are Psychosocial Resources Stress Buffers?

232.6 Stephanie TEIXEIRA-POIT, *North Carolina A&T State University, USA*; Bonnie FIELDS, *North Carolina A&T State University, USA*; Marjorie JENKINS, *Cone Health, USA*; Vanessa GHARBI, *University of North Carolina at Greensboro & North Carolina A&T State University, USA*; Serena LOWE, *North Carolina A&T State University, USA* and Frances KENDRICK, *North Carolina A&T State University, USA*

Contextualizing the Impact of Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) Transitions from Open-Bay to Single Family Rooms

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

232.7 Beverley BRATHWAITE, *University of Roehampton, United Kingdom* and Rosemary GODBOLD, *University of Hertfordshire, United Kingdom*

Racism and Clinical Decision Making- No Place to Hide.

232.8 Kuheli DAS, *Dibrugarh university, India*

Life in the Camp: A Study about Women's Health in Conflict Affected Area of Btad, Assam, India

232.9 William CABIN, *New York University Silver School of Social Work, USA*

"It's a Repository for Low-Income People": The Social Construction of Bias in the American Medicare Home Health Benefit

12:30-14:20

233 Inequality in Health Care - Empirical Studies about Health Care Professions**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Kristian LARSEN, *UCSF Rigshospitalet, Denmark*; Anette Lykke HINDHEDE, *University Hospitals Centre for Health Research, Rigshospitalet, Denmark* and Marte FEIRING, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway***Chair:** Randi WAERDAHL, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

233.1 Marte FEIRING, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway*
The Reproduction of Professional Hierarchies in Today's Health Care Field

233.2 Kristian LARSEN, *UCSF Rigshospitalet, Denmark* and Anette Lykke HINDHEDE, *University Hospitals Centre for Health Research, Rigshospitalet, Denmark*

Health Capital: Patient's Investments in Their Bodies and the Reception in the Healthcare Field

233.3 Joanna BLACKWELL, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Hannah HENDERSON, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Adam EVANS, *University of Copenhagen, Denmark* and Jacquelyn ALLEN-COLLINSON, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*

"You're the Expert, You Tell Me What I Ought to Do" - Socio-Cultural Influences on the Cardiac Patient Journey: Exploring Health Care Relationships

233.4 Alex FISHER, *Institute of Applied Health Research, University of Birmingham, United Kingdom* and Richie CARREON, *Faculty of Health, Liverpool John Moores University, United Kingdom*

Beyond the Interview - Qualitative Methods for the Inclusion of RARE Disease Groups in Research

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

233.5 Jaconiah Shelumiel MANALAYSAY, *University of the Philippines-Diliman, Philippines*

A Rapid Review on the State of Medical Sociology Literature in the Philippines

233.6 Sarah MACLEAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*
A Socio-Material Exploration of Alcohol and Drug Service Provision for Young People

233.7 Emily CARVALHO, *Collective Health Institute, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil, Brazil*; Marcelo CASTELLANOS, *Collective Health Institute, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil*; Ana TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Reconcavo Baiano, Brazil*; Mônica ANGELIM, *Federal University of Bahia, Brazil* and Alain Lucien Louis COULON, *Paris 8 University, France*
Non Clinical Support Workers of a Referral Hospital in Bahia, Brazil, in the Face of Covid-19: Discussing Invisible Labor and Its Consequences

14:30-16:20

234 Inequalities in Health, Mental Health, and Discrimination. Part II**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Nelson BARROS, *University of Campinas, Brazil***Chair:** Nelson BARROS, *University of Campinas, Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

234.1 Mihai-Bogdan IOVU, *Babeş-Bolyai University Cluj-Napoca, Romania*; Florin LAZAR, *University of Bucharest, Romania*; Emanuel Adrian SÂRBU, *University of Bucharest, Romania* and Cosmin GHEȚĂU, *Babeş-Bolyai University Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

Screen Time and Development of Internalizing and Externalizing Problems Among Romanian Urban Highschoolers

234.2 Felicia LAZARIDOU, *Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, Charité University Medicine, Germany* and Andreas HEINZ, *Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, Charité University Medicine, Germany*

Racism, Clinical Psychosis and Subclinical Psychosis Symptomatology: The Role of Ascribed Migrant Status and Post-Migration Stress

234.3 Chinwe OBUAKU-IGWE, *University of the Western Cape, South Africa*

Exploring the Effectiveness of Mental Health First Aid Program for Young People in South Africa

234.4 Harold NEIGHBORS, *University of Michigan, USA*; Sherrill SELLERS, *Miami University -- Oxford, OH, USA*; Reed DEANGELIS, *University of North Carolina, USA*; Alexis DENNIS, *McGill University, Canada* and Anjali PUROHIT, *National Institutes of Health, USA*

Black-White Differences in Goal-Striving Stress and Depression in the Nashville Stress and Health Survey

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

234.5 Jagsir SINGH, *Bebe Nanaki University College, India* and Ramanjeet KAUR, *Social Security, Women and Child Development Department, Government of Punjab, India*

Marginalization in Urban Social Space and Its Implications for Child Health: A Study of Urban Punjab (India)

234.6 Jayashree SHIVANANDA, *Karnatak University, India*
Gender Equity Dynamics and Health Seeking Behavior of Women in Matrilineal Families

RC16

Sociological Theory

Program Coordinator: Craig BROWNE, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

235 Theorizing the Social World in the Digital Age. Part I

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Erik SCHNEIDERHAN, *University of Toronto, Canada*

Chair: Martin LUKK, *University of Toronto, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

235.1 Ronald JACOBS, *University at Albany, SUNY, USA* and Eleanor TOWNSLEY, *Mount Holyoke College, USA*
Civil Society in the Age of the Algorithm

235.2 Aditya RAJ, *Indian Institute of Technology Patna, India*
Network Analysis and Computational Modeling in Sociology

235.3 Victor ROUDOMETOF, *University of Cyprus POB 20537, Cyprus*
Globalization, Glocalization and the ICT Revolution

235.4 Pranoti CHIRMULEY, *St Xavier's College Mumbai, India*
Choices 'Democratic' and Freedoms Compromised.

15:30-17:20

236 Antipodean Social Theory

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Peter BEILHARZ, *La Trobe University / Sichuan University, Australia* and Rachel BUSBRIDGE, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

Co-chairs: Peter BEILHARZ, *La Trobe University / Sichuan University, Australia* and Rachel BUSBRIDGE, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

Discussant: Jeffrey ALEXANDER, *Yale University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

236.1 Eduardo DE LA FUENTE, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Landscape and Antipodean Social Theory: On the Theoretical Affordances of Sandstone

236.2 Sian SUPSKI, *Thesis Eleven, Australia*
When Are We at Home

236.3 Fran COLLYER, *University of Karlstad, Sweden*
Australian Sociologists: Knowledge Making, Identity and Global Position

236.4 Bradley WEST, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Antipodean Travels and National Matters: Meaningful Mobility and Reimagining of the Australia and Turkey through Witnessing Acts

17:30-19:20

JS-22 Materialist Sociology: Biometabolism, Technometabolism, Technoaddiction

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-22.

JS-16 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part I

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research and RC16 Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-16.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-23 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part II

Committees: RC07 *Futures Research (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-23.

10:30-12:20

237 Theorising Elites

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Marcus MORGAN, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*; Narzanin MASSOUMI, *University of Exeter, United Kingdom* and Tom MILLS, *Aston University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Bradley WEST, *University of South Australia, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

237.1 Roger BURROWS, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
The New Class Realities of Rentier Capitalism: Theorising Elites in the Asset Economy

237.2 Adam DINSMORE, *University of York, United Kingdom*
Theorising 'Elites' across Discursive-Material Terrain: A Poststructuralist Approach to England's 'Red Wall'

237.3 Hanna-mari HUSU, *LUT University, School of Engineering Science/Social Science, Finland* and Matti KOJO, *LUT University School of Engineering Science/Social Sciences, Finland*
The Impact of Crises on the Hegemony of Nuclear Power Elite in Finland: A Neo-Gramscian Approach

237.4 Charles BOSVIEUX-ONYEKWELU, *CNRS - Centre Norbert Elias, France*
The Concept of Sociodicy: A Useful Heuristic to Describe the Social Domination of Elites

15:30-17:20

238 Social Imaginaries and Political Forms. Part I**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Craig BROWNE, *University of Sydney, Australia***Chair:** Kathya ARAUJO, *Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****238.1** Angelos MOUZAKITIS, *Univeristy of Crete, Greece*
Social Imaginaries and Modernity: Revisiting the Conception of Autonomy in Castoriadis's Works**238.2** Craig BROWNE, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
The Political Forms of Modernity: The Gauchet-Badiou Debate over Democracy and Communism**238.3** Jeremy SMITH, *Federation University, Australia*
Metropolitan Imaginaries and Regional Cities in the North Americas**238.4** Celso VILLEGAS, *Kenyon College, USA*
Social Imaginaries and the Civil Sphere: A Cultural-Sociological Typology of Solidarity and Conflict**238.5** Josafat MORALES, *Universidad Popular Autonoma del Estado de Puebla (UPAEP), Mexico*
From Oil to Lithium: Extractivism in the Mexican Social Imaginary As Political Legitimiser.

17:30-19:20

239 RC16 Business Meeting**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Wednesday 28 June**

08:30-10:20

240 Ulrich Beck and COVID-19 Pandemics**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Sang-Jin HAN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea***Chair:** Shujiro YAZAWA, *Center of Glocal Studies, Seijo University, Japan***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****240.1** Young-Hee SHIM, *Hanyang University, Republic of Korea*
Who Will be the Agency of Social Change in the Covid-19 Era?**240.2** Sang-Jin HAN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Ulrich Beck and the Diverging Pathways of the COVID-19 Governance

10:30-12:20

241 Social Theory in China, Social Theory of China**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Jack BARBALET, *Australian Catholic University, Australia* and Xiaoying QI, *Australian Catholic University, Australia***Chair:** Xiaoying QI, *Australian Catholic University, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****241.1** Hon Fai CHEN, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*
Market Town, Diffused Religion, and Industrial Metropolis: C.K. Yang As a Chinese Social Theorist**241.2** Jack BARBALET, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Understanding Chinese Society: Examining the Concept of Ritual.**241.3** Ji RUAN, *Guizhou Minzu University, China*
'Ritualized Relational Work' As Ethical Support for Corruption: How Do Banquets Promote Guanxi Exchange Among Rural Cadres in China**241.4** Laurence ROULLEAU-BERGER, *French National Center of Scientific Research -ENS Lyon, France*
Non-Hegemonic Theory and Post-Western Sociology from China to Europe**241.5** Weiyi HU, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Being Chinese: Moving Beyond the Dichotomy of China and the Occident

15:30-17:20

JS-69 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part I**Committees:** *RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC16 Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-69.

17:30-19:20

JS-79 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part II**Committees:** *RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC16 Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-79.

19:30-20:50

242 Charisma, Populism, or Charismatic Populism?**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Paul JOOSSE, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong***Chair:** Paul JOOSSE, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****242.1** Lorenzo VIVIANI, *University of Pisa, Italy*
Towards a Weberian Theoretical Framework on the Differences between Charismatic and Populist Leadership**242.2** Rudolf METZ, *Corvinus University of Budapest, Hungary*
Folk Devil or Folk Hero? Strategic Use of Emotions in Viktor Orbán's Politics

242.3 Paul JONES, *Research School of Social Sciences, College of Arts and Social Sciences, the Australian National University, Australia*
The Utility of 'Modern Demagogy' for the Charisma/ Populism Analytic

242.4 Valentin SOUBISE, *Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, France*
Incarnation Charismatique Et Stratégie De La Refondation Populiste Au Sein Du Mélenchonisme En France

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-83 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part III

Committees: *RC16 Sociological Theory (Host); RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis*

See Joint Session Details for JS-83.

10:30-12:20

243 The New Trinity: Simmel. Tarde. Mead

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Olli PYYHTINEN, *Tampere University, Finland*

Co-Chair: Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

243.1 Andrea BRIGHENTI, *University of Trento, Italy, Italy*
Simmel and Tarde: Beyond an Equilibrium Theory of Social Life

243.2 Alberto CORDEIRO DE FARIAS, *Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ), Brazil*
Simmel's Sociology of Imagination.

243.3 Nick OSBALDISTON, *College of Arts, Society and Education, Australia*
Simmel, the Adventure, Memory and the Self.

243.4 Boris TRAEUE, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
Reconstructing Sympathy through Relational Theory

15:30-17:20

JS-103 Theories of Practice: New Perspectives in Urban Theory and Research

Committees: *RC03 Community Research (Host); RC16 Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-103.

17:30-19:20

244 Cultural Sociology: Hermeneutics, Semiotics, Dialectics

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Jean-Francois COTE, *UQAM, Canada*

Chair: Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Discussant: Jean-Francois COTE, *UQAM, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

244.1 Csaba SZALO, *Masaryk University FSS Jostova, Czech Republic*
The Incompatibility and Dialogue between Theoretical Perspectives: Habitus, Absorbed Coping, and Embodied Understanding.

244.2 Nelson ARTEAGA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico*
Structural Hermeneutics, Dialectical Hermeneutics: Is a Synthesis Possible?

244.3 Victor LIDZ, *Drexel University College of Medicine, USA*
Limitations of Parsons on Norms

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

245 Configuration and Codes and Sustainability Part I

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Gilles VERPRAET, *University Paris Ouest Nanterre, France* and Erik SCHNEIDERHAN, *University of Toronto, Canada*

Chair: Christian GIRARD, *The University of the South Pacific, Fiji*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

245.1 Ariane HANEMAAYER, *Brandon University, Canada*
Socially Possible Worlds: Grounding Normative Statements Beyond Ontological Actualism

245.2 Liubov KLEPIKOVA, *Moscow State University of Railway Engineering, Russian Federation*
The Container Model of Society: The Concept's Origins and Its Theoretical Potential for the Modern Social Transformations Research

245.3 Yoland WADSWORTH, *Foundation for Human Inquiry for Living Systems, Australia*
From the Paradigm Wars to a 'New, New Paradigm' of 'Full Cycle Science' As an Inquiring-for-Life Meta-Epistemology – the Making of a Trans-Disciplinary Sociology for a New Era

10:30-12:20

JS-127 Thinking through and Beyond Capitalism after the Great ResetCommittees: *RC16 Sociological Theory (Host); RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-127.

15:30-17:20

246 Social Imaginaries and Political Forms. Part II**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Jeremy SMITH, *Federation University Australia, Australia***Chair:** Jeremy SMITH, *Federation University Australia, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****246.1** Oday URAIQAT, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
Conflict As a Global Social System: A Treatise on Sociological Theory**246.2** William BRADLEY, *Ryukoku University, Japan*
Social Distortions in the Social Imaginary of the 21st Century Global North**246.3** Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*
Singularity and Social Resistance in the Interplay of Imaginaries, Politics and Religion**246.4** Rana SUKARIEH, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*
Political Imaginaries of Solidarity in Transnational Social Movements: Barriers and Opportunities**246.5** Ben GOOK, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Sean CUBITT, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Cultural Politics: Disaffection and Imagination

17:30-19:20

247 Configuration, Code and Sustainability Part II**Language:** English, French**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Gilles VERPRAET, *University Paris Ouest Nanterre, France***Chairs:** John CASH, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Ben GOOK, *University of Melbourne, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****247.1** Gilles VERPRAET, *University Paris Ouest Nanterre, France*
Zeit Diagnosis and Dialectics of Control : Contribution of Configurational Analysis**247.2** Giulio PITROSO, *Griffith University, Australia*
The Gaming Capital. a Study of Gaming Communities through Bourdieusian Theories**247.3** Caroline SCHOEPPF, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Philippines*
Whiteness and Privilege at Work in Hong Kong: Why Do White Western Migrants Receive Higher Returns to Education on the Hong Kong Labor Market?

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

248 Classical Social Theory and Emotions Revisited**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina*; Vincenzo ROMANIA, *Università degli Studi di Padova, FISPPA,, Italy* and Massimo CERULO, *University of Perugia (IT), Italy***Chair:** Jack BARBALET, *Australian Catholic University, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****248.1** Lorenzo BRUNI, *Università di Perugia, Italy*
Emotional Recognition. Emotions, Sociality and Morality in a Meadian Perspective**248.2** Maria MAIRANO, *CIC-UNLAM ; UBA, Argentina*
An Approach to Digital Sensibilities from Theoretical Contributions of Norbert Elias**248.3** Rodanthe TZANELLI, *Sociology and Social policy, United Kingdom*
Transducing Scheler through the New Mobilities Paradigm**248.4** Alessandra POLIDORI, *Università Perugia, France* and Salzano SALZANO GIULIA, *Università Perugia, Italy*
No Way Home: The Erasmus's Experiences of "Leaving" through Socio-Phenomenological Lenses**DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:****248.5** Helmut STAUBMANN, *University of Innsbruck, Austria*
Emotions and the Crisis of Basic Concepts in Classical Sociology**248.6** Amy VANDERHARST, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Relational Loneliness and Mead's Theory of the Self**248.7** Rock CHUGG, *Freelance, Australia*
A Division of Labour: The Impact of Sociology on Psychology**248.8** Eliana DEBIA, *CONICET-IIGG-FSOC-UBA, Argentina*
Love and Lovelessness in Mary Wollstonecraft's Thought.

12:30-14:20

249 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part IV**Location:** 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Bradley WEST, *University of South Australia, Australia***Chair:** Bradley WEST, *University of South Australia, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****249.1** Joshua KLEIN, *Iona University, USA*; Daniel PATTEN, *Purdue University, USA*; Gabrielle LIRIANO, *Iona University, USA*; Puneet KAUR, *Iona University, USA*; Myles CHIARELLO, *Iona University, USA*; Trent CRESPO, *Iona University, USA* and Rachele LACROIX, *Iona University, USA*
Authoritarianism and Imperial Legitimation in US College Students

249.2 Yulia BELINSKAYA, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Joan Ramon RODRIGUEZ-AMAT, *Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom*
Broken Mirrors and Fake News: The Russian Authoritarianism from Der Spiegel.

14:30-16:20

250 Theorizing Desires: Sexualizing Sociological Theories

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Alan MARTINO, *University of Calgary, Canada*; Ying-chao KAO, *Virginia Commonwealth University, USA* and Ying-chao KAO, *Virginia Commonwealth University, USA*

Chair: Rock CHUGG, *Freelance, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

250.1 Salvador VIDAL-ORTIZ, *American University, USA*
Translating the Queer of Color Critique: The Impossibility of Applying a (racialized, queer theory-based) U.S. Concept in Latin America - for a Truly Hemispheric Approach

250.2 Anna WOZNY, *University of Michigan, USA*
The Land of Rising Celibacy: Racialized Masculinity, (A) Sexuality, and the Global Gender Order

250.3 Alexander KONDAKOV, *University College Dublin, Ireland*
Decentralising the Panopticon: How Neo-Disciplinary Power Relations Work

250.4 Ying-chao KAO, *Virginia Commonwealth University, USA*
Toward a "Liquid Sociology" of Modern Conservatism: Theorizing the Anti-LGBTQ Movements Flowing between Taiwan and the United States

RC17

Sociology of Organization

Program Coordinators: Robert VAN KRIEKEN, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

251 More Than a Buzzword: Wellbeing in Organizations

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jamie FERRILL, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

Chair: Jamie FERRILL, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

251.1 Phoenix WANG, *Renmin University of China, China*
Stress Management and Status Disparity in 911 Dispatch

251.2 Natalia MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, *University of Sydney, Australia*
The Gig Economy, Academic Work and Resigned Hope in Early Career Sociologists

251.3 Maria SANTOS, *SOCIUS / Lisbon School of Economics and Management, Portugal*
Burnout Syndrome: The Case of Financial Professionals

17:30-19:20

252 Meta-Organizations, Meta-Organizing and Grand Challenges (Part 1)

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Heloise BERKOWITZ, *LEST CNRS Aix Marseille University, France*; Martine GADILLE, *CNRS Lest Aix Marseille University, France* and José Augusto LACERDA, *Universidade Federal do Pará, Brazil*

Chair: Benjamin GROSSMANN-HENSEL, *Chair of Organization and Management, Switzerland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

252.1 Heloise BERKOWITZ, *LEST CNRS Aix Marseille University, France*; Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway* and Kurt RACHLITZ, *NTNU, Norway*
The Value of Meta-Organizations for Solving Complex Ecological Problems

252.2 Jose Augusto FERNANDES, *Federal University of Pará (UFPA), Brazil*; Kavita Miadaira HAMZA, *Universidade de São Paulo - USP, Brazil*; Gabriela Nobre DIAS, *Universidade de São Paulo - USP, Brazil* and Graziella Maria COMINI, *Universidade de São Paulo - USP, Brazil*
Meta-Organizations and Bioeconomy in Brazilian Amazon

252.3 Mathilde GOUTEUX, *Aix Marseille Univ, CNRS, LEST, Aix-en-Provence, France*
Literature Review on Meta-Organization and Grand Challenges

252.4 Philippe COULOMBEL, *Toulouse School of Management, France*

Tackling Grand Challenges in Multi-Stakeholder Meta-Organizations: An Institutional Work Perspective

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

253 The Recombinant Strengths of Organisations Employing New Technologies

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Dean PIERIDES, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom* and Abigail MARKS, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*

Chairs: Dean PIERIDES, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom* and Abigail MARKS, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*

Panelists: Catherine CASLER, *University of Stirling, Scotland* and Graham SEWELL, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

15:30-17:20

254 Meta-Organizations, Meta-Organizing and Grand Challenges (Part 2)

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Heloise BERKOWITZ, *LEST CNRS Aix Marseille University, France*; Martine GADILLE, *CNRS Lest Aix Marseille University, France* and José Augusto LACERDA, *Universidade Federal do Pará, Brazil*

Chair: Kurt RACHLITZ, *NTNU, Norway*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

254.1 Heloise BERKOWITZ, *LEST CNRS Aix Marseille University, France* and José Augusto LACERDA, *Universidade Federal do Pará, Brazil*
"Indigenous Meta-Organizations": Learnings from the the Amazonian Forest

254.2 Benjamin GROSSMANN-HENSEL, *Chair of Organization and Management, Switzerland*
Between Meta-Organization and Sub-Organization: Bureaucracies As Internal Reflectors of Complex Environments

254.3 Ricardo MELLO DUARTE, *FGV, Brazil* and Alexandre FARIA, *FGV, Brazil*
The Disputes over State Capacities to Fight Hunger and Promote Food Security in Brazil

254.4 Alison BUCK, *Eastern Kentucky University, USA* and Kylie PARROTTA, *California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, USA*
A Negotiated Order Approach to Organizational Identity Change Processes

17:30-19:20

JS-47 Historical Sociology of Organizations. Part I

Committees: RC56 *Historical Sociology (Host)*; RC17 *Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-47.

19:30-20:50

255 RC17 Business Meeting

Location: M4 (Crown)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

256 How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 1)

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Leopold RINGEL, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Kathia SERRANO VELARDE, *Heidelberg University, Germany* and Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway*

Chair: Kathia SERRANO VELARDE, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

256.1 Yingjian LIANG, *Indiana University, USA*
Job Search As Cultural Adaptation: How Organizations Make People before Hiring Them

256.2 Alice NEUSIEDLER, *Yale University, USA*
Formatting Engagement in Participative Art Collaborations

256.3 Nicholas HILL, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Cameron DUFF, *RMIT University, Australia*
Infrastructures of Care: Fixing 'Glitches' in Mental Health, AOD, and Housing Services

256.4 Julia DESSAUER, *University of Virginia, USA*
Assistants As Agents: Precarious Labor in Hollywood

15:30-17:20

JS-68 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part I

Committees: *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host)*; *RC24 Environment and Society* *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food* and *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-68.

17:30-19:20

JS-77 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part II

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host)*; *RC17 Sociology of Organization* *RC24 Environment and Society* and *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-77.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-85 Crisis and State Capacities 1: Crises and Challenges

Committees: *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host)*; *RC18 Political Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-85.

10:30-12:20

257 Author Meets Critics: Richard Badham & Brenda Santiago - Ironies of Organizational Change

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Stewart CLEGG, *UTS, Australia***Chair:** Stewart CLEGG, *UTS, Australia***Panelist:** Stewart CLEGG, *UTS, Australia*

15:30-17:20

JS-104 Whistleblowing and Social Justice

Committees: *RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host)*; *RC17 Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-104.

17:30-19:20

JS-109 Organizing through Standards and Value Hierarchies

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host)*; *RC17 Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-109.

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

258 Organizational Networks: Innovation and Learning in Response of Organizational Challenges**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Adriana FASSIO, *Facultad de Ciencias Económicas Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina* and Maria Gabriela RUTTY, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*

Chair: Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

258.1 Mayya SHMIDT, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Sharing Economy in Sweden: A Sociological Study of the Organizational Field for Non-Commercial Sharing.

258.2 Matjaz URSIC, *University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences, Slovenia*
Studying Interdisciplinary through the Analysis of Cognitive Networks between Scientists in Spatial Sciences – the Case of Slovenia

258.3 Letitia DEL FABBRO, *Griffith University, Australia*
Extra-Organisational Knowledge Exchange: An Exploration of Relational Agency and Capacity Building through an Intersectoral Place-Based Health Promotion Network

258.4 Alberto LUSOLI, *Digital Democracies Institute, Simon Fraser University, Italy*
Between Hope and Despair: The Bootstrap Worker As a New Professional Figure

15:30-17:20

259 How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 2)

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Leopold RINGEL, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Kathia SERRANO VELARDE, *Heidelberg University, Germany* and Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway*

Chair: Leopold RINGEL, *Bielefeld University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

259.1 Raimund HASSE, *University of Lucerne, Switzerland*; Hoky HWANG, *UNSW Sydney, Australia* and Hannah MORMANN, *University of Lucerne, Switzerland*
New Professionals and the Organizational Making of the Individual. Universities As Model Case.

259.2 Kaoru SONODA, *Japan Society for the Promotion of Science, Japan*
How Should Organizations Deal with Individual Personalities and Social Aspects?: A Case Study of Japanese Companies' Employment Relationships with Highly Skilled Foreign Workers

259.3 Elisabeth STRIETZEL, *Bielefeld University, Germany* and Can David TOBIAS, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
How to Become a (temporary) Member of a Ranking-Producing Organization

259.4 Cass SEVER, *University at Albany, State University of New York, USA*
You Are Harmful: How Social Science Technology Can Dominate Organizations

17:30-19:20

260 How Organizations Make People: Identities, Subjectivities, and Agencies (Part 3)

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Leopold RINGEL, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Kathia SERRANO VELARDE, *Heidelberg University, Germany* and Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway*

Chair: Michael GROTHE-HAMMER, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

260.1 Anna KHANUKAEVA, *Uppsala university, Sweden*
Expectation Work. Postdocs Sense Making of Academia

260.2 Jan HAYES, *RMIT University, Australia* and Sarah MASLEN, *University of Canberra, Australia*
How Engineers Account for Their Professional Identities

260.3 Leonie BUSCHKAMP, *Leibniz University Hannover (LCSS - Leibniz Center for Science and Society), Germany* and Tim SEIDENSCHNUR, *University of Kassel (INCHER - International Center for Higher Education Research), Germany*
Contests and the Making of People. a Comparative Perspective on Organizational Socialization in Different Types of Organizations.

260.4 Matt WADE, *La Trobe University, Australia*
The Demand for Good Feelings during Bad Times: Automated Hiring Software and the Growing Affective Gap between Employers and Job Applicants

260.5 Annika KOCH, *University of Potsdam, Germany* and Maja APELT, *University of Potsdam, Germany*
(How) Do Moral Values of Organizations Shape Their Members' Identities? Examples from Public High Schools and the Armed Forces in Germany

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

261 (Meta)Theorizing in Organizational Sociology

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Thiago PIMENTEL, *Federal University of Juiz de Fora / UFJF, Brazil* and Robert JUNGSMANN, *Trier University, Germany*

Chairs: Thiago PIMENTEL, *Federal University of Juiz de Fora / UFJF, Brazil* and Robert JUNGSMANN, *Trier University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

261.1 Wei ZHAO, *University of California, Riverside, USA* and Jianhua GE, *Renmin University, China*
Synthesis of Two Field Theories: The Dual Institutional Process and Differential Organizational Status

261.2 Ronald STAPLES, *Friedrich-Alexander-University, Germany*
No New Organization. Organization As a Modern Approach on How to Translate Meaning.

261.3 Takis JAKOB, *University of Trier, Germany*
Potentials of a Rhizomatic Organization Theory: Deleuze, Guattari and the Decentralized Autonomous Organization

261.4 Amanda GROSS, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*
What Is Management and Organization Studies Made of? an Invitation to Recover the Multiplicities and the Interdependence within the Field in Face of the Grand Challenges and the Anthropocene

261.5 Lini BARUAH, *Dibrugarh University, India*
The Role of Organization in the Development of Social Structure in Society: A Sociological Study

10:30-12:20

262 Organizations and Digital Innovation**Location:** M4 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Cornelia FEDTKE, *Helmut Schmidt University, Germany*; Marco JOESTINGMEIER, *Helmut-Schmidt-Universität Hamburg, Germany* and Anna SKRIPCHENKO, *Helmut Schmidt University, Germany***Chair:** Cornelia FEDTKE, *Helmut Schmidt University, Germany***Co-Chair:** Marco JOESTINGMEIER, *Helmut Schmidt University, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****262.1** Timothy MARJORIBANKS, *Swinburne University of Technology, Australia***Contested Power: Strategically Managing Digital Innovation in the Production of Newspapers****262.2** David SEIBT, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*
Digitalization As Recombination: New Patterns of Co-Construction between Industrial Organizations and Their Users**262.3** Andreas WALKER, *ADG Scientific - Center for Research and Cooperation e.V., Germany* and Katharina ISACK, *ADG Scientific - Center for Research and Cooperation e.V., Germany*
The Digitisation of Cooperatives during the Covid-19 Pandemic

12:30-14:20

JS-147 Historical Sociology of Organizations. Part II**Committees:** *RC56 Historical Sociology (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-147.

14:30-16:20

JS-151 Organising Precarity and Inequality in the Gig Economy**Committees:** *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-151.

RC18

Political Sociology

Program Coordinators: Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, *EHESS, University of Paris 8, France* and Naoko TOKUMITSU, *French Research Institute on East Asia (IFRAE), France*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

263 Security Policies and Their Effects: Repression, Securitization and Precarity // Fluctuations of Political Capital in Authoritarian Contexts

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Catharina PEECK-HO, *Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany*

Chairs: Rebecca GUEZ, *University Paris-Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France*; Benjamin RIVIALE, *University Paris-Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France* and Guillaume CORNU, *University of Paris Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France*

Discussants: Rebecca GUEZ, *University Paris-Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France*; Benjamin RIVIALE, *University Paris-Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France* and Guillaume CORNU, *University of Paris Nanterre, Institut des Sciences sociales du Politique, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

263.1 Catharina PEECK-HO, *Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany*
Securitization within European Democracies: The Example of the British Prevent-Strategy.

263.2 Adriane SANCTIS, *Center for the Analysis of Freedom and Authoritarianism (LAUT), Brazil* and Mariana CELANO DE SOUZA AMARAL, *University of Sao Paulo (USP), Brazil*
Securitizing the Road to Autocracy: Public Security Policies As Strategies of Democratic Erosion in Hungary, Poland, Turkey, India and Brazil

263.3 Nicolas TARDITS, *Université Paris Nanterre, ISP, France* and Franck DUCHESNE, *Université Paris Nanterre, ISP, France*
Les « Bons » Notables De l'Empire Redéfinition Des Qualités Politiques En Configurations Monopolistiques

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy RC20 Comparative Sociology RC56 Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

17:30-19:20

JS-16 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part I

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC07 Futures Research and RC16 Sociological Theory

See Joint Session Details for JS-16.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

264 Preferences for Redistribution in the Global South

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Liza STEELE, *CUNY John Jay College & The Graduate Center, USA*; Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany* and Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

264.1 Elisa REIS, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Felix LOPEZ, *IPEA, Brazil*
Change and Continuity in the Perceptions of Poverty, Inequality, and Role of the State Among Brazilian Elites

264.2 Manuela MENDOZA HORVITZ, *Universidad de O'Higgins, Chile* and Gabriel OTERO, *Central University of Chile, Netherlands*
The Power of Diversity: Class, Networks and Attitudes Towards Inequality

264.3 Gonzalo FRANETOVIC, *University of Milan, Italy*
Preferences for Income Redistribution in Unequal Contexts: Changes in Latin America between 2008 and 2018

10:30-12:20

265 Globalisation at a Crossroads: Current Perspectives and Future Assessments

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Manfred STEGER, *University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA*

Chair: Manfred STEGER, *University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA*

Discussant: Manfred STEGER, *University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

265.1 Paul JAMES, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Disjunctive Globalization in the Age of the Great Unsettling

265.2 Ingrid KOFLER, *Free University of Bolzano, Italy*
Deglobalization of Reglobalization?

265.3 Amentahru WAHLRAB, *The University of Texas at Tyler, USA*
Globalization and Nonviolence in the 21st Century

265.4 Barbara WEJNERT, *Dept. of Environment and Sustainability and Dept. of Transnational Studies, State University of New York, Univ. at Buffalo, USA*
Global Democracy Retrenchment and Rise of Autocracy: Challenges to Environmental Politics

265.5 Kennedy chi-pan WONG, *University of Southern California, USA*
How Should We Talk about 'We'? Mapping 'Our' Authoritarian Struggles to the Broader World

15:30-17:20

266 Analyzing the Links between Authoritarian Political Practices and Reactionary Ideas

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Boris ATTENCOURT, *Ecole des hautes études en sciences sociales (EHESS), France* and Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, *Catholic Institute of Paris, France*

Chair: Boris ATTENCOURT, *Ecole des hautes études en sciences sociales (EHESS), France*

Co-Chair: Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, *Catholic Institute of Paris, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

266.1 Felix SCHILK, *Technische Universität Dresden, Germany*
The Metapolitics of Reaction

266.2 Claude DARGENT, *Cresppa, France*
Autoritarisme d'Extrême-Droite Et Rapports Sociaux De Sexe En France Aujourd'Hui

266.4 Luciano SANTANDER, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Authoritarian Mechanisms of Neoliberalism: On the Implementation and Validity of the Hegemony of Neoliberalism in Latin America

266.5 Natalia GRANATO, *Universidade Federal do Paraná, Brazil*
Bonapartismo En El Estado Brasileño: Un Estudio Sobre El Gobierno Del Presidente Jair Bolsonaro

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

266.6 João Mauro CARVALHO, *NA, Brazil*; Pedro Luis PANIGASSI, *UNESP, Brazil*; João Túbero Gomes SILVA, *UNESP, Brazil*; Laura Gabrieli Pereira SILVA, *UNESP, Brazil* and Talic Jaber SLEMAN, *UNESP, Brazil*
Digitalization, Public Sphere and Patterns of Authority: Analysis of Political Mobilization By Far-Right through Digital Social Media.

17:30-19:20

JS-51 Political Socialization in Changing Times: Generations and Agents.

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-51.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-58 Is Nationalism Democratic or Authoritarian?

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity

See Joint Session Details for JS-58.

10:30-12:20

267 New Theories of Political Sociology: Power, Social Psychology, and Macro-Bargaining

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Thomas JANOSKI, *University of Kentucky, USA*

Chair: Darina LEPADATU, *Kennesaw State University, USA*

Panelist: Thomas JANOSKI, *University of Kentucky, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

267.1 Kate BROWN, *Georgia Institute of Technology, USA*
The Field of Power: A New Analytic Strategy for Political Sociology

267.2 Jeffrey BROADBENT, *University of Minnesota, USA*
The Dimensions of Power: A Relational Research Method

267.3 Jakob HARTL, *University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Storming the Capital. Power, Domination, and (Mis-) Recognition

267.4 Simeon NEWMAN, *University of Michigan, USA*
Social Theory and the Sociology of Clientelism: A Critical Prolegomenon and Gramscian Proposal

267.5 Anand RAJA, *Prof. Rajendra Singh (Rajju Bhaiya) University, India*
The Meeting of Hindu Nationalism and Vikas: A Power Play

267.6 Thomas JANOSKI, *Kentucky Univ, USA*
The Generalized Other As the Site of Political Identity

15:30-17:20

JS-71 Doing Research on Young People with Young People: Co-Productions, Co-Authoring and Collaborations

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC18 Political Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-71.

17:30-19:20

268 Invited Session : Authoritarianisms and Democracies through the Intermediaries of Public Action

Language: English, French

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Naoko TOKUMITSU, *French Research Institute on East Asia (IFRAE), France* and Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, *Catholic Institute of Paris, France*

Chair: Vicente ESPINOZA, *Universidad Santiago de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

268.1 Elise MASSICARD, *Sciences Po CERI, France*
The Political Effects of the Involvement of Non-State Actors in Governing

268.2 Isabelle THIREAU, *Centre for Studies on China, Korea and Japan, France*
From Public Gatherings to Intermediary Publics: Acting Together in Tianjin (PRC)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-85 Crisis and State Capacities 1: Crises and Challenges

Committees: RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC18 Political Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-85.

10:30-12:20

269 Crisis and State Capacities 2: Shifting State Capacities

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Stephanie ALENDA, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile and Alan SCOTT, University of New England, Australia

Chair: Stephanie ALENDA, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

269.1 Paul DU GAY, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark and Thomas LOPDRUP-HJORTH, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark
“Reason of State” As an Organising Stance for the World As We Find It.

269.2 Sonal SHARMA, Johns Hopkins University, USA
The Personal Is Bureaucratic: Bureaucratic Practices and Paid Domestic Work in South Africa

15:30-17:20

270 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited Part III

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Chad GOLDBERG, University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States

Chair: Felipe GARCIA, Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

270.1 Mark GOULD, Haverford College, USA
Fascism: Towards a General Sociological Theory

270.2 Spyros SOFOS, The London School of Economics, United Kingdom
The Construction of ‘auctoritas’ and the ‘people’ in Turkish Populism

270.3 Zezheng LIN, School of Foreign Languages, Renmin University of China, China; Jing ZHANG, Renmin University of China, China and Jingcheng LI, Renmin University of China, China
Metamorphosis of Power Governmentality : a Demolition Process at the Heart of Peking

17:30-19:20

JS-105 Building Local Participatory Democracies in the Era of Threatened National Democracies and Resurgent Authoritarianism.

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC18 Political Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-105.

19:30-20:50

271 RC18 Business Meeting

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Stephanie ALENDA, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

JS-121 Combating Homelessness in Welfare State Regimes: A New Paradigm Shift in Local Social Policy?

Committees: RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy (Host); RC18 Political Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-121.

15:30-17:20

272 Conservative Mobilizations of Local Organizations : Power Relations and Tensions Around Democracy

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, Catholic Institute of Paris, France and Naoko TOKUMITSU, Inalco, France

Chair: Maricel RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, Catholic Institute of Paris, France

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

272.1 Juan Jesús MORALES, Universidad Católica Silva Henríquez, Chile
Los Think Tanks En Chile En Tiempos De La Politización (2011-2022). Análisis Del Campo, Estudios De Caso y Proceso Constitucional

272.2 Belen DIAZ, Freie Universitat Berlin, Germany
“Make Neoliberalism Cool Again”: Right-Wing Subject (Trans-) Formations in Brazil

272.3 Susan GOODWIN, Sydney University, Australia; Jessica GERRARD, University of Melbourne, Australia and Helen PROCTOR, University of Sydney, Australia
2. Grassroots Conservatism and Participatory Politics: Mobilisations Against the ‘Perils of Progressivism’ in Australian Schools.

JS-130 Complexity in the Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe (II)

Committees: *RC51 Sociocybernetics (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-130.

17:30-19:20

JS-137 The Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe

Committees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC51 Sociocybernetics*

See Joint Session Details for JS-137.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

273 Meritocracy and Refinement of Authoritarianism in Growing Inequality

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Siyu LI, *Ecole Normale Supérieure de Paris- PSL, France* and Hanzhang LIU, *Pitzer College, USA*

Chair: Siyu LI, *Ecole Normale Supérieure de Paris- PSL, France, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

273.1 Cinzia LOSAVIO, *University Paris 1 - Pantheon Sorbonne (Geographie-cites UMR 8504), France*

Building Wealth through a Stratified and High-End Inclusion: The New Social Ladder of Internal Migrants in Urban China: The Case of Zhuhai (Guangdong)

273.2 Junghaa WANG, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Gender Gap in Meritocratic Belief: Examining South Korea's 2022 Presidential Election

273.3 Edna MULERAS, *CONICET/ Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Self-Centering Process, Meritocratic Conceptions and Political Identity in Working Class in Argentina in the 21st Century.

273.4 Kaja GADOWSKA, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
Practices for Staffing Public Sector Positions in Poland. Resurgence of the Nomenclature System

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

273.5 Emilia ȘERCAN, *Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies, University of Bucharest, Romania* and Raluca RADU, *Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies, University of Bucharest, Romania*
Why Four Romanian Pms Have Plagiarised PhD Theses (in the last decade)

10:30-12:20

274 Toward a New Political Sociology of Health

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Rima WILKES, *University of British Columbia, Canada*; Daniel SILVER, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Eric MYKHALOVSKIY, *York University, Canada*

Chair: Cary WU, *York University, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

274.1 Zhe CHEN, *Tsinghua University, China*
Political Ideology and Health Status in the East Asian Context: Evidence from Mainland China, Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan

274.2 Kaitlyn JAFFE, *University of Michigan, Canada*; Kayte SPECTOR-BAGDADY, *University of Michigan, USA* and Lindsey RICHARDSON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Drug Policy, Politics, and the Production of Knowledge in Multisite Substance Use Trials

274.3 Fernanda LOBATO, *Sciences Po Paris, France*
Sex Work and PTSD : On the Emergency of a Public Health Controversy

12:30-14:20

275 The State and Society Relationship in East Asian Countries Under COVID-19 Pandemic

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Hidehiro YAMAMOTO, *University of Tsukuba, Japan*

Chair: Naoko TOKUMITSU, *French Research Institute on East Asia (IFRAE), France*

Panelists: Kwang-Yeong SHIN, *Chung-Ang University, Republic of Korea*; Hyun-Chin LIM, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*; Valeria DONATO, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*; Sae OKURA, *University of Tsukuba, Japan* and Taisuke FUJITA, *Nagasaki University, Japan*

Discussant: Hidehiro YAMAMOTO, *University of Tsukuba, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

275.1 Kwang-Yeong SHIN, *Chung-Ang University, Republic of Korea* and Hyun-Chin LIM, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Covid-19 Pandemic and the Legitimacy of the State in South Korea: Public Health Crisis, Political Contention, and the Public Opinion

275.2 Valeria DONATO, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
#Fightvirus to Win "Hearts and Minds": Rethinking Propaganda through Covid-19

275.3 Sae OKURA, *University of Tsukuba, Japan*
How Did the Japanese Nursing Association Respond to the COVID-19 Crisis?: New State and Society's Relationship during the Pandemic

275.4 Taisuke FUJITA, *Nagasaki University, Japan* and Hidehiro YAMAMOTO, *University of Tsukuba, Japan*
Can Rawls Explain People's Attitudes Toward the State's Role Under the COVID-19 Pandemic?

275.5 Woontaek LIM, *Keimyung University, Republic of Korea*
Northeast Asia International Order and Governance Tasks after COVID-19

14:30-16:20

276 Social Constraint and Self-Control in Times of Pandemic Crisis

Language: English, French

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Naoko TOKUMITSU, *Inalco, France* and Cesar CASTELLVI, *Paris Cité University, France*

Chair: Naoko TOKUMITSU, *French Research Institute on East Asia (IFRAE), France*

Discussant: Hidehiro YAMAMOTO, *University of Tsukuba, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

276.1 Raisa TY, *University of Eastern Philippines, Philippines*
Who and What Is Essential?: COVID-19 Quarantine Guidelines in the Provinces in Samar Island, Philippines

276.2 Shaozhi ZHONG, *School of Economics, Renmin University of China, China* and Jason LIN, *School of Foreign Languages, Renmin University of China, China*
To Devote the Body for Harmony: A Comparison Study on Beijing Elite Universities' Dynamic Zero-COVID Policy during the 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China

276.3 Hidehiro YAMAMOTO, *University of Tsukuba, Japan* and Taisuke FUJITA, *Nagasaki University, Japan*
What Limits on Freedom Are Permissible?: A Comparative Analysis of Japan, Korea, and China Under COVID-19

RC19

Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy

Program Coordinators: Tracy FENWICK, *22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia* and Enrique DELAMONICA, *UNICEF, USA*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology (Host); RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy RC20 Comparative Sociology RC56 Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

277 Wealth, Welfare and the Asset Economy. Part I

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ben SPIES-BUTCHER, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Adam STEBBING, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Tom BAKER, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Lisa ADKINS, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Gareth BRYANT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Martijn KONINGS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Claire PARFITT, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Hang LEE, *Macquarie University, Australia*

Chair: Tom BARNES, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

277.1 Tom BAKER, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Intermediating Impoverishment: Consultants and the Emergence of Social Finance Markets

277.2 Rachel ROWE, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
A Tale of Two Bonds: The Technoscientific Features of Experimental Finance in Social Services and Public Health

277.3 Jacob BROOM, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
The Mutating Face of Australian Social Impact Bonds and the Financialisation of Policy Life

277.4 Claire PARFITT, *University of Sydney, Australia*
The Possibilities and Limits of Ethical Capital As a Vehicle for Political Action

277.5 Ben SPIES-BUTCHER, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Michael BEGGS, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Gareth BRYANT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Connecting Fiscal, Monetary and Social Policy: COVID Responses and the Asset Economy

10:30-12:20

278 Advanced democracies.

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Cornelia WALTHER, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Chair: Mathieu LIZOTTE, *University of Ottawa, Canada*

Discussant: Sunyu HAM, *KIHASA, Republic of Korea*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

278.1 Roberta ADAMI, *Glasgow Caledonian University, United Kingdom*
At Risk of Poverty and Social Exclusion in Europe: A Study on Genders and Cohorts after Retirement

278.2 Koichi HIRAOKA, *Tokyo Online University, Japan*
Managerialist Trends and the Role of the Performance Evaluation of Social Welfare Plans in Local Governments in Japan.

278.3 Sanna KARKKAINEN, *Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland*; Merita MESIAISLEHTO, *Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland* and Netta TUOMINEN, *Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland*
Patterns of Employment and Use of Social Benefits and Services Among Persons with Partial Work Capacity

278.4 Arianna GATTA, *University of Queensland, Italy*
A Welfare for the Truly Needy? Targeting, Conditionality and Non-Take up of Welfare Among the Homeless in Italy

278.5 Sunyu HAM, *KIHASA, Republic of Korea*
The Development of Care Policies and the Gender Wage Gap in Korea

15:30-17:20

JS-44 Variegated Intersections of Social Policy and Finance

Committees: RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy (Host); RC02 Economy and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-44.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

279 Wealth, Welfare and the Asset Economy. Part II

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ben SPIES-BUTCHER, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Gareth BRYANT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Lisa ADKINS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Martijn KONINGS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Adam STEBBING, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Hang LEE, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Tom BAKER, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Chair: Claire PARFITT, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

279.1 Lisa ADKINS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Gareth BRYANT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Sarah CAMERON, *Griffith University, Australia* and Martijn KONINGS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
The Asset-Owners' Welfare State

279.2 Hang LEE, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Xiaoguang FAN, *Zhejiang University, China*; Peng LU, *Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, China* and Lisa A. KEISTER, *Duke University, USA*
Top Wealth Households in China and the U.S.

279.3 Mathieu LIZOTTE, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
Facing Today's Challenges with Lessons from the Past: The Evolution of Wealth Inequality in Canada and the United States in the Aftermath of the 2008 Financial Crisis

279.4 Tom BARNES, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Considering Asset-Based Inequality through the Lens of Career Development and Loss: The Case of Australia's Auto Manufacturing Workers

279.5 Ben SPIES-BUTCHER, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Adam STEBBING, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Crisis Responses in the Asset Economy: Comparing Social Policy COVID Measures in Australia, Chile and Korea

15:30-17:20

280 Social Protection in Africa and Asia: Challenges and Innovations

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Enrique DELAMONICA, *UNICEF, USA*

Chair: Tracy FENWICK, *22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

280.1 Fen ling CHEN, *ICSW, Taiwan*
New Welfare Productivism? Social Policies for the Pandemic in North-East Asia Region of ICSW

280.2 Kolawole OMOMOWO, *University of Namibia, Namibia*
The Practice of Collective Consumption of Housing in a Fragmented Social Policy Context, Windhoek, Namibia

280.3 Bo MA, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Shenjing HE, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
One-on-One Pairing Mechanism Under China's Targeted Poverty Alleviation Scheme and Its Implications for Poverty Governance: Evidence from a County in Western China

280.4 Amiya DAS, *Centre for Public Policy and Governance, India*
Seeing like a Citizen: Welfare Provisions and Negotiations of Poor in Everyday Life

17:30-19:20

JS-82 Professional Transformations in Public Sector/Social Services Management: Trends and Challenges – between Managerial 'Governmentality' and Authoritarian Governance?

Committees: RC52 *Sociology of Professional Groups (Host)*; RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy*

See Joint Session Details for JS-82.

19:30-20:50

281 RC19 Business Meeting

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

282 Sensibilities, Pandemic and Social Policies

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Angelica DE SENA, *UNLAM-UBA-CIES, Argentina*; Andrea DETTANO, *CONICET, Argentina* and Rebeca CENA, *CCONFINES-CONICET, Argentina*

Chair: Cristina GOMES, *FLACSO Mexico, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

282.1 Arkadiusz KARWACKI, *Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland* and Joanna STANKOWSKA, *Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland*
What Social Policy Is Expected By the Middle Class? the Universal Conditions and Local Experiences Based on the Diaries.

282.2 Rebeca CENA, *CONICET/CONFINES, Argentina*
Social Policies, Gratitude and "Alleviation"

282.3 Andrea DETTANO, *CONICET, Argentina*
Emociones y Consumo En Receptores De Políticas Sociales Del Municipio De La Matanza, Buenos Aires, Argentina

282.4 Angelica DE SENA, *UNLAM-UBA-CIES, Argentina*
Políticas Sociales y Políticas De Las Sensibilidades: Revisión Analítica De Algunos Programas Sociales En La Argentina Pos Pandemia Del Covid-19

10:30-12:20

283 Reconsidering Concepts and Ideas in Current Welfare State Policies

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Birgit PFAU-EFFINGER, *University of Hamburg, Germany* and Patricia FRERICKS, *University of Kassel, Germany*

Chair: Birgit PFAU-EFFINGER, *University of Hamburg, Germany*

Discussant: Fen ling CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

283.1 Emily CLARK, *University College London, United Kingdom*
Is the Universal Basic Income a Neoliberal Policy? Analysing the Constitution of the Universal Basic Income in UK Policy Discourse During the Covid-19 Pandemic.

283.2 Chao-Ching WANG, *National Chung -Cheng University, Taiwan* and Shu-Yung WANG, *Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*
Driving Forces for Taiwan's Childcare Policy to Adopt Regulated Market and Its Divergence

283.3 John Eustice O'BRIEN, *Portland State University (ret.), Monaco*
Thomas Piketty's Package of Structural Reform: Intellectual Fame without Practical Consequences?

283.4 Hsiao-Mei JUAN, *National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*
The Rationalities of Welfare Chauvinism and the Future of the Welfare State

283.5 Kosuke SAKAI, *The University of Tokyo, Japan* and Hyewon PARK, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
A Theoretical Examination of the Concept of Familialism in Compressed Modernity: Toward Further Development of Welfare Regime Typology

15:30-17:20

284 RC19 Open Session Global South emerging economies**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Tracy FENWICK, 22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia**Chair:** Frank SOWA, Nuremberg Institute of Technology Georg Simon Ohm, Germany**Discussant:** Tracy FENWICK, 22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

284.1 Joakim PALME, Uppsala University, Sweden and Carolina JANSON, Stockholm University, Sweden
Social Protection in East and Southeast Asia and the Great Recession

284.2 Jimi ADESINA, University of South Africa, South Africa
Antinomies of Segregated Social Policy: What Lessons for a Post-Covid-19 Architecture in Africa?

284.3 Karita KAN, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Waiting for Development: Land, Livelihoods, and Lockdown in Rural China

284.4 Miguel LATTZ, Australian National University, Australia
Social Equality Versus Equality of Opportunities and Their Impact on Social Policy. the Years after the Chilean Estallido Social.

284.5 Diego MAGGI, Darcy Ribeiro Institute of Information and Research, Brazil and Camila STAMM, Universidade Federal do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
The "Social Revolution of Maricá": Social Policy, Basic Income and Development of a Brazilian City

17:30-19:20

285 Eco-Social Policies: Is a Consensus between the Ecological, Social and Economic Possible?**Location:** 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Madelaine MOORE, Bielefeld University, Germany and Alexandra KAASCH, Bielefeld University, Germany**Chair:** Frank SOWA, Nuremberg Institute of Technology Georg Simon Ohm, Germany**Discussant:** John BERTEN, Bielefeld University, Germany**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

285.1 Siri HETTIGE, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka
Balancing Economic, Social and Ecological Imperatives in Facing Multiple Challenges in Sri Lanka

285.2 Adeline OTTO, KU Leuven, Belgium and Matteo MANDELLI, KU Leuven, Italy
What Just Transition Do We Want? Suggestions for Public Opinion Research on Eco-Social Policies

285.3 Kenneth NELSON, University of Oxford, England and Arvid LINDH, Stockholm University, Sweden
Carbon Taxes, Redistribution, and Environmental Attitudes in Comparative Perspective.

285.4 Joakim PALME, Uppsala University, Sweden; Maria NORDBRANDT BERGSTRÖM, Department of Government, Uppsala University, Sweden; Moa MÅRTENSSON, Department of Government, Uppsala University, Sweden and Lauri PETERSON, Department of Government, Uppsala University, Sweden
Combating Climate Change through Institutional Complementarities? Social Protection Policies and Citizen Support for Fossil Fuel Taxes in Europe

285.5 Romana XEREZ, Instituto Superior de Ciências Sociais e Políticas- Universidade de Lisboa - CAPP, Portugal
Global ECO Social Policy and Welfare System in the Portuguese Speaking Countries

285.6 Greg MARSTON, The University of Queensland, Australia
Social Policy and Just Transitions: The Need to Go Beyond Jobs and Retraining

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

285.7 Robin SCHULZE WALTRUP, Bielefeld University, Germany; Madelaine MOORE, Bielefeld University, Germany and Tim PAULSEN, Bielefeld University, Germany
Subsidising Jobs or Ecocide? Analysing Agricultural Subsidies through the Lens of Eco-Social Policy

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

286 Intersectionalities - Race, Gender and Social Class Discrimination, Religion and Political Identification.**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Cristina GOMES, FLACSO Mexico, Mexico**Chair:** Rebeca CENA, CCONFINES-CONICET, Argentina**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

286.1 Yurie MOMOSE, The University of Tokyo, Japan
Intersectionality and Employment Policies: Women with Health Problems

286.2 Hildegard THEOBALD, University of Vechta, Germany
The Intersection of Gender, Socio-Economic Class and Migration in Elderly Care: Sweden and Germany Compared

286.3 Silje FEKJAER, Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway; Lars Inge TERUM, Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway and Einar OVERBYE, Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway
Activation Policies: Who Deserves to be Sanctioned? a Vignette Experiment of Possible Ethnic Discrimination Among Norwegian Street-Level Bureaucrats

286.4 Jan ALAM, Department of Sociology, Kohat University of Science and Technology, Kohat KPK, Pakistan
Religious Identity and Politics: Exploring the Factors of Political Persecution Faced Religious Minorities in Pakistan

10:30-12:20

JS-121 Combating Homelessness in Welfare State Regimes: A New Paradigm Shift in Local Social Policy?

Committees: *RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy (Host); RC18 Political Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-121.

15:30-17:20

287 RC19 Keynote Address: Social Safety Nets in OECD Countries: Tracing Three Decades of Change

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tracy FENWICK, *22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia*

Chair: Tracy FENWICK, *22 Haydon Allen Bldg, SPIR, Australia*

Panelist: Peter WHITEFORD, *Australian National University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

287.1 Peter WHITEFORD, *Australian National University, Australia*
Social Safety Nets in OECD Countries: Tracing Three Decades of Change

17:30-19:20

288 Beyond the Extremely Poor: Social Policies and Individual Strategies in the Global South

Language: English, French

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Monica BUDOWSKI, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland* and Daniel KUENZLER, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*

Chair: Daniel KUENZLER, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*

Discussant: Monica BUDOWSKI, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

288.1 Ilcheong YI, *UNRISD, Switzerland*; Alexandra KAASCH, *Bielefeld University, Germany* and Kelly STETTER, *International Social Security Association, Switzerland*
Emerging Trends in Social Policy from and for the South: Institutions and Actors

288.2 Lauren GRAHAM, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Ariane DE LANNOY, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
A Service System Strengthening Approach on to Promoting Service Delivery to Neet Youth in Underserved Communities

288.3 Sandeepan TRIPATHY, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Being in Debt to Avoid Poverty

288.4 Marina JOSEPH, *Youth for Unity and Voluntary Action (YUVA), India* and Roshni NUGGEHALLI, *Youth for Unity and Voluntary Action (YUVA), India*
Improving Social Protection in India through Partnerships between Civil Society and the State

288.5 Chitra NAIR, *Govt. K NM College, India*
Food for Life, Food for Thought – an Evaluation of Hunger Free District Project and Community Kitchens in Kerala (India) As a Model to Build Social Capital and Good Governance

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

289 Global Social Policy in Times of Crisis: Covid-19 and the Role of International Organizations

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: John BERTEN, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Alexandra KAASCH, *Bielefeld University, Germany* and Madelaine MOORE, *Bielefeld University, Germany*

Chair: Robin SCHULZE WALTRUP, *Bielefeld University, Germany*

Discussant: Alexandra KAASCH, *Bielefeld University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

289.1 Nathaniel UMUKORO, *Western Delta University, Nigeria*; Maryanne WAMAHIU, *University of Bayreuth, Germany* and Tim DORLACH, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*
Global Ideas and Domestic Politics: Nigeria's School Feeding Program before and after Covid-19

289.2 Thurid EGGERS, *University of Bremen, Germany*; Christopher GRAGES, *University of Hamburg, Germany* and Birgit PFAU-EFFINGER, *University of Hamburg, Germany*
Informalizing Childcare during the Pandemic? Policies Towards Childcare during the First Wave of the COVID-19 Pandemic in Different Types of Care Arrangements

289.3 Alexandra KAASCH, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Monika Ewa KAMINSKA, *University of Bremen, Germany*; Kerstin MARTENS, *University of Bremen, Germany*; John BERTEN, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Kirby GRABO, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Sooahn MEIER, *University of Bremen, Germany* and Madelaine MOORE, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
Global Social Policy Ideas in the Covid-19 Crisis: Expansion or Retrenchment?

289.4 Hannah DAWSON, *Southern Centre for Inequality Studies, South Africa*
Redistributive Politics and the Possibilities of Crisis: The Case of Social Protection in South Africa during Covid-19

289.5 Eleonora CLERICI, *Sapienza, University of Rome, Italy*
Local Organizations As an Answer Against Abyssal Exclusion and Advanced Marginality in European Cities

RC20

Comparative Sociology

Program Coordinators: Kseniya KIZILOVA, *World Values Survey Association, Austria* and Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

290 VET Around the World. Comparing Vocational Education and Training Systems and Outcomes Globally

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Judith OFFERHAUS, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*

Chair: Asha GUPTA, *Directorate of Hindi Medium Implementation, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

290.1 Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany* and Judith OFFERHAUS, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*
Institutions, Interests and Barriers: Collective Skill Formation and Continuing Vocational Education and Training

290.2 Shin ARITA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
What Are the Social Conditions for the Successful VET in Japan?

290.3 Kai-heng LIN, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Bringing Firm Back in the Developmental Skill Formation Model: The Case of Taiwan (1966-1983)

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC09 *Social Transformations and Sociology of Development* RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy* RC20 *Comparative Sociology* RC56 *Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice*

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

17:30-19:20

291 Current Research in Comparative Sociology

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Chair: David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

291.1 Rinko ARAI, *Graduate School of Human Sciences, Osaka University, Japan*
The Internalisation of State Ideologies By Minorities: A Comparison of the National Language Education in China and Japan

291.2 Junmin WANG, *University of Memphis, USA*
Comparative Advantage, Industrial Policy, or Developmental State? Developing a Socio-Political Account for China's Technological Statism

291.3 Olga LI, *Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
Challenging Authoritarian Regimes: Political Grievance and the Perceived Consequences of Political Action

291.4 Eurne BARTOLOME PERAL, *University of Deusto, Spain*; Raúl TORMOS, *CEO-Gencat, Spain* and Maksim RUDNEV, *Independent Researcher, Turkey*
Patterns of Change in the Justifiability of Euthanasia across OECD Countries

291.5 Durgesh SOLANKI, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*
Plaguing the Empire: Repertoires of Colonial Governance

291.6 Jacob THOMAS, *UCLA, USA*
Bureaucratic and Organizational Amenability to the Racial Diversification of Immigrants: The Intersectional Subversion of White-Only Immigration Policies By the Point System

19:30-20:50

292 Comparative Sociology: Research and Methods

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Chair: David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

292.1 Elena STOYKOVA, *Assistant Professor, Bulgaria*
Sociology Around the World: Mapping and Content Analysis of Bachelor's Programs

292.2 Julianna Paola RAMIREZ LOZANO, *CENTRUM Catholic Graduate Business School. Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú.*, Peru and Marta ORTEGA-GASPAR, *Universidad de Málaga, Spain*
Centennials Consumption Culture. a Comparative Analysis of Peru and Spain.

292.3 Naoki ISO, *Tokyo University of the Arts, Japan*
Culture, Class, Distinction in Japan

292.4 Bakhrom MIRKASIMOV, *Westminster International University in Tashkent, Uzbekistan*; Rustamjon URINBOEV, *University of Lund, Sweden* and Nozima TOKHIROVA YUSUPOVA, *Westminster International University in Tashkent, Uzbekistan*
Sociology Literature in Central Asia: Meta Review for 1991-2021

292.5 Kunio MINATO, *Kochi University, Japan*
Pattern of Exclusionist Attitude Toward People with Different Culture in East Asia: With Special Attention to Mongolia

292.6 Cristina GOMES, *FLACSO Mexico, Mexico*
Racism in Sweden and Latin America - Subtle or Explicit, It Hurts

Tuesday 27 June

15:30-17:20

293 Values in Transition and Development: New Findings from the World Values Survey

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Kseniya KIZILOVA, *Institute for Comparative Survey Research, Austria*; Christian HAERPFER, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Marita CARBALLO, *voicesconsul-tancy, Argentina*

Chair: Xiaoxu YANG, *Louisiana State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

293.1 David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*
Education and Opinions on Economic Issues

293.2 Christian HAERPFER, *United Arab Emirates University, Austria* and Kseniya KIZILOVA, *Institute for Comparative Survey Research, Austria*
Support for Democracy in USA, Canada and UK

293.3 Kunio MINATO, *Kochi University, Japan*
Mongolian Attitude Toward People with Different Culture: A Discussion from Analyses of the World Values Survey Data

293.4 Pilar RODRIGUEZ MARTINEZ, *University of Almeria, Spain* and Ana Maria LOPEZ NARBONA, *University of Malaga, Spain*
Intersectionality on the Perception of Health

293.5 Hye Won KWON, *University of Turku, Finland* and Rengin FIRAT, *Korn Ferry Institute, USA*
Cultural Nuances of Agency-Well-Being Relationship: Testing Person-Culture Match and Cultural Heterogeneity Hypotheses with World Values Survey

293.6 Aminath RIYAZ, *The Maldives National University, Maldives*; Sheena MOOSA, *The Maldives National University, Maldives*; Aishath Zeen NAEEM, *The Maldives National University, Maldives*; Aishath HASSAN, *The Maldives National University, Maldives* and Maurifa HASSAN, *The Maldives National University, Maldives*
Determinants of Happiness and Life Satisfaction in the Maldives: Findings from the World Values Survey Wave 7

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

294 The Comparative Political Sociology of Public Opinion, Policy and Social Inequality

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany*

Chair: Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

294.1 Anthony ROBERTS, *Colorado State University, USA*; Emilia RAVETTA, *Colorado State University, USA* and Alex HAGAN, *Colorado State University, USA*
Occupational Polarization, Threat Perception, and Mass Preferences for Restrictive Immigration Policy: A Conditional Process Model

294.2 Naoki AKAEDA, *Kansai University, Japan* and Ken'ichi IKEDA, *Doshisha University, Japan*
The Welfare State and Freedom of Choice: An International Comparative Analysis

294.3 Hsin-hsin PAN, *Department of Sociology, Soochow University, Taiwan*
Rally Around Populist Leader Under the Shadow of War

10:30-12:20

295 Comparative Sociology: Theory and Methods

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: David L. WEAKLIEM, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Chair: Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

295.1 Takeshi HAMANO, *University of Kitakyushu, Japan*
Bridging National Surveys Under COVID-19 Era: Re-Inventing a New Agenda on Comparative Family Research in International Sociology

295.3 Zoltan LAKATOS, *Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary*
The Dead-End of Construct Variance and How to Work Around It with Geometric Data Analysis

295.4 Serge PAUGAM, *Centre Maurice Halbwachs (EHESS/ENS/CNRS/PSL), Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France*; Tugce BEYCAN, *Centre Maurice Halbwachs (ENS/EHESS/CNRS/PSL), Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France* and Marcelo MINO, *Centre Maurice Halbwachs (ENS/EHESS/CNRS/PSL), Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France*
Social Bonds and Diversity Index in the United-States: The Relevance of the Durkheimian Theoretical Approach of Social Attachment

17:30-19:20

296 RC20 Business Meeting

Location: M3 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

297 Values, Social Structures and Social Interactions: The Consequences and Challenges of the Pandemic

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Marita CARBALLO, *Voices Research and Consultancy, Argentina*

Chair: Ionel SAVA, *University of Bucharest, Romania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

297.1 Yiwen WU, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*
COVID Prevention As a Chinese Morality: How Chinese International Students Formed Social Resilience amid the COVID-19 Pandemic

297.2 Lekha N. B., *Sree Narayana College, Chempazhanthy, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India, India* and Antony PALACKAL, *University of Kerala, India*
Disconnection and Distress in the Age of Pandemic: A Comparative Study Among Students in Higher Education

297.4 Hilal ARSLAN, *Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, Turkey*; Alanur CAVLIN BOZBEYOGLU, *Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, Turkey* and Emetullah Mümine BARKCIN, *Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, Turkey*
Patterns and Determinants of Happiness Inequality in Turkey: As an Alternative Way to Understand Social Inequalities

297.5 Anna ANDREENKOVA, *Institute for comparative social research CESSI, Russian Federation*
Belief in the Just World in European Cultures – Comparative Analysis

15:30-17:20

298 Trust and Social Capital in Cross-Cultural Perspective: Examining the Key Indicators and Newest Trends

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Kseniya KIZILOVA, *Institute for Comparative Survey Research, Austria* and Christian HAERPFER, *University of Vienna, Austria*

Chair: Ionel SAVA, *University of Bucharest, Romania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

298.1 Tetiana KOSTIUCHENKO, *Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine*
Measuring Social Capital: Applying Resource Generator in Studying Networks Mobilizing Potential

298.2 Nuseybe AGIRMAN, *Kırklareli University, Turkey*
The Impact of Generalized Trust and Institutional Trust on Formal Volunteering and Charitable Giving in Turkey

298.3 Andrew DAWSON, *York University, Canada* and Isabel KRAKOFF, *York University, Canada*
Does Political Distrust Threaten Democratic Stability? a Cross-National Empirical Investigation of Trust in Partisan and Non-Partisan Institutions

298.4 Kseniya KIZILOVA, *Institute for Comparative Survey Research, Austria* and Christian HAERPFER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Support for Democracy and Understanding of Democracy in Post-Soviet Eurasia

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

299 Comparative Analysis of Transnational Migration Communities and the Formation of New Urban Ethnicity in the Global Cities in the Age of Artificial Intelligence and Online Culture

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Tetsuo MIZUKAMI, *Rikkyo University, 3-34-1, Japan* and Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, Japan*

Co-chairs: Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, USA* and Tetsuo MIZUKAMI, *Rikkyo University, 3-34-1, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

299.1 Makiko OTA, *Rikkyo University, Japan*
Return Migrants, It-Bpo Industry, and Virtual Home-Based Workers in the Philippines during the COVID-19 Pandemic

299.2 Mitsuko ONO, *Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia, Mahidol University, Thailand*
International Retirement Migration in Thailand and Malaysia

299.3 Helena HOF, *University of Zurich / Max Planck Institute for the Study of Religious and Ethnic Diversity, Switzerland*
Foreign Entrepreneurs' 'Urban Transnationalism': Rooted in the Urban Space, Growing Businesses in the Digital Space

299.4 Loikdzhon MIROV, *Technological University of Tajikistan, Tajikistan*
Neet-Youth and Effect of Migration on Returned Migrants in Tajikistan before and after COVID19

10:30-12:20

JS-124 Indigenous Sociology, Indigenous Lifeworlds

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC20 Comparative Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-124.

15:30-17:20

300 Happiness, Well-Being and Life Quality in Comparative Perspective

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Kseniya KIZILOVA, *Institute for Comparative Survey Research, Austria* and Marita CARBALLO, *voices-consultancy, Argentina*

Chair: Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

300.1 Georg MUELLER, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*
Comparing Countries with Regard to Their Resilience Against Unhappiness

300.3 Mads LARSEN, *University of Oslo, Norway* and Nina WITOSZEK, *University of Oslo, Norway*
An Evolutionary Model for Prosocial Well-Being

300.4 Asha GUPTA, *Directorate of Hindi Medium Implementation, India*
Happiness: Economics, Religiosity and Politics

17:30-19:20

301 Comparative Sociology of Public Opinion

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christian HAERPFER, *World Values Survey Association, Austria*

Chair: Aminath RIYAZ, *The Maldives National University, Maldives*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

301.1 Nitzan RIMON-ZARFATY, *Sapir Academic College, Israel* and Silke SCHICKTANZ, *Department of Medical Ethics and History of Medicine, University Medical Center Göttingen (UMG), Germany*

Frozen in Time – a Comparative Analysis of Emerging Temporalities Among Social Egg Freezing Users in Germany and Israel

301.2 Ionel SAVA, *University of Bucharest, Romania*
Networks As (new) Structure Method in Social Mobility Studies. Comparative Methodology in Studying Social Embeddedness across European Landscape during the COVID-19 Pandemic

301.3 Akio INUI, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*; Christian IMDORF, *Leibniz University Hannover, Institute of Sociology, Germany*; Birgit REISSIG, *German Youth Institute, Germany*; Jan SKROBANEK, *University of Bergen, Norway*; Maki HIRATSUKA, *Hosei University, Japan*; Takeshi HORI, *Joetsu University of Education, Japan* and Yoshie MIURA, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*
Youth Transition and Social Security: A Comparative Study of Japan, Germany, Norway, Switzerland, and the UK

301.4 Deisy DEL REAL, *University of Southern California, USA*
Inside the Liberal Paradoxes: How State Actors Outside the Limelight Deploy Multiple (Contradictory) Frames to Pass Inclusive Immigration Policies

301.5 Robbe GEERTS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*; Frederic VANDERMOERE, *University of Antwerp, Belgium* and Stijn OOSTERLYNCK, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
The Pitfalls of Inequality. a Comparative Analysis of Green Purchasing Behavior in European Countries

Saturday 1 July

14:30-16:20

JS-150 Female Employment, Gender Equality and Women Empowerment across the Globe

Committees: RC32 Women, Gender and Society (Host); RC20 Comparative Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-150.

RC21

Regional and Urban Development

Program Coordinators: Sonia ROITMAN, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Miguel Angel MARTINEZ LOPEZ, *University of Uppsala, Sweden*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

302 Leisure in the City. Part I

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jan RATH, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Danielle CHEVALIER, *University of Leiden, Netherlands*

Chairs: Jan RATH, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Danielle CHEVALIER, *Leiden Law School, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

302.1 Franz BUHR, *University of Lisbon, Portugal* and Agustin COCOLA-GANT, *University of Lisbon, Portugal*
Beyond Leisure: Specialty Coffee Shops As Coworking Sites in Lisbon

302.2 Meng XU, *Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Guelph, Canada*
Beyond 'the Magic of the Mall': The Mall As Social Infrastructure in China

302.3 Samuel HOLLERAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Leisure, Memorialisation, and the Cemetery-Park Overlap in Australian Cities

302.4 Shu-Wei HUANG, *D-School, National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
Beerscape in Taipei: From Commercial to Craft

17:30-19:20

303 Leisure in the City. Part II

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jan RATH, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Danielle CHEVALIER, *University of Leiden, Netherlands*

Chairs: Jan RATH, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Danielle CHEVALIER, *Leiden Law School, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

303.1 Janek BECKER, *TU Dortmund University, Germany*
Leisure on the Margin - Reflections on the Spatial Analysis of Leisure Practices in Marginalized Neighbourhoods

303.2 Linjie ZHANG, *University of Warwick, United Kingdom*
The Weak Public Cultural Space: Power and Interaction in Bookstores

303.3 Amanda WISE, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Selvaraj VELAYUTHAM, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Kristine AQUINO, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Swagger, Urban Leisure & the Non-Citizen Precariat: Singapore's Migrant Domestic Worker Volleyball Scene

303.4 Manu MAHAJAN, *SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE, NEW DELHI, India*
Leisure As a New Urban Commodity - CASES from Delhi, India

303.5 Ge ZHU, *Renmin University of China, China*
The Production of Authenticity in Leisure Spaces: Infrastructuralized Heritage, Internet Celebrity and State-Led Redevelopment

19:30-20:50

304 RC21 Business Meeting

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

305 Civil Society, Public Institutions and Governance

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Asato SAITO, *Yokohama National University, Japan*

Chair: Asato SAITO, *Yokohama National University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

305.1 Murat SENTURK, *Istanbul University Department of Sociology, Turkey*
Creating Inclusive and Resilient Communities in the City By Volunteering

305.2 Atsuhiko AOKI, *The university of Tokyo, Japan* and Toshio TAGUCHI, *Akira Tamura Memorial - A Town Planning Research Initiative NPO, Japan*
How Did They Live in the Period of the Innovative Local Government?: Life Histories of Young Workers in Administrative Reforms of Local Government in the 1960s and 1970s in Japan.

305.3 Norihiro NIHEI, *The University of Tokyo, Japan* and Masao MARUYAMA, *The University of Shiga Prefecture, Japan*
The Transformation of Civil Society Organizations in the Tokyo Metropolitan Area from 2006 to 2019

305.4 Ijlal NAQVI, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Schools of Citizenship

305.5 Aditya MOHANTY, *Central University of South Bihar, India*
Notes on the Coming of a Topological Citizenship Among the Valmiki in Delhi

10:30-12:20

JS-35 The Collaboration and Solidarity of Local and Ethnic Residents in Global Cities

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-35.

15:30-17:20

306 Workspace Conflicts, Urban Lives and Livelihoods: Emerging Politics, Planning and Practice across the Global North and South. Part I**Location:** 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Myfanwy TAYLOR, *University College London, United Kingdom*; Carl GRODACH, *Monash University, Australia* and Sara GONZALEZ, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom***Chair:** Jessica FERM, *University College London, United Kingdom***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****306.1** Leon Felipe TELLEZ CONTRERAS, *University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom* and Felipe RANGEL, *University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*
Contesting Low-Cost Workspace Landscapes: Experiences from Sao Paulo and Mexico City**306.2** Elena BESUSSI, *The Bartlett School of Planning, UCL, United Kingdom*
"We Just Want to Stay Here": The Struggle of Camley Street for a Place to Work**306.3** Hanbyul SHIM, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Hack the Place, Hack the Policy, Hack the Modern: Manufacturers' Struggle for Inner-City Occupation**306.4** Fathima RAYAMMARAKKAR FASAL, *PhD Scholar, India*
Ethno-Religious Migrant Communities and Their Role in Co-Production of Urban Spaces: A Study of Migrant Businesses and Local Marketplaces in Bangalore

17:30-19:20

307 Workspace Conflicts, Urban Lives and Livelihoods: Emerging Politics, Planning and Practice across the Global North and South. Part II**Location:** 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Myfanwy TAYLOR, *University College London, United Kingdom*; Carl GRODACH, *Monash University, Australia* and Sara GONZALEZ, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom***Chair:** Jessica FERM, *University College London, United Kingdom***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****307.1** Muhammet Esat TIRYAKI, *Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany*
Conflicts in Marketplaces: A Comparative Study at the Maybachufer Market, Berlin and the Fatih Çarşamba Market, Istanbul**307.2** Ha THAI, *RMIT University, Australia*; Lu YAN, *RMIT University, Australia* and Brent GREENE, *RMIT University, Australia*
Post-Industrial Waterfronts As Inclusive Live/Work/Visit Places**307.3** Nidhi SOHANE, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India* and Rasha LALA, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*
Navigating the Work-Home Boundary: Socio-Spatial Reading of Home As Workspace

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

308 Climate urbanism and the subaltern**Location:** 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Peter WALTERS, *The University of Queensland, Australia***Chair:** Sonia ROITMAN, *The University of Queensland, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****308.1** Ritwika BASU, *Durham University, United Kingdom*
Fetishization of Infrastructure in Urban Climate Resilience and Geographies of Subaltern Mobilities**308.2** Shanel KHALIQ, *Syracuse University, USA*
Urban Design and Climate Change: The Case of Islamabad's BRT**308.3** Augustin BAUCHOT, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Derailing Adaptation? a Pacific Islands Perspective on Urban Climate Change Adaptation and Subaltern Politics.**308.4** Sangay TAMANG, *INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY (Indian School of Mines) Dhanbad, India*
"out of Sight, out of Mind" the Politics of Waste in Darjeeling Himalayas, India

10:30-12:20

JS-63 Housing and School Choices in the Unequal City: Uneasy Trade-Offs, New Combinations and Socio-Spatial Consequences**Committees:** RC21 *Regional and Urban Development (Host)*; RC04 *Sociology of Education*

See Joint Session Details for JS-63.

15:30-17:20

309 Trying to Connect: Examining Social and Infrastructural Inequalities. Part I**Location:** 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Christian ROSEN, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*; Pearl PUWURAYIRE, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany* and Nina GRIBAT, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany***Chair:** Christian ROSEN, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****309.1** Vrashali KHANDELWAL, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*; Ananya PEDDIBHOTLA, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*; Herry GULABANI, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India* and Sudeshna MITRA, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*
Repair As Infrastructure: Case of Bengaluru, India**309.2** Sara ALIDOUST, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
House-Sitting and Opportunities for an Infrastructure of Care in Unequal Cities**309.3** Rodrigo AGUEDA, *State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Beyond the Joá: Infrastructure Building Future(s) in Rio De Janeiro

309.4 Shanel KHALIQ, *Syracuse University, USA*
Big Infrastructure and Development: Mass Transit in Islamabad

17:30-19:20

310 Trying to Connect: Examining Social and Infrastructural Inequalities. Part II

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Christian ROSEN, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*; Pearl PUWURAYIRE, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany* and Nina GRIBAT, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*

Chair: Christian ROSEN, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

310.1 Wahyu ASTUTI, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Assembling Water Flow: Infrastructures and Speculation in Jakarta Metropolitan Area

310.2 Sudeshna MITRA, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*; Vrashali KHANDELWAL, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India* and Herry GULABANI, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*
Unpacking Adoption and Adaptation in Infrastructure Assemblages: Case of Bengaluru, India

310.3 Meric KIRMIZI, *Sociology, Ondokuz Mayıs University, Turkey*
The Role of Japanese Neighbourhood Associations As Social Infrastructure

310.4 Rajendra BHISE, *YUVA, India* and Marina JOSEPH, *Youth for Unity and Voluntary Action (YUVA), India*
Planning for Inclusion: Reflections on Grassroot Interventions in Urban Planning to Reduce Social and Infrastructure Inequalities in Indian Cities

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-86 New Urban Mobilizations and Solidarities - Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC21 *Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-86.

311 Governing Urban Marginality in the Post-Covid City. Part I

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Daniel KUDLA, *Memorial University, Canada*; Andrew CLARKE, *UNSW Sydney, Australia* and Lutfun Nahar LATA, *The University of Melbourne,, Australia*

Chairs: Daniel KUDLA, *Memorial University, Canada*; Andrew CLARKE, *The University of New South Wales, Australia* and Lutfun Nahar LATA, *The University of Melbourne,, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

311.1 Jamie PECK, *Univ. of British Columbia, Canada* and Nik THEODORE, *University of Illinois Chicago, USA*
Cities for a Guaranteed Income: The New Urban Politics of Antipoverty Policy in the United States

311.2 Christopher HERRING, *UCLA, USA*
"Prescribing Housing to Treat COVID-19: Towards a Sociology of Housing in the Time of Pandemic"

311.3 Anup TRIPATHI, *Flame University, India*
Urban Marginality in the Post-Covid World: Re-Imagining Universal Housing As Infrastructures of Care

311.4 Mai YOSHIDA, *The University of Kitakyushu, Japan*
Pandemic Shock on Manila's Street Vendors: Focusing on Labor Informalization and Stratification

311.5 Sara FERLANDER, *Sodertorn University, Sweden*
Social Sustainability in Marginalised Suburban Areas

10:30-12:20

312 Governing Urban Marginality in the Post-Covid City. Part II

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Daniel KUDLA, *Memorial University, Canada*; Andrew CLARKE, *The University of New South Wales, Australia* and Lutfun Nahar LATA, *The University of Melbourne,, Australia*

Chairs: Daniel KUDLA, *Memorial University, Canada*; Andrew CLARKE, *The University of New South Wales, Australia* and Lutfun Nahar LATA, *The University of Melbourne,, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

312.1 Avanka FERNANDO, *University of Colombo, Sri Lanka*
Elevated Marginality: An Ethnographic Study of Everyday Life in a Tower Block in Colombo

312.2 Aileen Grace ANDAL, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Of Play, Poverty, and Pandemic: Insights from Slum-Dwelling Children during the COVID-19 Pandemic and Its Early Aftermath in the Philippines

312.3 Melek KIRTIL, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
The Impact of Social and Spatial Inequalities on Juvenile Delinquency

15:30-17:20

313 Emotions and Social Experiences in the Cities Today. Part I

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ana CERVIO, *CONICET- Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*; Fabio LA ROCCA, *Université Paul Valéry Montpellier 3, France* and Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina*

Chair: Talja BLOKLAND, *Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

313.1 Paolo CONTINI, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy* and Letizia CARRERA, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy*
Between Fear and Resentment. Flâner between Urban Emotions for a Political Walk.

313.2 Judith SCHNELZER, *Institute for Urban and Regional Research, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria*
Navigating Subtle and Mundane Residential Displacements - Unravelling How Intense Emotions Are Shaping (Im) Material Practices and Urban Experiences of the Viennese Middle Class

313.3 Anette STENSLUND, *Southern University Denmark, Denmark*
Atmospheres at the Heart of the Urban Design Processes

313.4 Mehmet ali AKYURT, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
"Felt Population": A Qualitative Study on the Subjective Perception of Population Density in Istanbul

17:30-19:20

JS-110 Spatial Scales and the Analysis of Biographies and Family (Hi)Stories

Committees: RC38 *Biography and Society (Host)*; RC21 *Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-110.

314 Emotions and Social Experiences in the Cities Today. Part II

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ana CERVIO, *CONICET- Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina* and Fabio LA ROCCA, *Université Paul Valéry Montpellier 3, France*

Chair: Stijn OOSTERLYNCK, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

314.1 Maria PATRICIO-MULERO, *Universite Toulouse Capitole, France*
Dancing in the Street As Feminist Empowerment. the Choreographic Discourse of Bellywarda and L'Armée Des Roses

314.2 Alexander KRAHMER, *Fachhochschule Erfurt, Germany*
Urban Experience and Emotions. the Role of Social Conflicts

314.3 Javier ROMANO, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*
Cuerpos y Fronteras: El Derecho a La Ciudad En Situación De Movilidad

314.4 Huishu DENG, *Heritage, Culture and City Research Group, College of Humanities, EPFL, China* and Florence GRAEZER BIDEAU, *Heritage, Culture and City Research Group, College of Humanities, EPFL, Switzerland*
The Leisure Activities in Community "Vacant" Lots: How the Grassroots Practices Appropriate the Public Space in China

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

315 Knowledge and Power Contestation in Transforming Urban Spaces in India

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Pritpal RANDHAWA, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India* and Rachna MEHRA, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India*

Chair: Liza WEINSTEIN, *Northeastern University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

315.1 Ruchika LALL, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*; Rashee MEHRA, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India* and Malavika NARAYAN, *Cornel University, USA*
Co-Producing Knowledge in Action: Reflecting from the Main Bhi Dilli Campaign for Equitable Planning in Delhi

315.2 Vidya PANCHOLI, *University of the West of Scotland/Compound13 Lab, India*; Graham JEFFERY, *University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom* and Ben PARRY, *Bath Spa University, United Kingdom*
Rethinking Disposability: Reimagining Urban Transformations Via an 'Urban Lab'

315.3 Dhiren SWAIN, *Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, India*
Politics of Committees: Bureaucratic Authority and Democratic Negotiation in "Jaga Mission" Odisha, India

315.4 Rachna MEHRA, *Dr.B.R.Ambedkar University Delhi, India* and Pritpal RANDHAWA, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India*
Insurgent Cities: Urban Social Movements and Mobilization in India

315.5 Sneha ANNAVARAPU, *Assistant Professor of Sociology, Singapore*
Aesthetics of Authority: Smart Policing, Unruly Citizens, and the Politics of Visibility

10:30-12:20

316 Political Contestations Along the Urbanization Continuum

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Liza WEINSTEIN, *Northeastern University, USA* and Xuefei REN, *Michigan State University, USA*

Chair: Liza WEINSTEIN, *Northeastern University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

316.1 Arnisson Andre ORTEGA, *Syracuse University, USA* and Aileen Grace ANDAL, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Post Urban-Rural Frontiers? Examining Diverse Island Urbanisms in the Philippines

316.2 Chetna KUANR, *Northeastern University, USA*
Situating Space in the Rise of Aam Aadmi Party: Tracing the Emergence of Resistance and Political Subjectivity Among Urban 'Slum' Dwellers and Rural Farmers Against Authoritarianism in India

316.3 Shahnaz ZADEGAN, *Payame Noor University(PNU), Iran*
Gentrification and the Secret of Iranian Resilience Against Inflation and Covid-19 Pandemic

316.4 Delario LINDSEY, *Marymount University, USA* and Matt BAKKER, *Marymount University, USA*
And Yet, They Persisted: Urban Inequalities, Community Change and the Resilience of Historically Black Neighborhoods in the US Capital Region.

15:30-17:20

JS-133 Understanding the Entanglements of Urban Disasters

Committees: *RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC43 Housing and Built Environment and RC39 Sociology of Disasters*

See Joint Session Details for JS-133.

17:30-19:20

JS-134 (Re)Turning to Urban (new) Normality

Committees: *RC03 Community Research (Host); RC21 Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-134.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

317 Urban Art between Community and Artwashing

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Margret KUSENBACH, *University of South Florida, USA*

Chair: Margret KUSENBACH, *University of South Florida, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

317.1 Kahoruko YAMAMOTO, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*
Creating Legitimacy to “Regenerate” Urban Inner Areas: How Art Under the Creative City Policy Changes the Local Context

317.2 Petr VASAT, *Georg-Simmel Center for Metropolitan Studies, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany*
Transforming Community through Painting: The Emergence of Macromurals in Latin America

317.3 Peer SMETS, *Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, Netherlands*
Arts As a Way of Connecting People in Low-Income Neighbourhoods in Amsterdam. a Matter of Social and Infrastructural Inequalities?

317.4 Eline BAERT, *K.U. Leuven, Belgium* and Caroline NEWTON, *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*
Navigating Spheres of Conflict. Artist’s Collectives and Temporary Use in Social Housing Redevelopments in the City of Ghent (Belgium).

10:30-12:20

JS-140 Digital Urbanism

Committees: *TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC21 Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-140.

12:30-14:20

318 Contesting Urban Governance. New Forms of Citizenship and the Power of Protest across Institutional Contexts. Part I

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Nanke VERLOO, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Diane DAVIS, *Harvard University, USA*

Chair: Elena VACCHELLI, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*

Discussant: Juan OSORIO, *PRATT INSTITUTE, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

318.1 Amogh ARAKALI, *Indian Institute for Human Settlements, India*
Economies and Environmental Citizenship: Linkages between Economic Growth and Citizen-Led Environmental Activism in Bengaluru, India

318.2 Laura WAINER, *The Bernard & Anne Spitzer School of Architecture The City College of New York, CUNY, USA*
Politics By Design: City Production Meets Democracy Building at a Housing Project in South Africa

318.3 Juan OSORIO, *PRATT INSTITUTE, USA*
Planning Crisis: The Promise of New Political Actors & Forms of Agency in Post-Disaster Mocoa

318.4 Amelia THORPE, *UNSW, Australia*
Bodies on the Line: Performing Post-Automobile Citizenship

318.5 Maria Victoria SANCHEZ BELANDO, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Challenges and Chances of Citizen-Driven Initiatives in Encouraging More Equity Power Relations in Governing the City. Learnings from the Case of Barcelona.

318.6 Wara URWASI, *Northwestern University, United States*
Evict or Invest: Community Distinction and Variations of Urban Informality Governance in Jakarta’s Democratic Setting

14:30-16:20

319 Contesting Urban Governance. New Forms of Citizenship and the Power of Protest across Institutional Contexts. Part II

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Nanke VERLOO, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Diane DAVIS, *Harvard University, USA*

Chair: Asato SAITO, *Yokohama National University, Japan*

Discussant: Juan OSORIO, *PRATT INSTITUTE, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

319.1 Esther HERNANDEZ MEDINA, *Pomona College, United States*
Institutional Catalysts and Citizen Participation: The Case of the Historic Center’s Fiduciary Fund in Mexico City

319.2 Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*
Governance of Metropolis: A Comparative Study of Mexico City and Sao Paulo

319.3 Yuri KAZEPOV, *Department of Sociology, Austria*; Byeongsun AHN, *University of Vienna, Austria*; Michael FRIESENECKER, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Jana BRANDL, *University of Vienna, Austria*

How Context Matters: Challenges of Localizing Participatory Budgeting in Vienna

319.4 Franca ROESCHERT, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom* and Elena VACCHELLI, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*

Participation and Contested Forms of Citizenship in the City of Sanctuary

319.5 Sulfi ar AMIR, *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

Experimenting Collaborative Urbanism in Southeast Asia

319.6 Hossein HAMDIEH, *Rieslingstraße, 19, Germany*
A Religious Urban Festival, Inequality, and Resistance: What Happens When Order Cease to be Implemented in Tehran, Iran

RC22

Sociology of Religion

Program Coordinators: Susan CARLAND, *Monash University, Australia*; Olga ODGERS ORTIZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico*; Michael OKYEREF, *University of Ghana, Ghana*; Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*; Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Cecilia DELGADO-MOLINA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

320 Decolonising Studies of Religions in Oceania: South-South Flows of Diverse Worldviews across the Indian and Pacific Oceans

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Michael OKYEREF, *University of Ghana, Ghana*; Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia* and Enqi WENG, *Deakin University, Australia*

Chair: Olga ODGERS ORTIZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

320.1 Enqi WENG, *Deakin University, Australia* and Rosie SHORTER, *Deakin University, Australia*
Reporting from the (Dis)Locating Coloniality Project on Decolonising Studies of Religion in Australia

320.2 Cullan JOYCE, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Meditation, Ritual, and the Body: Ecstatic and Cathartic Expressions of Country.

320.3 Michael OKYEREF, *University of Ghana, Ghana*; Richard MAFURIRANWA, *Curtin University, Australia* and William ABUR, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Transnational Religious Flows and the Role of Religion in Settlement of the African Community in Australia.

320.4 Enqi WENG, *Deakin University, Australia*; Yin PARADIES, *Deakin University, Australia*; William ABUR, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Monika WINARNITA, *Deakin University, Australia* and Rosie SHORTER, *Deakin University, Australia*
Decolonising the Study of Religion in Australia

15:30-17:20

321 The Experiences of Secularity in Muslim-Majority Contexts

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Abdie KAZEMIPUR, *University of Calgary, Canada* and Sari HANAFAI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

Chair: Sari HANAFAI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

321.1 Abdie KAZEMIPUR, *University of Calgary, Canada*
Secularization of Islam or Secularization of Muslims? the Case of Post-Revolutionary Iran

321.2 Syed Farid ALATAS, *National Univ of Singapore, Singapore*
Coloniality and Secularity Among Muslims: A Decolonial View of the Modern Human Condition

321.3 Housamedden DARWISH, *Leipzig University, Germany*
(Political) Islam in a (Political) Secular Environment

321.4 Rachid JARMOUNI, *University Moulay Ismail, Morocco*
The Dialectic of Personal Freedoms between Moral Changes and the Intransigence of Political and Religious References: The Status of Moroccan Youth As a Case Study

JS-11 Religious Actors and Social Movements in Contemporary World

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-11.

17:30-19:20

322 Religious Change in Europe

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Milda ALISAUSKIENE, *Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania* and Olga BRESKAYA, *University of Padova, Italy*

Chair: Rosie SHORTER, *Deakin University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

322.1 Titus HJELM, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
The Secular Religion of Political Discourse in Finland

322.2 Milda ALISAUSKIENE, *Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania*
The Perception of Gender Equality Among Women of Faith in the Baltic States: Driving Tractors or Sharing the Childcare and Housework?

322.3 Andrew LYNCH, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Religion, Art, and the Crisis of Grand Narratives: Post-Secular Challenges and European Contexts

322.4 Felicien FAURY, *Paris Dauphine University, France*
Catholic Culture and National Identity Among Radical Right Voters in France

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

323 Measuring Religiosity in East Asia

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Koki SHIMIZU, *Hokkaido University, Japan* and Yoshihide SAKURAI, *Hokkaido University, Japan*

Chair: Titus HJELM, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

323.1 Jonathan EVANS, *Pew Research Center, USA*; Kelsey Jo STARR, *Pew Research Center, USA* and Manolo CORICHI, *Pew Research Center, USA*
Relationships between Traditional and New Measures of Religious Belief and Practice in East Asia

323.2 Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*; Yunping TONG, *Pew Research Center, USA* and Marcin STONAWSKI, *Center for Advanced Studies of Population and Religion (CASPAR) at Cracow University of Economics, Poland*
Why Pew Research Center Is Changing Our Approach to Measuring Religion in China and the Big Impact This Will Have on Our Description of the Global Religious Landscape

323.3 Joel TEJEDO, *Asia Pacific Research Center, Philippines*
Public Measures, Risks, and Changes of Life during Covid-19 Pandemic: A Quantitative Analysis

323.4 Gholamreza KHOSH FAR, *Golestan University, Iran*; Korosh GHOLAMI KUTENAE, *Golestan University, Iran*; Nahid SADEGHI RASHTI, *Humanities and Social Sciences Faculty, Golestan University, Iran* and Sima ZAREEI, *Tejarat Bank, Gorgan, central Branch., Iran*
Examining the Relationship between Religiosity and Social Hope with an Emphasis on the Role of Religion in Iran (Case study: Citizens of Gorgan and Aqqa)

JS-28 Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Public Sphere

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC22 Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-28.

10:30-12:20

JS-34 Religious Actors and Social movements: Gender and Sexual Diversity

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC22 Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-34.

15:30-17:20

JS-43 Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Ecological Turn

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC22 Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-43.

17:30-19:20

324 RC22 Presidential Session I Henrietta Nyamnjoh "Stoking the Flames of Faith: The Challenge of Keeping Religiosity Activated in COVID and Post-COVID Times"

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*

Chair: Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*

Panelist: Henrietta NYAMNJOH, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*

19:30-20:50

325 RC22 Business Meeting

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

326 Religious Change in Latin America

Language: English, Spanish

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Olga ODGERS ORTIZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico* and Renee DE LA TORRE, *CIESAS Occidente, Mexico*

Chair: Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Panelists: Hugo RABBIA, *Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, Argentina* and Cristina GUTIERREZ ZUNIGA, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

326.1 Renee DE LA TORRE, *CIESAS Occidente, Mexico* and Alejandro FRIGERIO, *CONICET, Argentina*
Lo Que Se Ve No Se Pregunta: Regímenes De Pluralidad Religiosa En Argentina y En México

326.2 Luis BAHAMONDES, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*; Cristina GUTIERREZ ZUNIGA, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico* and Hugo RABBIA, *Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, Argentina*
De Las Identificaciones Nominales a Los Creyentes Adversativos: En Torno a Las Reconstrucciones Del "Ser Religioso" y "No Religioso" En Argentina, Chile y México

326.3 Olga ODGERS ORTIZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico*; Hugo Jose SUAREZ, *Ciudad Universitaria, Mexico* and Felipe ORELLANA, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile*
Creyentes En Movimiento: Reconfiguración De Las Religiosidades En Contextos De Movilidad

326.4 Olga OLIVAS HERNANDEZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte A.C., Mexico* and Rodrigo TONIOL, *UFRJ, Brazil*
Salud y Religión. Un Campo De Estudio En Perspectiva Latinoamericana

10:30-12:20

327 Exploring changes in religiosity: new patterns and trends

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*

Chair: Paul BRAMADAT, *University of Victoria, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

327.1 Elisabeth SIROIS, *Université d'Ottawa, Canada*
Between Cultural Religion and Laïcité in Québec: Relationship to Religion and Social Representations of Catholicism of Young Québécois Aged 20 to 30

327.2 Timothy CLYDESDALE, *The College of New Jersey, USA*
Exploring the Surprising Impact of Spirituality over Religiosity in Life Statuses of US Twentysomethings

327.3 Roberto CIPRIANI, *Università Roma Tre, Italy*
Religiosity in Italy. a Multi-Methods Approach.

327.4 Megha DHADOTI, *NMKRv College for Women, India*
Resurgence of Religion: A New Avatara in the Post-Pandemic World

327.5 Changhoon SEOG, *Sunmoon University, Republic of Korea*
A Review Study on the Measurement of Religiosity in Korea

JS-62 Demographic Change, Economic Outcomes and Religious Belief

Committees: *RC41 Sociology of Population (Host); RC22 Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-62.

15:30-17:20

328 Religion in Oceania

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Rosie SHORTER, *Deakin University, Australia*

Chair: Susan CARLAND, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

328.1 Adam POSSAMAI, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Nothing to Declare...Apart from Holy Water: Material Religion and Border Control in Fiji

328.2 Stephen REID, *Christian Research Association, Australia*
Understanding the Catholic Community in Australia: History, Methods, and Applications

328.3 Mark JENNINGS, *University of Divinity, Australia*
"My Whole Life Was the Two Suburbs That Surrounded the Church:" LGBTQ+ Experiences of Australian Pentecostal-Charismatic Churches As "Greedy Institutions"

328.4 Mehrnosh LAJEVARDI FATEMI, *Dr., Australia*
Imams' Role in Muslim Communities in Sydney

328.5 Benjamin LEWIS, *Monash University, Australia*
Endogamy As an Anchor: Exploring Australian Jews' Attitudes Towards and Experiences of Inter-Cultural Partnering

328.6 Gisele ISHIMWE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Settlement Experiences and Pentecostalism Among Black African Young Adults in Australia

17:30-19:20

329 Religious Change in the Middle East and North Africa

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Hossein GODAZGAR, *University of Warwick, United Kingdom*

Chair: Rafael CAZARIN DE BRITO, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

329.1 Esen KIRDIS, *Rhodes College, USA*
Religion & Youth in the Middle East

329.2 Jose SANCHEZ GARCIA, *Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain*
Tawab (repenting) and Muslaha (reconciliation): Mediation Processes Among Youth Streets Groups in Magrib

329.3 Ece ESMEYER, *Kadir Has University, Turkey*
Plying between the Secular and the Pious Communities: An Ethnographic Case Study on Muslim Young Women in Turkey

329.4 Saeid YARMOHAMMADI, *University of Montreal, Canada*
Conceptualizations of Social Justice in Iran, between Religion and Politics

329.5 Ruth KARK, *Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel* and Shay WINEAPPLE, *Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel*
The Relationship between the Christian Mission and Israel As a Modern Jewish Nation State: Israel's Response in Light of Christian Missionary Activity, 1948-2008

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

329.6 Afsaneh TAVASSOLI, *Alzahra University, Iran*
Affinity and Inconsistency between Islam and Feminism in Contemporary Iran

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

330 Keynote Session: Tom Smith "Spirituality and Religion: Trends and Cross-National Comparisons"

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*

Chair: Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*

Panelist: Tom W SMITH, *University of Chicago, USA*

Discussants: Mark CHAVES, *Duke University, USA* and Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

330.1 Tom W SMITH, *University of Chicago, USA*
Spirituality and Religion: Trends and Cross-National Comparisons

10:30-12:20

JS-94 Religion and Science

Committees: *RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology (Host); RC22 Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-94.

15:30-17:20

331 Keynote Speech Session - Jörg Stolz "Is the Secular Transition a Global Phenomenon? New Evidence and Problems"

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Michael OKYEREF, *University of Ghana, Ghana*

Chair: Ryan CRAGUN, *University of Tampa, USA*

Discussants: Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA* and Monika WOHLRAB-SAHR, *Universität Leipzig, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

331.1 Jörg STOLZ, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*
Is the secular transition a global phenomenon? New evidence and problems.

17:30-19:20

332 Nonreligion: Meaning, Practice, and Consequences across the Life Course, Part 1

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jacqui FROST, *Purdue University, USA*

Chair: Jacqui FROST, *Purdue University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

332.1 Timothy CLYDESDALE, *The College of New Jersey, USA*
Exploring Social Context and Life Course in the Journeys of Religiously Unaffiliated US Twentysomings

332.2 Katja STREHLE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
"But then I Came to my Senses": Australian Women's Stories of Becoming Non-Religious.

332.3 Merril SILVERSTEIN, *Syracuse University, USA*
Has Gender Egalitarianism Weakened Religiosity in Baby-Boom Women? a Developmental-Historical Approach

332.4 Jean-philippe PERREAULT, *Université Laval, Canada*; Elisabeth SIROIS, *Université d'Ottawa, Canada* and Marie LENOBLE, *Université Laval, Canada*
The Religious Among Nonreligious Young Quebecers: Age or Generation Effect?

332.5 Ryan CRAGUN, *University of Tampa, USA*; Alexandra RODRIGUEZ, *Howard University, USA*; Jesse SMITH, *Western Michigan University, USA* and David SPEED, *University of New Brunswick, Canada*
Religiosity Is Declining but Giving Is Increasing: Can the Nonreligious Really be Less Generous?

333 Religion Poster Session

Language: English, Spanish

Location: Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Olga OLIVAS HERNANDEZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte A.C., Mexico*

Chair: Michael OKYEREF, *University of Ghana, Ghana*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

333.1 Leonid ISSAEV, *Institute for African Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation* and Alisa SHISHKINA, *HSE University, Russian Federation*
Islamic Education in Russian Regions: A Tool for Youth De(radicalization)?

333.2 Dr. Mouneshwar BADIGER, *SSCA Government First Grade College K. K. Koppa, Belagavi, Karnataka State, India, India*
Implications of Modernity on Spiritual Practices of Indian Youth

333.3 Cullan JOYCE, *University of Divinity, Australia*
'Demons Make War on Those Who Are at the Summit of Prayer': How Early Christian Contemplative Practices Responded to Harmful Experiences.

333.4 Hien NGUYEN, *The University of Western Australia, Australia*
Transnational Religion: Continuity and Adjustment of Religious Beliefs and Rituals Among Vietnamese Migrant Grandparents in Australia

333.5 Ryushun KIYOFUJI, *The University of Kitakyushu, Japan*
Multicultural Coexistence with Buddhist Vietnamese Immigrants in Japan

333.6 Conrad HACKETT, *Pew Research Center, USA*
Pew Research Center's Global Research on Religion (surveys, demographic analysis, religious restrictions): Ask Me Anything!

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

334 Remembering the Contributions of Departed Scholars Including James Beckford, Gary Bouma & Roland Robertson

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*

Chair: Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*

Panelists: Adam POSSAMAI, *University of Western Sydney, Australia*; Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia* and James SPICKARD, *University of Redlands, USA*

10:30-12:20

335 Spirituality, Wellbeing and Risks

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Galen WATTS, *KU Leuven, Belgium*; Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia* and Paul BRAMADAT, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Chair: Galen WATTS, *KU Leuven, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

335.1 Geraldine MOSSIERE, *Université de Montreal, Canada*
'Feels Good or Not Good?' Intersecting Emotions, Energy and Awareness to Reach a Sense of Well-Being. the Case of Core Energetics' Practice.

335.2 Jessica TARGETT, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Jonathan DAVIES, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Alex BURGER, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Julieta GALANTE, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Nicholas VAN DAM, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Unusual Experiences with Secular and Spiritual Meditation in the US: Prevalence, Predictors, Endorsement, and Valence Perceptions

335.3 Sumedha DUTTA, *Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India, India*

Beyond the Sacred - Profane Dichotomy? New Religious Movements and Their Concept of Wellness through Spirituality in South Asia

335.4 Vivian GERRAND, *Deakin University, Australia*
Understanding Processes of Radicalisation within Wellness Communities in an Age of Polarisation.

335.5 Karina VILLALBA, *University of Central Florida, USA*; María-José DEL PINO-ESPEJO, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide UPO, Spain*; Ayme BARREDA, *Universidad Nacional de San Agustín de Arequipa, Peru*; Doris CEVALLOS-ZAMBRANO, *Universidad del Valle, Ecuador* and Gilbert RAMIREZ, *Florida International University, USA*
Connection with God in Times of the Pandemic: Association between Mental Health, Substance Use, and Spirituality Among Young Adults in Peru and Ecuador

335.6 Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Healthy Lifestyles, Healing and Holistic Spirituality in Contemporary Times

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

335.7 Anna HALAFOFF, *Deakin University, Australia*
Spirituality, Wellbeing and Risks

15:30-17:20

336 Religion and Wellbeing in Asia in Times of Crisis

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Kashing NG, *Hokkaido University, Japan* and Yoshihide SAKURAI, *Hokkaido University, Japan*

Chair: Milda ALISAUSKIENE, *Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

336.1 Miki KURIHARA, *Sophia University, Japan*
Verbal Communications in Teaching and Learning Holistic Thoughts: Insights from Practice of Yoga Teachers in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

336.2 Maria Cecilia MEDINA, *University of the Philippines, Philippines*
The Josefa Segovia Foundation Inc. (JSF) and the Wellbeing of Indigenous Communities in Davao City, Philippines

336.3 Rajeev DUBEY, *Banaras Hindu University, India*
COVID-19 Pandemic and the Role of Religious Institutions in India

336.4 Arvind SURAJ, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India*
The Dynamics between Faith, Healing and Hansen's Disease in a Hindu Sect

17:30-19:20

337 Nonreligion: Meaning, Practice, and Consequences across the Life Course, Part 2

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jacqui FROST, *Purdue University, USA*

Chair: Ryan CRAGUN, *University of Tampa, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

337.1 Masoumeh RAHMANI, *Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand*; Peter ADDS, *Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand* and Geoff TROUGHTON, *Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand*
Explaining Māori Atheism in Aotearoa New Zealand

337.2 Jacqui FROST, *Purdue University, USA* and Penny EDGELL, *University of Minnesota, USA*
Wellbeing across the Nonreligious Life Course

337.3 Ignacio CACERES, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Nonreligion and Social Cohesion: Evidence from Latin America

337.4 Julia MARTINEZ-ARINO, *University of Groningen, Netherlands*
"My Life Hasn't Changed Much": Change and Continuity in Catholic Apostates' Lives

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

338 Religion As an Instrument of Rooting for the Liquid Identity of Migrants Part 1

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Susan CARLAND, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Michael OKYEREFU, *University of Ghana, Ghana*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

338.1 Tunde ALABI, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Muslim and Hijab Penalties in the United States and United Kingdom? the Case of Nigerian Immigrants

338.2 Zai LIANG, *State University of New York at Albany, USA* and Bo ZHOU, *Guangzhou University, China*
Africans in China: The Role of Religion in the Process of Social Integration

338.3 Yelena KOPILOV, *The Open University, Australia* and Dana KAPLAN, *The Open University of Israel, Israel*
The Chosen People in the Lucky Country: Immigration Goals As Determinants of Religious Self-Identity Among Israeli Migrants and Expats in Australia

338.4 Paolo BOCCAGNI, *University of Trento, Italy*
Home Is Where the Rug Is Laid Down. Unpacking Religiosity As a Tool of Homemaking in an Asylum Reception Centre

338.5 Yamini krishna C, *FLAME University, India* and Nisha MATHEW, *Mahindra University, India*
Transnational Techno-Religious Networks and Temple Urbanism in Contemporary South India

10:30-12:20

339 Religion and Health. Intersections and (Dis)Agreements in Contemporary Societies.**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** CCH3 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Olga OLIVAS HERNANDEZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte A.C., Mexico* and Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain***Chair:** Olga ODGERS ORTIZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico***Discussant:** Lorena NUNEZ, *University of the Witwatersrand Johannesburg, South Africa***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****339.1** Francis BENYAH, *Abo Akademi University, Finland*
Culture, Religion, and the Limits of Human Rights Legislations for Persons with Mental Health Problems in Ghana**339.2** Olga OLIVAS HERNANDEZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte A.C., Mexico*
Therapeutic Assemblages and Tensions between Health and Religion. Migrant Populations Experiences in Mexico.**339.3** Noli TIRKEY, *Independent Researcher, India*; Swati SOREN, *Central University of Jharkhand, India*; Joy LAKRA, *Independent Researcher, India*; Kanchan Thomasina EKKA, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India*; Smriti SOREN, *Independent Researcher, India* and Pradeep MINJ, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India*
Traditional Ethos and Adivasi/Tribal/Indigenous Religious Practices and Learnings: A Case Study of Sarna Sthals in Jharkhand, Eastern India**339.4** Laetitia STAUFFER, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*
Harmony, Vibration, Karma, Kleshas and Traumas : Yoga and (non-)Spiritual Meaning-Making Regarding Health Condition**339.5** Rafael CAZARIN DE BRITO, *Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain*
"It's like Riding a Roller Coaster". Science, Religion, and Health Among Transgender and Gender Nonconforming People.

12:30-14:20

340 Religious Diversity in Australia**Location:** CCH3 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Douglas EZZY, *University of Tasmania, Australia***Chair:** Susan CARLAND, *Monash University, Australia***Panelists:** Rebecca BANHAM, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Douglas EZZY, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Geraldine SMITH, *University of Tasmania, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****340.1** Douglas EZZY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Attitudes Toward Religious Diversity in Australia**340.2** Rebecca BANHAM, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Geraldine SMITH, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Greg BARTON, *Deakin University, Australia*
Migration and Religious Diversity in Australia**340.3** Geraldine SMITH, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
The Role of Play in the Multifaith Movement in Australia**340.4** Rebecca BANHAM, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Douglas EZZY, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Greg BARTON, *Deakin University, Australia*
Policing in Diverse Australia: Community Engagement and Respect in Tasmania and Victoria

14:30-16:20

JS-152 Religion As an Instrument of Rooting for the Liquid Identity of Migrants Part 2**Committees:** RC22 *Sociology of Religion (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-152.

RC23

Sociology of Science and Technology

Program Coordinators: Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*; Leandro RAIZER, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil* and Alice ABREU, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Monday 26 June

17:30-19:20

341 Quantification and Power: Values, Normative Agendas and Policy Paradigms behind Numbers. Part II

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Marianna ZIELENSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Carlotta MOZZANA, *Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

Chair: Marianna ZIELENSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

341.1 Alexandra VINSON, *University of Michigan, USA*
The Ethics of Quantification: Investigating the Uptake and Use of Situational Judgment Test Scores in Medical School Admissions

341.2 Georgia VAN TOORN, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Disability, Deservingness, and the Quantification of Bodily Difference

341.3 Jaya MATHUR, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Sensations, Subjectivity, and Science : Exploring the Fraught Metrics of Pain

341.4 Rachel AALDERS, *Australian National University, Australia*
Healthy Finances: Making Sense of Dollar Data As a Measure of Wellbeing

341.5 Antoine HARDY, *UMR5116 - CNRS Centre Emile-Durkheim, France*
Numbers and Power Struggle in Academia

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-24 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part IV

Committees: RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology (Host)*; RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture*

See Joint Session Details for JS-24.

10:30-12:20

JS-32 International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Labour-Capital Relations

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-32.

15:30-17:20

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I

Committees: RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC10 *Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management* RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology* and TG10 *Digital Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-39.

17:30-19:20

342 Digital Innovation in the Innovation Society: Sociological Perspectives

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Stefan KIRCHNER, *Technische Universität Berlin, Germany*; Ingo SCHULZ-SCHAEFFER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*; David SEIBT, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany* and Arnold WINDELER, *Technische Universität Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Ingo SCHULZ-SCHAEFFER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

342.1 Trina DAS, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Contribution of Interactions between Start-Ups and Academia in Digital Innovation: An Empirical Study in Technology Development

342.2 Patrik DAHL, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*
Formulating Problems and Solutions: The Case of Hackathon Events and Data-Based Innovation in Digital Societies.

342.3 Gerald AHABWE, *Makerere University, Uganda*
Tinkering with Prepaid Technology for Water: User Perspectives and Lessons from the Slums of Kampala, Uganda.

342.4 Vinay BRANDON, *Delhi School of Economics, University of Delhi, India*
The Crypto Fix: Encoding Monetary Trust in the Digital Age

342.5 Rima ZILINSKAITE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Science and Web 2.0: Prosumption in the Creation and Dissemination of Scientific Knowledge

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

343 Bringing Intersectionality to Science: How Equity Diversity and Inclusion Impacts Scientific Policies and Practices. Part I

Language: English, Spanish, French

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Alice ABREU, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Chair: Alice ABREU, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

343.1 Tsamiyah LEVI, University of Campinas, Brazil and Anamaria FONSECA DE ALMEIDA, University of Campinas, Brazil
The Diffusion of Certifications and Gender Equality Plans in Science: Activism and Institutional Change

343.2 Liisa HUSU, Örebro University, Sweden; Helen PETERSON, Örebro University, Sweden; Helene SCHIFFBAENKER, Joanneum Research, Austria and Angelika SAUER, Joanneum Research, Austria
Research Funding Organisations As Change Agents for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: European Perspectives

343.3 Giuseppe PELLEGRINI, *Observa - Science in Society, Italy* and Chiara PICCOLO, *Observa - Science in Society, Italy*
Deliberative Participation As a Contribution to a Constructive Relationship between Science and Society

343.4 Anna RANSIEK, Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, FU Berlin, Germany and Anina MISCHAU, Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, FU Berlin, Germany
Being a Woman or Being a Mathematician? (Self-)Perceptions of Female Early-Stage Researchers in an Excellent Mathematical Research Environment.

343.5 Denise ORTIZ, University of California, Los Angeles, USA
"Know My Worth": Foundations for Faculty of Color Recruitment, Retention, and Promotion in STEM

10:30-12:20

JS-65 Sociology and the Climate Science-Politics Gap

Committees: RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology (Host); RC24 Environment and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-65.

15:30-17:20

344 Biopolitics, Culture and Digital Control in the Context of Technology Assessment. Part I

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Elena GAVRILINA, Institute of Scientific Information for Social Sciences, Russian Academy of Science (INION), Russian Federation and Aleksandra KAZAKOVA, Gubkin Russian State University of Oil and Gas, Russian Federation

Chair: Elena GAVRILINA, Institute of Scientific Information for Social Sciences, Russian Academy of Science (INION), Russian Federation

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

344.1 Yu-hui KAO, Soochow University, Taiwan
Mediating Effect of Institutional Trust on the Public Attitude Toward State Surveillance.

344.2 Barbara AMBROGIO, University of Calabria, Italy
Industry 4.0 and Unproductive Labour

344.3 Ingo SCHULZ-SCHAEFFER, Technical University of Berlin, Germany
Analyzing Digital Innovations: How Useful Are Script Analysis, Role Analysis, and Affordance Analysis?

344.4 Ana RIVOIR, Universidad de la República, Uruguay
Protecting Personal Data in the Digital Society in Latin America

344.5 Mohammad MOZUMDER, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies, Bangladesh
The Quotidian Use of Mobile Phone: Turning the Ordinary to the Extraordinary

344.6 Sindhe JAGANATH RAMANNA, Gulbarga University, India
Enabling Education through Technology: Edtech Induced Challenges for National Education Policy of India

17:30-19:20

345 Microbial Knowledge in Biopolitical Times

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Sonja VAN WICHELEN, University of Sydney, Australia and Katherine KENNY, University of Sydney, Australia

Chairs: Sonja VAN WICHELEN, University of Sydney, Australia and Katherine KENNY, University of Sydney, Australia

Panelists: Nikolai SIIMES, University of Auckland, New Zealand; Katherine KENNY, University of Sydney, Australia and Natasha ROONEY, Deakin University, Australia

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

345.1 Sonja VAN WICHELEN, University of Sydney, Australia
Governing Fecal Microbiota Transplants: Biovalue and More-Than-Human Legalities

345.2 Nikolai SIIMES, University of Auckland, New Zealand
A Wine Glass Half Full: Consipience and the Microbiopolitics of Natural Ferments in a Post-Pasteurian World.

345.3 Katherine KENNY, University of Sydney, Australia
The Microbiopolitics of (self)Care

345.4 Natasha ROONEY, Deakin University, Australia
Micro and Macrocossms: Ayurveda and the Microbiome

345.5 Milanovic MILANOVIC, Sup'Biotech, France and Cecile VERMOT, Sup'biotech, France
When Viruses Innovate! Agricultural Phagotherapy and Biopolitics in the Microbial Turn

345.6 Sambit MALLICK, Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India
Gene Editing of Livestock: Implications for Science, Technology, Innovation and Development Policies in India

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

346 Bringing Intersectionality to Science: How Equity Diversity and Inclusion Impacts Scientific Policies and Practices. Part II

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Alice ABREU, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Liisa HUSU, *Orebro University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

346.1 Carmen LECCARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*; Ilenya CAMOZZI, *Department of Sociology and social research, University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*; Sveva MAGARAGGIA, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*; Arianna MAINARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy* and Zenia SIMONELLA, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
Including Diversity and Daily-Life Experiences in Science: Some Evidence from the "Allinteract" European Research Project

346.2 Ata HESHMATI, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Women's Bodies Resisting Against the Gendering of Science and Technology after the Islamic Revolution of Iran (1980s)

346.3 Alice ABREU, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Luis Felipe Coimbra COSTA, *Programa de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computação (PESC/COPPE), Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), Brazil*; Yuri LIMA, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Luciana Maria Azevedo NASCIMENTO, *Programa de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computação (PESC/COPPE), Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), Brazil*
Including Women and Girls in Computer Science: What Are the Challenges and What Is Working in Latin America?

10:30-12:20

JS-94 Religion and Science

Committees: RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-94.

15:30-17:20

347 Theoretical Models, Challenges, and Prospects for the Sociological Studies of Artificial Intelligence and Human-Machine Interactions in the Age of Online Culture

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, Japan* and Yu-cheng LIU, *Soochow University, Taiwan*

Chair: Leandro RAIZER, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

347.1 Natalia TREGUBOVA, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*; Anastasia IVANOVA, *St Petersburg State University, Russia* and Andrey REZAEV, *Rikkyo Institute for Global Urban Studies, USA*

Looking at the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence and Human-Machine Interactions through the Lens of Social Analytics: Basic Theoretical and Methodological Approaches

347.2 Roslyn MICKELSON, *UNC Charlotte, USA*; Mary Lou MAHER, *UNC Charlotte, USA*; Amirhossein GHASEMI, *UNC Charlotte, USA*; Dongsong ZHANG, *UNC Charlotte, USA*; Gordon HULL, *UNC Charlotte, USA*; WenWen DOU, *UNC Charlotte, USA* and Minwoo LEE, *UNC Charlotte, USA*

Resisting Resurgent Authoritarianism with Trustworthy and Human-Centric AI

347.3 Yu-cheng LIU, *Soochow University, Taiwan*
The Quantification of Humanity and Its Discontents: Cases from Self-Driving Technologies

347.4 Il-sun CHOI, *Mahidol University, Thailand*
"Inclusive Smart City" and "Human Centered AI"

347.5 Bettina KRINGS, *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany* and Antonio MONIZ, *Universidade Nova de Lisboa, FCT-UNL, CICS.NOVA, Portugal*
Artificial Intelligence on "New" Working Environments in Industry: Challenges and Prospects for Sociology

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

347.6 Lilla VICSEK, *Corvinus University of Budapest, Hungary*
Sociology of AI Expectations: Visions about the Roles of AI in Society

17:30-19:20

348 The Robert K. Merton Award for Distinguished Contribution to the Sociology of Science and Technology

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*

Chair: Alice ABREU, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

19:30-20:50

349 RC23 Business Meeting

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Leandro RAIZER, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil*

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-117 International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Sovereignty and Infrastructural Power

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-117.

10:30-12:20

350 Collaborative Robots: New Socio-Technical Constellations and Dominant Narratives**Location:** M10 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Andreas BISCHOF, *Chemnitz University of Technology, Germany*; Bettina KRINGS, *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*; Martin MEISTER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany* and Ingo SCHULZ-SCHAEFFER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany***Chair:** Bettina KRINGS, *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****350.1** Marcus PERSSON, *Linkoping University, Sweden*; Clara IVERSEN, *Uppsala University, Sweden* and David REDMALM, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Robot Animals and the Emotional Labor of Caregivers**350.2** Atte OKSANEN, *Tampere University, Finland* and Pekka RASANEN, *University of Turku, Finland*
Are They Going to Replace Us? Perceptions of Robots, AI, and Technological Futures Among Europeans**350.3** Ingo SCHULZ-SCHAEFFER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*; Martin MEISTER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*; Kevin WIGGERT, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany* and Tim CLAUSNITZER, *Technical University of Berlin, Germany*
The Impact of Narratives on the Development of Collaborative Robots. a Comparison of Care Robots and Industrial Cobots**350.4** Sara KEBIR, *CRIL - Univ Artois - CNRS, France*; Cecile CARRA, *LEM - CNRS - UMR 9221, France* and Karim TABIA, *CRIL - CNRS - UMR 8188, France*
Acceptance of Smart Home Technologies for Aging in Place

15:30-17:20

351 Quantification and Power: Values, Normative Agendas and Policy Paradigms behind Numbers. Part I**Location:** M10 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Marianna ZIELENSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Carlotta MOZZANA, *Univeristà degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Italy***Chair:** Leandro RAIZER, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****351.1** Hyun JUNG, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Quantification As a Symbolic Capital in Sociological Field**351.2** Marianna ZIELENSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Magdalena WNUK, *Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland* and Malgorzata GAWRONSKA, *Uniwersytet Warszawski, Poland*
Taming the Strange Animal - How the European Parliament and the European Commission Representatives Use the Arope Composite Poverty Index in Their Power Games**351.3** Pauline BOYER, *SAGE, France*
Open Data in Higher Education and Research: The Dangers of Transparency**351.4** Walter BARTL, *Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Population Registers and Census Taking in Germany: More Than a Technical Relationship

17:30-19:20

352 Digital Neoliberalism and Surveillance Capitalism: Technology Induced Monopoly**Location:** M10 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Somashekher CHINNAPPA, *Bangalore University, India***Chair:** Siddharamesh HIREMATH, *Bangalore Central University, India***Co-chairs:** Nagendrappa PATIL, *Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi, India* and Subhaschandra NATIKAR, *Karnataka University, India***Discussant:** Nanjanasiddaiah DODDASIDDIAH, *Karnata State Open University, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****352.1** Jenny DAVIS, *The Australian National University, Australia*
Failing Fast: Start-up Culture and the Silicon Valley Creep**352.2** Anjanappa BADADA HANUMAPPA, *Kuvempu University, India*
Sociology of Science & Technology- Revisualization of Sociological Framework**352.3** Niklas STRUEVER, *University of Siegen, Germany*
Voice Assistants at the Center of the Smart Home: How Alexa Controls the Smart Home**352.4** Vasudha M C, *Jyoti Nivas College Autonomous, India*
Taming the Soft Despotism: The Regulation of Big Tech Industry in India**352.5** Spencer ADAMS, *Berkeley Rhetoric, USA*
Scientific Labor and the Category of Subsumption**Saturday 1 July**

08:30-10:20

353 State Role in the Post-Pandemic Market of Ideas**Location:** M10 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Dennis MCNAMARA, *3700 O St NW, USA***Chair:** Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation***Panelist:** Dennis MCNAMARA, *3700 O St NW, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****353.1** Dennis MCNAMARA, *3700 O St NW, USA*
Japan's Educational Diplomacy – Building Knowledge Nodes in Thai Manufacturing**353.2** Modho GOVIND, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Transfer of Knowledge from University to Industry in Post-Covid Era: A Study of Indian Biological Scientists in National and International Context**353.3** Mei-Ling LIN, *National Open University, Taiwan*
Effects of Covid 19 on Digital Transformation. Evolving Education Technologies in a Post-Pandemic Context**353.4** Santosh KUMAR, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Understanding Objectification of Indians As Subjects through Dividing Practices Including Science and Religion; Democracy and Populism; And the Global North and the Global South

RC24

Environment and Society

Program Coordinator: Debra DAVIDSON, *University of Alberta, Canada*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC24 *Environment and Society* RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements* and RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-3.

354 Confronting the dragons of destruction: Environmental confrontations with capitalism and colonialism.

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Katie MOON, *University of New South Wales, Australia*

Chair: Asrafi AKRAM, *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Bangladesh*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

354.1 Elaine COBURN, *Glendon Campus, York University, Canada*
Climate Change and the International Monetary Fund

354.2 Alba GONZÁLEZ VEGA, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*
Reflexiones De La Contabilidad Ambiental Desde El Desarrollo Sostenible y La Responsabilidad De La Empresa
Reflections of Environmental Accounting from Sustainable Development and Corporate Responsibility

354.3 Katie MOON, *University of New South Wales, Australia* and Dru MARSH, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
A Relational Framework to Reconnect Property Rights to the Common Good

354.4 Buchari MENGGE, *Hasanuddin University, Indonesia*; Suparman ABDULLAH, *Hasanuddin University, Indonesia* and Sawedi MUHAMMAD, *Hasanuddin University, Indonesia*
Urban Small-Scale Fishing Community within the Vortex of Social Exclusion (Case of Urban Fishing Community in Makassar City, Indonesia)

354.5 Vanessa BOWDEN, *University of Newcastle, Australia*; Daniel NYBERG, *University of Newcastle, Australia*; Christopher WRIGHT, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Olivia HAMILTON, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Busy-Ness and Ignorance – the Political Inertia of Climate Politics in Australia

15:30-17:20

356 New research in environmental attitudes, values, behaviours and practices.

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jo LINDSAY, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Riti CHATTERJEE, *Just Transition Research Centre, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

356.1 Katarzyna IWINSKA, *Collegium Civitas, Poland* and Jacek BIELINSKI, *Collegium Civitas, Poland*
"You Can be Eco-Friendly but Not at Your Own Expense" - Underlying the Fundamental Factors of Private-Sphere Pro-Environmental Behaviour in 5 European Countries.

356.2 Jo LINDSAY, *Monash University, Australia*
Something Old, Something New and Something Borrowed: A New Perspective on Low-Waste Consumption Practices

356.3 Dorit ZIMAND-SHEINER, *Ariel University, Israel* and Sabina LISSITSA, *Ariel University, Israel*
When Bad News Became Good News - Factors Predicting Gen Z's Decline in Purchase Intentions after Receiving Negative Environmental Information - Fashion Brand Shein As a Case Study

356.4 Krzysztof MACZKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*; Maciej MILEWICZ, *Faculty of Sociology, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland*; Daria PANIOTOVA, *Faculty of Psychology and Cognitive Science, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland* and Klaudia RODZIEJCZAK, *Faculty of Psychology and Cognitive Science, Poland*
Q-Deliberation As a Method to Study and Consult Environmental Issues

356.5 Modho GOVIND, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Determinants of Pro-Environment Behaviour of People in Urban India: An Application of the Extended Theory of Planned Behaviour

355 Environmental Sociology Roundtables

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Pradip SWARNAKAR, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*

ROUNDTABLES:

Contending with Waste Management

Chair: Pradip SWARNAKAR, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

355.1 Federico Maria JELO DI LENTINI, *University of Catania, Italy*
The Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Food Waste and the Environmentally Unsustainable PPE Consumption.

355.2 Jihye KIM, *Seoul National University Environmental Planning Institute, Republic of Korea*
Worlding with Marine Debris -Alliance and Split of Beings in Marine Conservation in East Asia-

355.3 Oludele SOLAJA, *Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria*; Sunday ALUKO-AROWOLO, *Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria*; Olumide ONAFESO, *Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria* and Oluwaseyi ADELOWOKAN, *Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria*
A Socio-Ecological Investigation on Plastic Bottle Waste Brick As an Option for Plastic Pollution Reduction and Construction Block Deficit in Nigeria

355.4 Asrafi AKRAM, *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Bangladesh* and Mohammad HASAN, *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Bangladesh*
Impacts of Menstrual Waste on Water Bodies: A Study on Northern Bangladesh

The Places Where We Live

Chair: Piotr MATCZAK, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

355.5 Federico Maria JELO DI LENTINI, *University of Catania, Italy* and Nicola CAVALLOTTI, *University of Milan, Italy*
From the Coast Onward. Research Trajectories for the Urban and Social Regeneration of a Coastal Periphery

355.6 Piotr MATCZAK, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*
The Potential of Cultural Ecosystem Services in Local Urban Planning

Sociological examination of climate change impacts

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

355.7 Thomas SAFFORD, *University of New Hampshire, USA*
Climate Change and the Water-Society Nexus in the Amazon Region

355.8 Edgar BURNS, *Waikato University, New Zealand, New Zealand*
The Great Climate Retreat from the World's Coasts: Writing Long-Term Strategy

355.9 Subhaschandra MALLED, *Gulbarga university, India*
Climate Change Effect on Farmers in Karnataka: A Social Study

Democratic Governance of Environmental and Climate Emergencies

Chair: Bahubali PATIL, *C.S.I.B.E.R., University Road Kolhapur (Maharashtra), India, India*

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

355.10 Suresh RAJORA, *University of Kota, India*
Climate Change, Growth and Net Zero: Tough Choices to Indian Policy Makers

355.11 Pritha SARKAR, *Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Science in Policy-Making: Examining the Opinion of Scientists on Innovation and Development of Solar Energy in India

355.12 Jihun HA, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
The Effect of Policy Naming on Climate and Environmental Policy Acceptance

355.13 Kien NGUYEN-TRUNG, *BehaviourWorks Australia, Australia*
Involving Traditional Owners in the Creation of a Sustainable Transformative Change: Lessons Learned from a Climate Adaptation Mission in Victoria, Melbourne

17:30-19:20

JS-22 Materialist Sociology: Biometabolism, Technometabolism, Technoaddiction

Committees: RC24 Environment and Society (Host); RC16 Sociological Theory

See Joint Session Details for JS-22.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-26 Human Dimensions of Development and Sustainable Development Goals

Committees: TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice (Host); RC24 Environment and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-26.

357 Re-conceptualizing Socio Ecological Systems in an Era of Climate Change

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Stewart LOCKIE, *James Cook University, Australia*

Chair: Stewart LOCKIE, *James Cook University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

357.1 Thijs VAN DOOREMALEN, *Centre for Sociological Research, KU Leuven, Belgium*
The Political (in)Significance of Extreme Weather Events in the United States and Europe

357.2 Joan David TABARA, *Sustainability.eu - Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain*
Towards a Theory of Possibilities for Regenerative Sustainability. Repositioning Transformative Human Agency for the Emergence of Positive Tipping Points.

357.3 Justin SZASZ, *University of Oregon, USA* and Andrew SZASZ, *University of California, Santa Cruz, USA*
The Concept of Societal Brittleness and Its Relevance for a Sociology of Climate Change

357.4 Fabio D'ANDREA, *University of Perugia, Italy*
Environment As a Short Circuit in the Knowledge Production System

357.5 Jihye KIM, *Seoul National University Environmental Planning Institute, Republic of Korea*; Soonyawl PARK, *Innercity Inc. City-Society Center, Republic of Korea* and Saerom AHN, *Seoul National University, Institution for Sustainable Development, USA*
Why Environmental Sociology Concepts Fail to Capture Reality: To Break the Impasse of Concepts in Environmental Sociology

357.6 Andrea LAMPIS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
The Normalization of Precarity: An Ethnography of Energy Spaces and Life at Risk in Vila Nova Esperança (São Paulo, Brazil)

10:30-12:20

JS-33 Marine Justice, Ocean Studies, and Coastal CommunitiesCommittees: *RC24 Environment and Society (Host); RC03 Community Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-33.

15:30-17:20

JS-41 Globalization-Induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, Identity and Ecological issues). Part ICommittees: *RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC24 Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-41.

358 Revitalizing participatory democracy to address climate and environmental disruptions**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Lotsmart FONJONG, *University of Buea, Cameroon***Chair:** Lotsmart FONJONG, *University of Buea, Cameroon***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****358.1** Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *UGDU, CRRID, India*
Towards Participatory Irrigation and Forest Management in Foothills of Shivalik Range of Himalayas for Climate Change Mitigation: A Re-Study of Sukhomajiri Experiment**358.2** M. Anwar HOSSEN, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*
Decolonizing Democracy for Environmental Sustainability in Bangladesh**358.3** Noel CHELLAN, *Howard College Campus, South Africa*
Unequal Natures in South Africa: Towards a Democratic Ward-Based Model for the Protection and Management of Nature and Natural Resources in South Africa**358.4** Gillian PAXTON, *James Cook University, Australia*
Articulating Reef Futures: Community Narratives on Human-Assisted Ecosystem Adaptation in the Great Barrier Reef**358.5** Jose Javier MANYAS NAVARRO, *Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain*; Antonio ALEDO, *Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain*; Guadalupe ORTIZ, *University of Alicante, Spain* and Jordi CORTINA-SEGARRA, *Department of Ecology of the University of Alicante, Spain*
Embedding Socio-Political Barriers in Ecological Restoration Praxis with the Support of Collaborative Causal Maps**358.6** Xavier LEMAIRE, *University College London, United Kingdom*
Energy Citizenship and the Social Acceptability of Large Wind Energy Projects

17:30-19:20

359 Climate change vulnerability and adaptation across the North and South**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Debra DAVIDSON, *University of Alberta, Canada***Chair:** Imran SABIR, *Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****359.1** Esther OLIVER, *University of Barcelona, Spain* and Sandra RACIONERO-PLAZA, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Analysing the Social Impact of Climate Change**359.2** Dolgion ALDAR, *UNDP Timor-Leste, Mongolia* and Tselmegsaikhan LKHAGVA, *Independent Research Institute of Mongolia, Mongolia*
An Assessment of Climate Change Vulnerabilities: The Case of Mongolia**359.3** Carmit LUBANOV, *Tahadhari Center for Climate and Migration in Euro-Med (TCCMEM), Israel*
Climate Migration in Euro-Med Region - What Can We Learn from National Characteristics in the Fields of Environment, Culture and Economic Development in Relating to Outlining of Climate Migration Policy in Regional Scale?**359.4** Haisu HUANG, *University of Oregon, USA*
Class Inequalities and Climate Disaster**Wednesday 28 June**

08:30-10:20

JS-60 Materiality, Brutality and Risk: Decolonial Readings of the Twin Climate and Energy CrisisCommittees: *RC24 Environment and Society (Host); TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-60.

10:30-12:20

JS-65 Sociology and the Climate Science-Politics GapCommittees: *RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology (Host); RC24 Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-65.

360 Energy Consumption Patterns and Behaviors**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Sun-Jin YUN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea* and Jongmun PARK, *Korea Environment Institute, Republic of Korea***Chair:** Soonyawl PARK, *Innercity Inc. City-Society Center, Republic of Korea*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

360.1 Jongmun PARK, *Korea Environment Institute, Republic of Korea* and Sun-Jin YUN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Segmentation of Lifestyles for Home Appliances Using Sociodemographic Variables in Korea

360.2 Agne BUDZYTE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania* and Audrone TELESIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*
Building Energy Resilience: Motivational Barriers for Prosumers in Energy Transition

360.3 Hiroshi KOMATSU, *Matsuyama University, Japan*
A Fundamental Discussion on Shifting Transport Modes: Do the Modes Differ Among Cities?

360.4 Yanyan CHEN, *Fukuoka Institute of Technology, Japan*
A Causal Analysis of Energy Reduction Behaviors in Daily Life

15:30-17:20

JS-68 **Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part I**

Committees: *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC24 Environment and Society RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food and TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-68.

361 **New Directions in Environmental Sociology**

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Debra DAVIDSON, *University of Alberta, Canada*

Chair: Suresh RAJORA, *University of Kota, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

361.2 Xiaorui HUANG, *Drexel University, USA*
Not All Emissions Are Created Equal: Multidimensionality in Nations' Greenhouse Gas Emissions and the Affluence/Emissions Nexus

361.3 Rebecca PEARSE, *Australian National University, Australia*; Lauren RICKARDS, *RMIT, Australia*; David SCHLOSBERG, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Hannah DELLA BOSCA, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Oli MORAES, *RMIT, Australia*
The Conditions of Possibility for Environmental Justice

361.4 Paul JOBIN, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Coping with the Climate War and Resurgent Authoritarianism

361.5 Luigi PELLIZZONI, *University of Pisa, Italy*
Post-Security and Environmental Governance

361.6 Fengshi WU, *University of New South Wales, Australia*; Ellie MARTUS, *Griffith University, Australia* and David SONNENFELD, *SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry, USA*
Environmental Politics Under Authoritarian Rule: Policy, Power, and Advocacy

17:30-19:20

JS-77 **Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part II**

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization RC24 Environment and Society and RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-77.

19:30-20:50

362 **RC24 Business Meeting**

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-87 **Transforming Traditional Knowledge System of Mountains: A Threat to Sustainability**

Committees: *WG05 Famine and Society (Host); RC24 Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-87.

10:30-12:20

JS-96 **Traditional Water Cultures and the Modern Life**

Committees: *RC24 Environment and Society (Host); RC03 Community Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-96.

15:30-17:20

363 **Environmental Inequalities**

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Robbe GEERTS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium* and Frederic VANDERMOERE, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

Chair: Robbe GEERTS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

363.1 Shubhda ARORA, *Indian Institute of Management Lucknow, India*
Aesthetics of a Dystopia: Representation of Cityscapes and Environmental Inequalities

363.2 Patricia ROMERO-LANKAO, *University of Toronto Scarborough, Canada*; Rebecca EFROYMSON, *Back Ridge Laboratory, USA* and Nicole ROSNER, *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA*
Engaging Communities and Stakeholders to Achieve Energy Equity: Lessons and Best Practices

363.3 Atsushi NOZAWA, *Tokyo Keizai University, Japan*
Environmental Justice Versus Human Rights: Via a Lesson from Minamata Disease

17:30-19:20

364 Gendering the Sociology of Climate Change**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Angeline LETOURNEAU, *University of Alberta, Canada***Chair:** Angeline LETOURNEAU, *University of Alberta, Canada***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****364.1** Karla ELLIOTT, *Monash University, Australia*
*Engaging Men in Climate Action and Care for the Environment***364.2** Vibha ARORA, *IIT Delhi, India*
*Gender, Environmental Inequalities, and Sustainable Consumption Among Delhi's Middle Class***364.3** Yun-chung TING, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan* and Hung-Hong LIN, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
*Hidden Drivers of Sustainable Energy Transition: The Effects of Economic Growth, Democracy and Gender Equality on the Development of Renewable Energy***364.4** Mumita TANJEELA, *Department of Sociology, East West University, Dhaka, Bangladesh*
*Gendered Struggle of Bangladeshi Women in Coping with Climate Change: Need for Gender Transformative Approaches***Friday 30 June**

08:30-10:20

365 Sustainable Energy Transitions I: Frameworks, Drivers and Barriers**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Mark STODDART, *Memorial University, Canada***Chair:** Mark STODDART, *Memorial University, Canada***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****365.1** Riti CHATTERJEE, *Just Transition Research Centre, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
*The Implications of Sustainable Livelihood Framework for Just Transition Policies and Practice: An Empirical Study from Northeastern Coalfields of India***365.2** Gregory TRENCHER, *Kyoto university, Japan*
*Critically Examining Proposed Pathways to Net-Zero By 2050 for BP, Chevron, Exxonmobil and Shell***365.3** Patricia ROMERO-LANKAO, *University of Toronto Scarborough, Canada* and Nicole ROSNER, *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA*
*Towards Equity and Justice in Energy Transitions in Los Angeles***365.4** Tadeusz RUDEK, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland* and Hui Tzu HUANG, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*
*A Journey to the West? a Reflexive Public Reason for Energy Transition in China and Taiwan.***365.5** Hajime KIMURA, *University of Toyama, Japan*
Deadlock in and New Intervention Pathway Toward Sustainable Energy Transitions: An Analysis on ESG Investment Using the Treadmill of Production Model

10:30-12:20

366 Sustainable Energy Transitions II: Frameworks, Drivers and Barriers.**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Catherine Mei Ling WONG, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands***Chair:** Catherine Mei Ling WONG, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****366.1** Olena POTOPNYK, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
*"Black Gold" Vs Green Energy: Drivers Towards Energy Transition in Poland***366.2** Josephine DIONISIO, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*; Laurence DELINA, *Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong*; Jergil Gyle GAVIERES, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines* and Joey OCON, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
*Social Networks for Renewable Energy Transition in Small Off-Grid Islands in the Philippines***366.3** Hua-Mei CHIU, *National Sun Yat-Sen University Taiwan, Taiwan*
*Social and Environmental Conflicts in Taiwan's Energy Transition***366.4** Markku LEHTONEN, *Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain*; Mika KARI, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland* and Tapio LITMANEN, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland*
*The Promise of Small Nuclear Reactors: Constructing and Deconstructing a Nuclear Renaissance in Canada and Finland***366.5** Midori AOYAGI, *Inst for Environmental Studies, Japan* and Ritsuko OZAKI, *University of Winchester, United Kingdom*
Energy Poverty in Southeast Asia: Climate Change Mitigation and the Quality of Life

15:30-17:20

367 Bringing nature in: Human-wildlife interactions.**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Tyler BATEMAN, *University of Toronto, Canada***Chair:** Farhat NAZ, *Indian Institute of Technology Jodhpur, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****367.1** Clayton FORDAHL, *University of Memphis, Sociology Department, USA*
*Charismatic Creatures: Lessons from Sociological Theory for Conservation***367.2** Deniz DILER, *Bogazici University, Sociology Department, Turkey*
*Forming an Alliance between Interdisciplinary Fields of Political Ecology and Critical Animal Studies for Earth Liberation***367.3** Gavin John SMITH, *Australian National University, Australia*
*Rewilding Sociology? How Displaced Brown Snakes on the Urban Fringe Can Contribute to Sociological Practice***367.4** Penney WOOD, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Exploring the Use of a Relational Paradigm for Understanding Human-Wildlife Coexistence

367.5 Tyler BATEMAN, *University of Toronto, Canada*; Daniel SILVER, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Alicia EADS, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Material Facts and Cultural Meanings of Invasive Species in Toronto, Ontario

17:30-19:20

368 Immaterialities: Norms, Culture and Religion in environmental politics and practice.

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Patricia ROMERO-LANKAO, *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA*

Chair: Patricia ROMERO-LANKAO, *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

368.1 Anjali YADAV, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Common Pool Resources, Social Norms and Public Policy

368.2 Abida SHARIF, *Fatima Jinnah Women University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan* and Imran SABIR, *Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan*
Faith-Based Affirmative Action for Environmental Conservation: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan

368.3 Zanetta JANSEN, *University of South Africa, South Africa*
Religion at the Center of the Environmental Movement: Laudato Si, Climate Change and Social Justice, a Case Study

368.4 Patria Gwen BORCENA, *Greenresearch Environmental Research Group, Inc., Philippines*
Philippine Based Laudato Si' Champions Versus Poverty and Climate Emergency

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

369 Expertise for Transformative Change

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Rolf LIDSKOG, *Environmental Sociology Section, Örebro University, Sweden*

Chair: Rolf LIDSKOG, *Environmental Sociology Section, Örebro University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

369.1 Vincent BACKHAUS, *James Cook University, Australia* and Stewart LOCKIE, *James Cook University, Australia*
Embedding Indigenous Expertise in Marine Governance: A Co-Design Approach to Invasive Species Research and Control on the Great Barrier Reef, Australia

369.2 Alexander RUSER, *University of Agder, Norway*
Counter-Expertise, Weaponised Common Sense and the Promises of Local Climate Knowledge

369.3 Damien KRICHEWSKY, *University of Bonn, Germany*
Fostering Transformative Change in Biodiversity Governance: Reflections on an Action Research in the Field of Access & Benefit-Sharing

369.4 Midori AOYAGI, *Inst for Environmental Studies, Japan*
Media Discourse and the Experts' Roles in the Scientific Evaluation of the Children's Thyroid Study.

369.5 Katriona MCGLADE, *University of East Anglia, United Kingdom*
Challenging Expertise: Knowledge-Ing in Scottish Climate Change Adaptation

10:30-12:20

370 Roles and Impacts of Non-State Actors for Climate Change Mitigation

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Koichi HASEGAWA, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan* and Sun-Jin YUN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*

Chair: Koichi HASEGAWA, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

370.1 Sun-Jin YUN, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
What Should Successful Climate Governance be like?: Implications and Lessons from the 2050 Carbon Neutrality Commission in Republic of Korea

370.2 Takashi NAKAZAWA, *Department of Sociology, Toyo university, Japan* and Tomoyuki TATSUMI, *Toyohashi SOZO Junior College, Japan*
Declarations for Net-Zero By 2050 As a Turning Point for Climate Policy: Linkages between Vertical and Horizontal Diffusion

370.3 Carmit LUBANOV, *Tahadhari Center for Climate and Migration in Euro-Med (TCCMEM), Israel*
Paradigm Shift from IPCC to IPCCRC- Mediterranean as Model 'Cradle of Partnership' (COP) for Climate Regionality

370.4 Alexander RUSER, *University of Agder, Norway*
Roundup the Unsuspicious Suspects: The Role of Small Non-State Actors and Informal Networks to Undermine Climate Change Consensus

370.5 Vidas VILCINSKAS, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania* and Agne BUDZYTE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*
Can Trust Issues Lead to a Lack of Civic Engagement in Non-State Actors Activities for Climate Change Mitigation?

370.6 Karin GUSTAFSSON, *Örebro University, Sweden*
"Listen to the Science". the Climate Youth Movement's Trust in Science.

12:30-14:20

JS-145 Environment and Work: Links and Threats

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work (Host)*; RC24 *Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-145.

14:30-16:20

371 Social Dynamics of Climate Change Policy-Making and Political Action**Location:** 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Mark STODDART, *Memorial University, Canada* and Pradip SWARNAKAR, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India***Chair:** Pradip SWARNAKAR, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

371.1 Rajshri SHUKLA, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India, India*
Tracing Policy Changes in the Indian Climate Discourse: Comparing Policy Beliefs and Advocacy Coalition during Copenhagen, Paris and Glasgow Climate Conferences

371.2 Yixi YANG, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Dynamics in Climate Policy Discussion Network on China's Weibo: A Longitudinal Network-Behaviour Co-Evolution Analysis

371.3 Keiichi SATOH, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*; Antti GRONOW, *University of Helsinki, Finland* and Tuomas YLÄ-ANTTILA, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Opportunity Structures and Advocacy Coalitions in Climate Politics: A Network Approach

371.4 James GOODMAN, *University of Technology, Australia*
Decarbonising Electricity: The Promise of Renewable Energy Regions in India, Germany and Australia

371.5 Mark STODDART, *Memorial University of Newfoundland & Labrador, Canada*; Yasmin KOOP-MONTEIRO, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and David TINDALL, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Climate Heroes, Villains, and Climate Justice: Instagram As an Arena for Counter-Discourse and Mobilization at COP26

371.6 Lotsmart FONJONG, *University of Buea, Cameroon*
Farmers' Perception and Response to Climate Change across Agro-Ecological Zones in Conflict-Ridden Communities in Cameroon

371.7 Koichi HASEGAWA, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan*
Youth Action for Climate Crisis Protection: Fridays for Future, Global and Japan

RC25

Language and Society

Program Coordinators: Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*; Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan* and Rika YAMASHITA, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

372 Language, Religion, and Linguistic Rights in Times of Crisis

Language: English, French

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ovgu ULGEN, *University of Montreal, Canada*

Chair: Marjorie MAIDO, *Iloilo Science And Technology University, Philippines*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

372.1 Musa YUSUPOV, *Chechen State University, Law Faculty, Russian Federation*
The Linguistic and Religious Dominance of Identity in the Context of Regional Conflict

372.2 Beatriz XAVIER, *Health Sciences Research Unit: Nursing /Coimbra Nursing School, Portugal*
The Use of Words As an Expression of Rights. the Institutional Language of Care Services in the Face of Unsupported Immigration, a Case Study in Portugal

372.3 Phyllis MWANGI, *Kenyatta University, Kenya* and Gatitu KIGURU, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*
"Hustler" Vs. "Dynasty" Discourse in Kenya: A Herald of Issue-Based-Politics or a New Frontier in Othering

372.4 Agnieszka WOLOWICZ, *University of Warsaw, The Faculty of Education, Poland*
Research Involving People with Disabilities

372.5 Magdalena LEMANCZYK, *Institute of Political Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
When the Narrative of State Power Meets the Narrative of a National Minority. the Case of the German Minority in Poland.

17:30-19:20

373 Language As a Tool for Oppression and Resistance within Institutional Practices

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Frida PETERSSON, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*; Johan LINDWALL, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden* and Beatriz XAVIER, *Coimbra Nursing School, Portugal*

Chair: Beatriz XAVIER, *Coimbra Nursing School, Portugal*

Co-chairs: Frida PETERSSON, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden* and Johan LINDWALL, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

373.1 Gabriela MEZZANOTTI, *University of South-Eastern Norway, Norway* and Alyssa Marie KVALVAAG, *Nord University, Norway*
Racialized Human Rights: Discriminatory Responses and Everyday Coloniality in Migration Governance in the Global North

373.2 Teruhiro YAMAKITA, *Nihon University, Japan*
Suffering from 'Ghosts': A Former Homeless Person and the Supporting Practices of Housing First in Tokyo

373.3 Aryo DANUSIRI, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia* and Dea BELLA, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
Endangered Language and the Afterlife of Language Development in Hamap Language, Alor, East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia

373.4 Norah ATAMBO, *Kenyatta University, Kenya* and Emily OGUTU, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*
Language and Gendered Political Discourses: How Do Women Politicians in Kenya Reconstruct Their Political Agency?

373.5 Maxime MARECHAL, *Institut Convergences Migrations, France*
Critical Interpreters. Language Interpreting and the Instruction of Asylum Claims in France

373.6 Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan*
"Gaman" and "Gacha": How Young People Deal with Social Inequality in Japan

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

374 Discourse Analysis Methodology and the Role of Written Narratives in Sociological Research

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Anna ODROWAZ-COATES, *Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*

Chair: Anna ODROWAZ-COATES, *Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

374.1 Guillaume FERNANDEZ, *University of Geneva, Switzerland*
A Configurational Approach to Discourse Analysis

374.2 Urszula MARKOWSKA-MANISTA, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Anna ODROWAZ-COATES, *Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*
Research with a Sensitive Group in a Sensitive Context - Participatory Approaches and Counter-Narratives of Young People in Poland

374.3 Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*
What's Worth Writing about: Theoretical and Methodological Issues in a Corpus of Daily Social Work Notes

374.4 Joanna PAWLOWSKA, *The Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*
Narratives of Women about Their Identity and Name Choices after Marriage

374.5 Mariusz BARANOWSKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland*
Topic Modelling on Climate Change Scepticism: Machine Learning Approach

374.6 Piotr CICHOCKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*
Reflecting Populist Tensions over Climate Change Policy in Academic Discourse

15:30-17:20

JS-40 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part I

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-40.

17:30-19:20

JS-45 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part II

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-45.

19:30-20:50

375 RC25 Business Meeting

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-59 Language and Work: The Post-Pandemic Evolutions of Categorizations Toward (Un)Employment and Working Conditions

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-59.

10:30-12:20

376 The Interplay of Language, Migration and Mobility: Policy and Practice

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Magdalena LEMANCZYK, *Institute of Political Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland* and Rika YAMASHITA, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan*

Chair: Rika YAMASHITA, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan*

Co-Chair: Magdalena LEMANCZYK, *Institute of Political Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

376.1 Wai-chi CHEE, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Language Policies and Racialized Linguistic Privilege within Educational Settings in Hong Kong

376.2 Tobias JANSSEN, *Gothenburg University, Sweden*
Language As an Ideological Fantasy: The Role of Swedish Language within the Swedish Refugee Settlement Program

376.3 Marek TROSZYNSKI, *Collegium Civitas, Poland*
Refugees, Immigrants and Invaders. How the Language We Talk about Migrants Is Changing.

376.4 Agnieszka BALCERZAK, *LMU Munich, Germany* and Magdalena LEMANCZYK, *Institute of Political Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
Walls Saying No to War: Exploring the Language of Anti-War Street Art in Poland and Germany

376.5 Cecilio LAPRESTA-REY, *University of Lleida, Spain;* Josep UBALDE BUENAFUENTE, *UdL-Universitat de Lleida, Spain;* Amado ALARCON ALARCON, *University Rovira i Virgili, Spain;* Ángel HUGUET, *University of Lleida, Spain;* Judit JANÉS, *University of Lleida, Spain* and Adelina IANOS, *University of Lleida, Spain*
Language Knowledge, Linguistic Acculturation Profiles and Occupational Aspirations: The Case of the Second Generation in Catalonia

15:30-17:20

JS-72 Everyday Practices of 'Othering': Ongoing Developments. Part III

Committees: *RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-72.

17:30-19:20

JS-80 Language and Immigrant Generations: New Entanglements.

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-80.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

377 Media, Social Exclusion and Audience Empowerment

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Nadezhda GEORGIEVA-STANKOVA, *Trakia University, Bulgaria*

Chair: Beatriz XAVIER, *Coimbra Nursing School, Portugal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

377.1 Carlo Sorrentino CARLO SORRENTINO, *Department of Political and Social Sciences, University of Florence, Italy;* Laura SOLITO, *University of Florence, Italy;* Silvia PEZZOLI, *University of Florence, Italy;* Letizia Materassi LETIZIA MATERASSI, *Department of Political and Social, University of Florence, Italy* and Giacomo BUONCOMPAGNI, *Department of Political and Social Sciences, University of Florence, Italy*
Social Construction of Anti-Semitism and the Point of View of Italian Journalism

377.2 Marjorie MAIDO, *Iloilo Science And Technology University, Philippines*
It Takes a Farm to Destroy a Woman: The Violence of Trolling in the Philippines

377.3 Laura GARBES, *University of Minnesota - Twin Cities, USA*
American Public Radio Voice and Outsiders within

377.4 Stefani NUGROHO, *Atma Jaya Catholic University of Indonesia, Indonesia*
Talking Back through Tiktok: Countering the Stereotypes of the Chinese Indonesian in Comedy Sketches

377.5 Cheng-Jun WANG, *Nanjing University, China*
"Overthrow the Capitalists Again": The Production and Reproduction of the Private Capital De-Legitimization Discourse on Chinese Social Media

15:30-17:20

JS-101 Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part I

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC15 Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-101.

17:30-19:20

JS-111 The Language of Risk. Part I

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-111.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-118 Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part II

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC15 Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-118.

10:30-12:20

378 Discursive Discourses of Political Violence

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Everlyn KISEMBE, *Moi University, Kenya*; Gatitu KIGURU, *Kenyatta University, Kenya* and Phyllis MWANGI, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*

Chair: Phyllis MWANGI, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*

Co-Chair: Everlyn KISEMBE, *Moi University, Kenya*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

378.1 Nancy LANGAT KORIR, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*
Handshake or Hand-Cheque: An Analysis of the Discursive Construction of the Kenyan 2017 Post-Election Political Pact in the Daily Nation Newspaper.

378.2 Vladimir PAPERNI, *The University of Haifa, Israel*
The Ideological Discourse of the Contemporary Russian Autocracy: Functions and Registers

378.3 Eunice NYAMASYO, *Kenyatta University, Thika Road, Nairobi, Kenya* and Quin JUMA, *United States International University - Africa, Kenya*
The 'Transgressive' Nature of Trade Union Discourse in the Kenyan Academy: The Case of the Kenyatta University Universities Academic and Staff Union (UASU)

378.4 Erzsebet BARAT, *University of Szeged, Hungary*
Countering the Prevalence of Hate-Rhetoric in Rightwing Populist Political Communication: The Case of Hungary

378.5 Ishani DEB, *University of Calcutta, India*
Asymmetrical Linguistic Field: The Study of Adolescent Bengali Speakers Encountering English Hegemony and Their Political Marginalization

15:30-17:20

379 Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part III

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Viviane DE MELO RESENDE, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

Chair: Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

379.1 Victoria DUDINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation* and Viktoriia SAIFULINA, *St. Petersburg University, Russian Federation*
Online Discourse of Vaccine Hesitancy Concerning COVID-19 Vaccination in Russian-Language Social Media

379.2 Akihiko SATO, *Kwansei Gakuin University, Japan*
Between Promoter and Obstructionist of Vaccination: Vaccine-Induced Sufferings and Anti-Vaccination Discourse in Japan

379.3 Tomiaki YAMADA, *Matsuyama University, Japan* and Norio HAYASAKA, *NPO Ryochans, Japan*
Distancing from the Languages of Victims: From the Life History of Mr. Norio Hayasaka, a Hemophiliac Infected HIV Due to Tainted Blood Products in Japan

379.4 Idalina ODZIEMCZYK STAWARZ, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
The Language of Health Threats and Preventive Measures - Biographical Narratives of the Older People Vaccinated and Unvaccinated Against Influenza during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

380 Intersections of Gender, Sexuality, and Age (Youth) Looking at Language

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Rika YAMASHITA, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan* and Chandrabali DUTTA, *HIRALAL MAZUMDAR MEMORIAL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, India*

Chair: Rika YAMASHITA, *Kanto Gakuin University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

380.1 Mark SEILHAMER, *National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*
Intersections of Gender, Age, and Language Learning in Neoliberal Taiwan

380.2 Kyoko TAKEUCHI, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
Multiple Interpretations of Non-Binary Gender Identity Categories: An Analysis of the Narratives of Gender-Nonconforming People in Japan

380.3 Anusuya MOITRA, *Muralidhar Girls' College, India*
Sexuality, Sign Language and Deaf Culture : A Sociological Exploration in Kolkata

380.4 Purity NTHIGA, *Kenyatta University, Kenya* and Phyllis MWANGI, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*
Youth Linguaging: A Peek into Their Attitude Towards Sex and Sexuality

380.5 Marta SOLER GALLART, *Universidad de Barcelona, Spain* and Ana VIDU, *University of Deusto, Spain*
Does Yes Always Mean Yes? Analyzing Consent for the Prevention of Gender Violence

380.6 Manzuma AHSAN, *East West University, Bangladesh*
The Cultural Construction of Women through Language: Exploring Gender Identity in Bangladesh

12:30-14:20

JS-148 Language on/of Youth Under COVID-19 Pandemic

Committees: *RC25 Language and Society (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth*

See Joint Session Details for JS-148.

14:30-16:20

JS-153 The Language of Risk. Part II

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-153.

10:30-12:20

381 The Functional Perspective of the Regional Languages in the Modern World

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Musa YUSUPOV, *Chechen State University, Russian Federation*

Chair: Phyllis MWANGI, *Kenyatta University, Kenya*

Panelist: Cristina BOBOC, *Ghent University, Belgium*

Discussant: Erhan GUNEYSU, *Anglia Ruskin University, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

381.1 Erhan GUNEYSU, *Anglia Ruskin University, United Kingdom*
Language Policy and Status of the Endangered Languages in the Middle East

381.2 Mahmoud DHAOUADI, *University of Tunis, Tunisia*
Linguistic confinement and people and societies' relationships with their languages

381.3 Cristina BOBOC, *Ghent University, Belgium*
'do You Speak Po Russky?' Politics of the Accent in Urban Azerbaijan

381.4 Lluís CATALÀ-OLTRA, *Universidad de Alicante, Spain*; Rodolfo MARTINEZ-GRAS, *University of Alicante, Spain* and Clemente PENALVA, *University of Alicante, Spain*
The Weight of Minority Languages in the Digital Communication at European Universities in Multilingual Settings

RC26

Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

Program Coordinators: Flaminia SACCA, *Università della Tuscia, Italy* and Luca MASSIDDA, *Tuscia University, Italy*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-10 Panel Discussion: Accrediting Your Undergraduate or Graduate Program in Sociological Practice: A Workshop on Process, Benefits, and Outcomes By the Commission on the Accreditation of Programs in Applied and Clinical Sociology (CAPACS)

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

See Joint Session Details for JS-10.

17:30-19:20

382 The Socio-Political Dimension of Gender Relations in Times of Crisis and of Resurgent Authoritarianism

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Flaminia SACCA, *Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy*

Chair: Flaminia SACCA, *Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

382.1 Valentina RAFFA, *University of Messina, Italy*
Working for "Another" Representation of Gender-Based Violence: The Politics of Feminist Movements and Anti-Violence Centres in Contemporary Italy

382.2 Rosalba BELMONTE, *Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Italy*
The Journalistic Representation of Gender-Based Violence in Pandemic Times an Analysis of the Italian Newspapers'

382.3 Luca MASSIDDA, *Tuscia University, Italy*
Marginalized & Stereotyped. the Political Representation of Gender-Based Violence in the 2022 Italian Election Campaign.

382.4 Emanuela SUSCA, *Università degli studi di Urbino "Carlo Bo", Italy*
Smart Kids? Children As Protagonists of Smart Societies

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

383 Social Economy's Transformative Power, Creative Sectors and the Art of Local Resilient Recovery

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Georgios TSOBANOGLOU, *Sociology Department, University of the Aegean, Lesvos, Greece, Greece*

Chair: Nikita POKROVSKY, *National Research University - High School of Economics, Russian Federation*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

383.1 Nikos SARRIS, *National Centre for Social Research, Greece*
Poverty and Social Exclusion As a Main Indicator of the EU 2030 Target: Current Situation and Perspectives in EU Member-States

383.2 Nectarios OUDENIOTIS, *University of the Aegean, Greece* and Georgios TSOBANOGLOU, *University of the Aegean, Greece*
Social Capital Formation Among Third Sector Organizations

383.3 Mukesh RANGA, *CSJM University, India* and Neelam RANGA, *Culture and Environment Conservation Society, India*
Impact of Digitalization on Rural Empowerment

383.4 George GANTZIAS, *Hellenic Open University, Greece*
Dynamics of Cultural Economy in Digital Society: The Information Communication Creative Industrial Content Sectors in the Era of Artificial Intelligence and Robot

10:30-12:20

JS-36 Transformative Research, Education and World Social Forum

Committees: RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-36.

17:30-19:20

JS-48 Integrative and Disintegrative Processes in Europe and Eurasia: Public Opinion, State Politics and Media Discourse.

Committees: WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations (Host); RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

See Joint Session Details for JS-48.

19:30-20:50

384 RC26 Business Meeting

Location: M5 (Crown)

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

385 Legal and Educational Instruments to Contrast Gender-Based Violence

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Rosalba BELMONTE, *Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Italy* and Michele NEGRI, *University of Tuscia - Viterbo - Italy, Italy*

Chair: Rosalba BELMONTE, *Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

385.1 Flaminia SACCA, *Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy*
Tackling Stereotypes and Prejudices. Educating to Contrast Gender Based Violence

385.2 Luca MASSIDDA, *Tuscia University, Italy*
Trails & Bias. Stereotypes and Gender Discrimination in the Legal Representation of Male Violence Against Women

385.3 Fabio MOSTACCIO, *University of Messina, Italy*
Italy's New Policies to Tackle Violence Against LGBT+ People: The Beginning of a New Era?

385.4 Antonio TRAMONTANA, *University of Messina, Italy*
Gender-Based Violence on Instagram between Stereotypes, Prejudices, and Social Innovation. a Visual Analysis of the Imaginary of #Violenzadigenere

17:30-19:20

386 Political Leadership between Pandemic and Post-Pandemic Times

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Luca MASSIDDA, *Tuscia University, Italy*

Chair: Luca MASSIDDA, *Tuscia University, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

386.1 Andrea MICONI, *IULM, Italy*
Authoritarianism without Autocracy. Constituent Power in the Age of Covid-19

386.3 Flaminia SACCA, *Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy*
Political Leaders in Pandemic and Post Pandemic Times: Inclusive Democrats and Resurgent Authoritarians.

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

387 Social-Technical Dynamics, Cultural Issues and Artificial Intelligences in Smart Cities: Info-Communication Policy and Society

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: George GANTZIAS, *Hellenic Open University, Greece*

Chair: George GANTZIAS, *Hellenic Open University, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

387.1 James SANTOS, *Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil* and Carolina CARVALHO, *Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Worldwide AI Ethics: A Review of 200 Guidelines and Recommendations for AI Governance

387.2 Georgios TSOBANOGLOU, *University of the Aegean, Greece* and Charalambos LOUCA, *American College, Cyprus*
Sustainable Development: Looking the Culture and Communication of the Past As a Way to the Future of Sustainability in Greece.

387.3 Mikolaj BIESAGA, *Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland*; Anna DOMARADZKA, *Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland*; Magdalena ROSZCZYNSKA KURASINSKA, *Univeristy of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmieście 26/28, 00-927 Warsaw, Poland*; Szymon TALAGA, *Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland* and Andrzej NOWAK, *Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland*
The Effect of the Pandemic on European Narratives on Smart Cities and Surveillance

387.4 Anna DOMARADZKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Anna WNUK, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Tomasz OLEKSY, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Mateusz TROCHYMIAK, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Right to the Smart City

387.5 Massimiliano RUZZEDDU, *University Niccolò Cusano, Italy*
Understanding Smart Societies: The Role of Sociological Theory

15:30-17:20

388 Life after and Beyond the City: Challenging Alternatives to Disturbing Urbanization

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Nikita POKROVSKY, *National Research University - High School of Economics, Russian Federation*

Chair: Georgios TSOBANOGLOU, *University of the Aegean, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

388.1 Nikita POKROVSKY, *National research university "Higher School of Economics", Russian Federation* and Uliana NIKOLAEVA, *Institute of Sociology RAS, Russian Federation*
Counter-Urbanization and Centrifugal Migration in the Age of Social Turbulence

388.2 Tatiana SIDORINA, *Higher School of Economics National Research University, Russian Federation*
Disturbing Urbanization: Pro Et Contra of Technical Authoritarianism

388.3 Valentina SHILOVA, *Korpus 5, Russian Federation* and Kirill BIKOV, *Institute of Sociology of the Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Ac, Russia*
Human Capital and Lifestyle of the Rural Population of the Central Federal District of Russia: Projections of the Past, Present and Future

388.4 Alena MAKSHANCHIKOVA, *National Research University Higher School of Economics, Russian Federation*
The Formation of Localities in the Practices of Deurbanization Mobility: Analysis of Sociocultural Transformations of Rural Areas Cases 2020 – 2022

388.5 Egor NIKISHIN, *Higher school of economics, Russian Federation* and Alena MAKSHANCHIKOVA, *National Research University Higher School of Economics, Russian Federation*
Reverse Migration in Pandemic Crisis: Russia's out-of-TOWN Spaces As an Adaptation Resource

389.3 Andrea MILLEFIORINI, *Università della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Italy*
Environmentalism and Ecologism. Next New Ideologies?

389.4 Michal NAWROCKI, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Studying Populism As a Knowledge Phenomenon: Theory and Practice

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

389 Conspiracy Theories, Populism and Crisis in the Global World

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Lorenzo VIVIANI, *University of Pisa, Italy*

Chair: Lorenzo VIVIANI, *University of Pisa, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

389.1 Felix SCHILK, *Technische Universität Dresden, Germany*
The Narrative Style in Politics or Linking Conservatism and Conspiracy Theory

389.2 Gregor BONGAERTS, *University Duisburg-Essen, Germany*
The Societal Production of Insecurity.

RC27

Sociology of Sport

Program Coordinators: Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Brent MCDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*; Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Marcelle DAWSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Ramon SPAALJ, *Victoria University, Australia* and Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

390 Sport and Media

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Brent MCDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*; Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Marcelle DAWSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Ramon SPAALJ, *Victoria University, Australia* and Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: David ROWE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

390.1 Satwinder REHAL, *The University of the Philippines Open University, Philippines*
No Longer Elusive: Discourses over the Philippines' First Olympic Gold Medal

390.2 Nicholas HOOKWAY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
'As Close to Perfection As Possible': Roger Federer As Late Modern Moral Hero

390.3 Liang XIAO, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*; Kate DELMO, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia* and Amelia JONES, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
From Individual Satisfaction to Collective Resonance: The Social Identity Formation in Consuming Tencent Nba Live Streaming Service

390.4 Ivana MATTEUCCI, *Urbino University Carlo Bo, Italy*
Media Sports Events As a Stage for Digital Activism and Social Movements

390.5 Pratichi MAJUMDAR, *GendV Project, University of Cambridge, India*
Pandemic and Online Chess Boom: Creation of a New Digital Community in Indian Sports

19:30-20:50

391 Sport, Economies and Mega-Events

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

Chair: Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

391.1 David ROWE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Sport, Diplomacy, Gender and Region: Positioning the FIFA Women's World Cup Australia and New Zealand 2023

391.2 Rodrigo DE SOUSA, *University of Coimbra, Brazil*
Rio De Janeiro for Sale: Urban Entrepreneurship Strategies in the Construction of the Commodity City

391.3 Yasuo SHIMIZU, *Doshisha University, Japan*
Tokyo Marathon and Japan: In the Situation of COVID-19 and Tokyo 2020

Tuesday 27 June

15:30-17:20

392 Sport, Health and Wellbeing

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

Chair: Sanjay TEWARI, *LN Mithila University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

392.1 Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*
Discrediting the Binary: Gendered Knowledge, Inclusive Practice and the Accreditation of Exercise Professionals in Australia

392.2 Chloe SHER, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Race, Nativity, and Inequality in Physical Activity: An Intersectional and Life Course Approach

392.3 Noelle BRIGDEN, *Marquette University, USA*
Mama Fit Goes to El Salvador: Fitness in a Transnational Society

392.4 Vanessa GARCIA GONZALEZ, *Universidad Autónoma Chapingo UAC771230988, Mexico*
Calculating Risks: A Mechanism to Medicalize Physical (in) Activity

392.5 Steven JACKSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*; Dan PORTER, *University of Otago, New Zealand* and Marcelle DAWSON, *University of Otago, New Zealand*
The Well-Being Pandemic: Outline of a Contested Terrain and Research Agenda

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

393 Sport and Politics

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

Chair: Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

393.1 Lone THING, *Norwegian School of Sport Science, Norway* and Stine FRYDENDAL, *Copenhagen University, Denmark*
"Sport on the Warpath": An Figurational Reflection on the Role of Sport in an Interdependent World

393.2 Federico GENOVESI, *Ulster University, United Kingdom*
Solidarity Grassroots Football and Right to the City: How Solidarity to Refugees and People Seeking Asylum, and Resistance to the Commodification of Public Space Intersect in Italian Grassroots Football.

393.3 James CONNOR, *University of New South Wales, Australia* and Vanessa MCDERMOTT, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Wada's Global Education Strategy: Work As Imagined Versus Work As Done – Reflections from Oceania and the 2022 Wada Global Education Conference.

393.4 Narayana VAN AMSTEL, *Federal University of Parana, Brazil* and Wanderley MARCHI JR., *Universidade Federal do Paraná, Brazil*
Ideal Type of Sport: A Weberian Approach

393.5 Aleksandr GONASHVILI, *St. Petersburg State Technological Institute (Technical University), Russian Federation*
Sporting Practices of Intellectual Workers: The Results of an Empirical Study

15:30-17:20

394 Sport and Development

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

Chair: Michael SAM, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

394.1 Mitchell MCSWEENEY, *University of Minnesota, USA*
"We Narrate Home Stories to Each Other...and We Try to Forget about All the Stresses and All the Travel": Constructing Diasporic Communities through Sport for Refugee Belonging and Livelihoods in Uganda

394.2 Shalu SINHA, *Central University of South Bihar, India* and Samapika MOHAPATRA, *Central University Of South Bihar, India, India*
Reflecting upon Implementation of Khelo India Programmes: A Study of Participation of School Children in Bihar (India)

394.3 Sophie BYRNES, *Victoria University, Australia*
The Process of Co-Creating Sustainable Solutions for Female Basketball Participation in Melbourne's West.

394.4 Ramon SPAALJ, *Victoria University, Australia*; Jonathan MAGEE, *Monash University, Australia*; Ruth JEANES, *Monash University, Australia*; Dawn PENNEY, *Edith Cowan University, Australia* and Justen O'CONNOR, *Monash University, Australia*
Informal Sport, Belonging, and Cultural Capital Among Hazara Migrants in Australia

394.5 Madara STRAUME, *University of Latvia, Latvia*
The Role of Social Networks in the Development of Career of Professional Athletes

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

395 Sport, Bodies and Identities

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

395.1 Belinda WHEATON, *University of Waikato, New Zealand* and Lucen LIU, *University of Waikato, New Zealand*
Dis-Connected Coastal Bluespace Relationships in Aotearoa New Zealand: Ethnic Chinese Communities in the City of Sails

395.2 Cyriac BOUCHET-MAYER, *Santesih. Univ. Montpellier, France*
Sports Experiences and the Construction of Homosexual Scripts in West African Context

395.3 Gaowei CHEN, *Tongji University, China*
Body, Knowledge and Modernity: The Origins and Early Development of Modern Sports in China

395.4 Valerie ISSAK, *University of Haifa, Israel*
Sports and Social Inequality – School As Social Agent in the Decisions of Women to Pursue a Career in Sports

395.5 Dr Rakesh Kumar TIWARI, *Buddha Institute of Technology, GIDA, Gorakhpur, India* and Ravi PRAKASH, *Government Degree College, Nanauta, Mughalsarai, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India*
Self Identity and Sports: A Sociological Study

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

396 Sport, Exclusion and Inequities

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Brent MCDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: Ramon SPAALJ, *Victoria University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

396.1 Sevket ISIK, *Anadolu University, Turkey*
The Active Role of Sports in the Struggle of Stigmatized Individuals Against Discrimination

396.2 Carla LUGUETTI, *Victoria University, Australia*; Brent MCDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia* and Fiona MCLACHLAN, *Victoria University, Australia*
Enhancing Social Inclusion of Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Communities in Sport: Generating Ripple Effects?

396.3 Regan MAY, *Victoria University, Australia* and Brent MCDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*
Mainstream Sports Clubs Celebrating Cultural Diversity and the Social Inclusion They Promote: An Exploratory Case-Study.

396.4 Susan ERIKSSON, *South Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences, Finland*
Inclusion and Exclusion in Youth Sports – Case of Young Persons with Profound Intellectual Disabilities

396.5 Zeana HAMDONAH, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Masjid Ball: The Influence of Mosque-Based Physical Activity Programs on the Physical Cultural Practices of Young Muslim Women

17:30-19:20

397 Global Sport Practices**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Brent MCDONALD, Victoria University, Australia**Chair:** Sanjay TEWARI, LN Mithila University, India**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****397.1** Anvar NATTUKALLINGAL, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India., India**Finding' Home Grounds' Far Away from Home: Malabari Migrants and Football in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia(KSA).****397.2** Sanjay TEWARI, LN Mithila University, India
Research in Sociology of Sports in India and Possibilities for the Western World**397.3** Octavio MAZA, Universidad Autónoma de Aguascalientes, Mexico**Amateur Sport and Work, a Relationship to Increases Productivity****397.4** Jiaxin LI, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain; Enrique LÓPEZ ADÁN, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain and Alfonso de la RUBIA RIAZA, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain**From the First Step to the Development: The Sustainable Development of Equestrian Policy in China****397.5** Felicia LAZARIDOU, Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, Charité University Medicine, Germany and Tina NOBIS, Department of Integration, Sport and Soccer, Berlin Institute for Empirical Integration and Migration Research - BIM, Humboldt University Berlin, Germany**Racist Stacking in the German Football Bundesliga: A Disruption to the Sports As Social Cohesion Narrative at the Institutional Analysis Level**

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

398 RC27 Business Meeting**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

RC28 Social Stratification

Program Coordinator: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

399 Comparative Analysis of Social Inequalities between Early and Late Industrialized Countries

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide Univ. / AUB, Spain* and Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*

Chair: Emmanuelle BAROZET, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

399.1 Andrew ZOLA, *Sciences Po, France* and Ettore RECCHI, *Sciences Po, Paris, France*
Do You Think You Stand Where You Actually Stand? the Interplay of Subjective and Objective Social Status in Nine Industrialized Countries (2002-2018)

399.2 Joy CHOWDHURI, *Guest Faculty, Delhi School of Economics,, India*
Social Justice through Affirmative Action Policy in Brics Countries: A Sociological Perspective

399.3 Joanna KITSNIK, *Sophia University, Japan*
Bite the Bullet and Carry on? the Robust Role of Individual Beliefs on Enduring Unequal Income Distribution — Evidence from 34 Countries

399.4 Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*; Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Department of Sociology, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain* and Ildelfonso MARQUES-PERALES, *Universidad de Sevilla, Spain*
Social Mobility Under Mutual Index View. a Comparison between Early and Late Industrialized Countries.

399.5 Peng WANG, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Social Mobility during the Transition to the Third Industrial Revolution: A Comparison between the United States and China

399.6 Marcelo BOADO, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*; Rafael REY, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*; Santiago ESCUDER, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay* and Augusto RICARDI, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico*
La Movilidad Social y El Efecto De La Educación En Los Pequeños Países

15:30-17:20

400 Stratification in Early Childhood and Achievements in the Life Course

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Yossi SHAVIT, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*

Chair: Yossi SHAVIT, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

400.1 Marta FACCHINI, *INED, France*; Lidia PANICO, *INED, France* and Carlo BARONE, *Sciences Po, France*
How Does Parents' Employment Uncertainty Affect Children Early Skills Development? Patterns and Mechanisms in France

400.2 Khatia NADARAIA, *Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain*
Socioeconomic Family Background and Major Depressive Disorder at Age 50 and over

400.3 Sylvia NIENHAUS, *Bochum University (Ruhr-Universität Bochum), Germany*
Counteracting Inequalities in Early Childhood - Can Educational Curricula in Kindergarten Do the Job?

17:30-19:20

402 Stratification and Inequality in Diverse Societies

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Chair: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

402.1 Han ZHANG, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
The Intergenerational Legacy of Early-Life Malnutrition during the Great Leap Forward Famine in China

402.2 Indera PATTINASARANY, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
Anxiety, Depression, and Social Class before- and during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia

402.3 Arnie TRINIDAD, *Department of Sociology, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland* and Daniel FAAS, *Trinity College Dublin, Ireland*
In a Liminal Space: Filipino Migrant Nurses in Ireland and Their Conflicting Class Status and Lifestyles

402.4 Serra HATIPOGLU, *Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University, Turkey*; Elizabeth H. BAKER, *The University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA* and Magdalena SZAFIARSKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*
Unfavorable VISA Status and Intersecting Acculturation Factors Linked to Depression

402.5 Hao LIANG, *Cornell University, USA*
Multidirectional Residential Integration: Residential Trajectories of Chinese Immigrants in the Tokyo Metropolis, Japan

402.6 Janet VUOLO, *The Ohio State University, USA* and Michael VUOLO, *The Ohio State University, USA*
Parental Concern and Teacher Recognition of Student Speech and Language Needs: The Role of Fundamental Causes in Schools As a Standardizing Institution

401 Cutting-Edge Research in Social Stratification

Location: Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Chair: Wojtek TOMASZEWSKI, *The University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

401.1 Yurie MOMOSE, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
Does the Impact of Social Exclusion on Health Inequalities Differ between Genders?

401.2 Louis-Andre VALLET, *CNRS, France*
Temporal Dynamics of the Interaction between Education, Class Origin and Class Destination: How It Has Evolved in France Along the Educational Expansion

401.3 Sho FUJIHARA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
Roles of Education in Social Mobility: A Unified Approach

401.4 Akiko YAMAZAKI, *Japan Society for the Promotion of Science, Japan*
Factors in Upward Mobility of the Socio-Economic Hierarchy in Contemporary France: from the Life Stories of 'non-Productive Elites'

401.5 Wataru NAKAZAWA, *Rikkyo University, Japan*
Social Class and Gender in a Solitary Society: The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic in Japan

401.6 Misako NUKAGA, *University of Tokyo, Japan* and Yuiko FUJITA, *Meiji University, Japan*
Dilemmas and Disparities Among Working Mothers in Japan: The Meaning of Paid Work and Mothering Under Neo-Liberal Motherhood Discourse

401.7 Kenji ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan* and James LAURENCE, *Economic and Social Research Institute, Ireland*
Co-Ethnic Neighborhood Quality and the Educational Opportunites: Upper Secondary Education Enrolment in Japan

401.8 Audrey BECK, *San Diego State University, USA*; Joseph GIBBONS, *San Diego State University, USA* and Brian Karl FINCH, *University of Southern California, USA*
Gentrification's Association with Racial/Ethnic-Segregation, Income-Segregation, and Income Inequality in the United States

401.9 Shuhei NAKA, *Meiji Gakuin University, Japan*
Public Attitudes Towards State Support for the Self-Employed during the Covid-19 Crisis in Japan

401.10 Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
Long-Term Impact of Childhood Experience on Life Satisfaction during Adulthood

401.11 Wolfgang LAUTERBACH, *University of Potsdam, Germany*
Educational Expansion and the Family: How Do Family Generational Mobility Patterns Effect Children's Success in Middle Adulthood?

401.12 Hsing-Jung CHEN, *Graduate Institute of Social Work, National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*
Well-Being Among Youth with ACEs in Taiwan's Educational Systems

401.13 Wolfgang LAUTERBACH, *University of Potsdam, Germany*; Steve ENTRICH, *University of Innsbruck, Austria* and Soo-yong BYUN, *Pennstate University, USA*
What Drives Socio-Economic Success in Middle Adulthood in Germany and the USA? an International Comparison of Long-Lasting Impacts of Family Background and Individual Resources in Youth When Controlling for Education

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

403 Experiences and Consciousness of Inequality

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Chair: Ineke MAAS, *Padualaan 14, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

403.1 Pamela ARONSON, *University of Michigan-Dearborn, USA*
How the #MeToo Movement Has Reshaped Discourses about Sexual Consent and Assault

403.2 Robin SAALFELD, *Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena, Germany*
What's Mine Is Yours!? Property Arrangements Among German Couples

403.3 Martin SANCHEZ-JANKOWSKI, *University of California Berkeley, USA* and Corey ABRAMSON, *University of Arizona, USA*
The Social Stratification of Hope: Lessons from Pandemic Times

403.4 Rosario COLLATÓN CHICANA, *Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos, Peru*
Perceptions of Poverty and the Possibilities of Getting out of It in Crisis Contexts

403.5 Galen WATTS, *KU Leuven, Belgium*
From Outer to Inner: Self-Awareness, Therapeutic Discourse, and Emerging Forms of Cultural Capital Among the Millennial Professional Class in Toronto, Canada

10:30-12:20

404 Youth, Young Adults and Stratification

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Chair: Hyunjoon PARK, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

404.1 Mario LUCCHINI, *University of Milano-Bicocca - department of sociology and social research, Italy*; Davide BUSSI, *University of Milano-Bicocca - department of sociology and social research, Italy*; Carlotta PIAZZONI, *University of Milano-Bicocca - department of sociology and social research, Italy* and Serafino NEGRELLI, *University of Milano-Bicocca - department of sociology and social research, Italy*
Transition to Adulthood in Italy in the Last Century. an Empirical Analysis Using Data Coming from Italian Lives (ITA.LI)

404.2 Maximilian SCHIELE, *Institute for Employment Research, Germany* and Louis CHAUVEL, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
Comparing the Effect of Socio-Economic Status on PISA Scores across Different Immigrant Minorities: Is the Effect of SES on Learning Outcomes Due to the Home Environment or Home External Factors?

404.3 Ssu-chin PENG, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan* and Ping-Yin KUAN, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*
The Effect of Parent-Child Discrepancies in Educational Expectation on Adolescents' Mental Health in Taiwan

404.4 Liza REISEL, *PO Box 3233 Elisenberg, Norway*; Atika KHURANA, *College of Education, University of Oregon, USA* and Fartein Ask TORVIK, *Centre for Fertility and Health, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Norway*
Pubertal Maturation and Gender Gaps in Educational Achievement in Norway and the United States

404.5 Fernanda PISMEL, *CNRS Centre Max Weber UMR 5283 - Fernanda PISMEL, France*
More Playgrounds, Police Officers or Other Kids to Play with? Children's Reflections on How to Improve Their Leisure in a Suburb of Curitiba, Brazil.

404.6 Aude BERNARD, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Does Internal Migration Contribute to the Intergenerational Transmission of Socio-Economic Inequalities?

15:30-17:20

405 Global Trends in Education and Stratification

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Claudia BUCHMANN, *The Ohio State University, USA*

Chair: Claudia BUCHMANN, *The Ohio State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

405.1 Satoshi ARAKI, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
The Skills Trap: Explaining the Emerging Inequality in Education, Skills, and Well-Being

405.2 Steve ENTRICH, *University of Innsbruck, Austria* and Soo-yong BYUN, *Pennstate University, USA*
Social Selectivity in Study Abroad from a Comparative Perspective: Impact of National Internationalization Strategies in Germany, Japan and the United States

405.3 Nicola PENSIERO, *University of Southampton, United Kingdom*
Parental Schooling, Educational Attainment, Skills and Earnings: A Trend Analysis across 15 Countries

405.4 Gregor SCHAFFER, *FernUniversität in Hagen, Germany*
Vertical and Horizontal Stratification in Higher Education: Students' Educational Strategies for Institutional Distinction

405.5 Anne SCHIPPLING, *CIES-Iscte, Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology, Portugal* and Pedro ABRANTES, *Universidade Aberta, Portugal*
The Worldwide Spread of the International Baccalaureate: Cosmopolitanism and (Global) Inequalities

17:30-19:20

406 Effects of Disruptive Events

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jennie BRAND, *UCLA, USA*

Chair: Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

406.1 Ravaris MOORE, *New York University, USA*
Heterogeneous Effects of Police Shootings on Crime Reporting Practices and Changing Implicit Sentiment Toward Police

406.2 Rene IWO, *University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, USA*; Elizabeth FRANKENBERG, *University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, USA* and Duncan THOMAS, *Duke University, USA*
Scholastic Dreams: How Does Disaster Damage Impact Educational Aspirations and Outcomes Among Post-Tsunami Youth in Indonesia?

406.3 Yael NAVON, *Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel, Israel*; Carmel BLANK, *Ruppin Academic Center, Israel* and Yossi SHAVIT, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
Time Heals? on the Effects of Death in the Family on Children's Educational Achievements

406.4 Kristin TURNEY, *University of California, Irvine, USA*; Amy Gong LIU, *University of California, Irvine, USA* and Estefani MARIN, *University of California, Irvine, USA*
Stepping in and Stepping Away: Variation in How Children Navigate Responsibilities Stemming from Paternal Incarceration

406.5 Irma MOOI-RECI, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Matthew CURRY, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Parental Joblessness and Children's Personality Traits

19:30-20:50

407 RC28 Business Meeting

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

408 Integrated Data on People, Time, and Places in Research on Social Stratification and Mobility

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Tomasz ZAJAC, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Wojtek TOMASZEWSKI, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Mark WESTERN, *University of Queensland, Australia*

Chair: Tomasz ZAJAC, *The University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

408.1 Ineke MAAS, *Padualaan 14, Netherlands* and Marco H.D. VAN LEEUWEN, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*
Modernization and Career Mobility: A Study of the Netherlands between 1813 and 1922

408.2 Sofie WIERSMA, *University of Groningen, Netherlands*; Anja-Kristin ABENDROTH, *Bielefeld University, Germany*; Zoltan LIPPENYI, *University of Groningen, Netherlands* and Rafael WITTEK, *University of Groningen, Netherlands*

Female CEOs As Agents of Change: The Lasting Impact of Early-Career Imprints

408.3 Marek BOZYKOWSKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*; Agnieszka CHLON-DOMINCZAK, *National Information Processing Institute, Poland* and Mikolaj JASINSKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*

The Men, the Women, and the Virus. Gender Labour Market Inequalities and Their Regional Differences in the Context of COVID-19 Pandemics.

408.4 Chi ZHANG, *Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (Guangzhou), China* and Zhuoni ZHANG, *Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (Guangzhou), China*
Socioeconomic Status and Access to Urban Eldercare Resources: Interrelated Predictors for Elderly's Mental Well-Being

10:30-12:20

409 Multi-Generational Perspective in Social Stratification Research

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Chair: Kenji ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

409.1 Marc SZYDLIK, *University of Zurich, Department of Sociology, Switzerland* and Tamara BOSSHARDT, *University of Zurich, Department of Sociology, Switzerland*
Inequality across Multiple Generations: The Case of Inheritances

409.2 Bhaskar NEOG, *Indian Institute of Technology Jammu, Jammu, India*
Intergenerational Transmission of Human Capital in India: The Role of Gender and the Extended Family

409.3 Aguru ISHIBASHI, *Senshu University, Japan*
Four-Generations Mobility in Japan: The Effects of the Middle Generations' Multiple Traits

409.4 Hirohisa TAKENOSHITA, *Keio University, Japan*; Kayo NOZAKI, *Osaka University of Economics, Japan*; Teruyuki TAMURA, *Tokai University, Japan* and Hideo AKABAYASHI, *Keio University, Japan*
Father's Side or Mother's Side? Lineage Differences in the Role of Grandparental Resources on Grandchildren's Education in Japan

409.5 Andrea HENSE, *Sociological Research Institute Goettingen (SOFI), Germany* and Miriam SCHAD, *Technical University (TU) Dortmund, Germany*
Mentalities and Cross-Generational Strategies of Maintaining the Social Status of Middle Class Families

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

409.6 Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
Educational Reproduction and Mobility across Multiple Generations in Japan

15:30-17:20

410 Social Mobility Using Historical Data

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Per ENGZELL, *University College London, United Kingdom*

Chair: Fumiya UCHIKOSHI, *Princeton University, USA*

Discussant: Ineke MAAS, *Padualaan 14, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

410.1 Fangqi WEN, *Australian National University, Australia*; Erik WANG, *Australian National University, Australia* and Mike HOUT, *New York University, USA*
The Twilight of Chinese Aristocracy: How Family Pedigree, Father's Position, and the Imperial Exam Shaped Social Mobility, 618-907 CE

410.2 Louis HENDERSON, *Jesus College, Oxford, Canada* and Moritz KAISER, *University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom*
'We Don't Need No Education': Human Capital Formation and Social Immobility in Industrialising Coventry, 1790-1850

410.3 Keongsuk PARK, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*; Hee Jin PARK, *Kyung-buk National University, Republic of Korea*; Kwang-Ryeol BAEK, *The Academy of Korean Studies, Republic of Korea*; KyongJin LEE, *SungKyunKwan University, Republic of Korea*; Seung-Min, BAEK, *Ajou University, Republic of Korea*; Jun Sang PARK, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea* and Hyo-Min KIM, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Disaster, Authority, and Selection of Records: Typology of Patrilineal Succession in Joseon Society(1392-1910)

17:30-19:20

411 Schools and Inequality

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Markus KLEIN, *University of Strathclyde, United Kingdom* and Katherin BARG, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*

Chair: Valentina PERINETTI CASONI, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

411.1 Hannah GLINKA, *Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Compositional Effects on Math Competences of Refugee Students in Germany

411.2 Benjamin ROSCHE, *Cornell University, USA* and Michael MACY, *Cornell University, USA*
The Consolidation Paradox. Why SES Disparities By Race Cannot Explain the Racial and SES Segregation in US High School Friendship Networks and What Does.

411.3 Izumi MORI, *Sophia University, Japan*
Does Entrance into Private Junior High School Make an Actual Difference in Students' Learning? a Case in Japan

411.4 Teruki SANADA, *Doshisha University, Japan*
Effect of out-of-School Education in Entering Higher Education: A Focus on Post-Tracking in High Schools

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

412 Racial and Ethnic Inequality

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Yao LU, *Columbia University, USA*

Chair: Lincoln QUILLIAN, *Northwestern University, USA*

Discussant: Kayla THOMAS, *Yale University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

412.1 Tristan IVORY, *Cornell University, USA*; Chuling HUANG, *School of Industrial and Labor Relation, Cornell University, USA* and Guilherme Kenji CHIHAYA, *Nord University, Norway*
Dividing Lines: The Role of Minority Status on Labor Market Outcomes in Latin America and Sub-Saharan Africa

412.2 Erika ARENAS, *University of California Santa Barbara, USA*
Color-Status Exchange: Evidence from Mexico

412.3 Wojtek TOMASZEWSKI, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Tomasz ZAJAC, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Mark WESTERN, *University of Queensland, Australia* and Nikita SHARMA, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Labor Market Outcomes of University Graduates of Migrant Background in Australia: The Relevance of Cultural, Linguistic, and Educational Capital in the Country of Origin

412.4 Magda BORKOWSKA, *University of Essex, United Kingdom* and Neli DEMIREVA, *University of Essex, United Kingdom*
Taking the Long View: Lifecourse Employment Trajectories through the Lens of Ethnicity and Gender.

412.5 Kasimir DEDERICHS, *Nuffield College, University of Oxford, United Kingdom* and Dingeman WIERTZ, *UCL Social Research Institute, University College London, United Kingdom*
Cracks in a Bridge - Ethnic Segregation across and within Voluntary Associations

10:30-12:20

JS-91 Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part I

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC28 Social Stratification

See Joint Session Details for JS-91.

413 Studying Educational Inequality with Big Data and Computational Methods

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Siqi HAN, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Chair: Siqi HAN, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

413.1 Mael LECOURSONNAIS, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Haley MCAVAY, *Sciences Po Paris, France*
The Enduring Influence of Residential Disadvantage on Educational Attainment: Towards a Longitudinal Machine Learning Approach

413.2 Xiaojie XU, *Stockholm University, Sweden*
How Do Women and Men Differ in Their Intergenerational Income Mobility across Cohorts? the Role of Education

413.3 Mael LECOURSONNAIS, *Linköping University, Sweden*; Maria BRANDÉN, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Erik ROSENQVIST, *Linköping University, Sweden*
How Distance to University Impacts Academic Aspirations?

15:30-17:20

JS-100 Family Structure and Social Stratification in Transformation. Part II

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC28 Social Stratification

See Joint Session Details for JS-100.

17:30-19:20

414 Advancing Research on Gender Inequalities: A Life Course Perspective

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Janeen BAXTER, *University of Queensland, Australia*; Alice CAMPBELL, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Rennie LEE, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Leah RUPPANNER, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Janeen BAXTER, *University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

414.1 Andreas WEILAND, *University of Bamberg, Germany*
Gendered Careers and Retirement Incomes of Couples across Europe

414.2 Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
The Gender Gap in Unpaid Work in Later Life in Japan

414.3 Francisco PERALES, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Tomasz ZAJAC, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Wojtek TOMASZEWSKI, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Melissa JOHNSTONE, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Pay Disparities between Male and Female Tertiary-Education Graduates in Australia: Where Is the Gap Greatest?

414.4 Zhenchao QIAN, *Brown University, USA*; Yifan SHEN, *Brown University, Hong Kong* and Susan SHORT, *Brown University, USA*
Educational Hypogamy and Wives' Earnings Advantage? Husbands' and Wives' Earnings Divergence after Marriage

414.5 Audrey AU YONG LYN, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*; Patrick McDONALD, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland* and Louisa ROOS, *Trinity College Dublin, Ireland*
A Country of One's Own: An Intersectional View on Legal Resident Status of Foreign Spouses in Switzerland

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

415 Session on New Developments of Intra- and Intergenerational Social Mobility

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Xi SONG, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*

Chair: Siqi HAN, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

415.1 Kaspar BURGER, *University of Zurich, Switzerland*; Francesca MELE, *University of Zurich, Switzerland*; Jeylan MORTIMER, *University of Minnesota, Department of Sociology, USA* and Xiaowen HAN, *University of Minnesota, Department of Sociology, USA*

The Intergenerational Reproduction of Self-Direction at Work: Revisiting Class and Conformity

415.2 Hunter YORK, *Princeton University, USA*; Xi SONG, *University of Pennsylvania, USA* and Yu XIE, *Princeton University, USA*

Gradationalism Revisited: Intergenerational Occupational Mobility Along Axes of Occupational Characteristics

415.3 Jun XIANG, *Shanghai University, China*; Peng WANG, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Tony TAM, *Department of Sociology, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Intergenerational Closure of Occupational Status in the USA and China: A Tale of Two Regimes

415.4 Luiz Carlos ZALAF CASEIRO, *University of São Paulo, Brazil* and Aguinaldo NOGUEIRA MACIENTE, *International Labour Organization - ILO, Brazil*

Inequalities in Pay and Occupation Among STEM Graduates: What Do Administrative Data from the Brazilian Government Reveal?

415.5 Xavier ST-DENIS, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada* and Edward HADDON, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada*

Obstacles to Transitions between Occupations with Similar Skill Requirements: A Multidimensional Topological Model of Intragenerational Occupational Mobility in the United Kingdom

10:30-12:20

416 Child Development and Educational Inequalities

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Carlo BARONE, *Sciences Po, France*

Co-Chair: Yossi SHAVIT, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

416.1 Kim STIENSTRA, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*
Why Do Some Children Perform Better Than Others? Genetic and Environmental Differences in Learning Growth

416.2 Yossi SHAVIT, *Tel Aviv University, Israel* and Dana SHAY, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
Family Income in Early Childhood and Subsequent Scholastic Achievements in Israel

416.3 Julie PEREIRA, *Sciences Po, France* and Coulangeon PHILIPPE, *CNRS/Sciences Po, France*
Assessing the Efficiency and Redistributive Impact of a Musical Intervention Program in French Pre-Elementary Schools. Lessons from a Quasi-Experiment.

416.4 Han LIU, *University at Albany, USA*
Early Childhood Health, Home Environments, and Educational Achievements

416.5 Katherin BARG, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom* and Valentina PERINETTI CASONI, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
Socioeconomic Bias in Teacher Assessments of Primary School Students: The Mediating Role of Student Attitudes, Student Behaviour and Parental Involvement

417 Stratification and Inequality in Education - the Role of Context

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Hanna AYALON, *Tel Aviv University, Israel* and Louis-Andre VALLET, *French National Centre for Scientific Research - CNRS - Sorbonne University, France*

Chair: Hiroshi ISHIDA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

417.1 Guang GUO, *the university of north carolina at chapel hill, USA*
Socioeconomic and Genomic Roots of Verbal Ability

417.2 Marion FISCHER-NEUMANN, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*
The Role of Older Siblings in the Educational Attainment of Children with and without Migration Background

417.3 Yannie CHEUNG, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Gender Participation in Fields of Academic Study: Global Expansion of Women's Enrollment to Humanities, Natural Sciences and Social Sciences in Higher Education from 1990s to COVID-19 Era

417.4 Fumiya UCHIKOSHI, *Princeton University, USA*
New Gender Segregation through Privatization?: The Role of Private Sectors in Shaping the Underrepresentation of Women in STEM and Selective Colleges in Japan

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

417.5 Laura WIESBOECK, *Institute for Advanced Studies, Austria*
Careers of Female Early-Stage Researchers with Childcare Responsibilities in the COVID19-Pandemic

417.6 Melike AKBIYIK, *Istanbul University Department of Sociology, Turkey*
Career Plans of Sociology Students in Turkey after Pandemic

15:30-17:20

418 Regionally Different? the Relevance of Geo-Spatial Inequalities for Labour Market Outcomes

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Judith OFFERHAUS, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*

Chair: Judith OFFERHAUS, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

418.1 Franziska MEYER, *Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany* and Oliver WINKLER, *Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Place of Residence Does Matter for Educational Integration: The Relevance of Spatial Contexts for Refugees' Transition to VET in Germany

418.2 Linda HOFFMANN, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany* and Alexandra WICHT, *University of Siegen, Germany*
»Should I Stay or Should I Go?« Prevalence and Predictors of Spatial Mobility Among Youth in the Transition to Vocational Education and Training in Germany

418.3 Jonas DETEMPLE, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*
The Gendered Role of Mobility for Adolescents' Status Attainment in Vocational Education and Training (VET)

418.4 Cyril JAYET, *Sorbonne University, France*
Territorial Inequalities, Technological Transformations and Social Mobility in France

17:30-19:20

419 Income Inequality, Class and Consumption

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Celi SCALON, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Jesica PLA, *University of Buenos Aires, Argentina*

Chair: Celi SCALON, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

419.1 Carlo BARONE, *Sciences Po, France*; Florian HERTEL, *University of Hamburg, Germany* and Oscar SMALLENBROEK, *Sciences Po, France*
Social Class and Income Inequalities: Macro, Meso and Micro Level Approaches in Comparative Perspective

419.2 Oscar MAC-CLURE, *Universidad de Los Lagos, Chile*; Emmanuelle BAROZET, *Universidad de Chile, Chile* and Carolina AGUILERA, *Instituto de Ciencias Sociales - ICSO, Chile*
One's Place in Times of Crisis: Social Position According to Class or Other Attributes

419.3 Di ZHU, *Institution of Sociology, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, China* and Shun GONG, *Institute of Sociology, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, China*
Not Spending ≠ Not Willing to Spend —an Empirical Analysis of the Impact of Macro Provision on Consumption

419.4 Alex CHOW, *Stanford University, USA*
The Post-Liberal Social Classes: Actual and Perceived Levels of Income Inequality and Associated Values

419.5 Pia BLOSSFELD, *University of Innsbruck, Austria*; Holger LENGFELD, *Universität Leipzig, Germany* and Florian KLEY, *Leipzig University, Germany*
Changing Middle Class Size in Germany - Based on Different Indicators

419.6 Elisio ESTANQUE, *UNESP-Franca/SP, Brazil*
Middle Class and Identity Struggles in Brazil: A Case in Bahia

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

420 Impact of the Covid Pandemic for Gender Inequality in Work and Family

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Claudia BUCHMANN, *The Ohio State University, USA*

Chair: Claudia BUCHMANN, *The Ohio State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

420.1 Joanna SIKORA, *Australian National University, Australia*
Negotiating a Mid-Stage STEM Career in Times of COVID-19: Reflections of Female-Identifying STEM Professionals

420.2 Aida VILLANUEVA, *University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA*
Mothers' Paid Labor and Household Dynamics in the Context of the COVID-19 Pandemic: Evidence from a High-Mortality Context

420.3 Marita JACOB, *Institute of Sociology and Social Psychology (ISS), Germany*; Lina TOBLER, *University of Cologne, Institute of Sociology and Social Psychology, Germany*; Lukas FEVERS, *University of Cologne, Institute of Sociology and Social Psychology, Germany*; Veronika KNIZE, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany* and Bernhard CHRISTOPH, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany*
When the Burden Lifts: The Effect of School and Day Care Re-Openings on Parents' Employment and Life Satisfaction

10:30-12:20

421 Innovation in Sociological Research of Gender and Socio-Economic Policies

Location: 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Chair: Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

421.1 Natalie NITSCHKE, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany* and Ansgar HUDDE, *University of Cologne, Germany*
Countries Embracing Maternal Employment Have Opened Schools Sooner after COVID-19 Lockdowns

421.2 Jos SLABBEKOORN, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*; Ineke MAAS, *Padualaan 14, Netherlands* and J. Cok VROOMAN, *The Netherlands Institute for Social Research | SCP & Utrecht University, Netherlands*
Benefit Receipt at the Intersection of Gender, Age and Migration Background: The Role of Economic, Social, Cultural, and Person Capital

421.3 Yuliya KOSYAKOVA, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany* and Zerrin SALIKUTLUK, *Humboldt University Berlin, Germany*
Gender Gap Dynamics Among Refugees and Recent Immigrants: Different Start, Different Patterns?

421.4 Ji CAO, *the Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Ling ZHU, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Occupational Gender Segregation, Intra-Occupation Inequality, and Gender Wage Gap Dynamics in the United States: A Causal Mediation Approach

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

421.5 Irma MOOI-RECI, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Meir YAISH, *University of Haifa, Israel* and Lyn CRAIG, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Does Parental Education Shape Gender Wage Gaps over the Life Course? New Insights from Australia

12:30-14:20

422 Immigration, Integration, and Attitudes Toward Immigrants**Location:** 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Yao LU, *Columbia University, USA***Chair:** Zai LIANG, *State University of New York at Albany, USA***Discussant:** Zai LIANG, *State University of New York at Albany, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

422.1 Lincoln QUILLIAN, *Northwestern University, USA* and Arnfinn H. MIDTBOEN, *University of Oslo, Norway*
Race or Immigrant Status? a Meta-Analysis of Field Experiments of Discrimination Against Foreign-Born and Native-Born Minorities in 13 Countries

422.2 Tristan IVORY, *Cornell University, USA*; Guilherme Kenji CHIHAYA, *Nord University, Norway*; Ly TRAN, *Deakin University, Australia* and George TAN, *Adelaide University, Australia*
Degrees of Unfreedom: Foreign-Born University Graduate Labor Market Outcomes in Australia, Sweden, and the United States

422.3 Weiqian XIA, *Stockholm University, Sweden*; Jani TURUNEN, *Sodertorn University, Sweden*; Jan SAARELA, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland* and Siddartha ARADHYA, *Stockholm University, Sweden*
The Returns to Returning – Economic Returns to Remigration to Finland with Sibling Comparison Design

422.4 Judith KOHLENBERGER, *Vienna University of Economics and Business, Austria*; Isabella BUBER-ENNSER, *Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria*; Bernhard RENGES, *Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria*; Ingrid SETZ, *Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria*; Olena TARASIUK, *IIASA, Austria*; Ekaterina PRONIZIUS, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Konrad PEDZIWIATR, *Cracow University of Economics, Poland*
Ukrainian Refugees in Vienna and in Kraków

14:30-16:20

423 Social Stratification Research in the Aging Population**Location:** 110 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan***Chair:** Mark WESTERN, *University of Queensland, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

423.1 Tatiana BARANOWSKAYA, *Russian State University for the Humanities, Russian Federation*

Social Distance and Inclusion: Features of Integration of the Elderly

423.2 Pei-Chun KO, *Monash University, Australia*; Changmin PENG, *University of Massachusetts Boston, USA* and Jeffrey BURR, *University of Massachusetts Boston, USA*
Examining Socially Productive Activities Among Older Adults in Urban China: The Role of Household Registration System- Hukou

423.3 Sawako SHIRAHASE, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
The Intergenerational Conflict Reconsidered: Focusing on the Intention of Wealth Transfer from Parents to Children

423.4 Khatia NADARAIA, *Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain*
Cognitive Aging Trajectories of People Aged 50 and over in European Countries

RC29

Deviance and Social Control

Program Coordinators: Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de México, Mexico*; Paul HATHAZY, *Universidad Nacional de Cordoba, Argentina* and Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

424 Criminal Organizations, Drugs and the Youth

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Nirmal CHAKRABARTI, *West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, India*

Chair: Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*

Discussant: Teresa NAVARRETE, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

424.1 Teresa NAVARRETE, *344617, Mexico*
Life Histories of Young People Who Have Participated in Organized Crime Groups

424.2 Ethan MOORE, *University of St Andrews, United Kingdom*
A New Framework for Understanding Cryptomarket Participants

424.3 Pedro CAMARGOS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
The War on Organized Crime after Redemocratization in Brazil: From Human Rights Discourse to Militarization of Security

424.4 Emilio AYOS, *Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani (FSOC-UBA), Argentina*; Tatiana JACK, *Facultad de Ciencias Sociales Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina* and Guadalupe LÓPEZ, *Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani - Facultad de Ciencias Sociales - Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
The Reorientation of Interventions Towards Young People in the Context of Pandemics and the Issue of Police Violence. Analysis of the "Enviñ" Programme (Argentina, 2020-2021)

424.5 Lina OLSSON, *Växjö Municipality, Sweden*; Belinda FÄRDIG, *Arabo family therapy, Sweden* and Goran BASIC, *Linnaeus University, Sweden*
Interactions of Power and Social Pedagogical Recognition: An Analysis of Narratives of Pupils Who Use Alcohol and Drugs in an Upper-Secondary School Context in Sweden

15:30-17:20

425 Policing and Punishment in Global Perspective

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Mariana POSSAS, *Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), Brazil* and Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de México, Mexico*

Chair: Nirmal CHAKRABARTI, *West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, India*

Discussant: Emeka OBIOHA, *Walter Sisulu University, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

425.1 Ariadne NATAL, *Peace Research Institute Frankfurt (PRIF), Brazil*
Determinants of Police Lethality in Brazil

425.2 Emeka OBIOHA, *Walter Sisulu University, South Africa*
Barriers to Accessing the Criminal Justice Services in Post-Apartheid South Africa: Reflections on the Policing System

425.3 Antonio FUENTES DIAZ, *Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla, Mexico*
Las Armas De La Paz: El Efecto Pacificador De La Defensa Comunitaria En El Sur De México

425.4 Rodrigo AZEVEDO, *Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil* and Fernanda VASCONCELLOS, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Deciphering the Sphinx: Police and Criminal Justice in the Face of Authoritarian Temptation

17:30-19:20

426 Comparative Juvenile Correctional Education: Toward the Transcendence of Globalized Penal Populism

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Yasukiyo SUGIMOTO, *University of Miami, USA* and Carolina GONZALEZ LAURINO, *Universidad de la Republica, Uruguay*

Chair: Yasukiyo SUGIMOTO, *University of Miami, USA*

Discussant: Yasukiyo SUGIMOTO, *University of Miami, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

426.1 Teemu VAUHKONEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Evaluation of a Finnish Youth Crime Intervention Model

426.2 Stavroola ANDERSON, *Australasian Corrections Education Association, Australia*; Helen FARLEY, *Australasian Corrections Education Association, New Zealand* and Jocelyn HUMBLEY, *Australasian Corrections Education Association, Australia*
Empathy through Education

426.3 Marília RAMOS, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*; Leticia SCHABBACH, *UFRGS, Brazil*; Melissa DE MATTOS PIMENTA, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*; Ana Paula Motta COSTA, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil* and Aline HELLMANN, *Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
The Implementation of the National Socio-Educational Assistance System (SINASE) to Assist Young Brazilian Offenders

426.4 Driss HARRASS, *Ryukoku University Criminology Research Center, Japan*
Understanding the Ongoing Get Tough Movement Regarding Juvenile Justice Practice in France and Japan – Tracking a Common Direction of Change

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

427 Prison, Penitentiary Studies and Human Rights

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jacqueline SINHORETTO, *Federal University of Sao Carlos, Brazil* and Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Mary Luz SANDOVAL ROBAYO, *Universidad de Caldas, Colombia*

Discussant: Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

427.1 Parishmita DUTTA, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India*
Impacts of COVID-19 Pandemic in Prison Administration System: Mitigation Strategies of Indian States and Union Territories Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Prison Administration System: Mitigation Strategies of Indian States and Union Territories

427.2 Sultan KHAN, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*
The Role of Faith Based Organisations (FBOs) in the Rehabilitation of Offenders

427.3 Teresa CONSOLI, *University of Catania, Italy*; Daniela FERRARELLO, *University of Catania, Italy* and Fabrizio SIRACUSANO, *University of Catania, Italy*
The Role of University in Prison: A Study on Italian Institutions

427.4 Chukwunwike NWANGWU, *Carmelite Prisoners' Interest Organisation (CAPIO) Nigeria, Nigeria*; Uchenna Clara INNOCENT, *Department of Psychological Medicine, University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Nigeria* and Amarachi MABIA, *Department of Sociology and Anthropology Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria*
Stakeholders Perspective on Correctional Officers' Attitude As Predictors to Recidivism in Maximum Security Custodial Center in Southeast, Nigeria: A Qualitative Analysis

427.5 Maneesha MISHRA, *KIIT, India*
Combating Green Crimes in India: Analysing the Role of Wildlife Forensics through the Perspective of Green Criminology

427.6 Ines DURAN MATUTE, *CIESAS, Mexico* and Rodrigo CAMARENA, *Instituto Tecnológico Autónomo de México, Mexico*
Bears and Rivers As Rights Holders: Between Capitalist Fetishization and Ambivalent Instrumentality

15:30-17:20

428 Policing, Violence and Public Security in a Global Perspective

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Ariadne NATAL, *Peace Research Institute Frankfurt (PRIF), Brazil*

Discussant: Nirmal CHAKRABARTI, *West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

428.1 Nirmal CHAKRABARTI, *West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, India* and Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*
Smart Policing in India: Quandaries to Urban Transformation

428.2 Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*
Police Strategies after Pandemic. between Abusive Authoritarianism and Community Approaches Estrategias Policiales Después De La Pandemia Covid 19: Entre El Autoritarismo Abusivo y El Acercamiento a Los Ciudadanos

428.3 Hina FAZAL, *Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan* and Muhammad ASIF, *Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan*
Justification and Legitimacy of Police Violence: A Cultural Explanation

428.4 Sergio ADORNO, *Apartamento 32, Brazil*
Organized Crime, Public Opinion Makers and Police Organizations in Contemporary Brazil

19:30-20:50

429 RC29 Business Meeting

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

430 Social Violence, Urban Studies and Cybercrime

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Mary Luz SANDOVAL ROBAYO, *Universidad de Caldas, Colombia* and Miguel Angel VITE PEREZ, *Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, Mexico*

Chair: Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

430.1 Yuetong ZHAO, *Sichuan Academy of social sciences, China* and Jianxing BAI, *Fudan University, China*
Interpretation of Foucault's Micro Power Thought: Take the Documentary "Ermao" As an Example

430.2 Miguel Angel VITE PEREZ, *UAM/IPN, Mexico* and Altamirano Santiago Mijael ALTAMIRANO, *IPN, Mexico*
La Desigualdad Social Espacial ¿Causa De La Violencia Social Urbana?

430.3 Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*
ICTs in Risk Management: An Appraisal of Urban Policing in India

430.4 Markus KAAKINEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland* and Teemu VAUHKONEN, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Cybercriminal Communities: Online Communities and the Development of Young People's Cybercriminal Behavior

430.5 Suleman LAZARUS, *The Mannheim Centre for Criminology, London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE), United Kingdom*; Mark BUTTON, *Director of Centre for Counter Fraud Studies at University of Portsmouth, United Kingdom* and Afe ADOGAME, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*
Advantageous Comparison: Using Twitter Responses to Understand Similarities between Cybercriminals ("Yahoo Boys") and Politicians ("Yahoo men")

10:30-12:20

431 Insecurities, Violence and Democracy in the Global South

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jose Alfredo ZAVALETA, *Universidad de Veracruz, Mexico*

Chair: Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

431.1 Mary Luz SANDOVAL ROBAYO, *Universidad de Caldas, Colombia*
Violencia e Izquierda Democrática En Colombia: Las Elecciones De 2022

431.2 Sergio ADORNO, *Apartamento 32, Brazil*
New Facts and New Meanings of Violence in Contemporary Brazilian Society: Hatred, Cruelty, Intolerance, Radicalism

431.3 Gabriel TENENBAUM EWIG, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*
Los Protectores Del Capital: Los Servicios Que Brinda Uruguay Al Tráfico Internacional De Las Drogas Ilegales.

431.4 Jose Alfredo ZAVALETA, *Universidad de Veracruz, Mexico*
Las Arenas Públicas En Torno Del Corredor Del Istmo De Tehuantepec, México

431.5 Emilio AYOS, *Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani (FSOC-UBA), Argentina* and Tatiana JACK, *Facultad de Ciencias Sociales Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Young People, Work and Education: Perspectives and Problematizations on the Question of Insecurity in Post-Pandemic Argentina (2021-2022)

431.6 Erick GALAN-CASTRO, *Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología, Mexico*
Los Colectivos De Familiares De Desaparecidos y La Construcción De Paz En Veracruz. Oportunidades y Estrategias De Acción Colectiva.

15:30-17:20

432 Drugs, Organized Crime and Illicit Markets

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Vincenzo SCALIA, *University of Winchester, United Kingdom*

Chair: Miguel Angel VITE PEREZ, *Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, Mexico*

Discussant: Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

432.1 Scott DUXBURY, *University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, USA* and Dana HAYNIE, *Ohio State University, USA*
Embedded Risks: Network Trade Structure and Drug Purchasing Trajectories on a Darknet Drug Market

432.2 Andre SARLI, *University of Geneva, Switzerland*
The Digital Cartel? Experiences of Marginalized Teenagers in Brazil with Drug Cartels through Social Media

432.3 Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
Exception, Policing and Executive Power during the Ottawa Occupation By Freedom Convoy Protesters

432.4 Pamela Irving JACKSON, *Rhode Island College, USA*
Storming the Capital: Hate Crimes, Far-Right Domestic Terrorism, and Democratic Backsliding in the U.S., Canada and Europe

432.5 Gustavo HIGA, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*; Roberta NOVELLO, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*; Pedro CALLARI TRIVINO MOISES, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil* and Felipe GARCIA, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*
The History of Authoritarianism Repertoire in Brazilian Academic Debate (1970-2000)

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

433 Gender Violence: Atrocities on Women and Other Vulnerable Groups in Covid Era

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Mariana POSSAS, *Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), Brazil* and Arpita MITRA, *KIIT School of Law, India*

Chair: Arturo ALVARADO MENDOZA, *El Colegio de Mexico, Mexico*

Discussant: Maneesha MISHRA, *KIIT, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

433.1 Thierry DELPEUCH, *CNRS, France*; Paul HERBINGER, *VICESSE | Vienna Centre for Societal Security, Austria*; Jarmo HOUTSONEN, *POLAMK, Finland* and Norbert LEONHARDMAIR, *VICESSE | Vienna Centre for Societal Security, Austria*
Fight Against Domestic Violence and the 2020 COVID-19 Lockdown in the European Union

433.2 Gyanendra YADAV, PATLIPUTRA UNIVERSITY, India
The COVID-19 Pandemic and Violence Against Women in India: A Sociological Interpretation.

433.3 Maria Isabella CRISTEA, Public University of Navarre, Spain
Intimate Partner Violence in the Spanish Digital Press

433.4 Yashfeen ADIL, Jadavpur University, India
Veiled Muslim Women and Agency: A Study of the Swadhinta Andolan 2.0 in Kolkata, India

433.5 Jhilli MOHAPATRA, Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences-Deemed to be University, India
Women Employees in Hospital Sector : A Study on Techno-Stress during Covid 19 Pandemic in a Super Speciality Hospital in Bhubaneswar, India

RC30

Sociology of Work

Program Coordinators: Maria Eugenia LONGO, *Institut National de la Recherche Scientifique, Canada*; Flora BAJARD, *CNRS-LEST, France*; Delphine MERCIER, *Laboratoire d'Economie et de Sociologie du Travail, AMU CNRS, France*; Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia* and Guzel BAIMURZINA, *Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

434 The Frontiers of Work and in Work.

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Delphine MERCIER, *UMR 7317 CNRS - Aix-Marseille Université, France* and Martin PONTIER, *Laboratoire d'Economie et de Sociologie du Travail, France*

Chair: Delphine MERCIER, *UMR 7317 CNRS - Aix-Marseille Université, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

434.1 Premilla D'CRUZ, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India* and Ernesto NORONHA, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India*
Co-Working with a Dolly Trolley: A Case of Human-Robot Interaction in Indian Restaurants

434.2 Klara OBERG, *Halmstad University, Sweden*
The Multiplication of Borders - an Example from the Construction Sector

434.3 Erynn CASANOVA, *University of Cincinnati, USA*
Pathways through Poverty: The Labor Trajectories of Domestic Workers in Ecuador

434.4 Brendan CHURCHILL, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Gendering the Gig Economy

434.5 Nobuko HOSOGAYA, *Sophia University, Japan* and Noriko ARAI, *Sophia university, Japan*
Reintegration of Japanese Female Repatriates' Host Country Experiences and Their Career Prospects in Labor Market at Home

15:30-17:20

435 Work and Employment Key Issues in Australia and Oceania

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada* and Flora BAJARD, *LEST Institute of Labour Economics and Industrial Sociology, France*

Chair: Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

435.1 Nareen YOUNG, *University of Technology Sydney - Jumbunna Institute for Indigenous Education and Research, Australia*
Redefining 'Indigenous Employment' in Indigenous Terms

435.2 Darryn SNELL, *RMIT University, Australia*
Work in Transition in Australia

435.3 Nerida SPINA, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Kathleen SMITHERS, *Charles Sturt University, Australia* and Jess HARRIS, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Gig Work and Employment Relations in Academia

435.4 Elizabeth HUMPHRYS, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Climate Change: Work Health and Safety, Green Jobs, and Just Transitions

435.5 Roger PATULNY, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
The State of Personal and Interpersonal Emotional Labour in Australia: Results from a National Survey

435.6 Tom BARRATT, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
Connecting the Regulation and Sociology of Gig-Work in Australia

17:30-19:20

JS-20 International Migration and Economic Informalization : A Denationalized Perspective - Part I

Committees: RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC02 Economy and Society and RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-20.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

436 Work Precarities in the Global South, Part I.

Language: English, Spanish

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Dasten JULIAN, *Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile* and Sandra GUIMENEZ, *IESCO-UNPAZ - UBA, Argentina*

Chair: Dasten JULIAN, *Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

436.1 Dahiana AYALA, *Laboratoire d'Économie et de Sociologie du Travail, France* and Annie LAMANTHE, *Laboratoire d'Économie et de Sociologie du Travail, France*
Mercado Laboral Informal En Paraguay: Una Aproximación a Los Empleos Segmentados y Heterogéneos

436.2 Tatiana KARABCHUK, *UAE University, United Arab Emirates* and Aizhan SHOMOTOVA, *UAU, United Arab Emirates*
Labour Market in the UAE: Moving Towards Decent Work?

436.3 Daniel AMOAH, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Ghana in the Age of Cities: Exploring Critical Challenges to the Urban Informal Sector

436.4 Betina FREIDIN, *Universidad de Buenos Aires y CONICET, Argentina*; Matías BALLESTEROS, *University of Buenos Aires and CONICET, Argentina*; Agustín WILNER, *Universidad de Buenos Aires y CONICET, Argentina* and Josefina ROQUES, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Experiencias De Precariedad Laboral y Sus Vínculos Con La Salud En Varones Adultos De Clase Popular Del Conurbano De Buenos Aires, Argentina

436.5 Mariana FERNANDEZ MASSI, *IDIHCS (CONICET/ Universidad de La Plata), Argentina*; Marina ADAMINI, *Instituto de Geografía, Historia y Ciencias Sociales (IGEHC) - CONICET, Argentina* and Julieta LONGO, *Instituto de Investigaciones en Humanidades y Ciencias Sociales (IDIHCS) - CONICET/UNLP, Argentina*
El Empleo Típico Como Norma En Argentina: Discursos, Estadísticas y Normativas

436.6 Eileen OTIS, *Northeastern University, USA*
From Partner to Bully: The Rise of Precarity in China's Walmart Retail Stores

10:30-12:20

437 Estudios Del Trabajo En América Latina. Algunos Ejes Temáticos En Un Cambio De Época

Language: English, Spanish

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Flora BAJARD, *LEST Institute of Labour Economics and Industrial Sociology, France* and Dasten JULIAN, *Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile*

Chair: Dasten JULIAN, *Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

437.1 Antonio ARAVENA, *Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile*
Los Estudios Sindicales En Chile: Debates Epistemológicos y Teóricos.

437.2 Omar MANKY, *Universidad del Pacífico, Peru*
Trabajo y Medio Ambiente: Mapeando La Discusión En América Latina

437.3 Ricardo ANTUNES, *UNICAMP (Campinas), Brazil*
Nuevos Laboratorios De Experimentaciones Del Trabajo En El Capitalismo Pandémico

437.4 Tania AILLON, *Instituto de Estudios Sociales y Económicos de la Universidad Mayor de San Simón (Cochabamba), Bolivia*
Sobre El Crecimiento De La "Informalidad" En La Era De La Digitalización De Los Procesos Productivos

15:30-17:20

JS-42 International Migration and Economic Informalization: A Denationalized Perspective - Part II

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work (Host)*; RC02 *Economy and Society* and RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-42.

17:30-19:20

JS-50 Navigating the Other Side of the Classroom: Exploring Teachers' Experiences at Work

Committees: RC04 *Sociology of Education (Host)*; RC30 *Sociology of Work*

See Joint Session Details for JS-50.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-59 Language and Work: The Post-Pandemic Evolutions of Categorizations Toward (Un) Employment and Working Conditions

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work (Host)*; RC25 *Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-59.

10:30-12:20

438 Implications of Authoritarian Policies on Workers and Labor Precariousness

Language: English, Spanish

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Tania GARCIA-RAMOS, *Universidad de Puerto Rico, PR*

Chair: Tania GARCIA-RAMOS, *Universidad de Puerto Rico, PR*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

438.1 Qiong (Miranda) WU, *Central European University, Austria*
Hukou and Labor Precariousness between the State and Market Sectors in Contemporary China

438.2 Virgen CACERES CRUZ, *University of Puerto Rico, PR*
Implications of Authoritarian Neoliberal Labor Policies in Puerto Rico

438.3 Jason LIN, *School of Foreign Languages, Renmin University of China, China* and Shaozhi ZHONG, *School of Economics, Renmin University of China, China*
Slaughter for Living: A Study on Massive Family-Based Butcher Migrants' Welfare Conditions in Beijing

438.4 S. m. anowarul kayes SHIMUL, *East West University, Bangladesh*
How the Ready-Made Garment Workers of Bangladesh Mobilise Protest Movements at the Verge of Union Extinction?

438.5 Rebeca CENA, *CONICET/CONFINES, Argentina*
"a Tientas": Experiencias De Receptores De Políticas Sociales De Empleo

15:30-17:20

JS-73 Femmes Migrantes Sur Le Marché Du Travail Subalterne/Migrant Women in the Subaltern Labor Market

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-73.

17:30-19:20

439 Workers, Precarity and Exploitation of the “Post-Work” Era in Africa**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia* and Ellison TJIRERA, *University of Namibia, Namibia***Chair:** Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****439.1** Crispin CHINGUNO, *Sol Plaatje University, South Africa*
Platform Economy Contested Spatial Fixes in Johannesburg**439.2** Daniel AMOAH, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Exploring the Experience of Tax Payment in the Urban Informal Economy in Ghana**439.3** Ruth CASTEL-BRANCO, *Southern Centre for Inequality Studies, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*
Beyond Post-Work Utopias: Recentring Production within Distributive Politics**439.4** Kolawole OMOMOWO, *University of Namibia, Namibia*
The Unions Are Afraid? Trade Unions Perspective on Minimum Wages in the Contexts of Unemployment, Poverty and Inequality**439.5** Adou APPIAH, *Departement d'anthropologie et de sociologie, Côte D'Ivoire*
Syndicalisme Et Résilience Ouvrière : Quand Les Militants Se Défendent Eux-Mêmes

19:30-20:50

440 RC30 Business Meeting**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Thursday 29 June**

08:30-10:20

JS-88 Women in an Occupational Gender Segregation Global Labor Market**Committees:** RC32 *Women, Gender and Society (Host)*; RC30 *Sociology of Work*

See Joint Session Details for JS-88.

10:30-12:20

441 Uncertainty and Inequality: The Long-Term Effects of the Pandemic on Workers Careers and Experiences**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Marco ALBERIO, *Université du Québec à Rimouski, Canada* and Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada***Chair:** Marco ALBERIO, *Université du Québec à Rimouski, Italy***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****441.1** Meraiah FOLEY, *University of Sydney Business School, Australia*
Does Working from Home Mean Working All the Time? Technology-Enabled Work Intensification in the Legal Profession Post-COVID**441.2** Patricia VENDRAMIN, *University of Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium*
Effects of the Pandemic on the Value of Work for Young People**441.3** Edward HADDON, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada* and Xavier ST-DENIS, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada*
Longitudinal Trends in Perceived Financial and Labour Market Insecurity Among Gig-Workers in the United States during the COVID-19 Pandemic.**441.4** Tania GARCIA-RAMOS, *University of Puerto Rico, PR*; Virgen CACERES CRUZ, *University of Puerto Rico, PR* and Katherine RIVERA RODRÍGUEZ, *University of Puerto Rico, PR*
Labor and Social Impact of COVID-19 on Women in the Global South**441.5** Wen FAN, *Boston College, USA* and Phyllis MOEN, *University of Minnesota, USA*
The Future(s) of Work? Disparities Around Changing Job Conditions When Remote/Hybrid or Returning to Working at Work**441.6** Guven SAVUL, *The Confederation Turkish Trade Unions, Turkey*
A Wolf in Sheep's Clothing: The Risks of Remote Work for the Future of Labor**441.7** Saman RASHID, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden* and Anna OLOFSSON, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*
Rising Inequalities in the Wake of the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Study of Foreign Born's Labour Market Situation 2019-2022

15:30-17:20

442 The Grey Areas of Vulnerabilities in the World of Work**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia***Chair:** Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****442.1** Catherine ORIAN WEISS, *RMIT University, Australia*
Social Reproduction Theory and the Position of Wigrant Women in the Subaltern Labour Market**442.2** Wen-Jui HAN, *New York University, USA*
Work Schedule Patterns and Health over Thirty Years of Working Lives in the United States: NLSY79 Cohort**442.3** Zoe BAKER, *University of York, United Kingdom*
'I Do Feel like Employers Do Look at You Differently': Inequalities in Access to Professional Employment for Care-Experienced Graduates**442.4** Laura Isabel SCHOGER, *University of Hanover, Germany*
The Role of Education in Coping with Work-Related Stressors

17:30-19:20

443 Current Theoretic and Methodologic Challenges in Sociology of Work**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Guzel BAIMURZINA, *Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation* and Andrei POPOV, *Vologda Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences (VoIRC RAS), Russian Federation***Chair:** Guzel BAIMURZINA, *Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****443.1** Bongwiwe MNCWANGO, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
Job Satisfaction: An Underdeveloped Concept in the South African Sociology of Work**443.2** Linda GIBSON, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom* and Robert DINGWALL, *Dingwall Enterprises Ltd, United Kingdom*
Community Health Workers in Uganda and the Division of Labour: An Analysis of the Structural Barriers to the Genesis of an Occupation**443.3** Peter ROBERT, TARKI, *Inc, Hungary*
Excluded from Work, Excluded from Politics? Young People's Integration at Work and Engagement in Political Participation**443.4** Lisa MORAN, *South East Technological University, Ireland* and Lorraine GREEN, *Edge Hill University, UK, United Kingdom*
Exploring the Multidimensionality of Veterinarian's Communications in the UK and Ireland: Knowledge, Cultural Scripts and Power in Large and Small Animal Veterinary Clinics**443.5** Irina GRIGORYEVA, *State University of Saint Petersburg, Russian Federation*
Socially-Oriented Npos and Social Enterprises As Drivers of Denationalization in Social Services: Barriers and Opportunities**Friday 30 June**

08:30-10:20

444 Conflicts and Normative Transactions in Multicultural Work Contexts**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Bernard FUSULIER, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium* and Diane-Gabrielle TREMBLAY, *Teluq, Canada***Chair:** Bernard FUSULIER, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****444.1** Merle JACOBS, *York University, Canada*
Is There Equity in Multiculturalism? Racism in the Work Environment -Nursing As an Example**444.2** Charlotte CORCHETE, *Sciences Po (CRIS), France*
The Role of Human Skills in Multicultural Tensions at Work: The Case of France**444.3** Anne GILLET, *CNAM-LISE-CNRS, France* and Diane-Gabrielle TREMBLAY, *University of Quebec (Teluq), Canada*
Intercultural Work in the Sky. Rules, Relations and Cultures**444.4** Carole YEROCHEWSKI, *CRIMT Université de Montréal, Canada*
Systemic Racism and Authoritarian Management: Differentiated Experiences According to Social Relationships in Terms of Qualification/Gender/Race

10:30-12:20

445 Transformation of Industrial Relations and Emerging Organization: Digital, Rationalization and Storage Industry.**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Delphine MERCIER, *UMR 7317 CNRS - Aix-Marseille Université, France*; David GABORIEAU, *Lab'URBA, ANR WORKLOG, France* and Carlotta BENVENEGNU, *LEST/CRESPPA, France***Chair:** Delphine MERCIER, *UMR 7317 CNRS - Aix-Marseille Université, France***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****445.1** Laura GOOD, *University of Sydney, Australia*
The Experience of Digitalisation in a Feminised Industry: Retail Workers and the Future of Work**445.2** Francesco IANNUZZI, *"Ca' Foscari" University of Venice, Italy*; Guglielmo MEARDI, *Scuola Normale Superiore - Firenze, Italy*; Devi SACCHETTO, *University of Padua, Italy* and Nicola QUONDAMATTEO, *Scuola Normale Superiore - Firenze, Italy*
Differentiated Factory Regimes: Transformations of Labour and Workplace Politics in the Italian Shipbuilding Industry**445.3** Eileen OTIS, *Northeastern University, USA*
Realization Labor: Labor Regimes and the Movement of Goods at the End of the Supply Chain**445.4** Hongzheng PAN, *London School of Economics and Political Science, China*
Platform Riders Under COVID-19 in Mainland China**445.5** Tomoko FUKUDA, *Chiba University, Japan*
Agglomeration/Dispersion of Used Car and Used Auto Parts Trade Industries By South Asian Migrant Entrepreneurs in Japan

15:30-17:20

446 Traditional and New Mechanisms of Social Protection of Workers**Location:** P2 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Guzel BAIMURZINA, *Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation* and Andrei POPOV, *Vologda Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences (VoIRC RAS), Russian Federation***Chair:** Andrei POPOV, *Vologda Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences (VoIRC RAS), Russian Federation*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

446.1 Ilana NUSSBAUM BITRAN, *Universität Bremen, Germany* and Irene DINGELDEY, *University of Bremen, Germany*
The Posted Workers Directive – Social Protection of Workers Under Transnational European Solidarity?

446.2 Boyeong JEONG, *the Sinchon Centre for Cultural Politics, Republic of Korea*
A Study of the Diffusion Process of Youth Job-Seeking Subsidy in South Korea: Using Fuzzy Set Ideal Type Analysis to Assess Governance Strategies of Youth Movement

446.3 Klaus SCHMIERL, *Institute for Social Science Research, Germany*
Threats for Works Councils and Trade Unions in the Logistics Sector

446.4 Shintaro MATSUNAGA, *Nagano University, Japan*
Why Do Freelance Animators Belong to a Firm?: Manufacturing Consent with “Schedule Gifts” and Its Ambivalence in the Japanese Animation Industry

446.5 Nelly ROMANOVICH, *The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration (RANEPA), Russian Federation*
Survival Skills of Russian Entrepreneurs Against the Backdrop of a Crisis

446.6 Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia* and Emma NANGOLO, *Independent scholar, Namibia*
An Analysis of Jobs and Livelihoods Affected By Covid-19 Pandemic: A Social Protection Perspective

17:30-19:20

447 Understanding Care Work in a Context of Crisis: Health, Risks and Labour Conflicts

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Isil ERDINC, *Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium* and Maria Cecilia TRIONFETTI, *Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium*

Chair: Flora BAJARD, *LEST Institute of Labour Economics and Industrial Sociology, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

447.1 Kanu PRIYA, *Indian Institute of Technology, India*
The Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Home Care Workers: A Study of New Delhi

447.2 Cyrine GARDES, *Center for the Sociology of Organizations (Sciences Po Paris), France*; Émilie BILAND-CURINIER, *Center for the Sociology of Organizations (Sciences Po Paris), France* and Jérôme PÉLISSE, *Center for the Sociology of Organizations (Sciences Po Paris), France*
Does Remote Social Work Increase Labor Conflicts? Evidence from Social Workers' Pandemic Experiences in France

447.3 Isabelle RUELLAND, *University of Quebec in Montreal UQAM, Canada*
Citizen Care Workers in Public Health: Critical Reflection Based on Research on Community Outreach Practices on COVID-19 in Disadvantaged Neighbourhoods in Canada

447.4 Sven SVENSSON, *University of Gävle, Sweden*; Annika STRÖMBERG, *University of Gävle, Sweden*; Birgitta WIITAVAARA, *University of Gävle, Sweden* and David HALLMAN, *University of Gävle, Sweden*
Preconditions to Follow Hygiene Routines Among Temporary Aged Care Workers in Sweden during and after COVID-19

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

448 Post-Pandemic Possibilities for Workplace Change

Language: English, Spanish

Location: P2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Helen SAMPSON, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom* and Jose RAMALHO, *UFRJ, Brazil*

Chair: Helen SAMPSON, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

448.1 Rodrigo SANTOS, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Ana Paula VASCONCELOS GONÇALVES, *Universidade Federal do Maranhão, Brazil*
How Decent Is Work in the Automotive Production Network? An Operational Typology of Quality of Work in a Brazilian Region

448.2 Jens THOEMMES, *Université Toulouse-Jean Jaurès, France*
Collective Bargaining of Distant Work in France and Germany

448.3 Maria BRIDI, *Federal University of Paraná, Brazil* and Alexandre ZANONI, *Federal University of Paraná, Brazil*
Digital and Platform Work in Brazil in the Midst of a Pandemic: Resistance, Trends, and Challenges for Unionism

448.4 Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada* and Xavier ST-DENIS, *Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Canada*
The Aftermath of the Pandemic: Exacerbated Advantages and Disadvantages in the Labour Market

448.5 Nobuko HOSOGAYA, *Sophia University, Japan* and Noriko ARAI, *Sophia university, Japan*
A Study on the Identification of Factors for Promoting Employees' Participation in Networking Groups in Japan

448.6 Joanna ANDRASZAK, *Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain*
Why Telecommuting Was Not Here to Stay? the Case of Social Services at the Municipal Level in Spain during the COVID-19.

448.7 Marco ALBERIO, *Università di Bologna, Italy* and Labarchède LABARCHÈDE, *UQAR, Canada*
Community Action Workers Facing the Needs of Seniors in the Context of a Health Crisis. a Worker's Perspective.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

448.8 Sidnei MACHADO, *Universidade Federal do Paraná - UFPR, Brazil* and Ana Flávia DINIZ MACHADO, *Universidade Federal do Paraná (UFPR), Brazil*
New Paradigms of Labour Regulation in Brazil's Post-Pandemic Period

448.9 Maria Cecilia TRIONFETTI, *Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium*
Rethinking Forms of Resistance through the Prism of Occupational Health

10:30-12:20**JS-142 Participation Chances, Inequality and Risks of Exclusion in Prolonged Working Lives in Europe**

Committees: *RC11 Sociology of Aging (Host); RC30 Sociology of Work*

See Joint Session Details for JS-142.

12:30-14:20**JS-145 Environment and Work: Links and Threats**

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC24 Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-145.

14:30-16:20**JS-154 Trade Unions Under Authoritarianism in the Global South**

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC44 Labor Movements*

See Joint Session Details for JS-154.

RC31**Sociology of Migration**

Program Coordinator: Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-4 Return Migration during a Pandemic: Challenges and Interventions

Committees: RC46 *Clinical Sociology (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-4.

449 Migration in Asia – Integration and Cultural Diversity

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Terence Chun Tat SHUM, *Hong Kong Metropolitan University, China* and Pui Yan Flora LAU, *Department of Sociology, Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*

Chair: Terence Chun Tat SHUM, *Hong Kong Metropolitan University, China*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

449.1 Yao-tai LI, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Integration Along the Class Lines? the Everyday Interactions and Boundary Making/Unmaking between Mainland Skilled Professionals and Locals in Hong Kong

449.2 Nana OISHI, *The University of Melbourne, Australia* and Akira IGARASHI, *Osaka University, Japan*
Why Do Nationalists Support Migration?: Structural Economic Nationalism and Multicultural Transformation in Japan

449.3 Allen KIM, *International Christian University, Japan*
Pandemic Cooking, Community and Sense of Belonging in Japan: The Coping Strategies of Foreign-Born Seminarians amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic.

449.4 Bubbles Beverly ASOR, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
Caring for 'Liminal' Migrants: The Role of Religious Organisation in the Incorporation of Filipino Migrants into South Korea

449.5 Gustavo Henrique VIEIRA MEIRELES, *Kanda University of International Studies, Japan*
The Migration Process and Integration Strategies of Brazilian Migrants Living in Okinawa Prefecture

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

449.6 Tushar DAKUA, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India*
Cross Border Migration between India and Nepal: A Study on Integration of Indian Immigrants

15:30-17:20

JS-9 Navigating Aging, Social Well-Being, and Cultural Expectations Among Migrant and Transnational Families

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration (Host)*; RC06 *Family Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-9.

450 Smartphones As Micro-Homes, Away from Home? Comparing Forms of Portable and Digital Homemaking Among Migrants and Displaced Young People

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia* and Paolo BOCCAGNI, *University of Trento, Italy*

Chair: Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia*

Co-Chair: Paolo BOCCAGNI, *University of Trento, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

450.1 Lucas CE SANGALLI, *University of Goettingen, Germany*
Images of War, Images of Home – the Role of Smartphones in the Construction of Belongings of Sudanese Living Abroad

450.2 Iwona LEONOWICZ-BUKALA, *University of Information Technology and Management in Rzeszow, Poland, Poland*
The Role of Smartphones in Maintaining Contact with the World Left behind. the Case of Young Ukrainian Refugees in Poland

450.3 Yuhan WANG, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
Atmosphere of Homemaking: Studying a Digital Platform As a Portable Homeland

450.4 Jayakumar MADHAVAN SARASAMMA, *University of Kerala, India*
ICT Mediated Intimacy: Virtual Co-Presence of Long-Distance Couples in Kerala, India

17:30-19:20

JS-20 International Migration and Economic Informalization : A Denationalized Perspective - Part I

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work (Host)*; RC02 *Economy and Society* and RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-20.

451 Conceptualising Transnational Youth Mobilities and Transitions amidst Social Challenges

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Anita HARRIS, *Deakin University, Australia*; Sharlene SWARTZ, *University of Fort Hare, South Africa* and Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*

Chair: Anita HARRIS, *Deakin University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

451.1 Valentina CUZZOCREA, *Universita di Cagliari, Italy*
The Collective Dimension of Mobility and Its Post Pandemic Promises for Youth

451.2 Alexandra MIROWSKI RABELO DE SOUZA, York University, Canada

After the Migration-for-Development Program: A Study of STEM Student-Migrants Turned Immigrants to Canada

451.3 Sohoon YI, Kyungpook National University, Republic of Korea; Susan BANKI, University of Sydney, Australia and Joowon YUK, Kyungpook National University, Republic of Korea
Planning While Precarious: The Impact of COVID-19 on Young Temporary Migrants in Australia

451.4 Ashika NIRLAULA, Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration & Integration Program, Canada
International Students and the Pandemic: Changing Migration Aspirations and Pathways?

451.5 Paolo BOCCAGNI, University of Trento, Italy
Achieving Normality, Modernity, and the “Good Life”: Migration As Aspired Transition to Adulthood Among Young Asylum Seekers in Italy

451.6 Martina BOESE, La Trobe University, Australia and Iain CAMPBELL, Centre for Employment and Labour Relations Law, University of Melbourne, Australia
Shifting Ground: Transnational Mobility and Experiences of Precarious Work Amongst Working Holiday Makers in Australia, 2015-2022

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

451.7 Catherine GOMES, RMIT University, Australia
The Wellbeing Turn: A Necessary Consideration in International Student Mobility

451.8 Yan WANG, Institute for Culture and Society, Western Sydney University, Australia
‘Growing up in the Middle’ - Exploring the Interaction between Intergenerational Relationships and Transnational Youth Mobile Transition Among PRC-Born Chinese (PRCC) Youth in Australia and Australia-Born Chinese (ABC) Youth in China

451.9 Alexandra LEE, Deakin University, Australia
(Re)Claiming Place for a Future: Examining Transnational Mobility As an Enabling Factor in Young Asian Australians’ Reconstructions and Reclamations of Future Possible Selves (and societies)

451.10 Hao ZHENG, Deakin University, Australia
Chinese Queer Female Students’ Queer and Adult Identity Making in Australia

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-29 Working Abroad: The Experience of Mobile Professionals in Foreign Labour Markets

Committees: RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-29.

452 Tackling East Asian Migration Regimes: Challenges and Opportunities for East Asian Democracies

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Emiko OCHIAI, Kyoto University, Japan and Akihiro KOIDO, University of Asia in Tokyo, Japan

Chair: Akihiro KOIDO, University of Asia in Tokyo, Japan

Discussant: Nana OISHI, University of Melbourne, Australia

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

452.1 Yen-fen TSENG, Department of Sociology, National Taiwan University, Taiwan
Transforming Exclusive Migration Regime? Opportunities and Challenges of Reforming Taiwanese Immigration Policy

452.2 In-jin YOON, Korea University, Republic of Korea
Trends of International Migration and Issues of Migrant Integration in South Korea

452.3 Reiko OGAWA, Chiba University, Japan
Contested Nexus between Migration and Refugee Regimes in Japan

452.4 Kikuko NAGAYOSHI, Institute of Social Science, the University of Tokyo, Japan
The Labor Market Positions of Immigrant Workers in Japan: Skill Transferability and Institutionalized Inequality

452.5 Sara PARK, University of Helsinki, Finland
Toward Historical Comparison of Migration Regime: The Concept of “Immigration Control Regime” in Japan

10:30-12:20

JS-35 The Collaboration and Solidarity of Local and Ethnic Residents in Global Cities

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-35.

453 Social and Spatial Mobility: New Entanglements of Class and Migration

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Catriona STEVENS, School of Arts and Humanities, Edith Cowan University, Australia; Maja CEDERBERG, University of Gothenburg, Sweden and Jamie COATES, University of Sheffield, United Kingdom

Chair: Catriona STEVENS, School of Arts and Humanities, Edith Cowan University, Australia

Co-Chair: James COATES, University of Sheffield, United Kingdom

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

453.1 Lan anh HOANG, The University of Melbourne, Australia
Vietnamese Migrants in Australia: Downward Social Mobility, Class Identity, and Belonging

453.2 Manashi RAY, West Virginia State University, USA
Social Mobility in Transnational Spaces: Subjective Perceptions of Indian Women Entrepreneurs

453.3 Jock COLLINS, University of Technology, Australia
Spatial and Class Dimensions of Recent Refugee Settlement in Australia

453.4 Sylvia ANG, Monash University, Australia
Stuck between the Global North and South: Middling Migrants in Australia and Singapore

453.5 Pu HAO, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong
Landholdings and the Immobility of Rural Citizens in China

453.6 Rose BUTLER, *Deakin University, Australia* and Eve VINCENT, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Class, Migration and Capital in Contemporary Australia through the Lens of Cross-Class Relationships

453.7 Arne WORM, *University of Goettingen, Center of Methods in Social Sciences, Germany* and Johannes BECKER, *University of Goettingen, Germany*
Class, Social Mobility and Displacement in the Middle East Region – Complex Interrelations from a Biographical and Multi-Generational Perspective

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

453.8 Dhara PATEL, *Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany*
Housing Practices of Indian Diaspora in Frankfurt: Welfare-State Equity or Nationally-Bounded Inequalities?

453.9 Milos DEBNAR, *Ryukoku University, Japan*
The Role of Class in Shaping Decisions to Move, Stay and Leave – the Case of European Migrants in Japan

453.10 Laura OSO CASAS, *Universidade da Coruña, Spain* and Laura SUAREZ GRIMALT, *UNIVERSITY OF A CORUÑA, Spain*
Navigating Spatial and Social Mobility through the Transnational Space: An Intergenerational and Gender Approach

15:30-17:20

JS-42 International Migration and Economic Informalization: A Denationalized Perspective - Part II

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC02 Economy and Society and RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-42.

454 How Does Migration Scholarship Contribute to Public Discourse?

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David BARTRAM, *University of Leicester, United Kingdom*

Chair: Cristian DONA REVECO, *University of Nebraska at Omaha, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

454.1 Risa MURASE, *University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, USA*
The Invisible Glass: From Criminality to Conditional Exclusion in Japanese Media Coverage of Migrants

454.2 Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Australian Scholarship on Temporary Migrant Work: Changing Policies or Challenging Perspectives on Migration?

454.3 Anna TRIANDAFYLLIDOU, *Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University, Canada* and Ashika NIRAUULA, *Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration & Integration Program, Canada*
Portability of Concepts and Language across Countries: Equity and Diversity

454.4 Anna TRIANDAFYLLIDOU, *Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University, Canada* and Rica CASTANEDA, *CERC in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University, Canada*
Portability of Concepts in Migration Governance

454.5 Sylvain BECK, *CI Migration fellow (2022-2025), France* and Benedicte BRAHIC, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom*
The Invisibilisation of French Emigration in Public Discourses, a Significant Case for Migration Studies?

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

454.6 Patrycja BUXTON, *University of Stavanger, Norway*
Ties That Bind: Applying a Feminist Sociological Imagination to Working with Polish Women in an Inter/National Domestic Violence Context

17:30-19:20

JS-46 Gender in Skilled Migration: Beyond Western Perspectives

Committees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-46.

455 Migrant Activisms

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ana LOPEZ-SALA, *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Spain* and Luin GOLDRING, *York University, Canada*

Chair: Abdie KAZEMIPUR, *University of Calgary, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

455.1 Hector Eloy RIVAS-SANCHEZ, *Athabasca University, Canada*
Migrant Insurgencies in the Post-Pandemic Border Regime: Undocumented Activism in Canada

455.2 Davide NICOLOSI, *University of Catania, Italy*
Networks of Pro-Social Activism in Favour of Migrants: A Case-Study in Sicily

455.3 Lisa BONFERT, *TU Dortmund University, Luxembourg* and Karolina BARGLOWSKI, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
'Migrant Organizations' and the Affective Dimension of Social Protection Practices across Different Migration Biographies

455.4 Teresa SORDE-MARTI, *Univ Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*; Gisela REDONDO-SAMA, *Rovira i Virgili University, Spain* and Maria VIEITES CASADO, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Refuge-ED: Enhancing the Live Prospects of Unaccompanied Minors in Spain

455.5 Daniel STAGEMAN, *John Jay College of Criminal Justice, CUNY, USA* and Arlana HENRY, *Rutgers University, USA*
Amenable to Removal: The Effects of Ideological and Fiscal Incentives on US County Sherriffs' Entrepreneurial Approaches to Immigration Enforcement

19:30-20:50

456 RC31 Business Meeting

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-57 Gender-Based Violence and Migration: Global PerspectivesCommittees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-57.

457 Forced Migration and Trafficking in Persons in the Contemporary World: The Variables of Gender, Human Rights and Covid-19 Pandemic

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Arun Kumar ACHARYA, *Sambalpur University, India* and Jennifer CLARK, *University of Texas Rio Grande Valley and South Texas College, USA*Chair: Arun Kumar ACHARYA, *Sambalpur University, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****457.1** Farhan Navid YOUSAF, *Institute of Social and Cultural Studies, University of the Punjab, Pakistan*
Trafficking of Child Domestic Workers: A Gender and Human Rights Perspective**457.2** Kailash Chandra DAS, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India*; Tushar DAKUA, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India* and Margubur RAHAMAN, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India*
Is Human Trafficking a Serious Problem in India: Who, Where, and How?**457.3** Matthias SCHNEIDER, *Potsdam University, Germany*
Male Violence and Masculinities of Solidarity in Smuggling and Trafficking**457.4** Saroj RATH, *University of Delhi, India* and Ms LEENA, *Indian Institute of Foreign Trade, India*
Trafficking in Persons in India: Dealing with the Surprising Lack of Legal Infrastructure**457.5** Ibrahimia Amadou DIA, *African Centre for the Study and Research on Migration - African Union Commission, Mali*
Human Trafficking in Africa: A Human Rights-Based Approach**457.6** Jennifer CLARK, *University of Texas Rio Grande Valley and South Texas College, USA*
The COVID-19 Pandemic: Securitization, Authoritarian Neoliberalism, and Trafficking in Persons.**457.7** Pooja RISHI, *South Texas College, USA* and Jennifer CLARK, *University of Texas Rio Grande Valley and South Texas College, USA*
Of Borders, Trumpian Walls and Security Discourses: Performing National Security at the Southern Border**457.8** Olaya GARCIA VAZQUEZ, *Universidad Pontificia Comillas, Spain* and Carmen MENESES FALCÓN, *Universidad Pontificia Comillas de Madrid, Spain*
Human Trafficking Survivors in Spain: The Variables of Gender, Citizenship and Covid-19 Pandemic**457.9** Sushree BEHERA, *Sambalpur University, India*
Trafficking of Labour Migrants and Exposure to Interpersonal Violence: Evidence from India

10:30-12:20

JS-66 The Covid-19 Crisis, Gender, and the Price of Migrants' InvisibilityCommittees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-66.

458 Gender, Migration, and Agency: Marriage Migration to Emerging Destinations

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Hsin-Chieh CHANG, *Fudan University, China*Chair: Hsin-Chieh CHANG, *Fudan University, China***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****458.1** Retika ADHIKARI, *University of Michigan, USA*
Divorce-As-Care: Bhutanese Refugee Women and Their Migration Strategies**458.2** Clara Wai-chun TO, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Divorce As a Strategy of Empowerment: Remarried Chinese Immigrant Women Navigating Immigration and Social Policies in Hong Kong**458.3** Chia-yuan HUANG, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Geopolitics, Gender and Cross-Strait Marriage: Recent Taiwanese Female Marriage Migrants in China**458.4** Akwi SEO, *Fukuoka Women's University, Japan*
Building a Sisterhood across Borders: Marriage Migrant Women's Human Rights Movement in Korea**458.5** Seiko MIZUSHIMA, *University of the Philippines - Diliman, Philippines*
Power Relations and Capital Acquisition in the Lives of Intermarried Migrant Filipino Women in Japan**458.6** Sana ASHRAF, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Home Role Negotiations and the Transnational Trajectories, a Qualitative Study on Second-Generation British Pakistani Women Spouses**458.7** Ayla DENIZ, *Ankara University, Turkey* and E. Murat ÖZGÜR, *Ankara University, Turkey*
Changing the 'Vulnerable Foreign Bride' Image: How Ukrainian Brides Became Diaspora Representatives in Turkey?

15:30-17:20

JS-73 Femmes Migrantes Sur Le Marché Du Travail Subalterne/Migrant Women in the Subaltern Labor MarketCommittees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-73.

459 Is This Home? Return Migration and the (mis)Appropriation of the Ancestral Place of Origin

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Mariusz DZIEGLEWSKI, *Pedagogical University of Cracow, Poland*; Melissa BLANCHARD, *CNRS, France* and Francesca SIRNA, *CNRS, France*

Chair: Mariusz DZIEGLEWSKI, *Pedagogical University of Cracow, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

459.1 Hila ZABAN, *Kinneret Academic College on the Sea of Galilee, Israel*
The Appropriation of the Ancestral Homeland: The Case of Privileged Jewish Migration to Israel

459.2 Fira CHMIEL, *LICH, UNSAM/CONICET, Argentina*
On the Way Back in the Trail of Breadcrumbs: Childhood Memories on Houses at the Return from Exile

459.3 Ilze KOROLEVA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia*; Aleksandrs ALEKSANDROVS, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia*; Inta MIERINA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia*; Ginta ELKSNE, (1) *University of Latvia*; (2) *Riga Stradins University, Latvia* and Maija KRŪMIŅA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia*
Typologisation of Remigrants and Analysis of Return Stories: The Case of Latvia

459.4 Abdie KAZEMIPUR, *University of Calgary, Canada*
Return Migrants in a New International Migration Ecosystem: The Interplay of Return Migration, Culture of Migration, and Anti-Migration Narrative, with a Focus on Iran

459.5 Phillip CHA, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Betrayal of Motherland: The Effect of Interaction with Koreans on Korean-Japanese's Identity Construction

459.6 Keaki MATSUDAIRA, *National Institute for Japanese Language and Linguistics, Japan*
Japanese Americans' Return Home and the War: Senses of "Home" and "Homelessness"

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

459.7 Haoyu ZHAO, *Nanyang technological university, China*
In between Senses of Belonging and Strangeness: Return Migrants' Practices of Homing at Rural Ancestral Home in the Context of Urbanization

459.8 Yuko TSUJITA, *Institute of Developing Economies (IDE-JETRO), Japan*; Hisaya ODA, *Ritsumeikan University, Japan* and Irudaya Rajan SEBASTIAN, *International Institute of Migration and Development, India*
Return Migration and Intentions to Emigrate Again: A Study of Indian Nurses Returned from Gulf Cooperation Council Countries

17:30-19:20

JS-80 Language and Immigrant Generations: New Entanglements.

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-80.

460 Street Level Bureaucracies and Their Impact on Migrant In/Exclusion

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia* and Elisabeth SCHEIBELHOFER, *University of Vienna, Austria*

Chair: Martina BOESE, *La Trobe University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

460.1 Francis COLLINS, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Bureaucratic Encounters and Emotional Governance in New Zealand's Temporary Migration Regime

460.2 Adriana KEMP, *Tel Aviv University, Israel* and Julia RESNIK, *Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel*
Urban Governance of Liminality: Legal Children Frontline Actors and Institutional Legacies in Tel-Aviv and Jerusalem

460.3 Eduardo BARBERIS, *University of Urbino, Italy* and Silvia PITZALIS, *DESP, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
Building up the True Refugee. Legal Operators' Performative Work within the Asylum Process in Italy

460.4 Lidwina GUNDAKER, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany*; Yuliya KOSYAKOVA, *University of Bamberg, Germany* and Gerald SCHNEIDER, *University of Konstanz, Germany*
Global Norms, Regional Discrimination: Administrators, the Public Mood, and German Asylum Decision-Making

460.5 Sarah MARSHALL, *York University, Canada*
Conceptualizing Deservingness Amongst Street-Level Bureaucrats: Gatekeepers or Facilitators?

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

460.6 Octavio SACRAMENTO, *University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro - Centre For Transdisciplinary Development Studies // Purchase order n.: NE001.2023.0000556, Portugal*; Elizabeth CHALLINOR, *Center for Research Network in Anthropology (CRIA) - NOVA, FCSH, Portugal* and Pedro Gabriel SILVA, *University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro - Centre for Transdisciplinary Development Studies, Portugal*
Rights on the Ground: Street Level Bureaucrats' Understandings and Practices of Refugee Protection in Portugal

460.7 Rachel ROSEN, *University College London (UCL) Institute of Education, United Kingdom* and Eve DICKSON, *University College London, United Kingdom*
(EN)Countering Raceless Narratives: Migrant Mothers and Children with 'NO Recourse to Public Funds'

460.8 Francesca BIANCHI, *University of Siena, Italy* and Miriam CUEVAS, *University of Siena, Italy*
Local Reception Systems for Refugees and Asylum Seekers in Italy: Practices, Perspectives and Social Work Dilemmas of Practitioners

460.9 Tomoko WATARAI, *Yokohama City University, Japan*
Complex, Dynamic, and Sensitive: Street-Level Bureaucracy As a Reflexive Contact Zone

460.10 Giovanni MATERA, *Harvard University, Weatherhead Center for International Affairs, USA*
Do Organizations Supporting Migrant People Suffering from Mental Illness Overlap or Cooperate? Insights from a Vignette Study on Cultural Mediation between Organizations.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-84 Citizenship and InequalityCommittees: *RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-84.

461 Exploring International Migration from the Sending Country Perspective: The Case of the Philippines**Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Rizza Kaye CASES, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines* and Bubbles Beverly ASOR, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines***Chair:** Rizza Kaye CASES, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****461.1** Sanley ABILA, *University of the Philippines Visayas, Philippines*
Mental Health Education for Filipino International Merchant Seafarers**461.2** Seiko MIZUSHIMA, *University of the Philippines - Diliman, Philippines*
From Labour Migration to Marriage Migration: Intermarried Filipino Women Migrants and Their Integration in Japan**461.3** Tricia OKADA, *Tamagawa University, Japan*
Trans Belonging and Transgendered Lives in Japan during COVID-19

10:30-12:20

JS-92 Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler RelationsCommittees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

See Joint Session Details for JS-92.

462 Recent Developing Immigration and Integration Policies**Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Hideki TARUMOTO, *Waseda University, Japan***Chair:** Hideki TARUMOTO, *Waseda University, Japan***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****462.1** David BARTRAM, *University of Leicester, United Kingdom*
Do Immigrant Integration Policies Influence Subjective Well-Being Among Non-Immigrants? an Evaluation of Policy Change**462.2** Yasuhiro HITOMI, *Musashi University, Japan*
The Development and Transformation of the Refugee Policies: The Case of Japan**462.3** Tunde ALABI, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Being Nigerian Vs Being British/American: Identification and the Meaning of Integration Among Nigerian Migrants in the United States and United Kingdom**462.4** Valentyna PLIUSHCH, *Institute of Sociology, the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine*
Migration Policies for Asylum Seekers from Ukraine in Israel**DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:****462.5** Cristian DONA REVECO, *University of Nebraska at Omaha, USA*
Understanding Immigrant Integration and Integration Policies in a Semi-Peripheral Country. the Case of Chile**462.6** Marta JASKULSKA, *Kazimierz Wielki University, Poland*
Migration Policies of Polish Cities. Municipal Government in Poland As an Initiator and Entity Implementing Migration Policies**462.7** Deisy DEL REAL, *University of Southern California, USA*
Seemingly Inclusive Liminal Legality: The Fragility and Illegality Production of Colombia's Legalization Programs for Venezuelan Migrants**462.8** Marcio DE OLIVEIRA, *Federal University of Paraná, Brazil* and Sarah LEMOS SILVA, *University of Brasília, Brazil*
La Inserción Laboral De Los Inmigrantes Venezolanos y Haitianos En Brasil**462.9** Luciana GANDINI, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
Migration Policies and Governance in Latin America: Between Openness and Generosity, and Closure and Containment

15:30-17:20

JS-99 Crossing Borders – Shifting Orders? Intersectional Perspectives on the Ukrainian War and the Reorganization or European Border SpacesCommittees: *RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-99.

17:30-19:20

JS-108 Migration and AgeingCommittees: *RC11 Sociology of Aging (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-108.

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

JS-123 Educational Migration in the Post-Pandemic World: Exploring Continuities and DiscontinuitiesCommittees: *RC04 Sociology of Education (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-123.

15:30-17:20

JS-130 Complexity in the Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe (II)Committees: *RC51 Sociocybernetics (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-130.

17:30-19:20

JS-137 The Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC51 Sociocybernetics

See Joint Session Details for JS-137.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

463 Indian Migrants in India and Abroad**Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Aditya RAJ, *Indian Institute of Technology Patna, India***Chair:** Aditya RAJ, *Indian Institute of Technology Patna, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

463.1 Hisaya ODA, *Ritsumeikan University, Japan*; Yuko TSUJITA, *Institute of Developing Economies (IDE-JETRO), Japan* and Irudaya Rajan SEBASTIAN, *International Institute of Migration and Development, India*
Analyzing the Migration Experiences of Tamil Nurses Returned from Malaysia

463.2 Bali BAHADUR, *Central University of Punjab, India*
International Migration of Students from Punjab: Extent, Reasons and Implications

463.3 Adrienne ATTERBERRY, *State University of New York (SUNY) at New Paltz, USA*
Parenting within a Transnational Context: The Case of Indian and Indian American Return Migrants and Their Families

463.4 Jagdish Chander MEHTA, *D.A.V. College, Chandigarh (India), India*
Irregular International Migration from India to Europe: Issues of Concern

463.5 Radhika CHAKRABORTY, *National University of Singapore, India*
Gendering the Merchant Diaspora: Sindhi Women's Life Stories

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

463.6 Atinder KAUR, *Punjab Agricultural University Ludhiana, India*
Covid-19 and Return Migration: Increasing Indebtedness in Migrant Families (India).

10:30-12:20

464 Religions and Migrations: The Experience of the Boundaries and Borders**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Paolo CONTINI, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy*; William CALVO-QUIROS, *American Culture and Latina/o Studies | University of Michigan, USA* and Letizia CARRERA, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy***Chair:** Paolo CONTINI, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

464.1 Hung-jen YANG, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Evading Religious Regulation, Becoming Yiguandao Followers: A Case Study of Chinese Guest-Workers from Mauritius Back to China

464.2 Sandra PERTEK, *University of Birmingham, United Kingdom*
Religion, Forced Migration and Gender-Based Violence: An Intersectional and Ecological Analysis

12:30-14:20

465 Precarious Legal Status Trajectories**Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Luin GOLDRING, *York University, Canada***Chair:** Hector Eloy RIVAS-SANCHEZ, *Athabasca University, Canada***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

465.1 Sarah WALKER, *University of Bologna, United Kingdom*
From 'Child' to 'Worker' or How Precarious Legal Status Trajectories Shape Former Unaccompanied Minors Long-Term Social and Economic Well-Being and Differential Inclusion. an Italian Case Study

465.2 Nihal KAYALI, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*
Uncertain Practices: How Syrian Refugee Doctors Work in Istanbul

465.3 Zoran SLAVNIC, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Ognjen OBUCINA, *Institut national d'études démographiques (INED), France*
Refugees' Precarious Legal Status and Integration Outcomes in Sweden

465.4 Matt WITHERS, *Australian National University, Australia*
Lost in Space (and Time): Precarious Legal Status and Transnational Family Separation in the Pacific Labour Scheme

465.5 Karen BLOCK, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Migrant Domestic Workers and Their Children Born in Lebanon: "They Are Kind of Stuck"

465.6 Ritika TANOTRA, *York University, Canada* and Monisha POOJARY, *York University, Canada*
Who Wants to Live in the City Anyway? Exploring the "End" of Precarity through the Rural and Northern Immigration Pilot (RNIP)

14:30-16:20

JS-151 Organising Precarity and Inequality in the Gig Economy

Committees: RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-151.

JS-152 Religion As an Instrument of Rooting for the Liquid Identity of Migrants Part 2

Committees: RC22 Sociology of Religion (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-152.

RC32

Women, Gender and Society

Program Coordinator: Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

466 Home Is Not so Sweet Home: Shadow Pandemic from COVID 19

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Bula BHADRA, *Sister Nivedita University, India*

Chair: Bula BHADRA, *Sister Nivedita University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

466.1 Abha CHAUHAN, *Indian sociological Society, India*
Gender-Based Violence during Covid-19 Pandemic in India: Shifting Equations within the Domestic Sphere

466.2 Shweta PRASAD, *Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India*
Intimate Partner Violence and Covid-19

466.3 Andrew EROMONSELE, *Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria* and Agatha N.T. EGUAVOEN, *Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria*
Accused without Proofs: The Tale of Young Nigerian Children Branded As Witchcraft

466.4 Joanna ANDRASZAK, *Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain*
How Has the Pandemic Affected the Professionals of the Care Network for Victims of Gender-Based Violence? a Qualitative Perspective.

466.5 Usha PATIL, *Mahvir Mahavidyalaya, India*
Impact of COVID-19 on Women in Kolhapur District, Maharashtra. India.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

466.6 Arun Kumar ACHARYA, *Sambalpur University, India*; Jose Juan CERVANTES NINO, *UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE NUEVO LEON, Mexico* and Manuel BARRAGAN CODINA, *Universidad Autonoma de Nuevo Leon, Mexico*
COVID-19 Pandemic and Transgender Women in India: Socio-Economic Vulnerability and Vaccine Hesitancy

466.7 Lopamudra SENGUPTA, *Bangabasi College, India*
Knowing the Unknown SPACE: Reinventing the Meaning of Home from the Narratives of (Trans) Gender Persons in Urban Kolkata during Covid 19 Pandemic
Knowing the Unknown SPACE: Reinventing the Meaning of Home from the Narratives of (Trans) Gender Persons in Urban Kolkata during Covid 19 Pandemic
Knowing the Unknown SPACE: Reinventing the Meaning of Home from the Narratives of (Trans) Gender Persons in Urban Kolkata during Covid 19 Pandemic

466.8 Vedran HALAMIC, *University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Croatia*; Ksenija KLASNIĆ, *University of Zagreb, Croatia* and Jasminka LAZNJAK, *University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Croatia*
I Organize Everything Around the House! Quantitative Analysis of Gender Inequalities in Mental Load in Croatian Households

15:30-17:20

467 Decolonizing the Sociology of Gender and Sexualities

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Vrushali PATIL, *Florida International University, USA*

Chair: Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

467.1 Marisela VELAZQUEZ, *Children's Hospital Los Angeles, USA*; Debra MILES, *James Cook University, Australia* and Theresa PETRAY, *James Cook University, Australia*
Gender in the Courts: Women's Intersections of Gender, Race and Structural Processes in Australian District and Supreme Courts

467.2 Sohee KWON, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
A Decolonial Feminist Analysis of Institutionalised Australian Sociology

467.3 Jayati LAL, *Wake Forest University, USA*
Men without Gender? Theorizing Social Reproduction, the Coloniality of Class, and the Gender of Working-Class Men

467.4 Lekha N. B., *Sree Narayana College, Chempazhanthy, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India, India* and Antony PALACKAL, *University of Kerala, India*
Celebrating the Feminine: Intersectionality of Nature, Culture & Woman

467.5 Tina SPIES, *Professor of Sociology at Univ. of Kiel, Germany* and Elisabeth TUIDER, *Universitat Kassel, Germany*
#Stayathome, #Carecounts and #Homeeverything. the Bourgeoisiation of Care Work and the Whitewashing of the Home Office in Corona Times

17:30-19:20

468 Feminist Pedagogies, Positionality and Situatedness

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Danai MUPOTSA, *University of Witwatersrand, South Africa*

Chair: Agatha N.T. EGUAVOEN, *Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma Nigeria, Nigeria*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

468.1 Tendayi GARUTSA, *North West University, South Africa*
Strategies to Enhance a Feminist Classroom: An Auto-Ethnography

468.2 Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Privilege, Entitlement and Situatedness: Nordic Student Anxieties in a Feminist Classroom

468.3 Caroline NEWTON, *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*
To a Design Based on Solidarity

468.4 Nthabiseng MOTSEMME, *UNIVERSITY OF JOHANNESBURG, South Africa*; Malehoko TSHOAEDI, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*; Babalwa MAGOQWANA, *Nelson Mandela University, South Africa* and Edith PHASWANA, *UNIVERSITY OF SOUTH AFRICA, South Africa*
Teaching As Remembrance and RE-Memberment: Centering African Maternal Legacies of Knowledge in Decolonising Sociological Thought and Teaching

468.5 Igor GURRUTXAGA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*; Iraide ALVAREZ, *University of the Basque Country, Spain* and Mila AMURRIO, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Gender Really Matters in Group Work: A Visibilization and Politicization Teaching Sequence / EL Género Importa EN EL Trabajo EN Grupo: UNA Secuencia Docente De Visibilización Y Politización

468.6 Kiran BEDI, *Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana, India* and Kashmira KHANAM, *Central University of Haryana, India*
Awareness and Attitude of Teachers about Queerness: A Comparative Study of Government and Private Schools of Haryana

19:30-20:50

469 RC32 Business Meeting

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

470 Roundtable 1

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA*

ROUNDTABLES:

Motherhood, Work, and Family

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

470.1 Jiyeon LEE, *Korea university, Republic of Korea* and Soohan KIM, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*
The Paradox of Women Supervisors: Men and Women Managers' Use of Work-Family Policy during the COVID-19 Pandemic

470.2 Clara Wai-chun TO, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Conflict Resolution Strategies and Marital Stability in Cross-Border Stepfamilies in Hong Kong

470.3 Anelise ESTIVALET, *Stanford University, USA*
Social Mothers and the Professionalization of Motherhood in Brazil

470.4 Guzel BAIMURZINA, *Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation* and Flyura BURKHANOVA, *THE FEDERAL CENTER OF THEORETICAL AND APPLIED SOCIOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES, Russian Federation*
The Impact of Employment Factors on the Perception of Work-Life Balance Among Employees

470.5 Sre RATHA, *Manipal Centre for Humanities, India*
Being a Mother in STEM Academia in India: Examining Academic Cultures, Institutional Support and Individual Strategies to Maintain Work-Life Balance

470.6 Noelle BRIGDEN, *Marquette University, USA* and Jane MARTIN, *Independent Researcher, USA*
Why Did the Ethnographer Cross the Road? Research Reflections from a Fieldwork Family

LGBTQ+ Identities, Family, and Power

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

470.7 Leal RODRIGUEZ, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Saving Whose Face?: Masculinity Construction in One Philippine Private University

470.8 Liam LEONARD, *Monash University and Gender and Disaster Australia, Australia*
'Disaster Drag': An Intersectional, Queer Critique of Hypermasculinity in the Age of COVID

470.9 Mary KIHUHA, *St Paul's University, Kenya*
Invoking the Gods to Change One Owns Gender, Gender Fluidity from an African Perspective (Case study of the Agikuyu)

470.10 Md Abdur RASHID, *Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science And Technology University, Dinajpur-5200, Bangladesh*; Habiba BITHI, *Undergraduate Student, Department of Sociology, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur-5200, Bangladesh* and Md. Saidur Rashid SUMON, *Department of Social Work, University of Manitoba, Canada*
Living Experience of Transgender Community in a Permanent Settlement: A Study on the Manab Palli, Bangladesh.

Doing Ethnography and Fieldwork

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

470.11 Tamlynne MEYER, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Re-Examining Professional Identity: The Narrative of Black Women Lawyers in South Africa

470.12 Simrit DEOL, *University of Alberta, Canada* and Pirkko MARKULA, *University of Alberta, Canada*
Neoliberal Meritocracy Holds Us Tight in Different Ways: Memory Work of Bipoc Women Graduate Students

470.13 Carmela FERRARA, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy* and Concetta SORRENTINO, *freelance, Italy*
Women Held in a Men's Prison. Ethnography of the Trans Section of the Poggioreale Prison, in Naples, Italy

470.14 Phung SU, *UC San Diego, USA* and Phi SU, *Williams College, USA*
Embodied Truths: Gender, Sexualization, and Fieldwork As Relational Meaning-Making

470.15 Buddhima PADMASIRI, *Monash University, Australia*
Navigating Precarity and Power Dynamics: Fieldwork during Crises in Rural Sri Lanka.

Gender-Based Violence

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

470.16 Jingxian WANG, *university of Nottingham, United Kingdom*
Gender Violence Against a 'Silent Generation': The Birth and Journey of the 'Black Children' (heihaizi) Under China's One-Child Policy

470.17 Fatima FARINA, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
We Are at War. How the Coronavirus Spread within the Gender Based Violence Society

470.18 Jyoti DIWAKAR, *University of Delhi, India*
Revisiting Violence Against Women from Marginalised Women Perspectives

470.19 Mai YOKOYAMA, *Rikkyo University, Japan*
Comparing Rape Myths in Western Countries and Japan Using Various Rape Myth Acceptance Scales

Women's Empowerment

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

470.20 Hugo RIBADEAU DUMAS, *Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales (EHESS), France*
"Dosti Kranti Hai": Friendship As a Revolution? the (dis) Empowering Potentials of Extra-Household Socialisation in Urban India

470.21 Gurusamy SELLAMUTHU, *Gandhigram Rural Institute, India*
Empowerment of Dalit Women in Rural Tamil Nadu, India: Emerging Issues and Alternatives.

470.22 - MANISHA, *iips mumbai, India*
Is Empowerment Varies in Cross-Region and Local Brides of Haryana? a Study of Jind District

470.23 Guinea ADAMASTOS, *Research Scholar, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
From Sexism to Sexual Harassment in the Indian Legal Profession: A Rocky Road to Women Empowerment

470.24 Anita BRANDON, *State Institute of Rural Development, Rajasthan, India, India*
Women Empowerment in India : Initiatives and Impact

10:30-12:20

471 **In the Shadow of the Pandemic: The Impact of Authoritarian Trends and Tendencies on Gender and Sexual Politics.**

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Shweta ADUR, *California State University, Los Angeles, USA* and Gabriela FRIED AMILIVIA, *California State University Los Angeles, USA*

Chair: Gabriela FRIED AMILIVIA, *California State University Los Angeles, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

471.1 Veronica GONZALEZ, *University of California, Irvine, USA*
The Role of California's Sanctuary Policies in the Formal Help-Seeking of Latina Immigrant Survivors of Intimate Partner Violence

471.2 Monika FRACKOWIAK-SOCHANSKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland* and Marta ZAWODNA-STEPHAN, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*
Between the Personal and the Political. the Analysis of the Strategies Undertaken By Women Facing Oppression Due to Tightening up the Abortion Regulations in Poland

471.3 Marilyn PORTER, *Memorial University, Canada* and Linda CHRISTIANSEN-RUFFMAN, *Saint Marys University, Canada*
In the Shadow of the Pandemic: A Canadian Feminist Analysis

471.4 Ndeshi NAMUPALA, *University of Namibia, Namibia* and Nashilongweshipwe MUSHAANDJA, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
A Feminist Critique of Institutional Racism and Gender Essentialism: In Defence of Namibia's Track Athletes

471.5 Shushwi KE, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*
COVID-19 and Gender Inequality in India: Reproduction of Patriarchy

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

471.6 Hao CAO, *Wuhan University, China* and Yujie ZHONG, *Wuhan University, China*
Reconfiguring Gender Inequalities through Gender Empowerment in the Pandemic Makeshift Economy: Feminist Organizing in Shanghai's COVID Lockdown

15:30-17:20

472 **The "New Right" War on Gender and Intersectional Feminist Responses II**

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA* and Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil*

Chair: Myrna DAWSON, *University of Guelph, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

472.1 Manisha DESAI, *University of Connecticut, USA*
Beyond "Secularism and Rights?" Reflections on the Changing Landscape of Hindutva and Feminisms in India

472.2 Janet CONWAY, *Brock University, Canada*
The "New Right" in Liberal Canada: Intersectional Gendered Dimensions and Implications

472.3 Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA*
Gender Backlash and Responses in Comparative Perspective: Convergences in Resurgent Right-Wing Politics and in Feminist Responses in the USA and Brazil

472.4 Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil*
Anti-Gender Politics in Brazil: A Comparison with Latin America Neoconservative Experiences

17:30-19:20

JS-46 **Gender in Skilled Migration: Beyond Western Perspectives**

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration (Host)*; RC32 *Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-46.

473 **Building Feminist Academia: Research Experiences from the Social Sciences**

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Manuela MENDOZA HORVITZ, *Universidad de O'Higgins, Chile*; Francisca ORTIZ, *Millennium Institute for Care Research (MICARE), Chile* and Denisse SEPULVEDA, *Haute école de travail social, Chile*

Co-chairs: Manuela MENDOZA HORVITZ, *University of O'Higgins, Chile*; Francisca ORTIZ, *Millennium Institute for Care Research (MICARE), Chile* and Denisse SEPULVEDA, *Haute école de travail social, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

473.1 Hannah SOONG, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Sarah MCDONALD, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Maria VIEIRA, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Katie MAHER, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Mei FRENCH, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Helen STEPHENSON, *University of South Australia, Australia*

Socialising Feminist Ethics of Care during COVID-19: Multi-Ethnographical Accounts of Early-and-Mid-Career Researchers in the Academy

473.2 María-José DEL PINO-ESPEJO, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide UPO, Spain*; Karina VILLALBA, *University of Central Florida, USA*; Victoria CASTILLA, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide UPO, Spain*; Sánchez Tovar, Ligia SÁNCHEZ TOVAR, LIGIA, *Universidad de Carabobo, Venezuela*; Illescas Estévez, Eladia ILLESCAS, *Universidad de Málaga, Spain*; Ruiz Repullo, Carmen RUIZ REPULLO, *Universidad de Jaén, Spain* and M.Pilar MARTIN, *Adelphi University, USA*

Género, Educación Superior E Inclusión: La Visibilización De Las Madres Fundadoras En El Canon De La Sociología.

473.3 Claudia MATUS, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile* and Valentina RIBERI, *Center for Educational Justice, Chile*

The Vitality of the Gender Norm in Research

473.4 Aylin CAKIROGLU CEVIK, *TED University, Turkey*
Does the Feminization of Sociology Build Feminist Academia? the Case of Turkey

473.5 Jeff HEARN, *University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*; Deevia BHANA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*; Tamara SHEFER, *Women's and Gender Studies, University of the Western Cape, South Africa* and Annette VON ALEMANN, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

Feminist Knowledge Production through Building Transnational Feminist Academic Organising: The Case of RINGS

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

473.6 Mst Shahina PARVIN, *Department of Sociology, Brandon University, Canada*
Learning Indigenous Women's Stories of Opioid Use from the Intersections of Feminist-Based Interviewing Methods, Postcolonial, and Indigenous Feminist Scholarships

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-57 Gender-Based Violence and Migration: Global Perspectives

Committees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-57.

474 Theorizing Gender in Populist Times: Understanding the Challenge to Critical Social Sciences

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maitrayee CHAUDHURI, *Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), India*; Rituparna PATGIRI, *Indraprastha College for Women (IPCW), India* and Deepali DUNGDUNG, *Ranchi University, India*

Chairs: Maitrayee CHAUDHURI, *Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), India*; Deepali DUNGDUNG, *Ranchi University, India* and Rituparna PATGIRI, *Indraprastha College for Women (IPCW), India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

474.1 Gargi GAYAN, *Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University, India*
Examining the Idea of 'Self'-Learning within Gendered Spaces

474.2 Fouzia MANNAN, *East West University, Bangladesh*
Bound By Patriarchy: Women's Experience of Internal Migration in Bangladesh

474.3 Afsaneh TAVASSOLI, *Alzahra University, Iran*
A Sociological Approach to Understanding the Term Feminism (From women's rights to stigmatization)

474.4 Christina SCHARFF, *King's College London, United Kingdom*
Digital Feminist Activism and Neoliberalism

474.5 Jagmati SANGWAN, *AIDWA, India* and Shamsher SINGH, *FLAME University, India*
Women's Participation in Protests Against the Three Farm-Laws in India: Perspectives from the Ground

474.6 Surbhi DAYAL, *Indian Institute of Management Indore, India*
Masculinity and the Kanjar Community

474.7 Reyhaneh JAVADI, *University of Alberta, Canada*
Critical Analysis of Everyday Resistance Theories in Studying Iranian Women's Struggle for Rights

10:30-12:20

JS-66 The Covid-19 Crisis, Gender, and the Price of Migrants' Invisibility

Committees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-66.

475 Presidential Session: Masculinities in Authoritarian Times

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*

Chair: Bandana PURKAYASTHA, *University of Connecticut, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

475.1 Raewyn CONNELL, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Beyond Backlash: New Authoritarian Masculinities and Their Social Bases

475.2 Maitrayee CHAUDHURI, *Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), India*
'Feminism' in Contemporary Indian Public Discourse: State, Market and Media

475.3 Mary ROMERO, *Arizona State University, USA*
Masculinities and Anti-Immigration Politics in the US

475.4 Jeff HEARN, *Hanken School of Economics, Finland*
Authoritarian Masculinism: Globalizing, Mainstreamed, Contradictory, Converging, Banal, Autotelic?

475.5 Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*
White Masculinity Redeemed: Religious Fundamentalism in Authoritarian Times

15:30-17:20

476 Southern Theories, Connell, and Other Sociological Reflections on Lives during Times of Crises.**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Bandana PURKAYASTHA, *University of Connecticut, USA*; Manisha DESAI, *University of Connecticut, USA* and Roberta VILLALON, *St. John's University, USA***Chair:** Manisha DESAI, *University of Connecticut, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****476.1** Bula BHADRA, *Sister Nivedita University, India*
From Orient/Occident to Global North/South: A Conceptual Delusion**476.2** Caroline SCHOEPEF, *De La Salle University, Philippines*
The Coloniality of Global Knowledge Production: Understanding Intellectual Imperialism and Academic Dependency**476.3** Shabnoor NABI, *University of Toronto, Sociology Department, Canada*
On the Question of Postcolonial Sociology and Its Representation Politics: What Does It Reveal and What Does It Conceal?**476.4** Phoebe Zoe Maria SANCHEZ, *DeZIM-Institut, and College of Social Sciences in UP Cebu, Germany*
Democratic Institutions in Crisis-Ridden Male-Dominated Cognitive Empire: Misogynistic Attacks on Women Opposition Candidates**476.5** Chioma Daisy ONYIGE, *University of Port Hartcourt, Nigeria*
The Complexities of International Mobility for Global South Scholars in an Era of Covid-19

17:30-19:20

477 Global Perspectives on the Struggle for Reproductive Justice**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA***Chair:** Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****477.1** Bijoya ROY, *CENTRE FOR WOMEN'S DEVELOPMENT STUDIES, India*
Making Reproductive Health Safe: Stratified Reproduction and Reproductive Justice in India**477.2** Neo MOHLABANE, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
Reproductive Injustices in South Africa: A Case of Forced Sterilization of HIV Positive Black African Women**477.3** Romulo Jr NIEVA, *University of Otago, New Zealand*
Childbearing behind Bars: The Experience of Filipino Pregnant Prisoners**477.4** Esther HERNANDEZ MEDINA, *Pomona College, United States*
The Dominican Feminist Movement's Fight for Abortion Rights through Las Causales**477.5** Clara WARDI, *Graduate Programme in Sociology from University of Brasília (PPGSOL), Brazil*
Reproductive Injustice: An Analysis of Public Data on Women Denounced to the Police for Clandestine Abortion in Brazil**477.6** Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Universita, Italy*
Women's Bodies As Open Access Flesh. Reproduction, Technology, and Global Inequalities**478 Roundtable 2****Location:** Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil***Chair:** Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil***ROUNDTABLES:****Gender Segregation and Inequality****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****478.1** Elma BANYEN, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*; Dung JIDONG, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom* and Mathew NYASHANU, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*
Examining Gender Segregation and Its Impact on Maternal and Child Healthcare Services Delivery within the Community Health Workforce in the Upper West Region of Ghana.**478.2** Loikdzhon MIROV, *Technological University of Tajikistan, Tajikistan*
Social Exclusion and the Transition from School to Home: The Case of Young Girls Not in Education, Employment, or Training (NEET) in Central Asia and Caucasus**478.3** Smita MOHANTY, *Cognisphere Solutions Limited, India*; Parijat GHOSH, *PRADAN, India* and Sumita KASANA, *Cognisphere Solutions Limited, India*
A Journey Towards Making Half of the Sky for Women: Pradan Story**478.4** Suprava KHUNTIA, *Vashi, India*
Self-Help Group and Livelihood Patterns of Tribal Women**Sex, Health, and Justice****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****478.5** Usha RANA, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya Central Univ., India*
Girl Child Trafficking in Central India during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Sociological Analysis**478.6** Anuradha SHARMA, *University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, India, India* and Amithy JASROTIA, *University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, India*
Awareness of Sexual & Reproductive Health Rights Among Married Women Working in Higher Academic Institutions: A Sociological Study of Jaipur City, India**478.7** Hannah TAYLOR-ABDULAI, *University of Cape Coast, Ghana*
Abortion Decision Making in Africa from a Religious and Cultural Standpoint**478.8** Chenai CHIKOTO, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Kezia BATISAI, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Communicating and Interpreting Heterosexual Consent: Narratives of Female University Students in South Africa

Discrimination and Work**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

478.9 Paula PINTO, *University of Lisbon, Portugal*; Analia TORRES, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon Comp. 5162300210, Portugal*; Fatima ASSUNCAO, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon, Portugal*; Diana MACIEL, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon - Comp 5162300210, Portugal*; Bernardo COELHO, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon, Portugal* and Sara MERLINI, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon - Comp. 5162300210, Portugal*
Supportive, Resistant... or in-between? a Typology of Attitudes Towards Gender Equality Among University Leaders

478.10 Tamara KUENNEN, *University of Denver, USA*
Institutional and Cultural "Power and Control": Excavating the History of the Power and Control Wheel

478.11 Suchet KUMAR, *Rayat Bahra University India, India*
Parental and Organizational Support to Employees in Call Centres

478.12 Nedha DE SILVA, *Monash University, Australia*
Navigating the Informal Economy during Crisis: A Case Study on Financialization, Violence and Marginality Among Women Microfinance Borrowers from Post-War Sri Lanka

478.13 Buddhima PADMASIRI, *Monash University, Australia*
Precarious Work and Women: Employment in Agrarian Economies in Rural Sri Lanka

Gendered Organizations and Work**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

478.14 Riho NAGAYAMA, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*
An Analysis of the Interpretation of Their Work By Male Salespeople Working for a Japanese Cosmetics Company: Are They Key Players in Changing Gender Norms?

478.15 Julia KUBISA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Gender Equality Plans at Universities in Poland and Institutional Change between European Institutional and Local Political Pressures

478.16 Chie SAKAI, *Kansai University, Japan*
Women's Conflict with a Promotion in the Manufacturing Industry in Japan

478.17 Aida GHALEBEIGI, *Roy Morgan, Australia*; Karen DOUGLAS, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Victor GEKARA, *RMIT University, Australia*
Implementing Voluntary Workplace Gender Targets: A Case Study of Challenges and Opportunities in an Australian Transport Organisation

478.18 Valeria INSARAUUTO, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*
Perceived Gender Discrimination and the "Violence Continuum": Enabling or Contrasting Factor? a Study of the European Workplace

Women and Empowerment**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

478.19 Analia TORRES, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon Comp. 5162300210, Portugal*; Fatima ASSUNCAO, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon, Portugal*; Diana MACIEL, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon - Comp 5162300210, Portugal*; Bernardo COELHO, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon, Portugal* and Sara MERLINI, *CIEG/ISCSP - University of Lisbon - Comp. 5162300210, Portugal*
"Only When I Achieved Success, I Realised We Needed to Focus on Gender Equality"- Power Struggles in Female Academic Trajectories

478.20 Samapika MOHAPATRA, *Central University Of South Bihar, India, India* and Shalu SINHA, *Central University of South Bihar, India*
Still Women "the Second Sex" in Sports? (Analysis of few concerning issues from global and indian perspectives)

478.21 Sriti GANGULY, *OP Jindal Global University, India*
'Charity, Money and Respect': Women's Assertions and Negotiations through Multilevel Marketing in a Delhi Slum

478.22 Balraj BRAR, *Punjabi University Patiala, India*
Participation of Punjabi Women in Politics (1903-1947)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-88 Women in an Occupational Gender Segregation Global Labor Market

Committees: *RC32 Women, Gender and Society (Host); RC30 Sociology of Work*

See Joint Session Details for JS-88.

479 COVID-19: Intersectional Perspectives on Patriarchy and the Pandemic

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Arvinder A. ANSARI, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*

Chair: Arvinder A. ANSARI, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*

Discussant: Shushwi KE, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

479.1 Ajailiu NIUMAI, *Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion & Inclusive Policy, University of Hyderabad, India*
Racism, Cultural Differences and Hyphenated Identity of North East Indian Women in Hyderabad: A Feminist Perspective

479.2 Gerlinde MAUERER, *Department of Sociology, University of Vienna, Austria, Austria*
Parental Leave Policies and Gender Inequalities in the Uptake of Parental Leave. Empirical Evidence from Austria.

479.3 Haseena ABDULKADER, *affiliated to the University of Calicut, India*
Economic Impact of Covid 19 and Gendered Violence's Among Working Women in Kerala

479.4 Rahat SHAH, *Institute of Sociology, Goethe university Frankfurt, Germany, Germany*
Stigmatization, Differential Treatment, and Social Exclusion: The Lived Experiences of Female Breadwinning Couples in a Patriarchal Society

479.5 Suaad Zayed AL-ORAIMI, *Suite 202, USA*
The Role of Emirati Women during the COVID-19 Pandemic and the Challenges

479.6 Izabela KORBIEL, *Vienna University, Austria*
Home Academia. Female Researchers and Their Working Conditions during the COVID-19 Pandemic.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

479.7 Fen ling CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*
Gender Inequality When Work at Home during the Covid-19 Pandemic

10:30-12:20

480 Authors Meets Critics**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Manashi RAY, *West Virginia State University, USA***Chair:** Manashi RAY, *West Virginia State University, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

480.1 Melanie HEATH, *McMaster University, Canada*
Forbidden Intimacies: Polygamies at the Limits of Western Tolerance

480.2 Jane FREEDMAN, *Université Paris 8, France* and
 Evangelia TASTSOGLU, *Saint Mary's University, Canada*
Author Meets Critic: Gender-Based Violence in Migration : Interdisciplinary, Feminist and Intersectional Approaches, London & New York : Palgrave Macmillan, 2022

15:30-17:20

481 Gender and Queer Formations Under Authoritarianism in the Global South**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Cenk OZBAY, *SABANCI UNIVERSITY, TUZLA VD, Turkey* and Ayse Betul CELIK, *Sabancı University, Turkey***Chair:** Nilay CABUK KAYA, *University of Ankara, Turkey***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

481.1 Ayse SAKTANBER, *Orta dogu Teknik Universitesi, Turkey*
Queer Student Activism and Its Discontents in Turkey

481.2 John Andrew EVANGELISTA, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
The Nation Could be a Queer Thing: Contestatory Forms of Homonationalism in the Philippines

481.3 Debadatta CHAKRABORTY, *University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA*
Shaheen Baghs and Their Aftermath: How Female Protestors Shape India's Current Resistance Movement Against Fascism

481.4 Barbare JANELIDZE, *University of Kassel, Germany*
Unfolding of the Secular Self and Controversies over Sexuality in Post-Soviet Georgia

481.5 Andrew EROMONSELE, *Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria* and Agatha N.T. EGUAVOEN, *Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria, Nigeria*
Cultural Authoritarianism: The Case of Unmarried Young Female Adults in Nigeria.

481.6 Lea VAJSOVA, *Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria*
Feminism and the Women's Movement in Bulgaria: Dynamics of Change in Activism after the Rejection of the Istanbul Convention

17:30-19:20

482 Empowerment of Women in India and Abroad**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Deepti KAUSHIK, *Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India***Chair:** Binoyjyoti DAS, *SSS/CSSS, JNU New Delhi, India***Discussant:** Rajni BALA, *Baring Union Christian College, Batala, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

482.1 Sally BASHFORD-SQUIRES, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*
The Impact of Social Enterprise Projects on Women's Health in the Teso Sub-Region, Uganda.

482.2 Fouzia MANNAN, *East West University, Bangladesh*
Does Education Really Empower Women? Revisiting the Role of NGOs in Bangladesh

482.3 Mahesh SHUKLA, *Govt, TRS College of Excellence, Rewa (M.P.) India, India* and Gargi MISHRA, *Awadhesh Pratap Singh University, Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, India, India*
Role of Self-Help Groups in Empowerment of Indian Rural Women (With special reference to Rewa District, Madhya Pradesh, India)

482.4 Mahamuni THAMILARASAN, *University of Madras, India*
Rural Indian Women's Outlook: Venture on Achieving the Gender Equality (5th SDG)

482.5 Ajailiu NIUMAI, *Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion & Inclusive Policy, University of Hyderabad, India*
Empowerment of Women through Self Help Group: A Study of Kudumbashree

482.6 Manisha SHARMA, *Banaras Hindu University, India*
Widows of Tradition: Moving Towards Self-Employment

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

482.7 Annie DOUGLAS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Empowering Instruments or Agents? Analysing Development Discourses of Young Women's Empowerment in the Pacific

482.8 Yashfeen ADIL, *Jadavpur University, India*
Covid-19 and Entrepreneurship: A Study of the Muslim Women in Kolkata, India

482.9 Manita SUBBA, *Sikkim Manipal University, India*
Life of a Woman Vendor: Economic and Political Empowerment in Juxtaposition to Social Empowerment

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-119 Persistence and Change: Collaborative, Conceptual and Contextual Global Understandings of Gender-Based and Intersectional Violence

Committees: TG11 Violence and Society (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-119.

483 Female Migration, Poverty and Inequality

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Chioma Daisy ONYIGE, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Chair: Chioma Daisy ONYIGE, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

483.1 Jaciane MILANEZI, Brazilian Center of Analysis and Planning - "Centro Brasileiro de Análise e Planejamento (CEBRAP)", Brazil
Race and Reproduction on the Move: The Reproductive Care of Immigrant Women in São Paulo, Brazil.

483.2 Wai-chi CHEE, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong and Ping lam IP, University of Alberta, Canada
Displacement of Self in Transnational Motherhood: Mainland Chinese Cross-Border Mothers in Hong Kong

483.3 Kazi sharmin RASHID, School of Social Sciences, Australia
Integration into Australian Labor Market: The Case of Transnationally-Married Muslim Bangladeshi-Australian Women.

483.4 Sulpecia PONCE, MSU-Iligan Institute of Technology, Philippines
Gender-Based Needs Assessment of Ground Zero Meranao IDPs in Iligan City: Implications for Sustainable Intervention Programs

483.5 Mina OGBANGA, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Migration As a Tool to Addressing Poverty: Case Study of Selected Social Investment Programs in Rivers State

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

483.6 Oneza FARID, Aqsa Women's Degree College, India
Health Issues and Precarious Condition of Migrant Muslim Women Workers in the Informal Garment Sector of Bhiwandi, India.

10:30-12:20

484 Gender-Based Violence and Inequalities of Social Class and Race/Ethnicity

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Alicia Itati PALERMO, Universidad Nacional de Luján, Argentina

Chair: Alicia Itati PALERMO, Universidad Nacional de Luján, Argentina

Co-Chair: Bula BHADRA, Sister Nivedita University, India

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

484.1 Isadora VIANNA SENTO SE, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro UERJ, Brazil
The Increase in Femicides during the Pandemic in Rio De Janeiro: Reports from Legal Operators

484.2 Montserrat SAGOT, Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica
What Is Justice for a Victim of Femicide? Feminist Proposals to End Violence Against Women in Central America.

484.3 Beatriz Elba SCHMUKLER, Universidad Autónoma de Querétaro, Mexico
Critical Methodologies for Gender Training: Working for Intergeneric Encounters

484.4 Clarissa DAHMEN, STATEC, Luxembourg and Guillaume OSIER, STATEC, Luxembourg
Violence Against Men and Women: The Impact of Different Indicators on Perceptions of Gender (In)Equality

484.5 Ana VIDU, University of California, Berkeley, USA
Uniswithheart: Student Networks Leading the Struggle for Universities Free of Sexual Violence

15:30-17:20

485 Gendering Nationalism in 21st Century China 1

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Stevi JACKSON, University of York, United Kingdom

Chair: Nana OISHI, The University of Melbourne, Australia

Panelists: Kailing XIE, University of Birmingham, United Kingdom; Stevi JACKSON, University of York, United Kingdom and Sanna ERIKSSON, University of York, United Kingdom

17:30-19:20

486 Secular Authoritarianism and Gender Inequalities in Plural Societies

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Deepak Kumar VERMA, Dr B R Ambedkar University of Social Sciences, India

Chair: Deepak Kumar VERMA, Dr B R Ambedkar University of Social Sciences, Dr Ambedkar Nagar PIN 453441, India, India

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

486.1 Oneza FARID, Aqsa Women's Degree College, India
Gendered Politics: Hate Against Muslim Women in India

486.2 Idongesit ESHIET, University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria
The Law and Gender Inequality in Contemporary Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects

486.3 Mariko OGAWA, The University of Tokyo, Japan and Kawazura MITSUKO, Diversity Research Environment Promotion Headquarters, Japan
The Specialties of Women Consultants Who Stand Against Gender Injustice at the Forefront of Counselling and Support in the Public Sector

486.4 Melody HMANGAIMAWI, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, India
Customary Law and Women: Current Concerns and Future Possibilities in Northeast India

486.5 Vicky DEMOS, 1214 Orchard Circle, USA
Church, State, and Women's Rights in Greece from World War II to the End of the Twentieth Century

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

486.6 Suriya S, *Department of Development Studies, Madras School of Social Work, India*
Secularising Marriage: A Leeway in Hindu Law

488.5 Chwen-der LIN, *Department of Mass Communication, Chinese Culture University, Taiwan*
"Cyberyaos" in Contemporary China's Pearl River Delta

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

488.6 Hao CAO, *Wuhan University, China* and Xingyi ZHANG, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*
Discursive Contestations and Coalitions in Debating the Third-Child Policy in China

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

487 The Future of Global Gender Inequality and Intersectionalities**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil***Chair:** Solange SIMOES, *Eastern Michigan University, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

487.1 Liz MOUNT, *Flagler College, USA*
"New" TRANS Women: Reproducing Intersections of CLASS and Gender in Postcolonial India

487.2 Weifeng TAO, *Australian National University, Australia*
The Invisible Sexual Minorities: Queer Men's Sexuality and Identity Construction in Australia

487.3 Raquel LATORRE, *Universidad de Almería, Spain*
An Intersectional Perspective in Gender Roles in Sexuality and Care of Women with Functional Diversity

487.4 Chioma Daisy ONYIGE, *University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria* and Wisdom FAFI, *University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria*
The Intersectionality of Conflict, Migration and Human Trafficking in West Africa

487.5 Valerie GRAND'MAISON, *University of Guelph, Canada*; Clothilde PARENT-CHARTIER, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Karen SOLDATIC, *PO Box 11, Australia*
Stigma As Structure of Disablement: Towards Collective Justice

10:30-12:20

488 Gendering Nationalism in 21st Century China 2**Location:** 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Seagh KEHOE, *University of Westminster, United Kingdom***Chair:** Stevi JACKSON, *University of York, United Kingdom***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

488.1 Jiangrui LIU, *Chongqing University, China*
Divergence in Chinese Sexual Attitudes: An Age-Period-Cohort Analysis

488.2 Xiaowan CANG, *University of Oxford, China*
Reshaping Reproductive Culture in Pro-Natalist China

488.3 Tianqi HUANG, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
The Gendered Burden of Reproduction in the "New Fertility Era": A Study of in Vitro Fertilisation (IVF) Journeys in China

488.4 Heqing HUANG, *Gonville & Caius College, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
The 'Deferrer' Role: Female Health Professionals' Positioning in a Chinese Hospital

12:30-14:20

JS-146 Gendered Intergenerational Experiences of Social Mobility in Migration**Committees:** RC32 Women, Gender and Society (Host); RC38 Biography and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-146.

14:30-16:20

JS-150 Female Employment, Gender Equality and Women Empowerment across the Globe**Committees:** RC32 Women, Gender and Society (Host); RC20 Comparative Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-150.

RC33

Logic and Methodology in Sociology

Program Coordinator: Biagio ARAGONA, *Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

489 Recent Developments and Current Approaches to the Analysis of Panel Data

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jochen MAYERL, *University of Technologie Chemnitz, Germany*

Chair: Henrik ANDERSEN, *Chemnitz University of Technology, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

489.1 Heng-chin CHO, *National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan* and Chia-Keey KHOR, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

The Transitions Patterns of Gender Ideologies from Adolescence to Adulthood for Taiwanese

489.2 Christian DUDEL, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*; Daniel SCHNEIDER, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*; Angelo LORENTI, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany* and Mikko MYRSKYLA, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*

Discrete-Time Multistate Modeling for Life Course Analysis

489.3 Dominik BECKER, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*

Digging a Little Deeper: A Simulation Study on the Sensitivity of Different Approaches to Mediation to Variation in the Autocorrelation of "y"

489.4 Thomas ZIMMERMANN, *Goethe-University Frankfurt, Germany*

The Relationship between Educational Aspirations and School Achievement

19:30-20:50

490 RC33 Business Meeting

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

491 Relational Data and Geo-Data: Research Strategies of Analysis and Visualization

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Biagio ARAGONA, *Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*

Chair: Biagio ARAGONA, *Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

491.1 Modesto ESCOBAR, *Universidad de Salamanca, Spain* and Cristina CALVO, *University of Salamanca, Spain*
Interactive Network Graphs Online to Analyze Surveys and Other Databases

491.2 Giuseppe PADRICELLI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*; Suania ACAMPA, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy* and Noemi CRESCENTINI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*
The Algorithm Role in Medical Practices: The Case of Tonicapp

491.3 Antonio DE FALCO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*; Ciro Clemente DE FALCO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy* and Marco FERRACCI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*
Social Stratification and Geo-Media: An Empirical Analysis

491.4 Natalia MARTINI, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
Using Geospatial Technologies in Urban Ethnography

15:30-17:20

492 Integrating Survey Data from Different Sources: Comparability, Quality, and Applications

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Marta KOLCZYNSKA, *Institute of Political Studies of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*; Piotr JABKOWSKI, *Faculty of Sociology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland* and Piotr CICHOCKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*

Chair: Piotr CICHOCKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

492.1 Markus QUANDT, *GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, Germany*
Using Comparative Survey Data to Describe the Religious Heterogeneity of Societies - a Test Application

492.2 Vera TOEPOEL, *Utrecht University, Netherlands* and Anne ELEVELT, *CBS, Netherlands*
Combining Research Grade Accelerometers, Activity Trackers and Survey Data to Measure Physical Activity

492.3 Sebastian HÜLLE, *Institute for Employment Research (IAB), Germany*
Maximizing Linkage and Panel Consent Using Repeated Queries with Varying Framings

492.4 Philip ADEBAHR, *University of Technologie Chemnitz, Germany*; Manuel HOLZ, *University of Technologie Chemnitz, Germany*; Peter KRIWY, *University of Technologie Chemnitz, Germany* and Jochen MAYERL, *University of Technologie Chemnitz, Germany*
Of the Same World? Methodological Challenges When Integrating Survey, Epidemiological and Social Media Data.

492.5 Ireneusz SADOWSKI, *Institute of Political Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
Straying on the Limits of Equivalence. Case Study in Dilemma of International Value Comparison.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

492.6 Piotr JABKOWSKI, *Faculty of Sociology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland*
Obstacles in Conducting Valuable Analysis Based on Data from Multiple Sources. a Case Study of Methodological and Technical Challenges in Multilevel Cross-National Analyses on Attitudes Toward the Environment

492.7 Marta KOLCZYNSKA, *Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
Modeling Macro-Level Public Opinion: Challenges and Opportunities

17:30-19:20

493 Innovation in Data Collection

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Vera TOEPOEL, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

Chair: Pei-shan LIAO, *128 Academia Road, Sec.2, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

493.1 Vera TOEPOEL, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*
Using Sensor Data to Augment Surveys

493.2 Chia-jung TSAI, *Pompeu Fabra University, Spain*
Explaining the Negative Attitudes Toward Refugee Population— an Online Survey Experiment

493.3 Guannan ZOU, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, China*
Beyond “Insider” and “Outsider” in the Field: Reflections on the Roles of Human Geographers in Shifting Contexts

493.4 Francesco AMATO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*
The Issue of Data Accuracy When Data Collection Is Performed through Black-Boxed Digital Technologies

493.5 Lucas PAGE PEREIRA, *Ecole Normale Supérieure Paris-Saclay, France*; Bertille DECOUPLIGNY, *ENS Paris-Saclay, France*; Marc VERBOORD, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*; Eva Pina MYRCZIK, *University of Copenhagen, Denmark* and Neta YODOVICH, *University of Haifa, Israel*
On the Trail of the Everyday Cultural Conversation: Benefits and Limitations of Use of the Experience Sampling Method (ESM) in Sociology.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

494 New Trends in Digital Social Research

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Felice ADDEO, *Università di Salerno, Italy*; Francesco MAZZEO RINALDI, *University of Catania, Italy* and Gabriella PUNZIANO, *University of Naples Federico II, Department of Social Sciences, Italy*

Chair: Biagio ARAGONA, *Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

494.1 Davide BENNATO, *University of Catania, Italy*
Tracking the Traces in the Digital World. OSINT Approaches in Digital Methods.

494.2 Yuhan WANG, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
Dissolving the Screens: Understanding Digital Platforms through an Atmosphere Approach

494.3 Francesco MAZZEO RINALDI, *University of Catania, Italy*; Elvira CELARDI, *Università di Catania, Italy*; Vincenzo MIRACULA, *University of Catania, Italy* and Antonio PICONE, *Università di Catania, Italy*
Artificial Intelligence and Text Mining: Challenges in Social and Evaluative Research

494.4 Tatiana BARANOWSKAYA, *Russian State University for the Humanities, Russian Federation*
Digitalization of the Interview: On the Online Methods during the Pandemic

494.5 Renata NEMETH, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary*; Jakab BUDA, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary* and Bori SIMONOVITS, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Education and Psychology, Hungary*
The Language of Discrimination: Assessing Attention Discrimination By Hungarian Local Governments Using Machine Learning

15:30-17:20

495 Methods of Social Network Analysis

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Peter CARRINGTON, *University of Waterloo, Canada*

Chair: Francesco MAZZEO RINALDI, *University of Catania, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

495.1 Scott DUXBURY, *University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, USA*
A General Framework for Micro-Macro Analysis in Social Networks Research

495.2 Pranita SHRESTHA, *School of Architecture, Design and Planning, Australia*
Poverty, Power and Patronage -a Socio-Spatial Network Analysis and the Emergence of Three Squatter Settlements in Kathmandu, Nepal-

495.3 Keiichi SATOH, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan* and Hao LIANG, *Cornell University, USA*
Accelerators of Homophily: Examining the Effect of Actor-Level Network Formation Principles on Whole Network Structure with Agent-Based Modeling and Climate Change Policy Networks.

495.4 Tetiana KOSTIUCHENKO, *Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine* and Iulia DUKACH, *Texty.org.ua, Ukraine*
Digital Resistance in Russia's War in Ukraine: Studying Social Media Disinformation Campaigns with SNA Tools

17:30-19:20

496 Doing Qualitative Research in Turbulent Times

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Inga GAIZAUSKAITE, *Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany* and Claire WAGNER, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*

Chair: Grazina RAPOLIENE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

496.1 Inga GAIZAUSKAITE, *Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany*; Björn EGNER, *Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany* and Jan KROTKÝ, *Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany*
Comparative Focus Group Discussion Research: Dealing with Challenges of Field Work Reality

496.2 Sylwia MECFAL, *University of Lodz, Institute of Sociology, Poland*; Adrianna SURMIAK, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Beata BIELSKA, *Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, Poland*
Qualitative Researchers in Poland and Their Research Practices in the COVID-19 Pandemic – between Experiencing a Slow Disaster, Slowing Down and Social Acceleration?

496.3 Claire WAGNER, *University of Pretoria, South Africa* and Malefane MAINE, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*
Using or Losing a Participatory Video Approach in a Doctoral Study during COVID

496.4 Iker JIMENO, *Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain*
Adopting Qualitative Research to the Context of Covid-19: Tourism Planning and Social Participation in the 2020 Lockdown (Spain).

498.2 Nate BREZNAU, *University of Bremen, Germany* and Hung NGUYEN, *University of Bremen, Germany*
The Role of Public Opinion in Policy Making: Classification in German Parliamentary Debates, 1991-2017, Using Transformer Machine Learning Models

498.3 Cristobal TORRES-ALBERO, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain* and Alba VILLAMARIN, *Universidad Autonoma de Madrid, Spain*
Covid-19 Pandemic: Alternative Methodological Approaches Using Big Data & Machine Learning Techniques for a Massive Literature Review and Understanding the Social Media Discourse

498.4 Modesto ESCOBAR, *Universidad de Salamanca, Spain* and Cristina CALVO, *University of Salamanca, Spain*
Interactive Analytical Networks

498.5 Robert ACKLAND, *School of Sociology, Australian National University, Australia* and Mathieu O'NEIL, *School of Communication, University of Canberra, Australia*
Heuristics for Identifying Echo Chambers in Political Discussions on Twitter

498.6 Honeylet SANTOS, *University of the Philippines School of Statistics, Philippines*
Making Sense of Big Text Data: An Application of Topic Modeling Techniques to Online Newspaper Articles and Social Media Text.

498.7 Stefan KNAUFF, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
A Regionalized Analysis of Stereotyping on German Twitter

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

497 Participatory Visual Research. Disentangling Power Dynamics Using Collaborative Techniques

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Alessandra DECATALDO, *University of Milan Bicocca, Italy*

Chair: Concetta RUSSO, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*

Co-Chair: Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

497.1 Sarah MCCOOK, *RMIT University, Australia*
Show Me How You Feel: Using Visual Research Methods to Explore Men's Experiences of Gender Politics and Social Change in Australia

497.2 Wander VAN DER VAART, *University of Humanistic Studies, Netherlands*
Visual, Emotional and Interactive Aspects of the Life History Calendar Method

497.3 Donatella POLIANDRI, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*; Letizia GIAMPIETRO, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*; Nicola GIAMPIETRO, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*; Monica PERAZZOLO, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy* and Giuseppe C. PILLERA, *INVALSI - National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System, Italy*
Schools Self-Evaluation through Video Making: A Case Study

15:30-17:20

498 Big Data Analysis for Social Sciences I

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Belen CASAS MAS, *University Complutense Madrid, Spain*

Chair: Juan Antonio GUEVARA, *European University of Madrid, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

498.1 Yelena MEJOVA, *ISI Foundation, Italy*
Big Social Media Twitter Data for Studying Social Connection: Case Study of Loneliness

17:30-19:20

499 Data Quality of Cross-National Surveys

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Pei-shan LIAO, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

Chair: Chyi-in WU, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

499.1 Tom W SMITH, *University of Chicago, USA*
Comparison Error Lessons from the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)

499.2 Miloslav BAHNA, *Institute for Sociology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia* and Ondrej BUCHEL, *Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia*
Dynamics of Low-Effort Responding across European Societies

499.3 Pei-shan LIAO, *128 Academia Road, Sec.2, Taiwan*
A Comparison of Cross-National Surveys from the TSE Perspective Using the Relationship between Religion and Happiness As an Example.

499.4 Piotr JABKOWSKI, *Faculty of Sociology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland* and Piotr CICHOCKI, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*
New Insight into the Quality of the within-Household Respondent Selection Methods in Cross-National Surveys. Findings from the European Social Survey (ESS), 2002-2020

499.5 Daniel KRÄHMER, *LMU Munich, Germany*; Laura SCHAECHTELE, *LMU Munich, Germany* and Andreas SCHNECK, *LMU Munich, Germany*
Care to Share? Investigating Determinants of Code Sharing Behavior in the Social Sciences

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

500 From Interviewing to Diaries: Data Quality in Quantitative and Qualitative Social Research

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Dimitri PRANDNER, *Johannes Kepler University of Linz / Empirical Social Research Unit, Austria* and Martin WEICHBOLD, *University of Salzburg, Austria*

Chair: Martin WEICHBOLD, *University of Salzburg, Austria*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

500.1 Inga GAIZAUSKAITE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*
"Forced" Choice of Remote Interviewing: A Pitfall or a Benefit for Data Collection?

500.2 Mienke BRUG, *University of humanistic studies, Netherlands*
Third Person Help in Research with Children and Adolescents in Namibia

500.3 Alfredo MATRELLA, *Sapienza, Italy* and Michela CAVAGNUOLO, *Sapienza, Italy*
From Marienthal to Digital Methods: Audio Diaries By Using Whatsapp in Social Research

500.4 Ozana CUCU-OANCEA, *Institute of Sociology, Romania*
Reflections on the Resilience of Diary Methods in Times of Crisis or How Did I Cope with the Methodological Challenges of Exploring Romanian People's Attitudes Towards Celebrating Easter during the First National Covid-19 Lockdown

17:30-19:20

501 Big Data Analysis for Social Sciences II

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Juan Antonio GUEVARA, *European University of Madrid, Spain*

Chair: Belen CASAS MAS, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

501.1 Ciro Clemente DE FALCO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*; Gabriella PUNZIANO, *University of Naples Federico II, Department of Social Sciences, Italy*; Domenico TREZZA, *University of Naples, Italy* and Ferdinando IAZZETTA, *La Sapienza, Italy*
Cross-Platform Political Communication By Target and the New Season of Politics in Italy

501.2 Ana FERNANDEZ-ZUBIETA, *Complutense University of Madrid, Spain*; Juan Antonio GUEVARA, *Complutense University, Spain*; Rafael CABALLERO, *Complutense University of Madrid, Spain* and José Manuel ROBLES, *Complutense University of Madrid, Spain*
Digital Activism Masked. the Fridays for Future Movement and the "Global Day of Climate Action": Testing Social Function and Framing Typologies of Claims on Twitter

501.3 Zsófia RAKOVICS, *Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary*
Investigating Dynamic Social Networks of Politicians Constructed By the Similarity of Their Speeches

501.4 Robert HELMRICH, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany* and Jens DOERPINGHAUS, *Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB), Germany*
Surveys and Big Data: Closing the Gap?

501.5 Zsófia RAKOVICS, *Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary*
Investigating Language- and Political Polarization through Two Decades of Parliamentary Speeches

501.6 Ildiko BARNÁ, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary*; Renata NEMETH, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Research Center for Computational Social Science, Hungary*; Tibor PÓLYA, *ELKH TTK, Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology, Narrative and Historical Psychology Research Group, Hungary* and Réka BERBEKÁR, *ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Social Sciences, Hungary*
Examining the Different Political Sides' Memorialization of Using Tools of Natural Language Processing and Narrative Psychology

Saturday 1 July

12:30-14:20

502 Using Social Media for Social Research: Theoretical and Methodological Challenges

Location: 111 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Felice ADDEO, *Università di Salerno, Italy* and Cristiano FELACO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*

Chair: Francesco MAZZEO RINALDI, *University of Catania, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

502.1 Rocco MAZZA, *Università degli studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli, Italy* and Camilla VOLPE, *Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy*
Reputational Capital and Vintage Fashion: A Cross-Platform Analysis on Instagram and Tiktok

502.2 Juan FERNANDEZ-PRADOS, *University of Almeria, Spain*; María PUNTA-GARCÍA, *University of Almeria, Spain*; Cristina CUENCA PIQUERAS, *University of Almeria, Spain* and María TORRES HARO, *Universidad de Almería, Spain*
Analysis of Digital Social Networks in the Third Sector: Case Study in Andalusia

502.3 Ferdinando IAZZETTA, *La Sapienza, Italy* and Francesca LENZI, *Foro Italico, Italy*
The Obesity and Diabetes Narrative on Twitter

502.4 Valentina D'AURIA, *University of Salerno, Italy*; Vincenzo ESPOSITO, *Università Sapienza di Roma, Italy* and Francesco NOTARI, *University of Salerno, Italy*
Exploring an Italian Online Community of Incel. a Netnographic Study.

RC34

Sociology of Youth

Program Coordinators: Sharlene SWARTZ, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*; Howard WILLIAMSON, *University of South Wales, United Kingdom*; Ilaria PITTI, *University of Bologna, Italy* and Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

503 Marginalised Youth, Street Cultures and Mediation

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Carles FEIXA, *University Pompeu Fabra, Spain*; Pam NILAN, *University of Newcastle, Australia* and Carmen LECCARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

Chair: Pam NILAN, *University of Newcastle, Australia*

Co-Chair: Carmen LECCARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

Discussant: Carmen LECCARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

503.1 Carles FEIXA, *University Pompeu Fabra, Spain*
Transnational Gangs, Street Cultures and Mediation: The Life Stories of Three Latin Kings

503.2 Bryan Lee CELESTE, *The University of Newcastle, Australia*
Cultural Performances As Agency and Mediation in the Everyday Presentation of Indigenous Youth Identity

503.3 Unaloam CHANRUNGMANEKUL, *Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand*
Identities, Engagement and Participation: Myanmar and Thai Youth's Perspectives on Documentary Interpretation and Media Design for Mobilising Human Rights

503.4 Ligia LAVIELLE PULLÉS, *Universidad de Oriente, Cuba*
Spirit and Defiance: Three Case Studies of Informal Groups in Santiago De Cuba.

503.5 Paolo GRASSI, *University of Milan Bicocca, Italy*
"Hands up, This Is Not a Concert". Mediation and Educational Policies on the Margins of the City of Milan

503.6 Jose SANCHEZ GARCIA, *Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain* and Rachid TOUHOUH, *National Institute of Statistics and Applied Economics, Morocco*
"Ummi" the Mediator: Resolving Conflicts Among Youth Street Groups in Moroccan "Houma"

503.7 Margot MECCA, *Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain* and Eduard BALLESTÉ ISERN, *University Pompeu Fabra, Spain*
Exploring Mediations through Creativity: Ethnography and Theater with Maghrebi Unaccompanied Migrant Youth in Barcelona

JS-6 To Grant or Not to Grant? Use and Timing of Media Tools in Families with Teen and Pre-Teen Ager

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-6.

15:30-17:20

JS-7 Climate Crisis, Mental Health and Youth Resistance

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC15 Sociology of Health

See Joint Session Details for JS-7.

17:30-19:20

504 Becoming Adults As Children of Immigrants

Language: English, French

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Giulia MARROCCOLI, *University of Turin, Italy* and Roberta RICUCCI, *University of Turin, Italy*

Chair: Clarence BATAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

504.1 Dolly ELIYAHU-LEVI, *Levinsky College of Education, Israel* and Michal MEISHAR, *Levinsky College of Education, Israel*
African Refugee and Asylum Seeker Youth Grow Young Leadership

504.2 Arianna SANTERO, *University of Turin, Italy*
The Transition to Adulthood in Transnational Families: Gaps between Aspirations, Expectations and Practices in a Life Course Intersectional Perspective

JS-17 Children and Youth Navigating Gender

Committees: RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth

See Joint Session Details for JS-17.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-30 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (1)

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change and RC04 Sociology of Education

See Joint Session Details for JS-30.

10:30-12:20

JS-37 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (2)

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC04 Sociology of Education and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-37.

15:30-17:20

505 Presidential Session: The Sociology of Youth Today

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sharlene SWARTZ, University of Fort Hare, South Africa and Judith BESSANT, RMIT University, Australia

Chair: Sharlene SWARTZ, University of Fort Hare, South Africa

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

505.1 Dan WOODMAN, University of Melbourne, Australia
The Sociology of Youth (and Young Adulthood?)

505.2 Steven THREADGOLD, University of Newcastle, Australia
Between Youth and Young People: Living Breathing Young People and Their Conceptual and Disciplinary Doppelgangers.

505.3 Sherene IDRIS, Deakin University, Australia and Anita HARRIS, Deakin University, Australia
Race, Racialisation and Whiteness in Australian Youth Sociology

505.4 Howard WILLIAMSON, University of South Wales, United Kingdom
A Longitudinal Ethnography over Half a Century

505.5 Ben GOOK, University of Melbourne, Australia; Valentina CUZZOCREA, Università di Cagliari, Italy and Bjørn SCHIERMER, Oslo University, Norway
Still Together: Forms of Collectivity in Contemporary Youth Practices

17:30-19:20

506 Conservatism, Authoritarianism, and Chauvinism within Youth Culture Around the World

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Tomohiko ASANO, Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan; Naoki IGUCHI, Mejiro University, Japan and Hiroyuki KUBOTA, Nihon University, Japan

Chair: Naoki IGUCHI, Mejiro University, Japan

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

506.1 Kunal SHAHDEO, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India
Angry Hindu Men: The Young Blood of Hindu Nationalism

506.2 Malki PORYES, Ben-Gurion University, Israel
God Is My Buddy: Haredi Youth Online and the Formation of the Haredi Generation Z (Referring to the Ultra-orthodox Jewish society in Israel)

506.3 Pam NILAN, University of Newcastle, Australia and Gregorius Ragil WIBAWANTO, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia
The Life-Affirming Nexus of Religion and Youth Activism in Indonesia

506.4 Tomohiko ASANO, Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan
The Puzzle of Authoritarianism of Japanese Youth

506.5 Tomu OGAWA, Showa Women's University, Japan
The Social Problematization of Patriotism in Japanese Youth Discourse

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

506.6 Elif CAN, ENS de Lyon, France
"How Happy Is the One Who Says I Am a Turk" Socialization of Young People to the Turkish Nationalism in the School Context and the Production of Racist Discourses

506.7 Tianqi ZHANG, Nagasaki University, Japan
Queer(ing) Lives and Spaces on Japanese Campuses

506.8 Jakub NIEDBALSKI, University of Lodz, Poland
The Impact of Individuals with Profound Intellectual and Multiple Disabilities on Peer Relationships of Non-Disabled Siblings

507 The Experiences of Rural Youths in the Context of the Covid 19 Pandemic

Language: Spanish, English, French

Location: Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Maria Virginia NESSI, UBA, Argentina

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

507.1 Chandrikaben RAVAL, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad -Gujarat, India and Shailaja DHRUVA, Part 2, opp. Star Bazaar, India
Change and Challenges of Educated Rural Youth in Context of the COVID-19 Pandemic

507.2 Maria Virginia NESSI, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina
Rural Youth Research in Pandemic Times: Methodological Approaches through an Argentinean Case

19:30-20:50

508 RC34 Business Meeting

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-61 When Students Protest about the Climate Crisis: Realities, Reactions and Results

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-61.

10:30-12:20

509 Young People's Experiences and Relationships in the Global Pandemic (1)**Location:** 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA*; Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India* and Christina SCOTT, *Whittier College, USA***Chair:** Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****509.1** Eleanor FORMBY, *Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom* and Jo WOODIWISS, *University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom***LGBT+ Life in and after 'Lockdown': Young People's Experiences during the COVID-19 Pandemic in England****509.2** Elma LAGUNA, *University of the Philippines, Philippines* and Sanny boy AFABLE, *Population Institute University of the Philippines, Philippines*
The Struggle Is Real: School, Work and Life in Lockdown**509.3** Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India*
Contestation between the Belongingness and the Self-Processes – Family and Community Relationships Experiences and Wellbeing of Indian Youth during Pandemic**509.4** Sofia LAINE, *The Finnish Youth Research Network, Finland*
Young People's Leisure Time in Urban Environments during Covid-19 Pandemic**509.5** Giulia MARCHETTI, *University of Western Australia, Australia* and Anita HARRIS, *Deakin University, Australia*
Youth Transnational Im/Mobility, Transitions to Adulthood and Pandemic Time

15:30-17:20

JS-71 Doing Research on Young People with Young People: Co-Productions, Co-Authoring and Collaborations**Committees:** RC34 *Sociology of Youth (Host)*; RC18 *Political Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-71.

17:30-19:20

510 The Challenges and Affordances of Longitudinal Youth Research**Location:** 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Julia COOK, *University of Newcastle, Australia*; Johanna WYN, *Youth Research Centre, Australia* and Quentin MAIRE, *The University of Melbourne, Australia***Chair:** Hernan CUERVO, *5/100 Leicester St, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****510.1** Joan DEJAEGHERE, *University of Minnesota, USA* and Aditi ARUR, *Christ University, India*
Combining Prospective and Retrospective Qualitative Interviews to Understand Lower Casted Indian Girls' Educational Trajectories**510.2** Ana MIRANDA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Argentina*
Grammars of Youth: Studying Youth Transitions from Latin America.**510.3** Quentin MAIRE, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*; Johanna WYN, *Youth Research Centre, Australia* and Julia COOK, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
The Unfulfilled Promise of Education: A Longitudinal Analysis of Young Australians' Education and Work Experiences across Two Generations**510.4** Sigita KRANIAUSKIENE, *Klaipeda university, Lithuania*
Combining Life Stories and Life Course Data in Search for Structural Changes of Transition to Adulthood: The Case of Longitudinal Youth Research in Lithuania**510.5** Carmen LECCARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
The Challenge of Longitudinal Research in the "Suspended Transition"**DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:****510.6** Lesley ANDRES, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
The Challenges of Capturing Complexity through Longitudinal Survey Research: The Case of the Canadian Paths on Life's Way Project**510.7** Tanja STRECKER, *Youth Policy Labs, Germany*; Andrea HORTA HERRANZ, *Youth Policy Labs, Germany*; Ashley PITSCHMANN, *Youth Policy Labs, Germany*; Friedemann SCHWENZER, *Youth Policy Labs, Germany* and Johannes EICK, *Youth Policy Labs, Germany*
Ray-MON: Monitoring Erasmus+/Yia from 2014 until 2020**510.8** Linzi LADLOW, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Anna TARRANT, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom* and Laura WAY, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*
Re-Accessing Participants: Doing Qualitative Longitudinal Research with Young Fathers**510.9** Evelina LANDSTEDT, *Karlstad University, Dept of Social and Psychological Studies, Sweden* and Victoria LÖNNFJORD, *Karlstad University, Dept Social and Psychological Studies, Sweden*
From Preschool to Adulthood – Challenges and Possibilities of the Swedish SOFIA-Study**Thursday 29 June**

08:30-10:20

511 Youth Work and Authoritarianism: Responses to Social Conditions**Location:** 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Trudi COOPER, *270 Joondalup Drive, Australia*; Hilary TIERNEY, *MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY, Ireland* and Tim CORNEY, *Victoria University, Australia***Chair:** Tim CORNEY, *Victoria University, Australia***Co-Chair:** Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****511.1** Jai COOPER, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
'a Jump into Cold Water' - Hysteresis in Youth Environmental Workfare**511.2** Ben LOHMEYER, *Flinders University, Australia*
Youth Work, School Bullying and 'Public Executions' – Preparing Young People to Accept Authoritarianism

511.3 Joel MCGREGOR, *Swinburne University of Technology, Australia* and Ben LOHMEYER, *Flinders University, Australia*
Examining ‘Soft’ Authoritarianism in Third Sector Organisations in the Context of Youth Mentoring within Neoliberal Outsourcing of Government Services

511.4 Charles WICKINS, *Justice & Society, University of South Australia (UniSA), Australia*; Deirdre TEDMANSON, *Justice & Society, University of South Australia (UniSA);, Australia* and Sue KING, *Justice & Society, UniSA, Australia*
Outcomes and Consequences for Vulnerable Youth within the Context of Service Provision.

10:30-12:20

512 Youth in the Global South: Opportunities, Challenges and Articulations

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Abeer MUSLEH, *Bethlehem University, Palestine* and Sharmla RAMA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Chair: Rachid JARMOUNI, *University Moulay Ismail, Morocco*

Co-Chair: Kiran ODHAV, *North West University, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

512.1 Septrin CALAMBA, *Alfred Deakin Institute for Citizenship and Globalisation, Deakin University, Australia*
Everyday Peace Practices As Disruptors to Conflict: The Hidden Transcripts of Youth’s Participation in Peacebuilding

512.2 Lanre IKUTEYIJO, *Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Nigeria* and Olumayowa OLANIYI, *CLEEN Foundation, Nigeria*
The Nigerian Youth and the Endsars Protests: Implications for Participatory Policing and Innovative Democracy in Nigeria

512.3 Daniel MIRANDA, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Youth Citizen Participation: Between Social Reproduction and Political Socialization

512.4 Ruoxi LIU, *Department of Sociology, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Alternative-Seeking of the Self-Employed Cultural Workers in China: Decentralisation, Decentralised Cultural Production, Communal Spaces, Daily Practices, and Mobility

512.5 Valentin CHENIER, *Tampere University, Finland*
An Ethnography of Moroccan Skateboarding Culture: Grassroot Community Enterprises and Youths’ Transition to the Job Market

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

512.6 Qing tingting LIU, *University at Albany, SUNY, USA*
Cosmopolitan Imaginary and Temporal Liminality: --a Comparative Study on Chinese Youth Mobility in Australia and North America

512.7 Adam COOPER, *Human Sciences Research Council; Stellenbosch University, South Africa*
“Morphing between the Margins”: How Youth Make a Living across Multiple Spaces in South Africa, the Global South and Beyond

512.8 Yan JIANG, *Institute of Education, Xiamen University, China*
Doing Personhood: Another Breakthrough of Vocational Education Qualification —a Qualitative Study on the Group Culture of Higher Vocational Students

15:30-17:20

513 Youth Transitions in a Post-Pandemic World: Challenges and Opportunities for Youth and Young Adults in the Sphere of Work (1)

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Hernan CUERVO, *5/100 Leicester St, Australia* and Ana MIRANDA, *FLACSO Argentina, Argentina*

Chair: Hernan CUERVO, *5/100 Leicester St, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

513.1 Adam COOPER, *Human Sciences Research Council; Stellenbosch University, South Africa* and Bernard DUBBELD, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*
Gigs, Hustles and Hope: Mixed Livelihoods for Global Youth Beyond the Wage

513.2 Brendan CHURCHILL, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Making a Life with Less: The Impact of Underemployment on Young Australians

513.3 Costanza GUAZZO, *university of torino, Italy*
Is Work Not Working Anymore? the Cultural Meaning of Work for Young Highly-Skilled Basic Income Recipients during the Pandemic in Italy

513.4 Laima ZILINSKIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Life Scenarios of 1990-2000 Cohorts: Lithuanian Case

513.5 Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*; Noemi NOVELLO, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*; Sara RECCHI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy* and Federico PALEARDI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
Youth Unemployment and the School-to-Work Transition Phase: The Case of Italy and Pctos As an Education Policy Tool

513.6 Yi-fu CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*; Tsui-o TAI, *Department of Sociology, National Taipei University, Taiwan* and Hsin-Yi YEH, *Department of Sociology, National Taipei University, Taiwan*
The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Work Experiences Among Taiwanese Young Adults

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

513.7 Ruttia BHULA-OR, *Chulalongkorn University, Thailand*; Chadatan OSATIS, *College of Population Studies, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand* and Montakarn CHIMMAMEE, *Social Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand*
Aiming for Transitions or Not: The Subjective Life Plans of Thai Youth Not in Employment, Education, or Training (NEET) in the Post-Pandemic Period

513.8 Jiayue HU, *the University of Tokyo, Japan*
The Transition to Adulthood of Two Generations Under Two Regimes in China

513.9 Xabier TIRAPU, *UPNA/ I-Comunitas, Spain*
Juventud y Precariedad: Reflexión Sobre Las Transiciones a La Aduldez Para Comprender Las Disonancias Intergeneracionales

17:30-19:20

514 Youth Transitions in a Post-Pandemic World: Challenges and Opportunities for Youth and Young Adults in the Sphere of Work (2)

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Hernan CUERVO, *5/100 Leicester St, Australia* and Ana MIRANDA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Argentina*

Chair: Ana MIRANDA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

514.1 Maria-Carmen PANTEA, *Universitatea 'Babes-Bolyai', Romania*
Crafting Professional Identities in Call Centers. a Critical Theory Perspective

514.2 Ariane DE LANNOY, *University of Cape Town, South Africa* and Lauren GRAHAM, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Supporting the Most Vulnerable Neet Youth to Reconnect to Learning and Earning Opportunities: Lessons from a Coaching Program in South Africa

514.3 Kenneth ROBERTS, *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom*
Education-to-Work Transitions in Post-2004 European Union Member States after 30-PLUS YEARS of Transformation

514.4 Sonia MARTIN, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Representations of Youth Unemployment in a Pre- and Post-Pandemic Context: A Critical Examination of Two Key Periods in Australian Social Policy

514.5 Heng XU, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong*
Coming Back for Alternative Adulthood Transition: Return Mobility, Waithood, and Bounded Agency of Well-Educated Returnees in Post-Pandemic China

514.6 Ruta BRAZIENE, *Lithuanian Social Science Centre Institute of Sociology, Lithuania* and Sonata VYŠNIAUSKIENĖ, *Lithuanian Social Research Centre, Lithuania*
Youth Transition from School to Work in Lithuania Aftermath COVID 19 Pandemic

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

514.7 Maria CORROCHANO, *University Federal de São Carlos, Brazil* and Luis Paulo BRESCHIANI, *Fundação Getúlio Vargas, Brazil*
Youth Entrepreneurship in the Cities' s Outskirts of Brazil: Meanings and Disputes

514.8 Ilenya CAMOZZI, *Department of Sociology and social research, University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy* and Barbara GRÜNING, *Department of Sociology and social research, University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
The Interplay between Study Abroad and Professional Trajectories in a Post-Pandemic Scenario. the Case of Italian Graduates

JS-112 To Participate or Not to Participate? Social Movements 4.0 and the Return of Dichotomies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-112.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

515 Global South Youth Studies: The RC34 Oxford University Press Handbook Presidential Project

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Adam COOPER, *Human Sciences Research Council; Stellenbosch University, South Africa* and Clarence BATAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*

Chairs: Howard WILLIAMSON, *University of South Wales, United Kingdom* and Laura KROPFF CAUSA, *National University of Rio Negro - CONICET, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

515.1 Rara Sekar LARASATI, *Independent, Indonesia*; Bronwyn WOOD, *Thorndon, New Zealand* and Ben LAKSANA, *Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand*
Rural Indonesian Youths' Conceptions of Success

515.2 Ragi BASHONGA, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
"Maybe Your Home's the One That's Lost": On 'Returning', 'Home', and the (re)Claiming of 'African' Identity in the Film Black Panther

515.3 Roshni NUGGEHALLI, *Youth for Unity and Voluntary Action (YUVA), India*
Youth Protagonism in Urban India

515.4 Sharlene SWARTZ, *University of Fort Hare, South Africa*
Epistepaxis: Recognising the Practices of Youth in the Global South As Knowledge

10:30-12:20

516 Youth in Latin America and the Caribbean: Pandemic Impacts on Inequalities from an Intersectional Perspective

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina* and Agustina CORICA, *FLACSO, Argentina*

Chairs: Agustina CORICA, *FLACSO, Argentina* and Laura KROPFF CAUSA, *National University of Rio Negro - CONICET, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

516.1 Milena ARANCIBIA, *FLACSO, Argentina* and Ana MIRANDA, *FLACSO, Argentina*
Covid-19 and Gender: Impacts on the Labour and Family Trajectories of Women from Different Generations in Argentina

516.2 Melissa DE MATTOS PIMENTA, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Youth and Violence in Brazil and Latin America: Addressing the Impact of Covid19 on Mortality Rates from an Intersectional Perspective

516.3 Andrea BAUTISTA LEON, *Universidad La Salle Mexico, Mexico*
Intersectionality and Its Impact in the Access to Higher Education in Mexico

516.4 Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina*
El Impacto De La Pandemia En Las Desigualdades Socioeconómicas y De Género De Estudiantes Avanzadxs y Graduadxs Universitarixs Del Gran Buenos Aires.

516.5 Maria CORROCHANO, *University Federal de São Carlos, Brazil* and Felipe TARÁBOLA, *Universidade Federal de São Carlos - UFSCar, Brazil*

Strengthening Networks in the Cities' Outskirts: Young Black Women during the Pandemic and Post-Pandemic Crisis

15:30-17:20

517 Young People's Experiences and Relationships in the Global Pandemic (2)

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA*; Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India* and Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany*

Chair: Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

517.1 Julianne VIOLA, *Imperial College London, United Kingdom* and Luke MCCRONE, *Imperial College London, United Kingdom*

Social Connection and Belonging at University during the COVID-19 Era: Challenges and Opportunities for Young People

517.2 Ilaria PITTI, *University of Bologna, Italy*
Practices and Cultures of Boredom: Young People's Experiences of Doing Nothing in Covid Time

517.3 Damla TOPBAS, *Izmir Katip Celebi University, Turkey* and Nilay CABUK KAYA, *University of Ankara, Turkey*
"It's Not Only about the COVID-19 Pandemic!": Future Post-COVID-19 Expectations of Young People in Turkey

517.4 Mumita TANJEELA, *East West University, Bangladesh* and Masum BILLAH, *Department of Sociology, East West University, Dhaka, Bangladesh*
How Students Developed Coping Strategies during COVID-19? a Sociological Study Among University Level Students in Dhaka City, Bangladesh

517.5 Justyna SARNOWSKA, *SWPS University, Poland* and Justyna KAJTA, *SWPS University, Poland*
Planning for the Future in the Shadow of the Crisis: Young Women's Gendered Transitions-to-Adulthood in Poland during COVID-19

JS-128 Approaching Planetary Youth Research

Committees: WG01 *Sociology of Local-Global Relations (Host)*; RC34 *Sociology of Youth*

See Joint Session Details for JS-128.

17:30-19:20

518 Across Youth Emotions and Aspirations: Educational Institutions, Inner Entrepreneurship and Social Imaginaries

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sophie AGULHON, *Paris 8 Vincennes-Saint-Denis University, France*; Evelyne BAILLERGEAU, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Gerardo ROMO, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico*

Chairs: Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina* and Howard WILLIAMSON, *University of South Wales, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

518.1 Alexandre ZARIAS, *Fundação Joaquim Nabuco, Brazil* and Luiz JUNIOR, *UFPE, Brazil*

Youth and Their Future Aspirations: Reflections on the Relationship between School and Inner Entrepreneurship

518.2 Sari ALFI-NISSAN, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel* and Michal PAGIS, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel*

Glitches in the Discourse of Aspiration: Between Enterprise and Compromise

518.3 Sampson BLAIR, *SUNY Buffalo, USA*
Adolescents' Perceptions of Spousal, Parental, and Worker Self-Efficacy: Examining Gender Differences in Their Views of Future Adult Roles

518.4 Ewa KRZAKLEWSKA, *Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland*

Emotions and Mobility – Changing Social Imaginaries of Study Abroad

518.5 Dr. Mouneshwar BADIGER, *SSCA Government First Grade College K. K. Koppa, Belagavi, Karnataka State, India, India*
Implications of Modernity on Cultural Practices of Indian Youth

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

518.6 Walkens SAINVAL, *Paris Dauphine - PSL University, France*

Investigating Youth's Social Imaginaries in an Elite Educational Institution

518.7 Evelyne BAILLERGEAU, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands*

How Young People Frame Alternative Futures: The Power of Social Interactions and Context in European Secondary School Settings

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

519 Digital Citizenship and Digital Skills of Young People (1)

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Airi-Alina ALLASTE, *Tallinn University, Estonia* and Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany*

Chair: Airi-Alina ALLASTE, *Tallinn University, Estonia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

519.1 Julia COFFEY, *University of Newcastle, Australia, Australia*
Editing the Self: Understanding Young People's Digital Self-Image and Editing Practices

519.2 Kenichi ITO, *Gunma University, Japan*
A Prerequisite for Digital Citizenship: Health Problems Associated with the Problematic Internet Use

519.3 Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany* and Stepanka KADERA, *Ludwig-Maximilian-University Munich, Germany*
Critical Digital Skills of Young People: Social Disadvantages Continued Online?

519.4 Pawel ZALEWSKI, *University of Warsaw, Faculty of Sociology, Poland*
Class Differences in Digital Capital Accumulation: How Social Background Dictates Digital Socialisation of Young Adults in Poland

519.5 Alexandra JAMES, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia*; Andrea WALING, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia*; Jennifer POWER, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia* and Gene LIM, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia*
Self-Reflection, Curiosity and Identity Practice in Digital Sexual Health Curation

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

519.6 Aleksejs SNITNIKOVS, *Riga Technical University, Latvia*; Ilze KOROLEVA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia* and Aleksandrs ALEKSANDROVS, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, University of Latvia, Latvia*
The Patterns of Youth's Usage of the Internet and the Emerging Learning Styles: The Case of Latvia

10:30-12:20

520 Digital Citizenship and Digital Skills of Young People (2)

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany* and Airi-Alina ALLASTE, *Tallinn University, Estonia*

Chair: Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

520.1 Hao ZHENG, *Deakin University, Australia*
Queer International Students' Self-Expression and Civic Engagement on Social Network Sites

520.2 Jerome CLEOFAS, *De La Salle University, Philippines*
Digital Citizenship and Global Civic Engagement Among Young Filipino Netizens

520.3 Brady ROBARDS, *Monash University, Australia* and Darren GRAF, *Monash University, Australia*
Young people's social media use in the context of imagined employment futures

520.4 Airi-Alina ALLASTE, *Tallinn University, Estonia*
Becoming (digital) Citizen in Estonia. New Migrants' Perception of Their Integration and Participation

520.5 Hang LI, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*; Chi Fai CHUI, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*; Wang On LI, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*; Tak Sang CHOW, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong* and Ho Shing CHEUNG, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*
Social Media Use, Prosocialness, Life Satisfaction and Political Participation of Hong Kong Young People

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

520.6 Jose GUTIERREZ, *Universidad de Valladolid, Spain*
Social Media Lab. a Media Education and Citizenship Project

12:30-14:20

JS-148 Language on/of Youth Under COVID-19 Pandemic

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society (Host)*; RC34 *Sociology of Youth*

See Joint Session Details for JS-148.

14:30-16:20

521 Young People, the 'crisis of Democracy' and Political Transformation

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Rob WATTS, *RMIT, Australia* and Judith BESSANT, *RMIT University, Australia*

Chairs: Sarah PICKARD, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France* and Sharlene SWARTZ, *University of Fort Hare, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

521.1 Janina SUPPERS, *University of Waikato, Germany*
Young People's Emerging Democratic Participation: A Mixed-Methods Case Study Exploring 'Youthful Politics' in a Rural Community in Germany

521.2 Georgios KYROGLOU, *University of Bristol - UK, United Kingdom* and Matt HENN, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*
Young Political Consumers between the Individual and the Collective: Evidence from the UK and Greece

521.3 Cécile VAN DE VELDE, *Université de Montréal, Canada*
Listening to Anger: Youth Voices and the Transformation of Democracy

521.4 Syafiqah ABDUL RAHIM, *Malaysian Youth Council, Malaysia*
Exploring Safe Space for Collective Democratic Practice in All about Girls

521.5 Debadatta CHAKRABORTY, *University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA*
Gendered-Racialized Phobic Coalitions: Transnational Authoritarianism, Youth Mobilization and Nationalist Politics of the Indian Diaspora in the US

RC35

Conceptual and Terminological Analysis

Program Coordinators: David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany* and Arthur BUENO, *University of Frankfurt, Germany*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

522 Phenomenology and Critical Theory

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Jochen DREHER, *University of Konstanz, Germany* and Alexis Emanuel GROS, *University of Buenos Aires, Argentina*

Chair: Craig BROWNE, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

522.1 Jochen DREHER, *University of Konstanz, Germany*
Critical Phenomenology and the Life-World

522.2 Ken TAKAKUSA, *Keio University, Japan*
Prescientific Experience As a Ground for Critical Theory: Schutz, Habermas, and Honneth

522.3 Carlos Daniel BELVEDERE, *Universidad Nacional de General Sarmiento, Argentina*
Five Frankfurtian Topics in the Work of Alfred Schutz

522.4 Alexis Emanuel GROS, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
The Role of Doxa in Contemporary Critical Theory

17:30-19:20

523 Social Cohesion: Political Discourse and Sociological Conceptualization I

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Arthur BUENO, *University of Passau, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

523.1 David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*
The Social Cohesion Bias: Conceptual Blind Spots in the Contemporary Discourse on Societal Integration

523.2 Arne KOEVEL, *University of Bremen, Germany* and Stefan HOLUBEK-SCHAUM, *University Bremen, Germany*
Revisiting Parsons: Social Integration through Consensus and Conformity Theoretical and Empirical Explorations

523.3 Natalie GRIMM, *Sociological Research Institute Goettingen (SOFI), Germany*; Andrea HENSE, *Sociological Research Institute Goettingen (SOFI), Germany* and Ina KAUFHOLD, *Sociological Research Institute Goettingen (SOFI), Germany*
Reconstructions of Different Understandings of Social Cohesion and the Experiences of Different Status Groups

523.4 Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile* and Ignacio CACERES, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Concepts, Measurement and Indicators of Social Cohesion: A Longitudinal Perspective

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

524 Conviviality/Convivialisme Studies and the Renewal of Sociology

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Sergio COSTA, *Rudesheimerstr. 54-56, Germany* and Juan PIOVANI, *National University of La Plata / National Scientific and Technical Research Council, Argentina*

Chair: Mariana TEIXEIRA, *CEBRAP (Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning), Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

524.1 Katharina-Victoria PEREZ-HAMMERLE, *The University of New South Wales, Australia* and Katie MOON, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
The Real Nature of Conviviality Is Onto-Epistemological

524.2 Clara RUVITUSO, *Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut, Berlin, Germany*
The Production and Circulation of Knowledges Under the Lens Conviviality-Inequality: Topics for Sociological Research and Challenges

524.3 Juan PIOVANI, *Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina*
The Idea of Conviviality and Its Methodological Implications

524.4 Sergio COSTA, *Rudesheimerstr. 54-56, Germany*
Climate Crisis, Anthropocentrism and the Renewal of Sociology

524.5 Elis DE AQUINO, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Perception of Inequalities and Conviviality in Higher Education: Narratives of University Students from Rio De Janeiro's Periphery

17:30-19:20

525 Social Cohesion: Political Discourse and Sociological Conceptualization II

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: David STRECKER, *Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

525.1 Stephan SKOLARSKI, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
The Rise of Populism and the Threat to Social Cohesion

525.2 Aliye KELESOGLU, *University of Malaya, Malaysia*
How Can Social Capital be Detrimental: An Investigation of the Malaysia Case

525.3 Fabio BRAUN CARRASCO, *Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany*
The "Social" As Normative Category

525.4 Gustavo LIMA E SILVA, *University of São Paulo, Brazil*
A Phenomenology of Injustice: Iris Marion Young on the Experiential Grounds of Critique

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

526 Elusive Concepts of the Social. Simultaneous Analysis from Different Socio-Cultural Contexts.

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Alejandro BIALAKOWSKY, *Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani - Facultad de Ciencias Sociales - Universidad de Buenos Aires - CONICET, Argentina*; Pablo DE MARINIS, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani, CONICET, Argentina* and Gina ZABLUDOVSKY, *UNAM, Mexico*

Chair: Fabio BRAUN CARRASCO, *Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

526.1 Pablo DE MARINIS, *Universidad de Buenos Aires - CONICET, Argentina* and Alejandro BIALAKOWSKY, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Elusive Concepts in Sociology? a Simultaneous Approach between "Southern" and "Northern" Reflections about Society, Community, Mass/Crowd and People

526.2 Gina ZABLUDOVSKY, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
El Concepto De Carisma

526.3 Naoki ISO, *Tokyo University of the Arts, Japan*
Social Knowledge and Understanding: A Critique of the Native Point of View

526.4 Eugenia FRAGA, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*; Juan TROVERO, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina* and Fermín ÁLVAREZ RUIZ, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
The Concept of Masses in Quijano, Marcuse and Portantiero

15:30-17:20

JS-69 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part I

Committees: RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-69.

17:30-19:20

JS-79 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part II

Committees: RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host)*; RC16 *Sociological Theory*

See Joint Session Details for JS-79.

19:30-20:50

527 RC35 Business Meeting

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-83 Can the New be Born? Critical Theory in Times of Interregnum. Part III

Committees: RC16 *Sociological Theory (Host)*; RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis*

See Joint Session Details for JS-83.

10:30-12:20

528 Critical Theories Revisited: Immanent Critique and Coloniality

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Stefan FORNOS KLEIN, *Universidade de Brasilia (UnB), Brazil* and Mariana TEIXEIRA, *CEBRAP (Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning), Brazil*

Chair: Stefan FORNOS KLEIN, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

528.1 Mariana OLIVEIRA, *Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil*
Subalternity As a Social Figure of Nonidentity: Spivak and Adorno

528.2 Felipe GRETSCHISCHKIN, *University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*
Politics As Protest: Decolonization and Praxis Around 1968

528.3 Mariana TEIXEIRA, *CEBRAP (Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning), Brazil*
Three Models for Decolonizing Critical Theory

17:30-19:20

529 The Peripheral Turn in Sociology: Rethinking Sociology As Nonexclusionary and Inclusive. Part I

Location: 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Mariana TEIXEIRA, *Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning, Brazil*

Chair: Stefan FORNOS KLEIN, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

529.1 Marcelo Carvalho ROSA, *UFRRJ, Brazil*
Ontoformativity: Southern Challenges to Peripheral Sociologies and Social Theories

529.2 Jeremy SIMPSON, *National Library of Australia, Australia*
Reclaiming Bourdieu for a Decolonised Sociology: The Challenge of the Peripheral-Postcolonial Turn

529.3 Glen Christian TACASA, *University of the Philippines Los Banos, Philippines*
Towards a National Democratic Sociological Imagination

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

530 New Horizon for the Memory Studies**Location:** 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Sachiko TAKITA-ISHII, *Yokohama City University, Japan* and Veridiana CORDEIRO, *University of São Paulo, Brazil***Chair:** Alejandro BIALAKOWSKY, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****530.1** Sachiko TAKITA-ISHII, *Yokohama City University, Japan*
Collective Memory Re-Considered--Memories of Japanese American Incarceration Looking through the Oriental Thoughts and Philosophy**530.2** Rieko SEMBA, *Yokohama City University, Japan*
The Relationship between "Ba" and Memory in Art-Based Research: Reflections from Practice with Filipino-Japanese Immigrants Second-Generation**530.3** Kelcie VERCEL, *Augustana University, USA* and Spencier CIARALLI, *Augustana University, USA*
Learning Sexual Pleasure: The Discovery of Affordances As Tacit Knowledge Production

15:30-17:20

JS-129 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Innovation and Dynamism**Committees:** *RC02 Economy and Society (Host); RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis*

See Joint Session Details for JS-129.

17:30-19:20

JS-135 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Relational and Cultural Analysis**Committees:** *RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-135.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

JS-138 Brokering Novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Societal Variation, Entrepreneurship**Committees:** *RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis (Host); RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-138.

10:30-12:20

531 The Peripheral Turn in Sociology: Rethinking Sociology As Nonexclusionary and Inclusive. Part II**Location:** 107 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Mariana TEIXEIRA, *Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning, Brazil***Chair:** Mariana TEIXEIRA, *CEBRAP (Brazilian Center for Analysis and Planning), Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****531.1** Stefan FORNOS KLEIN, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil*
Contributions By Lélia Gonzalez: Antiracism, Critique and Resistance**531.2** Fabio SANTOS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Intersectional Dialogues in Contested Canons: Lessons from W.E.B. Du Bois, Ida B. Wells, and Anna Julia Cooper**531.3** Camila MOZZINI-ALISTER, *University of the Sunshine Coast, Australia*
Under the Same Southern Cross: Exploring a New Sociological Model from the Intersections between Brazil and Australia

RC36

Alienation Theory and Research

Program Coordinators: Vessela MISHEVA, *Uppsala University, Sweden* and Dirk MICHEL-SCHERTGES, *Aarhus University, Denmark*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

532 Globalization, Alienation and the Cultural Patterns of Right-Wing Extremism

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Dirk MICHEL-SCHERTGES, *Aarhus University, Denmark*

Chair: Dirk MICHEL-SCHERTGES, *Aarhus University, Denmark*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

532.1 Lauren LANGMAN, *Loyola University of Chicago, USA*
Neoliberal Globalization Alienation and Dialectic of Social Change

532.2 Miri GAL-EZER, *Kinneret College on the Sea of Galilee, Israel*
Israelis' "Ukraine Weltschmerz" Disobedience Vs Alienated "Miga" Enclave on the "Wrong Side of History"

532.3 Terry MALEY, *York University, Canada*
Alienation and Authoritarianism Today: A New Phase of the Neoliberal Counterrevolution

532.4 Ladan ADHAMI-DORRANI, *York University, Canada*
The Ingrained Emotional Alienation in Amor Mundi

15:30-17:20

JS-14 The Rise and Fall of Authoritarian Populisms (Hopefully)

Committees: RC36 *Alienation Theory and Research (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-14.

17:30-19:20

533 Irrational Rationality: Informational and Knowledge-Based Alienation

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil*

Chair: Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

533.2 Dirk MICHEL-SCHERTGES, *Aarhus University, Denmark*
Democracy, Authoritarianisms and Political Economy of Critique

533.3 Johan FAGERBERG, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Fuzzy Knowledge and Practice: The Case of Social Work Education

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

JS-31 Art and Alienation

Committees: RC37 *Sociology of Arts (Host)*; RC36 *Alienation Theory and Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-31.

15:30-17:20

534 Alienation in the 21st Century: Revisiting, Reevaluating, Recentering. Part I

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: David EMBRICK, *University of Connecticut, USA*

Chair: Vessela MISHEVA, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

534.1 Dirk MICHEL-SCHERTGES, *Aarhus University, Denmark*
Far Right Political Contra-Revolution and Critical Social Aesthetics

534.2 Sara MOHAMED, *James Cook University, Australia*
Metabolic Rifts through an Intersectional Lens and Restorative Practices As Ways in Which to Address Environmental Alienation

534.3 Tomas KUMLIN, *Malardalen university, Sweden* and Tanya JUKKALA, *Malardalen university, Sweden*
Towards a Late Modern Existential Perspective on Alienation

17:30-19:20

535 Existential Perspectives on Alienation

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Tanya JUKKALA, *Malardalen university, Sweden* and Tomas KUMLIN, *Malardalen university, Sweden*

Chair: Tanya JUKKALA, *Malardalen university, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

535.1 Sunjin OH, *The University of Tokyo, Japan*
Responsibility for the Other As Prime Factor of Alienation from Time

535.2 Veronica GRONLUND, *Gothenburg university, Sweden*
Alienated Love in Patriarchal, Consumer Capitalism

535.3 Ramon MENENDEZ, *La Trobe University, Australia*
What Is It to 'be Authentic'? a Sociological Definition Rooted in Qualitative Data

535.4 Andrew BLASKO, *Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria*
The Ignorance of Knowledge: Ideology and the Humanistic Context of Science

535.5 Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil*
The Unnatural Divide between Culture and Nature: A Unified Sociological Approach to Spinoza on Alienation Theory

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

536 Flexible Employment and Alienation**Location:** M8 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Lu ZHENG, *Tsinghua University, China***Chair:** Andrew BLASKO, *Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

536.1 Zhaolun FAN, *Tsinghua University, China* and Lu ZHENG, *Texas A&M University, China*
Individualization and Familyism: A Comparative Study of China and Sweden

536.2 Andreas KJORLING, *University of Gavle, Sweden*; Gunnar BERGSTROM, *University of Gavle, Sweden*; Sven SVENSSON, *University of Gavle, Sweden* and Anna BERG JANSSON, *Lulea Technical University, Sweden*
Commodity or Producer? - Structural Views on Temporary Agency Workers within the Swedish Manufacturing Industry.

536.3 Tatiana GAVRILYUK, *University of Tyumen, Russian Federation*
Emotional Labor and Alienation of Frontline Service Workers: The Case of the Russian Food Service Industry

15:30-17:20

537 Alienation in the 21st Century: Revisiting, Reevaluating, Recentering. Part II**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** M8 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** David EMBRICK, *University of Connecticut, USA***Chair:** Vessela MISHEVA, *Uppsala University, Sweden***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

537.1 Tanya JUKKALA, *Malardalen university, Sweden*
Alienation Among Young Women in Marginalized Suburban Areas

537.2 Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil*
Nature-Related Alienation in the Business Class: Combining Social Representations and Collectivities Theory

537.3 Demet EVRENOSOGLU, *York University, Turkey*
A Feminist Social Reproduction Lens on Alienation

19:30-20:50

538 RC36 Business Meeting**Location:** M8 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Vessela MISHEVA, *Uppsala University, Sweden***Thursday 29 June**

10:30-12:20

539 New/Old Forms of Alienation and Resistance Under Advanced Neoliberalism**Location:** M8 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Terry MALEY, *York University, Canada***Chair:** Terry MALEY, *York University, Canada***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

539.1 Rodney DOODY, *York University, Canada*
Uncomfortably Numb: On the Administration and Experience of Alienation in the 21st Century

539.2 Olga SIMONOVA, *Higher School of Economics (HSE), Russian Federation*
The Contradictory Emotional Logic of Contemporary Therapeutic Culture: Between Emancipation and Alienation

539.3 Maor LEVITIN, *York University, Canada*
Authoritarianism, Alienation, and the Question of Left Leadership

539.4 Yen MAI, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Youth Civic Actions in an Authoritarian State: The Case of Vietnam

Friday 30 June**540 The Covid-19 Pandemic and Alienation****Location:** M8 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Andrew BLASKO, *Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria***Chair:** Andrew BLASKO, *Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

540.1 David EMBRICK, *University of Connecticut, USA* and Johnny WILLIAMS, *Trinity College, USA*
Alienation, Racism, & Democracy for Palestine

540.2 Vessela MISHEVA, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
Social and Cultural Framing of Policy Responses and Reactions to the First Wave of the Covid-19 Pandemic

540.3 Savita SINGH, *Indira Gandhi National Open University, India*
Alienation, Work, and Pandemic: Precarious India

540.4 Zhaolun FAN, *Tsinghua University, China*
Perceived Health Risk during the Covid Pandemic: A Sociological Approach

540.5 Silvia PEZZOLI, *University of Florence, Italy* and Carlotta BIZZARRI, *Università degli Studi di Firenze, Italy*
Women in between. the Careers and Biographical Adaptation of Italian Professional Women in the Pandemic

RC37

Sociology of Arts

Program Coordinator: Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

541 Societal representations in the arts

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Marisol FACUSE, *University of Chile, Chile*

Chair: Marisol FACUSE, *University of Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

Marcus REPA, *Sao Paulo University, Brazil*

Androids and Humans: Representations of Artificial Intelligences

541.1 Hugo BISPO, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
The Construction of Neoliberal Subjectivity: A Film Analysis of Fight Club

541.2 Shinichi AIZAWA, *Sophia University, Japan*
Examining the Traditional Rite of Inheriting Traditional Arts within the Social Class Structure in Japan's Regional Cities

541.3 Yu-cheng LIU, *Soochow University, Taiwan*
A Renewed Experience of Sense De/Synchronization: Inspiration from Digital Art

541.4 Michelle CATANZARO, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
'Burn the Patriarchy, Not the Planet': Female Participation and Visual Forms of Activism in the School Strikes for Climate Protests.

19:30-20:50

542 Theatres and Public Sphere

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*

Chair: Marisol FACUSE, *University of Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

542.1 Jeffrey HALLEY, *The University of Texas at San Antonio, USA*
Dada and the Experience of Shock: Culture and Everyday Life

542.2 Naomi GILHUIS, *Radboud University, Netherlands*
Dionysus at Play: Exploring the Potential of Theatre Plays As Vehicle for Moral Burden-Sharing By Veterans in the Wake of Moral Injury.

542.3 Matthew M CHEW, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
A Relational Framework for Analyzing Action-Oriented Entertainment Narratives: Chinese Fantasy Webnovels' Framing of Conflicts in Terms of 'the Oppressed Versus Oppressors' Instead of 'Good Versus Evil'

542.4 Marek SKOVAJSA, *Charles University, Czech Republic*
Classical Music's Democratic Natural: Dvořák in Europe and America

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

JS-31 Art and Alienation

Committees: RC37 Sociology of Arts (Host); RC36 Alienation Theory and Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-31.

15:30-17:20

543 Art and War

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Paulo MENEZES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil, Brazil*

Chair: Ana Lucia TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

543.1 Jesse CARLSON, *Acadia University, Canada*
National Imaginaries and Comparative Cultural Sociology through TV Series

543.2 Mathieu ARBOGAST, *Cems (EHESS) & Cresppa-GTM, France*
Social Acceptability of Contradictory Gender Norms: Lessons Learned from a Socio-Demographic Analysis of TV Series

543.3 Mauro ROVAI, *Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil*
Endless Exile – Alain Resnais's the War Is over

543.4 Alexandre DIALLO, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*
TV series in the era globalized threat: Killing Eve in the eye of feminist modern discourse.

543.5 Michela DONATELLI, *University Roma Tre, Italy*
The Conflict Dimension of the Public Library

17:30-19:20

JS-53 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development

Committees: RC03 Community Research (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts

See Joint Session Details for JS-53.

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

544 Arts and Democracy

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Paulo MENEZES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil, Brazil*

Chair: Jeffrey HALLEY, *University of Texas at San Antonio, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

544.1 Malfrid Irene HAGEN, *Independent researcher, Norway*
Sincere or Cynical? Analyzing the Public Discourse on Four Controversial Art Projects in Light of Goffman

544.2 Ana Lucia TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*
The Interpretative Challenge Posed By the New Peripheral Literatures: The Brazilian Case

544.3 Ayca KURTOGLU, *Acibadem Mehmet Ali Aydinlar University, Turkey* and Özgür Mutlu ULUS, *Acibadem Mehmet Ali Aydinlar University, Turkey*
Reading Democracy in Turkey through Political Approaches to Music

544.4 Aparupa PATNAIK, *KALINGA INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY, India*
Soft POWER, a New Race for Democracies

544.5 Volker KIRCHBERG, *Lueneburg, Germany*
Real Utopias – Arts and Culture As Catalysts

17:30-19:20

JS-81 Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part I

Committees: *RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-81.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

545 Literature, Conflict and Social Relations

Language: English, French

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ana Lucia TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*

Chair: Ana Lucia TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

545.1 Linjie ZHANG, *University of Warwick, United Kingdom*
The Oppressed in Indian Society and the Eros Turn of the Community: On Arundhati Roy's the Ministry of Utmost Happiness

545.2 Dilek HATTATOGLU, *Independent scholar, Turkey* and Ahu KARASULU, *Independent scholar, Turkey*
Under the Same Sky: Introductory Notes for Life-Imprisoned Kurdish Literature in Turkey

545.3 Rodrigo CZAJKA, *Universidade Federal do Paraná (UFPR), Brazil*
La Signification Politique De La Critique Littéraire Dans LES Œuvres D'astrojildo Pereira ET D'alvaro Lins

545.4 Ibrahim ABRAHAM, *Federation University Australia, Australia*
Suffering Subjectivity, Spiritual Insecurity and Coming-of-Age in the Literatures of the South

545.5 Ana MIJIC, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Michael PARZER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
The Art of Arriving: Reframing 'refugee Integration' through Literature

10:30-12:20

546 Arts in Cultural Diplomacy

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David HEBERT, *Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Norway*

Chair: Eduardo DE LA FUENTE, *University of South Australia, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

546.1 Ryan MARTIN, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
The Affordances of Musical Participation and Improvisation for Conflict Transformation

546.2 Laurence LAROCHELLE, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*
Transnational TV Series and Cultural Diplomacy: A Case Study

546.3 Frederic RAMEL, *SciencesPo, France*
Beyond Bellephonic Sound: Musical Diplomacies in the Ukraine War

546.4 Paula Costa DE CARVALHO, *University of São Paulo, Brazil*
Beyond Carnegie Hall: Strategies and Mediations in the Promotion of Bossa Nova in the United States

15:30-17:20

547 Art and Theory

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ana Lucia TEIXEIRA, *Federal University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*

Chair: Mauro ROVAL, *Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

547.1 Helmut STAUBMANN, *University of Innsbruck, Austria*
Jean Marie Guyau: Theoretical Foundations for Social Aesthetics Beyond Durkheim and Weber

547.2 Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*
New Entanglements of Religions, Politics, Economies and Cultures: The Peculiarities of the Theatre As Public Sphere

547.3 Jini KIM, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Creative Resistance, Oblivion, and Un-Representability of Social Trauma

547.4 Angelo MARTINGO, *University of Minho, Portugal*
Theorising the Language of Emotions: Arguments for a Neurosociology of Music:

547.5 Sohini CHANDA, *Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India* and Archana PATNAIK, *Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India*
Flexible Identity, Innovative Strategies, and Survival of Dänger Putul Nach: A Case Study from West Bengal, India

17:30-19:20

JS-113 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development IICommittees: *RC03 Community Research (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts*

See Joint Session Details for JS-113.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

548 Museos Inclusivos, Polifónicos y Participativos: Desafíos Para Las Instituciones Museales En El Siglo XXI**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Marisol FACUSE, *University of Chile, Chile* and Raíza CAVALCANTI, *Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile***Chair:** Malfrid Irene HAGEN, *Independent researcher, Norway***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

548.1 Marisol FACUSE, *University of Chile, Chile* and Raíza CAVALCANTI, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*
Museos Feministas: Discursos Críticos y Transformaciones En Las Prácticas Institucionales En Los Museos De Arte Del Siglo XXI

548.2 Dee BRITTON, *State University of New York, Empire State University, USA*
Monumental Dedication to the Confederacy: The 21st Century Edition

10:30-12:20

549 Solidarity in Arts and Culture**Location:** 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy***Chair:** Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

549.1 Alice NEUSIEDLER, *Yale University, USA*
Organizing for Solidarity with Participative Art Practices

549.2 Anna HICKEY-MOODY, *RMIT University, Australia*; Belinda JOHNSON, *RMIT University, Australia* and Stephanie ANDREWS, *RMIT University, Australia*
Embodied Archives of Down Syndrome: Making Cultural Histories

549.3 Carl Johnson ANACIN, *Griffith University, Australia*
Sariling Sikap, Suporta Lokal: The Do-It-Ourselves (DIO) Ethos in Online Communities of Independent Songwriters

549.4 Jaka PRIMORAC, *Institute for Development and International Relations (IRMO), Croatia*
The Limits of Project Work: Cultural Labour in the Midst of the Pandemic

15:30-17:20

550 Analyzing Films and Series As a Way to Social Knowledge**Location:** 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Paulo MENEZES, *University of São Paulo, Brazil***Chair:** Eduardo DE LA FUENTE, *University of South Australia, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

550.1 Siyoon LEE, *Sungkyunkwan University, Republic of Korea*
Hayao Miyazaki on Mimesis: Structural Asymmetry in Storytelling and Its Meaning of Social Critique

550.2 Priyam SINHA, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Social Disability As the New Bollywood: Notes on the Scripting Process

550.3 Rebeca HIPPERTT, *Universidade Federal de São Paulo, Brazil*
The Virtual Dimension in Naqoyqatsi: Impacts on Contemporaneity

550.4 Aleksandra BIERNACKA, *Institute of Philosophy and Sociology PAS, Poland*
Cross-Cultural Film Remakes' Use of Stereotypes As a Window for Probing a Social and Cultural Specificity. Example of "Brothers" By Jim Sheridan (2009) and "Brodre" By Susanne Bier (2004).

550.5 Heather MCLAUGHLIN, *Oklahoma State University, USA*
Laughing at Them or with Them? Analyzing Sexual Harassment in Workplace Comedy Television Series

17:30-19:20

551 Place and the Sociology of Art**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Eduardo DE LA FUENTE, *University of South Australia, Australia***Chair:** Jeffrey HALLEY, *University of Texas at San Antonio, USA***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

551.1 Laura HARRIS, *University of Southampton, United Kingdom*
Curating Windows, Creating Cultures: A Place-Based Analysis of a New Curatorial Trend

551.2 Ana GONCALVES, *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, CRIA, Portugal*
Placing Cultural Heritage and Inheritance into the Alley

551.3 Katrina SANDBACH, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Western Sydney Reimagined

551.4 Matjaz URSIC, *University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences, Slovenia*
When Is Local Too Local? - New Localism and the Potentials of Immovable Cultural Heritage

551.5 Sabrina PARRACHO SANT'ANNA, *Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Tensions and Disputes over the Glocality at the Inhotim Museum for Contemporary Art

551.6 Eduardo DE LA FUENTE, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Texturology: Knowing and Appreciating Places through Their Surface Textures

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

552 RC37 Business Meeting

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

RC38

Biography and Society

Program Coordinators: Maria POHN-LAUGGAS, *University of Göttingen, Germany* and Johannes BECKER, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-2 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part I

Committees: WG08 Society and Emotions (Host); RC38 Biography and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-2.

15:30-17:20

JS-8 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part II

Committees: RC38 Biography and Society (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions

See Joint Session Details for JS-8.

17:30-19:20

553 New Developments in Biographical Research

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Roswitha BRECKNER, *Univ of Vienna, Inst Sociology, Austria* and Kathy DAVIS, *VU University, Netherlands*

Chair: Georgios TSIOLIS, *University of Crete, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

553.1 Laura FENTON, *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*
'Can We Just Take a Break?': The Methodological Merits and Ethical Labour of Creative Biographical Interviewing

553.2 Elisabeth MAYER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Visual Biographies – Looking at the Images of a Lifetime As a Way to Do Biographical Research

553.3 Piotr SZENAJCH, *Lodz University, Poland*
Using the Photographer's Eye. Visual Competence As a Cognitive Tool in Biographical Research

553.4 Simone FEICHTER, *Department of Sociology, Austria*
The Potential of Musical Shaping of Biographical Experiences – Methodological Challenges and Methodical Approach

553.5 Miriam SCHAEFER, *Georg-August-University Goettingen, Germany* and Maria POHN-LAUGGAS, *University of Göttingen, Germany*
Of Glue Dots and Familial Relationships: Reflections on Family Sculptures in Biographical Multigenerational Research

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

553.6 Ana GONCALVES, *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, CRIA, Portugal*
Flashes of Lives: Photography As a Tool in Life and Family (hi)Stories

553.7 Izabela KORBIEL, *Vienna University, Austria*
Life on a Map. Creative Methods in Biographical Research.

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

554 Biographical Research – Contemporary Methodological and Ethical Concerns

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Kaja KAZMIERSKA, *University of Lodz, Poland* and Piotr SZENAJCH, *Lodz University, Poland*

Co-chairs: Kaja KAZMIERSKA, *University of Lodz, Poland* and Piotr SZENAJCH, *Lodz University, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

554.1 Roswitha BRECKNER, *Univ of Vienna, Inst Sociology, Austria*
Biographical Research with Visual Biographies in Social Media – Methodological and Ethical Challenges

554.2 Umut EREL, *PO Box 252, Walton Hall, United Kingdom*; Eirini KAPTANI, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*; Margaret O'NEILL, *University College Cork, Ireland* and Tracey REYNOLDS, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom*
Participatory Theatre As Research Method

554.3 Lisa MORAN, *South East Technological University, Ireland* and Liam O'FARRELL, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
Exploring Ethical and Technological Issues in Online Interviewing during COVID-19: A Thematic Analysis of International Research

554.4 Adam CARTER, *The University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
Lessons from the Rupaul's Drag Race Shady Edit: Ethical Storytelling in the Presentation of Video Methods Research

15:30-17:20

JS-38 Collective Memories of Violence: Remembering in Families and Local Communities

Committees: RC38 Biography and Society (Host); RC56 Historical Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-38.

17:30-19:20

555 Biographical Methods in Applied Social Research

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Michaela KOETTIG, *Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (FRA-UAS), Germany*; Priscila SUSIN, *PUCRS, Brazil* and Débora RINALDI, *Universidade Pontifícia Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*

Chair: Michaela KOETTIG, *Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

555.1 Eren YETKIN, *Koblenz University of Applied Sciences, Germany*

Youth Co-Research and Memory Work – about the Biographical Data Flourishing in Participatory Research Settings

555.2 Débora RINALDI, *Universidade Pontifícia Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*

Public Policy Analysis Via Qualitative and Biographical Research: Possibilities, Limitations, and Contributions

555.3 Priscila SUSIN, *PUCRS, Brazil* and Gabriele BACHI, *Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Episodic Interviews and Reconstructive Analysis in the Investigation of Safety Events in the Oil and Gas Industry in Brazil

555.4 Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina*
Femicide, Offenders and Trajectories: Identification of Prevention Points Based on Biographical Narratives of Perpetrators

555.5 Ornella LARENZA, *University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland - SUPSI, Switzerland*
Coping with No Access to Social Assistance: A Qualitative Longitudinal Study on Single Parents' Life Course in Switzerland

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

556 Conceptual Challenges in Biographical Research

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Susan BELL, *Drexel University, USA* and Lena INOWLOCKI, *Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany*

Chair: Lena INOWLOCKI, *Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

556.1 Gwendolyn GILLIERON, *LinCS, Université de Strasbourg, Morocco*
'I'm Not a Problem!' – Negotiating between Concepts of Analysis and the Perspectives of the Participants.

556.2 Anna SCHNITZER, *Martin-Luther-Universitaet Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Categories and Naming Practices in (Biographical) Migration Research

15:30-17:20

557 Same Interview, Different Perspectives – Invited Session

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Lena INOWLOCKI, *Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany*; Monica MASSARI, *University of Milan, Italy* and Gwendolyn GILLIERON, *LinCS, Université de Strasbourg, Morocco*

Chair: Monica MASSARI, *University of Milan, Italy*

Co-Chair: Gwendolyn GILLIERON, *LinCS, Université de Strasbourg, Morocco*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

557.1 Kathy DAVIS, *VU University, Netherlands*
Dreaming in Conditions of Precarity

557.2 Georgios TSIOLIS, *University of Crete, Greece*
Constructing a Singular Profile As a Freelancer: The Tension between Independence and Self-Exploitation

557.3 Priscila SUSIN, *PUCRS, Brazil*
Reconstruction of James' Biographical Case: Work Paths between Struggles and Opportunities

557.4 Me-Linh RIEMANN, *Catholic University of Leuven, Germany*
The Case of James: A Migrant's Path into the Gig Economy

17:30-19:20

558 The Social Construction of Migrants: Contested (Hi-)Stories of Migration from the Perspective of Biographical Research

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Steve TONAH, *University of Ghana, Ghana*; Arne WORM, *University of Goettingen, Germany* and Lucas CE SANGALLI, *University of Goettingen, Germany*

Chair: Anna SCHNITZER, *Martin-Luther-Universitaet Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

558.1 Ombretta INGRASCI, *University of Milan, Italy* and Federica CABRAS, *Univesrità degli Studi di Milano, Italy*
The Gendered Construction of "Bureaucratic Truths". Life Stories of Nigerian Migrants in Front of the Asylum Commissions in Italy

558.2 Johannes BECKER, *University of Leipzig, Germany*
The Varying Importance of Migration in City Life. a Comparative View on Biographies and Family (Hi)Stories in Two Cities in the Middle East

558.3 Daniel GUIGUI, *University College Dublin, Ireland*
Welcoming the Other: Comparing Munich and Dublin Based Hosts' Biographic Narratives of Cosmopolitan Hospitality in Response to the Russian-Ukrainian War

558.4 Ingrid BOSSELDAL, *Department of Educational Sciences, Lund University, Sweden*
Neither Swedish/American, Nor Chinese – Swedish and American Adoptees Reflects on Their Lack of Belonging

19:30-20:50

559 RC38 Business Meeting

Location: M13 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

15:30-17:20

560 Biographical Research in Extreme Places and Difficult to Reach Areas: Challenges and Strategies

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Karina REIF, *PUCRS, Brazil*; Hermilio SANTOS, *Apt 504 A, Brazil* and Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina*

Chair: Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina*

Co-Chair: Hermilio SANTOS, *Apt 504 A, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

560.1 Hermilio SANTOS, *Apt 504 A, Brazil*
Prisons, Border Spaces and Favelas: Building Access and Trust Strategy to Biographical Research

560.2 Lyudmila NURSE, *Oxford XXI think tank, United Kingdom*; Ian THOMPSON, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom* and Iryna KUZINA, *V.N. Karazin Kharkiv University, Ukraine*
Biographical Research Near the Front Line: Strategies, Challenges and Positionality

560.3 Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina* and María Florencia SANTI, *Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas, Argentina*
When Fieldwork Becomes Problematic: Ethical Dilemmas in Programs for Men Who Have Used Violence Against Women

560.4 Liza ZUNIGA, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*
The Emotional Journey of Doing Life Stories in Chilean Prisons

560.5 Karina REIF, *PUCRS, Brazil* and Francisco SCHUSTER RODRIGUES, *PUCRS, Brazil*
Characteristics of Research on Ultra-Deepwater Oil and Gas Platforms

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

560.6 Raphaela DELLAZERI, *PUCRS, Brazil*
Investigación En La Frontera: El Viaje Para Llegar Al Pueblo Manchineri En La Selva Amazónica

560.7 Maria FIGUEROA, *Center of Anthropology and Ethnology Research, Mexico*
Community Gender Alert (ECG) : Decolonizing Quantitative Methodologies for Documenting Violence Against Indigenous Women in Mexico

17:30-19:20

JS-110 Spatial Scales and the Analysis of Biographies and Family (Hi)Stories

Committees: RC38 *Biography and Society (Host)*; RC21 *Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-110.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-114 Black Lives and the New Wave of Antiracist Mobilization within and across World Regions

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC38 *Biography and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-114.

10:30-12:20

561 Biographical Perspectives in the Research Field of Political Participation

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Irini SIOUTI, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt/Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences UAS, Germany* and Georgios TSIOLIS, *University of Crete, Greece*

Chair: Georgios TSIOLIS, *University of Crete, Greece*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

561.1 Irini SIOUTI, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt/Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences UAS, Germany*
Political Participation Processes Among the Younger Generation in Families of Labour Migrants in Germany

561.2 Alexandra ZAVVOU, *University of Crete, Greece*; Pavlos HATZOPOULOS, *Independent Researcher, Greece*; Nelli KAMBOURI, *Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences, Greece* and Eleftheria PAPASTEFANAKI, *University of Crete, Greece*
Feminist and Queer Activisms and the Transformation of Gender Studies in Greece: Encounters on Gender Related Violence.

561.3 Natalia WAECHTER, *Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Germany*
How to Become a Political Activist in the FFF Movement? Reflexion on Biographical Narratives of Young Activists.

15:30-17:20

562 Biography and Disaster: From Methodological Perspectives

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Tazuko KOBAYASHI, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan* and Gaku OSHIMA, *Meiji University, Japan*

Chair: Tazuko KOBAYASHI, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*

Co-Chair: Masaya NEMOTO, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

562.1 Fatih KAYA, *Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany*
Story-Telling Vs. Argumentation. Reconsidering the Importance of Argumentations in Narrative-Biographical Research

562.2 Yutaka IWADATE, *Bunkyo Gakuin University, Japan*
Small Traces of Disaster Experiences: Reading "the Tono Volunteer Diary"

562.3 Gaku OSHIMA, *Meiji University, Japan*
Continuing to Face the Unpredictable: Fukushima As a City Laboratory for a New Way of Life

562.4 Ryo SHOJI, *Toyo Gakuen University, Japan*
Applicability of the Biographical Approach to Resilience Theory: A Case Study of Returnees to an Evacuation-Order-Lifted Area in Fukushima after the Nuclear Power Station Accident

562.5 Jini KIM, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Social Disaster, Place, and Struggle for Collective Memory

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

563 Indigenous People's Experiences amid Socio-Historical Power Struggles

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Johanna SAGNER TAPIA, *Universidad de La Frontera, Chile*; Victoria TABOADA GOMEZ, *Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Germany* and Gabriela GARCES, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile*

Chair: Arne WORM, *University of Goettingen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

563.1 Denisse SEPULVEDA, *Haute école de travail social, Chile*
Mapuche People in Academia: Challenging Narratives about Displaced Indigenous Identities

563.2 Victoria TABOADA GOMEZ, *Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Germany*
Indigenous Women's Strategies Against Outsiderness: A Biographical Perspective on Historical Colonial Processes and Current Power Dynamics in the Paraguayan Chaco

563.3 Gabriela GARCES, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile* and Johanna SAGNER TAPIA, *Universidad de La Frontera, Chile*
Formación De La Identidad Étnica-Cultural En Biografías De Jóvenes Mapuche. Análisis Desde La Perspectiva Del Trauma-Histórico Transgeneracional.

12:30-14:20

JS-146 Gendered Intergenerational Experiences of Social Mobility in Migration

Committees: RC32 Women, Gender and Society (Host); RC38 Biography and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-146.

RC39

Sociology of Disasters

Program Coordinators: Michele COMPANION, *University of Colorado, USA* and Valerie INGHAM, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

564 Decolonizing Disasters Studies in the Global South: First-Hand Research Experiences

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Andrea LAMPIS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil* and Victor MARCHEZINI, *Brazilian Early Warning and Monitoring Center for Natural Disasters (CEMADEN), Brazil*

Chair: Andrea LAMPIS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

564.1 H. SAMARAWEEERA, *Department of Sociology, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka*
Understanding the Need for Decolonizing Disaster Recovery Process in Neoliberal Sri Lanka

564.2 Nayibe JIMENEZ PEREZ, *Universidad del Valle, Colombia*
Mechanisms Used By Local Bureaucracy for Disaster Risk Management: The Case of Local Government in Cali, Colombia.

564.3 Alvaro FEITOSA, *PPGCP/UFPI, Brazil* and Natanael SANTOS, *PPGS/UFSCar, Brazil*
Decolonizing Reparation: Post-Disaster Recognition's Strategies Raised By Affected Communities

564.4 Ayushi JAIN, *Ashank Desai Centre for Policy Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, India* and N.C. NARAYANAN, *Ashank Desai Centre for Policy Studies, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, India*
Green Neoliberalism in the Global South: Revisiting the Big Dam Debate in India

564.5 Maria angelika BALUNGAY, *University of Southern Mindanao, Philippines* and Melissa Lopez REYES, *De La Salle University, Philippines*
Poor Mental Health As a Correlate of Perceived Unmet Needs of Earthquake Survivors in Evacuation Camps: Posttraumatic Stress and Growth As Parallel Mediators

564.6 Cora HAGINO, *UFJF, Portugal*
EL Impacto De Cambios Climáticos EN La Reserva De Desarrollo Sostenible De Praia Do Aventureiro (ISLA GRANDE, BRASIL)

564.7 David TORRES, *National Institute of Anthropology and History, Mexico*
Relocation of Culturally Significant Values in the Recovery from Disasters

17:30-19:20

565 Overcoming Siloization Practices to Achieve All-of-Society-Based Inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction: Case Studies, Surveys and Theories

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Shigeo TATSUKI, *Doshisha University, Japan*

Chair: H. Tristan WU, *University of North Texas, USA*

Panelists: Aya TSUJIOKA, *Doshisha University, Japan*; Junko MORIYASU, *Hyogo Association of Certified Social Workers, Japan*; Miwako KITAMURA, *International Research Institute of Disaster Science, Tohoku University, Japan*; Michele COMPANION, *University of Colorado-Colorado Springs, USA* and Taku SUGANO, *Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

565.1 Aya TSUJIOKA, *Doshisha University, Japan* and Shigeo TATSUKI, *Doshisha University, Japan*
The Competencies of Inclusion Managers: From "Boundary Crossing" through "Boundary Spanning" Toward "Empowerment/Strength-Building"

565.2 Junko MORIYASU, *Hyogo Association of Certified Social Workers, Japan* and Shigeo TATSUKI, *Doshisha University, Japan*
Training and Empowerment of Social Service Professionals and Community Leaders for Inclusive Drr

565.3 Miwako KITAMURA, *International Research Institute of Disaster Science, Tohoku University, Japan*
LGBTQ+ People and Disasters in Japan: Informational Infrastructure Building for This 'Invisible' Population

565.4 Michele COMPANION, *University of Colorado-Colorado Springs, USA*
Use of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) to Promote Diversity and Inclusion in Drr

565.5 Taku SUGANO, *Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*
Why Inclusive Drr Is Needed "Now" in Japan, a Disaster-Prone Country: The Structure of Disaster Relief Legislation System and the Position of the Third Sector

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

566 Women Practitioners in Emergencies

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Bridget TEHAN, *Australasian Women in Emergencies Network, Australia*

Chair: Debra PARKINSON, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

566.1 Claire MOMSEN, *Social Policy Group, Australia*
Integrating Culturally, Ethnically and Linguistically Diverse Communities in Rapid Responses to Public Health Crises

566.2 Sandra PFISTER, *Disaster Competence Network Austria, Austria*
Reproducing the Gender Order in the Wake of Disasters

566.3 Sandra DEMA MORENO, *University of Oviedo, Spain*; Virginia COCINA DIAZ, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain*; Ana Gabriela FERNÁNDEZ SAAVEDRA, *FLACSO-Uruguay, Uruguay* and Rosario GONZÁLEZ ARIAS, *University of Oviedo, Spain*
Women's and Men's Leadership during the Chilean 2010 Earthquake and Tsunami: Facing the Emergency and the Recovery

566.4 Yajaira AYALA, *University of Delaware, USA*
Reframing Reality: An Analysis of the Experiences of Vulnerability and Resiliency Among Poor Black Women during Recovery

566.5 Mary Lou RASMUSSEN, *The Australian National University, Australia*; Rebecca WILLIAMSON, *The Australian National University, Australia*; Louisa ALLEN, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Celia ROBERTS, *Australian National University, Australia*
Pregnant Women's Experiences of Seeking Shelter and Health Care in the 2019-20 Bushfires in the ACT and NSW South Coast: Implications for Practice

566.6 Aditi SHARAN, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand* and JC GAILLARD, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Gender Beyond the Binary in Disasters: Viewpoints from the Hijra Community of India

10:30-12:20

567 Women, Men and Lgbtiqa+ People in Disasters

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Debra PARKINSON, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Debra PARKINSON, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

567.1 Aditi SHARAN, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand* and JC GAILLARD, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Disasters and the "Other Gender": Experiences of the Hijra Community in Disasters in India

567.2 Virginia COCINA DIAZ, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain*; Mar LLORENTE MARRÓN, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain* and Sandra DEMA MORENO, *University of Oviedo, Spain*
The Socioeconomic Consequences of Gender Relations in the Earthquakes in the Dominican Republic (2003), Honduras (2007 AND 2009) and Haiti (2010)

567.3 Liam LEONARD, *Monash University and Gender and Disaster Australia, Australia*
We Haven't Got You COVID: Including Lgbtiqa+ People in Disaster Planning, Response and Recovery

567.4 Stephen O'MALLEY, *Gender and Disaster Australia (GADAus), Australia*
Resilience in a Riskier World – Adapting and Transforming for the Future

567.5 Bob PEASE, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Disrupting Masculinism in Public Policy Responses to COVID-19: Unmasking the Gendered Dimensions of the Pandemic

567.6 Ilaria MICHELIS, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Later Is a Cis-Hetero Patriarchal Time Zone: Progress and Resistance in the Inclusion of People with Diverse Sogiesc in Humanitarian Response

15:30-17:20

568 Volunteers and Aid in Disaster Contexts

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Kyle BREEN, *Dalhousie University, Canada*; Mary NELAN, *University of North Texas, USA* and John MOY, *Queensland Fire and Emergency Services, Australia*

Chair: Kyle BREEN, *Dalhousie University, Canada*

Co-Chair: John MOY, *Queensland Fire and Emergency Services, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

568.1 Jowita RADZINSKA, *SWPS University, Poland* and Agnieszka GOLINSKA, *SWPS University, Poland*
'Whatever Happens, Have the Courage and Honor to Act Decent...' the Limits of Hospitality in the Polish Reception of People Fleeing the War in Ukraine

568.2 Lucie VIDOVICOVA, *Masaryk University, Czech Republic* and Světlana NEDVĚDOVÁ, *Masaryk University, Czech Republic*
The Front-Line Responses to Crises and Older People in Czechia

568.3 Hiroko KOUMOTO, *Tokoha University, Japan*
Help-Seeking and Help-Receiving Behaviors in Long-Term Life Restoration Process of Elderly People after a Disaster

568.4 Dominica MEADE, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Gender Dynamics in Community Volunteering Practices

568.5 Roni FRASER, *University of Delaware, USA*
Towards a Whole Community Approach during Disaster Response and Recovery: Understanding Stress and Mental Health Experiences of Volunteers Post-Disaster

568.6 Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey*
Social Construction of Volunteer Groups and Aid in Forest Fires

19:30-20:50

569 RC39 Business Meeting

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

570 Business Community Resilience, Protecting Livelihoods and Safeguarding Services

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Renae HANVIN, *Resilient Ready and corporate2community, Australia*

Chair: Renae HANVIN, *Resilient Ready, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

570.1 Valerie INGHAM, *Charles Sturt University, Australia* and Kris NEWTON, *Mountains Community Resource Network, Australia*
Resilient Villages

570.2 Andrea SPITERI, Victorian State Government, Australia; Braedan HOGAN, Victorian State Government, Australia and Pip MORRISON, Victorian State Government, Australia
Victoria's Approach to Sharing the Responsibility for Identifying and Supporting People Most at Risk in Emergencies

570.3 Tadashi NAKASU, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand
Approaches for Building Sustainable Communities in Flood-Prone Industrial Complex Areas

570.4 Yuwen GAO, Osaka University, Japan
A Study on Disaster Management Capacity of International Students at a Private University in Japan

570.5 Yixuan WANG, Osaka University, Japan
The Difference of Social Capital in Disaster Resilience between China and Japan: Comparative Case Analysis of the 2011 Great East Japan Earthquake and the 2008 Sichuan Earthquakes

570.6 Russell DIPPY, Charles Sturt University, Australia and DeMond MILLER, Rowan University, USA
The Emergence and Regulation of the Profession of Emergency Management

10:30-12:20

571 Compound Disasters, Extreme Weather, and the Impact of Livelihoods

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ziqiang HAN, Shandong University, China and Michele COMPANION, University of Colorado-Colorado Springs, USA

Chair: Ziqiang HAN, Shandong University, China

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

571.1 Litiao HU, Nanjing University, China
The Effect of Tropical Cyclone-Induced Multiple Hazards on Economic Production

571.2 Renae HANVIN, Resilient Ready, Australia
Saving Lives and Livelihoods: Lessons Learned from the NSW Business Community

571.3 Sebak SAHA, Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh
Household-Level Coping Strategies in Coastal Bangladesh: The Case of Cyclone Aila (2009)

571.4 Nithin RAJAMANI, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India
Livelihoods in Peril: A Sociological Analysis of Impact of Extreme Events on Wetland Based Livelihoods in Kerala, India.

571.5 Lifang HUANG, Chongqing Jianzhu College, China; Guo CHUNFU, Southwest University of Political Science & Law, China; Xueyuan WANG, Southwest University of Political Science & Law, China; Siyu ZHE, Southwest University of Political Science & Law, China and Huang YUMING, Southwest University of Political Science & Law, China
Study on the Adjustment of Health Code Apps in the Compound Context of High-Temperatures, COVID-19, Raging Wildfires: Case from Chongqing, China

571.6 Simon LAMBERT, NEIHR- National Coordinating Centre, New Zealand
Inland and Ocean: Indigenous Relocations Forced and Voluntary – Gulf of Mexico and Canadian Prairies

15:30-17:20

572 Displacement, Migration, and Relocation

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: H. Tristan WU, University of North Texas, USA

Chair: H. Tristan WU, University of North Texas, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

572.1 Olga OLEINIKOVA, University of Technology Sydney, Australia
Forced Migration Trajectories: Displacement and Pathways to Humanitarian Protection Among Ukrainian Arrivals to Australia

572.2 Ilim HALIMATUSA'DIYAH, UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta, Indonesia
Escaping from Environmental Catastrophes: 'Climate Refugees' and Gendered Dimension of Mobility Justice in Indonesia

572.3 Aytul KASAPOGLU, Baskent University, Turkey
A Relational Sociological Evaluation of Forced Migration, Which Has Become a Disaster in Turkey and Consent-Based Remigration

572.4 Simay OZLU DINIZ, Baskent University, Turkey
Amenity Migration and Relational Space

572.5 Jing-Chein LU, Central Police University, Taiwan
Social, Cultural, and Livelihood Reconnections after Relocation: Recovery of Relocated Aboriginal Communities after Typhoon Morakot in Taiwan

572.6 Kamil LUCZAJ, University of Lodz, Poland and Iwona LEONOWICZ-BUKALA, University of Information Technology and Management, Poland
The Well-Being of a Host, Wellbeing of a Guest. the Micro-Dynamics of Host-Guest Relations in Polish Homes after 24.02.2022

572.7 Saori KAWAZOE, Toyo University, Japan
Living in Two Locations in the Recovery Stage from Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Accidents

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

572.8 Pieter-wernich BREDENKAMP, North-West University, South Africa; Dewald VAN NIEKERK, North-West University, South Africa and Christo COETZEE, North-West University, South Africa
Exploring Disaster Risk Reduction through the Lens of Quantum Mechanics

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

573 Research and Best Practices for Disasters Yet to Come: Preparedness and Mitigation amid Global Disasters

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: DeMond MILLER, Rowan University, USA

Chair: DeMond MILLER, Rowan University, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

573.1 Benigno AGUIRRE, *Disaster Research Center US, USA*
CAN WE AGREE on Panic?

573.2 Janaina SILVA, *Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of São Paulo (IFSP), Brazil*; Victor MARCHEZINI, *Brazilian Early Warning and Monitoring Center for Natural Disasters (CEMADEN), Brazil* and Viviana AGUILAR-MUÑOZ, *Brazilian Early Warning and Monitoring Center for Natural Disasters (CEMADEN), Brazil*
Educational Practices for Disaster Risk Reduction at the Brazilian Federal Network of Scientific and Technological Professional Education

573.3 Anita BLEDSOE-GARDNER, *Johnson C. Smith University, USA*
The Silent Factor: Understanding the Critical Landscape of Medical Intelligence, Disasters, and Emergency Management

573.4 Alex ALTSHULER, *University of Haifa, Israel* and Anna USTER, *The Max Stern Yezreel Valley College, Israel*
Yes We Can!? a Theoretical and Empirical Examination of the Concept of Building Resilience through Cross-Sector Cooperation in Light of the Ongoing COVID-19 Crisis and Disasters Yet to Come

573.5 Johanna GARNETT, *Charles Sturt University & Torrens Resilience Initiative, Flinders University, Australia*
Incorporating Cultural Heritage into Disaster Risk Reduction Policy

573.6 Hsiang-Chieh LEE, *National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction, Taiwan*; Hui Hsuan YANG, *National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction, Taiwan* and Wai-In CHAO, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Differences in the Disaster Mitigation Behaviors of the General Public and of People in Hard-Hit Areas

573.7 Jenna HARB, *Australian National University, Australia*
Contradictions of Localization in (Transnational) Crisis Response: The Case of Lebanon

10:30-12:20

JS-89 **Childhoods at the Crossection of Disasters**

Committees: *RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); RC39 Sociology of Disasters*

See Joint Session Details for JS-89.

15:30-17:20

574 **The Rise of the Professional: Emergency Management and Community Responses to Disasters and Crises**

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: DeMond MILLER, *Rowan University, USA* and Russell DIPPY, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

Chairs: DeMond MILLER, *Rowan University, USA* and Russell DIPPY, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

574.1 John MOY, *Queensland Fire and Emergency Services, Australia*
Emergency Services Volunteers: Professionals or Potterer's?

574.2 Piero TELLERIAS, *University of Paris Pantheon-Sorbonne, France*

The Social Conditions of Policy Ideas' Transformation: Computational and Field Theory Analysis of the Disaster Reduction Literature and Practice

574.3 Keiko IKEDA, *Shizuoka University, Japan*
Recommending Equity in Inequal Institutions: Japan's Experiences of Policy Recommendation for Integrating Gender Perspectives to the Disaster Management Policies

574.4 Sebak SAHA, *Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh*
Weaknesses of NGOs' Post-Disaster Response and Recovery Operations: The Case of Cyclone Aila in Bangladesh

574.5 Hsiang-Chieh LEE, *National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction, Taiwan*; Hui Hsuan YANG, *National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction, Taiwan* and Mei-Chun LIN, *National Science and Technology Center for Disaster Reduction, Taiwan*
Including Social Vulnerability in Disaster Management Plans of the Local Government

17:30-19:20

575 **Examining the Illusion of Control: Single Truths, Complexity and Disaster Resilience**

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Margot RAWSTHORNE, *University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Margot RAWSTHORNE, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

575.1 Steve MATTHEWMAN, *University of Auckland | Waipapa Taumata Rau, New Zealand* and Shinya UEKUSA, *University of Canterbury, New Zealand*
Why We Don't Build Back Better: Coherence, Complexity and Control

575.2 Valerie INGHAM, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*; John HICKS, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*; Rabiul Mir ISLAM, *Charles Sturt University, Australia* and Lucia WUERSCH, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*
Disaster Fatigue

575.3 Amanda HOWARD, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Pam JOSEPH, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Spirit of Place: Communities Acting in Disasters

575.4 Mel TAYLOR, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Fiona MILLER, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Barbara RYAN, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*; Kim JOHNSTON, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*; Anne LANE, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Kat HAYNES, *Natural Hazards Research Australia, Australia*
Navigating Aspects of Control in Response to the 2022 Eastern Australia Floods

575.5 Christo COETZEE, *North-West University, South Africa*
The Rise of Complexity Sciences in Drr and Implications for Traditional Disaster Management Tools

575.6 H. SAMARAWEEERA, *Department of Sociology, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka*
Complexity of Disaster Resilience Discourse: With Special Reference to Neoliberal Sri Lanka

575.7 Ivana RUIZ-ESTRAMIL, *Centre for Social Studies University of Coimbra - Institute for International Cooperation and Development Studies University of the Basque Country, Portugal*
Climate Crisis, Asylum and Refuge: Environmental Justice from International Protection

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-115 COVID-19: Patterns in Domestic Military Operations

Committees: RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution (Host); RC39 Sociology of Disasters

See Joint Session Details for JS-115.

10:30-12:20

576 Cultural Heritage and Disaster

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Johanna GARNETT, *Torrens Resilience Initiative & CSU, Australia*

Chair: Johanna GARNETT, *Charles Sturt University & Torrens Resilience Initiative, Flinders University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

576.1 Shunsuke TAKEDA, *Hosei University, Japan*
The Impact of COVID-19 on the Succession of Traditional Festivals and Community Resilience: The Case of Yama, Hoko, Yatai Float Festivals in Japan

576.2 Marlon ERA, *De La Salle University, Philippines*; Alejandra ALBUERNE, *University College London, United Kingdom*; Fatemeh Farnaz AREFIAN, *Silk Cities, United Kingdom*; Leila BEN-GACEM, *Blue Fish Consulting, Tunisia*; Deniz DERYA, *Ozyegin University, Turkey*; Zeynep Ece ATABAY, *Yindiz Technical University, Turkey* and Rohit RANJITKA, *Kathmandu Valley Preservation Trust, Nepal*
Mobilizing Intangible Heritage for Resilience and Recovery: The Case of Tunisia and Nepal

576.3 Takayuki II, *Senshu University, Japan*
Comparison of Memorial Museums after the Great East Japan Earthquake and Tsunami of 2011

576.4 Shinya FUJIMOTO, *Doshisha University, Japan*
The Role of Disaster Schema in Evacuation Decision-Making: Findings from Post-Disaster Social Surveys in Japan

576.5 Haorui WU, *Dalhousie University, Canada*
Discovery, Protection, and Advancement: Utilization of Co-Design Approach to Protect the Rural Intangible Grassroots Place-Making Heritage

15:30-17:20

JS-133 Understanding the Entanglements of Urban Disasters

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC43 Housing and Built Environment and RC39 Sociology of Disasters

See Joint Session Details for JS-133.

17:30-19:20

577 A Dialogue on Community Engagement and Disaster Research

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Joy SEMIEN, *Texas A & M, United States*

Chair: Joy SEMIEN, *Texas A & M, United States*

Panelists: Tiffany COUSINS, *Virginia Tech, USA* and Mason ALEXANDER, *Texas A & M University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

577.1 Adam CHORYNSKI, *Poznań University of Life Sciences, Poland*; Iwona PINSKWAR, *Poznań University of Life Sciences, Poland* and Dariusz GRACZYK, *Poznań University of Life Sciences, Poland*
Small Communities Resilience to Extreme Weather Events – Conditions Influencing Local Activities

577.2 Manomita DAS, *Massey University, New Zealand*; Julia BECKER, *Massey University, New Zealand*; Emma HUDSON-DOYLE, *Massey University, New Zealand* and Sara K. MCBRIDE, *United States Geological Survey, USA*
Strengthening Disaster Preparedness from the Ground up – Study of Community Groups in New Zealand

577.3 Tiffany COUSINS, *Virginia Tech, USA*
Utilizing Citizen Participation to Manage Pluvial Flooding

577.4 Mason ALEXANDER, *Texas A & M University, USA*
Resilience in Recovery: Understanding Long Term Recovery Groups Coordination of Unmet Needs

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

578 Disasters and Crime

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Benigno AGUIRRE, *Disaster Research Center US, USA*

Chair: Benigno AGUIRRE, *University of Delaware, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

578.1 Rogelio RAMOS TORRES, *Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios Superiores en Antropología Social, Mexico*
September 2017 Earthquake Insights: From Criminal Species Extermination to Criminality As a New Element in the Relationship between Fishermen and Domestic Sea. the Case of Paredon Bay in Chiapas, Mexico

578.2 Jenniffer SANTOS-HERNANDEZ, *Graduate School of Planning, University of Puerto Rico-Río Piedras, Puerto Rico*
¿Cuándo Entenderán Que Nos Mienten? a Case Study of White-Collar Corruption in Post-Disaster Puerto Rico

578.3 Anna MATSUKAWA, *National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience, Japan* and Rika OHTSUKA, *National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience, Japan*
Impact of Typhoon-Induced Power Outages on Property Crime in Japan

578.4 Ziqiang HAN, *Shandong University, China*; Jie LIU, *Shandong University, China* and Wei JIA, *Qingdao University, China*
Noncompliance Behavior during the Covid-19 in China

578.5 Piero TELLERIAS, *University of Paris Pantheon-Sorbonne, France* and Antoine GALLARD CUILANDRE, *University of Paris Pantheon-Sorbonne, France*
Illusions That Control: Disaster Risk Reduction and Counterterrorism Preparedness in a Never-Ending Security Crisis

10:30-12:20

579 **Toward a Critical Disaster Studies in Japan and Beyond: Issues in Theory and Research**

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Paola CAVALIERE, *Osaka University, Graduate School of Human Sciences, Japan* and Junko OTANI, *Osaka University, Japan*

Co-chairs: Paola CAVALIERE, *Osaka University, Graduate School of Human Sciences, Japan* and Junko OTANI, *Osaka University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

579.1 Jing LI, *Osaka University, Japan*
Japan's Disaster Medical System and Response to the Covid-19

579.2 James GOLTZ, *Natural Hazards Center, University of Colorado, Boulder, USA* and Katsuya YAMORI, *Disaster Reduction Systems, Disaster Prevention Research Institute, Kyoto University, Japan*
Disasters without Borders: The Coronavirus Pandemic, Global Climate Change and the Ascendancy of Gradual Onset Disasters

579.3 Shin NOZAKA, *Waseda University, Japan*
Social Vulnerability and the Reasons of Victims' Death in the 2011 Tohoku Earthquake and Tsunami: Based on the Researches on Victims and Local History in Otsuchi Town, Iwate Prefecture

579.4 Julia GERSTER, *Tohoku University, Japan* and Akihiro SHIBAYAMA, *Tohoku University, Japan*
Storytelling and the Arts As Tools in Disaster Education: Tohoku University's "Kataritsugi" and the Stories of 3.11

579.5 Lisette ROBLES, *JICA, Japan*
They Who Can't Stay and Yet Who Can't Move: Examining Disaster Displacement of Those Affected By the 2020 South Japan Flooding

579.6 Miki MOCHIZUKI, *Faculty of Informatics, Shizuoka University, Japan*
What Are the Reconstruction Issues 10 Years after the Great East Japan Earthquake? : Case Studies of Tsunami-Affected Area in Miyagi Prefecture

12:30-14:20

580 **The Intersection of Health and Disasters**

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tricia WACHTENDORF, *166 Graham Hall, USA*

Chair: Diamond CUNNINGHAM, *Tulane University, USA*

Panelist: Tricia WACHTENDORF, *166 Graham Hall, USA*

Discussant: Diamond CUNNINGHAM, *Tulane University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

580.1 Tricia WACHTENDORF, *166 Graham Hall, USA* and Nancy RIOS-CONTRERAS, *Chapman University, USA*
COVID-19: Social Impacts on Delawareans with HIV

580.2 Roni FRASER, *University of Delaware, USA* and Sarah DEYOUNG, *University of Delaware, USA*
The Compound Nature of the COVID-19 Pandemic and Hurricane Response: A Study of Maternal-Child Health Following Hurricane Ida, Louisiana, USA.

580.3 Alex GREER, *SUNY Albany, USA*; Haley MURPHY, *Oklahoma State University, USA*; H. Tristan WU, *University of North Texas, USA* and Lauren CLAY, *University of Maryland Baltimore County, USA*
Hurricane Evacuation, Sheltering, and Re-Entry Decision-Making in the Context of COVID-19

580.4 Amabelle EMBORNAS, *Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology, Philippines* and Isidro ARQUISAL, *Mindanao State University-Iligan Institute of Technology, Philippines*
Disaster Preparedness Among Nurses in Iligan City, Northern Mindanao, Philippines

580.5 DeMond MILLER, *Rowan University, USA* and Sotirios CHTOURIS, *University of the Aegean, Greece*
The Role of Clinical Sociology in Disaster Resilience, Health, and Care

580.6 Inaki RUBIO MENGUAL, *University of Basque Country UPV/EHU, Spain* and Alvaro VILLAR, *University of Basque Country UPV/EHU, Spain*
Discounted Deaths: The Eruption of COVID-19 in the Geriatric System of the Community of Madrid

14:30-16:20

581 **Technology and Disasters**

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Roslyn PRINSLEY, *Australian National University, Australia*

Chair: Russell DIPPY, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

581.1 Sandra PFISTER, *Disaster Competence Network Austria, Austria*
Bourdieu Meets Disaster Robots. the Introduction of Innovative Technologies in the Field of Emergency Response

581.2 Lufang FENG, *lanzhou university, China*
A Scientometric Review of Big Data Technology in Disaster Management

581.3 Paolo CRIVELLARI, *IUT, University Of Toulouse III, France*
Technology in Disaster Prevention and Management: Innovation, Governance and (concealed) Knowledge

581.4 Pablo AZNAR-CRESPO, *Department of Sociology I of University of Alicante, Spain*; Antonio ALEDO, *Department of Sociology I of the University of Alicante, Spain* and Guadalupe ORTIZ, *University of Alicante, Spain*
Methodology for Creating a Library of Early Warning Messages

581.5 Jenniffer SANTOS-HERNANDEZ, *Graduate School of Planning, University of Puerto Rico-Río Piedras, Puerto Rico*; Nnenia CAMPBELL, *Natural Hazards Center, University of Colorado Boulder, USA*; Sara K. MCBRIDE, *United States Geological Survey, USA* and Lorna JARAMILLO-NIEVES, *University of Puerto Rico-Río Piedras, PR*

Disasters As Processes: Trust, Information Seeking, and Protective Action Decision Making

581.6 Kahoruko YAMAMOTO, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*

Post-Disaster Diaspora: Fukushima Evacuees Seeking a Third Way "Home"

RC40

Sociology of Agriculture and Food

Program Coordinators: Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA* and Matt COMI, *Marshfield Clinic Research Institute, USA*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

582 Food and Social Change

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

Chairs: Eloisa MARTIN, *United Arab Emirates University, United Arab Emirates* and Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

582.1 Md. ISLAM, *Associate Professor, Department of Social Sciences, BNU-HKBU United International College, China*
Curry Nationalism: The Emergence of Indian (South Asian) Cuisine in China

582.2 Shivani RAJPUT, *Miranda House, University of Delhi, India* and Beauty THOUNAOJAM, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Sociological Study of Cross-Cultural Consumption: A Case Study of Ngari

582.3 Shamayeeta GHOSH, *Jhargram Raj College (Girls' Wing), Affiliated to Vidyasagar University, India*
Foodways of Package Tours in Contemporary Bengal: Situating 'Bengali Cuisine' in the Culinary Culture of Kundu Special

582.4 Sheila MANKA, *North West University, South Africa*
I Eat What I Desire: Modern Foods and Benefits within the Mankon Community, North West Region, Cameroon

582.5 Vien DINH, *Kyoto University, Japan*
Multi-Cultural Transformation through Practices of Foraging and Consuming Wild Edible Plants Among Vietnamese Immigrants

17:30-19:20

583 Food System Shocks and Food Security Vulnerabilities: Moving Beyond Business As Usual I

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Carol RICHARDS, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Rudolf MESSNER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

Chairs: Carol RICHARDS, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Rudolf MESSNER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

583.1 Phoebe STEPHENS, *Dalhousie University, Canada*
Food Crises: What Makes These Perfect Storms so Perfect?

583.2 Maura BENEGLIAMO, *University of Pisa, Italy* and Luigi PELLIZZONI, *University of Pisa, Italy*
Preparedness in Agriculture and Food Security: The Emergent European Approach and Some Evidence from the Italian Case

583.3 Mustafa KOC, *Ryerson University, Canada*
Food Insecurity, Armed Conflict and the Invisible Hunger

583.4 Elizabeth RANSOM, *The Pennsylvania State University, USA*
Food Security amidst Disasters in a Post-Growth World: Opportunities and Tensions

583.5 Rachel CAREY, *n/a, Australia*
Unpacking "the Surprise Chain": The Governance of Food Security during Food System Shocks

583.6 Lesley FRANK, *Acadia University, Canada*
Affordable and Physical Food Access in the First-Food System: Persistent Challenges and Unanticipated Shocks for Infant Food Security

583.7 Rudolf MESSNER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Carol RICHARDS, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
Producing Sustainable Food Security: Socio-Technical Transitions in Australian Agriculture

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

584 Agri-Food Sustainability in a Post-COVID World

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Kiran ODHAV, *North West University, South Africa* and Sheila MANKA, *North-West University, South Africa*

Chair: Kiran ODHAV, *North West University, South Africa*

Co-Chair: Sheila MANKA, *North-West University, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

584.1 Camille FREEMAN, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Retaining Consumer Demand for Ethical and Sustainable Food Consumption: Lessons Learned from the Impacts of COVID-19 on Australian Alternative and Local Food Systems

584.2 Yildiz ATASOY, *Simon Fraser University, Canada*
Farming Imaginaries and Enrichment-Value Creation in Ankara-Turkey

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

584.3 Thandeka KHOWA, *North-West University, South Africa* and Tafadzwa MUKASI, *MANCOSA, South Africa*
Agro Processing As a Tool for Poverty Alleviation Strategy: A Case of Raymond Mhlaba Municipality

584.4 Aryama BHATTACHARYA, *Diamond Harbour Women's University, India*
Women in Agriculture : The Socio-Economic Change in Postpandemic Period

15:30-17:20

585 Sociology of Agriculture and Food Roundtables**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Matt COMI, *Marshfield Clinic Research Institute, USA* and Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA***ROUNDTABLES:****Roundtable A****ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

585.1 Eugenia PETROPOULOU, *Department of Sociology, University of Crete, Greece*
Changing Landscapes of Food Consumption? Consumers' Perceptions Towards Short Food Supply Chains in Greece

585.2 Rachel RECKINGER, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
Goodness Groceries! Can a Mobile Sustainable Food Shopping App Foster Food Literacy and Ethical Choices? Entailments for Suppliers, Citizens and Researchers

585.3 Jean-Pierre POULAIN, *CERTOP UMR-CNRS, France* and Vincent SIMOULIN, *University of Toulouse, CERTOP UMR-CNRS, France*
Protein Transition: Bridging Theoretical Models to Enhance Connection of Scientific Nutrition and Public Policies

Roundtable B**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

585.4 Carolina COIMBRA VIEIRA, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*; Sophie LOHMANN, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany* and Emilio ZAGHENI, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*
The Value of Cultural Similarity for Predicting Migration: Evidence from Food and Drink Preferences in Facebook Data

585.5 Romain BLANCANEUX, *Kyoto University, France*
lots As a Mean of Power over Producers. the Case of Geographical Indication Manganji Sweet Green Peppers, Maizuru, Japan

585.6 Bruce MUIRHEAD, *University of Waterloo, Canada* and Jodey NURSE, *McGill University, Canada*
Dairy and Eggs in Canada: Superior Performance Using Superior Methods

Roundtable C**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

585.8 Hugh CAMPBELL, *University of Otago, New Zealand*
Farm Fencelines As Technologies of Power

585.9 Siphon SISHUBA, *North-West University, South Africa* and Kiran ODHAV, *North West University, South Africa*
Cabral's Ideas and Its Relevance to Africa Agronomy

Roundtable D**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

585.10 Yildiz ATASOY, *Simon Fraser University, Canada*
Agriculture By Algorithm: Big Data, Digitalization, and Biotechnology in Climate-Change Adaptation

585.11 Suzanne VALLANCE, *AgResearch, New Zealand*
Killing the Digital Deer: Innovative Technologies and Animal Welfare

585.12 Atakan BUKE, *Universität Leipzig, Germany*
Digital Imaginaries of Agriculture and Rural in Vodafone Smart Village in Turkey

585.13 Mukesh RANGA, *CSJM University, India*
An Assessment of Impacts of AI Revolution on Agriculture in India

Roundtable E**ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

585.14 Tomislav RIMAC, *ESCI, Pompeu Fabra University, Spain*
Innovation As a Deviant Behavior: A Comparative Study of Introduction of New Agricultural Practices, Forms of Organizing, and Modes of Collaboration

585.15 Marta GOSPODARCZYK, *Faculty of Sociology/ Doctoral School of Social Sciences, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Innovation - What Is It Good for? the Case of Agricultural Drought Compensations in Poland

585.16 Maaz GARDEZI, *Virginia Tech, USA*
Reconfiguring Meanings and Possibilities through Digital Agriculture: Lesson for Innovation Dynamics

585.17 Masashi TACHIKAWA, *Nagoya University, Japan*
Seamless Application of Gene Editing on Agriculture and Beyond: Farm-Nature Assemblage on the Horizon

17:30-19:20

586 Food System Shocks and Food Security Vulnerabilities: Moving Beyond Business As Usual II**Location:** 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Carol RICHARDS, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Rudolf MESSNER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia***Chairs:** Carol RICHARDS, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Rudolf MESSNER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

586.1 Melissa NAVARRA, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines* and Anke NIEHOF, *Wageningen University, Netherlands*
Household Food Systems during Lockdown: Food Diaries of Filipino Mothers in Poor Urban and Sub-Urban Households

586.2 Alana MANN, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Donald REID, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Evaluating Community-Based Food System Action in Tasmania

586.3 Rebecca LINDBERG, *Deakin University, Australia*; Amber BASTIAN, *Deakin University, Australia*; Fiona MCKAY, *Deakin University, Australia*; Paige VAN DER PLIGT, *Deakin University, Australia*; Courtney PARKS, *Gretchen Swanson Center For Nutrition, USA*; Amy YAROCH, *Gretchen Swanson Center For Nutrition, USA* and Sarah MCNAUGHTON, *Deakin University, Australia*
International Collaborative to Identify and Improve Food Insecurity Risk Factors Among Low-Income Young Families in Melbourne and Omaha

586.4 Winifredo DAGLI, *School of Environmental Design and Rural Development, University of Guelph, Canada* and Eduardo ROQUINO, *University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines*
Food Self-Sufficiency As Contested Socio-Technical Imaginaries

586.5 Marvin Joseph MONTEFRIO, *Yale-NUS College, Singapore* and Anacrita ABASOLO, *University of the Philippines, Los Baños, Philippines*
Neighborhood Food Retailers, Food Security, and Rural Precarity in Times of Crisis

586.6 Ireen KABEMBO, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*; Gilbert SIAME, *University of Zambia Department of Geography & Environmental Studies, Zambia*; Progress NYANGA, *University of Zambia Department of Geography & Environmental Studies, Zambia*; Dorothy NDHLOVU, *University of Zambia Department of Geography & Environmental Studies, Zambia*; Garikai MEMBELE, *University of Zambia Department of Geography & Environmental Studies, Zambia*; Brenda MWALUKANGA, *GFA Consulting Group, Zambia* and Eunice IMASIKU, *University of Zambia Department of Geography & Environmental Studies, Zambia*
Food and Nutrition Loss in Urban Agrifood Chains: Leveraging Lessons Learnt from the Africities Project to Address Food Loss in Lusaka, Zambia.

586.7 Anthonia UZOIGWE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Food Insecurity Among University Students in Aotearoa

586.8 Amrutha PAMPACKAL, *Cornell University, USA*
Pathways Towards Sustainable Food Security: A Study of Forest-Proximate Communities in Odisha, India

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-55 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics I

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); RC07 Futures Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-55.

10:30-12:20

587 Food and Social Change II

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

Chair: Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

587.1 Elisabeth GOTSCHI, *University of Natural Resources and Applied Life Sciences, Austria*; Stefan VOGEL, *University of Natural Resources and Applied Life Sciences, Austria* and Manuela LARCHER, *University of Natural Resources and Applied Life Sciences, Austria*
The Role of Social Norm, Attitudes and Cultural Preferences in Choosing Organic Food Items. Two Case Studies of High School Students in Austria

587.2 Yisag KIM, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
College Student's Choice of Dining As Symbolic Capital in Korea

587.3 Tina BARTELMESS, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*
Twitter-Hashtag #Ichbinarmutsbetroffen (#IamPoor) - Perspectives on Food Poverty

587.4 Sweta TIWARI, *MAHATMA GANDHI CENTRAL UNIVERSITY, India*
From Farm to Platter: Gauging the Impact of Act East Policy on Indigenous Food Practices and Culture of Konyak Nagas of India

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

587.5 Cecilia DIAZ-MENDEZ, *University of Oviedo, Spain*; Rocío PÉREZ GAÑÁN, *Universidad de Oviedo, Spain* and Cristian GONZALEZ GARCIA, *University of Oviedo, Spain*
¿Real... Food Influencers?: A Critical and Comparative Review

587.6 Daisuke YASUI, *Ritsumeikan University, Japan*
Food Consumption and Social Activities : On the Purchase of Ethical Food

15:30-17:20

JS-68 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part I

Committees: *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC24 Environment and Society RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food and TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-68.

17:30-19:20

JS-77 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part II

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization RC24 Environment and Society and RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-77.

19:30-20:50

588 RC40 Business Meeting

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

589 Exploring the emerging landscape of agtech innovation: venture capital, intermediaries, and the limits of "green capitalism"

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA*

Chair: Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA*

Co-Chair: Sarah SIPPEL, *University of Meunster, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

589.1 Andre MAGNAN, *University of Regina, Canada*
Growing Links between Digital Ag and Finance Capital in Canada: Examining the Cases of Veripath and Farmersedge

589.2 Phoebe STEPHENS, *Dalhousie University, Canada*
Nothing Ventured, Nothing Gained? Exploring the Shift in Venture Capital Investments Toward e-Grocery

589.3 Angga DWIARTAMA, *Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB), Indonesia* and Paul STOCK, *University of Kansas, USA*
A New Digital Peasantry?: Evaluating the Entrepreneurial Spirit of Indonesia's 'Millennial Farmers' Project

589.4 Saurabh GUPTA, *Hiran Magri, India* and Rashid KHAN, *University of Hohenheim, Germany*
How Do Agri-Entrepreneurs Make Use of Digital Technologies? Case-Studies from India

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

589.5 Robert ARCIDIACONO, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Digital Agriculture, Agroecology and Agricultural Innovation Discourse in Australia

589.6 Mylene TANFERRI, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*
Strange Ways to Connect – Entering Agtech Settings to Conduct Ethnographic Fieldwork

10:30-12:20

JS-90 Extending Critical Approaches to Agtech and Foodtech: Dialoguing Insights from the Insides and Outsides of Technology Design Projects

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); TG10 Digital Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-90.

JS-95 The Potential of Food Movements and Intersectional Food Inequalities

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-95.

15:30-17:20

JS-97 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics II

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); RC07 Futures Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-97.

17:30-19:20

JS-109 Organizing through Standards and Value Hierarchies

Committees: *RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-109.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

590 Food and Social Change III

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Mariana CALCAGNI, *FU Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Mariana CALCAGNI, *FU Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

590.1 Ayumi SUGIMOTO, *Akita International University, Japan*
Changing and Unchanging Farming: Farmland Consolidation and Diverse Reactions Among Farmers in a Japanese Community

590.2 Ester COIS, *University of Cagliari, Italy* and Barbara BARBIERI, *University of Cagliari, Italy*
Branding of Stereotypes in Entrepreneurship in the Agri-Food Sector: Using Gender to Make Strategic Marketing

590.3 Ko-hsuan SHAO, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan* and Yu-Hua CHEN, *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
Where Have All the Foxtail Millets Gone? Revitalization of Indigenous Bio-Cultural Heritage in Central Taiwan

590.4 Jean-Pierre POULAIN, *Taylor's Toulouse University Ctr/CERTOP UMR-CNRS, Malaysia* and Vincent SIMOULIN, *University of Toulouse, CERTOP UMR-CNRS, France*
Protein Transition: Bridging Theoretical Models to Enhance Connection of Scientific Nutrition and Public Policies.

590.5 Elise MOGNARD, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*
Proteins & Amino Acids Requirements: History of a Normative Definition

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

590.6 Maitreyee BARDHAN ROY, *Diamond Harbour Women University, India*
A Shift in Earning Trend in Women : 21st Century Women Community Born to the Agricultural Families.

15:30-17:20

591 Good Farm Animal Welfare in Sustainable Food Systems

Location: 102 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Hilde BJORKHAUG, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway* and Bruce MUIRHEAD, *University of Waterloo, Canada*

Chair: Bruce MUIRHEAD, *University of Waterloo, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

591.1 Suzanne VALLANCE, *AgResearch, New Zealand*; Peter EDWARDS, *Landcare Research, New Zealand* and Martin ESPIG, *AgResearch, New Zealand*
Animal Welfare in the Negotiation of a Social License to Farm

591.2 Hilde BJORKHAUG, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway* and Bruce MUIRHEAD, *University of Waterloo, Canada*
Animal Welfare Standards in the Chicken & Egg (food) System

591.3 Brit LOGSTEIN, *Ruralis, Norway* and Hilde BJORKHAUG, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway*
What Prevents Better Animal Welfare?

591.4 Wesley TOURANGEAU, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*
Ethical Meat As Both Cultural Hegemony and Sustainability Leverage Point

591.5 Kae SEKINE, *Aichi Gakuin University, Japan*
Animal Welfare Struggles in Japan: Analyses on External Pressures and Internal Incentives

RC41

Sociology of Population

Program Coordinator: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

592 Addressing Population Change through Social, Health and Other Public Policies

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Andrzej KULCZYCKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*

Chair: Andrzej KULCZYCKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

592.1 Chandrika KB, *Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India*
Health Care Service to Underprivileged Children in India: An Appraisal of Integrated Child Development Scheme in Karnataka State

592.2 Emily PARKER, *University of Michigan, USA*; Rebecca SCHUT, *The University of Chicago, USA* and Courtney BOEN, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*
The U.S. Health Care Safety Net and Farmworker Health, 1989-2016

592.3 Mohammad Mainul ISLAM, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*; Md. Anwer HOSSAIN, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh* and Rahul Kumar SANJOWAL, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*
Bangladesh at Fifty: Changes and Challenges on Population and Development

592.4 Anastasia SOKOLOVA, *Vologda Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*
Commuting and Return Labour Migration in Russian Scientific Discourse

17:30-19:20

JS-21 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part I

Committees: RC41 Sociology of Population (Host); RC55 Social Indicators

See Joint Session Details for JS-21.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-27 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part II

Committees: RC55 Social Indicators (Host); RC41 Sociology of Population

See Joint Session Details for JS-27.

15:30-17:20

593 Behavioural Perspectives of Control and Elimination of Communicable Diseases

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Loretta Favour NTOIMO, *Federal University Oye Ekiti, Nigeria*; Dorothy ONONOKPONO, *Department Of Sociology and Anthropology University of Uyo, Nigeria* and Justin DANSOU, *School of Statistics Planning and Demography, University of Parakou, Benin, Benin*

Chair: Loretta Favour NTOIMO, *Federal University Oye Ekiti, Nigeria*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

593.1 Taiwo Olabode KOLAWOLE, *Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria*
Malaria Elimination in Nigeria: A Political Economy Perspective

593.2 Daniel GRACE, *University of Toronto, Canada*; Mackenzie STEWART, *University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, Canada*; Ezra BLAQUE, *University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, Canada*; Heeho RYU, *University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, Canada*; Mark GASPARD, *University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, Canada*; Cathy WORTHINGTON, *University of Victoria, Canada* and Mark GILBERT, *British Columbia Centre for Disease Control, Canada*
Challenges to Communicating the Undetectable Equals Untransmittable (U=U) HIV Prevention Message: Healthcare Provider Perspectives

593.3 Rebecca SCHUT, *The University of Chicago, USA* and Sneha MANI, *University of Pennsylvania, USA*
The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Health Screenings: Trends and Implications for Population Health Disparities

17:30-19:20

594 Child and Youth Indicators and Their Well-Being: Vital Statistics for Planning and Development

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India*

Chair: Mohammad Mainul ISLAM, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

594.1 Gloria Luz NELSON, *Retired Professor of Sociology, Philippines* and Mari Juni Paulette GONZALES, *UP Open University, Philippines*
The Stories of Filipino Pregnant Teenagers and Teenage Mothers during the COVID-19 Pandemic

594.2 Dhansay TANDAN, *Dr. Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar (M.P.), India* and Sarvendra YADAV, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Central University Sagar, India*
An Anthropometric Assessment of Nutritional Status Among Birhors of Central India: A Tribal Group Facing Double Marginalization

594.3 Sandip CHAUDHARI, *SBES College of Artst and Commerce, Aurangabad-431001(India), India*
Demographic Dividend in India: An Evaluation

594.4 Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India*
Childhood Indicators in India and Children's Well-Being: Data, Discussion and Debate for Policy

594.5 Pia BLOSSFELD, *University of Innsbruck, Austria*
How the Rise of Higher-Educated Origin Families across Cohorts Influences Sons' and Daughters' Tertiary Education in West Germany?

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

595 Contemporary Demographic Transitions

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

595.1 Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*
The Second Mortality Transition and the Extension of the Human Life Span

595.2 Adam CHEUNG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Declining Fertility in the Context of Political Polarization and Resurgent Authoritarianism

595.3 Jesus GARCIA-GOMEZ, *University of Salamanca, Spain, Spain*
Completed Fertility Among Latin American Immigrants and Their Descendants in Spain

595.4 Peng XU, *Zhongnan University of Economics and Law, China* and Yu HOU, *Zhongnan University of Economics and Law, China*
Educational Assortative Mating and Family Income Inequality Among Internal Migrant Population in China

595.5 Judith KOOPS, *Radboud University, Netherlands*
Worldwide Changes in Unplanned Pregnancies

595.6 Gurusamy SELLAMUTHU, *Gandhigram Rural Institute, India*
Social Structure and Status of Girl Child in Rural Tamil Nadu :Implications for Population Change.

10:30-12:20

JS-62 Demographic Change, Economic Outcomes and Religious Belief

Committees: RC41 *Sociology of Population (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-62.

19:30-20:50

596 RC41 Business Meeting

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

597 COVID-19 and the World Population

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Mohammad Mainul ISLAM, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

597.1 Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*
En – Epi – Pan – Demic Reflections on Epidemiology

597.2 Andrzej KULCZYCKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*
Drawing Light from the Covid-19 Pandemic: Advancing Vaccination Efforts, Metrics and Reporting Systems for Future Pandemic Preparedness and Ongoing Adult Vaccination Programming

597.3 Nicole DE WET, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*
Perpetuation of Household Food Insecurity during COVID-19 in South Africa

597.4 Elena BASTIDA, *Florida International Univ, USA*; Carlos BARRETO BECK, *University of Texas at Austin, USA* and Wissam AL KHOURY, *Florida International University, USA*
Early Childhood Adversity and Early Mortality in an Ethnically Diverse Population

15:30-17:20

598 Demography and Religion

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

598.1 Andrzej KULCZYCKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*
Religion, Low Fertility and Competing Visions of Tradition in Europe and Latin America: A Comparative Analysis of Catholicism, Pronatalist Stresses, and the Natural Order in Poland and Brazil

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

599 Demography and War

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Jonathan ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

599.1 Ismet KOC, *Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, Turkey* and Melike SARAÇ, *Hacettepe University, Institute of Population Studies, Turkey*
Timing of Reproductive Events from Menarche to Menopause Among Host Community and Syrian Refugee Women in Turkey

15:30-17:20

600 Disease Progression and Mortality in Prospective Studies

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Elena BASTIDA, *Florida International Univ, USA*

Chair: Elena BASTIDA, *Florida International Univ, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

600.1 Guang GUO, *the university of north carolina at chapel hill, USA*
Sharply Heightened Mortality Among African American Women: BMI-Prone Genetic Variants and Socioeconomic Disadvantage

600.2 Nicolas SACCO ZEBALLOS, *Penn State, USA*
The Uneven Demographic Transition in Argentina: Historical Patterns and Future Perspectives

600.3 Neeru GUPTA, *University of New Brunswick, Canada*
Cardiometabolic Health Disparities Among Sexual Minority Populations: Evidence Using National Linked Data Sources in a Context of Universal Coverage

600.4 Collin PAYNE, *The Australian National University, Australia*
Inequality in Healthy Life Expectancy in the Asia-Pacific: A Cross-National Analysis

600.5 Anagha TENDULKAR - PATIL, *Sophia College for Women, India*
Feminization of Ageing: Reflections and Apprehensions

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

601 New Family Structures

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Andrzej KULCZYCKI, *University of Alabama at Birmingham, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

601.1 Sabrina ZEGHICHE, *Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada*
'My Eyes, My Smile... They Belong to Someone I Don't Know' – the Impact of Insemination Fraud on Family Ties

601.2 Isabel COTE, *Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada*; Flavy BARRETTE, *Université du Québec en Outaouais, Canada* and Kevin LAVOIE, *Université Laval, Canada*
Witnessing One's Mother's Surrogacy. Experience of Canadian Youth.

601.3 Rosa Maria CAMARENA-CORDOVA, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, UNAM, Mexico*
Family Structures in Mexico

601.4 Gayle KAUFMAN, *Davidson College, USA* and D'Lane COMPTON, *University of New Orleans, USA*
Marriage Attitudes after Marriage Equality

10:30-12:20

602 General Population Issues

Location: 112 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

Chair: Ofra ANSON, *Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

602.1 Loretta Favour NTOIMO, *Federal University Oye Ekiti, Nigeria*

Does Bride Wealth Give a Man Power over a Woman? Conflict of Culture and Women's Rights in Nigeria

602.2 Ana Cristina MARQUES, *University of Kurdistan Hewler, Iraq*; Mamilan HUSSEIN, *University of West London, United Kingdom* and Khellan NAWZAD, *N/A, Iraq*
Divorce between a 'problem' and a 'solution'? Economic, Social and Cultural Consequences of Divorce for Women's Lives, in the Kurdistan Region-Iraq

602.3 Robert HUMMER, *University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill, USA*; Aura MISHRA, *University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill, USA*; Chantel MARTIN, *University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill, USA*; Lauren GAYDOSH, *University of Texas at Austin, USA*; Debra UMBERSON, *University of Texas at Austin, USA*; Kathleen Mullan HARRIS, *University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, USA* and Allison AIELLO, *Columbia University, USA*
Familial Loss in the Early Stages of the Life Course and the Biological Aging of U.S. Adults

602.4 Loretta Favour NTOIMO, *Federal University Oye Ekiti, Nigeria*; Friday OKONOFUA, *Centre of Excellence in Reproductive Health Innovation (CERHI), University of Benin, Nigeria*; Bola EKEZUE, *Fayetteville State University, USA*; Rosemary OGU, *University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria*; Victor OHENHEN, *Central Hospital Benin, Nigeria* and Hadiza GALADANCI, *Bayero University Kano, Nigeria*
Outcome of Interventions to Improve the Quality of Intrapartum Care in Nigeria's Referral Hospitals: A Quasi-Experimental Research Design

RC42

Social Psychology

Program Coordinator: Alison BIANCHI, *The University of Iowa, USA*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

603 Invited Session: Dr. Cecilia Ridgeway

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Alison BIANCHI, *Dept of Sociology and Criminology, USA*

Chair: Alison BIANCHI, *Dept of Sociology and Criminology, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

603.1 Cecilia RIDGEWAY, *Stanford University, USA*
Status: Why Is It Everywhere? Why Does It Matter?

17:30-19:20

604 Lecturing Diversity – Lessons from the Classroom.

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Charles PUTTERGILL, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*

Chair: Charles PUTTERGILL, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

604.1 Zitha MOKOMANE, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*
The Value in the Valley: An Autoethnographic Reflection of Teaching in a Context of Structural Inequalities during COVID-19

604.2 Kylie PARROTTA, *California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, USA*; Jessica SHAVER, *California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, USA*; Julia SEAYER, *California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, USA* and Ali BERGQUIST, *California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, USA*
Analysis of Content Warning Usage across Course Modalities

604.3 Leslie PICCA, *University of Dayton, USA*
Pedagogical Techniques for Racial Dialogue at a Predominately White Institution

604.4 Sepetla MOLAPO, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*
Classroom Diversity: Lessons from South Africa

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

605 Perceptions and Preferences about Inequality, Meritocracy and Redistribution

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*

Chair: Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

605.1 Miguel LATTZ, *Australian National University, Australia*
“Chileans’ Anger at Inequality Boils over”: The “Estallido Social” and the Role of Perceptions and the Legitimacy of Economic Inequality in Social Protests

605.2 Mathieu LIZOTTE, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
Distributive Justice, Moral Intuitions and Politics: How Do Values and Moral Judgements Shape Political Attitudes?

605.3 Yifei HUANG, *Peking University, China*
Intergenerational Mobility and Perception of Social Justice in China

605.4 Pei ZHONG, *South China Normal University, China*
The Impacts of Income Inequality Perception on Inclinations to Nationalism in China: Evidence from CGSS2008

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

605.5 Seoyoung CHOI, *sogang university, Republic of Korea*
Firm Size and Unemployment Policy Preference in South Korea -Do High-Income, High-Security Workers in Large Companies Dislike the Expansion of Unemployment Benefits?

17:30-19:20

606 Women and Children with Disability : Their Psycho-Social Susceptibility in the Modern Society.

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Maitreyee BARDHAN ROY, *Diamond Harbour Women University, India*

Chair: Alison BIANCHI, *Dept of Sociology and Criminology, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

606.1 Lopamudra SENGUPTA, *Bangabasi College, India*
Parenting a Differently Abled CHILD: Some Aspects of Rehabilitation in India.

606.2 Maitreyee BARDHAN ROY, *The Calcutta Heart Clinic and Hospital Society, India*
An Analytical Study of the Women and Disability- the Legal Politics in India.

606.3
Women and Disability: A Nadir of Marginalization

606.4 Aryama BHATTACHARYA, *Diamond Harbour Women’s University, India*
Women and Disability: A Genre of Marginalization

19:30-20:50

607 Securing Full Citizenship: Social Psychological Perspectives on Building Inclusive Communities**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Charles PUTTERGILL, *University of Pretoria, South Africa***Chair:** Charles PUTTERGILL, *University of Pretoria, South Africa***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****607.1** Sepetla MOLAPO, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*
Responsibility As Care: Thinking Solidarity Beyond Productive Forms of Care**607.2** Cawo ABDI, *University of Minnesota, USA*
Muslim Refugee Schooling: Inclusion/Exclusion in the US Public Education System.**607.3** Daniela NETO, *Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra, Portugal* and Raquel RIBEIRO, *Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra, Portugal*
The Challenges of Building Inclusive Communities: The Contribution of Studying Housing Social Representations and Practices in Portugal**Thursday 29 June**

15:30-17:20

608 RC42 Business Meeting**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Friday 30 June**

10:30-12:20

609 Social Alienation**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil***Chair:** Humberto FERNANDES, *Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****609.1** Jimin OH, *Sogang Univ., Republic of Korea*
Symbolic Struggle for the Recognition of Women in Patriarchal Confucian Funeral**609.2** Karla HENRIQUEZ OJEDA, *Université catholique de Louvain, Chile*
Academics Together and Challenged to Survive the Crisis and the Health Crisis**609.3** Dhaneeswar BHAI, *University of Edinburgh, School of Social and Political Science, Centre for South Asian Studies, United Kingdom*
Social Alienation and Suicide of Dalit Students: Everyday Reality of Indian Higher Education**609.4** Lakshmi S., *Govt. K.N.M. Arts & Science College, University of Kerala, India*
Screen-Media Parenting Practices & Its Impact on Social-Interaction of Pre-Schoolers.**Saturday 1 July**

08:30-10:20

610 Social Psychology in the Age of COVID**Location:** 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Robert SHELLY, *Ohio University, USA* and Ann SHELLY, *Ashland University, USA***Chair:** Juan Carlos CASTILLO, *Universidad de Chile, Chile***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****610.1** Yushan WANG, *University of Pennsylvania, China* and Qiwei SHI, *Columbia University, USA*
"My Media Mirror and Myself": Chinese People's Social Media Performances and Body Anxiety during COVID-19

RC43

Housing and Built Environment

Program Coordinator: Flavio DE SOUZA, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil*

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

611 Housing Affordability and Inequality during the COVID19 pandemic

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Paulina NEISCH, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Chair: Alan MORRIS, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

611.1 Akane MURAKAMI, *Momoyama Gakuin University (St. Andrew's University), Japan*
Japan's Housing Cost and Subjective Well-Being during the COVID-19 Pandemic

611.2 Paulina NEISCH, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Urban Patterns of Neighborhoods' Inequities during Covid-19 Pandemic

611.3 Gopi TADAKA, *JAWAHARLAL NEHRU UNIVERSITY, India*
Commercialization of Land and Commodification of Housing in the Neo-Liberal Era: A Sociological Study of Hyderabad City

611.4 Meryem KUCUK, *Dr., Turkey*
Urban Transformation and Segregation: The Case of Zeytinburnu, Istanbul

611.5 Claudia BA, *Technical University Darmstadt, Germany* and Sybille FRANK, *Technical University Darmstadt, Germany*
Berlin's Neighbourhoods in the Tourist Trap? Routines of Sharing Unsettled By New Urban Tourism

Wednesday 28 June

612 Housing Inequality in China

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Youqin HUANG, *University at Albany, SUNY, USA*

Chair: Alan MORRIS, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

612.1 Jianling LI, *University of Texas at Arlington, USA* and Changdong YE, *Department of Landscape Architecture & Urban planning, South China Agricultural University, China*
Metro-Induced Housing Gentrification in Guangzhou, China: A Spatial-Temporal Analysis

612.2 Fangqi WEN, *Australian National University, Australia* and Cheng CHENG, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Why Women Own Less in China? Sibship Structure, Intersibling Transfer, and Gender Inequality in Homeownership

612.4 Ling ZHU, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Has It Become Easier or Harder to be Homeowners in Contemporary Urban China? Evidence from an Age-Period-Cohort Analysis

17:30-19:20

613 Housing Inequality in Australia and New Zealand

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia*

Chair: Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

613.1 Greta WERNER, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Boundaries between Private and Public in the Construction of Limits on Social Housing in Sydney, Australia.

613.2 Jessica TERRUHN, *University of Waikato, New Zealand*
Housing Inequalities in Aotearoa New Zealand: Insights on the Role of Racism and Discrimination

613.3 Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Why Do Some Highly Disadvantaged Australian Families Become Homeless and Others Do Not? Resources in the Context of Disadvantage, Housing and Welfare

613.4 Alan MORRIS, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Housing and Inequality in Australia

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

614 Pathways into Sharing: From Space-Commoning to Collaborative Housing Practices

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Helena CERMENO MEDIAVILLA, *University of Kassel, Germany* and Carsten KELLER, *University of Kassel, Germany*

Chair: Helena CERMENO MEDIAVILLA, *University of Kassel, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

614.1 Laura GOH, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Barriers to Collaborative Housing: A Challenge Beyond Hacking the Planning System

614.2 Patricia LONCLE, *EHESP, France* and Emmanuelle MAUNAYE, *Université Rennes1, France*
Young People and Shared Housing: Between Free Choice and Constraints

614.3 Phuong NGUYEN, *University of Zurich, Switzerland*
The Family We Choose: Co-Living 4.0 and Community Building in the Digital Era

614.4 Merrick MORLEY, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Shared Spaces and Community Practices: Evidence from New Multi-Residential Dwellings in Melbourne

15:30-17:20

615 Social Design. from Theory to Practice in Building Inclusive Society.**Location:** 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Grzegorz GAWRON, *University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland* and Paulina ROJEK-ADAMEK, *Pedagogical University of Kraków, Poland***Chair:** Grzegorz GAWRON, *University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

615.1 Sophie NEMOZ, *Laboratory of Sociology and Anthropology (MSHE CNRS UAR 3124), France*
From Socialist Utopia to Social Heterotopia in Besançon, a Historical Sociology of French Cooperative Housing.

615.2 Krzysztof JANAS, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Drawing Things Together. Design As a Practice of Negotiating the Shape of a Collective World

615.3 Elisa SPERANDIO, *University of Arizona, School of Geography, Development and Environment, USA*
Urban Politics of Migrant Hospitality: Homesharing Traditions and Innovations in Bologna and Torino

617.5 Ana CAVALCANTI, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil* and Flavio DE SOUZA, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil*
Housing Development Policy Needs and Demands: The Entrepreneurial Role of the Government Invisibly Implanted By Public Policies in Brazil.

617.6 Flavio DE SOUZA, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil* and Ana CAVALCANTI, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil*
Metadiscourse in Housing the Poor: Fundamental Structural Contrasts in Land Tenure Security Programmes for the Urban Poor in Recife, Brazil.

15:30-17:20

JS-133 Understanding the Entanglements of Urban Disasters**Committees:** RC21 Regional and Urban Development (Host); RC43 Housing and Built Environment and RC39 Sociology of Disasters

See Joint Session Details for JS-133.

19:30-20:50

616 RC43 Business Meeting**Location:** 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Friday 30 June**

08:30-10:20

617 Housing Policies and Practices: Authoritarian Means to Dispossess the Urban Poor or the Tolerance of Neglected Citizens?**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Flavio DE SOUZA, *Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil***Chair:** Catherine HASTINGS, *Macquarie University, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

617.1 Avanka FERNANDO, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom*
High-Life in a High-Rise: An Ethnography of Everyday Life in a Post-Resettlement Housing Project in Colombo, Sri Lanka

617.2 Christian ROSEN, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*
Hybrid Arrangements in the Formalisation of Pueblos Jovenes in Arequipa, Peru

617.3 Daniel KUDLA, *Memorial University, Canada*
Examining the Local Policy-Making Process of Canada's National Homelessness Strategy across Atlantic Canada

617.4 Thandeka KHOWA, *North-West University, South Africa* and Siphosiso SISHUBA, *North-West University, South Africa*
A Qualitative Enquiry into Rdp Houses As a Source of Sustainable Livelihoods: Imperial Reserve, Mmabatho Local Municipality, South Africa

RC44

Labor Movements

Program Coordinator: Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

618 Learning from the Past: Historical Approaches to Labour Strategy and Their Contemporary Applications

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Maya ADERETH, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*

Chair: Tom BARNES, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

618.1 Maya ADERETH, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*
When to Labour Movements Support Universal Demands? an Organizational Perspective

618.2 Karen DOUGLAS, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Cathy BRIGDEN, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Peter FAIRBROTHER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Why History Matters for Unions

618.3 Carole YEROCHEWSKI, *CRIMT Université de Montréal, Canada*
The Gilets Jaunes, a Conflict of Subaltern Workers

618.4 Larry ISAAC, *Vanderbilt University, USA* and Brittney ROSE, *Vanderbilt University, USA*
Racial Justice and the New U.S. Labor Militancy

15:30-17:20

619 Organising in the Platform Economy

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Chris TILLY, *University of California Los Angeles, USA*

Chair: Bridget KENNY, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

619.1 Valeria PULIGNANO, *KU Leuven, Belgium*; Karol Muszyński KAROL MUSZYŃSKI, *KU Leuven, Belgium* and Maite Tapia MAITE TAPIA, *Michigan State University, USA*
It Takes Three to Tango: Bargaining Power in Online Freelancing Platform Work in Europe

619.2 Mateus MENDONCA, *London School of Economics and Political Science/ University of São Paulo, Brazil*
Understanding the Mobilizing and Organizing of Food Delivery Platform Workers in the UK and Brazil

619.3 Lutfun Nahar LATA, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Digital Labour Platforms, Resistance and Labour Protection in Bangladesh

619.4 Jing WANG, *Department of Sociology, Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Gig Workers' Resistance and State-Labour Relations in the Platform Economy—Cases from Platform Food Delivery Workers and Platform Domestic Workers in China

619.5 Rianka ROY, *University of Connecticut, USA*
'Online Is Just a Backup': Shortcomings of Virtual Protests for Tech Workers' Unions in India

619.6 Francisca GUTIERREZ CROCCO, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile* and Pablo PEREZ AHUMADA, *Universidad de Chile / COES, Chile*
Towards the Institutionalization of Labor Protest? an Analysis of Collective Action By Platform Workers in Six Latin American Countries

17:30-19:20

620 Migrant and Precarious Labour in Logistics: Mapping Employment Regimes and Reconnecting Workers Solidarities Along the Global Supply Chain

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Gabriella ALBERTI, *University, United Kingdom*; Adam MROZOWICKI, *University of Wroclaw, Poland* and Jo CUTTER, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*

Chair: Ruth MILKMAN, *CUNY Graduate Center, USA*

Discussant: Devi SACCHETTO, *University of Padua, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

620.1 Bridget KENNY, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*
The Infrastructural Labour of Logistics: Reorganising Warehouse Workers in South Africa

620.2 Chris FORDE, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Gary GRAHAM, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Ioulia BESSA, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Marketa DOLEZALOVA, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Gabriella ALBERTI, *University, United Kingdom*; Jo CUTTER, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom* and Zinovijus CIUPIJUS, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*
Employer Responses to Supply Chain Crises, Skills and the Use of Migrant Labour: Evidence from the UK Warehousing Sector

620.3 Adam MROZOWICKI, *University of Wroclaw, Poland* and Szymon PILCH, *Institute of Sociology, Poland*
Organising Potentials in Logistics in Times of Crises. the Case of Poland

620.4 Joe MORRIS, *Sheffield University, United Kingdom*
Performance-Scheduling in the UK's Warehouses: Race, Restraint and Resistance

620.5 Hans-christian STEPHAN, *TU Chemnitz, Germany*
The New Labour Mobility Regime in Leipzig Logistics Cluster after the End of Cheap Labour

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

621 Repertoires of Action

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Chris TILLY, *University of California Los Angeles, USA*

Chair: Michael GILLAN, *M261 35 Stirling Highway, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

621.1 Ruth BARTON, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Narratives, Stories and Ideas: The Missing Links in Union Repertoires.

621.2 Ben SCULLY, *University of Witwatersrand, South Africa*
Trade Unions and Public Employment Workers: The Epwp in South Africa

621.3 Peter FAIRBROTHER, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Christian LEVESQUE, *HEC, Montreal, Canada*
Union Power and Regional Governance

621.4 Stephanie LIMONCELLI, *Loyola Marymount University, USA*
Will the Real Victim Please Stand up? International Organizations, Businesses, and the Framing of Labor Exploitation in the UN Global Compact

621.5 Rina AGARWALA, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*; Chris TILLY, *University of California Los Angeles, USA* and Aabid FIRDAUSI, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*
The Golden Hour of Informal Workers' Organizational Experiments Under Neoliberalism: A Cross-Country Study

15:30-17:20

622 Labour Politics in East Asia

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Jenny CHAN, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong* and Eli FRIEDMAN, *Cornell University, USA*

Chair: Eli FRIEDMAN, *Cornell University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

622.1 Chris CHAN, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom* and Wing Yin Anna TSUI, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Democratic Trade Unions in Authoritarian State: Lesions from the New Trade Union Movement in Hong Kong

622.2 Chun-Yi LEE, *University of Nottingham, school of Politics and International Relations, United Kingdom* and Bonny LING, *Institute for Human Rights and Business, United Kingdom*
Cost of Taiwan's 'Silicon Shield': The Human Implication of 'Made in Taiwan'

622.3 Jiwei QIAN, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Whole-of-Nation Innovation, Labor Market, and Industrial Transformation in China

622.4 Lefeng LIN, *Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University, China*
Social Mobilization: A Pragmatic Logic of Chinese Trade Union Reform

622.5 Mujun ZHOU, *Zhejiang University, China*
The Interstitial Emergence of Labor NGO Activism in China and Its Contradicting Institutionalization, 1996-2020

17:30-19:20

JS-49 Labor Unrest, Social Revolts and Revolutions, 1851-2020: Findings from the Global Social Protest Database

Committees: *RC44 Labor Movements (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change and RC02 Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-49.

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

623 Labour Internationalisms from Above and Below

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Katherine NASTOVSKI, *York University, Canada* and Kim SCIPES, *Purdue University Northwest, USA*

Chair: Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

623.1 Kim SCIPES, *Purdue University Northwest, USA*
What Have We Learned about Building Global Labor Solidarity?

623.2 Katherine NASTOVSKI, *York University, Canada*
The Trials and Tribulations of Institutionalizing a Rank-and-File Led Labour Internationalism

623.3 Aabid FIRDAUSI, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*
War of Position in Global Garment Production Networks – the Case of the Asia Floor Wage Alliance

623.4 Sonal SHARMA, *Department of Sociology, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore (USA), USA*
Solidarities with Difference: Immigrant Workers and Alliance Building in Domestic Workers' Movement in South Africa

623.5 Antonio ARAVENA, *Universidad Diego Portales, Chile*
El Sindicalismo En Empresas Multinacionales Que Operan En Chile En El Marco Del COVID-19

15:30-17:20

624 Global and Regional Trade Unions and the Future of Work Regulation

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Michael GILLAN, *M261 35 Stirling Highway, Australia* and Dimitris STEVIS, *Colorado State University, USA*

Chair: Kim SCIPES, *Purdue University Northwest, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

624.1 Juliane REINECKE, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom* and Jimmy DONAGHEY, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Stitching Governance for Labour Rights: Towards Transnational Industrial Democracy?

624.2 Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Strategies for Tackling Gbv in the Workplace: The Iuf's Experiment with Global Agreements to Fight Sexual Harassment

624.3 Michael GILLAN, *M261 35 Stirling Highway, Australia*
The Global Unions and the Quest for a Living Wage

624.4 Dimitris STEVIS, *Colorado State University, USA*
The Environmental Politics of Global and Regional Union Organizations: The Impacts of Positionality and Ideology

17:30-19:20

625 RC44 Business Meeting

Location: M2 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

626 Rethinking Unionism

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Tom BARNES, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

Chair: Vichhra MOUYLY, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

626.1 Jamie MCCALLUM, *Middlebury College, USA*
An Injury to All: Essential Workers and Public Health during the Pandemic

626.2 Bradon ELLEM, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Resource Unions in Crisis

626.3 John MASHAYAMOMBE, *Nelson Mandela University, South Africa*
Sanitised Workplace Order: A Glimpse into the Character of Two New Mining Operations in South Africa

626.4 Kumiko HAGIWARA, *St. Andrew's University, Japan*
The Effect of Marketization on Childcare Union in Japan: State Suppression of the Care Movement or Step Toward a New Upsurge?

626.5 Iain CAMPBELL, *Centre for Employment and Labour Relations Law, University of Melbourne, Australia*
Power Resources Theory and Australian Trade Unions

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

626.6 Tom BARNES, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Reimagining the 'Ideal Worker': Evidence from Australian Warehouse Logistics

10:30-12:20

627 Strikes: Past, Present and Futures

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Josep Maria ANTENTAS, *Universitat Ramon Llull, Spain*

Chair: Ernesto NORONHA, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

627.1 Alpan BIRELMA, *Ozyegin University, Turkey*
An Unexpected Strike Wave in a Low-Strike Country Under Deepening Authoritarianism: Strikes at the Beginning of 2022 in Turkey

627.2 Katia PILATI, *University of Trento, Department of Sociology and Social Research, Italy* and Sabrina PERRA, *University of Cagliari, Italy*
Explaining Labor Movements Today: Workers' Economic and Political Strikes

627.3 Pablo PEREZ AHUMADA, *Universidad de Chile / COES, Chile* and Rosario PINTO, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile*
Why Do Union Members Are More Willing to Strike and Protest Than Non-Union Members? Evidence from Argentina and Chile

627.4 Denise VESPER, *Saarland University, Germany*; Cornelius KÖNIG, *Saarland University, Germany* and Norma RUF, *Saarland University, Germany*
Willingness to Strike Among Flight Attendants

627.5 Josep Maria ANTENTAS, *Universitat Ramon Llull, Spain*
The Multiple Debates on the Strike: In Search of Complementarity and an Overall Vision

627.6 John KALLAS, *Cornell University ILR School, USA*
Emerging Categories of Strikes in the United States

15:30-17:20

628 Gendered Workplace Violence: What Role for the Labour Movement?

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Vichhra MOUYLY, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Bradon ELLEM, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

628.1 Allyson STOKES, *Memorial University, Canada*
#MeToo and Sexual Misconduct in Entertainment: Worker Perspectives on Labour, Activism, and Unions

628.2 Vichhra MOUYLY, *The University of Sydney, Cambodia*
Addressing Gbhv: A Critical Assessment of Garment Union Strategies in Cambodia

628.3 Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Petr MATOUS, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Jie YIN, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Kristy WARD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Tweeting Against Workplace Violence and Harassment: The Global Unions' Use of Social Media in the Campaign for the Ratification of C190

19:30-20:50

629 Collective and Connective Action: Workers and Social Media

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Joerg NOWAK, *Universidade de Brasilia, Brazil* and Marco SANTANA, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Ernesto NORONHA, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

629.1 Simon JOYCE, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom* and Mark STUART, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*
Old Unions and New Technology: Connective and Collective Action from Above and below

629.2 Alexandre FRAGA, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Mobilizaciones En El Contexto De La Pandemia: El Uso De Las Redes Sociales Por Organizaciones De Trabajadoras Del Hogar En Brasil

629.3 Mateusz KAROLAK, *University of Wrocław, Poland*
Making of the Essential Workers? the Twitter Discourse of Polish Trade Unions during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

629.4 Estu Putri WILUJENG, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
Indonesian Digital Laborers' Protest: Strike and Spamming

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

630 Labour Relations and Strategic Industries in Brazil

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Joerg NOWAK, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil* and Leonardo MELLO E SILVA, *University of São Paulo, Brazil*

Chair: Mark ANNER, *State College, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

630.1 Joerg NOWAK, *Universidade de Brasília, Brazil*; Ricardo FRAMIL FILHO, *University of São Paulo, Brazil* and Gabriel Souza Martins JUNCAL, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Interest Formation of Workers in the Global and Fragmented Economy

630.2 Danilo MENDES, *Universidade Federal de São Carlos (UFSCar), Brazil* and Leonardo MELLO E SILVA, *University of São Paulo, Brazil*
Attempts to Regulate the Oil Sector: Petrobras' Global Union Network

630.3 Filipe MELO, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Labour Resistance Against Factories Shutdown in the Global South: The Case of Ford Motor Company in Brazil

10:30-12:20

631 Labour and the Green Transition

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Bradon ELLEM, *University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Bradon ELLEM, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

631.1 Dimitris STEVIS, *Colorado State University, USA*
Labour Unions and Green Transitions in the USA: Contestations and Explanations

631.2 Vera TRAPPMANN, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Jo CUTTER, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Felix SCHULZ, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom* and Ursula BALDERSON, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*
Worker Representation in the Green Transition

631.3 Diane SICOTTE, *Drexel University, USA*; Kelly JOYCE, *Drexel University, USA* and Arielle HESSE, *Drexel University, USA*
Negotiating the Future: U.S. Labor Unions and Low-Carbon Energy Transition

631.4 Darryn SNELL, *RMIT University, Australia* and AI RAINNIE, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Reclaiming Just Transition: Unions and the Fight for Nature and Jobs

17:30-19:20

632 Labour and Climate Change

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Bradon ELLEM, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Frances FLANAGAN, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Caleb GOODS, *University of Western Australia, Australia*

Chair: Adam MROZOWICKI, *University of Wrocław, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

632.1 Torsten GEELAN, *Department of Sociology, University of Copenhagen, Denmark*
Transitioning to a just low carbon economy: a critical and interdisciplinary review of the role of the trade union movement

632.2 Naorem MANGANG, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India* and Pradip SWARNAKAR, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
From Coal to Renewables: A Study of the Perspectives of Indian Coal Industry's Labour Unions

632.3 Rebecca PEARSE, *Australian National University, Australia*
Segmented Transition: Patterns in a Life-History Study of Electricity Workers amidst Industrial Change

632.4 Omar MANKY, *Universidad del Pacífico, Peru*
A Pessimistic Exploration of the Links between Exploitation and Commodification in Latin America.

632.5 Elias KOENIG, *Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies (IASS) Potsdam, Germany*
Striking Fossil Capital - Towards a Theory of the Climate Strike

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

633 Authoritarian Innovations in Labour Governance

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Michael GILLAN, *M261 35 Stirling Highway, Australia*

Chair: Peter FAIRBROTHER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

633.1 Mark ANNER, *State College, USA* and Cirila QUINTERO, *Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico*
Between Labor Control and Worker Empowerment: Authoritarian Innovations and Democratic Reforms in Mexico

633.2 Adam MROZOWICKI, *University of Wrocław, Poland*
Authoritarian Innovations in the Polish Industrial Relations: From Liberal to Illiberal Illusory Corporatism?

633.3 Isil ERDINC, *Universite libre de Bruxelles, Belgium*
Authoritarian Innovations in Labour Governance in Turkey

633.4 Ernesto NORONHA, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India* and Premilla D'CRUZ, *Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, India*
The Interface between Authoritarian Innovations and Labour: Implications for Indian Workers

633.5 Chris RHOMBERG, *Fordham University, USA*
*Authoritarian Innovation in the United States: The Role of
Judicial and Subnational Labor Governance*

633.6 Steven TUFTS, *York University, Canada*
*North American Unions and Response to Covid-19: Enabling or
Resisting Authoritarian Populism?*

14:30-16:20

**JS-154 Trade Unions Under Authoritarianism in
the Global South**

Committees: *RC30 Sociology of Work (Host); RC44 Labor
Movements*

See Joint Session Details for JS-154.

RC45 Rational Choice

Program Coordinator: Jun KOBAYASHI, *Seikei University, Japan*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

634 Computational Social Science and Rational Choice

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Rense CORTEN, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*; Yoshimichi SATO, *Kyoto University of Advanced Science, Japan*; Bas HOFSTRA, *Radboud University, Netherlands*; Hiroki TAKIKAWA, *University of Tokyo, Japan* and Kazuto MISUMI, *Kyushu University, Japan*

Chair: Yoshimichi SATO, *Kyoto University of Advanced Science, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

634.1 Rense CORTEN, *Utrecht University, Netherlands* and Paul SCHULER, *University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom*
Quantity over Quality? Rating Dynamics in Online Markets

634.2 Giacomo VACCARIO, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*; Luca VERGINER, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland* and Frank SCHWEITZER, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*
Reproducing Scientists' Mobility: A Data-Driven Model

634.3 Masayuki KANAI, *Senshu University, Japan*
The Role of Trust on Wellbeing in Different Social Settings

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

635 Dynamics of Capitals and Social Inequality from the Rational Choice Perspective

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Masayuki KANAI, *Senshu University, Japan*

Chair: Masayuki KANAI, *Senshu University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

635.1 Jun KOBAYASHI, *Seikei University, Japan*
Beauty Capital: Roles of Physical Attractiveness on Social Inequalities from Rational Choice Perspective

635.2 Roland ZARZYCKI, *Collegium Civitas, Poland*
Transformations of Capital, Justification and Rationalization Structures

635.3 Dolly ORTIZ, *UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE AGUASCALIENTES, Mexico*
Racionality and Time

15:30-17:20

636 Evolution of Social Norms and Cooperation

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Andreas DIEKMANN, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

Chair: Andreas DIEKMANN, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

636.1 Ana MACANOVIC, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*; Milena TSVETKOVA, *London School of Economics and Political Science, United Kingdom*; Wojtek PRZEPIORKA, *Utrecht University, Netherlands* and Vincent BUSKENS, *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

Signals of Belonging: Emergence of Signalling Norms As Facilitators of Parochial Cooperation

636.2 Roland ZARZYCKI, *Collegium Civitas, Poland*
The Strategies of Pretense and Disguise As Norm-Destabilizing Factors

636.3 Frank SCHWEITZER, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*; Luca VERGINER, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland* and Giacomo VACCARIO, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

Should the Government Reward Cooperation? Insights from an Agent-Based Model of Wealth Redistribution

636.4 Kazuto MISUMI, *Kyushu University, Japan*
Free Rider As Stock of Social Capital in Local Community

Wednesday 28 June

637 What makes sociology credible?

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Gianluca MANZO, *Sorbonne University, France*

Chair: Gianluca MANZO, *Sorbonne University, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

637.1 Emily ERIKSON, *Yale University, USA*
Sociology As the Study of Second-Order Consequences

637.2 Lucas SAGE, *European University Institute, France*
Scientific Interactions and Its Consequences on Inequality: A Mechanism-Based Perspective.

637.3 Clemens KRONEBERG, *Institute of Sociology and Social Psychology, University of Cologne, Germany*
Analytical Sociology: Methodological Reflections on Theory, Methods, and Data

637.4 Andreas FLACHE, *University of Groningen/ ICS, Netherlands*
On Credible Sociological Model Building: Potential and Pitfalls of Empirically Realistic Agent-Based Models

19:30-20:50

638 RC45 Business Meeting

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

639 RC45 Open Oral Session on Advances in Rational Choice Research

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jun KOBAYASHI, *Seikei University, Japan*

Chair: Jun KOBAYASHI, *Seikei University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

639.1 Andreas DIEKMANN, *University of Leipzig, Germany*; Wojtek PRZEPIORKA, *Utrecht University, Netherlands* and Felix RIES, *University of Leipzig, Germany*
Emergence of Inefficient Norms

639.2 Naoki SUDO, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*
Why Did Increasing Number of Newly Infected Individuals Positively Affect Trust in the Government during the COVID-19 Pandemic?

639.3 Guillermina JASSO, *Two Washington Square Village, USA* and Yoshimichi SATO, *Kyoto University of Advanced Science, Japan*
Rational Choice and the Justice Pulse: Inferring Justice from Inequality

639.4 Rafael PLANCARTE, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*
Game Theory and Internalist Perspective on Rational Choice: Possibilities for a Coherent Connection

639.5 Marek BOZYKOWSKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland* and Mikolaj JASINSKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Strength in Unity, Strength in Dispersion. Power Indices in the European Parliament Under Different Game Theory Models.

639.6 Kunihiro KIMURA, *Tohoku University, Japan*
Question Formats, Response Styles, and Satisficing: A Bounded Rationality Approach to Questionnaire Design.

17:30-19:20

640 Rational Choice and Unintended Consequences amid Social Crisis

Location: 214 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Naoki SUDO, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*

Chair: Naoki SUDO, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

640.1 Ilias LATYPOV, *National Research University Higher School of Economics, Russian Federation*

Rational Choice and Unintended Consequences Under Restrictions during a Pandemic: Theoretical Reflection

640.2 Jörg STOLZ, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*; Alexi GUGUSHVILI, *University of Oslo, Norway*; Francesco MOLTENI, *University of Milan, Italy* and Jean-Philippe ANTONIETTI, *University of Lausanne, Switzerland*
A Counterexample to Secularization Theory? Assessing the Georgian Religious Revival

640.3 Xuan WEN, *Free University of Berlin, Germany*
Unintended Dilemma: A Sociological Analysis of the Domestic Waste Disposal in Rural China

RC46

Clinical Sociology

Program Coordinator: Tina UYS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-4 Return Migration during a Pandemic: Challenges and Interventions

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC31 Sociology of Migration

See Joint Session Details for JS-4.

15:30-17:20

JS-10 Panel Discussion: Accrediting Your Undergraduate or Graduate Program in Sociological Practice: A Workshop on Process, Benefits, and Outcomes By the Commission on the Accreditation of Programs in Applied and Clinical Sociology (CAPACS)

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

See Joint Session Details for JS-10.

17:30-19:20

641 RC46 Business Meeting

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Emma PORIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*

Chair: Emma PORIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

642 The History of Clinical Sociology in Different Regions of the World

Language: English, French

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Jan Marie FRITZ, *University of Cincinnati (USA) and University of Johannesburg (SA), USA* and Zarine ROCHA, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Chair: Zarine ROCHA, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Discussant: Puspa WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

642.1 Jan Marie FRITZ, *Univ. of Cincinnati and Univ. of Johannesburg, USA*
Alice Stokes Paul and Clinical Sociology

642.2 Jacques RHEAUME, *Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Canada*
The Development of Clinical Sociology in Canada, France, Latin America.

10:30-12:20

643 Certified Clinical Sociologists: In and out of the Academy

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Melodye LEHNERER, *College of Southern Nevada, USA*

Chair: Melodye LEHNERER, *College of Southern Nevada, USA*

Discussant: Sara CUMMING, *Sheridan College, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

643.1 Mariam SEEDAT-KHAN, *University of KwaZulu Natal, South Africa*
Professional Development Gains: COVID-19 Aacs Certification and Clinical Practice

15:30-17:20

644 Community Resilience Innovations in Food Security and Health: Towards Resilient Recovery from the COVID-19 Pandemic

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Emma PORIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*; Maria Aurora Teresita TABADA, *Visayas State University, Philippines* and Mary Angeline SATAKE, *Nagoya Gakuin University, Japan*

Chair: Sara CUMMING, *Sheridan College, Canada*

Panelist: Nirvana PILLAY, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

644.1 Edgardo TULIN, EDGARDO, *Visayas State University, Philippines*; Maria Aurora Teresita TABADA, *Visayas State University, Philippines* and Lilian NUNEZ, *Visayas State University, Philippines*
Root Crops for Food Security and Community Resilience

644.2 Monica MURERO, *University Unina, Italy*
Interdigital Agents Innovating Digital Care during and beyond COVID-19 : a bottom-up future for Digital Health?

644.3 Michiko KADOBAYASHI, *Japan Women's University, Japan*
"Awareness Contexts" Reflected in Cancer Tobyo-Ki

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

645 Mythical Thinking, Religion and Politics. What about Democracy Today?

Language: English, French

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jacques RHEAUME, *Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Canada*

Chair: Jacques RHEAUME, *Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

645.1 Michael MARANDA, *Western Michigan University The Evaluation Center, USA* and Augie DIANA, *Retired National Institutes of Health & Independent Consultant, USA*
Using the Cry Freedom to Undermine Local Governments in the United States—the COVID-19 Pandemic.

645.2 Ayoub AITDRA, *Mohammed V University in Rabat, Morocco* and Toufiq KOSSARI, *L'université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah de Fès, Morocco*
La Sociologie Clinique Face à l'Autoritarisme Dans Le Maroc Actuel : Quels Enjeux Épistémiques Et Politiques Pour Les Récits De Vie ?

645.3 Louisa BARALONGA, *Université Sorbonne Paris Cité (Denis Diderot - Paris 7), France*
Laïcité En Débat En Formation En Travail Social Dans Un Contexte Post-Attentat En 2016

645.4 Margarita KALASHNIKOVA, *St. Tikhon's Orthodox Humanitarian U., Russian Federation* and Natalia EROKHOVA, *RUDN University, Russian Federation*
Project "Death Cafe"

17:30-19:20

646 Addressing the Opportunities, Challenges and Lessons of Paid Domestic Work

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: David DU TOIT, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Chair: Ugljesa RADULOVIC, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

646.1 David DU TOIT, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Labor Agency, Resistance and Resilience: The Experiences of Migrant Male Domestic Workers in South Africa

646.2 Bianca TAME, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Matching 'Comfortable Others': Private Employment Agencies Response to an 'Intimate Workplace Crisis' in South Africa's Domestic Sector

646.3 Tengetile NHLEKO, *University of Cape Town, Eswatini*
Emerging Trends in the Platformization of Domestic Work in South Africa: Marginal Formalization and Deepening Informalization of Domestic Work Employment

646.4 Mayte VAZQUEZ, *Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios Superiores en Antropología Social, Mexico*
Trabajo Del Hogar, Movilidad Social y Estigma: Una Mirada Auto-Etnográfica

646.5 Kritika PANDEY, *University of Southern California, USA*
Fighting for Rights While Negotiating Informality: Struggles of Domestic Worker Organizing and Everyday Inequalities during COVID-19

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

647 Womxn Navigating Academic Exclusion

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Mariam SEEDAT-KHAN, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Chair: Mariam SEEDAT-KHAN, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Discussant: Nirvana PILLAY, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

647.1 Amitra WALL, *SUNY Buffalo State College, USA*
Making It in the Academy: Self Reflection of Challenges and Successes

647.2 Aradhana RAMNUND-MANSINGH, *MANCOSA, South Africa*
South African Lone Mothers Challenges: Graduation in Adversity

647.3 Aradhana RAMNUND-MANSINGH, *MANCOSA, South Africa*
The Queen Bees and Imposters Are Responsible! Women in Academia – the Unspoken Challenges

10:30-12:20

648 Strengthening Democracy through Participation in Local Governance

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Emma PORIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines* and Noralene UY, *Ateneo de Manila University and International Recovery Platform, Philippines*

Chair: Mieko YAMADA, *Purdue University Fort Wayne, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

648.1 Okesh DHARAMPAL, *central university of Haryana, India* and Yudhveer YUDHVEER, *Central University of Haryana, India*
Practice and Participation of Young Women in Village Panchayat: A Study of Haryana

648.2 Tetiana LUKERIA, *Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Ukraine*
The Role of Local Self-Government Reform in Strengthening Local Democracy

648.3 Marek NOWAK, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland* and Anna BERNACIAK, *University of Economics and Business, Poznan, Poland*
Environmental and Social Challenges of Managing a Satellite City at the End of the Intensive Suburbanization Phase. a Case Study of Luboń Near Poznań (2020-22)

648.4 Marilena MACALUSO, *Palermo University, Italy*
The Political Participation of Migrants: The Council of Cultures in Palermo

648.5 Pragna RUGUNANAN, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
"Refugees, Family Well-Being and Urbanisation Trends in Africa"

15:30-17:20

JS-104 Whistleblowing and Social Justice

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization

See Joint Session Details for JS-104.

17:30-19:20

JS-105 Building Local Participatory Democracies in the Era of Threatened National Democracies and Resurgent Authoritarianism.

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology (Host); RC18 Political Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-105.

19:30-20:50

649 Marginalized Communities As Agents of Social Change

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Puspa WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*

Chair: Puspa WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

649.1 Mariam SEEDAT-KHAN, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa* and Johanna ZULUETA, *Toyo University, Japan*
Women on the Edge of COVID-19: A Clinical Focus on Family, Work and Community.

649.2 Kamil LUCZAJ, *University of Lodz, Poland*
Working-Class Academics As Agents of Social Change. Les Miraculés Versus Institutional Doxa

649.3 Tinovimba PATSIKA, *None, Zimbabwe*
Unheard Voices – the Lived Experiences & Coping Mechanisms of Young Zimbabwean Homosexuals.

649.4 Flavia Alessandra DE SOUZA, *Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz, Brazil*
The Association of People with Sickle Cell Disease (APEDFI) and black women with sickle cell disease (SCD) in Ilhéus-BA (Brazil): oppressions, mobilization and achievements

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

650 Citizen Involvement and Co-Production of Care in Vulnerable Communities

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Isabelle RUELLAND, *University of Quebec in Montreal UQAM, Canada*

Chair: Isabelle RUELLAND, *University of Quebec in Montreal UQAM, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

650.1 Jeff WILL, *Bldg 1/1901, USA* and Tracy MILLIGAN, *UNF Center for Community Initiatives, USA*
Community Partners in Evaluation and Change: Reflections on a Quarter-Century Evaluation of an Intervention Project Addressing Racial Disparities in Health Outcomes

650.2 Sachio ISHIDA, *Asia University, Japan*
Cares to Lessen Solitary Communities and Loneliness in Japan

650.3 Kentaro ISHIJIMA, *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*
How to Recognize Innate Disposition of Care Workers

650.4 Jacques RHEAUME, *Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Canada*
Community Development in the City: A Clinical Sociology Approach

15:30-17:20

651 Clinical Sociologists in Poverty Eradication Efforts

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Puspa WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*

Chair: Anthony KAZIBONI, *University of Johannesburg (UJ), South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

651.1 Swazi HLATSHWAYO, *UKZN Student, South Africa*
Poverty, Suicide and COVID-19

651.2 Nadia CAROLISSEN, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Exploring Business Incubator Social Processes & Developing Youth Entrepreneurial Human Capital

651.3 Natalia EROKHOVA, *RUDN University, Russian Federation* and Margarita KALASHNIKOVA, *St. Tikhon's Orthodox Humanitarian U., Russian Federation*
Chronic Multigenerational Poverty: Psychosociogenetics' Perspectives

651.4 Lesego PLANK, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
A Reflective Analysis of Grassrootfamily-a Mgazato
(Crowdfunding) Initiative

17:30-19:20

652 **Springer's Clinical Sociology Book**
Series: Celebrating the New Books and
Submitting Your Proposal

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jan Marie FRITZ, *University of Cincinnati*
(USA) and University of Johannesburg (SA), USA

Chair: Jan Marie FRITZ, *University of Cincinnati (USA) and*
University of Johannesburg (SA), USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

652.1 Puspa WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia* and Halim
 WAN, *Taylor's University, Malaysia*
Clinical Sociology: Moving from Theory to Practice

652.2 Zarine ROCHA, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Applied and Clinical Sociology in Aotearoa New Zealand

652.3 Harry PERLSTADT, *Michigan State University, USA*
Social Science Research Ethics

652.4 Vidette BESTER, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Crossing Mineral Borders and Boundaries: A Look at Artisanal
Mining in South Africa

RC47

Social Classes and Social Movements

Program Coordinators: Breno BRINGEL, *State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Sabrina ZAJAK, *Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany*; Simin FADAEI, *The University of Manchester, United Kingdom* and Shruti TAMBE, *Savitribai Phule Pune University, India*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

653 RC47 Opening Session: Global Dialogues in Social Movement Studies

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Paolo GERBAUDO, *Scuola Normale Superiore, Italy*

Chair: Ana Margarida ESTEVES, *Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa NIF: 501 510 184, Portugal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

653.1 Geoffrey PLEYERS, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium*
A Global Sociology of Social Movements after the Decolonial Turn

653.2 Simin FADAEI, *The University of Manchester, United Kingdom*
Social Movements, Global Marxism and Decolonial Perspectives

653.3 Sabrina ZAJAK, *DEZIM Institute, Germany*
Dialogues between Social Movement Studies and Research on Migration and Racism

653.4 Breno BRINGEL, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain, and State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Social Movements and the Geopolitics of Socioecological Transitions

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC24 *Environment and Society* RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements* and RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-3.

15:30-17:20

JS-11 Religious Actors and Social Movements in Contemporary World

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-11.

17:30-19:20

654 Food for Justice

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Marco Antonio TEIXEIRA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

Chair: Mariana CALCAGNI, *FU Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

654.1 Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*
Social Movements As Agents of Change: Fighting Intersectional Food Inequalities, Building Food As Webs of Life

654.2 Lea ZENTGRAF, *Heidelberg University, Germany*
Food Movements in Germany: An Explorative Mapping

654.3 Marco Antonio TEIXEIRA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*
Food Movements in the Brazilian Amazon: Struggles for Socio-Ecological Transformation

654.4 Eryka GALINDO, *Heidelberg University, Germany*
Human Coexistence with the Semiarid Region and Fights for Transformations in Food Systems: The Case of the Brazilian Semiarid Articulation (ASA)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-28 Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Public Sphere

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-28.

10:30-12:20

JS-34 Religious Actors and Social movements: Gender and Sexual Diversity

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-34.

15:30-17:20

JS-43 Religious Actors and Social Movements: The Ecological Turn

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

See Joint Session Details for JS-43.

17:30-19:20

655 Intersectional Gender Politics on the Right, Antifeminist Backlash, and Feminist Politics of Resistance**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Janet CONWAY, Brock University, Canada**Chair:** Manisha DESAI, University of Connecticut, USA**Discussant:** Janet CONWAY, Brock University, Canada**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

655.1 Julia LAUREAU, *Universite Catholique de Louvain, Belgium*
Right-Wing Mobilizations and Feminist Resistance in Contemporary Poland : The Struggle over Abortion As a Case Study

655.2 Manisha DESAI, *University of Connecticut, USA* and Rianka ROY, *University of Connecticut, USA*
To Wear or Not to Wear: Hijab, Feminists, and Fundamentalists

655.3 Melina BONERZ, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
The Mexican Women's Movement and #Ellasnomerepresentan: On the Linkage between Digital Antifeminism and State Repression

655.4 Antonio ALVAREZ-BENAVIDES, *National Distance Education University / GESF, Spain* and Francisco JIMÉNEZ AGUILAR, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Anti-Feminism, Secularization and Gender in the Spanish Far-Right Vox

655.5 Danielle COENGA-OLIVEIRA, *Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada*
Anti-Gender Campaigns in Brazil: The Consolidation of an Antifeminist State

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

655.6 Magdalena MUSZEL, *Fundacja Zatoka, Poland*
Feminist Movements and Opposing Anti-Gender Campaigns in Poland.

656.3 Alexis CORTES MORALES, *Universidad Alberto Hurtado, Chile*
El Ciclo De Movilización y El Rechazo a La Nueva Constitución En Chile

656.4 Charif ELALAOUI, *Université de Caen, France*
The Yellow Vests and Working-Class Neighborhoods, What (dis)Articulations ?

656.5 Lugin SETYAWATI, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
Youth Digital Activism: The Meaning Making of Social and Political Engagements

656.6 Paolo GERBAUDO, *Scuola Normale Superiore, Italy*
Video-Sharing and Social Movements: Imitation As the New Logic of Participation?

10:30-12:20

657 Capitalism and Class in Contemporary Social Movements**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Simin FADAEI, *The University of Manchester, United Kingdom*; Paolo GERBAUDO, *King's College London, United Kingdom*; Ana Margarida ESTEVES, *Instituto Universitario de Lisboa, ISCTE - IUL, Portugal* and Daniele DI NUNZIO, *Fondazione Giuseppe Di Vittorio, Italy***Chair:** Simin FADAEI, *The University of Manchester, United Kingdom***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

657.1 Alexandre MARTINS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Class and Queer Struggles: The Critique of Capitalism in Contemporary Latin American Queer Politics

657.2 Shray MEHTA, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Agrarian Populism and Authoritarian Hegemony in India: Farmers' Movements and Electoral Politics at Crossroads

657.3 Elisio ESTANQUE, *UNESP-Franca/SP, Brazil* and Daniel Gameiro FRANCISCO, *University of Coimbra, Portugal*
Remaking Class Divisions and Territories: Space, Class Conflict and Consent in Two Portuguese Districts - Setúbal and Aveiro

657.4 Ahmed MORI, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*
The Politics of Real Utopias: Labor Regimes in a Cleveland Laundry Cooperative

15:30-17:20

JS-76 The Criminalization of Struggles for Rights, Democratic Regression, and Legal Mobilisation. Part I**Committees:** RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC12 Sociology of Law

See Joint Session Details for JS-76.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

656 Social Movements Democratic Practices**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Sabrina ZAJAK, *German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Berlin & Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany***Chair:** Sabrina ZAJAK, *DEZIM Institute, Germany***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

656.1 Cristina FLESHER FOMINAYA, *Aarhus University, Denmark* and Natalia MIRANDA, *Aarhus University, Denmark*
State-Movement Relations in Comparative Perspective: Findings from the Deminova Project

656.2 Philipp ALTMANN, *Universidad Central del Ecuador, Ecuador*
Discursive Shifts and Strategic Alliances in the National Indigenous Uprisings in Ecuador in 2019 and 2022

17:30-19:20

658 Social Movements, Decolonial Perspectives and Struggles Against Coloniality of Power**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Phoebe Zoe Maria SANCHEZ, *DeZIM-Institut, and College of Social Sciences in UP Cebu, Germany***Co-chairs:** Caroline SCHOEPEF, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Philippines* and Matthew M CHEW, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****658.1** Bhumika MUCHHALA, *Thrid World Network, USA*
Structural and Knowledge Power of Austerity in the World Economic Order: Examining Dependency in the Global Political Economy and Rethinking Delinking through Decoloniality**658.2** Ruth AMWE, *Princeton Theological Seminary, USA*
Constructing Spaces of Duality: Feminizing Social Movements and Methods in Nigeria**658.3** Judith ALTROGGE, *Institute of Migration Research and Intercultural Studies (IMIS) Osnabrueck University, Germany*
Transnational Activist Struggles Against Deportation As Political Remittances to the Gambia**658.4** Omar LUJAN, *Ryerson University, Canada*; Nick DREHER, *Ryerson University, Canada* and Funmi ASOLO, *Ryerson University, Canada*
Eurocentrism, Decoloniality, and Potential Alternatives: Addressing Western Traditions in the Study of Sanctuary, Solidarity, and Hospitality**658.5** Phoebe Zoe Maria SANCHEZ, *University of the Philippines Cebu, Philippines*
"Corporate Impunity in Sustained Modern-Day Coloniality of Power: The Case of the Pantaron Range, Talaingod, Davao Del Norte, Philippines"

19:30-20:50

659 RC47 Business Meeting**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Thursday 29 June**

08:30-10:20

JS-86 New Urban Mobilizations and Solidarities - Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives**Committees:** *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC21 Regional and Urban Development*

See Joint Session Details for JS-86.

10:30-12:20

JS-95 The Potential of Food Movements and Intersectional Food Inequalities**Committees:** *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-95.

15:30-17:20

660 Collaborative Research with Social Movements**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Laurence COX, *Maynooth University, Ireland* and Alberto ARRIBAS, *Maynooth University, Ireland***Chair:** Breno BRINGEL, *State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****660.1** Izaro GOROSTIDI, *University of Basque Country, Spain*; Andere ORMAZABAL, *University of the Basque Country, Spain* and Igor GURRUTXAGA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Collaborative Research with Social Movements**660.2** Katia VALENZUELA FUENTES, *Universidad de Concepción, Chile*
Militant Research and Autonomous Politics in Post-Uprising Chile**660.3** Aide ESU, *University of Cagliari, Italy* and Valeria DESSI, *University of Cagliari, Italy*
Prefiguring the Future of an Anti-Military Occupation Movement in Italy: A Case Study of Collaborative Research Production**660.4** Daniele DI NUNZIO, *Fondazione Giuseppe Di Vittorio, Italy*
Intervention Research and Labour Movements: Theory, Experiences and Challenges

17:30-19:20

661 Social Movements, Solidarity Economy and Common Goods**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** P3 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Julian REBON, *Universidad de Buenos Aires- Conicet, Argentina* and Jose ITZIGSOHN, *Brown University, USA***Chair:** Antonio ALVAREZ-BENAVIDES, *National Distance Education University / GESP, Spain***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****661.1** Ana Margarida ESTEVES, *Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa NIF: 501 510 184, Portugal*
Approaches to Localism and Multi-Level Governance in Transnational Solidarity Economy Movement Networks: A Comparative Analysis**661.2** Julian REBON, *Universidad de Buenos Aires- Conicet, Argentina* and Jose ITZIGSOHN, *Brown University, USA*
The Social and Institutional Bases of the Solidarity Economy**661.3** Theresa PETRAY, *James Cook University, Australia* and Janine GERTZ, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
"for the Good of Gugu Badhun People": Indigenous Economic Development, Sharing and Sovereignty**661.4** Fabio SANCHEZ, *Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos, Brazil*
Interrogations Regarding the Reconfiguration of Social Movements – from the Grammar of Rights to the Solidarity Economy

661.5 Yerko GARCIA, *Pontifical Catholic University of Chile, Chile*
Un Acercamiento a La Diversidad De Procesos De Economización. El Caso De Las Economías Mapuche, En Los Proyectos De Intervención Territorial (ERNC y Forestales).

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-114 Black Lives and the New Wave of Antiracist Mobilization within and across World Regions

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); RC38 Biography and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-114.

10:30-12:20

662 Far-Right Movements, Authoritarianism and Pandemic

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Emanuele TOSCANO, *University G. Marconi, Italy* and Antonio ALVAREZ-BENAVIDES, *John Jay College of Criminal Justice, City University of New York, USA*

Chair: Daniele DI NUNZIO, *Fondazione Giuseppe Di Vittorio, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

662.1 Andrea GRIPPO, *Guglielmo Marconi University, Italy*
No-Vax and Extreme Right. the Conspiracy Side of the Pandemic

662.2 Emanuele TOSCANO, *University G. Marconi, Italy*
Contagious Freedom. How the Far Right Has Ridden the Free-Vax Movements between Mistrust and Moral Panic

662.3 Pamela ARONSON, *University of Michigan-Dearborn, USA*
Generational Humor, Identity, and Conflict on Social Media during the Pandemic

662.4 Antonio ALVAREZ-BENAVIDES, *National Distance Education University / GESP, Spain* and Francisco JIMÉNEZ AGUILAR, *Universidad de Granada, Spain*
National Priority and the Welfare-Ultrationalism. the Spanish Cultural Associations of National Help.

662.5 Lucas GOMES, *Universidade Federal do Paraná, Brazil*
L'extrême Droite Au Brésil: Les Proximités Et Les Differences Entre Les Bolsonarismes Et Les Lavajatismes

662.6 Aliye KELESOGLU, *University of Malaya, Malaysia*; Ying Hooi KHOO, *University of Malaya, Malaysia* and Jatswan SINGH, *University of Malaya, Malaysia*
Islam and Ethno-Religious Identities for Social Movement Mobilisation: A Case Study of an Islamic Movement in Malaysia

15:30-17:20

JS-131 Emotions and Environmental Activism

Committees: *RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-131.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

JS-141 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part I

Committees: *RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC07 Futures Research and RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements*

See Joint Session Details for JS-141.

12:30-14:20

663 Social Movements and the State

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Paolo GERBAUDO, *Scuola Normale Superiore, Italy* and Kate ALEXANDER, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Chair: Paolo GERBAUDO, *Scuola Normale Superiore, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

663.1 Stellamarina DONATO, *LUMSA University of Rome, Italy* and Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Università, Italy*
Movements' Dynamics and Government Responsiveness to Violence Against Women: Political and Social Changes in Spain and Italy

663.2 Josep Maria ANTENTAS, *Universitat Ramon Llull, Spain*
Social Movements, the State and Internationalism

663.3 Iolanda BIANCHI, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
Creating a Non-Appropriable State: The Use of the Concept of the Common By New Municipalist Platforms

663.4 Piyush PUSHKAR, *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*
Universal, Free and Comprehensive: NHS Values and Class Consciousness

663.5 Zitian SUN, *McGill University, Canada*
Pitfalls of Popularity: The Dynamic of the 1989 Tiananmen Student Movement

14:30-16:20

664 Religious and Social Movements

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Geoffrey PLEYERS, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium*

Chair: Lucia Ratih KUSUMADEWI, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

664.1 Christian SPERNEAC-WOLFER, *Institute für Social Research, Germany*
Four Styles of a Religious Critique of Capitalism: The Idolatry, the Eschatological, the Social, and the Moral Critique

664.2 Marton CSANADY, *Karoli Gaspar University of the Reformed Church in Hungary, Hungary*
The Relationship between the Rejection of the covid19 Vaccine and the Perception of the War in Ukraine with Religiosity in Hungary in 2022

664.3 Joseba GARCIA MARTIN, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Catholic Movements, Neoconservatism and "Moral Panic." the Opposition to the Legalization of Euthanasia in Spain

664.4 Ayantika BHATTACHERJEE, *Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, India*
Religious Reform, Identity Politics, and Social Change in the Matuas of WEST Bengal: An Ethnographic Study

RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Program Coordinators: Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy*; Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*; Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom* and Tova BENSKI, *College of Management Academic Studies, Israel*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research* RC24 *Environment and Society* RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements* and RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-3.

665 Social Movements, Socio-Ecological Practices and Climate Change

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*

Chair: Tova BENSKI, *College of Management Academic Studies, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

665.1 Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy* and Alessandra SCIERI, *University of Catania, Italy*
Social Discourses and Creative Collective Actions of the Fridays for Future Movement in Italy

665.2 Cristina MIRANDA DE ALMEIDA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Art and Climate Change

665.3 Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*
Climate Crisis, Socio-Ecological Practices, and the Impact of Social Mobilization

665.4 Bartosz SLOSARSKI, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Environmental Data Activism. the Use of Environmental Data As a Repertoire of Action and „Universal Language” of Nature Governance

665.5 Jonathan D. SMITH, *Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia*
How Environmental Movements in Indonesia Weave Together Local Knowledges of Religion and Science into New Socio-Ecological Practices

15:30-17:20

JS-14 The Rise and Fall of Authoritarian Populisms (Hopefully)

Committees: RC36 *Alienation Theory and Research (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-14.

666 Social Movements and Transitional Justice ‘from below’: Exploring Grassroots Activism in Armed Conflicts and Post-Conflict Contexts

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*

Chair: Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

666.1 Vaclav MASEK, *Center for Advanced Genocide Research, Guatemala*
Temporal Imaginations: Collective Memory and Collective Action in Post-Peace Guatemala

666.2 Satyanarayana GATTU, *Osmania University, India*
Social Transformation of Post-Independent Indian Society (The need for Second Freedom Struggle)

666.3 Elizabeth MABER, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Grassroots Activism, Gender Justice and Emerging Solidarities in Post-Coup Myanmar

666.4 Natalia MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Transitional Justice and Forensic Exhumations: Reconciling Post Conflict Violence in Spain

666.5 Sandra RIOS OYOLA, *University College Roosevelt, Netherlands*
Social Representations of Human Dignity in Colombia

17:30-19:20

667 Social Movements, State and Civil Society: Perspectives from the Global South. Part I

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Iswar NAIK, *Ravenshaw University, Cuttack, Odisha, India*

Chair: Aparupa PATNAIK, *KALINGA INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

667.1 Joseph ASOMAH, *University of Manitoba, Canada*
Can Social Media Help Combat Corruption in Developing Countries? Evidence from Ghana

667.2 Yans DIPATI, *PUC-RIO, Brazil*
Rewriting the Social in Light of Gilles Deleuze’s Molar/Molecular Dialectics: A Study on Black Women’s Movement in Brazil

667.3 Radhika K, *university of hyderabad, India*
Reflections of Kerala State Transgender Policy on the Life of Transgender People.

667.4 Kaan AGARTAN, *Framingham State University, USA* and Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*
Social Movements and Radical Democracy: Colombia and Turkey Compared

667.5 Sampat KALE, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences - Tuljapur Campus, India*
Assessing the Role of Civil Society Organisations in Sustainable Development of Adivasis in India

667.6 Thalles BREDA, *UFScar - Universidade Federal de São Carlos, Brazil*
Homeless Workers Movement in Brazil: Relations with the State and Civil Society from a Historical and Conjunctural Perspective

19:30-20:50

668 Social Movements, State and Civil Society: Perspectives from the Global South. Part II

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Iswar NAIK, *Ravenshaw University, Cuttack, Odisha, India*

Chair: Aparupa PATNAIK, *KALINGA INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

668.1 Moussa Khalil DIABATE, *ONG Rassemblement des grins de Côte d'Ivoire, Côte D'Ivoire*; Issa SORE, *ONG LA BONNE CAUSE, Côte D'Ivoire* and Kouyate SOULEYMANE, *UFRICA UNIVERSITE FELIX HOUPHOUET BOIGNY, Côte D'Ivoire*
Youth, Facebook and Political Participation in West Africa

668.2 Daniel ZIPP, *Oberlin College, USA*
Mobilizing Enduring Stability: Chinese Officials' Toolkit for Social Stability Maintenance

668.3 Dobrosława WIKTOR-MACH, *Cracow University of Economics, Poland*
Kurdish Environmental Movements - Dilemmas of Networking, Framing and Strategy

668.4 Prafulla NATH, *Assam university diphu campus, Indonesia*
Relooking the Assam Movement: Memories, Memoire and the Vernacular Press

668.5 Sergio BARBOSA, *University of Coimbra, Portugal*
Protest Mobilization on Whatsapp: Explaining Participants' Approaches before and during COVID-19 in Brazil

668.6 Euiyoung KANG, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Becoming Citizens and Changing the Citizen: Dual Strategy of Mental Disability Movement in South Korea

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-30 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (1)

Committees: RC34 *Sociology of Youth (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change* and RC04 *Sociology of Education*

See Joint Session Details for JS-30.

10:30-12:20

JS-37 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (2)

Committees: RC34 *Sociology of Youth (Host)*; RC04 *Sociology of Education and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-37.

669 Social Movements Challenges in a Post-Pandemic World: New Agendas, New Dynamics

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy*; Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*; Tova BENSKI, *College of Management Academic Studies, Israel* and Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*

Chair: Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

669.1 Randa ABDEL-FATTAH, *Macquarie University, Australia*
COVID 19 As a Rhetorical Shield: Cultural Boycotts and the Case of the 2022 Sydney Festival

669.2 Yvan YONAH, *Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Essential Workers and Their Movements: Examining Nurses and Platform Delivery Riders' Struggles for Better Working Conditions Under the Pandemic

669.3 Thanggoulen KIPGEN, *IIT Kanpur, India* and Biswambhar PANDA, *North Eastern Hill University, India*
Theoretical Formulations on New Social Movement: A Critical Appraisal

669.4 Giorgia MAVICA, *University of Catania, Italy*; Davide NICOLOSI, *University of Catania, Italy* and Alessandra SCIERI, *University of Catania, Italy*
Violent Extremism and New Collective Actors in Pandemic Times

15:30-17:20

JS-41 Globalization-Induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, Identity and Ecological issues). Part I

Committees: RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host)*; RC24 *Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-41.

17:30-19:20

JS-49 Labor Unrest, Social Revolts and Revolutions, 1851-2020: Findings from the Global Social Protest Database

Committees: RC44 *Labor Movements (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change* and RC02 *Economy and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-49.

670 Social Movements, environment and social justice**Location:** 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Kaan AGARTAN, Framingham State University, USA**Chair:** Natalia MIRANDA, Aarhus University, Denmark**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

670.1 Sampat KALE, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences - Tuljapur Campus, India* and Nishi FRANCIS, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Tuljapur Campus, Maharashtra India, India*
"Ground-Eye View of Existing Climate Change Induced Vulnerabilities and Response of Social Movements in India"

670.2 Judith BESSANT, *RMIT University, Australia* and Rob WATTS, *RMIT University, Australia*
Channelling Touraine: Solidarity Research and Young Climate Activists

670.3 Keisuke MORI, *Senshu University, Japan*
Knowledge Production Process of Grassroots Environmental Activism Against the Newly Emerged Environmental Pollution: A Case Study of Pfas Pollution from U.S. Military Bases

670.4 Morena TARTARI, *University of Padua, Italy*
Public Pro-Environment Activism and Socio-Ecological Practices Promoted By the Humanist Movement in Europe

671.4 Bojan BACA, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*
A Rebellion with(out) a Cause? Popular Protest and Elite Transformation in Socialist Montenegro, 1988–1990

671.5 Gemita OYARZO, *Universidad Autonoma de Chile, Chile*
La Reinvencción De Lo Político: Actores, Proyectos Colectivos En Disputa, Trayectorias De Movilización e Institucionalización De Los Movimientos Sociales Del Chile Del Proceso Constituyente.

671.6 Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*
Understanding the 2021 Colombian Protests: Places, Spaces, and Bodies of Resistance and Solidarity

10:30-12:20

JS-67 Urban Collective Action

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-67.

15:30-17:20

672 Violent Extremism and Authoritarianism: Which Relation with Social Movements?**Location:** 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy*; Francesco ANTONELLI, *Università degli Studi "Roma Tre", Italy* and Kevin MCDONALD, *Middlesex University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Liana DAHER, *University of Catania, Italy***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

672.1 Grzegorz PIOTROWSKI, *University of Gdansk, Poland*
Pink, Glitter, Antifascism - Intersections of Contemporary Antifascist Movement in Poland.

672.2 Sui-ting KONG, *Durham University, United Kingdom*; Stevi JACKSON, *University of York, United Kingdom* and Petula Sik-Ying HO, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Royalism As Anti-Authoritarianism? Hongkonger Identities, Mourning and Colonial Nostalgia

672.3 Augusto GAMUZZA, *University of Catania, Italy*; Anna Maria LEONORA, *University of Catania, Italy* and Giorgia MAVICA, *University of Catania, Italy*
How to Deal with the Protean Chameleon? Participatory Methodological Options (and challenges) in Religious Social Movements and Community Empirical Research

672.4 Mehr LATIF, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*; Kathleen BLEE, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*; Matthew DEMICHELE, *RTI International, USA* and Pete SIMI, *Chapman University, USA*
Drivers of Disillusionment and Exit Among White Supremacists: A Gendered Analysis

672.5 Zitian SUN, *McGill University, Canada*
The Art of Blaming: Repression in the 2019 Hong Kong Protest

672.6 Bojan BACA, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*
From Infrapolitical Resistance to Political Rebellion: Trajectories of Dissent and Dynamics of Contention in Montenegro's Antibureaucratic Revolution

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-61 When Students Protest about the Climate Crisis: Realities, Reactions and Results

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-61.

671 The construction of dissent: strategies and collective identities**Location:** 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Natalia MIRANDA, Aarhus University, Denmark**Chair:** Kaan AGARTAN, Framingham State University, USA**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

671.1 Soonyawl PARK, *Innecity Inc. City-Society Center, Republic of Korea* and Saerom AHN, *Seoul National University, Institution for Sustainable Development, USA*
Deconstruction of Urban Commons Movements in Seoul: How to Conceive of Commons Crisscrossing Differentiated Society?

671.2 Ryoko KOSUGI, *Saitama University, Japan*
The Rise and Fall of Student Activism in Tokyo in the Late 20th Century: Focusing on State-Level Policy Regulating Campus Locations

671.3 Hang LI, *Hong Kong Shue Yan University, Hong Kong*
Strategic Interaction and Tactical Shift in the Hong Kong Pro-Democracy Movement

17:30-19:20

JS-81 Music and Society: Identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part I

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC37 Sociology of Arts and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-81.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

673 Gezi in Retrospect: Recalling Mass Protests and Reclaiming Alternative Political Imaginations

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Kaan AGARTAN, Framingham State University, USA

Chair: Derya OZKAYA OZTURK, University of Graz, Austria

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

673.1 Selin Bengi GUMRUKCU, Rutgers University, USA
Historicizing Gezi Park Protests

673.2 Begum FIRAT, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, Department of Sociology, Turkey
Solidarity Failed: Organizing the Neighbourhood Ten Years after Gezi

673.3 Deborah GOULD, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA
Political Emotion, Political Horizons, and the Question of Composition in 2023

10:30-12:20

JS-93 La Lucha Contra Los Extractivismos En América Latina y El Futuro De La Región | Struggle Against Extractivism in Latin America and the Future of the Region

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host); RC07 Futures Research

See Joint Session Details for JS-93.

15:30-17:20

JS-102 Mobilizing Emotions by Social Movements and in Contemporary Humanitarian Effort

Committees: WG08 Society and Emotions (Host); RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-102.

674 Gender Mobilizations in Times of Rising Authoritarianism

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Tova BENSKI, College of Management Academic Studies, Israel

Chair: Lauren LANGMAN, Loyola University of Chicago, USA

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

674.1 Devika TIWARI, Lady Shree Ram College for Women, India, India
The Negative Impact of Authoritarianism on Women: with Regard to Body Autonomy

674.2 Tova BENSKI, College of Management Academic Studies, Israel
"Women Wage Peace" the Return of the Mother

674.3 Temitope ORIOLA, Dept of Sociology, Canada
Unpacking the #Bringbackourgirls Movement: Mobilization, Internal Dynamics and State Repression

674.4 Jessica MENDES, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil
The Brazilian Feminist Movement: Diachronic and Synchronic Reflections on Its Structuring and Organization

674.5 Fateme EJAREDAR, University of Calgary, Canada
The Body of Women As a Battlefield in the Islamic Republic: How a Feminist Movement Can Threaten an Authoritarian State

674.6 Tae KIM, DeZIM-Institute, Germany; Merih ATES, DeZIM-Institute, Germany and Elias STEINHILPER, DeZIM-Institute, Germany
The Role of Emotions for Antiracist Mobilization: Results from a Cross-Sectional Survey in Germany

17:30-19:20

JS-112 To Participate or Not to Participate? Social Movements 4.0 and the Return of Dichotomies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

See Joint Session Details for JS-112.

675 RC48 Business Meeting

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

676 Globalization-Induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, Identity and Ecological issues). Part II

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Binay Kumar PATNAIK, Dept. of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India

Chair: Bibhuti Bhusan MOHANTY, Department of Sociology, India

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

676.1 Sipra SAGARIKA, Fakir Mohan University, Balasore, Odisha, India
Niyamgiri Movement in Odisha : A Sight for Entanglements of Indigenous Communities, Religion, Politics and Economy

676.2 Amiya DAS, Tezpur University, India
Extractive Development and Everyday Resistance: Solidarity and Peoples Movement in the Global South.

676.3 Thounaojam SOMOKANTA, *Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
South Asian Dams at a Tipping Point? the Case of Tipaimukh Dam in Manipur, India

676.4 Anna-lena RUELAND, *Leiden University, Netherlands*
Resisting Big Science: How the Opposition Movement Against the Thirty Meter Telescope Sustained Momentum

10:30-12:20

677 Assessing the Trajectories of People's Movements in South Asia

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dipti Ranjan SAHU, *University of Lucknow, India*

Chair: Dipti Ranjan SAHU, *University of Lucknow, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

677.1 Debal SINGHARROY, *603, Asiad Games Village, New Delhi 110049, India*
New Contexts and Changing Contours of Agrarian Protests in India

677.2 Binay Kumar PATNAIK, *Dept. of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Studying Kashipur Resistance Movement through Michael Cernea's Impoverishment Risks and Reconstruction Model of Displacement

677.3 Rohit JAIN, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Tuljapur Campus, India*
Shifting Contours of Social Movements: Study of Forest Rights Movement and Labour Movement in India

677.4 Deep CHAND, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*
Protest Against Citizenship (Amendment) Act [Caa:2019] in India: Understanding Conflict Escalation through Protest-Repression Studies

677.5 Debbani BHATTACHARYA, *Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India*
Gorkhaland Movement- Identity Politics or Politics of Identity

677.6 Tahmin BARKATI, *TISS, School of Social Work, India*
Restructuring the City of Kolkata: A Study on the Spatiality of Protest.

677.7 Meghna ARORA, *Vardhaman College, Bijnor, India*
The Social and Political Context of Dalit Mobilization in Western Uttar Pradesh: an Analysis of Voice, Facilitative and Coordinative Effects

15:30-17:20

JS-132 The Prospects of a Pluriversal Transition to a Post-Capitalist, Post-Carbon Future

Committees: RC09 *Social Transformations and Sociology of Development (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-132.

678 Generational Creativity in Contemporary Youth Activism

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Paola REBUGHINI, *Milan University, Italy* and Lidia LO SCHIAVO, *University of Messina, Italy*

Chair: Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

678.2 Natalia MIRANDA, *Aarhus University, Denmark*
Alter-Activism and Engagement Among Actors of Young Adulthood.

678.3 Vittorio TAVAGNUTTI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
Political Generations and Gender in the Romani Ethnic Mobilization in Italy: An Intersectional Perspective

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

679 Nature vs Culture: emerging conflicts and citizens' rights

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Kaan AGARTAN, *Framingham State University, USA*

Chair: Kaan AGARTAN, *Framingham State University, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

679.1 Prafulla NATH, *Assam university diphu campus, Indonesia*
Development Vis-a-Vis Nature in Assam Context: People's Right and the State

679.2 Jhakendra GHARTI MAGAR, *Saraswati Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Nepal*; Dharendra GHARTI MAGAR, *Saraswati Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Nepal* and Om Prakash GHARTI MAGAR, *Saraswati Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Nepal*
Trophy Hunting in the Himalaya: Conflict between State and Local People in Dhorpatan Hunting Reserve, Nepal

679.3 Cora HAGINO, *UFJF, Portugal*
Parque Estadual De Ibitipoca (Minas Gerais, Brasil) y Su Privatización: Conflictos y Resistencias

10:30-12:20

JS-141 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part I

Committees: RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change (Host)*; RC07 *Futures Research and RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements*

See Joint Session Details for JS-141.

12:30-14:20

680 Agrarian and Rural Movements : Changing Dynamics and New Alliances**Location:** 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Debal SINGHARROY, 603, *Asiad Games Village, New Delhi 110049, India***Chair:** Debal SINGHARROY, 603, *Asiad Games Village, New Delhi 110049, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

680.1 Marcelo Carvalho ROSA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*; Priscila CARVALHO, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais/ Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil* and Camila PENNA, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Modes of Gathering: Methodological Contributions for Studying Landless and Rural Collective Action Dynamics

680.2 Keshab SILWAL, *Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal*
The Commune Practices in Rural Nepal: A Study of Collectivization during and after the Maoist Insurgency

680.3 Binay Kumar PATTNAIK, *Dept. of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India* and Manoranjan DAS, *Ravenshaw University, Cuttack, India*
Analyzing Anti-Posco Movement of Odisha: Through New Social Movement Perspective

680.4 Dipti Ranjan SAHU, *University of Lucknow, India*
Dynamics of People's Protest: Issues and Perspectives

14:30-16:20

681 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part II**Location:** 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Ligia TAVERA FENOLLOSA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico***Chair:** Ligia TAVERA FENOLLOSA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

681.1 Paola REBUGHINI, *Milan University, Italy* and Lidia LO SCHIAVO, *University of Messina, Italy*
Critical Agency and Creative Imagination: Snapshots of the Future in Youth Movements

681.2 Ana-Maria NIKOLAS, *DeZIM-Institut, Germany*
Migrant Youth Activism and Alternative Inclusive Futures:

681.3 Anna-Britt COE, *Umeå University, Sweden*
How Do Social Movements Construct Long-Term Visions through Interactions between Generations of Activism? the Case of Two Generations of Feminist Activism in Peru and Ecuador

681.4 Begonya ENGUIX GRAU, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain*
Feminist Nationalism and Future Visions: The Case of Catalonia

681.5 Aleksandra WAGNER, *Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland*
Beyond the Horizons: The Eu's Narratives on Post-Transition World

RC49

Mental Health and Illness

Program Coordinator: Silvia KRUMM, *Ulm University, Germany*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

682 Mental health and the community

Language: Spanish, English

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Felipe SZABZON, *Escola Nacional de Saúde Pública, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal* and Cristóbal ABARCA BROWN, *Universidade Federal do São Paulo, Brazil*

Chair: Silvia KRUMM, *Ulm University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

682.1 Ireen KABEMBO, *Lingnan University, Hong Kong*
'who Will Take Care of My Child When I Die? a Skeptical Engagement with Family Caregivers of Youth with Substance Use Disorders in Zambia'.

682.2 Wenju CHEN, *National Taipei University, Department of Social Work, Taiwan*
The New Pathway of Addictions-Recovery: The Relationship between Recovery Capital, Trauma and Quality of Life (QOL) of Substance Use Among Adults in Taiwan.

682.3 Ya GUO, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Senhu WANG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
What Matters More for Employees' Mental Health in Contemporary China: Job Quality or Job Quantity?

682.4 Agata KRASOWSKA, *University of Wrocław, Poland*
Experiencing a Mental Crisis and Forced Loneliness in the Biographies of Workers

17:30-19:20

683 Victimization and Experiences of Violence Among Mental Health Service Users

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Silvia KRUMM, *Ulm University, Germany*

Chair: Silvia KRUMM, *Ulm University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

683.1 Juliet WATSON, *RMIT University, Australia* and Chris MAYLEA, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Gender-Based Violence in Mental Health Settings: Manifestations of Gendered Oppression

683.2 Emma TSERIS, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Listening to Women's Accounts of Psychiatric Coercion.

683.3 Sampurna KUNDU, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*; Sanghmitra ACHARYA, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, Centre of Social Medicine and Community Health, School of Social Sciences, New Delhi, India* and Sampurna SINGH, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Linkages of Intimate Partner Violence (IPV), Coercive Control, Alcoholism and Mental Well-Being: A Community-Based Study in Delhi

683.4 Michelle JUDD DE LA LUZ, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Being a Woman within an Anexo: Violence Against Women Suffering from Substance-Related and Addictive Disorders in Mexico

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

684 Social Relationships and Mental Health and Illness

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Reinhold KILIAN, *Ulm University, Germany*

Chair: Reinhold KILIAN, *Ulm University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

684.1 Jeremy DIXON, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*; Rachel FORRESTER-JONES, *The University of Western Ontario, Canada* and Beth JAYNES, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*
Exploring Romantic Need As Part of Mental Health Social Care Practice

684.2 Vineetha SIVAKUMAR, *Alliance University, India*
Institutional Seclusion and Mental Health

684.3 Eunha HWANG, *Korea university, Republic of Korea*
How the Memories about Home Environment Shapes School Drop-out Adolescents' Depression: The Moderating Effects of Supportive Relational Experiences

15:30-17:20

685 Models of Mental Health Problems

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Dirk RICHTER, *Bern University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland* and Jeremy DIXON, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*

Chair: Michele KADRI, *ILMD, FIOCRUZ, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

685.1 Bruce COHEN, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Medicalizing the Prison-Industrial Complex: Theorizing the Relationship between Criminality and Mental Illness

685.2 Dirk RICHTER, *Bern University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland* and Jeremy DIXON, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*
Models of Mental Health Problems: A Quasi-Systematic Review of Theoretical Approaches

685.3 Monika FRACKOWIAK-SOCHANSKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland* and Dorota MROCZKOWSKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*
Critical Analysis of the Mental Health Diagnosis Process from a Critical Sociocultural and Gender Perspective – on the Example of Eating Disorders in Men

685.4 Yuki KAWAMURA, *Hitotsubashi University, Japan*
Reflective Process in Case Conferences: Focusing on Structures That Enable Equal Dialogue

17:30-19:20

686 The Social Genesis of Cognitive Difficulties

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Pia RINGOE, *Aalborg University, Denmark*

Chair: Reinhold KILIAN, *Ulm University, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

686.1 Kjeld HOGSBRO, *Aalborg University, Department of Sociology and Social Work, Denmark*
Towards a Sociology of Mental Disease

686.2 Dirk RICHTER, *Bern University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland*
Variation Is the Norm: A Multidimensional Account of Neurocognitive Diversity

687.5 Masum BILLAH, *Department of Sociology, East West University, Dhaka, Bangladesh*; Sadika AKHTER, *School of Health and Social Development, Deakin University, Melbourne, Australia* and Shannon RUTHERFORD, *School of MDP- Public Health, Griffith University, Brisbane, Australia*
Exploring Mental Health Challenges and Coping Strategies in University Students during COVID-19: A Case Study in Dhaka, Bangladesh

687.6 Bronwen LICHTENSTEIN, *UNIVERSITY OF ALABAMA, USA*; Stephanie MCCLURE, *UNIVERSITY OF ALABAMA, USA*; Kathryn OTHS, *UNIVERSITY OF ALABAMA, USA* and Pamela PAYNE-FOSTER, *UNIVERSITY OF ALABAMA, USA*
Medical Mistrust and COVID-19 Among African Americans in the US Deep South

687.7 Hsing-Jung CHEN, *Graduate Institute of Social Work, National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*; Wen-Chi WU, *Department of Health Promotion and Health Education, National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan* and Tony Szu-Hsien LEE, *Department of Health Promotion and Health Education, National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*
The Link between Emotional Regulation Strategies and Internet Addiction: The Mediating Role of Epidemic Fear

687.8 James LINN, *Optimal Solutions in Healthcare and International Development, USA* and Jorge CHUAQUI, *Universidad de Valparaiso, Chile*
Covid-19 in Chile: Psychological and Societal Outcomes

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

687 Covid-19 and Mental Illness: A Syndemic & Structural Perspective

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: James LINN, *Optimal Solutions in Healthcare and International Development, USA* and Michele KADRI, *ILMD, FIOCRUZ, Brazil*

Chair: Anna-Iena ALMQVIST, *Malardalen University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

687.1 Breno FONTES, *Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil*
The Epidemic of COVID 19 in Brazil: The PLACE of Mental Health Care

687.2 Michele KADRI, *ILMD, FIOCRUZ, Brazil*
COVID-19 and Mental Health Among Indigenous Peoples of the Brazilian Amazon

687.3 Reinhold KILIAN, *Psychiatry and Psychotherapy II, Ulm University, Günzburg, Germany*; Jutta LEHLE, *Ulm University, department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy II, Germany*; Friedrich MEIXNER, *Ulm University, Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy II, Germany*; Sabrina REUTER, *Ulm University, Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy II, Germany* and Annabel MUELLER-STIERLIN, *Ulm University, Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy II, Germany*
Perceived Empowerment and the Impact of Negative Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Quality of Life of Persons with Severe Mental Illness.

687.4 Delfino VARGAS, *Programa Universitario de Estudios del Desarrollo, Mexico* and Emilia LUCIO, *Faculty of Psychology, National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Effects of COVID-19 on Mental Health in Mexico, from a Syndemic Perspective

15:30-17:20

688 Social and Emotional Well-Being of Adolescents and Young Adults Living in Rapidly Changing Real and Virtually Constructed Worlds

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Takashi ASAKURA, *Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan*

Chair: Takashi ASAKURA, *Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

688.1 Jie WANG, *South China Normal University, China*; Jiajun Li, *Sun Yat-Sen University, China*; Qiang WU, *Renmin University of China, China* and Haining WANG, *Sun Yat-Sen University, China*
Effects of Cyberbullying and Traditional Bullying Victimization on Adolescents' Psychological Distress in China: Gender-Based Parent-Child and Teacher-Student Relationships As Moderators

688.2 Ravita YADAV, *International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai, India*
Association between School Dropouts, Early Marriages, Childbearing, and Mental Health in Early Adulthood of Women: Evidence from a Cohort Study in Bihar, India

688.3 Antwan JONES, *George Washington University, USA*; Hiromi ISHIZAWA, *The George Washington University, USA* and Fran BUNTMAN, *The George, USA*
The Mental Health Consequences of Parental Incarceration from Adolescence to Young Adulthood

688.4 Marie UENO, *Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan*; Yuka MASUKO, *School Health for All Cambodian Children Project, Cambodia*; Kalyan LY, *School Health for All Cambodian Children Project, Cambodia*; Sokheng THAY, *School Health for All Cambodian Children Project, Cambodia* and Somaly SAY, *School Health for All Cambodian Children Project, Cambodia*
The Association between Mental Health and Overall Health, Safety Behavior, and Social Relationship Among University Students in Cambodia

688.5 Hye Won KWON, *University of Turku, Finland* and Ji Hye KIM, *Sogang University, Republic of Korea*
Adolescents' Self-Efficacy and Life Satisfaction: The Importance of Cultural Orientations

688.6 Lynn TANG, *The University of Liverpool, United Kingdom*
Suicide and Political Crisis: The Perceptions of Hong Kong Young People on Protest-Related Suicides

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

688.7 Samia SHABNAZ, *American International University-Bangladesh, Bangladesh* and Monira HOSSAIN, *American International University-Bangladesh, Bangladesh*
Perceived Stress and Stressors Among Undergraduate Students: A Study in Bangladesh

688.8 Pragati BARTHWAL, *D.A.V(P.G)college, India*
Social Media and Adolescent Mental Health and Development. Risks, Pitfalls, Opportunity and Growth.

19:30-20:50

689 RC49 Business Meeting

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

JS-126 Mental Health and Risk

Committees: RC49 Mental Health and Illness (Host); TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty

See Joint Session Details for JS-126.

17:30-19:20

690 Social Inclusion of Mentally Ill Persons

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jorge CHUAQUI, *Universidad de Valparaiso, Chile*

Chair: Takashi ASAKURA, *Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

690.1 Egle SUMSKIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*; Violeta GEVORGIANIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*; Jurga Mataityte DIRZIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania* and Rasa GENIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Changing Geographies of Stigma Following Deinstitutionalization

690.2 Jorge CHUAQUI, *Universidad de Valparaiso, Chile*
Gaps for Real Inclusion of Mentally ILL Persons in Chile

690.3 Olga BORODKINA, *St Petersburg University, Russian Federation* and Alevtina STARSHINOVA, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation*
Key Issues of Social Inclusion of Children and Youth with Mental and Autism Spectrum Disorders

690.4 Tracey LAPIERRE, *University of Kansas, USA*
Hegemonic Ideologies of Motherhood As a Barrier to Fertility Among Women with Disabilities

RC50

International Tourism

Program Coordinators: Can-Seng OOI, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

691 Paradoxes of Mobilities

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Hazel TUCKER, *University of Otago, New Zealand* and Erdinc CAKMAK, *Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands*

Chair: Hazel TUCKER, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

Co-Chair: Erdinc CAKMAK, *Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

691.1 Richard ROBINSON, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
The (Tourism Worker) Clash: 'Should I Stay or Should I Go...'

691.2 Shamayeeta GHOSH, *Jhargram Raj College (Girls' Wing), Affiliated to Vidyasagar University, India*
The Past and Present of Package Tours in West Bengal: An Ethno-Historical Documentation of Continuities and Paradoxes

691.3 Max HOLLERAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Pandemics and Georbitrage: Digital Nomadism before and after COVID-19

691.4 Gada MAHROUSE, *Concordia University, Canada*
The Tourist and the Refugee As Racialized Figures of Mobility

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

692 Open Forum: Envisioning a Future of Sociology in Tourism Studies

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom* and Can-Seng OOI, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Chair: Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*

Co-Chair: Can-Seng OOI, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

10:30-12:20

693 Mobilities after Covid 19 – Social and Wellbeing Perspectives on Tourism in Unsettling Times

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Regina SCHEYVENS, *Massey University, New Zealand*

Chair: Faith ONG, *University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

693.1 Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*
Wellbeing through tourism in a post-covid world or how tourism failed to build back better: new times, new entanglements, but the same injustices remain.

693.2 Regina SCHEYVENS, *Massey University, New Zealand* and Apisalome MOVONO, *Massey University, New Zealand*
"Tourism Must Compliment Our Way of Life": Prioritising Wellbeing of Destination Communities

693.3 Becky SHELLEY, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Can-Seng OOI, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Anxieties after COVID-19: Mobilising Tourism Assets for Children's Wellbeing

693.4 Alexandra YINGST, *University of Iceland, Iceland*
Understanding Precarious, Migrant Labor Onboard Cruise Ships in the Time of COVID-19

693.5 Md Azmain Muhtasim MIR, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
"You Tell Us What That Needs to Look like?" Incorporating Local People's Voice in Tourism Activities in the West Coast of Tasmania

19:30-20:50

694 RC50 Business Meeting

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

695 Silenced and Unheard Voices: Human Rights in Tourism

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Oscar VOROBYOVAS-PINTA, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Anne HARDY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Chair: Becky SHELLEY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

695.1 Oscar VOROBYOVAS-PINTA, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Anne HARDY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Human Rights, Travellers and Tourism: Towards a Research Agenda for Understanding Tourists' Perceptions of Human Rights Abuses

695.2 Shea CALVIN, *University of Newcastle, Australia*; Tamara YOUNG, *University of Newcastle, Australia* and Margurite HOOK, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Amplifying Aboriginal Voices: Photovoice and the Citizen Social Science Agenda

695.3 Richard EK, *Karlstad University, Sweden*; Åsa ANDERSSON, *independent scholar, Sweden*; Stuart REID, *Dalarna University, Sweden*; Janne SIRNIO, *independent scholar, Sweden* and Ulrika ÅKERLUND, *Karlstad University, Sweden*
Tourism's Healing Power? the Case of a Possible Sápmi 'trail of Tears' Walking Trail As a Vehicle for Justice

695.4 Wei wally ZHANG, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Anne HARDY, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Uncovering the Motivations and Decisions of Immigrant Entrepreneurs in Tourism

695.5 Mahendrasinh DODIYA, *Placeholder, India*
Heritage, Travel & Tourism Industry and Policy: Sociological Context (With Special Reference to Gujarat State-India)

17:30-19:20

696 Tourism Paradoxes: Contradictions, Controversies, and Challenges

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Erdinc CAKMAK, *Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands*; Hazel TUCKER, *University of Otago, New Zealand* and Keith HOLLINSHEAD, *Organising committee, United Kingdom*

Chair: Erdinc CAKMAK, *Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands*

Co-Chair: Hazel TUCKER, *University of Otago, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

696.1 Jundan ZHANG, *Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden*
Paradoxes of Intention: A Conceptual Exploration on How Nature Guides Mediate and Interrupt

696.2 Rasul MOWATT, *North Carolina State University, USA*
Colonial Pedagogy & Touring Empires

696.3 Denise CONTESSA, *University of Pisa, Italy*
Filtered Identities and Its Contradictions in the Tourist City. Evidences from Bologna, Italy

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

697 Decolonising Asian Tourism in the New Entanglements of International Tourism

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Elaine YANG, *Griffith University, Australia* and Faith ONG, *University of Queensland, Australia*

Chair: Elaine YANG, *Griffith University, Australia*

Co-Chair: Faith ONG, *University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

697.1 Richard AQUINO, *University of Canterbury, New Zealand*; Robert Charles CAPISTRANO, *Arizona State University, USA* and Paul Anthony NOTORIO, *De La Salle University - Dasmariñas, Philippines*
Branding a Nation's Hospitality

697.2 Wenzhuo ZHANG, *Australian National University, Australia*
(Re)Interpretations of Harbin's Russian-Era Heritage: Heritage Tourism in the Changing China

697.3 Chin ee ONG, *Sun Yat Sen university, China*
Decolonising Asian Tourism in Thought and Practice: Macao As Plasmatic Modernity

697.4 Jundan ZHANG, *Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden*
Unlost in Translation: Issues of Languages in Re-Centering Critical Debates within Tourism Studies

697.5 Honggen XIAO, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, China* and Xinru LIU, *Wuyi University, China*
Confucianism, Taoism and Tourism

697.6 Can-Seng OOI, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Scholarship As a Never-Ending Process: Asianising Knowledge and Its Perils

15:30-17:20

698 Politics and Borders

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Jack SHEPHERD, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*; Daniel LAVEN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden* and Rami ISAAC, *Centre for Sustainability, Tourism & Transport, Netherlands*

Chair: Jack SHEPHERD, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*

Co-chairs: Daniel LAVEN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden* and Rami ISAAC, *Centre for Sustainability, Tourism & Transport, Netherlands*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

698.1 Isabella YE, *University of Greenwich, United Kingdom* and Samira ZARE, *University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*
The Stories of the Unheard: Border-Crossing, Passports, and Travel Experiences

698.2 Michael LUONGO, *Purdue University, USA* and Sandra SYDNOR, *Purdue University Hospitality and Tourism Management, USA*
Understanding Tourist Motivations in Visiting Current and Former Conflict Zones

698.3 Natan URIELY, *Ben Gurion University, Israel* and Unger UNGER, *Kineret College, Israel*
On-Site Animosity and National Identity: Business Travelers on Stage

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

699 New Digital/Social Entanglements in Tourism: Implications for Sustainability, Industry and Communities.

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Scott MCCABE, *Nottingham University, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

699.1 Octavio SACRAMENTO, *University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro - Centre For Transdisciplinary Development Studies // Purchase order n.: NE001.2023.0000556, Portugal*
Turismo De Masas y Riesgos De Bioseguridad: Evidencias De La Pandemia De Covid-19

699.2 Gada MAHROUSE, *Concordia University, Canada*
The Paradoxical Privileged Mobilities of Post-COVID-19 'Digital Nomads'

699.3 Tyler RIORDAN, *University of Queensland, Australia*; Gerhard HOFFSTAEDTER, *University of Queensland, Australia* and Richard ROBINSON, *University of Queensland, Australia*
At What Cost? the Corporeal Dimensions of Convenience

699.4 Robert Charles CAPISTRANO, *Arizona State University, USA* and Paul Anthony NOTORIO, *De La Salle University - Dasmariñas, Philippines*
Exploring the Philippine Meetings, Incentives, Conventions, and Exhibitions Industry: A Post-Pandemic Policy Perspective

700.2 Richard EK, *Karlstad University, Sweden*; Åsa ANDERSSON, *independent scholar, Sweden*; Stuart REID, *Dalarna University, Sweden* and Janne SIRNIO, *independent scholar, Sweden*
Tourism As Colonial Anti-Geopolitics? the Case of a 'Trail of Tears' Walking Trail in Sápmi, in Times of Reconciliation and Green Postcolonialism

700.3 Xinru LIU, *Wuyi University, China* and Honggen XIAO, *The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, China*
Tourism and the Alleviation of Poverty: A Study on Rural Community Development in Fujian, China

Saturday 1 July

700 Tourism As Geopolitical Strategy: State Action, Soft Power and Ordinary Practices and Repertoires in International and Domestic Tourism

Location: M8 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Thiago PIMENTEL, *Federal University of Juiz de Fora / UFJF, Brazil*; Dominic LAPOINTE, *Université du Québec a Montreal, Canada* and Oleg ANAFASIEV, *Russian State University of Tourism and Service (Moscow), Russian Federation*

Chair: Oscar VOROBJOVAS-PINTA, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

700.1 Marcela BIFANO DE OLIVEIRA, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico* and Thiago PIMENTEL, *Federal University of Juiz de Fora / UFJF, Brazil*
Tourism As a Spatial Solution: The Process of Extensive and Concentrated Urbanization of Tourism in Sun and Beach Destinations on the Periphery of Capitalism

RC51

Sociocybernetics

Program Coordinator: Patricia Eugenia

ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

701 Citizen-Science: Systemic Perspectives on Group, Community Empowerment and Co-Decision

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

Chair: Saburo AKAHORI, 2-6-1 Zempukuji, Japan

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

701.1 Magdalena ROSZCZYNSKA KURASINSKA, *Univeristy of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmiescie 26/28, 00-927 Warsaw, Poland* and Nina WROBLEWSKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Technological Enablers of Citizen Science – a Diagnosis of Technological Advancement of NGOs in Poland

701.2 Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
SDG Rural Labs: Approaching Rural Contexts to Social Citizen-Science.

701.3 Pedro ESCRICHE, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain* and Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
Citizen-Social Science in Spain: A Second Order Observation

701.4 Alvaro MALAINA, *University Complutense of Madrid, Spain*
A Constructive Criticism of Social Complex Systems Modelling from Gilles Deleuze's Rhizome Theory and Bruno Latour's Actor-Network Theory

701.5 Hui PAN, *Nanjing University, China*
The Spatial Operation of Power: The Tension between Administrative Boundaries and the Living World: The Example of the "Toilet Revolution" Project in Rural China

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

702 4P and Cognitive Policy Making in Health: A Sociocybernetic Approach

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

Chair: Toru TAKAHASHI, *Chuo University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

702.1 Alberto TURON, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*; Jorge NAVARRO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*; Juan AGUARÓN, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain* and José María MORENO-JIMENEZ, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
Assessment of the Commitment of Citizens to Public Policies Using Sentiment Analysis and Social Network Analysis on Twitter through Machine Learning

702.2 Jorge NAVARRO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*; Alberto TURON, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*; Alfredo ALTUZARRA, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain* and José María MORENO-JIMENEZ, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
Sentiment Analysis on Twitter of the Different Stakeholders Involved in the COVID-19 Vaccination Process in Spain By Using Machine Learning

702.3 Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
Public Health, Citizen Participation and Individual Responsibility: A Socio-Cybernetic Approach.

10:30-12:20

703 Evolution of Meaning: Toward a Synthesis between Systems Theory and the Sociology of Knowledge

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Saburo AKAHORI, *Tokyo Woman's Christian University, Japan*

Chair: Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

703.1 Ayumi HIGUCHI, *University of Fukuoka, Japan*
Change in Meaning of "Organization"

703.2 Toru TAKAHASHI, *Chuo University, Japan*
Massive Information Flow and Social Reality: A Sociocybernetic Consideration on the Social Construction of Meaning

703.3 Saburo AKAHORI, *Tokyo Woman's Christian University, Japan*
How Can the Digital Revolution Transform the Meaning of Modernity?: A Systems Theoretical Reconsideration

703.4 Rodrigo GONZALEZ, *Universidad Adolfo Ibañez, Chile*
Communicating about Automation or an Automated Communication? Systems Theory and Media Studies in the Current Understanding of Algorithmic Technologies

703.5 Fabio GIGLIETTO, *Università di Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*; Nicola RIGHETTI, *University of Vienna, Austria*; Rita MARCHETTI, *University of Perugia, Italy* and Roberto MINCIGRUCCI, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
Unintentional Exposure to Political News on Facebook's Religious Pages during the 2022 Italian Election Campaign

17:30-19:20

704 Sociocybernetic Perspectives on Power

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jorge CARDIEL, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Saburo AKAHORI, 2-6-1 Zempukuji, Japan

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

704.1 Mikael KIVELÄ, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Terminatio - Nomenclature As Disciplinary and Modulatory Power

704.2 Fernando ILHARCO, *Catholic University of Portugal, Portugal*
The Grounding and Self-Referential Character of Communication - the Cases of Social Stability and Social Change

704.3 Czeslaw MESJASZ, *Cracow University of Economics, Poland*
Money As Information: A Complex Systems Perspective

704.4 Iris BALSAMO, *A360,SU, Argentina*
Evolution of Causality from Aristotle to Einstein. a Cognitive Tool for Everything

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-56 Childhoods and Systemic Inequalities

Committees: *RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); RC51 Sociocybernetics*

See Joint Session Details for JS-56.

15:30-17:20

705 RC51 Business Meeting

Location: M3 (Crown)

Chair: Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

706 Female Biocapital, Technology and the Market: A Multilevel Research Field. Part One

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Universita, Italy*

Chair: Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Universita, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

706.1 Yoshie YANAGIHARA, *Tokyo Denki University, Japan*
The Waning of a Beautiful Rhetoric: Current Protests and Development of the Egg/Surrogacy Market in Japan

706.2 Eleane PROO, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Las Experiencias De Las Mujeres Gestantes Mexicanas En La Industria De La Subrogación: Significados De La Práctica y El Cuerpo. Análisis Sociológico Con Enfoque Feminista.

706.3 Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad of Zaragoza, Spain* and Ana Lucía HERNÁNDEZ-CORDERO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*
Gestational Surrogacy in Spain: Online Markets and Discourses

17:30-19:20

707 Female Biocapital, Technology and the Market: A Multilevel Research Field. Part Two

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Universita, Italy*

Chair: Consuelo CORRADI, *Lumsa Universita, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

707.1 Zairu NISHA, *Ramanujan College, University of Delhi, India*
Rhetorics of Choice and Coercion on Surrogate Motherhood

707.2 Amarpreet KAUR, *University of Birmingham, United Kingdom*
Changing the Female Biocapital Market Via Reproductive Technologies

707.3 Maria Carmela AGODI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*; Ilenia PICARDI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy* and Sole Alba ZOLLO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*
What's in an Image? the Public Life of the Digital Fetus

707.4 Daniela BANDELLI, *LUMSA, Italy*
For a Sociology of Placenta, a Neglected Form of Woman and Child's Biocapital

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

708 Understanding Political Crises in the 2020s - a Sociocybernetics Approach

Location: M3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Andrew MITCHELL, *Kumamoto University, Japan*

Chair: Fabio GIGLIETTO, *Università di Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

708.2 Daghan IRAK, *University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*
Identitarianism Malgré Lui: Europeanness and Anti-Immigration Movement in Turkey

708.3 Kenneth VAUGHAN, *University of Central Oklahoma, USA*
Religion and Support for Far-Right Platforms: Comparing Italy, Hungary, and the Netherlands

708.4 Andrew MITCHELL, *Kumamoto University, Japan*
Global Crises in the 2020s - a Luhmannian Observation

15:30-17:20

JS-130 Complexity in the Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe (II)

Committees: *RC51 Sociocybernetics (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC31 Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-130.

17:30-19:20

JS-137 The Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in EuropeCommittees: *RC31 Sociology of Migration (Host); RC18 Political Sociology and RC51 Sociocybernetics*

See Joint Session Details for JS-137.

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

709 Understanding Digital and Surveillance Capitalism from Sociocybernetic Perspectives**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** M3 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Juan Carlos BARRON-PASTOR, *Center for Research on North America, UNAM, Mexico***Chair:** Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****709.1** Aaron CID RAMÍREZ, *División de Ciencias Naturales e Ingeniería, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana, Mexico*
Surveillance Capitalism As an Auto-Organization and Complex Process.**709.2** Juan Carlos BARRON-PASTOR, *CISAN UNAM, Mexico*
Virtual Communities at Transnational Cyberlocalities from Mexico and US**709.3** Jorge CARDIEL, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Investment Management Corporations and Global Financial Capitalism**709.4** Emerson PALMIERI, *Universidade de São Paulo (USP), Brazil*
A Critique of the Idea of 'informational Overload' in the Digital Space.

RC52

Sociology of Professional Groups

Program Coordinators: Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal* and Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-1 COVID-19 Pandemic and Global Health Workforce Policies and Governance: Challenges and Issues at the Forefront

Committees: RC52 *Sociology of Professional Groups (Host)*; RC15 *Sociology of Health*

See Joint Session Details for JS-1.

15:30-17:20

710 Professions, Politics, and the State

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*

Chair: Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - FCSH, Portugal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

710.1 Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*
The Role of Politics in Professional Regulatory Change: Three Case Studies from Canada

710.2 Debby BONNIN, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*
Professionalisation and the Public Service – an Examination of South African Initiatives and Debates

710.3 Sida LIU, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Crisis As Opportunity: Professional Career Paths at Two Historical Turning Points in Hong Kong

710.4 Clemence MARTIN DONATI, *Paris Nanterre University, France*
Regulating Hypnosis in France in an Interprofessional Competition Context : Relationships between Professional Groups and the State

710.5 Liat MILWIDSKY, *The Open University of Israel, Israel* and Tammy SAGIV SCHIFTER, *The Israeli Sociological Association, Israel*
Cooperation, Synthesis, and Balance: Scientific Knowledge Featuring in Precautionary Principle

17:30-19:20

711 Professions, the State, and Regulation

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Gregor SCHAFFER, *FernUniversität in Hagen, Germany*

Chair: Gregor SCHAFFER, *FernUniversität in Hagen, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

711.1 Roman SMIRNOV, *Free University of Berlin, Germany*
Silence of the Labs: Adaptation Strategies of Russian Scholars during the Russian-Ukrainian War

711.2 Mst Shahina PARVIN, *Department of Sociology, Brandon University, Canada* and Ariane HANEMAAYER, *Brandon University, Canada*
The Opioid Crisis: The Problematization of Professional Responsibility in Pain Medicine

711.3 Emrah YILDIZ, *ankara haci bayram veli university, Turkey*
The Rise of Economics As a Profession in Turkey

711.4 Tiantian LIU, *Central China Normal University, China*; Guanghuai ZHENG, *Central China Normal University, China* and Jiangang ZHU, *Nankai University, China*
Whistleblowing in Social Organizations: Insights into Governance Absorption on Durability

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-29 Working Abroad: The Experience of Mobile Professionals in Foreign Labour Markets

Committees: RC52 *Sociology of Professional Groups (Host)*; RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

See Joint Session Details for JS-29.

15:30-17:20

712 Interprofessional Teamwork in Healthcare. Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemics

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - FCSH, Portugal*

Chair: Tracey ADAMS, *Social Science Centre, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

712.1 Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - FCSH, Portugal*
From New Public Management to New Public Governance: Multidisciplinary Health Teams in the Context of the COVID 19

712.2 Nancy COTE, *Université Laval, Canada*; Andrew FREEMAN, *Université Laval, Canada*; Dave LAVERDIÈRE, *Université Laval, Canada* and Yasmine FRIKHA, *Université Laval, Canada*
New Modes of Collaboration during COVID-19: Reflections on the Conditions of Emergence and Sustainability for Long-Term Improvement of the Health System

712.3 Gustavo NIGENDA, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico* and Patricia ARISTIZABAL, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Health Interprofessional Training and Practice in Mexico: The Initial Signs of a Monopoly Crack

712.4 Marie-pierre BOURDAGES-SYLVAIN, *Téluq University, Canada* and Nancy COTE, *Université Laval, Canada*
The Changing Role of Middle Managers in Healthcare Organizations

17:30-19:20

713 Going Beyond Organisational Professionalism. Exploring the Role of Work Settings for Professionals in the Digitalised Era: Session II - Organisation & Professions

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Lara MAESTRIPIERI, *DASTU/Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

Chair: Thiago PIMENTEL, *Federal University of Juiz de Fora / UFJF, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

713.1 LEI JIN, *CHINESE UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG, Hong Kong*
Indifferent, Coerced or Embracing? Clinical Pathways and Autonomy of Chinese Physicians

713.2 Deepthi SHANKER, *Global Institute of Business Studies (GIBS), India*
Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Coworking Spaces in the Knowledge Society

713.3 Muriel SURDEZ, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*
How Platforms Reconfigure Professional Groups. the Confrontation between Connective and Protective Professionalism Among Swiss Hoteliers

713.4 Carmen BUZEA, *Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania*; Ana-Maria CAZAN, *Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania* and Mihaela GHEORGHE, *Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania*
Perceived Organizational Support, Work Commitment and Self-Reported Academic Productivity of Romanian Sociologists during Covid-19 Pandemic

713.5 Judith BENNETT, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Susan AINSWORTH, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Julian WEBB, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Newlaw Down Under: Extending Organizational Professionalism with New Structures

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

714 Professional Work. Part I

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*

Chair: Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

714.1 Sundeep AULAKH, *LUBS, United Kingdom*
'Lipstick Innovation!' Contextualizing Disruptive Innovation through Digital Technologies in Professional Services: Boundary-Work in Law and Auditing

714.2 Bertil ROLANDSSON, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden* and Magnus BERGQUIST, *University of Halmstad, Sweden*
Automated Decision Making and Professional Work in Healthcare.

714.3 Jeronimo CRACOGNA, *University of Belgrano, Argentina*
Technological Changes during Pandemics: Opportunities for Growth and Organizational Challenges for Argentinean Torts and Labor Lawyers.

714.4 Kathrin EHMANN, *BIBB - Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, Germany* and Marco SEEGER, *BIBB - Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, Germany*
Technological Change, Work Organization and Rationalization in Professional Work – Insights from Germany

714.5 Corinne DELMAS, *UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL/LATTS (UMR 8134), France*
The Porosity of Work Boundaries in the Age of Digitalisation and Teleworking: The Case of the Notary's Office in France

714.6 Masayo FUJIMOTO, *Doshisha University, Japan*
Changes in Professional Job Descriptions Due to Automation of Technology

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

714.7 Krzysztof LEPCZYNSKI, *Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, Poland*
Slaves of Passion? Work of Journalists in Cognitive Capitalism

15:30-17:20

715 Professional Work. Part II

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Tracey ADAMS, *University of Western Ontario, Canada*

Chair: Sundeep AULAKH, *LUBS, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

715.1 Jelena ATANACKOVIC, *University of Ottawa, Canada*; Henrietta BOATENG, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Ivy BOURGEOULT, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
An Intersectional Contextualized Path Framework of Mental Health, Leaves of Absence and Return to Work Among Professional Workers

715.2 Milan MARKOVIC, *Texas A&M University School of Law, USA* and Gabriele PLICKERT, *California State Polytechnic University Pomona, USA*
Prosecutorial Moonlighting

715.3 Orly LINOVSKI, *University of Manitoba, Canada*
Financializing Professionals: Experiences of Urban Planners in Publicly-Traded Firms

715.4 Anita Cecilia HIRSCH ADLER, *Colonia Letran Valle, Mexico*
Conflicts Expressed By Graduate Academics in Mexican Universities about Their Work Conditions

715.5 Wei ZHAO, *University of California, Riverside, USA*; Andrew MCBRIDE, *University of North Carolina at Charlotte, USA* and Quinn BLOOM, *University of California, Riverside, USA*
Pride and Prejudice: Professional Work, Occupational Identity, and Technology Framing

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

715.6 Rohith JYOTHISH, *O.P. Jindal Global University, India*
Engineering Software Service Professionals: Hiring and Training Practices in Thiruvananthapuram City in India

17:30-19:20

JS-82 Professional Transformations in Public Sector/Social Services Management: Trends and Challenges – between Managerial ‘Governmentality’ and Authoritarian Governance?

Committees: RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups (Host); RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy

See Joint Session Details for JS-82.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

716 Oppressors or Saviours? The Role of Professions in a Changing World

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Michael SAKS, University of Suffolk, United Kingdom

Chair: Michael SAKS, University of Suffolk, United Kingdom

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

716.1 Duncan HONORE-MORRIS, *S P Jain School of Global Management, Australia*
Unshackling the Iron Cage through Perennial Gales of Creative Destruction: Can the Accounting Profession Survive As a Social Institution?

716.2 Charles BOSVIEUX-ONYEKWELU, *CNRS - Centre Norbert Elias, France*
Should We Trust Large Law Firms to Take Care of Society? a Critical Assessment of Lawyers’ Pro Bono Practice

716.3 Somashekher CHINNAPPA, *Bangalore University, India*
Physicians in Digital Transformation of Medical Profession in India

716.4 Gupteswar PATEL, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Viet-Hai PHUNG, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Ian TRUEMAN, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*; Vanessa BOTAN, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom* and Niroshan SIRIWARDENA, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*
Power Dynamics in out-of-Hospital Emergency Care: The Community First Responder – Ambulance Clinician Relationship in the United Kingdom

716.5 Angelique WILDSCHEUT, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
The Declining Importance of the Constructs of Profession/Al/Isation for Sociological Analysis?

17:30-19:20

717 Professions and Inequalities

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Debby BONNIN, University of Pretoria, South Africa

Chair: Debby BONNIN, University of Pretoria, South Africa

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

717.1 Talara LEE, *University of Sydney Business School, Australia*; Rae COOPER, *University of Sydney Business School, Australia* and Meraiah FOLEY, *University of Sydney Business School, Australia*
Do You See What I See? Explaining (gendered) Perceptions of Gender Inequality in the Australian Legal Profession

717.2 Scott TUTTLE, *University of Kansas, USA*
Equal Pay for Disproportionate Work: Assessing Cultural Taxation in the Legal Profession

717.3 Anne BRESEE, *Western University, Canada* and Tracey ADAMS, *Social Science Centre, Canada*
Restratification in Academia: The Struggle for Professional Identity

717.4 Magali GRAMMARE, *CNRS/BETA University of Strasbourg, France*
Gendered Professions, Prestigious Professions: When Stereotypes Condition Career Choices

717.5 Shalini PUNJABI, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Corporate Hiring and Talent Signalling in an Elite Professional Labour Market in India: A Social Construction

717.6 Anna RANSIEK, *Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, FU Berlin, Germany* and Anina MISCHAU, *Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, FU Berlin, Germany*
(Gendered) Gatekeeping in the Recruitment and Support of (female) Early-Stage Researchers in a Mathematical Cluster of Excellence

19:30-20:50

718 RC52 Business Meeting

Location: M12 (Crown)

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

719 Challenges of Professional Groups and Professionalism in Latin America in a Context of Disputes between Authoritarianism and Democracy

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Marta PANAIÁ, *CONICET-UBA, Argentina*; Maria da Gloria BONELLI, *Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos, Brazil* and Alfredo HUALDE, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte, Mexico*

Chair: Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - FCSH, Portugal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

719.1 Maria Eugenia SAN MARTIN, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
La Profesionalización Del Mando De Las Mujeres Policías. Un Estudio De Caso Sobre La Policía Federal Argentina.

719.2 Amanda LIMA, *University of São Paulo - Center for the Study of Violence (NEV-USP), Brazil*
Legal Professions and Anti-Corruption Operations: The Case of Lava Jato

719.3 Tharuell KAHWAGE, *Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil*

Occupational Prestige, Gender and Judicial Clerks of a Domestic Violence Court

719.4 Fabiana OLIVEIRA, *UFSCar - Federal University of Sao Carlos, Brazil*; Maria da Gloria BONELLI, *Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos, Brazil*; Jacqueline SINHORETTO, *Federal University of Sao Carlos, Brazil*; Frederico ALMEIDA, *Unicamp, Brazil* and Fabio SA E SILVA, *University of Oklahoma, USA*
Legal Professionals and Democracy in Brazil: Local-Global Struggles to Reshape Professional Forces in the Judicial and Public Safety Systems

719.5 Patricia ARISTIZABAL, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*; Gustavo NIGENDA, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*; Laura Paola SANCHEZ, *National Institute of Epidemiology "Dr. Juan H. Jara", Argentina*; Stefania CEDEÑO, *Latin American Nursing Education Network, Ecuador*; Martin JUSTO, *National Institute of Epidemiology "Dr. Juan H. Jara", Argentina* and Bernardo TAVERNA, *National Institute of Epidemiology "Dr. Juan H. Jara", Argentina*
Disturbance of the State-Profession Dynamic in a Globalised World after the Ravages of the COVID-19 Pandemic: Disputes between Systemic Powers and Labour Rights.

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

719.6 Marta PANAI, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Las Profesiones En Cuestión

17:30-19:20

720 Professionalization and Counter-Professionalization in Early-Childhood Education and Care

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Lara MAESTRIPIERI, *DASTU/Politecnico di Milano, Italy*; Rakefet SELA-SHEFFY, *Tel Aviv University, Israel* and Netta AVNOON, *The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel*

Chair: Harald MIEG, *Humboldt-Universitaet zu Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

720.1 Chrysa KEUNG, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Professional Ethics for Early Childhood Teaching Profession

720.2 Kumiko HAGIWARA, *St. Andrew's University, Japan*
Professional Identities and Market-Centered Childcare Policies: Can Japanese Registered Nursery Teachers Evade the Professionalization Trap?

720.3 Lara MAESTRIPIERI, *DASTU/Politecnico di Milano, Italy* and Raquel GALLEGU, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Emerging Professionalization in Social Innovation. the Case of Early Childhood Education and Care in Barcelona

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

721 RC52 Open Session I: Professionalism, Ethics and Social Change

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Helena SERRA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - FCSH, Portugal*

Chair: Debby BONNIN, *University of Pretoria, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

721.1 Gregor SCHAFER, *FernUniversität in Hagen, Germany*
Ambiguity between Social Stratification and Methodological Nationalism: The Case of High-Skilled Migrants

721.2 Harald MIEG, *Humboldt-Universitaet zu Berlin, Germany*
Professional Ethics: Responsibility, Accountability, or Duty? a Clarification of Terms and Research

721.3 Duncan HONORE-MORRIS, *S P Jain School of Global Management, Australia*
Are We Playing Chicken Little with the Accounting Profession? a Dilemma of Employability of (non)Professional Thinking Graduates; Is This an Apparent Failure to Embed Professionalism and Professional Skills throughout the Curriculum?

721.4 Xuewen YAN, *Cornell University, USA*
English Hegemony from below: How Chinese Scholars Navigate Academic Production in an Anglicized World

721.5 Gilles VERPRAET, *University Paris Ouest Nanterre, France*
Linking Professionalisms for Sustainable State : New Dialectics of Control

12:30-14:20

722 RC52 Open Session II: Corporatism, Bureaucratization and Their Implications for Professionalism

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Somashekher CHINNAPPA, *Bangalore University, India*

Chair: Sindhe JAGANATH RAMANNA, *Gulbarga University, India*

Co-Chair: Nagendrappa PATIL, *Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi, India*

Discussant: Abdul Gaffar KHAN, *Gulbarga University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

722.1 Raghavendra GUDAGUNTI, *Near Gopalswamy Temple, India*
Spate of Merger and Acquisitions in Healthcare Industry: Implications for Medical Profession and Health Services in India

722.2 Sudha KHOKATE, *Bangalore University, India*
Deepening Inequities in Access to Health Care System. a Study of COVID-19 Situation in India.

722.3 Suchet KUMAR, *Rayat Bahra University India, India*
Professionalism As a Means of Organizational Control in Call Centres

722.4 Anuragini SHREEYA, *University of Delhi, India*
Bureaucratic Training in India: The Ambiguity of Rules in a Bureaucrat's Work

14:30-16:20

723 The Changing Paradigm of Professions and Professional Groups in the Era of Globalization

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Virendra P. SINGH, *Chairman, GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), Raj Nagar Extension Ghaziabad-201017, India, India* and Deepthi SHANKER, *Global Institute of Business Studies (GIBS), India*

Chair: Sarvesh TRIPATHI, *GGSIIP University New Delhi, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

723.1 Pankaj Kumar SINGH, *Maharana Pratap Govt. PG College, Dept of Sociology 243633 Bilsi (Budaun) - India, India*
Caste Class and Religion in Legal Profession of a Town in Central Uttar Pradesh, India.

723.2 Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India*
Status of Yunani Medical System in Medieval and Modern India

723.3 Diego BARRAGAN, *Researcher, Colombia*
Everyday Labors and Time Measurements. an Approach to Public Accountants in Colombia.

723.4 Rachna SAKSENA, *Institute for social action and research, India*
The Pharma Industry during Covid-19 :Indian Resurgence and the Pathways

723.5 Preeti TIWARI, *Global Research and Educational Foundation India (GREFI), B-1205A, KM Residency, Raj Nagar Extension, Ghaziabad-201017, India*
The Role of Health Professionals in Combating the Crisis of Covid-19 in India

723.6 Manju GOYAL, *RETIRED PROFESSOR AND PRINCIPAL, India*
Impact of Covid-19 on Real Estate Professionals in the National Capital Region of India

RC53

Sociology of Childhood

Program Coordinators: Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Valeria LLOBET, *CONICET / UNSAM, Argentina*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

724 The Intersection between Spatial and Generational Orders for Understanding Childhood

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Tobia FATTORE, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Susann FEGTER, *University of Technology Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Tobia FATTORE, *Macquarie University, Australia*

Co-Chair: Susann FEGTER, *University of Technology Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

724.1 Colette MC AULEY, *CASCADE Research Centre, Cardiff University, United Kingdom*
Daily Lives of Young Children in Foster Care: Spatial Context and the Influence of the Intergenerational Order

724.2 Lars ALBERTH, *Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany*
Absent Bodies and "Institutional Doppelgänger" – on the Generational Structure of a Family Court's Space

724.3 Lisa FISCHER, *Institute of Educational Science, Technical University Berlin, Germany*; Stella MAERZ, *School of Social Work, University of Vechta, Germany*; Yasmina GANDOUZ-TOUATI, *University of Vechta, Germany* and Miriam KOST, *Institute of Educational Science, Technical University Berlin, Germany*
Well-Being in Socio-Spatial Contexts: Intersectional Perspectives on Children's Experiences in out-of-School Learning Settings

724.4 Jan MASON, *University of Western Sydney, Australia*; Gabrielle DRAKE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*; Janet FALLOON, *Western Sydney University, Australia* and Lise MOGENSEN, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Greta Thunberg's Climate Activism: Challenging Generational and Economic Power

17:30-19:20

JS-17 Children and Youth Navigating Gender

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood (Host)*; RC34 *Sociology of Youth*

See Joint Session Details for JS-17.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-25 Digital Mediation of Children's Learning and the Changing Ecology of Home-School-World Connectivity

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood (Host)*; TG10 *Digital Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-25.

10:30-12:20

725 Opening Session of RC53 Sociology of Childhood

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Co-Chair: Valeria LLOBET, *CONICET / UNSAM, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

725.1 Sarada BALAGOPALAN, *Dept of Childhood Studies, Rutgers University, Camden, USA*
Opening Session of RC53 Sociology of Childhood "They Will Adjust": Relationalities and Entrepreneurial Self-Making in Young Women's School-to-Work Transitions in Mumbai, India

17:30-19:20

726 Intersectionality and Cultural Politics of Childhood

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Chandrabali DUTTA, *HIRALAL MAZUMDAR MEMORIAL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, India* and Mariam MEYNERT, *Lund University, Sweden*

Chair: Chandrabali DUTTA, *HIRALAL MAZUMDAR MEMORIAL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

726.1 Mariam MEYNERT, *Lund University, Sweden*
Culture and Politics of the Subaltern Child As Located in the Indian Context.

726.2 Nirmali GOSWAMI, *Tezpur University, India* and Navarupa BHUYAN, *Tezpur university, India*
Class, Gender and Community Identity at School: Girls' Style on Saraswati Puja in Assam

726.3 Marisela VELAZQUEZ, *Children's Hospital Los Angeles, USA*; Lindsay SLAY, *Children's Hospital Los Angeles, USA*; Michele KIPKE, *Children's Hospital Los Angeles, USA*; Mariam TAIWO, *Children's Hospital Los Angeles, USA* and Jeremy T. GOLDBACH, *The Brown School, Washington University in St. Louis, USA*

Transitions in Drug Use Among Young Individuals: Intersections of Sexual and Gender Minority Youth of Color and Personal Illicit Drug Use

726.4 Andrea LIZAMA, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Living the Gender Gap within the Classroom: Students' Experiences from Two Chilean Schools

726.5 Leroy GHISLAIN, *University Rennes 2 (France), France*
Injunctions to Child Autonomy

726.6 Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey*
Social Construction of Childhoods Related to Multiple Sclerosis Illness

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

JS-56 Childhoods and Systemic Inequalities

Committees: *RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); RC51 Sociocybernetics*

See Joint Session Details for JS-56.

10:30-12:20

727 Institutional, Political and Cultural Challenges in the Studies of Childhood

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Maria Raquel MACRI, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*

Chair: Sharmla RAMA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

727.1 Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Cristiana CARNEIRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Beatriz TAKEITI, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

The Postgraduate Program of Interdisciplinary Childhood, Adolescence and Youth Studies at the Federal University of Rio De Janeiro: Challenges for the Development of an Area Studies

727.2 Mauricio PADRON-INNAMORATO, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*

Educación, Pobreza y Cultura Como Elementos Claves Para Explicar El Fenómeno Del Trabajo Infantil. El Caso Mexicano Como Ejemplo

727.3 Patrick CHANDA, *School of Graduate Studies, Lingnan University, Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Income Inequality, Country-Level Social Support, Gender Inequality and Gender Differences in Children's Subjective Well-Being. a Multilevel Cross-National Study

15:30-17:20

728 Hearing the Voices of Children Revisited? Silencing and the Generational Order

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Lars ALBERTH, *Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany* and Doris BUEHLER-NIEDERBERGER, *University of Wuppertal, Germany*

Chair: Lars ALBERTH, *Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

728.1 Tobia FATTORE, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Gabrielle DRAKE, *Western Sydney University, Australia*; Janet FALLOON, *Western Sydney University, Australia*; Jan MASON, *University of Western Sydney, Australia* and Lise MOGENSEN, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
School and Well-Being: Education, Self-Determination and Adult-Imposed Aspirations

728.2 Xiaorong GU, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*
Theorizing 'Silence' in Childhood Studies

17:30-19:20

729 Critical Perspectives on Children's Rights

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Didier REYNAERT, *HOGENT University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Belgium*; Afua TWUM-DANSO IMOH, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom* and Wouter VANDENHOLE, *Hogent University, Belgium*

Chair: Tobia FATTORE, *Macquarie University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

729.1 Therese MORTENSEN, *Lund University, Denmark*
Human Rights As Social Service: Vernacular Rights Cultures in a Rights-Based and Neoliberal India

729.2 Anandini DAR, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India*
Children's Suffrage Rights: Southern Perspective on Decolonizing Children's Rights and Childhood

729.3 Basia VUCIC, *Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*
Children's Rights As the Weapons of the Weak.

729.4 Monica PATTERSON, *Carleton University, Canada*
Ethics Vs. Participation? Navigating the Tensions within Collaborative Research with Children in South Africa

729.5 Prerna GAUTAM, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai, India, India*
Child Rights in Situations of Armed Conflict: The Case of Kashmir

729.6 Verena MARKE, *Leuphana University Lüneburg, Germany*
Child Participation and the Right to be Heard – Community Rights in Progressive School Education in the US, Hawai'i

729.7 Archana RATH, *O.P. Jindal Global University, India*
Rethinking Child Citizenship in India: Age, Agency and Law

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

729.8 Valeria LLOBET, *CONICET / UNSAM, Argentina* and Carla VILLALTA, *FFyL-UBA, CONICET, Argentina*
Building a Political Perspective. Human Rights Standards and Indicators in the Field of Children's Rights in Argentina

729.9 Seran DEMIRAL, *Istanbul Arel University, Turkey*
Philosophical Inquiry and Creative Writing with Children on Rights of the Human and the Environment

729.10 Frida PETERSSON, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*; Damon BARRETT, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden* and Russell TURNER, *University of Gothenburg, Sweden*
Injecting Drug Use Among Legal Minors and the Best Interests of the Child

729.11 Verena MARKE, *Leuphana University Lüneburg, Germany*
The Right of the Child to be Heard (Art. 12, UN-CRC) and a Philosophy of Children's Voices

19:30-20:50

730 RC53 Business Meeting

Location: M4 (Crown)

Chairs: Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Sharmila RAMA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

JS-89 Childhoods at the Crossover of Disasters

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood (Host)*; RC39 *Sociology of Disasters*

See Joint Session Details for JS-89.

15:30-17:20

731 COVID-19: Deepening Inequalities for the Marginalized Children

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Bula BHADRA, *Sister Nivedita University, India*

Chair: Chandrabali DUTTA, *RC 53, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

731.1 Mariam MEYNERT, *Lund University, Sweden*
Intersectionality As an Approach to Impact of Covid 19 on Children

731.2 Bula BHADRA, *Sister Nivedita University, India*
COVID 19: Deepening Digital Divide for Marginalized Children of India

731.3 Nadezda PRISYAZHNAYA, *Institute of Social sciences, Russian Federation* and Nadezhda VYATKINA, *Sechenov University, Russian Federation*
Covid-19 As an Imperative of a New Childhood

731.4 Chandni BASU, *Sister Nivedita University, Kolkata, India, India*
Searching for Freedom – between the Sky and the Earth

731.5 Anusuya MOITRA, *Muralidhar Girls' College, India*
Care in Contagion : An Account of (Dis)Able Children's Lived Experiences in Kolkata during Covid 19 Pandemic

731.6 Ishani DEB, *University of Calcutta, India*
Sequestered Adolescents and the Legal Loopholes in Juvenile Justice Act 2015: The Legal Marginality of Teenagers during Covid 19

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

732 Slow Violence, Crises of Care, and Possible Futures

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M4 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Valeria LLOBET, *CONICET / UNSAM, Argentina*; Marjorie MURRAY, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile* and Rachel ROSEN, *University College London (UCL) Institute of Education, United Kingdom*

Chair: Seran DEMIRAL, *Istanbul Arel University, Turkey*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

732.1 Cristina DELGADO VINTIMILLA, *York university, Canada* and Veronica PACINI-KETCHABAW, *Western University, Canada*

The Slow Violence of Mining: Children and Women Codesign Recuperative Practices

732.2 Valentina GLOCKNER, *Colegio de Sonora, Mexico* and Rachel ROSEN, *University College London (UCL) Institute of Education, United Kingdom*

Minorization Regimes and the Politics of Bordering

732.3 Marjorie MURRAY, *Institute for research in Violence and Democracy, Chile*

Displacements and Dissolutions: Mothers with Mental Health Problems and Everyday Violence Beyond the Caring Network in Santiago

732.4 Kaidong GUO, *UCL, United Kingdom*

Life Around the Hukou System: Debt, Education and Unstable Childhood from a Framework of Slow Violence

732.5 Marina MEDAN, *LICH - Universidad de San Martín / CONICET, Argentina* and Florencia PAZ, *LICH-Universidad de San Martín / CONICET, Argentina*
La Vida Cotidiana De Niños y Jóvenes En Barrios Populares: Violencias, Temporalidades Y Tramas Estatales

10:30-12:20

JS-125 Linking Ages - Pathways to Cross-Fertilizing the Fields of Age and Childhood Studies

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood (Host)*; RC11 *Sociology of Aging*

See Joint Session Details for JS-125.

RC54

The Body in the Social Sciences

Program Coordinators: Craig COOK, *Woodstock School, India* and Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-15 Violence & Body: Reflecting Our Own Limits and Beyond

Committees: TG11 *Violence and Society (Host)*; RC54 *The Body in the Social Sciences*

See Joint Session Details for JS-15.

17:30-19:20

733 Embodiment and Ground Theory. David Le Breton and His Contribution to the Sociology of the Body, a Commemorative Session

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Leticia SILVA, *Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil* and Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

Chair: Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

733.1 Frederic VANDENBERGHE, *Universidade Federal de Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Existential Anthropology: Facing the Body with David Le Breton

733.2 Anna WOJTEWICZ, *Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland*

Would I Do It Again This Way? Experiences of Research on the Bodily Practices of Four Generations of Polish Men

733.3 Alexandre ZARIAS, *Fundação Joaquim Nabuco, Brazil* and Anne SANTANA, *Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil*

Ruling the Skin: Body and Legislative Proposals in Brazil

733.4 Maria Denise DOURADO DA SILVA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

Pain Experiences in Female Parathletes: From the Contributions of David Le Breton

733.5 Mihaela ONET, *Université de Strasbourg, France*

Le Corps En Patrimoine Comme Enjeu Culturel De l'Immortalité De La Corporéité En Société

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

734 Bodies and Emotions in the Present Time

Language: English, Spanish, French

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

Chair: Dietmar WETZEL, *MSH Medical School, Hamburg & University of Basel, Switzerland*

Panelists: Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina* and Somdatta MUKHERJEE, *Sister Nivedita University, India, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

Kaouther DOUZI, *University of Liege, Belgium*

Doing a Study in a (Post) Revolutionary Context Reflection on a Study "the Performance of Bodies in Protest Assemblies in Tunisia on December 17, 2010".

734.1 Adrian SCRIBANO, *CONICET, Argentina*

Inner Planet, Values and Politics of Sensibilities

734.2 Somdatta MUKHERJEE, *Sister Nivedita University, India, India*

Bodies, Emotions & Borders: An Ethnography on Indian Army

734.3 Erynn CASANOVA, *University of Cincinnati, USA* and Jeremy BRENNER-LEVOY, *University of Cincinnati, USA*

Embodiment and the Boundaries of Gender, Race, and the Self in Cosplay

734.4 Katarzyna MANKOWSKA, *University of Nicolaus Copernicus in Toruń, Academia Rerum Socialium, Poland*

Experiencing the Body in the Process of Non-Binary Gender Identities Development in Polish Cultural Context.

734.5 Maxime DUVIAU, *TREE, France*

Prendre La Route, Entre Autonomies Et Responsabilités

734.6 Craig COOK, *Woodstock School, India*

Constructing Masculinities and Femininities through the Basketball Free Throw

19:30-20:50

735 Sea-Ing through Bodies, Health, and Sustainability

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Monica MESQUITA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal*

Chair: Monica MESQUITA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal*

Co-Chair: Leticia SILVA, *Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

735.1 Dennis ERASGA, *De La Salle University, Philippines*; Rito BARING, *De La Salle University, Philippines* and Delfo CANCERAN, *De La Salle University - Manila, Philippines*

Demonstrative Body: The Agency of a Filipino Devotee's Ritual Body at the Spectacle of the Black Nazarene's Traslación

735.2 Hsiao-Mei JUAN, *National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*
Artificial Natural Death: The Presentation of Good Dying in Hospice Care

735.3 Antonio Cristian PAIVA, *Universidade Federal do Ceará, Brazil*
El Cuerpo, Los Sentidos y El Sujeto En El Alzheimer: La Enfermedad Contada Por Los Familiares

735.4 Victoria D'HERS, *CONICET-IIGG, Argentina*
Haciendo Cuerpo La Naturaleza. Percepción Del Cuerpo, Sensibilidad y Crisis Ambiental En Grupos De Prácticas De Meditación En Buenos Aires.

Wednesday 28 June

15:30-17:20

JS-70 Diversities Bodies, Violence and Human Rights in the 21st Century: The Gender and Racism Issues

Committees: *RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences (Host); TG11 Violence and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-70.

17:30-19:20

JS-78 Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part I

Committees: *RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-78.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

736 Understanding Rising Authoritarianism: Affects, Emotions and Resonance in the Neoliberal Politics of the Body

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dietmar WETZEL, *MSH Medical School, Hamburg, Germany*

Chair: Craig COOK, *Woodstock School, India*

Co-Chair: Somdatta MUKHERJEE, *Department of Sociology Sister Nivedita University, Kolkata, India., India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

736.1 Sharon AVITAL, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
Panic and Disappearance-The Body and Technological Authority

736.2 Patrycja BUXTON, *University of Stavanger, Norway* and Ingunn STUÐSRØD, *University of Stavanger, Norway*
Female Body As the Site of Suffering and Recovering from Domestic Violence: Stories from Poland and Norway

736.3 Monica MESQUITA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal*
The Knowing of Neoliberal Tide. Decolonizing the Coast Zone!

17:30-19:20

737 Body throughout Time: The Role of Women in Theoretical and Social Movements

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Victoria D'HERS, *CONICET-IIGG, Argentina*

Chair: Victoria D'HERS, *CONICET-IIGG, Argentina*

Co-Chair: Somdatta MUKHERJEE, *Department of Sociology Sister Nivedita University, Kolkata, India., India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

737.1 Nicole JENKINS, *Howard Univeristy, USA*; Kwizera CHRISTELLA, *Independet scholar, France* and Sri yash TADIMALLA, *University North California Charlotte, USA*
Global Crowns: Black Women on Emotions Surrounding Natural Hair the Globe

737.2 Carmen RUIZ-REPULLO, *University of Jaen, Spain*; Laura PAVON-BENITEZ, *University of Granada, Spain*; Carmen RODRÍGUEZ-GUZMÁN, *University of Jaen, Spain* and Elena RUIZ-ANGEL, *University of Huelva, Spain*
Invisible Violence at the Centre: Strategies of Psychological Gender-Based Intimate Partner Abuse

737.3 Dulce MARTINEZ, *UAM-Xochimilco, Mexico*
Música, Cuerpo y Emociones: Una Reflexión Sobre El Perreo Como Estrategia De Lucha y Resistencia

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

JS-120 Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part II

Committees: *RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-120.

15:30-17:20

738 RC54 Business Meeting

Location: 215 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Craig COOK, *Woodstock School, India*

Chair: Victoria D'HERS, *CONICET-IIGG, Argentina*

RC55

Social Indicators

Program Coordinator: Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

739 Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of the 2020-2022 Pandemic on Quality of Life and Well-Being. Part I: Social Relations, Happiness, and Mental Well-being

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christian SUTER, *Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland*

Chair: Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

739.1 Yue QIAN, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Wen FAN, *Boston College, USA*

Two Years Later: The Early-2020 COVID-19 Outbreak in China and Subsequent Flourishing

739.2 Indera PATTINASARANY, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
Analyzing the Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Happiness in Indonesia

739.3 Magda BORKOWSKA, *University of Essex, United Kingdom*; Renee LUTHRA, *University of Essex, United Kingdom* and James LAURENCE, *Economic and Social Research Institute, Ireland*

Perceived Neighbourhood Cohesion and Mental Distress during the Covid-19 Pandemic

739.4 Joonmo SON, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
The Latent Classes of the Volunteer Satisfaction Index and Volunteering during the Pandemic

739.5 Jakob HARTL, *University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*; Reinhold SACKMANN, *Martin-Luther-University, Germany* and Ina MAYER, *University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*
Time Is a Great Healer? Social Cohesion over the Course of the Covid-19 Pandemic

739.6 Katsumi SHIMANE, *Senshu University, Japan* and Phuong DANG, *Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Institute of Sociology, Vietnam*

Deaths Under the Pandemic: From Simplified Ceremonies to Shrinking Relationships

15:30-17:20

740 Volunteerism in the Midst of the Pandemic

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Joonmo SON, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Joonmo SON, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

740.1 Augusto GAMUZZA, *University of Catania, Italy* and Francesca GRECO, *Prisma srl, Italy*
«a Concern for the Global North Is Only 'one' of the Problems of the Global South». Redefining International Volunteering for Development in a Syndemic Society

740.2 John MOY, *Queensland Fire and Emergency Services, Australia*
Emergency Services Volunteering in Australia; Pandemic Impacts

740.3 Mieko YAMADA, *Purdue University Fort Wayne, USA*
Sharing Grief in a Pandemic Era: A Study of Volunteers Working for a Grief Support Agency

740.4 Pildoo SUNG, *Duke-NUS Medical School, Singapore*
Profiles of Volunteer Motivations during the COVID-19 Pandemic and Their Implications for Volunteer Activities

740.5 Ester ZYCHLINSKI, *Ariel University, Israel* and Maya KAGAN, *Ariel University, Israel*
Aspects of Volunteerism in Time of Covid 19

740.6 Lina FERREIRA, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
The Covid-19 Pandemic and Collective Actions in Response to Impoverishment in Brazil

17:30-19:20

JS-21 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part I

Committees: RC41 *Sociology of Population (Host)*; RC55 *Social Indicators*

See Joint Session Details for JS-21.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-27 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part II

Committees: RC55 *Social Indicators (Host)*; RC41 *Sociology of Population*

See Joint Session Details for JS-27.

10:30-12:20

741 The Advantages of Analysing Longitudinal Data for Understanding Changes in Levels of Life Satisfaction

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Joonmo SON, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

741.1 Catherine BERHEIDE, *Skidmore College, USA*; David COTTER, *Union College, USA* and Megan CARPENTER, *St. Lawrence University, USA*
A Comparison of Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance before the COVID-19 Pandemic and during Its Immediate and Intermediate Stages: A Case Study of Academic Staff at Three Small Colleges in the United States

741.2 Marc CALLENS, *Universiteit Gent, Belgium* and Dries VERLET, *Universiteit Gent, Belgium*
The Impact of Covid-19 on Life Satisfaction: A Long-Term Perspective

741.3 Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Adjusting to the New 'Normal': A Comparison of Levels of Happiness before and during the Pandemic

741.4 Yuvisthi NAIDOO, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Revisiting the Question: Does More Money Mean Higher Well-Being?

741.5 Fereydoon RAHMANI, *ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, Canada*
Marginalized Communities' Quality of Life: Kurdish and Non-Kurdish People 1999-2019

15:30-17:20

742 Social Mechanisms of Wellbeing in Comparative Perspectives

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Masayuki KANAI, *Senshu University, Japan*Chair: Masayuki KANAI, *Senshu University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

742.1 Mads LARSEN, *University of Oslo, Norway* and Nina WITOSZEK, *University of Oslo, Norway*
Mechanisms of Prosociality: A Comparative Analysis of Nordic and Slavonic Altruism Toward Ukrainian Refugees

742.2 Yuling WU, *University of Science and Technology Beijing, China*
From "Production Centrality" to "Life Centrality": Research on the Changes of Work-Life Values in the Past 30 Years in China (1990-2018)

742.3 Yanwen WANG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Individuals' Experiences during the Cultural Revolution and Their Trajectories of Well-Being in Middle and Later Life

742.4 Tony TAM, *Department of Sociology, The Chinese University of HongKong, Hong Kong*
Identity Politics and the Evolution of Happiness in Taiwan, 1999-2021

742.5 Yusuke TSUKADA, *University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA*
Life Satisfaction Is Influenced By Perceived Job Insecurity Among Japanese Workers.

742.6 Carola HOMMERICH, *Sophia University, Japan* and Christina SAGIOGLOU, *University of Innsbruck, Institute of Psychology, Austria*
Social Affiliation Accounts for Intercultural Differences of Social Status Effects on Psychological Well-Being: A Comparative Study of Japan, Germany, and the United States

17:30-19:20

743 Pandemic Crisis, War, and Resurgent Authoritarianism: Challenges for the Future of Social Indicators Research

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christian SUTER, *Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland*Chair: Christian SUTER, *Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland*

Panelists: Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*; Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Enrico DI BELLA, *University of Genoa, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

743.1 Heinz-Herbert NOLL, *Social Indicators Research Centre Gesis, Germany*
Pandemic Crisis, War, and Resurgent Authoritarianism. Challenges for the Future of Social Indicators Research: Introductory Presentation

Wednesday 28 June

15:30-17:20

744 Socioeconomic Inequalities in Times of Change: Indicators for Assessing Them in a Global World

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*

Chair: Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

744.1 Einar OVERBYE, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway*
Converging and Diverging Trends in Global Welfare Outcomes

744.2 Frank WIETZKE, *Institut Barcelona d'Estudis Internacionals, Spain*
Dimensions of Social Class in Africa. Results from a Factorial Survey Experiment

744.3 WU HANIA, *Department of Sociology, Fudan University, China*
Revisiting the Tunnel Effect: Economic Growth, Income Inequality and the Subjective Well-Being Among the Chinese Population (2005-2017)

744.4 Cristian SEGURA CARRILLO, *Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Chile y España En Perspectiva Comparada: Procesos De Movilidad Social

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

745 Measuring and analyzing the impact of the 2020-2022 pandemic on quality of life and wellbeing. Part II: basic public services and public policy

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Christian SUTER, *Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland*

Chair: Monica BUDOWSKI, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

745.1 Ilan BIZBERG, *El Colegio de México, Mexico*
Latin American Health Systems, before, during and after the Pandemic.

745.2 Hugo CLAROS, *Independent, Peru*
Mapping the Responses to COVID-19 Pandemic in Peru through the Analysis of Massive Twitter Data. an Inquiry for Public Policy.

745.3 Dolgion ALDAR, *UNDP, Timor-Leste* and Munkhtuya ALTANGEREL, *UNDP, Timor-Leste*
The Socio-Economic Impacts of COVID-19 on Individuals, Households, and Communities in Timor-Leste

745.4 Regina SKIBA, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
Longitudinal Association between Shift Work, Health and Well-Being in Covid-19 Pandemic - an Outcome-Wide Analysis of Polish Garment Factory Workers

15:30-17:20

JS-98 Challenges and Opportunities in Measuring Violence

Committees: TG11 *Violence and Society (Host)*; RC55 *Social Indicators*

See Joint Session Details for JS-98.

17:30-19:20

746 Indicators to Compare Social Stratification and Inequalities Among Countries

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain* and Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*

Chair: Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide Univ. / AUB, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

746.1 Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Composite Indicators of Social Stratification to Compare Inequalities Among Countries: The Case of Spain and Argentina

746.2 Santiago POY, *Pontifical Catholic University of Argentina and National Council of Scientific and Technical Research, Argentina* and Eugenia DICHIERA, *Pontifical Catholic University of Argentina, Argentina*
Labor Market Inequalities and in-Work Poverty in Four Latin American Countries

746.3 Pablo MOLINA DERTEANO, *Programa Cambio Estructural y Desigualdad Social, Argentina*
The Role of General Politic Orientations in Welfare Goals

19:30-20:50

747 RC55 Business Meeting

Location: M9 (Crown)

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

748 Youth Wellbeing and Changes of Social Institutions

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Yi-fu CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*

Chair: Yi-fu CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

748.1 Mario LIONG, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*
Involuntary Migrants: Intimate Relationships and Life Choices of Hong Kong Young People in Taiwan

748.2 Georgia DURMUSH, *Australian Catholic University, Australia* and Kurt MARDER, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Decolonising Higher Education Institutions: Enabling Indigenous Australian Higher Education Youth to Define Their Social and Emotional Wellbeing.

748.3 Ting-Syuan LIN, *Stony Brook University, USA* and Ming-Chang TSAI, *Research Center for Humanities and Social Sciences, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Precarious Work in Early Adulthood: The Case of Taiwan

748.4 Katherine CAVES, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*; Patrick MCDONALD, *ETH Zürich, Switzerland*; Ladina RAGETH, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland* and Ursula RENOLD, *KOF Swiss Economic Institute, ETH Zurich, Switzerland*
Measuring the Social Institutions of Education Systems

748.5 Tatiana GAVRILYUK, *University of Tyumen, Russian Federation*
Young Frontline Service Workers in Russia: Class Contradictions and Striving for Wellbeing in Times of Change.

15:30-17:20

749 Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of the 2020-2022 Pandemic on Quality of Life and Well-Being. Part III: Children and young people

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Christian SUTER, *Université de Neuchâtel, Switzerland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

749.1 Oliver NAHKUR, *University of Tartu, Estonia* and Karoline TIHK, *Freelance researcher, Estonia*
Children's Overall Subjective Well-Being Change during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Global Multi-National Analysis

749.2 Haridhan GOSWAMI, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom*
Children's Wellbeing during COVID-19 Pandemic: An Exploratory Study Among 10-12 Years Old School Children in Bangladesh

749.3 Jennifer CHESTERS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
The Impact of the Pandemic and the Associated Restrictions on the Wellbeing of Young Australians: Evidence from Hilda 2001-2020

749.4 Tselmegsaikhan LKHAGVA, *Independent Research Institute of Mongolia, Mongolia; Byambasuren YADMAA, National Academy of Governance, Mongolia and Bold TSEVEGDORJ, IRIM, Mongolia*
Mongolian's Imagination of Subjective Well Being

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

750 Gender Equality Measurement. Part I

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Enrico DI BELLA, *University of Genoa, Italy*

Chair: Pedro LOPEZ-ROLDAN, *Univ Autonoma de Barcelona, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

750.1 Ewa KRZAKLEWSKA, *Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland; Marta WARAT, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland; Paulina SEKULA, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland and Joerg MUELLER, Universitat Oberta De Catalunya, Spain*

Measuring Gender Equality for Gender Equality Plans. Critical Reflections over the Indicators in Policy Design and Monitoring at the Institutional Level

750.2 Enrico DI BELLA, *University of Genoa, Italy*
Regional Gender Equality Measurement in the EU (REgem): Experiences from a European Jean Monnet Project

750.3 Sandra FACHELLI, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*
Comparative Analysis of Regional Gender Disparities

750.4 Babita TEWARI, *CSJM University, India*
Leisure-Time Physical Activity in Context of Gender Differences

10:30-12:20

751 Gender Equality Measurement. Part II

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Enrico DI BELLA, *University of Genoa, Italy*

Chair: Enrico DI BELLA, *University of Genoa, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

751.1 Georg MUELLER, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland*
Inequality and the Amount of Information Contained in Male and Female Gender

751.2 Heiwa DATE, *Shiga University, Japan*
How Can We "Neither Agree Nor Disagree?": A Content Analysis of Reasons for Intermediate Responses to Questions with Respect to Gender Role Attitudes in Japan

751.3 Leon FREUDE, *Universitat de Barcelona, Spain* and Mario DOMINGUEZ, *Universitat de Barcelona, Spain*
Validating a New Measurement Instrument for Homonationalist Values through a Delphi Method

751.4 Hasan AKCAN, *Turkish Sociological Association, Turkey* and Hilal ARSLAN, *Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies, Turkey*
Gender Data for Empowerment: Rights Based Approach to Measure and Monitor Gender Equality in Turkey

RC56

Historical Sociology

Program Coordinators: Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany* and Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC09 *Social Transformations and Sociology of Development* RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy* RC20 *Comparative Sociology* RC56 *Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice*

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

17:30-19:20

752 Historicising Power Relations and Habitus Formation. Part I

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

Chair: Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

752.1 Robert VAN KRIEKEN, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Power and the Social Unconscious: Mario Erdheim on Power and Collective Fantasy

752.2 Giovanni ZAMPIERI, *Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy*
Judge, Physician, Teacher, and Father. Metaphorizations of the Habitus in Early Modern Manuals for Confessors (1563-1750).

752.3 Catherine MARTIN, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
The Nation As Habitus: Theorizing Exclusionary Perceptions of National Belonging

752.4 Pawel BAGINSKI, *Doctoral School of Humanities, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Gender Power Relations and the Polish National Habitus in the Discourse on Violence Against Women

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

753 Historicising Power Relations and Habitus Formation. Part II

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

Chair: Karen SOLDATIC, *PO Box 11, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

753.1 Maurizio MELONI, *Deakin University, Australia*
Inventing the Middle Ages: Elias, Foucault, and the Colonization of Time

753.2 Lucy BROWN, *Charles University, Czech Republic*
Secularisation, Power and the Civilising Process: An Examination of Early Modern Witchcraft Trials

753.3 Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*
Habitus Formation and Power Dynamics in American Industrial Relations

15:30-17:20

JS-38 Collective Memories of Violence: Remembering in Families and Local Communities

Committees: RC38 *Biography and Society (Host)*; RC56 *Historical Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-38.

17:30-19:20

JS-47 Historical Sociology of Organizations. Part I

Committees: RC56 *Historical Sociology (Host)*; RC17 *Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-47.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

754 Sociology in Somber Times: Opening Windows into the Future

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Elisa REIS, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Elisa REIS, *Rua Conselheiro Lafayette, 4, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

754.1 Zoltan SIMON, *Bielefeld University, Germany* and Mathias ALBERT, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
Historical Change in Society and Nature – before Optimism and Pessimism?

754.2 Jiri SUBRT, *Charles University, Czech Republic*
Multiple Visions of the Future: Or Why Generals Usually Prepare for Past Wars

754.3 Jan P. NEDERVEEN PIETERSE, *University of California at Santa Barbara, USA*
Compare Globalization 1990-2020

754.4 Clayton FORDAHL, *University of Memphis, Sociology Department, USA*
Climate Change and the Micro-Foundations of Social Order: Lessons from Historical Catastrophes

754.5 Kathya ARAUJO, *Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile*
Neoliberalism, Democratization and the Circuit of Detachment: Risks and Opportunities.

754.6 Mariana MOTTA VIVIAN, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Sociology and the Mappings of Possible Futures: Aspirations and Anticipations in the Different Diagnoses of Brazil's Present

754.7 Joanne DILLABOUGH, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
The Subversive Archive in Historical Sociology: Hannah Arendt and the Authoritarian State

10:30-12:20

755 Historical Sociology As Relational Memory. Part I

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Fabio SANTOS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Karen SOLDATIC, *PO Box 11, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

755.1 Jasmine HARRIS, *University of Texas at San Antonio, USA*
Doing Historical Sociology: When Am I a Part of the Story?

755.2 Amy CHIN, *Vassar College, USA*
Relational Remembering: Asian American Daughters Interpreting Memories in the Veteran Household

755.3 Eva BAHL, *University of Goettingen, Germany*
Elmina and Cape Coast (Ghana) As Points of Intersection: Entangled Histories and Relational Memories

17:30-19:20

756 Historical Sociology As Relational Memory. Part II

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Fabio SANTOS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Fabio SANTOS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

756.1 Rachel ZHOU, *McMaster University, Canada*
Make America Great Again (MAGA), Global Britain, and the Chinese Dream: Nostalgia in Times of Uncertainty

756.2 Anna AMELINA, *Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus, Germany*; Manuel PETERS, *BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany*; Miriam TRZECIAK, *BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany* and Jana SCHAEFER, *BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany*
Approaching Contested Entanglements: Postsocialist Colonialities in Membership, Mobility and Memories

756.3 Chrysanthi ZACHOU, *The American College, Greece*
Collective Memory and the Ritual Enactment of National Identity: The Centennial Celebration of the Greek Asia Minor Disaster

19:30-20:50

757 RC56 Business Meeting

Location: M9 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

758 RC56 Open Session 1

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

Chair: Paddy DOLAN, *Technological University Dublin, Ireland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

758.1 Giovanni ZAMPIERI, *Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy*
The Salvation of the Soul, the Salvation of the Face. Strategy and Tactics within the Catholic Disciplinary Revolution (16th-18th centuries).

758.2 Tomasz ZARYCKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*
Bourgeois-Aristocratic Alliance As an Overlooked Source of Peripheral Nationalism

758.3 Nishan KAUSHALL, *York University, Canada*
Imperial Frontiers, Sacred Histories & Golden Ages: Tracing Modern Genealogies of Race, Religion and a 'Hindu' Nation

758.4 Shinichi AIZAWA, *Sophia University, Japan*
The Changing Memory of Schooling By Social Class Structural Reorganization through Societal Industrialization: Focusing on Japanese and German Postwar Educational Practices

Friday 30 June

759 RC56 Open Session 2

Location: M9 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Manuela BOATCA, *University of Freiburg, Germany*

Chair: Tomasz ZARYCKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

759.1 Chungse JUNG, *SUNY Cortland, USA*
Before Radical Sixties: Ethnic and Nationalist Mobilizations of the Global South in the Long 1950s

759.2 Saara KOIKKALAINEN, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland*
The Cinnamon Isle - Sri Lanka As a Utopia in the Travel Accounts of 19th Century British Colonialists

759.3 Matthew WAITES, *University of Glasgow, United Kingdom*
The British Empire's Regulation of Sexualities and Genders Beyond Heteronormativity: Global Historical Sociology and the Queer Analysis of Colonialism

759.4 Fabio SANTOS, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Kinship and Slave Ship: Decolonial Methods Against the Archival Grain

759.5 Robin ARCHER, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*
Radical Resistance and Radical Retreat on the Eve of the Great War

Saturday 1 July

12:30-14:20

**JS-147 Historical Sociology of Organizations.
Part II**

Committees: *RC56 Historical Sociology (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization*

See Joint Session Details for JS-147.

RC57

Visual Sociology

Program Coordinators: Gary BRATCHFORD, *University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom* and Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

760 Building and Integrating Cross-Disciplinary Perspectives of Visual Research

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

Chair: Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

760.1 Carolina CAMBRE, *Concordia University, Canada* and Susan HANSEN, *Middlesex University, United Kingdom*
The Visual Essay "Unbound" As Interdisciplinary Interface

760.2 Kaylan SCHWARZ, *University of Lethbridge, Canada*; Rebekah HUTTEN, *McGill University, Canada* and Claudia MITCHELL, *McGill University, Canada*
"I Struggled to 'Objectify' My Feminism": Examining Feminist Self-Identification through Object Elicitation

760.3 Ozlem ALIOGLU TURKER, *Ankara University, Turkey*
A Visual Analysis of Syrian and Ukrainian Displacements on Conventional and Social Media

17:30-19:20

761 RC57 Business Meeting

Location: M16 (Crown)

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

762 Visual and Multimodal Studies of the City. Part I

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

Chair: Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

762.1 Max HOLLERAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Samuel HOLLERAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
9/11 Steel: Distributed Memorialization

762.2 Ervin GRANA, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*

Visualizing Organizational Legitimacy: The Case of a Women-Led, Urban Poor Community Association in Barangay Tatalon, Philippines

762.3 Sabina ANDRON, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Interviewing Walls? Lessons and Methods from Urban Surfaces

762.4 Carmen LAMOTHE, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Public Stalls, Private Walls: Toilet Graffiti As Political Participation

17:30-19:20

JS-54 Why Do We Need the Visual? Understanding Educational Practices Using Visual Data and Methods.

Committees: RC04 *Sociology of Education (Host)*; RC57 *Visual Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-54.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

763 Visual and Multimodal Studies of the City. Part II

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Luc PAUWELS, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

Chair: Paolo FAVERO, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

763.1 Wendell Marcel COSTA, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*

The Symbolic-Temporal Dimension of the City in Contemporary South American Cinema

763.2 Anne BRESEE, *Western University, Canada*
Cemetery: It Is Not All Death

763.3 Jana VUKIC, *Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Croatia*; Djurdjica DEGAC, *Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Croatia* and Zvonimir BOSNJAK, *Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Croatia*
Visual Construction of the City in Education and Emerging Methodological and Ethical Issues

10:30-12:20

JS-64 Reconstructing Knowledge: Digital Humanities and Visual Culture

Committees: RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host)*; RC57 *Visual Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-64.

15:30-17:20

JS-75 The Algorithmic Turn in Visual StudiesCommittees: *TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC57 Visual Sociology*

See Joint Session Details for JS-75.

17:30-19:20

764 Future Visions of Society: Visual Data and Ethics**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Dennis ZUEV, *ISCTE-IUL, Portugal* and Gary BRATCHFORD, *The University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom***Chair:** Paolo FAVERO, *University of Antwerp, Belgium***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****764.1** Tzung-wen CHEN, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*
Virus, Particulate Matter, and Semiconductor Devices: Thick Governmentality and Regimes of Representation in Taiwan and South Korea**764.2** Tracy Xavia KARNER, *University of Houston, USA*
Access and Permission: The Rules of Visual Representation**764.3** Md Nazmul AREFIN, *University of Alberta, Canada*
Cinema As the 'Othering' Apparatus in Intensifying Polarization: The Construction of 'Us Vs Them' in Post-9/11 Indian Movies**764.4** Michela VOGLINO, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*
Future Landscapes of Aesthetic Accumulation in the Real Estate Market

17:30-19:20

766 Social Visualities: Palgrave Book Series Launch.**Language:** English, Spanish**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Dennis ZUEV, *University of St. Joseph, Macau SAR, Russian Federation* and Gary BRATCHFORD, *The University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom***Chair:** Dennis ZUEV, *University of St. Joseph, Macau SAR, Russian Federation***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****766.2** Veronica GREGORIO, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Visual Research in the Philippines**766.3** Gay MOKWENA, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
Materialising Identities after Apartheid: Shweshwe and the Long Shadow of Empire**Friday 30 June**

10:30-12:20

765 The Social Manifestations' Synthesis As Image**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M16 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Christiane WAGNER, *University of São Paulo, Institute of Advanced Studies, USP Global Cities Synthesis Center, Brazil***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****765.1** Luka VANDEBROEK, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
Memories of Congo: An Autoethnographic Exploration of How My Grandparents' Generation in My Belgian Family Negotiate Colonial Memories Using Photo-Elicitation**765.2** Pedro LISDERO, *CIECS (CONICET y UNC) / UNVM / CIES, Argentina* and Paula ZANINI, *CIECS, Argentina*
Experiencias Visuales, Sensibilidades y Sociedad: Aportes Desde Una Sociología De Los Cuerpos/Emociones**765.3** Yaarit BOKEK-COHEN, *Academic College of Tel Aviv-Jaffa, Israel*
A Visual Semiotic Analysis of Sperm Donors' Baby Photos As Major Marketing Material at the S[u]Permarket**765.4** Manjeeet CHATURVEDI, *Banaras Hindu University, India* and Ishita CHATURVEDI, *Robert Kennedy College, Zurich, India*
Visuals in Action

Working Groups

WG01

Sociology of Local-Global Relations

Program Coordinator: Nataliya VELIKAYA, *Russian State University for the Humanities, Russian Federation*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

767 The Upheavals in the Global Order and Their Ramifications for Democracy

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Virendra P. SINGH, *GLOBAL RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION INDIA (GREFI), India* and Parvez Ahmad ABBASI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University SURAT, India*

Chair: Sarvesh TRIPATHI, *GGSIIP University New Delhi, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

767.1 Preeti TIWARI, *Global Research and Educational Foundation India (GREFI), B-1205A, KM Residency, Raj Nagar Extension, Ghaziabad-201017, India*

Globalization, Modernity and Traditional Ideology: An Analysis of Conflicting Situation of Afghanistan

767.2 Deepthi SHANKER, *Global Institute of Business Studies (GIBS), India*

Indian Professional Education System in the Light of Ukraine-Russian Crisis

767.3 Priyanka JAIN, *Noida International University, India*
Reverse Migration of Indian Afghans in the Emerging World Order

767.4 Rachna SAKSENA, *Institute for social action and research, India*

The Dynamics of Indian Foreign Policy in the Light of Russia-Ukraine Crisis

17:30-19:20

768 WG01 Business Meeting

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

JS-48 Integrative and Disintegrative Processes in Europe and Eurasia: Public Opinion, State Politics and Media Discourse.

Committees: *WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations (Host); RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice*

See Joint Session Details for JS-48.

Wednesday 28 June

15:30-17:20

769 Post-Globalization Challenging Democracies

Location: 206 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dmitry IVANOV, *St. Petersburg state university, Russian Federation*

Chair: Dmitry IVANOV, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

769.1 Veronica KHANGCHIAN, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*

Contemporary Crises: Erosion of Democracy?

769.2 Nataliya VELIKAYA, *Institute of Social and Political Research of Russian Academy of Science, Russian Federation*
Public Legitimization of Political Power in Russia in the Context of a Special Military Operation

769.3 Dawei CHEN, *University of Toronto, Canada*
*A Theory of Dialectical Transnational Historical Materialism
for China's State Capitalism and the China-US Rivalry*

Friday 30 June

JS-128 Approaching Planetary Youth Research

Committees: *WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations (Host);
RC34 Sociology of Youth*

See Joint Session Details for JS-128.

WG05

Famine and Society

Program Coordinator: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development, India* and Joseph Benhar RAJAN, *Executive President, India*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

770 Environmental Crisis/Justice, Global Frameworks and Local Actions: An Agenda for Sustainable Development (Technical Session & Panel Discussion)

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Manish K. VERMA, *Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India*

Chair: P.P. BALAN, *Ministry of Panchayati Raj, India*

Co-Chair: Subhendu RAJ, *PGDAV E COLLEGE, India*

Panelists: Modho GOVIND, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India* and Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Department of Higher Education, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

770.1 Rekha SUMAN, *UILS AVA LODGE SHIMLA -4(HP) India, India* and Ranjit SINGH, *Guru Nanak Dev University, India*
"Impact of Climate Change on Apple Farming Based Rural Livelihoods in Shimla Ranges of the State of Himachal Pradesh"

770.2 Khushboo DUTTA, *BBAU, Lucknow, India*
Impact of Covid-19 on Sustainable Development Goals-3(health and well-being).

770.3 Soumyajit PATRA, *Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, India*
Sustainability and the Idea of "Minimum": "Individuals" in the Making of Our Future

770.4 Sumedha DUTTA, *Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India, India* and Anoop SINGH, *Central University of Punjab, India*
Interrogating the Sikh Response to Environmental Degradation and Climate Change: A Case Study of the Ecosikh in Punjab

15:30-17:20

JS-12 Resurgent Authoritarianism in the Context of SDG 1 on No Poverty, SDG2 on Zero Hunger and SDG 17 on Partnerships for the Goals: Sociology of New Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management (Host); WG05 Famine and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-12.

17:30-19:20

771 Panel Discussion on Covid Pandemic, Rising Authoritarianism, Food Insecurity and Emerging Cultural, Social, Economic, Political and Democratic Challenges

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Namita GUPTA, *Panjab University, India*

Chair: Dipti Ranjan SAHU, *University of Lucknow, India*

Co-Chair: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *CRRID, India*

Panelists: Suchet KUMAR, *Rayat Bahra University India, India*; Anupam BAHRI, *Panjab University, India*; Pirzada AMIN, *Islamic University of Science and Technology[IUST], India* and Sumedha DUTTA, *Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India, India*

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

772 Religious Diversity: Dialogue and Integration

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Pirzada AMIN, *Islamic University of Science and Technology[IUST], India*

Chair: Satish SHARMA, *HIMACHAL PRADESH UNIVERSITY, India*

Panelists: Bindu CHAUDHARY, *Amity University, India*; Shruti GUPTA, *National University of Singapore, India* and Sumedha DUTTA, *Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India, India*

Discussant: Deepak Kumar VERMA, *Dr B R Ambedkar University of Social Sciences, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

772.1 Hasan BANO, *Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India*
Muslim Women Law in Islam

772.2 Minakshi RANA, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India* and Shobhna SHOBNA, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India*
Perception of Women of Reproductive Autonomy: A Cross-Sectional Exploratory Study in Punjab

15:30-17:20

773 Panel Discussion on Religious Diversity, Marginalization of Minorities and Marginalised and Deepening Crises in the World

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Suchet KUMAR, *Rayat Bahra University India, India*

Chair: Pirzada AMIN, *Islamic University of Science and Technology[IUST], India*

Panelists: Minakshi RANA, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India*; Anilesh KUMAR, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong* and Sara AMIN, *The University of the South Pacific, Fiji*

Discussant: Riya SINGH, *MCM DAV Girls College, India*

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

774 Potential of Big Data in Poverty Assessment

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Rimma AKHMETIANOVA, *Centre for Strategic Research Republic of Bashkortostan, Russian Federation*

Chair: Atvir SINGH, *Ch. Charan Singh University, India*

Co-Chair: Jayashree AMBEWADIKAR, *Central university of Gujarat, India*

Panelists: Parijat GHOSH, *PRADAN, India*; Nidhi MISHRA, *Mahila Mahavidyalaya BHU, Varanasi, India*; Ouafae ELARABI, *Université Abdelmalek Essadi Tétouan, Morocco* and Nawa Raj KOIRALA, *Freelancer, Nepal*

Discussant: Bijoya ROY, *CENTRE FOR WOMEN'S DEVELOPMENT STUDIES, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

774.1 Rajiv GUPTA, *Government of Punjab, India* and Namita GUPTA, *Centre for Human Rights and Duties, Panjab University, Chandigarh (India), India*
Right to Housing for Poor in Rural India: A Critical Evaluation of Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana – Gramin in Punjab (India)

774.2 Anupam BAHRI, *Panjab University Chandigarh, India*
Social Inequalities in Rapidly Changing World.

774.3 Nidhi MISHRA, *Mahila Mahavidyalaya BHU, Varanasi, India*
Disabled Women and Family Support: A Study of Varanasi District, India

774.4 Pranaya SWAIN, *National Institute of Science Education and Research, Bhubaneswar, India* and Medha NAYAK, *Wildlife Trust of India, India*
Human-Elephant Interactions: Perspectives of Young Stakeholders on Conflict Mitigation and Conservation

15:30-17:20

JS-74 People-Centric Governance, Society, and Sustainable Development

Committees: WG05 Famine and Society (Host); RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

See Joint Session Details for JS-74.

17:30-19:20

775 Urbanization in Himalayas: Emerging Crises and Civil Society

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Satish SHARMA, *HIMACHAL PRADESH UNIVERSITY, India* and Shamsher SINGH, *FLAME university, India*

Chair: Jagdish Chander MEHTA, *D.A.V. College, Chandigarh (India), India*

Discussants: Dr. Mangal HASAN, *Northern Regional Language Centre, Patiala, India (NRLCPI), India*; Amarjit SINGH, *University of Campania Luigi Vanvitelli, Italy*; Anilesh KUMAR, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong* and Kalpeshkumar Ambalal CHAUHAN, *INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANPUR, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

775.1 Manish K. VERMA, *Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India*
Ecological Crisis, Climate Change and Its Impact in the Himalayan Region: Some Case Studies

775.2 Soumyajit PATRA, *Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, India*
Sustainability and the Idea of "Minimum": "Individuals" in the Making of Our Future

775.3 Kabran Aristide DJANE, *Peleforo Gon Coulibaly University, Côte D'Ivoire*
Environmental Education and Nutritional Behavior Based on Traditional Medicine: Reading from Internally Displaced Women's Experiences in the 2010 Post-Electoral Crisis in Ivory Coast

775.4 Krushna CHETTY, *Sabarmati University, Ahmedabad, India*
Migrant Women and Post COVID-19 in India: A Sociological Analysis

19:30-20:50

776 Panel Discussion on Famine, Poverty, Energy Poverty, Climate Change and Climate Justice

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Debal SINGHARROY, *603, Asiad Games Village, New Delhi 110049, India*

Chair: Sujata PATEL, *Umea University, India*

Panelists: Manish K. VERMA, *Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India*; Shweta PRASAD, *Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India*; Modho GOVIND, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India* and Jhaverbhai PATEL, *School of Social Sciences, India*

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

JS-87 Transforming Traditional Knowledge System of Mountains: A Threat to Sustainability

Committees: WG05 Famine and Society (Host); RC24 Environment and Society

See Joint Session Details for JS-87.

10:30-12:20

777 Women in Developing and Least Developed Countries: Emerging Issues and Alternatives

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Anupam BAHRI, *Panjab University, India* and Vandana SHARMA, *DAV College Sector 10 Chandigarh, India, India*

Chair: Eduardo ALMEIDA, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain*

Co-Chair: Lakhvir SINGH, *PUNJABI UNIVERSITY PATIALA, PUNJAB (INDIA), India*

Panelists: Bindu CHAUDHARY, *Amity University, India*; Rimma AKHMETIANOVA, *Institute for Strategic Studies of the Republic of Bashkortostan, Russian Federation* and Rani MEHTA, *Panjab University, India, India*

Discussant: Prashant ANAND, *Department of Sociology, University of Lucknow, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

777.1 Minakshi RANA, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India*; Sonia KAPUR, *University of North Carolina, Asheville, USA*; Nisha NISHA BHARGAVA, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India*; Shabnam SHABNAM, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India* and Riya RIYA SINGH, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India*
Exploring Pre-Existing Vulnerabilities of Domestic Violence Among Women in the Post COVID-19 Era: A Study across 3 Northern States of India

777.2 Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Department of Higher Education, India* and Abhidiksha SLARIYA, *Department of Sociology Panjab University, Chandigarh, India, India*
Dominant Role of Women in the Economic Life: A Study of Churah Tehsil, Chamba District of Himachal Pradesh, India

777.3 Bindu CHAUDHARY, *Amity University, India* and Madhurima MADHURIMA, *Panjab University, India*
Gender and Mental Health Intersectionality Among Elderly Living Alone in Chandigarh

17:30-19:20

JS-106 Climate Change, Poverty and Inequality in Globalizing World: Changing Socio-Economic, Environmental Fabric of Human Settlements, Neglect of Human Rights and Marginalization of the Poor

Committees: WG05 Famine and Society (Host); TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice

See Joint Session Details for JS-106.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

778 Interrogating Famine

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ping-Chun HSIUNG, *Department of Sociology, University of Toronto, Canada* and Vandana SHARMA, *DAV College Sector 10 Chandigarh, India, India*

Chair: Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Department of Higher Education, India*

Co-Chair: Suchet KUMAR, *Rayat Bahra University India, India*

Discussant: Thamali RANASINGHE, *The University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

778.1 Francieli CAMPOS, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
The Effect of Public Policies to Combat Hunger in RURAL Latin America and the Caribbean, from 2010 to 2020.

778.2 Rani MEHTA, *Panjab University, India, India*
Environmental Challenges and Health Risks in a Globalized Economy

778.3 Neelima LAKRA, *London School of Management Education, United Kingdom*
Climate, Employability and Labour Marginalisation in India: A Case Study

778.4 Anindya MISHRA, *Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, India* and Suraj DAS, *Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, India*
Food Security of the Local Communities and Climate Change in the Himalayas

15:30-17:20

779 Fostering Federalism, Decentralization and People Participation to Cope with Resurgent Authoritarianism and Strengthen and Sustain Democracies, Development and Good Governance

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development, India*

Chair: Sujata PATEL, *Umea University, India*

Co-Chair: Atvir SINGH, *Ch. Charan Singh University, India*

Panelists: P.P. BALAN, *Ministry of Panchayati Raj, India*; Joseph Benhar RAJAN, *Executive President, India*; Subhendu RAJ, *PGDAV E COLLEGE, India*; Hans RAJ, *Himachal Pradesh Legislative Assembly, India* and Nawa Raj KOIRALA, *Freelancer, Nepal*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

779.1 Ouafae ELARABI, *Université Abdelmalek Essadi Tétouan, Morocco*
Decentralization in Morocco after the Arab Spring and the Realization of the Fundamental Rights of the Local Population: Stakes and Boundaries "the Region of Fes-Meknes, Model"

779.2 Nawa Raj KOIRALA, *Freelancer, Nepal*
Federalism, Decentralization and Participation for Good Local Governance and Conflict Resolution: A Case of Nepal

779.3 Jayashree AMBEWADIKAR, *Central university of gujarat, India*
Engaging Role of Women Entrepreneurs in Social Development: Stories from India

779.4 Jagdish Chander MEHTA, *DAV College, Sector -10, Chandigarh, India* and Vandana SHARMA, *DAV College, Sector, 10 Chandigarh, India*
Family Life and Education Under the Dark Shadow of COVID-19 Pandemic in India: Some Observations

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

780 WG05 Business Meeting

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development, India* and Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Department of Higher Education, India*

Chair: Abha CHAUHAN, *University of Jammu, India*

WG06

Institutional Ethnography

Program Coordinator: Adriana SUAREZ-DELUCCHI, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom* and Lauren EASTWOOD, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

781 Institutional Ethnography in Educational Settings

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Josefine JAHREIE, *Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway* and Rebecca LUND, *University of Oslo, Norway*

Chair: Debra TALBOT, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

781.1 Rebecca LUND, *Centre for Gender Research, University of Oslo, Norway*

The Affective Economy of Professorship Qualifications: Ruling, Emotions and Resistance

781.2 Casey WRIGHT, *Western Michigan University, USA*
An Institutional Ethnography Examining Parental Leave from the Standpoints of Women Pursuing Scientific Doctorates in the United States

781.3 Mona OIKARINEN, *University of Western Australia, Australia*; David PEACOCK, *University of Alberta, Canada*; Christine GUPTILL, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Suzanne WIJSMAN, *University of Western Australia, Australia*
Pressure to Perform: An Institutional Ethnography of Australian Post-Secondary Music Students' Health

17:30-19:20

782 Different Perspectives on the Sociology of Knowledge

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Rebecca LUND, *University of Oslo, Norway*

Chair: Chen WANG, *Beijing Institute of Technology, China*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

782.1 Manuel FERNANDEZ ESQUINAS, *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Spain* and Paula ESPINOSA SORIANO, *Spanish Research Council - CSIC, Spain*
How Institutions Shape the System of Knowledge Production: A Comparative Approach on 'Institutional Quality'

782.2 Pei-ru LIAO, *National Pingtung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan*

Women's Protection or Patriarchal Control? an I.E. Journey in the Domestic Violence Prevention Network

782.3 Branwen PEDDI, *Ghent University, Belgium* and Joost DESSEIN, *ILVO (Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research), Belgium*

Understanding Knowledge Politics between Migrant and Local Farmers in Forikrom, a Community in the Transition Zone in Ghana

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

783 Doing Institutional Ethnography: Issues and Innovations I

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Liza MCCOY, *Department of Sociology, Canada* and Frank WANG, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*

Chair: Frank WANG, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

783.1 Elizabeth BRULE, *Queen's University, Canada*; Brittany MCBEATH, *Queen's University, Canada*; Justice SEIDEL, *Weeneebayko Area Health Authority, Canada* and Trinity VEY, *Queen's University, Canada*

Institutional Ethnographic Research and Concept Mapping in Indigenous Health Provision: Challenges and Opportunities of a Combined Research Project

783.2 Sarah MURRU, *KU Leuven, Belgium*
What about All That Data We Didn't Use? Putting in Dialogue Data Analysis in Institutional Ethnography with Other Methods.

783.3 Laura PARSON, *North Dakota State University, USA* and Fredricka SAUNDERS, *North Dakota State University, Bahamas*
Using Experience Sampling Method in an IE

783.4 Sophie HICKEY, *N/A, Australia*
A Change from below...from Above? Engaging Consumers As Knowers in Hospital Leadership, Governance and Monitoring

17:30-19:20

JS-52 Understanding the Sociological Interplay of Emotions

Committees: WG06 *Institutional Ethnography (Host)*; WG08 *Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-52.

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

784 Using Institutional Ethnography to Understand Justice and Power

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Elizabeth ABLETT, *University of Newcastle, United Kingdom*

Chair: Elizabeth ABLETT, *University of Newcastle, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

784.1 Gemma HUGHES, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Francesca RIBENFORS, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom*; Arne MUELLER, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom* and Sara RYAN, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*

Witness to Harm: Tracing the Ruling Relations in Fitness to Practice Hearings

784.2 Orla MURRAY, *Durham University, United Kingdom*
Beyond Reform: Using Feminist Abolitionist Discussions with Institutional Ethnography

784.3 Sue ADAMS, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Josephine DAVIS, *University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Ebony KOMENE, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Institutional Processes and Colonising Practices: Indigenous Nurse Practitioner Workforce Development

784.4 Jessica LANGSTON, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
Why Good Social Workers Do Bad Things: An Institutional Ethnography of Social Work Practice with Children and Families in the UK.

15:30-17:20

785 Various Approaches to Ethnography/ Institutional Ethnography

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Atinder KAUR, *Panjab Univeristy Chnadigarh, India*

Chair: Elizabeth ABLETT, *University of Newcastle, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

785.1 Wen-hui TANG, *National Sun Yat-sen University, Taiwan*
Trasnational Hybrid Mothering

785.2 Wanjuo CHENG, *National Changhua University of Education, Taiwan*
Risks of the Risk Management in Child Protective Services in Taiwan

785.3 Chen WANG, *Beijing Institute of Technology, China*
An Institutional Ethnography Analysis of Highly Skilled Chinese Immigrant Women's English Acquisition and Career Restoration Experience in Canada

19:30-20:50

786 WG06 Business Meeting

Location: M15 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

787 Using Institutional Ethnography in Socio-Legal Studies

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Morena TARTARI, *University of Padua, Italy* and Gary BARRON, *Lethbridge College, Canada*

Chair: Pei-ru LIAO, *National Pingtung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

787.1 Julia DAHLVIK, *University of Applied Sciences FH Campus Wien, Austria*

Multi-Sited Institutional Ethnography: Comparing Public Ombuds Institutions' Practices in Promoting Access to Justice in the Digital Era

787.2 Gary BARRON, *Lethbridge College, Canada*
Quantifying Justice in Canada

787.3 Morena TARTARI, *University of Padua, Italy*
Between Mothers' Needs and Judicial Actualities: The Experience of Single Mothers Who Are Victims of Domestic Violence with Children Custody Proceedings

787.4 Frank WANG, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*
"Sorry, I Cannot Understand Your Fear!"-- Engaging Family Violence Workers in Institution Ethnography Study

17:30-19:20

788 Exploring Intersections: Institutional Ethnography, Environment, and Development

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Adriana SUAREZ-DELUCCHI, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*

Chair: Sarah MURRU, *KU Leuven, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

788.1 Donnet COMERFORD, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom*
Understanding the Macro and Micro Levels of Climate Agreements and Education from the Perspective of a Small Fijian Village.

788.2 Lauren EASTWOOD, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*
Troubling Disjunctures in the Everyday World of UN Environmental Policy Making

788.3 George SMITH, *Bristol University, United Kingdom*
Networks of Resistance: Tracing the Role of Fetishes in Indigenous/Community-Conserved Areas (ICCAs) in Senegal

788.4 Adriana SUAREZ-DELUCCHI, *University College London, United Kingdom*
Becoming a 'good Producer' in the Agri-Environmental Project Organisation

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

789 The Politics of Institutional Ethnography: Representation, Reflexivity, and Method**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M15 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Orla MURRAY, Imperial College London, United Kingdom**Chair:** Sophie HICKEY, N/A, Australia**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

789.1 Elizabeth ABLETT, University of Newcastle, United Kingdom
Doing Research with/for Complainers: The Challenges of Reflexivity, Representation and Accountability

789.2 Abass ISIAKA, University of East Anglia, United Kingdom
This Space Is Not Built for People like Us: Exploring the Textual Relations of Students with Disabilities in Higher Education

789.3 Nanke VERLOO, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Political Rigor. Reflections on Power and Positionality in Ethnographic Action-Research.

789.4 Sophie HICKEY, N/A, Australia and Cheryl ZURAWSKI, Independent Scholar, Canada
Institutional Ethnography (IE) As a Sociology with Indigenous Peoples

10:30-12:20

790 The Legacy of Dorothy E. Smith: What is the Future of IE?**Location:** M15 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Liza MCCOY, Department of Sociology, Canada**Chair:** Lauren EASTWOOD, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany**Panelists:** Li-Fang LIANG, National Dong-Hwa University, Taiwan; Sophie HICKEY, Charles Darwin University, Australia; Orla MURRAY, Durham University, United Kingdom and Colin HASTINGS, University of Waterloo, Canada**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:***Introductory Remarks**Panel Discussion**Discussion*

17:30-19:20

791 Institutional Ethnography (IE) in Healthcare and Healthcare Education**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M15 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Caroline CUPIT, University of Leicester, United Kingdom and Grainne KEARNEY, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom**Chair:** Lauren EASTWOOD, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany**AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

791.1 Meng-hsuan HSIEH, National Taipei University, Taiwan and Heng-hao CHANG, National Taipei University, Taiwan

Choices Under the Intertwining of Multiple Professionals: An Institutional Ethnographic Analysis of the Participation in Decision-Making of People with Psychosocial Disabilities

791.2 Courtney PETRUIK, University of Calgary, Canada
Re-Framing End-of-Life Care Using the Institutional Language of "Harm-Reduction" and "Trauma-Informed Practice" to Legitimize Under-Recognized Care Strategies for Patients Experiencing Houselessness

791.3 Po-Fang TSAI, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan; Fang Yih LIAW, Department of Family and Community Medicine, Tri-Service General Hospital, National Defense Medical Center, Taipei, Taiwan, Taiwan; Yaw Wen CHANG, Department of Family and Community Medicine, Tri-Service General Hospital, National Defense Medical Center, Taipei, Taiwan, Taiwan and Chih-Chia WANG, Department of Family and Community Medicine, Tri-Service General Hospital, National Defense Medical Center, Taipei, Taiwan, Taiwan
The Appear and Disappear of Doctor's Opinion Paper in Long-Term Care: An Institutional Ethnography of Pgy Training in Discharge Plan

791.4 Rhonda MCKELVIE, Midland Cancer Network, New Zealand
A Self-Fulfilling Institutional Circle: How Nurse Staffing Strategies Take up New Public Management Priorities

791.5 Dani JACOBSON, University of Toronto, Canada; Daniel GRACE, University of Toronto, Canada; Janice BODDY, University of Toronto, Canada and Gillian EINSTEIN, University of Toronto, Canada
Women with Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting's Emotional Health Work and Reproductive Health Care Experiences

791.6 Rachel WEBSTER, Massey University, New Zealand; Sue ADAMS, University of Auckland, New Zealand and Jenny CARRYER, Massey University, New Zealand
Managing Healthcare Professionals As Resources and Patients As a Commodity: A Look at NPM in Action in Aotearoa New Zealand Primary Care

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

792 Doing Institutional Ethnography: Issues and Innovations II

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M15 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Liza MCCOY, *Department of Sociology, Canada* and Frank WANG, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*

Chair: Sue ADAMS, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

792.1 Rachel WEBSTER, *Massey University, New Zealand* and Rhonda MCKELVIE, *Midland Cancer Network, New Zealand*
Personal Disjunctures: Moments of 'Capture' for Researchers Conducting Institutional Ethnography

792.2 Suzanne VAUGHAN, *Arizona State University, USA*
Reflections on Doing, Thinking, and Writing Institutional Ethnography

792.3 Kjeld HOGSBRO, *Aalborg University, Department of Sociology and Social Work, Denmark*
IE and Governmentality Studies of Power

792.4 Jeanine GALLAGHER, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Nerida SPINA, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
Getting the Data Right: An Exploration of Activism across the Institution in the Implementation of a National Funding Model for Students with Disability

WG08**Society and Emotions**

Program Coordinator: Helena FLAM, *University of Leipzig, Germany* and Mariana NOBILE, *FLACSO Argentina, Argentina*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-2 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part I

Committees: *WG08 Society and Emotions (Host); RC38 Biography and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-2.

15:30-17:20

JS-8 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part II

Committees: *RC38 Biography and Society (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-8.

17:30-19:20

793 The Imperial Passion of Race: The Case of Max Weber. Invited Speaker

Location: M1 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Helena FLAM, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

Chair: Xiaoying QI, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*

Discussant: Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

793.1 Jack BARBALET, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
The Imperial Passion of Race: The Case of Max Weber

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

794 Feeling States

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Leon REICHLER, *IDZ Jena, Germany*

Chair: Cristian DONA REVECO, *University of Nebraska at Omaha, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

794.1 Olga SIMONOVA, *Higher School of Economics (HSE), Russian Federation*
The Post-Soviet Nostalgia or Retrotopia: The Memory of Soviet Times and Fluctuations of Social Order

794.3 Simone BRITO, *Federal University of Paraíba, Brazil*
Imagining a New Country through Auditing: Morals and Emotions in Brazilian Anticorruption Bureaucracy

794.4 Lea BARO, *DeZIM, Germany*
On "Feeling Represented" - How Affect Can Extend Our Understanding of Representation in Institutional Contexts

794.5 John CASH, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Organising Competing Forms of Affect and Emotion - States As Subjects That Feel

794.6 Bin ZHOU, *The University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Populist Cultural Nationalism on Chinese Social Media - an Emotion Discourse Analysis

15:30-17:20

795 Images and Emotions

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Helena FLAM, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

Chair: Stéphane MOULIN, *Université de Montréal, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

795.1 Jen RINALDI, *Ontario Tech University, Canada*
What Survivors See: Creative Condemnations of Total Institutionalization

795.2 Sharyn ROACH ANLEU, *Flinders University, Australia* and George SARANTOULIAS, *Monash University, Australia*
Signs and Posters, Images and Icons: Governing Contagion through Instruction, Information and Emotion Regulation

795.3 Taoyi YANG, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Analyzing "Feeling-Better" Videos: Sensuous Scenes and Dramaturgy of Affect

795.4 Helena FLAM, *University of Leipzig, Germany*
Racist Disdain and Murderer-Emotion in the Video Clip of the National Socialist Underground

17:30-19:20

JS-52 Understanding the Sociological Interplay of Emotions

Committees: *WG06 Institutional Ethnography (Host); WG08 Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-52.

19:30-20:50

796 WG08 Business Meeting

Location: M13 (Crown)

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

797 Emotions, Senses and Artifacts Related to Physical Distance during the COVID-19 Pandemic/Emociones, Sentidos y Artefactos Relacionados Con La Distancia Física Durante La Pandemia De Covid19

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Olga Alejandra SABIDO RAMOS, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana, Mexico

Chair: Maximiliano MARENTES, Universidad Nacional de San Martín (UNSAM), Argentina

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

797.1 Anne-maree SAWYER, La Trobe University, Australia and Sara JAMES, La Trobe University, Australia
How to Navigate a Pandemic: Emotions, Selves, and Lifestyle Choices in the Australian Media

797.2 Isabelle BEULAYGUE, University Of Nebraska at Omaha, USA and Cristian DONA REVECO, University of Nebraska at Omaha, USA
"Somos Gente De Contacto" a Qualitative Exploration of Emotional Regulation Among Latinos in Nebraska during the Covid-19 Pandemic

797.3 Anya HOMMADOVA, Sam Houston State University, USA
Self-Expressions of Loneliness By LGBTQ+ Members on Social Media during COVID-19 Lockdowns

797.4 Mariana NOBILE, FLACSO Argentina, Argentina
Interferences in the Secondary School Pedagogical Bonds during the Pandemic

17:30-19:20

JS-78 Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part I

Committees: RC54 *The Body in the Social Sciences (Host)*; WG08 *Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-78.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

798 Quantitative (Sociological) Research on Emotions: Challenges and Possibilities

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Marina ARIZA, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico

Chair: Marina ARIZA, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

798.1 Gennaro IORIO, University of Salerno, Italy; Marco PALMIERI, Department of communication and social research, Sapienza, University of Rome, Italy and Silvia CATALDI, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
Investigating the Social Dimension of Love in Individuals and Institutions with Secondary Data: The World Love Index

798.2 Fiorella MANCINI, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico and Karina VIDEGAIN, UNAM, Mexico
"Counting" Emotions: Socio-Emotional Well-Being and Class Inequalities in Mexico.

798.3 Ignacio LLOVET, Universidad Nacional de Lujan, Argentina and Graciela DINARDI, Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero, Argentina
Older Adults, Gender, and Emotions: COVID-19 in Buenos Aires, Argentina

15:30-17:20

JS-102 Mobilizing Emotions by Social Movements and in Contemporary Humanitarian Effort

Committees: WG08 *Society and Emotions (Host)*; RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

See Joint Session Details for JS-102.

17:30-19:20

JS-107 Education, Solidarity and Engagement: The Study of Morals and Emotions in Altruistic Educational Experiences

Committees: RC04 *Sociology of Education (Host)*; WG08 *Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-107.

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

799 Intersectional Perspectives on Love

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany and Ina SCHAUM, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany

Chair: Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, Institute for Social Research Frankfurt, Germany

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

799.1 Rahil ROODSAZ, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Enduring Midlife Love: Temporal Qualities and Possibilities

799.2 Kailing XIE, University of Birmingham, United Kingdom and Marius MEINHOF, Bielefeld University, Germany
The Partner, the Parents, the Nation – the Negotiation of Chineseness in Discourses on "Love" in Contemporary China

799.3 Maximiliano MARENTES, Universidad Nacional de San Martín (UNSAM), Argentina
The Love Stories Approach. Theoretical and Methodological Concerns about Studying Actually Existing Love Among Argentinean Gay Men

799.4 Hugo RIBADEAU DUMAS, *Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales (EHESS), France*
"Rahul, What Is Friendship?" - (Re)Defining Emotional Bonds Outside Kinship in Urbanising India

10:30-12:20

JS-120 Bodies, Emotions and Social Interaction. Part II

Committees: RC54 *The Body in the Social Sciences (Host)*; WG08 *Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-120.

15:30-17:20

JS-131 Emotions and Environmental Activism

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements (Host)*; WG08 *Society and Emotions*

See Joint Session Details for JS-131.

17:30-19:20

800 Social Justice and Emotions

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Cécile VAN DE VELDE, *Université de Montréal, Canada* and Stéphane MOULIN, *Université de Montréal, Canada*

Chair: Maximiliano MARENTES, *Universidad Nacional de San Martín (UNSAM), Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

800.1 Warren FRANCISCO, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
The Role of Emotions in Social Movement Activities in the Philippines: The Case of the Cordillera Peoples Alliance

800.2 Sighard NECKEL, *University of Hamburg, Germany*
Awareness: Paradoxes of an Emotion Program

800.3 Eunike PIWONI, *Universität Passau, Germany*
"Where Are You from?" the Affective and Emotional Dimensions of Being Confronted with an Othering Question

800.4 Stéphane MOULIN, *Université de Montréal, Canada*
Perception of Unfairness and Emotions at Work. a Comparative Analysis of Workers in Restaurants and Universities

800.5 Cécile VAN DE VELDE, *Université de Montréal, Canada*
Inequality, Injustice... Anger. Dynamics of Revolt Among Young Adults.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

801 Emotions, Subjectivities, and Sociodynamics of Inequalities | Emociones, Subjetividades y Sociodinámicas De Las Desigualdades

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Mariana NOBILE, *FLACSO Argentina - CONICET / FaHCE - UNLP, Argentina*

Chair: Stéphane MOULIN, *Université de Montréal, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

801.1 Sarah MCCOOK, *RMIT University, Australia*
"You Have to Make a Choice": Affective Tensions in Australian Men's Negotiation of Normative Masculinity and Social Change

801.2 Rebecca LEVY-GUILLAIN, *Centre for Research on social InequalityS. Sciences Po Paris, France*
The Production of Gender Inequalities in the Experience and Management of Emotions before Sex

801.3 Roberta Priscila CEDILLO HERNANDEZ, *UNAM, Mexico*
Gender on a Sensory-Affective Key. Challenges from Its Theoretical Conceptualization

801.4 Ruyue LIU, *City, University of London, United Kingdom*
Life Coach Online? the Rise of the Life Advice Influencer and the Self-Branding Practice in (post)Feminist Culture

801.5 Jesus DE LA PENA RODRIGUEZ, *Universidad de Granada, Spain*
Joy, Sadness, Anger, Fear and Inequality in the Settlement Process of Honduran Immigrants in Mexico City and Madrid.

12:30-14:20

802 Hatred Also Loves: Gender and Emotions in Today's Political Landscape

Language: English, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Begonya ENGUIX GRAU, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain*; Alexandre PICHEL-VAZQUEZ, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain* and Gabriela VERGARA, *CONICET, Argentina*

Chair: Begonya ENGUIX GRAU, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

802.1 Alba POLO-ARTAL, *Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia UNED, Spain*
Del Discurso De #Fronterasseguras e #Invasióninmigratoria Al #Nohablesenminombre y #Laviolencianotienesexo: El Papel De La Raza y Del Género En La Derecha Radical Española.

802.2 Alexandre PICHEL-VAZQUEZ, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Spain*
'a "Gender Politics" to Rule Them All': Antifeminist Political Sentimentality and the International Connections of the Spanish Far Right

802.3 Pedro LISDERO, CIECS (CONICET y UNC) / UNVM / CIES, Argentina
Trabajo Digital, Emociones y Género: Sentidos Del Trabajo, Procesos De Re-Mercantilización y Construcción De Subjetividades a Partir De Las Experiencias De Mujeres Trabajadores De “Delivery Por Plataforma” En Argentina

14:30-16:20

803 Emotions in Poverty Contexts

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Angelica DE SENA, UNLAM-UBA-CIES, Argentina; Rebeca CENA, CCONFINES-CONICET, Argentina and Andrea DETTANO, CONICET, Argentina

Chair: Andrea DETTANO, CONICET, Argentina

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

803.1 Giovanna TRUDA, University of Salerno, Italy
Poverty: Beliefs, Emotions and Rights

803.2 Maria Teresa MARTIN PALOMO, University of Almería, Spain and María Pia VENTURIELLO, Instituto Gino Germani (F.Ciencias Sociales - UBA)/Conicet, Argentina
Prácticas De Cuidado y Descuidos En Un Mundo Vulnerable: Emociones, Afectos y Dilemas En Los Tecnocuidados

Thematic Groups

TG03

Human Rights and Global

Justice

Program Coordinator: Loretta BASS, *Univ of Oklahoma, United States*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

JS-13 Securitizing the State? the Challenges of Illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology (Host)*; RC09 *Social Transformations and Sociology of Development* RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy* RC20 *Comparative Sociology* RC56 *Historical Sociology and TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice*

See Joint Session Details for JS-13.

17:30-19:20

JS-18 Collaborative Research I: Critical Reflections on Research Ethics and Methodological Practices

Committees: TG03 *Human Rights and Global Justice (Host)*; RC03 *Community Research*

See Joint Session Details for JS-18.

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-26 Human Dimensions of Development and Sustainable Development Goals

Committees: TG03 *Human Rights and Global Justice (Host)*; RC24 *Environment and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-26.

10:30-12:20

804 Marginalization, Wellbeing, and Justice

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Lukasz KRZYZOWSKI, *The University of Western Australia, Australia*

Chair: Brent SHEA, *Sweet Briar College, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

804.1 Maiara CORREA, *PhD student at University of Sao Paulo, Brazil*

Derechos Humanos y Garantías: ¿Cómo Llega La Remisión De Penas Al Sur?

804.2 Naresh KUMAR, *Central University of Gujarat, India*
Existing Multiple Deprivations and Covid-19 Pandemic: An Empirical Perspective of Marginalized in-Migrants Cycle Rickshaw Pullers in Delhi

804.3 Sudha KHOKATE, *Bangalore University, India*
The Rise in Domestic Violence during Covid-19: a Global and Human Rights Concern.

804.4 Brent SHEA, *Sweet Briar College, USA*
Social Justice and Ongoing Healthcare Financialization

804.5 Spyros GANGAS, *DEREE-The American College of Greece, Greece*
Beyond Abstract Universalism and Debilitating Relativism: Human Rights As Capabilities. Extending the Dialogue.

15:30-17:20

805 Gender, Sexuality, and Social Justice

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Louise BAUMANN, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Chair: Ahmed HAMILA, *University of Montreal, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

805.1 Suprava KHUNTIA, *Vashi, India*
Transgender and Human Rights: A Study in Mumbai City

805.2 Nidhi MISHRA, *Mahila Mahavidyalaya BHU, Varanasi, India*
Human Rights and Invisibility of Differently Abled Women: Marriage, Family and Reproductive Rights

805.3 Kashmira KHANAM, *Ph.D. Research Scholar Dept of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Haryana & ICSSR Doctoral Research Fellow, India*
Human Rights Violations in Workplace Against Transgender People in Assam, India

805.4 Saskia RAVESLOOT, *Sciences Po - Paris School of International Affairs, Belgium*
The Universal Periodic Review : Supporting the Ban on Intersex Genital Mutilation?

805.5 Ahmed HAMILA, *University of Montreal, Canada*;
Edward Ou Jin LEE, *University of Montreal, Canada* and
Roxane CARON, *University of Montreal, Canada*
Beyond the Human Rights Approach: Migrants with Diverse Sogje Navigating Structural Oppression

19:30-20:50

806 TG03 Business Meeting

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

807 Human Dimensions of Sustainable Development

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Apostolos PAPAPOPOULOS, *Harokopio University of Athens, Greece* and Loukia-Maria FRATSEA, *European Sociological Association (ESA), France*

Chair: Ahmed HAMILA, *University of Montreal, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

807.1 Vilde WINGE, *University of South-Eastern Norway, Norway*
Migration, Technology, and Control: A Critical Discourse Analysis Concerning Data Gathering and Information Sharing of Third-Country Nationals

807.2 Alessia MARZANO, *University of South-Eastern Norway (USN), Norway*
The Poietic Potentialities of Indigenous Creative Practices in Decolonizing the Concept(s) of Indigeneity

807.3 Ayumi SUGIMOTO, *Akita International University, Japan*
Market Economy for Non-Market Value: A Community Development Project in a Mountainous Area of Japan

807.4 Sanae YAMAMOTO, *Tokoha University, Japan*
Sustainable Development Goals and Social Transitions in Terraced Landscapes - a Case Study of Silk Road Area in China-

10:30-12:20

808 Status, Discourse, and Authoritarianism

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Namita GUPTA, *Panjab University, India*

Chair: Eric BRANDAO, *Rio de Janeiro State Court of Justice, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

808.1 Alexander KONDAKOV, *University College Dublin, Ireland*
Anti-Queer Hate Crime and the Rise of Authoritarianism (the Russian case)

808.2 Ding-yi LAI, *National Chung Cheng University, Taiwan*;
Wen-Cheng LIN, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan* and
Wen-chin WU, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
Aiding Repression: The Effects of Chinese Communication Aid on Media Freedom

808.3 Binoyjyoti DAS, *International Institute of Cosmic Sciences, India*
Dr B.R.Ambedkar and His Concept of Democracy

808.4 Eric BRANDAO, *Rio de Janeiro State Court of Justice, Brazil*
Inequalities and Access to Justice: The Realization of Human Dignity through Itinerant Justice

808.5 Rosario FIGARI LAYUS, *Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany* and Narda HENRIQUEZ, *Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú, Peru*
Dealing with the Past? a Critical Gender Perspective on Current Transitional Justice and Human Rights Policies in Post Conflict Contexts in Latin America: Pending Challenges and Questions

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

809 Global Human Rights and Children

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Yvonne VISSING, *Salem State University, USA*

Chair: Eric BRANDAO, *Rio de Janeiro State Court of Justice, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

809.1 Katie WRIGHT, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Reclaiming Child Rights: Victim-Survivor Activism Against Institutional Child Abuse

809.2 Jingxian WANG, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*
How the Human Respect Lost in Producing the 'Black Children' (heihaizi) Under the One-Child Policy in China

809.3 Sumant KUMAR, *Alliance University, India*
Future of Refugee Children in the World

809.4 Loretta BASS, *Univ of Oklahoma, USA* and Oyindamola OKUWA, *University of Oklahoma, Nigeria*
Migration, Racial-Ethnic Discrimination, and Mental Health Outcomes for U.S. Adolescents

15:30-17:20

810 Justice Systems, Reform, and Human Rights

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Ana Paula DELGADO, *Tribunal de Justiça do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Cristina GAULIA, *Escola da Magistratura do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (EMERJ), Brazil*

Discussant: Ana Paula DELGADO, *Tribunal de Justiça do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

810.1 Niborna HAZARIKA, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Constructing India's Northeast: A Study of Politics of Identity

810.2 Mauricio PADRON-INNAMORATO, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
Determinantes Del Acceso a La Justicia En El Ámbito Laboral Desde Una Aproximación Cuantitativa. Un Análisis Del Caso Mexicano

17:30-19:20

JS-106 Climate Change, Poverty and Inequality in Globalizing World: Changing Socio-Economic, Environmental Fabric of Human Settlements, Neglect of Human Rights and Marginalization of the Poor

Committees: WG05 *Famine and Society (Host)*; TG03 *Human Rights and Global Justice*

See Joint Session Details for JS-106.

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

811 Locating Human Rights in Globalized World

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Deepti KAUSHIK, *Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India* and Bhup SINGH, *Maharshi Dayanand University, India*

Chair: Mahesh SHUKLA, *Govt. TRS College For Excellence, Rewa (M.P.) India 486001, India*

Co-Chair: Ajailiu NIUMAI, *Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion & Inclusive Policy, University of Hyderabad, India*

Panelists: Manmeet KAUR, *Punjabi University, India* and Durgesh TRIPATHI, *Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGSIPU), India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

811.1 Ronald ANGEL, *University of Texas at Austin, USA* and Veronica MONTES DE OCA ZAVALA, *Instituto de Investigaciones Sociales, Mexico*
Non-Contributory Pensions As Human Rights in Mexico

811.2 Deepti KAUSHIK, *Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India*
Human Rights of Marginalised Sections in India

811.3 Ranjit SINGH, *Guru Nanak Dev University, India* and Rekha SUMAN, *UJLS AVA LODGE SHIMLA -4(HP) India, India*
Human Rights: A Need for Social Justice

811.4 Ritu SHARMA, *University of Delhi, India*
Disproportionate Rights and Inequalities of Labour in India

15:30-17:20

812 Pluriversal Approaches to Human Rights and Sdg's

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Gabriela MEZZANOTTI, *University of South-Eastern Norway, Norway* and Alyssa Marie KVALVAAG, *Nord University, Norway*

Chairs: Gabriela MEZZANOTTI, *University of South-Eastern Norway, Norway* and Alyssa Marie KVALVAAG, *Nord University, Norway*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

812.1 Paulina GARCÍA-DEL MORAL, *Department of Sociology & Anthropology, University of Guelph, Canada*
Missing and Murdered Indigenous Women and Girls in Canada and Indigenous Women's Human Rights Activism

812.2 Malini BALAMAYURAN, *Department of Political Science, Faculty of Arts, University of Peradeniya, Kandy, Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka*
Sri Lanka's Road to Aragalaya: An Assessment

812.3 Malek BEN ACHOUR, *Social science and cultural studies, Norway*
Exploring the Potential of Migration in Reducing Inequalities within and Among Countries

17:30-19:20

813 Rising Authoritarianism and Perspectives on Democracy in Globalized World**Location:** 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Bhup SINGH, *Maharshi Dayanand University, India* and Binoyjyoti DAS, *SSS/CSSS, JNU New Delhi, India***Chair:** Manish K. VERMA, *Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India***Co-Chair:** Durgesh TRIPATHI, *Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGSIPU), India***Panelist:** Bali BAHADUR, *Central University of Punjab, India***Discussant:** Jagsir SINGH, *Bebe Nanaki University College, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

813.1 Krunoslav NIKODEM, *University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Croatia* and Tijana TRAKO POLJAK, *University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Croatia*
Authoritarianism and Attitudes Toward the Environment in Rural and Urban Central Europe: A Cross-National Analysis of the Three Waves of EVS Data

813.2 Jhoner PERDOMO, *Central University of Venezuela. Institute of Economic and Social Research, Venezuela*
The Sustainable Wellbeing Approach and the Right of Future Generations to Counteract the Global Risk of Ecological Authoritarianism.

813.3 Stefani NUGROHO, *Atma Jaya Catholic University of Indonesia, Indonesia*
Repressions of Academic Freedom in Post-Authoritarian Indonesia

813.4 Joshua KLEIN, *Iona University, USA*; Daniel PATTEN, *Purdue University, USA*; Puneet KAUR, *Iona University, USA*; Myles CHIARELLO, *Iona University, USA*; Trent CRESPO, *Iona University, USA*; Rachele LACROIX, *Iona University, USA* and Jason PETERMANN, *Iona University, USA*
How Authoritarianism Legitimizes Imperialism

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

814 Perspectives on Mass Migration, Refugees, and Prisoners of War**Location:** 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizer:** Sumant KUMAR, *Alliance University, India***Chair:** Ivana RUIZ-ESTRAMIL, *Centre for Social Studies University of Coimbra - Institute for International Cooperation and Development Studies University of the Basque Country, Portugal***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

814.1 Ivana RUIZ-ESTRAMIL, *Centre for Social Studies University of Coimbra - Institute for International Cooperation and Development Studies University of the Basque Country, Portugal*
International Protection in the European Union in the Face of New Scenarios of Lack of Protection

814.2 Sladana ADAMOVIĆ, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Between Sexual and Migration Politics: Queer Migrants from Serbia and Bosnia-Herzegovina Living in Austria

814.3 Sumant KUMAR, *Alliance University, India*
Issues and Challenges of Migrant Worker's Social Security in Unorganised Sector in India

814.4 Carlos Alberto SILVA, *Universidade Federal Fluminense, Brazil*
Discussing Perspectives about Vulnerability and Prisoners of War: American Civil War and Andersonville

10:30-12:20

815 Precarious Workers, Precarious Residents and Authoritarian Politics**Location:** 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session Organizers:** Sayamol CHAROENRATANA, *Human Security and Equity Research Unit, Social Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand* and Cholnapa ANUKUL, *Foundation of Just Society Network, Thailand***Chair:** Ngamjahao KIPGEN, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:**

815.1 Cholnapa ANUKUL, *Public Sociological Association (Thailand), Thailand* and Sayamol CHAROENRATANA, *Human Security and Equity Research Unit, Social Research Institute, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand*
Visibility Politics of Urban Food Workers and Their Precariousness

815.2 Ngamjahao KIPGEN, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India*
Biodiversity Conservation, Livelihoods and Traditional Ecological Knowledge of the Kuki People

815.3 Chika SHINOHARA, *Momoyama Gakuin University, Japan*; Kumiko TSUCHIDA, *Komazawa University, Japan*; Sanae SUGAWARA, *Tohoku Gakuin University, Japan*; Takako KAWAI, *St. Andrew's University, Japan* and Ni Nengah SUARTINI, *Ganesha University of Education, Indonesia*
Certified Vs. Unskilled Migrant Care Workers: Work-Family Decisions and Rights

815.4 Deepali WIGHE, *Department of Sociology, Goethe University, Frankfurt, Germany, Germany*
Human Rights Issue from a Global Justice Perspective: A Case of De-Notified, Nomadic and Semi-Nomadic Tribes in India

12:30-14:20

816 Rising Authoritarianism and Challenges before Marginalized Communities in Globalized World

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Binoyjyoti DAS, SSS/CSSS, JNU New Delhi, India

Chair: Shweta PRASAD, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India

Co-Chair: Rajni BALA, Baring Union Christian College, Batala, India

Panelists: Deepti KAUSHIK, Ismail National Mahila PG College Budhana Gate, India; Bhup SINGH, Maharshi Dayanand University, India and Anupam BAHRI, Panjab University, India

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

816.1 Bhup SINGH, Maharshi Dayanand University, India
Marginalisation of Soldiers of Sanitation : A Human Right Concern

816.2 Jagsir SINGH, Bebe Nanaki University College, India; Lovepreet SINGH, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, India, India and Ramanjeet KAUR, Social Security, Women and Child Development Department, Government of Punjab, India
Educational Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Punjab: Prospects and Challenges

816.3 Manmeet KAUR, Punjabi University, India
Marginalized Community and Economic Justice

816.4 Unaloam CHANRUNGMANEKUL, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Thailand
Fear and Power: A Comparative Study of Myanmar and Thailand in Reaction to Documentary As Social Practice for Advocating Human Rights

TG04

Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty

Program Coordinator: Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

817 Risks, Catastrophes and Emancipation: Decolonizing Risk Sociology

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy* and Fabio D'ANDREA, *University of Perugia, Italy*

Chair: Aiste BALZEKIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

817.1 Bert DE GRAAFF, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*; Sabrina RAHMAWAN-HUIZENGA, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*; Hester VAN DE BOVENKAMP, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands* and Roland BAL, *Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands*
Framing the COVID-19 Pandemic: Multiplying 'Crisis' in Dutch Healthcare amidst High Uncertainties

817.2 John CASH, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Metamorphosis, Psychoanalysis and "the Art of Doubt"

817.3 Jeremy SIMPSON, *National Library of Australia, Australia*
Decolonising the Risk Society through the Case of Afghanistan: Catastrophe, Class and the Afghan Experience of Risk

817.4 Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy* and Giuseppe RICOTTA, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*
Risk, Cosmopolitanism and Epistemologies of the South

17:30-19:20

818 Theorizing Risk and Uncertainty. Part I

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Charlotte FABIANSOON, *Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: Charlotte FABIANSOON, *Victoria University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

818.1 Agnieszka KWIATKOWSKA, *Uniwersytet SWPS, Poland*; Jowita RADZINSKA, *SWPS University, Poland* and Agnieszka GOLINSKA, *SWPS University, Poland*
Settling in Uncertainty and Risk: Polish Responses to the COVID-19 Pandemic and the War in Ukraine

818.2 Helena JERONIMO, *ISEG School of Economics and Management, Universidade de Lisboa & CSG/Advance, Portugal*
Riscophrenia: The Risk Fallacy and the Repression of Uncertainty

818.3 Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Navigating Risk and Uncertainty – a New Perspective?

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

819 Mixed Themes: Methods/Methodologies - (voluntary) Risk-Taking

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*

Chair: Anna OLOFSSON, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

819.1 Aiste BALZEKIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*
Spatial Analysis of Risk Perception: Methodological Challenges and Analytical Strategies

819.2 Kirill GAVRILOV, *Independent researcher, Russian Federation*
The Perception of Abstract 'War' in Russia: The Psychometric Paradigm Approach

819.3 Isabela PINHO, *Universidade Federal de São Carlos, Brazil*; Gabriel PATRIARCA, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil* and Anna clara SOARES, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Taking and Avoiding Risks: Perceptions and Strategies in the Circulation of Cocaine through the Port of Santos, Brazil

819.4 Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Risk Taking and Social Recognition

15:30-17:20

820 Inequality, Power, and Intersectional Perspectives on Risk I

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Anna OLOFSSON, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*

Chair: Audrone TELESIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

820.1 Terra MANCA, *University of Alberta, Canada*; Laura AYLSWORTH, *University of Alberta, Canada*; S Michelle DRIEDGER, *University of Manitoba, Canada* and Shannon E MACDONALD, *University of Alberta, Canada*
"the People Who Care ... Are Vaccinated": An Intersectional Analysis of Inequalities in Responsibility to Prevent COVID-19

820.2 Joana MOSTAFA, *State University of Campinas (UNICAMP), Brazil*
The Risks of Sharing Suffering in a Context of Extreme Inequality and Violence amidst Brazilian Homeless Population

820.3 Anna OLOFSSON, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*; Katarina GIRITLI NYGREN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden* and Susanna OHMAN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden*
Intersectional Analysis of Risk

17:30-19:20

821 Inequality, Power, and Intersectional Perspectives on Risk II**Location:** M6 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Anna OLOFSSON, *RCR Mid Sweden University, Sweden*; Susanna OHMAN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden* and Katarina GIRITLI NYGREN, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden***Chair:** Anna OLOFSSON, *Mid Sweden University, Sweden***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****821.2** Danielle NEMBHARD, *James Cook University, Australia*
Risk Perception, Intersectionality and Climate (Mal)
Adaptation: Assisted Ecosystem Restoration of the Great Barrier Reef**821.3** Audrone TELESIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania* and Aiste BALZEKIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*
The Effects of Structural Vulnerabilities on Climate Change Risk Perception: International and Historical Comparative Perspective**Wednesday 28 June**

08:30-10:20

JS-60 Materiality, Brutality and Risk: Decolonial Readings of the Twin Climate and Energy Crisis**Committees:** *RC24 Environment and Society (Host); TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-60.

10:30-12:20

822 The Democratization of Risk and Prevention in a Sociological Perspective**Location:** M6 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Evelyne BAILLERGEAU, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Patrick BROWN, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands***Chair:** Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****822.1** Paolo CRIVELLARI, *IUT, University Of Toulouse III, France*
Industrial Risk Prevention between (a lot of) Technocracy and (little) Democracy**822.2** Evelyne BAILLERGEAU, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Gerlieke VELTKAMP, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands*
Participatory Health Promotion: An Advanced Form of Democratized Prevention?**822.3** Lavinia BIFULCO, *University of Milano Bicocca, Italy* and Lorenza DODI, *Milano Bicocca, Italy*
Risk, Uncertainty and Health Emergencies: What Can (qualitative) Social Research Do?**822.4** Terra MANCA, *University of Alberta, Canada*
"They Weren't Really Sure What to Do with Pregnant Clients:" a Qualitative Investigation of Discourses about Disease Risks and Uncertainties about Vaccination

15:30-17:20

JS-68 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part I**Committees:** *RC17 Sociology of Organization (Host); RC24 Environment and Society RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food and TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-68.

17:30-19:20

JS-77 Accountability and Sustainable Transitions: Toward an Integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part II**Committees:** *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC17 Sociology of Organization RC24 Environment and Society and RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

See Joint Session Details for JS-77.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

823 Emotions, Trust, Hope and Other Approaches of Managing Uncertainty and Non-Knowledge. Part I**Location:** M6 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia***Chair:** Chabel KHAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****823.1** Francisco Javier LOAISA, *University of Alicante, Spain* and Diana JARENO RUIZ, *Universidad de Alicante, Spain*
Who Trusts Science? a Scoping Review**823.2** David DUENAS-CID, *Gdansk University of Technology, Poland*
Trust, Distrust and Electoral Technologies: Revisiting the Electronic Voting Machines Failure in the Netherlands 2006-07**823.3** William BRADLEY, *Ryukoku University, Japan*
"We Wear Our Masks for More Than Protection": Analysis of the Post-Pandemic Easing of Advisories Related to Covid-19 in Japan**823.4** Gentaro KATO, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan*
Self-Restraint As a Measure Against COVID-19 in Japan: From the Perspective of Risk and Morality

10:30-12:20

824 Emotions, Trust, Hope and Other Approaches of Managing Uncertainty and Non-Knowledge. Part II**Location:** M6 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Patrick BROWN, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands***Chair:** Chabel KHAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

824.1 Rodrigo CARDOSO GONZALEZ, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*
Perception and Meanings of Risk in Digital Practices Among Young People from Mexico City

824.2 Elsie FOEKEN, *Monash University, Australia*
Temporal Risk Management in the Gig Economy: Agentic Responses to Uncertainty and Irregularity

824.3 Alice NAH, *Durham University, United Kingdom*
Navigating Risk and Uncertainty in High-Risk Activism: 'Ethical-Emotional Capture' and Its (dis)Contents

824.4 Jennifer BOSEN, *RWTH Aachen University, Germany*
Uncertain Futures - Constructions of Hope and Control By Adolescent Girls Under Lockdown

824.5 Stefanie PLAGE, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Cameron PARSELL, *The University of Queensland, Australia*; Rose-marie STAMBE, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Ella KUSKOFF, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Climbing, Stalling, Falling: How People Experiencing Housing Instability Anticipate Their Futures

17:30-19:20

JS-111 The Language of Risk. Part I

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-111.

19:30-20:50

825 TG04 Business Meeting

Location: M6 (Crown)

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

JS-126 Mental Health and Risk

Committees: *RC49 Mental Health and Illness (Host); TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

See Joint Session Details for JS-126.

15:30-17:20

826 Theorizing Risk and Uncertainty. Part II

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Charlotte FABIANSOON, *College of Arts & Education, Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: Charlotte FABIANSOON, *Victoria University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

826.1 Fabio D'ANDREA, *University of Perugia, Italy*
Better Get Ready. a Long-Term Perspective on Beck's Metamorphosis

826.2 Sojin LEE, *Yonsei university, Republic of Korea*
Suicidal Thought As a Gendered Ontological Anxiety Caused By Postmodernity: Focused on Korean Women Born after 1990

826.3 Hannah SOONG, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Sue NICHOLS, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Karen DOOLEY, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
Contesting the Framing of Digital Risk in Children's Social Life

Saturday 1 July

08:30-10:20

827 Risk and Space: Risk Perception and Risk Normalization

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Aiste BALZEKIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*

Chair: Aiste BALZEKIENE, *Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

827.1 Ikechukwu UMEJESI, *UNIVERSITY OF FORT HARE, EAST LONDON CAMPUS, SOUTH AFRICA, South Africa* and Tafadzwa MAMBIRAVANA, *Department of Sociology, University of Fort Hare, East London Campus, South Africa, South Africa*
When Development 'Becomes a Threat' to Society: An Examination of Risk Perceptions and Social Vulnerability in the N2 Toll Road Project in South Africa's Wild Coast Region

827.2 Àlex BOSO, *Ciemat, Spain*; Boris ÁLVAREZ, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile*; Álvaro HOFFLINGER, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile* and Sebastian IBARRA, *Universidad de Aysén, Chile*
Unveiling Spatial Patterns of Exposure and Risk Perception to Air Pollution: Lessons Learned from Emerging Studies

827.3 Krzysztof MACZKA, *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland*; Daria PANIOTOVA, *Faculty of Psychology and Cognitive Science, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland*; Klaudia RODZIEJCZAK, *Faculty of Psychology and Cognitive Science, Poland* and Maciej MILEWICZ, *Faculty of Sociology, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland*
Environmental Anxieties and Coping Strategies - Comparative Study of Poland, Ukraine and Hungary

827.4 Mika KARI, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland*; Niina KIVILUOMA, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland*; Matti KOJO, *LUT University School of Engineering Science/Social Sciences, Finland*; Markku LEHTONEN, *Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain*; Tapio LITMANEN, *University of Jyväskylä, Finland* and Hanna-mari HUSU, *LUT University, School of Engineering Science/Social Science, Finland*
Small Modular Reactors and the Spatial Distribution of Risk: Local Perceptions on the Novel Decentralised Model of Nuclear Energy Expansion in Canada and Finland

14:30-16:20

JS-153 The Language of Risk. Part II

Committees: *TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty (Host); RC25 Language and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-153.

TG07

Senses and Society

Program Coordinator: Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*; Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Mark PATERSON, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

828 The Political Life of Sensation

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

828.1 Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
The Contours of Sensory Jurisprudence and Urban Sanitation

828.2 Jean DURUZ, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Returning to Marseille: Sensing a Different Geo-Political Map of Citizenship and Belonging

828.3 Clara CIRDAN, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*
Sense and (museum) Sensibilities. a Study on Affective Practices in Museums.

828.4 Sneha ANNAVARAPU, *Assistant Professor of Sociology, Singapore*
A Bumpy Road to Development: The Everyday Politics of Potholes in Hyderabad, India

Tuesday 27 June

15:30-17:20

829 Excursions in Sensory Studies: Teaching, Doing, Writing

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

829.1 Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
On Resonance and the Sensory: Teaching and Pedagogical Interventions

829.2 Catherine EARL, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*
Sensing the Field: Exercising Sensory Ethnography As a Learning By Doing Approach in Graduate Fieldwork Training

829.3 Nicholas COPE, *RMIT University Vietnam, Vietnam*
Sarva Mangalam! an Exemplar of Practice-Based Research in the Academy

Wednesday 28 June

830 The Sense of Data and the Data of Sense: Bodies, Technologies, Spaces

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Mark PATERSON, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*

Chair: Catherine EARL, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

830.1 Andrea BRIGHENTI, *University of Trento, Italy, Italy* and Andrea PAVONI, *ISCTE-IUL, Portugal*
Atmiculture and New Algorithmic Urban Mobilities

830.2 Mark PATERSON, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*
The Future of Touch in Human-Robot Interactions

830.3 Alexia MADDOX, *RMIT University, Australia*; Naomi SMITH, *University of the Sunshine Coast, Australia*; Jacinthe FLORE, *RMIT University, Australia* and Luke HEEMSBERGEN, *Deakin University, Australia*
Senses of/in the City: A Speculative and Conceptual Exploration of Sensory Spaces of Play in the Digital City

830.4 Ben LYALL, *Monash University, Australia*
Self-Tracking and Cyberattacking: Social Media Reactions to Garmin's Ransom

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

831 Translating Sensory Experience

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Catherine EARL, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*; Andrew STIFF, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam* and Thierry BERNARD, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*

Chair: Mark PATERSON, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

831.2 Andrew STIFF, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*
Sensory Focused Moving Image Practice: Methods for Challenging an Agenda of Rapid Modernisation in Hcmc

831.3 Catherine EARL, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam*
Writing Sensations: A Practice Based Approach to Unsettling Anthropology and Ethnographic Writing

19:30-20:50

832 TG07 Business Meeting**Location:** M5 (Crown)**Session Organizer:** Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore***Chair:** Kelvin LOW, *National University of Singapore, Singapore***833.3** Ayesha MUALLA, *Shiv Nadar University, India*
Writing a Multisensorial Field**833.4** Ayaka YOSHIMIZU, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Saori HOSHI, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Transmediating Race and Senses through Subtitling in Translanguaging Classroom**Friday 30 June**

10:30-12:20

833 Experiencing Silence and Expanded Time; Other Sensory Pathways and Knowledge**Language:** English, French, Spanish**Location:** M5 (Crown)**Session Organizers:** Florence FIGOLS, *Concordia University, Canada* and RITA CASTRO, *University of Brasília, Brazil***Chair:** Andrew STIFF, *RMIT Vietnam, Vietnam***AUTHORS AND PAPERS:****833.1** Sarah MASLEN, *University of Canberra, Australia*
"Listening" As a Metaphor for Synesthetic Attention**833.2** Vicki KELLEHER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Research Outside of Time: Contacting Our inside World through Poetry

TG09

Sociological Teaching

Program Coordinator: Annette TEZLI, *University of Calgary, Canada* and Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*

Monday 26 June

15:30-17:20

834 Decolonising the Curriculum: Teaching and Pedagogical Interventions in Sociology

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*

Chair: Achla TANDON, *Hindu college, Department of Sociology, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

834.1 Noorman ABDULLAH, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
"Decolonising" Sociology through Teaching and Unlearning: Implications and Interventions

834.2 Ali KASSEM, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
On the Hollowing of Decolonisation and Possibilities for Teaching Otherwise

834.3 Khairul CHOWDHURY, *University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*
State of Sociology in Bangladesh: Decolonizing Curriculum and Knowledge

834.4 Miriam TRZECIAK, *BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany* and Franziska MÜLLER, *University of Hamburg, Germany*
Decolonial City Walks and Feminist Re-Negotiation of Urban Space As Alternative Approaches to Teaching: Unveiling Different Histories Beyond the Coloniality of Gender

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

835 Teaching then and Now: Transitions in Sociological Pedagogy

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Jake SALLAWAY-COSTELLO, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*

Chair: Jake SALLAWAY-COSTELLO, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

835.1 Annette TEZLI, *University of Calgary, Canada* and Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Hybrid Sociology Pedagogy As Post-Pandemic Adaptation

835.2 Sharmila RAMA, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa* and Ruth HOSKINS, *University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*

Teaching the Sociology Honours Research Module then and Now: Reflecting on Innovative Curriculum (Re)Design and Optimizing the Use of Technology to Enhance Student Engagement and Success

835.3 Oral ROBINSON, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Alexander WILSON, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Reconceptualizing Open Pedagogy in the Post-Pandemic Classroom to Meet Transformative Goals

Wednesday 28 June

08:30-10:20

836 Addressing Rising Authoritarianism through Sociological Teaching

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Annette TEZLI, *University of Calgary, Canada*

Chair: Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

836.1 Ling TANG, *Academy of Film, Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong* and Ren LIFEIYANG, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Public Sociology in Authoritarian China: Collaborative Auto-Ethnography about an Internet Academic Talk Show on Weibo

836.2 Amurabi OLIVEIRA, *Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil*
Teaching Sociology and "School without Party" in Brazil

836.3 Jake SALLAWAY-COSTELLO, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*
Disrupting Colonialities of Knowledge: Learning and Teaching Sociology through Immersion in Social Food Movements

836.4 Achla TANDON, *Hindu college, Department of Sociology, India*
Mediating Visibility Postulates

836.5 Denise HUMPHREYS, *University of Manitoba, Canada*
Addressing Settler Colonialism within Genocide Education in North American Post-Secondary Educational Institutions

19:30-20:50

837 TG09 Business Meeting

Location: M5 (Crown)

Thursday 29 June

17:30-19:20

838 Global Reach for Your Teaching Research and Artifacts: How to Publish in the ISA's 'Sociological Teaching' Online Platforms

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Annette TEZLI, *University of Calgary, Canada*

Chairs: Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Annette TEZLI, *University of Calgary, Canada*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

Workshop

Friday 30 June

15:30-17:20

839 Strategies for Making Sociology Locally and Globally Relevant for Students

Location: M5 (Crown)

Session Organizers: Stephanie MEDLEY-RATH, *Indiana University Kokomo, USA* and Saori YASUMOTO, *University of Osaka, Japan*

Chair: Jake SALLAWAY-COSTELLO, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

839.1 Heying ZHAN, *Georgia State University, USA* and Jing LIU, *Zhejiang University of Finance and Economics, China*
Teaching Global Aging and Social Policies in a Global Virtual Classroom

839.2 Susan BANKI, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Sohoon YI, *Kyungpook National University, Republic of Korea* and Joowon YUK, *Kyungpook National University, Republic of Korea*

Virtual Exchange in the Teaching of Social Justice and Sociology during the Pandemic: Initial Analysis of a Joint Australia-Korea Teaching Project

839.3 Katherine LYON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*; Nathan ROBERSON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*; Mark LAM, *University of British Columbia, Canada*; Daniel RICCARDI, *University of British Columbia, Canada*; Jennifer LIGHTFOOT, *University of British Columbia, Canada* and Simon LOLLIIOT, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Linguistic Diversity and Inclusive Multiple Choice Assessment: Implications for Teaching First Year Sociology Courses

839.4 Meredith EDELMAN, *Monash Business School, Australia* and Catrina DENVIR, *Monash Business School, Australia*

Developing Business Students' Criminological Imaginations: The Thrilling Tale of 1MDB

839.5 Moya BYDAWELL, *UNIVERSITY OF KWAZULU-NATAL, South Africa*

Engaging with the Personal Troubles of Students: A Reflection of the Emotional Labor Used in Facilitating an Understanding of the 'Sociological Imagination' with First Year Students at a South African University.

TG10

Digital Sociology

Program Coordinator: Regev NATHANSON, *University of Michigan, USA* and Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

JS-6 To Grant or Not to Grant? Use and Timing of Media Tools in Families with Teen and Pre-Teen Ager

Committees: RC06 Family Research (Host); RC34 Sociology of Youth and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-6.

15:30-17:20

840 Media Usage and Intimacies in the Next Generation

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Ichiyo HABUCHI, *Hirosaki University, Japan* and Izumi TSUJI, *Chuo University, Japan*

Chairs: Ichiyo HABUCHI, *Hirosaki University, Japan* and Izumi TSUJI, *Chuo University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

840.1 Samuel CABBAG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Desire and Discourse: Conviviality in Boy's Love Fandoms in the Philippines on Facebook

840.2 Masae YOSHIMITSU, *University of Nagasaki, Japan*
How Digitalization Has Affected the Spectacle of Intimacy in Live Entertainment: A Case Study of Japanese Female Fans of Boy Bands

840.3 Yukie HIRATA, *Japan Women's University, Japan*
Women and Digital Media - a Study of Korean Web Dramas and Their Audiences

840.4 Koh IWATA, *1-1-4-510 Higashi-Mikunigaoka, Japan*
Collapse of the "Friends Bubble": Transformation of Friendship and Media Usage in Japanese Youth

840.5 Eriko KIMURA, *Japan Women's University, Japan*
Social Media Usage and Romantic Relationship in Japanese Youth Culture

17:30-19:20

JS-19 Connected Seniors: Technology across the Life Course

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC11 Sociology of Aging

See Joint Session Details for JS-19.

19:30-20:50

841 TG10 Business Meeting

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

08:30-10:20

JS-25 Digital Mediation of Children's Learning and the Changing Ecology of Home-School-World Connectivity

Committees: RC53 Sociology of Childhood (Host); TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-25.

10:30-12:20

842 Digital Rights and Internet Freedom in the Big Data Era – Is It a Lost Battle?

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Esther BRAININ, *Ruppin Academic Center, Israel* and Sabina LISSITSA, *Ariel University, Israel*

Chairs: Esther BRAININ, *Ruppin Academic Center, Israel* and Sabina LISSITSA, *Ariel University, Israel*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

842.1 Jared WRIGHT, *TED University, Turkey*
Diversity and Inclusion in Data Activism: Frame Resonance and the Barrier of Problem Recognition

842.2 Eyal ECKHAUS, *Ariel University, Israel*; Nitza DAVIDOVITCH, *Ariel University, Israel* and Nili STEINFELD, *Ariel University, Israel*
The Privacy Circles Demonstrated in Student Reluctance to Activate Cameras during Remote Classes: The Self, the Collective and the Authority.

842.3 Bartosz SLOSARSKI, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Data Arenas or How to Deal with Datafication. Grassroots Data Activism in the Times of Data Power

842.4 Amparo COIDURAS, *University of San Jorge, Spain*
Researching Data Gathering Consciousness in the Design Process: Rethinking How Intelligent Objects and Services Are Being Designed.

842.5 Dennis ZUEV, *ISCTE-IUL, Portugal*
Reflecting on Some Methodological Challenges in Investigating Data Governance and "Digital Entrapments"

15:30-17:20

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part I

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture (Host); RC07 Futures Research RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology and TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-39.

Wednesday 28 June

10:30-12:20

843 Swipe Right or Swipe Left? Sociological Perspectives of Digital Sexual Spaces

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Alan MARTINO, *University of Calgary, Canada* and Nicole ANDREJEK, *McMaster University, Canada*

Chair: Karolina MIKOLAJEWSKA-ZAJAC, *University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

843.1 Simrit DEOL, *University of Alberta, Canada* and Pirkko MARKULA, *University of Alberta, Canada*
Is My Bikini Selfie Empowering or Contributing to My Objectification?: An Autonetnography of Postfeminist Sensibilities on Instagram

843.2 Cristiane MELO, *Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil*
Enjoying Myself: The Subjectivity of Pleasure and Desire in the Production of Adult Content in Brazil

843.3 Phiwokazi QOZA, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
A Critical Study of the Organization of Embodied Labour on Onlyfans during the State Administered Lockdowns in South Africa.

843.4 Bruno Henrique BARBOSA, *Department of Sociology - Federal University of Sao Carlos (UFSCar - Brazil), Brazil*
In Search of Sponsorship: A Digital Ethnography of Sugar Relationships in Brazilian Digital Media

843.5 Alexandra JAMES, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia*; Jennifer POWER, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia* and Andrea WALING, *Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health and Society, La Trobe University, Australia*
The Many Languages of Digital Sex: Digital Sexual Subjectivity, Sexting and Amateur Pornography

15:30-17:20

JS-75 The Algorithmic Turn in Visual Studies

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC57 Visual Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-75.

Thursday 29 June

08:30-10:20

844 Sociological Perspectives on Digital Methodologies

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Regev NATHANSOHN, *Sapir College, Israel* and Omer KEYNAN, *Sapir College, Israel*

Chair: Samuel CABBUAG, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

844.1 Sergio BARBOSA, *University of Coimbra, Portugal*
Triangulating Qualitative Methods to Investigate Whatsappers

844.2 Radim HLADIK, *Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic* and Yann RENISIO, *Centre for Research on Social Inequalities - CNRS/SciencesPo, France*
Top-Down or Bottom-up? Intellectual Organization of Scientific Knowledge through Disciplines and Topics

844.3 Muhammed ALAKITAN, *University of Cambridge, Nigeria*
Ethics, Context and Fabrication: Doing Social Media Ethnography in Nigeria

844.4 Karolina MIKOLAJEWSKA-ZAJAC, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Follow the Pattern: An Ecological Epistemology for the Study of Platforms' Societal Effects and Resilient Organizing

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

844.5 Glen BERMAN, *Australian National University, Australia*
Big Omissions in Big Data: Methodological Challenges in Studying Machine Learning Practice

844.6 Corina ILINCA, *Faculty of Sociology and Social Work, Romania*; Marian VASILE, *Faculty of Sociology and Social Work, Romania*; Iuliana PRECUPETU, *Research Institute for Quality of Life, Romania* and Stephen CUTLER, *University of Vermont, USA*
The Connection between Intersectional Disadvantage and Health in Later Life

10:30-12:20

JS-90 Extending Critical Approaches to Agtech and Foodtech: Dialoguing Insights from the Insides and Outsides of Technology Design Projects

Committees: RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food (Host); TG10 Digital Sociology

See Joint Session Details for JS-90.

15:30-17:20

845 Digitalization, Democracy and Trust

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David DUENAS-CID, *Gdansk University of Technology, Poland*

Chair: David DUENAS-CID, *Gdansk University of Technology, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

845.1 Terry FLEW, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Mediated Trust: Ideas, Interests, Institutions, Futures

845.2 Sulfi ar AMIR, *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*
Counting on the Machine: The Construction of Social Trust in Artificial Intelligence

845.3 Grazina RAPOLIENE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania* and Margarita GEDVILAITE-KORDUSIENE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*
Distrust and Fear - Obstacles for Digital Inclusion of the Older People in Lithuania?

845.4 Terrence CHEN, *New York University, USA*
Digital Technology and Democracy: Open Government and State-Citizen Relationship in Taiwan

845.5 Tatiana KARABCHUK, *UAE University, United Arab Emirates* and Osman ANTWI-BOATENG, *UAE University, United Arab Emirates*
Digitization and Confidence in National Institutions in the Gulf Countries

17:30-19:20

846 Sociological Theory for a Digital Society

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David DUENAS-CID, *Gdansk University of Technology, Poland*

Chair: David DUENAS-CID, *Gdansk University of Technology, Poland*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

846.1 Ori SCHWARZ, *Bar Ilan University, Israel*
Sociological Theory for Digital Society: The Codes That Bind Us Together

Friday 30 June

10:30-12:20

847 Responsible Digitalization

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

Chair: Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

847.1 Charlotte BRADLEY, *School of Cybernetics, Australian National University, Australia*
The Problem with Parrots: Narrow Conceptions of Meaning and Responsibility in Large Language Models

847.2 Lauren WAARDENBURG, *IESEG School of Management, France* and Ella HAFERMALZ, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*
We'Re in a Bit of a Situation: The Embodied and Material Realities of Data-Driven Work

847.3 Jeremie POIROUX, *Centre Marc Bloch, Computational Social Science Team, Germany* and Karl PINEAU, *Ecole de Design Nantes Atlantique, France*
Criticizing and Putting Criticism into Practice: The Case of Digital Designers

847.4 Anna CHERNOIVANOVA, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation* and Aleksei SHCHEKIN, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*
Life in a Modern City: Digital Practices of People in an Unstable Life Situation

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

847.5 Chitra NAIR, *Govt. K NM College, India*
Optimum Digital Skills As Species Capital for Older Adults – the Significance of Digital Language Brokering.

17:30-19:20

848 Society and Algorithms

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

Chair: Lauren WAARDENBURG, *IESEG School of Management, France*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

848.1 Carina KRAFT, *The University of Adelaide, Australia*
Taming the Algorithm? a Bourdieusian Approach on Negotiating Algorithmic Visibility of Politically Relevant Content on Social Media Platforms

848.2 Dorismilda FLORES-MÁRQUEZ, *Universidad De La Salle Bajío, Mexico*
Being There or Not: Presence and Absence in Times of Algorithms

848.3 Falk RAHN, *Leibniz University of Hanover, Germany*; Korbinian GALL, *Leibniz University of Hanover, Germany* and Katharina BRAUNSMANN, *Leibniz University of Hanover, Germany*
Algorithmic Decision Support Systems in Discourse: From a Tool to an Organizational Algorithm

848.4 Martin LUKK, *University of Toronto, Canada* and Erik SCHNEIDERHAN, *University of Toronto, Canada*
Algorithms in Social Welfare: Healthcare Fundraising Disparities on Gofundme

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

848.5 Biagio ARAGONA, *Universita degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy* and Francesco AMATO, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy*
Retracing Algorithms: How Digital Social Research Methods Can Track Algorithmic Functioning

848.6 Aysu KES-ERKUL, *Cerebrum Tech, Turkey*
Algorithmic Bias As a Social Issue: Participation and Inclusiveness in AI

848.7 Jeremie POIROUX, *Centre Marc Bloch, Computational Social Science Team, Germany*
Making Symbolism and Connectionism Coexist: The Case of Two Risk Prediction Tools in Public Administration

848.8 Paulina BENITEZ, *Independent Researcher, Chile*
Sociotechnological Change. Optimization of Interpersonal Ties and Asynchronous Communication.

Saturday 1 July

10:30-12:20

JS-140 Digital Urbanism

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology (Host); RC21 Regional and Urban Development

See Joint Session Details for JS-140.

12:30-14:20

849 Do We Need a Sociology of the Digital?

Location: 205 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

Chair: Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

849.1 Pratchi MAJUMDAR, *GendV Project, University of Cambridge, India*
The Internet, Storytelling and a Sociological Exploration of the Digital

849.2 Camila MOZZINI-ALISTER, *University of the Sunshine Coast, Australia*
Digital Sociology and Desire for Omnipresence: Introducing a Key Conceptual Tool

849.3 Sana AHMAD, *WZB Social Science Center Berlin, Germany*
Social Media Platforms and Social Relations: Using a Sociological Lens

849.4 Vern SMITH, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
Detangling (Social) Cyber-Deviance: Trolling, Online Harassment and Antidisestablishmentarianism on the Internet

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

849.5 Patricia RUIZ-ANGEL, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide (Sevilla), Spain*
Access to Digitisation in Spain during the Period 2006-2022.

TG11

Violence and Society

Program Coordinator: Myrna DAWSON, *University of Guelph, Canada* and Sylvia WALBY, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom*

Monday 26 June

10:30-12:20

850 Violence in the Contemporary Public Realm

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Charlotte FABIANSOON, *Victoria University, Australia*

Chair: Oliver NAHKUR, *University of Tartu, Estonia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

850.1 Monica MESQUITA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal*
Intellectual Structural Violence

850.2 Onur BILGINER, *Baskent University, Turkey*
On Political Resistance

850.3 Rosario FIGARI LAYUS, *Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany*
Violence Against Academic Freedom in Latin America: Science and Education at Risk?

850.4 Matthew HALL, *British University in Egypt, Egypt* and Ruth LEWIS, *University of Northumbria, United Kingdom*
Limitless Digital Gender-Sexual Violences: The Threat to Girls and Women of Emerging, Advanced, Technologies

850.5 Charlotte FABIANSOON, *Victoria University, Australia*
Navigating Violence in the Public Realm. the Interconnection between Hegemonic Ideology and Agency-Level Acceptance of Violence and Discrimination

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

850.6 Amit SINGH, *Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee, India, India* and Anindya MISHRA, *Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, India*
"We All Are Kashmiris but...": Competing Masculinities and Militarism in the (re)Production of Identity As 'Mukhbir'

850.7 Hugo BISPO, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Symbolic Violence and Neoliberalism: A Film Analysis of Fight Club (1999)

15:30-17:20

JS-15 Violence & Body: Reflecting Our Own Limits and Beyond

Committees: TG11 Violence and Society (Host); RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences

See Joint Session Details for JS-15.

17:30-19:20

851 Lethal Violence: Sociological Approaches to Homicide and Femicide/Femicide

Language: English, Spanish

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina*

Chair: Martin DI MARCO, *CONICET/IIGG, Argentina*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

851.1 Emmanuel ROHN, *University of Guelph, Canada* and Eric Y. TENKORANG, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Femicide in Sub-Saharan Africa

851.2 Myrna DAWSON, *University of Guelph, Canada*; Angelika ZECHA, *University of Guelph, Canada* and Haleakala ANGUS, *University of Guelph, Canada*
Identifying femicide using the UN statistical framework: Exploring the feasibility of sex/gender related motives and indicators to inform prevention

851.3 Carmen RUIZ-REPULLO, *University of Jaen, Spain*
¡Cuidado Con Ellos! La Importancia De La Despatologización Del Agresor Sexual

851.4 Jessica GILDERSLEEVE, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*; Annette BROMDAL, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*; Tait SANDERS, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia* and Heidi TONE, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*
The Murder of Mhelody Bruno: Media, Violence, and Justice

851.5 Diane CROCKER, *Saint Mary's University, Canada* and Mary ASPINALL, *St. Thomas University, Canada*
Promising Practices and Barriers to Help-Seeking in Severe Cases of Domestic Violence: Findings from the Canadian Domestic Homicide Prevention Initiative with Vulnerable Populations

19:30-20:50

852 TG11 Business Meeting

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Tuesday 27 June

10:30-12:20

853 The Consequences of Violence

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Lynn RAPAPORT, *Pomona College, USA*

Chair: Lynn RAPAPORT, *Pomona College, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

853.1 John Rey CODILLA, *Davao Oriental State University, Philippines*
Violent Incidents and School Safety: Avatar of Basic Education in the Era of Fire

853.2 Katie WRIGHT, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Public Inquiries and the Societalization of Child Abuse Crises

853.3 Phi SU, *Williams College, USA*
The Border within: Vietnamese Migrants Transforming Ethnic Nationalism in Berlin

853.4 Annette BROMDAL, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*; Amy MULLENS, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia* and Carol DU PLESSIS, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*
Navigating Intimate Trans Citizenship While Incarcerated in Australia and the United States

853.5 Doris BUEHLER-NIEDERBERGER, *University of Wuppertal, Germany* and Lars ALBERTH, *Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany*
Preserving a Respectable Self – Victim Narratives in Face of Institutional Programs and Closed Awareness Contexts of the Private Environment

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

853.6 Ben BORNSTEIN, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
The Double-Edged Sword of Multidimensional Victimhood: Competing Justifications of the Public Support for Victims of Terrorism

853.7 Md. Masudur RAHMAN, *Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University, Bangladesh* and Faizah SULTANA, *Centre for Genocide Studies, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*
Gender Based Violence (GBV) and Women's Empowerment in 21st Century: A Critical Analysis in Bangladesh

854.4 Lily IVANOVA, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Back to 'Settler': Challenges to Canadian Multiculturalism after Genocide

854.5 Laura RODRIGUEZ CASTRO, *Southern Cross University, Australia*
Post-Conflict and Post-Dictatorship Latin American Migration to Australia: Doing Difficult Memory-Work through Desire-Centred Research

854.6 David CUNNINGHAM, *Washington University in St Louis, USA*; Nicole FOX, *California State University Sacramento, USA* and Christian MADDOX, *Washington University in St Louis, USA*
Institutionalizing Violence: Trajectories of Memory and Redress in Three Cities

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

854.7 Fatma GOCEK, *University of Michigan, USA*; Jacob CAPONI, *University of Michigan Ann Arbor, USA*; Sadiyah MALCOLM, *University of Michigan, USA* and Aunrika TUCKER-SHABAZZ, *University of Michigan Ann Arbor, USA*
Locating "Women Autocrats" in the Global North and South

15:30-17:20

JS-98 Challenges and Opportunities in Measuring Violence

Committees: *TG11 Violence and Society (Host)*; *RC55 Social Indicators*

See Joint Session Details for JS-98.

17:30-19:20

855 Durkheim, Violence and Society

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Elizabeth COOK, *City, University of London, United Kingdom*

Chair: Elizabeth COOK, *City, University of London, United Kingdom*

Panelists: Rebecca SCOTT BRAY, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Fatma GOCEK, *University of Michigan, USA* and Aunrika TUCKER-SHABAZZ, *University of Michigan Ann Arbor, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

855.1 Fatma GOCEK, *University of Michigan, USA*; Aunrika TUCKER-SHABAZZ, *University of Michigan Ann Arbor, USA*; Jacob CAPONI, *University of Michigan Ann Arbor, USA* and Sadiyah MALCOLM, *University of Michigan, USA*
Undermining "Legitimate" Autocrats through the Analysis of Violence in the Global South

855.2 Rebecca SCOTT BRAY, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Marc TRABSKY, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Individual Acts and Institutional Care: Coronal Investigations Following Suicide

855.3 Emmanuel ROHN, *University of Guelph, Canada* and Eric Y. TENKORANG, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Structural Barriers to Help-Seeking Among Female Victims of Intimate Partner Violence in Ghana

855.4 Muhammad ASIF, *Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan*
Public Approval of Vigilante Violence in Pakistan

Wednesday 28 June

15:30-17:20

JS-70 Diversities Bodies, Violence and Human Rights in the 21st Century: The Gender and Racism Issues

Committees: *RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences (Host)*; *TG11 Violence and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-70.

Thursday 29 June

10:30-12:20

854 Violence, Culture and Traumatic Memory

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Lynn RAPAPORT, *Pomona College, USA*

Chair: Lynn RAPAPORT, *Pomona College, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

854.1 Elfriede WEDAM, *Loyola University Chicago, USA*
Can Faith-Based Organizations Change the Culture of Violence in Chicago?

854.2 Naomi GILHUIS, *Radboud University, Netherlands*; Teun EIKENAAR, *Radboud University, Netherlands* and Lars STEVENSON, *Radboud University, Netherlands*
Sisyphus in Court: A Study of the Dynamic between the Dutch Police Organization and Their Personnel in Light of Requests for Recognition in the Wake of Trauma

Friday 30 June

08:30-10:20

JS-119 Persistence and Change: Collaborative, Conceptual and Contextual Global Understandings of Gender-Based and Intersectional Violence

Committees: *TG11 Violence and Society (Host); RC32 Women, Gender and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-119.

10:30-12:20

856 The Precarity of (Social) Life: Mapping the Impact of the Global Pandemic on Violence(s) Against Women

Location: 108 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Kate FITZ-GIBBON, *Monash University, Australia* and Sandra WALKLATE, *Liverpool University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Kate FITZ-GIBBON, *Monash University, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

856.1 Kate FITZ-GIBBON, *Monash University, Australia* and Sandra WALKLATE, *Monash University, Australia*
Counting Women's Deaths 'with' Male Violence and 'from' Male Violence: Lessons from the Pandemic Practices of Counting Deaths.

856.2 Rebecca SCOTT BRAY, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Death Data and the Politics of Preventability: The COVID-19 Crisis and Fatal Violence

856.3 Marie SEGRAVE, *Monash University, Australia*
Precarity, Temporariness and Domestic and Family Violence: Illuminating the Violence of the Border

856.4 Naomi PFITZNER, *Monash University, Australia*
Helping from Home: Domestic and Family Violence Worker Wellbeing during the 'Shadow Pandemic'.

Saturday 1 July

12:30-14:20

JS-149 Political Economy and Violence: The Implications of Taking Violence Seriously for Theories of Hegemonic and Counter-Hegemonic Forces

Committees: *RC02 Economy and Society (Host); TG11 Violence and Society*

See Joint Session Details for JS-149.

Joint Session Details

Joint RC, WG and TG Committee Sessions

Monday 26 June

10:30 - 12:20

JS-1 CoViD-19 Pandemic and Global Health Workforce Policies and Governance: Challenges and issues at the Forefront

Committees: RC15 Sociology of Health, RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Stephanie SHORT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Noor Aman A HAMID, *Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia*

Chair: Alex ASAKITIKPI, *The Independent Institute of Education, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-1.1 Stephanie SHORT, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Vivian LIN, *Li Ka Shing Faculty of Medicine, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Kathleen LESLIE, *Athabasca University & Canadian Health Workforce Network, Canada*; Anne-Louise CARLTON, *RMIT University, Australia*; Madhan BALASUBRAMANIAN, *Health Care Management, Flinders University, Adelaide, Australia*; Raha MIRSHAHI, *University of Ottawa & Canadian Health Workforce Network, Canada* and Ivy BOURGEOULT, *Canadian Health Workforce Network, Canada*

Strengthening Health Practitioner Regulation: A Large-Scale Rapid Systematic Review

JS-1.2 Francesca SIRNA, *CNRS, France*
"in My Country, I Am a Specialised Nurse... but Here, I Was Hired As a Care Assistant..." the Integration of Health Professionals with Foreign Qualifications into the French Hospital Sector and the « Pandemic Challenge »: A Process of Recognition and/or Exclusion?

JS-1.3 Farah PURWANINGRUM, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Azmil TAYEB, *Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia*;

Stephanie SHORT, *The University of Sydney, Australia* and Hasbullah THABRANY, *ThinkWell, Indonesia*

Training of Doctors amidst Covid-19 Pandemic: A Regulatory Analysis of Indonesia's Health Workforce

JS-1.4 Ayse POLAT, *Assistant Professor, Turkey*; Zubeyde DEMIRCIOGLU, *Istanbul Medeniyet University, Turkey* and Huseyin KUCUKALI, *Istanbul Medipol University, Turkey*
The Domestication of Medicine: The Experiences of Contact-Tracing Teams in Turkey

JS-1.5 Flavio MARSIGLIA, *Arizona State University, USA* and Stephen KULIS, *Arizona State University, USA*
Community Health Workers Addressing the Unmet COVID-19 Needs of Communities

DISTRIBUTED PAPERS:

JS-1.6 Beverley BRATHWAITE, *University of Roehampton, United Kingdom*
The Disparities and Risk of COVID-19 in Black and Brown Nurses in the United Kingdom

JS-1.7 Gupteswar PATEL, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom* and Niroshan SIRIWARDENA, *Community and Health Research Unit, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom*
Role of Community First Responders during the Pandemic in England; An Understanding of Field and Power Dynamics

JS-2 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part I

Committees: WG08 Society and Emotions, RC38 Biography and Society

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Marina ARIZA, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*; Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany* and Irini SIOUTI, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt/Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences UAS, Germany*

Chairs: Marina ARIZA, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico* and Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-2.1 Zacharoula KASSERI, *Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece*
Conducting Qualitative Research in the Field of Drug Dependence: Emotional Risks and the Vulnerability of the Researcher.

JS-2.2 Christoph HEDTKE, *University of Applied Sciences Erfurt, Germany* and Katrin GROSSMANN, *University of Applied Sciences Erfurt, Germany*
How Emotions Impact the Research Process and Its Outcomes. the Example of Researching Nationalist, Regressive Movements in Peripheralized Places.

JS-2.3 Monica MASSARI, *University of Milan, Italy*; Gianluca GATTA, *University of Milan, Italy* and Simona MICELI, *University of Milan, Italy*
Affectivity and Embodied Knowledge in Biographical Research on Mediterranean Migration

JS-2.4 Alina BREHM, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Philipp LANGER, *International Psychoanalytic University Berlin, Germany*
Ambivalences of Research Empathy - Methodological Considerations in a Strong Reflexivity Perspective

JS-2.5 Elisabeth MAYER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Don't Look Too Closely into It - the Emotional Challenge in Visual Biographical Research

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-2.6 Michelle KING, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
Researching the Personal: The Contribution of Lived Experience in Liminal Research Spaces

JS-3 Fossil Capitalism, Climate Breakdown, and Green-Left Strategies

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society, RC07 Futures Research, RC24 Environment and Society, RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: William CARROLL, *University of Victoria, Canada*

Chair: Mark STODDART, *Memorial University, Canada*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-3.1 William CARROLL, *University of Victoria, Canada*
Refusing Ecocide: From Fossil Capitalism to a Livable World

JS-3.2 Hajime KIMURA, *University of Toyama, Japan*
"Treadmill of Production" and Climate Capitalism As Passive Revolution

JS-3.3 Angeline LETOURNEAU, *University of Alberta, Canada*
Out of the Pot and into the Fire: The Limitations of Renewable Technologies for a Just Transition

JS-3.4 Liam M'CLOUGHLIN, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*
Australian Climate Movement Strategy

JS-3.5 Ines DURAN MATUTE, *Benemerita Universidad Autonoma de México, Mexico*
Revealing and Contesting the Eco-Indigenous Rhetoric of Progressive Capitalism

JS-3.6 James GOODMAN, *University of Technology, Australia*
Climate Movements in Germany, India and Australia: Dynamics of Transition, Transformation and Emergency

Discussion

JS-4 Return Migration during a Pandemic: Challenges and interventions

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Johanna ZULUETA, *Toyo University, Japan*

Chair: Johanna ZULUETA, *Toyo University, Japan*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-4.1 Thanggoulen KIPGEN, *IIT Kanpur, India*
Back to the Village: Return and Reception of Northeast Migrants during the Covid-19 Pandemic in India

JS-4.2 Gyanendra YADAV, *PATLIPUTRA UNIVERSITY, India*
Pandemic 2020, Returned Migrants and Shifting Social Concerns in India: A Critical Analysis.

JS-4.3 Yasmin ORTIGA, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
A Time to Start Anew?: Negotiating Immobility Among Return Migrants in the Philippines

JS-4.4 Chiho OGAYA, *Ferris University, Japan* and Sera ONO, *Kobe University, Japan*
Experiences Transferred—How Reintegration Program for Women Returnees Expands during the Pandemic: the Case of the Philippines

JS-4.5 Zai LIANG, *State University of New York at Albany, USA*; Nan WANG, *Xi'an Jiaotong University, China* and Yuanfei LI, *Purdue University, USA*
Return Migration of International Students during COVID-19 Pandemic in China

JS-5 The Soldier-Scholar: Postsecondary Education of Future Military Officers

Committees: RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution, RC04 Sociology of Education

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada*

Chair: Jamie FERRILL, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-5.1 Unsal SIGRI, *OSTİM Technical University, Turkey*; Kadir VAROGLU, *Baskent University, Turkey* and Ugur GUNGOR, *Baskent University, Turkey*
An Analysis of Education of Junior Officers in the Turkish Armed Forces

JS-5.2 Hitoshi KAWANO, *Japan National Defense Academy, Japan*
A Hybrid Education and Leadership Development at the National Defense Academy of Japan (NDA)

JS-5.3 Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada*
The Demographics of Force Generation: Recruitment, Attrition and Retention of Citizen Soldiers

JS-6 to Grant or not to Grant? Use and timing of Media tools in Families with teen and Pre-teen Ager

Committees: RC06 Family Research, RC34 Sociology of Youth, TG10 Digital Sociology

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Brunella FIORE, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy*; Marco GUI, *University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy* and Chiara RESPI, *Università di Milano-Bicocca, Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale, Italy*

Chair: Donatella POLIANDRI, *INVALSI (Italian National Institute of Educational Evaluation), Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-6.1 Simone LANZA, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*
Green Time, Human Time or Screen Time?

JS-6.2 Ville-samuli HAVERINEN, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland*; Sari TUUVA-HONGISTO, *South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences, Finland*; Päivi ARMILA, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland* and Marta CHOROSZEWICZ, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland*
"Fear of Missing Real Life": From Parental Regulation to Youth's Self-Control of Screen Time

JS-6.3 Nili STEINFELD, *Ariel University, Israel*
"the Younger Ones Are Not Interested in These Kind of Stuff": Adolescents, Parents and Teachers Discuss Online Risks for Younger and Older Adolescents

JS-6.4 Andre SARLI, *University of Geneva, Switzerland*
Contested Right to Connect: Controversies about Teenagers Living in Shelter to Access Social Media and Mobiles

JS-6.5 Aron TELEGDICI-CSETRI, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania*; Viorela ducu CSETRI, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania*; Mihaela HARAGUS, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania* and Daniela ANGI, *Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania*
Children's Rights within the Digital Practices of Ukrainian and Moldovan Transnational Families

15:30 - 17:20

JS-7 Climate Crisis, Mental Health and Youth Resistance

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth, RC15 Sociology of Health

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Philippa COLLIN, *Western Sydney University, Australia*; Sanna AALTONEN, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland* and Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*

Chairs: Evelina LANDSTEDT, *Karlstad University, Dept of Social and Psychological Studies, Sweden* and Anne GOTFREDSEN, *Umeå University, Sweden*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-7.1 Seth BROWN, *RMIT University, Australia*
The Impact of the Climate Crisis and Other Crises on Young People's Health and Well-Being

JS-7.2 Peter KELLY, *Deakin University, Australia*
A 'Code Red for Humanity': Sociologies of School Strikes for Climate and the 'Problem' of the Anthropocene

JS-7.3 Milo KEI, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Australian School Strikers' Everyday Acts of Political Participation and Resistance

JS-7.4 Sarah WALKER, *University of Bologna, United Kingdom*
'God's Plan': Young African Men in Italy and Their Use of Hip Hop and Faith to Counteract the Negative Mental Health Impact of Anti-Immigrant Rhetoric

JS-7.5 Alude MAHALI, *Human Sciences Research Council, South Africa*
"I Just Want to Die": Reflections on Mental Health from a Cohort of Young African Graduates at the Intersection of Pandemic

DISTIBUTED PAPERS:

JS-7.6 Benjamin TEJERINA, *University of the Basque Country, Spain*; Joseba GARCIA MARTIN, *University of the Basque Country, Spain* and Ignacia PERUGORRIA, *Universidad del País Vasco-Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Spain*
"My Life Has Become a Never-Ending Sunday...". Everyday Life and Risk-Management Strategies Among the Spanish Youth during the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-7.7 Mohai BISWAS, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India* and Mohammed Illias SHEIKH, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India*
Psychological Implications of Unemployment Among Higher Educated Migrant Youth: A Study in Kolkata City

JS-8 Emotions in the Research Process: Methodological Challenges and Theoretical Reflections Part II

Committees: RC38 Biography and Society, WG08 Society and Emotions

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Irini SIOUTI, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt/Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences UAS, Germany* and Marina ARIZA, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*

Chair: Irini SIOUTI, *Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt/Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences UAS, Germany*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-8.1 Kaja KAZMIERSKA, *University of Lodz, Poland*
From the Biographical to Emotional Work – Specific Features of Contemporary Life Stories of Young Adults.

JS-8.2 Yayoi YUKAWA, *Keio University, Japan*
How Can We Write about an Adult Who Says "I'm Really a Small Child"? :Understanding Others' Experiences By Analyzing the Researcher's Emotional Transformation

JS-8.3 Julie BROWNLIE, *Edinburgh University, United Kingdom*; Simon ANDERSON, *Mr, United Kingdom* and Youssef AL HARIRI, *University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom*
Sentiment(al) Research

JS-8.4 Andrea DETTANO, *CONICET, Argentina* and María Victoria SORDINI, *INHUS-CONICET/UNMDP, Argentina*
Emotions in Virtual Ethnography in Facebook Groups of Social Policies in Argentina: Notes from Our Role of Researchers

JS-9 Navigating Aging, Social Well-Being, and Cultural Expectations Among Migrant and transnational Families

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration*, RC06 *Family Research*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Allen KIM, *International Christian University, Japan* and Johanna ZULUETA, *Toyo University, Japan*

Chair: Allen KIM, *International Christian University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-9.1 Jeehun KIM, *University of California, Irvine, USA* and Judith TREAS, *University of California, Irvine, USA*
Voluntary and Involuntary (im)Mobilities of Korea-Born Older Adults in Singapore and Los Angeles: Transnational Insights from Linked Lives, Social Welfare, Citizenship Choice, and Familism

JS-9.2 Hisano NIKURA, *Wako University, Japan*
The Thirty-Year Consequence of the "Feminization of Migration" in Japan: Through the Vulnerabilities of Thai Women's Social Security in Old Age

JS-9.3 Hien NGUYEN, *The University of Western Australia, Australia*
Older Vietnamese Migrants' Social Support Networks: Typologies and Determinants

JS-9.4 Irma BUDGINAITE-MACKINE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania* and Irena JUOZELIUNIENE, *Vilnius University, Lithuania*
Intergenerational Solidarity and Ambivalence in Lithuanian Transnational Families in the Context of Aging

JS-9.5 Catriona STEVENS, *School of Arts and Humanities, Edith Cowan University, Australia*
Past Decisions, Present Challenges and Future Anxieties: Chinese Migrant Grandparents' Reflections on (Grand) Parenting Expectations and Choices over Time

JS-9.6 Alinaya Sybilla FABROS, *University of California Berkeley, USA*
Left-behind or Left-Beyond: How Migration Regimes Engender Aging Return Prospects for Older Overseas Workers from the Philippines

DISCUSSION PAPERS:

JS-9.7 Pam PAPADELLOS, *University of Adelaide, School of Social Sciences, Australia*
Greek Migrants Ageing in Australia: An Intergenerational Perspective

JS-9.8 Yan ZHAO, *Nord University, Norway*
Exploring the Intergenerational Relationship through the Going-Abroad Stories of the Chinese Migrant Elderly Parents

JS-9.9 Rica CASTANEDA, *CERC in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University, Canada*
Immigrant Retirement and Transnational Practices

JS-10 Panel Discussion: Accrediting Your Undergraduate or Graduate Program in Sociological Practice: A Workshop on Process, Benefits, and Outcomes By the Commission on the Accreditation of Programs in Applied and Clinical Sociology (CAPACS)

Committees: RC46 *Clinical Sociology*, RC26 *Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice*

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Michael FLEISCHER, *Organizational Dynamics, USA*

Chair: Amitra WALL, *SUNY Buffalo State College, USA*

Panelists: Michael FLEISCHER, *Organizational Dynamics, USA*; Norma WINSTON, *University of Tampa, USA*; Pragna RUGUNANAN, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Tina UYS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-10.1 Michael FLEISCHER, *Organizational Dynamics, USA* and Norma WINSTON, *University of Tampa, USA*
A Brief History and Overview of Capacs Accreditation

JS-11 Religious Actors and Social Movements in Contemporary World

Committees: RC22 *Sociology of Religion*, RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Geoffrey PLEYERS, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium*

Chair: Geoffrey PLEYERS, *Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

JS-11.1 Esen KIRDIS, *Rhodes College, USA*
The Puzzling Rise of Fundamentalists into Political Power: A Comparison of Political Salafism in Egypt and Political Haredism in Israel

JS-11.2 Marie helene SA VILAS BOAS, *Universite Cote d'Azur, France*
Establishing God's Kingdom in Brazil : Traditionalist Catholic Movements in the State of Rio De Janeiro (Brazil)

JS-11.3 Janine TREVISAN, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*; Bianca LUNKES, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*; Maria Eduarda DE CESERO, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*; Leonardo NUNCIO, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*; Aline Selli DE ALMEIDA, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*; Laise PEDROSO, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil* and Valentine Della GIUSTINA, *IFRS - Campus Bento Gonçalves, Brazil*
Pentecostal Political Activism in 2022 Brazilian Federal Elections

JS-11.4 Arvind SURAJ, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India*
How Religious Becomes Political? Studying a Heterodox Sect of Varanasi

JS-11.5 Emil Albert SOBOTKA, *Rua Prof. Fitzgerald 192, Brazil*
Trivialization of Religiosity: Political Instrumentalization of Evangelicals in Brazil

JS-12 Resurgent Authoritarianism in the Context of SDG 1 on no Poverty, SDG2 on Zero Hunger and SDG 17 on Partnerships for the Goals: Sociology of new Entanglements of Religions, Politics and Economies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management, WG05 Famine and Society

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session organizer: P.P. BALAN, Ministry of Panchayati Raj, India

Chair: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, CRRID, India

Panelists: T.K. OOMMEN, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India; Debal SINGHARROY, 603, Asiad Games Village, New Delhi 110049, India and Abha CHAUHAN, University of Jammu, India

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-12.1 Rimma AKHMETIANOVA, Centre for Strategic Research Republic of Bashkortostan, Russian Federation
Digital Poverty Profile of the Region: A Case Study of the Republic of Bashkortostan

JS-12.2 P.P. BALAN, Ministry of Panchayati Raj, India
Breaking Authoritarianism: Sdgs Made People Friendly through Localising SDG

JS-12.3 Janaka HEMATHILAKA, Janathakshan, Sri Lanka
Strengthening Mobilization of Private and Sub-National Domestic Investments in Sri Lanka for the 2030 Agenda

JS-12.4 Subhendu RAJ, PGDAVE COLLEGE, India
Increasing Hunger & Poverty UNDER COVID 19 Progression in India

JS-13 Securitized the State? the Challenges of illiberal Democracies and Authoritarian Benevolence

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology, RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development, RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy, RC20 Comparative Sociology, RC56 Historical Sociology, TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Abu BAH, Northern Illinois University, USA and Cyril OBI, Social Science Research Council, USA

Chair: Temitope ORIOLA, Dept of Sociology, Canada

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-13.1 Abu BAH, Northern Illinois University, USA
Ethnic Politics, Illiberal Democracy and Power: The Cases of Sierra Leone and Guinea

JS-13.2 Enock NDAWANA, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Militarisation and Political (in) Security in Contemporary Zimbabwe

JS-13.3 Cristina BOBOC, Ghent University, Belgium
Azerbaijani Autocratic Middle Class.

JS-13.4 Piotr KULAS, Uniwersytet Warszawski, Poland
Authoritarian State or Authoritarian Society? Right-Wing Struggle for Recognition in Poland.

JS-13.5 Pedro CAMARGOS, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil
Penal Policy and the "War on Organized Crime" in Brazil Under Temer and Bolsonaro: Neoliberalism, Social Accumulation of Violence and Militarization of Security

JS-14 The Rise and Fall of Authoritarian Populisms (Hopefully)

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC36 Alienation Theory and Research

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Lauren LANGMAN, Loyola University of Chicago, USA

Chair: Lauren LANGMAN, Loyola University of Chicago, USA

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-14.1 Patricia WIDENER, Florida Atlantic University, USA
Bodies Under Threat: Resistance and Rapture in the U.S.

JS-14.2 Sheyla MORONI, Università degli Studi di Firenze, Italy and Erika CELLINI, University of Florence, Italy, Italy
From Peppa Pig to Young Partisan Movements.

JS-14.3 Howard LUNE, Hunter College, CUNY, USA
The Message Is the Medium

JS-14.4 Rodolfo LOBATO DA COSTA, PARANÁ FEDERAL UNIVERSITY, Brazil; Ana Maria MOTTA RIBEIRO, Fluminense Federal University, Brazil and Emmanuel Oguri FREITAS, Universidade Estadual de Feira de Santa, Brazil
The RISE of Pentecostalism in Areas of Agrarian Reform: The Social Construction of Forgetting the Fight for the LAND

JS-14.5 Miri GAL-EZER, Kinneret College on the Sea of Galilee, Israel
Israel Democratic "Staatschmerz" Protestors Vs Illiberal State's Alt-Right "Legal" and Illegal Violent Militias

JS-15 Violence & Body: Reflecting Our Own Limits and Beyond

Committees: TG11 Violence and Society, RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences

Location: M13 (Crown)

Session organizer: Monica MESQUITA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - MARE Recherche Centre, Portugal

Chair: Dietmar WETZEL, MSH Medical School, Hamburg & University of Basel, Switzerland

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-15.1 Kausiki SARMA, Lancaster University, India
Interplay between Habitus and Reflexivity in Agential Responses to Marital Violence

JS-15.2 Laura DAVY, Australian National University, Australia; Sally ROBINSON, Flinders University, Australia; Jan IDLE, Flinders University, Australia and Kylie VALENTINE, University of New South Wales, Australia
Regulating Vulnerability: Analysing Australia's Policy Approaches for Preventing and Responding to Violence Against People with Disability

JS-15.3 Jen RINALDI, Ontario Tech University, Canada
Huron's Double Bind: How Institutionalization Bears out on the Body

JS-15.4 Robert NONOMURA, Western University, Canada; Gursharan SANDU, Western University, Canada; Vivek GILL, Western University, Canada; Katreena SCOTT, Western University, Canada; Peter JAFFE, Western University, Canada; Julie POON, Western University, Canada and Anna-Lee STRAATMAN, Western University, Canada
Coercive Control in/and the Family Law System in Canada: Foregrounding Survivors' Voices

JS-15.5 Tarang MAHAJAN, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
Foregrounding Trauma and Embodiment in Ethical Feminist Research Modality

17:30 - 19:20

JS-16 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part i

Committees: RC07 Futures Research, RC16 Sociological Theory, RC18 Political Sociology

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Chad GOLDBERG, *University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States* and Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*

Chair: Gabriela FRIED AMILIVIA, *California State University Los Angeles, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-16.1 Jeffrey ALEXANDER, *Yale University, USA*
How the Civil Authority of Office Saved American Democracy

JS-16.2 Paul JOOSSE, *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Integrating the Study of Charisma and Populism through the Sociology of Emotions

JS-16.3 Chad GOLDBERG, *University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States*
Eros and Trumpism: A Marcusean Interpretation

JS-16.4 Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*
The Predicament of Democratic Authority

JS-16.5 Kathya ARAUJO, *Instituto de Estudios Avanzados, Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Chile* and Macarena ORCHARD, *Universidad Diego Portales, Chile*
Beyond Legitimacy: How to Study Authority in Contemporary Societies

JS-17 Children and Youth navigating Gender

Committees: RC53 Sociology of Childhood, RC34 Sociology of Youth

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Fiona NELSON, *University of Calgary, Canada*

Chair: Anandini DAR, *Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Delhi, India*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-17.1 Debora PICCIRILLO, *Center for the Study of Violence - University of Sao Paulo (NEV-USP), Brazil*
Gender Perceptions and Expectations Among Brazilian Adolescents

JS-17.2 Utsa MUKHERJEE, *Brunel University London, United Kingdom*
Growing up Queer in 21st Century India: Unpacking Everyday Geographies of Gender in the Lives of Lgbtqia+ Youth

JS-17.3 Anne GOTFREDSSEN, *Umeå University, Sweden* and Ida LINANDER, *Dept. of Epidemiology and Global Health, Umeå University, Sweden*
Young Trans People's Experiences of Leisure and Mental Health: Belonging, Creativity, and Navigation

JS-17.4 Barrie SHANNON, *University of South Australia, Australia*
Informal Sexuality Education for Trans and Gender Diverse Youth: Implications for School-Based Practice

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-17.5 Hillary FIELD, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
Exploring the Role of Specialist School Wellbeing Staff in Promoting Intersectional, Queer Student Inclusion.

JS-18 Collaborative Research i: Critical Reflections on Research Ethics and Methodological Practices

Committees: TG03 Human Rights and Global Justice, RC03 Community Research

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Tanja GANGAROVA, *The German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Germany*

Chair: David RADFORD, *University of South Australia, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-18.1 Beatriz PADILLA, *University of South Florida, USA*
Collaborative Research in Gender and Refugee Studies: When the Dream Methodology Is Not Possible

JS-18.2 Krista BYWATER, *Save the Children, USA* and Yeva AVAKYAN, *Save the Children, USA*
Who Has the Power?: Using Gender and Power Analysis to Advance Gender Equality and Social Justice

JS-18.3 David RADFORD, *University of South Australia, Australia*; Heidi HETZ, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Branka KRIVOKAPIC-SKOKO, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*
Researching with Refugee-Background Participants in Non-Crisis Contexts: Ethical and Methodological Considerations

JS-18.4 Alexandra KASSIR, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*
Collaborative Research and Coproduction of Knowledge in the Context of Protracted Displacement

JS-19 Connected Seniors: technology across the Life Course

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology, RC11 Sociology of Aging

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Anabel QUAN-HAASE, *Western University, Canada*

Chair: Esther BRAININ, *Ruppin Academic Center, Israel*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-19.1 Barbara BARBOSA NEVES, *Monash University, Australia*; Alan PETERSEN, *Monash University, Australia*; Mor VERED, *Monash University, Faculty of IT, Australia* and Adrian CARTER, *Monash University, School of Psychological Sciences, Australia*
What Can Artificial Intelligence in Care Homes Tell Us about Technology, Aging, and Ageism?

JS-19.2 Nidhi BANSAL, *Malaviya National Institute of Technology, India* and Heena CHOUDHARY, *Malaviya National Institute of Technology Jaipur, India*
Investigating Outcomes of Internet Use Among Older Adults in India

DiSt RiBUT ED PAPERS:

JS-19.3 Merril SILVERSTEIN, *Syracuse University, USA*; Woosang HWANG, *Texas Tech University, USA* and Xiaoyu FU, *Syracuse University, USA*
Digital Solidarity in Intergenerational Relationships

JS-19.4 Ana RIVOIR, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*
Elder People and Access to Data. a Case Study about the Postpandemic Challenges for the Digital Appropriation Gap.

JS-19.5 Grazina RAPOLIENE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*; Margarita GEDVILAITE-KORDUSIENE, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania* and Vaida TRETJAKOVA, *Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences, Lithuania*
Barriers for Older Users of Digital Technologies

JS-20 international Migration and Economic informalization : A Denationalized Perspective - Part i

Committees: RC30 *Sociology of Work*, RC02 *Economy and Society*, RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Zoran SLAVNIC, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Klara OBERG, *Halmstad University, Sweden*

Chair: Zoran SLAVNIC, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Co-Chair: Klara OBERG, *Halmstad University, Sweden*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-20.1 Johan Fredrik RYE, *Department of Sociology and Political Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway* and Sam SCOTT, *University of Gloucestershire, United Kingdom*
The Mobility-Immobility Dynamic and the 'Fixing' of Migrants' Labour Power

JS-20.2 Olaf TIETJE, *LMU Munich, Germany*
Migrant Cooperatives within the European Border Space

JS-20.3 Ray JUREIDINI, *Hamad Bin Khalifa University, Qatar*
Informal Financial Charges and Transfers in Corruption of Migrant Labour Recruitment

JS-20.4 Branka LIKIC BRBORIC, *Linköping University, Sweden*; Karin KRIFORS, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Nedžad MESIC, *Linköping University, Sweden*
Prearity of Race: The in/Formality Nexus and Translocal Histories of Thai and Roma Workers in Sweden

JS-21 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part i

Committees: RC41 *Sociology of Population*, RC55 *Social Indicators*

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Walter BARTL, *Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany* and Alberto VEIRA-RAMOS, *Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain*

Chair: Walter BARTL, *Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-21.1 Tahu KUKUTAI, *The University of Waikato, USA* and Victor THOMPSON, *Rider University, USA*
The Rise of the Identity State: Ethnicity, Citizenship and the Census

JS-21.2 Ram BHAGAT, *International Institute for Population Sciences, India*
Sate, Enumeration and Marginal Communities in India: Data and Development Policies

JS-21.3 Jon HOVLAND HONERUD, *University of South-Eastern Norway (USN), Norway*; Sigrunn TVEDTEN, *University of South-Eastern Norway (USN), Norway* and Gunhild TØNDEL, *Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway*
The Sociology of Quantification: Against a Consolidated Research Program

JS-22 Materialist Sociology: Biometabolism, technometabolism, technoaddiction

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society*, RC16 *Sociological Theory*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Haimo SCHULZ MEINEN, *University of Hannover, Germany*

Chair: Tyler BATEMAN, *University of Toronto, Canada*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-22.1 Marina FISCHER-KOWALSKI, *Institute for Social Ecology, Austria*
Energy Transitions and Social Revolutions

JS-22.2 Laurentiu TANASE, *Universitatea din București, Romania* and Haimo SCHULZ MEINEN, *University of Hannover, Germany*
Sustainable Human Life As Function of Technometabolism

JS-22.3 Xinwei ZHANG, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Going Back to West: The Rise of Chinese Television Format (1998 - 2022)

JS-22.4 Raymond MURPHY, *University of Ottawa, Canada*
Energy Demand: Sustainable Transition or Dangerous Addition to Fossil Fuel Emissions?

JS-22.5 Sophie NEMOZ, *University of Bourgogne Franche-Comté (LaSA MSHE CNRS UAR 3124), France*
Entre Constructions Et Contractions Argileuses, Retrait-Gonflement Anthropo-Lithique

tuesday 27 June

08:30 - 10:20

JS-23 Authority and Authoritarianism Revisited. Part ii

Committees: RC07 *Futures Research*, RC16 *Sociological Theory*

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Chad GOLDBERG, *University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States*

Chair: Zezheng LIN, *School of Foreign Languages, Renmin University of China, China*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-23.1 Habibul KHONDKER, *Zayed University, United Arab Emirates*
Semi-Authoritarianism or Authoritarian Democracy on the Rise: South Asian Perspective

JS-23.2 Uri BEN ELIEZER, *University of Haifa, Israel* and Adriana KEMP, *Tel Aviv University, Israel*
Questioning Neoliberal Authority: Changing Patterns of Peace Activities in Israel

JS-23.3 Fernando CASTANOS, *Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, Mexico* and Matilde LUNA, *Coyoacan, Mexico*
Disproportionate Judgement and Other Challenges to Democratic Equilibria Posed By Populist Discourse: An Interdisciplinary Discussion

JS-23.4 Felipe GARCIA, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*; Gustavo HIGA, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*; Pedro CALLARI TRIVINO MOISES, *Yale University, USA* and Roberta NOVELLO, *Center for the Study of Violence / University of São Paulo (NEV/USP), Brazil*
The Idea of Authoritarianism in Brazilian Sociology: A Critical Review

JS-23.5 Ruanzhenghao SHI, *University of Chicago, USA*
State Repression and Political Orientation of Collective Action in China: A Multiple-Case Study of Student Activism at Peking University

JS-24 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part iv

Committees: RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology, RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*

Chair: Nadia ASHEULOVA, *Institute for the History of Science and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-24.1 Giulio PITROSO, *Griffith University, Australia*
Gamers and Far Right's Values in Australia

JS-24.2 Tianyun LIU, *Southeast University, China*
Cyber Utopia: Birth and Death—the Spatiotemporal Utopianism of Cyberspace

JS-24.3 Juan FERNANDEZ-PRADOS, *University of Almeria, Spain*; Cristina CUENCA PIQUERAS, *University of Almeria, Spain*; María PUNTA-GARCÍA, *University of Almeria, Spain* and María TORRES HARO, *Universidad de Almería, Spain*
Digital Activism Around the World: Comparative, Intergenerational and Gender Analysis of Social and Political Activism.

JS-24.4 Santiago CARASSALE REAL, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Sede México, Mexico*; Javier CONTRERAS ALCANTARA, *El Colegio de San Luis, Mexico* and Liliana MARTINEZ PEREZ, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Sede Académica de México, Mexico*
Fronteras Digitales y Futuros Antroposintéticos: Tensiones Sociales y Políticas

JS-24.5 Karmvir PADDA, *University of Waterloo, Canada*
Radical or Radicalized? Role of Power, Discourse, and Subjectivity in the Jan 6th Insurrection

JS-25 Digital Mediation of Children's Learning and the Changing Ecology of Home-School-World Connectivity

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood, TG10 Digital Sociology*

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Sue NICHOLS, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Karen DOOLEY, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

Chair: Sue NICHOLS, *University of South Australia, Australia*

Co-Chair: Karen DOOLEY, *Queensland University of Technology, Australia*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-25.1 Liz TODD, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*; Lucy TIPLADY, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*; Luke BRAHALL, *Children North East, United Kingdom*; Suzanne BUTLER, *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*; Gwen DALZIEL, *Children North East, United Kingdom* and Cathryn GATHERCOLE, *Children North East, United Kingdom*
Collision, Separation and Appreciation of Home and School Lives in Covid-19 for Children and Young People

JS-25.2 Seran DEMIRAL, *Istanbul Arel University, Turkey*
"Artificial Intelligence Is like a Baby" Children's Commentaries on Technological Developments

JS-25.3 Ayse YILMAZ, *Bahcesehir University, Turkey*
Generational Relations and the Silencing of Children in the Making of School Shows at Public Primary Schools in Istanbul

JS-26 Human Dimensions of Development and Sustainable Development Goals

Committees: TG03 *Human Rights and Global Justice, RC24 Environment and Society*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Govt. College Chamba HP, India*

Chair: Bhup SINGH, *Maharshi Dayanand University, India*

Co-Chair: Hans RAJ, *Govt. of Himachal Pradesh, India*

Panelists: Harjinder SINGH, *Punjabi University Patiala, India, India*; Jasbir SINGH, *Punjab Institute of Oriental & Indian Languages (PIOIL), India* and Dr. Varinder SINGH, *Northern Regional Languages Centre, Patiala, India, India*

Discussants: Dr KAUR, *Association of Medical Social Workers, Pgimer, Chandigarh, India* and Dr. Jaspal SINGH, *Northern Regional Language Centre, Patiala, India, India*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-26.1 Sebat MALIK, *Giri Institute of Development Studies, Sector-O, Aliganj Extension, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India, India*
Impact of Migration on Mountains with Special Reference to Uttarakhand Himalayas in India

JS-26.2 Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, *Department of Higher Education, India*
CDM Based Exploitation of Natural Resources: A Threat to Existing Traditional Knowledge- a Case Study of Chanju Basin in Churah Tehsil of Chamba District of Himachal Pradesh

JS-26.3 Sreyasi CHATTERJEE, *Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, India*
Tradition of Conservation: A Sociological Exploration of the Role of Indigenous Culture and Knowledge Systems in

Promoting Ecological Conservation in Bara Mangwa and Chhota Mangwa of Darjeeling District in West Bengal India.

JS-26.4 Tanja GANGAROVA, *The German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Germany* and Yildiz YILDIZ, *Network BeKAM, Germany*
CBPR with Communities Affected By Racial Injustice: Reflections on Power and Privilege

JS-27 Making up People: Classification and Quantification in the Population Census. Part ii

Committees: RC55 Social Indicators, RC41 Sociology of Population

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Walter BARTL, *Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany* and Alberto VEIRA-RAMOS, *Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain*

Chair: Walter BARTL, *Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-27.1 Byron VILLACIS, *UC Berkeley, USA*
Quieter, Powerful and Uncontested: Implications of Methodological Changes in Population Censuses

JS-27.2 Saori KAMANO, *National Institute of Population and Social Security Research, Japan*
Can We Capture Same-Sex Couples in Surveys? Erasure of Same-Sex Couples in Population Census and Comparable Surveys in Japan

JS-27.3 Leila FARDEAU, *National Institute of Demographic Studies, France*; Eva LELIEVRE, *National Institute of Demographic Studies, France* and Loic TRABUT, *National Institute of Demographic Studies, France*
Complex Households, a Challenge for the Study of Families through Census Data. Principles for the Construction of a Typology, the Example of French Polynesia.

JS-28 Religious Actors and Social Movements: the Public Sphere

Committees: RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements, RC22 Sociology of Religion

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*

Chair: Claude DARGENT, *Cresppe, France*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-28.1 Adrian ROSENFELDT, *La Trobe University, Australia*
The English Post-9/11 God Debate between Religious Apologists and New Atheist Agitators

JS-28.2 Siyoon LEE, *Sungkyunkwan University, Republic of Korea*
How Korean Religions Enter the Public Sphere: From the Internal Competition Toward the External Engagement

JS-28.3 Matt WADE, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Christian Nationalism and the Movement to Build an 'Alternative Internet'

JS-28.4 Tyka RAHMAN, *State Islamic University (UIN) Bukittinggi, Indonesia*
Public Sphere and Islamization

JS-28.5 Victor ALBERT BLANCO, *Université Toulouse 2, France*

Loving and Controlling Diversity. Neighbors' Associations and Religious Pluralism in European Cities.

JS-28.6 Rajesh MISRA, *University of Lucknow, India*
Three Mass Mobilizations, Three Religions and Differential Equations: An Appraisal of People's Unrest in Contemporary India

JS-29 Working Abroad: the Experience of Mobile Professionals in Foreign Labour Markets

Committees: RC52 Sociology of Professional Groups, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: 109 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Elena SAMARSKY, *Independent Researcher, USA* and Ilana NUSSBAUM BITRAN, *Universität Bremen, Germany*

Co-Chair: Ilana NUSSBAUM BITRAN, *Universität Bremen, Germany*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-29.1 Ilju KIM, *Utsunomiya University, Japan* and Sung Chul NOH, *Saitama University, Japan*
Becoming a Transnational Professional: Skill Development Processes Among Migrant Professionals in Japan

JS-29.2 Minori MATSUTANI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan*
Professional Migrants in the Enclaved Labor Market: Japanese Migrant Workers in Transnational Corporations

JS-29.3 Aimi MURANAKA, *University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*
(Un)Expected Return? the Study on the Vietnamese It Professionals Mobilities and Japanese Private Intermediaries

JS-29.4 Jian-Bang DENG, *Tamkang University, Taiwan*
Skilled Migrants Go South: Taiwanese Professionals in Indonesia and Vietnam

JS-30 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (1)

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC04 Sociology of Education

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Ilaria PITTI, *University of Bologna, Italy* and Jacqueline KENNELLY, *Carleton University, Canada*

Chairs: Harriet ROWLEY, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom* and Demet LUKUSLU, *Yeditepe University, Turkey*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-30.1 Maja ADOLFSSON, *Department of Sociology at Umeå University, Sweden*
Exploring the Barriers, Enablers and Strategies for Political Action Among Youth Activists in Rural Sweden

JS-30.2 Milo KEI, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
Political Practices As Repertoires of Protest Action in Young School Strikers in Australia

JS-30.4 Hadrien HOLSTEIN, *Université Paris Nanterre, France*
How to Continue the War without Having Lived It? Patterns of Engagement and Participation of Young Republicans in Northern Ireland

JS-30.5 Cristhian URIBE MENDOZA, *Universidad Santo Tomas, Colombia*
I Protest, Therefore I Am. an Analysis of Youth Political Mobilization in Colombia (2019-2021)

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-30.6 Alice WEAVERS, *King's College London, United Kingdom*
'Pockets of Participation': Exploring the Experiences of Young People and Policymakers Involved in Youth Participation in National Policymaking in England.

JS-30.7 Ruben DIEZ GARCIA, *Complutense University of Madrid, Spain*; Gomer BETANCOR NUEZ, *Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED), Spain* and Josué GUTIÉRREZ BARROSO, *Universidad de La Laguna, Spain*
A Decade of Youth Activism in Spain: From the Indignados 15M Movement to the Pandemic

10:30 - 12:20

JS-31 Art and Alienation

Committees: RC37 *Sociology of Arts*, RC36 *Alienation Theory and Research*

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session organizer: Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*

Chair: Ilaria RICCIONI, *Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-31.1 Malfrid Irene HAGEN, *Independent researcher, Norway*
Diversity or Anomie? Does Contemporary Art Reflect Diversity or Anomie in Societies Marked By Changes and Crisis?

JS-31.2 Chien LEE, *Goldsmiths, University of London, Taiwan*
The Immersive and the Outside: Visitor Photography and the Art Experience in Taiwan

JS-31.3 Yasunori MORI, *Hakuhodo Incorporated, Japan*
Cultural Capital Determines How Happy One Feels in Japan

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-31.4 Priyam SINHA, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Disability, Stardom, Awards and the Comeback Genre in New Bollywood

JS-32 International Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Labour-Capital Relations

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society*, RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: June WANG, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Julia TOMASSETTI, *City University of Hong Kong, USA*

Chair: June WANG, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-32.1 Kenshin NAKANO, *Institute of Labor Economics and Industrial Sociology, Aix-Marseille University, France*
How Does the Platform Work Destabilize the National Employment Systems ?

JS-32.2 Jian XIAO, *Zhejiang University, China* and Wanyi CHENJIN, *Sun Yat-sen University, China*
"Emo-Slave"?: A Study on the Affective Labour in the Netease Cloud Music Platform

JS-32.3 Monique MCKENZIE, *The University of Sydney, Australia*
Visions of Digital Labour: How the Motivation for Accumulation Informs the Nature of the Platformed Labour Relationship.

JS-32.4 Chunhao HUANG, *Institute of Sociology, Academia Sinica, Taiwan*
The Digital Transformation of Labor Process in Taiwan's Mold Manufacturing and Plastic Injection Industry

JS-32.5 Julia TOMASSETTI, *Swinburne University of Technology, School of Business, Law and Entrepreneurship, Australia*
Original Content Producers and Contemporary Debates on Labour Law and Policy

Discussion**JS-33 Marine Justice, Ocean Studies, and Coastal Communities**

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society*, RC03 *Community Research*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Patricia WIDENER, *Florida Atlantic University, USA*

Chair: Patricia WIDENER, *Florida Atlantic University, USA*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-33.1 Monjurul AHSAN, *Center for Climate Justice-Bangladesh (CCJ-B), Bangladesh*
Loss and Damage in the Indigenous Way of Life and Opportunity for Sustainable Livelihood: A Case Study in Munda Community of Bangladesh

JS-33.2 Shaikh Mohammad KAIS, *University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh*
Debunking the Myths: Shrimp Aquaculture and Environmental Degradation in Bangladesh

JS-33.3 Danielle NEMBHARD, *James Cook University, Australia*
Intersectionality and Climate Justice: Implications for Assisted Ecosystem Adaption on the Great Barrier Reef

JS-33.4 Mark STODDART, *Memorial University of Newfoundland & Labrador, Canada* and Ásthildur BERNHARÐSDÓTTIR, *Bifröst University, Iceland*
Regionalizing the Sustainable Development Goals for Coastal and Island Communities: Lessons from Iceland and Newfoundland and Labrador

JS-33.5 Belinda WHEATON, *University of Waikato, New Zealand*; Rebecca OLIVE, *RMIT, Australia* and Jordan WAITI, *University of Waikato, New Zealand*
Understanding Coastal Communities and Ecologies: The Surf Zone in Aotearoa New Zealand

JS-34 Religious Actors and Social movements: Gender and Sexual Diversity

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements*, RC22 *Sociology of Religion*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*

Chair: Mar GRIERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-34.1 Cristhian URIBE MENDOZA, *Universidad Santo Tomas, Colombia*
The Impact of Evangelical Movements on the Recognition of LGBTI Rights in Latin America

JS-34.2 Neha REJI, *Ph.D. Sociology-Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India*
Church, Crisis, Women: A Study of the Ongoing Conflict between Jacobite and Orthodox Churches of Kerala Syrian Christians

JS-34.3 Nicola RIGHETTI, *University of Vienna, Austria*; Rita MARCHETTI, *University of Perugia, Italy*; Susanna PAGIOTTI, *University of Perugia, Italy* and Anna STANZIANO, *University of Urbino, Italy*
Religion-Based Movements and Right-Wing Alliances Against Abortion and LGBTIQ+ Rights. the Case of the Italian 2022 Elections on Twitter.

JS-34.4 Claude DARGENT, *Cresppe, France*
Collective Action on Gender Equality and Sexuality: The Weight of Religious Affiliations in Europe Today

JS-34.5 Cecilia DELGADO-MOLINA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*; Rosario RAMÍREZ-MORALES, *Universidad de Guadalajara, Mexico*; Rafael CAZARIN DE BRITO, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Erick Adrián PAZ, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM), Mexico*
Biomedical Narratives Around Gender and Sexuality in Religious Contexts: The Case of Digital Activisms in Mexico and Spain

JS-35 the Collaboration and Solidarity of Local and Ethnic Residents in Global Cities

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Tetsuo MIZUKAMI, *Rikkyo University, 3-34-1, Japan* and Dharma ARUNACHALAM, *Monash University, Australia*

Chairs: Tetsuo MIZUKAMI, *Rikkyo University, 3-34-1, Japan* and Dharma ARUNACHALAM, *Monash University, Australia*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-35.1 Tatsuto ASAKAWA, *Waseda University, Japan*
The Spatial Distribution of Bottom Workers in Tokyo

JS-35.2 Hanne WORSOE, *School of Social Science, Australia* and Sonia ROITMAN, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Solidarity Networks and Strategies in COVID-19 Lockdowns Experienced By International University Students in Brisbane/SEQ Australia

JS-35.3 Motohiro KOIZUMI, *Rikkyo University, Japan*
Multicultural Society and Art: The Significance and Limits of 'social Inclusion' through Collaborative Expression

JS-35.4 Nobuaki FUJIOKA, *Shizuoka University, Japan*
Relations between the Global City and Regional Cities in Building Solidarity Among Local and Ethnic Residents: A Case Study of Tokyo and Hamamatsu

JS-35.5 Karim MURJI, *University of West London, United Kingdom*; Susannah CRAMER, *Warwick University, United Kingdom*; Michael KEITH, *Oxford University, United Kingdom*; Steve PILE, *Open University, United Kingdom*; John SOLOMOS, *University of Warwick, United Kingdom* and Eda YAZICI, *Warwick University, United Kingdom*
Community between Openness and Closedness

JS-35.6 Stijn OOSTERLYNCK, *University of Antwerp, Belgium* and Fatima LAOUKILI, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
Creating Multicultural Collaboration in Local Civil Society in Superdiverse Urban Neighbourhoods. the Case of Borgerhout, Belgium.

JS-36 transformative Research, Education and World Social Forum

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management, RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

Location: M10 (Crown)

Session organizers: Erik LINDHULT, *Mälardalen University, Sweden* and Azril BACAL ROIJ, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

Chair: Nikita POKROVSKY, *National Research University - High School of Economics, Russian Federation*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-36.1 Azril BACAL ROIJ, *Uppsala University, Sweden* and Erik LINDHULT, *Mälardalen University, Sweden*
Dialogue As a Social Research Orientation and Method within the Framework of Participatory Action-Research

JS-36.2 Luz MONTELONGO, *Instituto de Investigaciones Gino Germani, Argentina*; Juan Bruno FERENAZ, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*; Jose Manuel Grima JOSE MANUEL GRIMA, *Instituto Gino Germani, Argentina* and Alberto Leonard BIALAKOWSKY, *Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Investigative Co-Production. a Look from the Dialogic Methodology

JS-36.3 Vera VRATUSA, *University of Belgrade, Serbia*
Is the World Social Forum Dead?

JS-37 Youth and Crises of Democracy: Exploring the Democratic Potential of Young People's Participation (2)

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth, RC04 Sociology of Education, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Cihan ERDAL, *Carleton University, Canada*; Demet LUKUSLU, *Yeditepe University, Turkey* and Harriet ROWLEY, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom*

Chairs: Iliaria PITTI, *University of Bologna, Italy* and Jacqueline KENNELLY, *Carleton University, Canada*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-37.1 James GORING, *School of Education, Deakin University, Australia*
Disadvantaged, Marginalised and/or Disengaged Young People and the Politics of Participation and Voice

JS-37.2 Ben LAKSANA, *Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand*
Learning Critical Consciousness: Higher Education Student Activists in Yogyakarta

JS-37.3 Lena MOLNAR, *RMIT, Australia*
'ignite That Change from within' - Young People's Use of Social Media to Drive Collective Action Against Gender-Based Violence

JS-37.4 Marina MEDAN, *LICH - Universidad de San Martín / CONICET, Argentina*
Citizenship Experiences in Youth Inclusion Programs in Argentina

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-37.5 Ma. glenda WUI, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*; Jessica Sandra CLAUDIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*; Carl REYES, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*; Rosselle Trishia REYES, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines* and Enrique Nino LEVISTE, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*
Online and Outspoken: Role of Political Conversations in Enhancing Youth Digital Civic Engagement

JS-37.6 Pekka KAUNISMAA, *Humak University of Applied Sciences, Finland*
Profiles of Participation in Voluntary Activities Among Finnish Youth

15:30 - 17:20

JS-38 Collective Memories of Violence: Remembering in Families and Local Communities

Committees: RC38 *Biography and Society*, RC56 *Historical Sociology*

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Gabriele ROSENTHAL, *Georg-August University of Göttingen, Germany*; Miriam SCHAEFER, *Georg-August-University Goettingen, Germany* and Deniz DEMIRHISAR, *IFEA (Institut français d'études anatoliennes) / CETOBAC - EHESS, Turkey*

Chair: Maria POHN-LAUGGAS, *University of Göttingen, Germany*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-38.1 Ashley BARNWELL, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
'Deep Stories' at the Dinner Table: Forgetting and Remembering Colonisation in Australian Settler Families

JS-38.2 Sarah KOENECKE, *Georg-August-University Goettingen, Germany* and Miriam SCHAEFER, *Georg-August-University Goettingen, Germany*
The Simultaneity of Persecution and Perpetration - (Competing) Memories of the German National Socialist Past in Families of Stigmatized Victims

JS-38.3 Fira CHMIEL, *LICH, UNSAM/CONICET, Argentina*
"a Place in Which to Put the Story": Childhood, Exile and Available Social Narratives to Place a Biographical Experience.

JS-38.4 Lucas CE SANGALLI, *University of Goettingen, Germany*
Physical Violence As a Component in the Transmission of Ethnic Belonging: Changing We- and They-Images in the Dialogue of Families from Sudan Living in Jordan

JS-39 Digital Futures between Domination and Participation. Part i

Committees: RC14 *Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture*, RC07 *Futures Research*, RC10 *Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management*, RC23 *Sociology of Science and Technology*, TG10 *Digital Sociology*

Location: 213 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Isabel DA COSTA, *CNRS, IDHES, ENS Paris-Saclay, France*

Chair: Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*

Discussant: Jose A. RUIZ SAN ROMAN, *Universidad Complutense, Spain*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-39.1 Naomi SMITH, *University of the Sunshine Coast, Australia*; Jenny DAVIS, *The Australian National University, Australia* and Aleesha RODRIGUEZ, *ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child, Queensland University of Technology, Australia*
The Internet: Moving from Failure to Flourishing

JS-39.2 Attila MARTON, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*
A Digital Future of Resilience. What Can We Learn from Ecological Thinking?

JS-39.3 Jiyoun KIM, *Hansung University, Republic of Korea*
Old but Smart Data for Smart Cities

JS-39.4 Anna CHERNOIVANOVA, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation* and Aleksei SHCHEKIN, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*
Between High Technology and Low Social Status: Digital Practices of People in an Unstable Life Situation

JS-39.5 Rewa MARATHE, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Feminists Speak Binary: Role of Digital Technology in Feminist Advocacy Work

JS-39.6 Kieran HEGARTY, *RMIT University, Australia*
Recording the Digital Present, Shaping Digital Futures: How People Relate to Their Ageing Digital Traces

JS-40 Everyday Practices of 'othering': ongoing Developments. Part i

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society*, RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*

Chair: Magdalena LEMANCZYK, *Institute of Political Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-40.1 Arvinder A. ANSARI, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India* and Hina KAUSAR, *Jamia Millia Islamia, India*
The Politics of the Veil in India: Contesting Stereotypical Representations of Muslim Women

JS-40.2 Shila KHAYAMBASHI, *York University, Canada*
"Where Are You from?": The Constant Reminder of Unhomeliness

JS-40.3 Gabriela MEZZANOTTI, *University of South-Eastern Norway, Norway* and Alyssa Marie KVALVAAG, *Nord University, Norway*
Interlocking Oppressions, Crossing Categories, and Rights: A Critical Analysis on the Impact of Categorization Defining Human Rights of Indigenous Migrants from Latin America

JS-40.4 Annavittoria SARLI, *University of Parma - IT00308780345, United Kingdom*
From "Being Othered" to "Promoting the Value of Otherness": Empowering Self-Narratives Among Migrant Immediate Descendants in Italy

JS-40.5 Yu-ying HU, *Kaohsiung Medical University, Taiwan*
The Revolting "Blue Gay": Sexualized Nationalism, Emerging National Others, and an Alternative to the Homonationalistic Construction in Contemporary Taiwan

JS-41 Globalization-induced Resistance Movements (involving Displacements, identity and Ecological issues). Part I

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC24 Environment and Society

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Binay Kumar PATTNAIK, Kanpur 208016, India

Chair: Binay Kumar PATTNAIK, Kanpur 208016, India

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-41.1 Akhaya Kumar NAYAK, *Indian Institute of Management Indore, India*
Revival of a Protest Movement: The Struggle of an Indian Village Against Mega Development Projects

JS-41.2 Bibhuti Bhusan MOHANTY, *Department of Sociology, India*
Displacement Movements and the Emerging State-TRIBE Relationship in India

JS-41.3 Apratyasita TRIPATHY, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*
Riot-Induced Displacement and Migration By the Tribals of Kandhamal: A Post-Facto Study

JS-41.4 Ngamjahao KIPGEN, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India*
Hydropower Projects, Resistance, and Environmentalism in Northeast India

JS-41.5 Dipti Ranjan SAHU, *University of Lucknow, India*
Assessing the Trajectories of People's Movements in Odisha, India

JS-42 international Migration and Economic informalization: A Denationalized Perspective - Part ii

Committees: RC30 Sociology of Work, RC02 Economy and Society, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Klara OBERG, *Halmstad University, Sweden* and Zoran SLAVNIC, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Chair: Klara OBERG, *Halmstad University, Sweden*

Co-Chair: Zoran SLAVNIC, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Discussant: David FASENFEST, *Wayne State University, USA*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-42.1 Hironori ONUKI, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
Making Decent Employers Perpetrators: A Denationalized Perspective on Informalization within Japan's Technical Intern Trainee Program

JS-42.2 Ahmet COLGECEN, *PhD, Hacettepe University, Turkey*
Turkey As a Transit Country on the International Migrant Route: Economic Informalization and Precarity

JS-42.3 Pei PALMGREN, *Stanford University, USA*
Governing Guestwork in the Global South: Temporal and Spatial Logics of Migration Control and Social Reproduction in Thailand

JS-42.4 Thamali RANASINGHE, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Michelle SYDES, *Griffith University, Australia*
Perceptions of Immigrants As a Threat to Economy, Culture and Security in Australia

JS-43 Religious Actors and Social Movements: the Ecological turn

Committees: RC22 Sociology of Religion, RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Karina Berenice BARCENAS BARAJAS, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Olga OLIVAS HERNANDEZ, *El Colegio de la Frontera Norte A.C., Mexico*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-43.1 Barbare JANELIDZE, *University of Kassel, Germany*
River Guardians: Socio-Ecological Movements in the Post-Soviet Georgia

JS-43.2 Jonathan D. SMITH, *Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia*
Studying Environmental Social Movements As Sites of (Inter)Religious Cooperation and Transformation in Indonesia

JS-43.3 Dobrosława WIKTOR-MACH, *Cracow University of Economics, Poland* and Konrad PEDZIWIATR, *Cracow University of Economics, Poland*
Catholic Environmental Movement in Poland and Its Key Challenges

JS-43.4 Rose-marie STAMBE, *The University of Queensland, Australia* and Cameron PARSELL, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Christianity, Helping the Poor, and Relationships to Drive Structural Transformation

JS-43.5 Somayeh TOHIDLOU, *Assistant Professor of Institute of Humanities and Cultural Studies, Iran*
The Constitutional Movement and the Continuation of Its Religious Activism until Today in Iran

JS-44 Variegated intersections of Social Policy and Finance

Committees: RC19 Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy, RC02 Economy and Society

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Asa MARON, *University of Haifa, Israel*

Chair: Ben SPIES-BUTCHER, *Macquarie University, Australia*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-44.1 Adam STEBBING, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Asset-Based Welfare, Risk and Inequality: The Rise of Self-Managed Superannuation Funds in Australia

JS-44.2 Lavinia BIFULCO, *University of Milano Bicocca, Italy* and Maria DODARO, *University of Padua, Italy*
Local Public Action for Financial Inclusion: Representations, Limits and Agency

JS-44.3 Kalpeshkumar Ambalal CHAUHAN, *INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANPUR, India* and Jillet Sarah SAM, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India, India*
Dealing with Credit Scores: The Work of Microfinance Loan Officers in Rural Gujarat, India

JS-44.4 Ray JUREIDINI, *Hamad Bin Khalifa University, Qatar*
Unhcr Refugee Zakat Fund

JS-44.5 Gustavo Jorge ZALDIVAR, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico*; Delfino VARGAS, *Programa*

Universitario de Estudios del Desarrollo, Mexico and Fernando CORTES, National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico
The Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Productivity Strata of the Economic Sectors of Mexico in 2005 and 2020.

DiSt RiBUT ED PAPERS:

JS-44.6 Armi MUSTOSMÄKI, University of Jyväskylä, Finland
The Figure of Femeconomicus – Postfeminist Reconfigurations of Femininity in Financialized Welfare State

17:30 - 19:20

JS-45 Everyday Practices of 'othering': ongoing Developments. Part ii

Committees: RC25 Language and Society, RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Stephanie CASSILDE, Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium

Chair: Anna ODRÓWAZ-COATES, Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-45.1 Maria Cristina BAYON, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México
Othering and Social Abjection Under the Neoliberal Paradigm. Declassifying Disadvantaged Youth Figures in Latin American Cities

JS-45.2 Ifeanyi NWACHUKWU, United Kingdom, United Kingdom
Exploring Voice and Marginalisation: Critical Reflections on Black Young People

JS-45.3 Gabriel LIU, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom; Dong DONG, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; Faustina YIP, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; Yan ZENG, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; Xin WEN, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; Daisy ZHANG, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong and Samuel WONG, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong
The Identitive Labor of Chinese Immigrants in COVID-19: The Good, the Bad and the Ugly

JS-45.4 Shahab MIRBABAEI, Karlstad University, Sweden
The Role of Phenotypical Markers in Swedish Racialization

JS-45.5 Charif ELALAOUI, Université de Caen, France
Les Gilets Jaunes Et Les Quartiers Populaires, Quelles (dés) Articulations ?

JS-46 Gender in Skilled Migration: Beyond Western Perspectives

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration, RC32 Women, Gender and Society

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Helena HOF, University of Zurich / Max Planck Institute for the Study of Religious and Ethnic Diversity, Switzerland; Joohyun Justine PARK, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany; Ruth ACHENBACH, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany; Megha WADHWA, Free University of Berlin, Germany and Aimi MURANAKA, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany

Chair: Megha WADHWA, Free University of Berlin, Germany

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-46.1 Minoru MATSUTANI, Otemon Gakuin University, Japan
Challenging Gendered Norms of Skilled Migrants in Transnational Companies: Case Study of Japanese Professionals in Germany

JS-46.2 Minjeong KIM, San Diego State University, USA and Iju KIM, Utsunomiya University, Japan
Diverging Paths for Highly-Skilled Immigrants: A Comparative Study of Two Male-Dominated Sectors

JS-46.3 Claudia WRIGHT, Utah State University, USA
Privileged Transmigrant Motherhood and the Reframing of Oppression As Liberation

JS-46.4 Christina KEFALA, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Women Who Tech: Strategies and Branding Among Foreign Women Entrepreneurs in China

JS-46.5 Ibrahimia Amadou DIA, African Centre for the Study and Research on Migration - African Union Commission, Mali
African Female Skilled International Migration, Brain Waste, and Precarity from an Intersectional Perspective

JS-47 Historical Sociology of organizations. Part i

Committees: RC17 Sociology of Organization, RC56 Historical Sociology

Location: M11 (Crown)

Session organizers: Robert VAN KRIEKEN, University of Sydney, Australia and Stewart CLEGG, UTS, Australia

Chair: Robert VAN KRIEKEN, University of Sydney, Australia

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-47.1 Stewart CLEGG, UTS, Australia
A History of the Present

JS-47.2 Dean WILSON, University of Sussex, United Kingdom
Genealogies of Platform Policing: Time, Economy and Organization

JS-47.3 Vera LINKE, Helmut-Schmidt University Hamburg, Germany
The Organizational Imaginary of Insurance

JS-48 integrative and Disintegrative Processes in Europe and Eurasia: Public opinion, State Politics and Media Discourse.

Committees: WG01 Sociology of Local-Global Relations, RC26 Sociotechnics, Sociological Practice

Location: 101 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Nataliya VELIKAYA, Institute of Social and Political Research of Russian Academy of Science, Russian Federation and Flaminia SACCA, Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy

Chair: Nataliya VELIKAYA, Russian State University for the Humanities, Russian Federation

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-48.1 Valentina SHILOVA, Korpus 5, Russian Federation
Management Using "Soft Power" on the Example of International Communications

JS-48.2 Camilla FOLENA, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy, Italy* and Gea DUCCHI, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
Decolonising Media Discourses during the Information Warfare: An East-Eurasian Perspective of the Russian-Ukrainian Conflict from Google News

JS-48.3 Sarvesh TRIPATHI, *GGSIIP University New Delhi, India*
Economic, Diplomatic and Geopolitical Narratives of Russia Ukraine Crisis By Media: A Study of Select Digital Print Media of India and West

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-48.4 Juma RASULI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Afghanistan*; Abdul SARWARI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, India* and Fatima KARIMI, *Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, India*
A Study on the Impact of Digital Marketing on Export Growth Afghanistan – India

JS-49 Labor Unrest, Social Revolts and Revolutions, 1851-2020: Findings from the Global Social Protest Database

Committees: RC44 Labor Movements, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC02 Economy and Society

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Beverly SILVER, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*

Chair: Beverly SILVER, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*

Panelists: Minhyoung KANG, *Jeonbuk National University, Republic of Korea*; Smriti UPADHYAY, *American University of Cairo, Egypt* and Beverly SILVER, *Johns Hopkins University, USA*

JS-50 Navigating the Other Side of the Classroom: Exploring teachers' Experiences at Work

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education, RC30 Sociology of Work

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Adrienne ATTERBERRY, *State University of New York (SUNY) at New Paltz, USA*

Chair: Adrienne ATTERBERRY, *State University of New York (SUNY) at New Paltz, USA*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-50.1 Nayani SARMA, *JAWAHARLAL NEHRU UNIVERSITY, India*
Teaching during a Pandemic: The Gender Dynamics (Qualitative Research)

JS-50.2 Warren ROMA, *University of Southern Queensland, Australia*
Leading Schools from the Rainbow: The Challenges and Complexities of Being an LGBT Primary School Leader in Australia

JS-50.3 Chrysa KEUNG, *The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Kindergarten Teachers' Emotions and Ethical Dilemmas at Work in the Time of COVID-19

JS-50.4 Scott FITZGERALD, *Curtin University, Australia*; Susan MCGRATH-CHAMP, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Mihajla GAVIN, *The University of Technology, Australia*; Rachel WILSON, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Meghan STACEY, *UNSW, Australia*
'Core' or 'Administration'?: Navigating Teacher Workload Strategies

JS-50.5 Alexandre VIRGINIO, *Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
High School Reform and Teaching Profession

JS-50.6 Djurdjica DEGAC, *Faculty of Humanites and Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Croatia*
'I Also Realized That I Don't Miss That Job at All' - Narrative Analysis of Female Teachers' Work-Family Trajectories and Their Intentions Towards Leaving the Profession

JS-51 Political Socialization in Changing Times: Generations and Agents.

Committees: RC18 Political Sociology, RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Daniel MIRANDA, *P. Catholic University of Chile, Chile* and Maria magdalena ISAC, *Centre for Political Research, KU Leuven, Belgium*

Chair: Natalia MIRANDA, *Aarhus University, Denmark*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-51.1 Zareh GHAZARIAN, *Monash University, Australia*; Jacqueline LAUGHLAND-BOOY, *Monash University, Australia*; Zlatko SKRBIS, *Monash University, Australia* and Jonathan F. SMITH, *Australian Catholic University, Australia*
Women and Political Participation in Australia

JS-51.2 Carina KRAFT, *The University of Adelaide, Australia*
Social Media Influencers As Agents in Political Socialisation Processes of Their Followers: Self-Perceived Opinion Leadership and the Creation of Online Communities

JS-51.3 Anthony SPIRES, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
The Authoritarian Society: Chinese Civil Society and the (Re) Production of Hegemonic Authoritarianism

JS-51.4 Felipe SÁNCHEZ-BARRÍA, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
Interest in Politics and Participation in Protests in Chile Today: A Longitudinal Analysis.

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-51.5 Santa Giuseppina TUMMINELLI, *University of Palermo, Italy* and Marilena MACALUSO, *Palermo University, Italy*
The Political Socialisation of Second Generation Migrants

JS-51.6 Robin ARCHER, *London School of Economics, United Kingdom*
Postmaterialist Values and Opposition to War: Comparing Generations

JS-52 Understanding the Sociological Interplay of Emotions

Committees: WG08 Society and Emotions, WG06 Institutional Ethnography

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Debra TALBOT, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Mariana NOBILE, *FLACSO Argentina, Argentina*

Chair: Debra TALBOT, *University of Sydney, Australia*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-52.1 Sarah MURRU, *KU Leuven, Belgium*
Diversity and Exclusion: An Institutional Ethnography Exploring Youth's Emotions Linked to Intersecting Experiences of Violence

JS-52.2 May-Linda MAGNUSSEN, *University of Agder, Norway*

Emotions and Ruling Relations in Academia

JS-52.3 Sweta TIWARI, *mahatma gandhi central university, bihar, India*

Unmasking Emotional Cartographies of Culture and Community in the 'Fieldwork/Field'

JS-52.4 Defne OVER, *Texas A&M University, USA*
Enemies, Emotions and the Making of Authoritarian Media: The Turkish Case

JS-52.5 Jimin OH, *Sogang Univ., Republic of Korea*
Social Dynamics of Women's Alienation and Empowerment in Patriarchal Rites

JS-53 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development

Committees: RC03 Community Research, RC37 Sociology of Arts

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Terry Nichols CLARK, *University of Chicago, USA* and Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada*

Chair: Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-53.1 Sabrina PARRACHO SANT'ANNA, *Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Cultural Dynamics and New Art Collectives in the Port Zone of Rio De Janeiro

JS-53.2 Margret KUSENBACH, *University of South Florida, USA* and Elizabeth STROM, *University of South Florida, USA*
Appropriation and Resistance in Vienna's Graffiti and Street Art Scene

JS-53.3 Hyesun JEONG, *University of Cincinnati, USA*
Cultural Placemaking of Street Art: Measuring the Impact of Street Art on Pedestrian Activity and Crime in Cincinnati

JS-53.4 Chia-ling LAI, *National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*
Art Biennials with Multiple Mobile Affordances Emerging in the Global Artistic Field: A Biennial Case Study of Taiwan's Military Archipelago Matsu

JS-53.5 Thanh-Nghi NGUYEN, *Van Lang University, Vietnam*
Graffiti Discourse in Vietnam: Wavering from Art to Vandalism

JS-54 Why Do We need the Visual? Understanding Educational Practices Using Visual Data and Methods.

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education, RC57 Visual Sociology

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Analia MEO, *CONICET, Argentina* and Ana Inés HERAS, *CEDESI-UNSAM- CONICET, Argentina*

Chair: Analia MEO, *CONICET, Argentina*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-54.1 Cathlene HILLIER, *Crandall University, Canada* and Jessica RIZK, *University of Waterloo, Canada*
Investigating Children's Digital Lives: Three Studies Using Visual Research in Canada

JS-54.2 Sue NICHOLS, *University of South Australia, Australia* and Liz TODD, *University of Newcastle, United Kingdom*
Participatory Visual Approaches to Enable Insight into the Complex in- and out- of School Lives of Children and Youth.

JS-54.3 Clarence BATAN, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines* and Vincent VALIENTES, *University of Santo Tomas, Philippines*
Utilizing "Visual Images" in Catechetical Education of the Philippine Catholic Church: Explorations, Discoveries, and Promises

JS-54.4 Graciela DE OLIVEIRA, *universidad nacional de san martin, Argentina*
Experiencias Interdisciplinarias En Residencias De Arte y Aprendizajes a Través De Intercambios De Saberes

JS-54.5 Natalia MOLEON TORRES, *Laboratorio de investigación en Ciencias Humanas, Escuela de Humanidades, Universidad Nacional de San Martin, Argentina* and María Amalia MIANO, *UNSAM CEDESI and INCLUIR Instituto para la Incl. Soc. y el Desarrollo Humano, Argentina*
Interacciones En Una Escuela De Alternancia: Narrar y Analizar Con Fotografías

Wednesday 28 June

08:30 - 10:20

JS-55 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics i

Committees: RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food, RC07 Futures Research

Location: 219 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Kiah SMITH, *U. Queensland, Australia* and Alana MANN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Chair: Alana MANN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-55.1 Peter ANDREE, *Carleton University, Canada* and Charles LEVKOE, *Lakehead University, Canada*
Civil Society Engagement in Food Systems Governance in Canada: Experiences, Gaps and Possibilities

JS-55.2 Kiah SMITH, *U. Queensland, Australia*
Fair Food Futures: 4 Scenarios for Translating Civic Food Politics into Food System Transitions in Australia

JS-55.3 Chul-Kyoo KIM, *Department of Sociology, Korea University, Republic of Korea*
Dynamics of Food Politics and Governance in Seoul, 2011 - 2022

JS-55.4 Kim NIEWOLNY, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Justice MADDEN, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Maureen MCGONAGLE, *Local Environmental Agriculture Project (LEAP), USA*; Katie TROZZO, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Eric BENDFELDT, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Garland MASON, *Virginia Tech, USA* and Kasey OWEN, *Virginia Tech, USA*
The Praxis of "Story Work" from Land to Table: Rhizomatic Considerations for Regional Food Systems

JS-55.5 Mario COSCARELLO, *University of Calabria, Italy*
New Stories for Food Futures. a Latin American Experience of Action Research

JS-56 **Childhoods and Systemic inequalities**

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood*, RC51 *Sociocybernetics*

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey* and Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

Co-chairs: Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey* and Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-56.1 Zoe BAKER, *University of York, United Kingdom*
Structure, Agency and Risk: How Does a Background of Care Affect Graduate Transitions?

JS-56.2 Patrick CHANDA, *School of Graduate Studies, Lingnan University, Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Socioeconomic and Gender Inequalities, Country-Level Social Support, Face-to-Face Bullying and Cyberbullying Victimization Among Adolescents. a Multilevel Cross-National Study

JS-56.3 Fernanda PISMEL, *CNRS Centre Max Weber UMR 5283 - Fernanda PISMEL, France*
More Playgrounds, Police Officers or Other Kids to Play with? Children's Reflections on How to Improve Their Leisure in a Suburb of Curitiba, Brazil

JS-56.4 Iskra PAVEZ, *Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins, Chile*; Juan ORTIZ, *Universidad Las Américas, Chile*; Pablo MARDONES, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile*; Valeria ACUÑA, *Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins, Chile*; Jendery JALDÍN, *Universidad Arturo Prat, Chile*; Sius-Geng SALINAS, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile* and Iciar DUFRAIX, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile*
Childhood in First Person

JS-56.5 Anete ABRAMOWICZ, *Universidade de Sao Paulo, Brazil*; Gabriela TEBET, *Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil* and Tatiane RODRIGUES, *Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos, Brazil*
Babies, Children and Wars.

JS-56.6 Eva LASZLO EVA, *UBB, Romania*
Staying Online: Experience of Cyber Childhood in Transnational Families, the Case of Moldavian and Ukrainian Left-behind Children

JS-57 **Gender-Based Violence and Migration: Global Perspectives**

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration*, RC32 *Women, Gender and Society*

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Erika BUSSE, *Macalester College, USA*; Veronica MONTES, *Bryn Mawr College, USA* and Beatriz PADILLA, *University of South Florida, USA*

Chair: Beatriz PADILLA, *University of South Florida, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-57.1 Francisco LANDEROS JAIME, *Cátedras Conacyt - El Colegio de Sonora, Mexico*; Lizeth Margarita RÍOS GARCÍA, *Instituto para las Mujeres en la Migración IMUMI AC, Mexico*; Sandra Lorena CANO PADILLA, *Instituto para las Mujeres en la Migración IMUMI AC, Mexico*; Yessica Pamela MAAS PÉREZ, *Instituto para las Mujeres en la Migración IMUMI AC, Mexico* and Valeria SCALISSE GARCÍA, *Instituto para las Mujeres en la Migración IMUMI AC, Mexico*
Transnacionalización De La Violencia y Mujeres Solicitantes De Asilo En México

JS-57.2 Lori WILKINSON, *University of Manitoba, Canada*; Catherine HOLTSMANN, *Muriel McQueen Centre for Family Violence Research, Canada* and Myrna DAWSON, *University of Guelph, Canada*
Feminist Intersectional Approaches to Understanding the Experiences of Gender-Based Violence Among Newcomer Women in Canada

JS-57.3 Erika BUSSE, *Macalester College, USA* and Veronica MONTES, *Bryn Mawr College, USA*
Gender-Based Violence Against Deported Women on the U.S.-Mexico Border

JS-57.4 Sara AMIN, *The University of the South Pacific, Fiji*
Motherhood and Institutional Violence Among Displaced Afghan Women

JS-57.5 Maria GONZALEZ FLORES, *Universidade da Coruña, Spain*
Re-Centering Resistance and the Tal'zat Movement: Lessons from Palestinian Feminist, Anticolonial, Emancipatory Mobilizations Against Gender-Based Violence(s)

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-57.6 Retno AGUSTIN, *CIRCLE Indonesia, Indonesia*
Gbv, Migration and Human Trafficking in Eastern Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia

JS-57.7 Cyriac BOUCHET-MAYER, *Santesih. Univ. Montpellier, France*
Gendered-Cultural Expectations and Subjective Violence: Intersectional Analysis of the Associative Support for Lgbtiq Asylum Seekers in France.

JS-57.8 Ilaria MICHELIS, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Between Intersectionality and Assistentialism: Feminist Organisations Supporting Migrant, Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Gbv Survivors in Europe

JS-57.9 Santa Giuseppina TUMMINELLI, *University of Palermo, Italy*
Vulnerability and Well-Being: Female Unaccompanied Migrant Minors in Italy

JS-58 **is nationalism Democratic or Authoritarian?**

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology*, RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Eric WOODS, *University of Plymouth, United Kingdom* and Robert SCHERTZER, *University of Toronto, Canada*

Chair: Anthony MORAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*

Co-Chair: Nicole SATHERLEY, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

Discussant: Wenzhuo ZHANG, *Australian National University, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-58.1 Rene VALDIVIEZO-SANDOVAL, *Universidad Iberoamericana Puebla, Mexico*
The Nationalist Project of the Mexican Government. Democracy or Authoritarianism?

JS-58.2 Simina DRAGOS, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
The Conditions Under Which Nationalism Slips into Authoritarianism: Lessons from the Romanian Context

JS-58.3 Nissim MANNATHUKKAREN, *Dalhousie University, Canada* and Ben ALBRECHT, *Dalhousie University, Canada*
Hindu Nationalism, Authoritarianism and Post-Truth: A Consideration of the Liberal Social Media Response

JS-58.4 Smriti UPADHYAY, *American University in Cairo, Egypt*
From Deferral to Denial? a Comparative-Historical Analysis of Exclusion within Nationalist Projects in India

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-58.5 Mireille MANGA EDIMO, *University of Yaounde II, IRIC, Cameroon*
Democratists or Nationalists? the Identity of Anglophone Secessionism in Cameroon

JS-58.6 Wenzhuo ZHANG, *Australian National University, Australia*
Never Forget the War Crimes of Unit 731: The Autocatalytic Evolution of Chinese Nationalism in Harbin

JS-58.7 Julius MOK, *Asia Institute, University of Melbourne, Australia*
The Ethnocracy of Singapore: Ethnonationalism of Hybrid Regimes

JS-58.8 Matthew M CHEW, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
The Articulation of Nationalism, Identitarianism, and Authoritarianism in Non-Western Societies: The Case of 'Cosmopolitan Nationalism' in China

JS-58.9 Shunsuke TANABE, *Waseda University, Japan*
The Types of Japanese Nationalism and Authoritarian/Democratic Attitudes : A Quantitative Analysis of the Relationship between Nationalism and Democracy

JS-59 Language and Work: the Post-Pandemic Evolutions of Categorizations toward (Un)Employment and Working Conditions

Committees: RC25 *Language and Society*, RC30 *Sociology of Work*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Adeline GILSON, *University of Tours, France* and Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*

Chair: Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-59.1 Heijin OH, *Korea University, Republic of Korea* and Jae-Mahn SHIM, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*
Meanings of Work Among South Koreans during the Economic and Health Problems Due to COVID-19

JS-59.2 Corinne DELMAS, *Gustave Eiffel University, France*
Towards a Re-Evaluation of Legal Employment and Work Standards in France? the Case of the Legal World.

JS-59.3 Letizia MATERASSI, *University of Florence, Italy* and Laura SOLITO, *University of Florence, Italy*
Tell Me It Visually. Infographic Contents for Healthcare Digital Communication during the Covid-19 Emergency

JS-59.4 Everlyn KISEMBE, *Moi University, Kenya*
The Role of Language in Mobility Along the Kenya-Uganda Highway

JS-59.5 Fatima FARINA, *University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy*
Back to Normality. Which One? Old and New Perspectives on Work in the Age of Crises

JS-60 Materiality, Brutality and Risk: Decolonial Readings of the twin Climate and Energy Crisis

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society*, TG04 *Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Andrea LAMPIS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*

Chair: Andrea LAMPIS, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-60.1 Catherine Mei Ling WONG, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Yixi YANG, *Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada*
Public Perceptions of Nuclear Energy in Relation to Climate Change in China

JS-60.2 Reo MAWATARI, *Nagoya City University, Japan*
How Does the Process of Extended Urbanization Incorporate a Remote Island?: The Case Study of Naoshima Island, Japan

JS-60.3 Sara MEJIA MUNOZ, *The University of Queensland, Australia*
Latin America Indigenous People and "Green Extractivism": A Challenged Relation

JS-60.4 Kathryn KOCHAN, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Public Displays of Attention: Exploring a Rare Form of Community Grievance Handling in the Global Mining Sector

JS-60.5 Thounaojam SOMOKANTA, *Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India, India*
Dams, Discourse and Ecology in Neoliberal India

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-60.6 Luis REINA-BERMEDEZ, *Universidade Federal Integracao Latinoamericana, Brazil*; Yesenia PARRADO, *Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Colombia* and Claudia RONDON, *Universidad Nacional Abierta y a Distancia, Colombia*
Political Economy Analysis of Energy Transition in Colombia: The Window of Opportunity of a New Government

JS-61 When Students Protest about the Climate Crisis: Realities, Reactions and Results

Committees: RC34 *Sociology of Youth*, RC48 *Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Sarah PICKARD, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*

Co-chairs: Dena ARYA, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom* and Cécile VAN DE VELDE, *Université de Montréal, Canada*

Panelists: Judith BESSANT, *RMIT University, Australia*; Philippa COLLIN, *Western Sydney University, Australia* and Sarah PICKARD, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*

Discussant: Eve MAYES, *Deakin University, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-61.1 Judith BESSANT, *RMIT University, Australia*
'Nothing More Practical Than a Good Theory': Arendt, Natality and Student Political Action

JS-61.2 Philippa COLLIN, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Student Climate Action and the Making of Viable Democratic Futures

JS-61.3 Sarah PICKARD, *Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France*
Realities, Reactions and Results about Youth-Led Environmental Activism on Climate Change

10:30 - 12:20

JS-62 Demographic Change, Economic Outcomes and Religious Belief

Committees: RC22 Sociology of Religion, RC41 Sociology of Population

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Vegard SKIRBEKK, *University of Oslo, Norway* and Jose NAVARRO, *TU Dresden, Japan*

Chair: Vinod CHANDRA, *Sri J N M P G College, Lucknow University, India*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-62.1 Sascha BECKER, *Monash University, Australia*
Religion and Growth

JS-62.2 Jose NAVARRO, *TU Dresden, Japan*
Are Non-Believers Richer Because Their Populations Grow Less? the Economic Growth Contribution of Populations By Religious Affiliation Compared to the Unaffiliated, 1970 - 2020.

JS-62.3 Weiqian XIA, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland*; Martin KOLK, *Stockholm University, Sweden*; Jan SAARELA, *Åbo Akademi University, Finland* and Vegard SKIRBEKK, *University of Oslo, Norway*
Nudged My Religion Away? - a Register-Based Study on the Impact of Deregulation Law on Religious Affiliation in Highly Secular Finland and the Sociodemographic Heterogeneity

JS-62.4 Asma KHAN, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*
Beliefs and Myths: British Muslim Women Making Sense of Their Economic Inactivity

JS-63 Housing and School Choices in the Unequal City: Uneasy Trade-Offs, New Combinations and Socio-Spatial Consequences

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development, RC04 Sociology of Education

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Quentin RAMOND, *Institute of Urban and Territorial Studies, Pontific Catholic University of Chile, France* and Marco OBERTI, *Observatoire sociologique du changement, Sciences Po, France*

Chair: Quentin RAMOND, *Institute of Urban and Territorial Studies, Pontific Catholic University of Chile, France*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-63.1 Peter RICH, *Cornell University, USA* and Ann OWENS, *University of Southern California, USA*
The Neighborhood-School Structure: A Unifying Framework for Studying Social Contexts within Segregated Systems

JS-63.2 Marta Margherita CORDINI, *Polytechnic of Milan, Italy* and Andrea PARMA, *Polytechnic of Milan, Italy*
The Relevance of Neighbourhood of Residence in Shaping the School Choice in a Quasi-Market Educational System. the Case of Milan

JS-63.3 Thomas MALOUTAS, *Dept of Geography, Harokopio University, Greece* and Katigo KEHROLOGOU, *Dept of Geography, Harokopio University, Greece*
Housing and School Choice in a Lower Middle-Class Neighbourhood of Athens

JS-63.4 Robert VIEF, *Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Urban and Regional Sociology, Germany*
Rent Increases, Mobility Patterns and School Segregation

JS-63.5 Nirmali GOSWAMI, *Tezpur University, India*
Schooling Aspirations and a Neighbourhood School in a North Indian City

JS-64 Reconstructing Knowledge: Digital Humanities and Visual Culture

Committees: RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture, RC57 Visual Sociology

Location: 211 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Christiane WAGNER, *University of São Paulo, Institute of Advanced Studies, USP Global Cities Synthesis Center, Brazil*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-64.1 Walter BARTA, *University of Houston, USA*
An Empirical Approach to the Analytic/Continental Divide

JS-64.2 Swati BANDI, *Indian Institute of Management Bangalore, India*
Digital Media Advocacy and Neoliberal Subjects-in-Waiting: A Critique

JS-64.3 Francisco CADIMA, *Universidade Nova de Lisboa (ICNOVA), Portugal*
Television and Cultural Diversity in Portugal

JS-64.4 Mayurakshi CHAUDHURI, *FLAME University, Pune, India* and Chiranjoy CHATTOPADHYAY, *FLAME University, Pune, India*
Images, Intersectionality, and Their Immersive Experiences: Comics As Socio-Cultural Artifacts in Digital Spaces

JS-65 Sociology and the Climate Science-Politics Gap

Committees: RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology, RC24 Environment and Society

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Thomas SAFFORD, *University of New Hampshire, USA*

Chair: Thomas SAFFORD, *University of New Hampshire, USA*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-65.1 Rolf LIDSKOG, *Environmental Sociology Section, Örebro University, Sweden*
Towards a Mega-Expertise? the IPCC, Transformative Change and the Future of Expertise

JS-65.2 Lorena ALVAREZ, *Universidad de Guanajuato, Mexico*
Climate Change and Sustainability Education: A Fragmented Conceptualization and the Pressing Reorganization of the Latin-American University

JS-65.3 Aldemir OLIVEIRA, *State University of Campinas, Brazil*; Gabriela VILLEN M. SCUTARI, *State University of Campinas, Brazil*; Leda GITAHY, *State University of Campinas, Brazil* and Aleix ALTIMIRAS-MARTIN, *Institute of Geoscience - Unicamp, Brazil*
Youtube and Amazonia on Fire: Dismantling Keystone Science and Technology Institutions

JS-65.4 Teresa DE LEON ESCOBEDO, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
Escalas, Sentido De Urgencia y Narrativas Sociales Sobre El Futuro. Contornos Del Debate Sobre Cambio Climático

JS-65.5 Hamid BULUT, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
Ebbs and Flow of Pro-Environmental Attitudes (and Behaviors): The Case of the 2021 European Flooding.

JS-66 The Covid-19 Crisis, Gender, and the Price of Migrants' invisibility

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration, RC32 Women, Gender and Society

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Manashi RAY, *West Virginia State University, USA*

Chair: Manashi RAY, *West Virginia State University, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-66.1 Jennifer GLICK, *Pennsylvania State University, USA* and Scott YABIKU, *Pennsylvania State University, USA*
Livelihoods, Migration, and Disruption Due to COVID-19

JS-66.2 Mika HASEBE, *Meiji Gakuin University, Japan*
The Struggle of Thai Massage Parlor Owners in Japan Under COVID 19

JS-66.3 Di WANG, *Renmin University of China, China*
House, the New Workplace? Gendered Experience of Korean Expatriates' Wives in Xi'an, China

JS-66.4 Carljohnson ANACIN, *Griffith University, Australia*
Utilizing Capitals As a Response to the Music Industry Precarity amid COVID-19 Pandemic: The Case of Filipino Cover Musicians in Australia

JS-66.5 Marco CASELLI, *Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Italy*
State Capacity and the Capacity to Aspire: The Case of Peruvians in Milan Facing the Pandemic

JS-66.6 Faiz ULLAH, *Macquarie University Sydney, Australia*; Nicholas HARRIGAN, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Shaun WILSON, *Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia*
The Welfare State Can Alleviate Hardship for Temporary Migrant Workers: Evidence from Two Lockdowns in Australia

DiStRiBUtED PAPERS:

JS-66.7 Naoko SUNAI, *Université Laval, Japan*
Multilayered Difficulties and Covid 19: A Case Study of a Pregnant Migrant Woman in Japan

JS-67 Urban Collective Action

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Mario DIANI, *University of Trento, Italy* and Anna DOMARADZKA, *Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw, Poland*

Chair: Anna DOMARADZKA, *University of Warsaw, Poland*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-67.1 Pawel KUBICKI, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
Urban Social Movements in Poland

JS-67.2 Sethulego MATEBESI, *University of the Free State, South Africa*
Transactional Activism and the Demise of Grassroots Organisation

JS-67.3 Grzegorz PIOTROWSKI, *University of Gdansk, Poland*
Dynamics of Contention within Polish Urban Movements

JS-67.4 Joan Ramon RODRIGUEZ-AMAT, *Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom* and Yulia BELINSKAYA, *University of Vienna, Austria*
City Invaders: 8-Bit Video Games for the Right to the City

JS-67.5 Maria Victoria SANCHEZ BELANDO, *University of Barcelona. Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes, 585 - 08007. Barcelona, Spain*
The Role of Community-Based Initiatives As Collective Action in Shaping Urban Governance Relations in a Southern European City: The Case of Barcelona.

JS-67.6 Jurate IMBRASAITE, *Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania*
Protest Mobilization and Innovative Repertoires of Collective Action: A Case of Šančiai Neighbourhood

15:30 - 17:20

JS-68 Accountability and Sustainable transitions: toward an integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part i

Committees: RC17 Sociology of Organization, RC24 Environment and Society, RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food, TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*; Rolf LIDSKOG, *Orebro University, Sweden* and Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-68.1 Vaughan HIGGINS, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Melanie BRYANT, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Marta HERNANDEZ-JOVER, *Charles Sturt University, Australia* and Russell WARMAN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Ordering Responsibility: Making a Shared Approach to Biosecurity Workable in Australia

JS-68.2 Heather LOVELL, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Tom BYRNE, *Tasmanian Government, Australia*; Fred GALE, *University of Tasmania, Australia*; Hannah MURPHY-GREGORY, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Marian SCHOEN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Accountability in Green Hydrogen Standards and Certification

JS-68.3 Vincent DUPONT, *HIVA KU Leuven, Belgium* and Diana PIETRZAK, *KU Leuven, Belgium*
The Rise of Quantification in High-Risk Supply Chains: Sustainability Champions' Human Rights 'Risk' Management

JS-68.4 Sarthak DAS, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India* and Sambit MALLICK, *Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, India*
Technoscience, Risk Society and Democratic Accountability: Field Notes on the Adoption of GM Crops in India and Community Seed Banks

JS-68.5 Angga DWIARTAMA, *Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB), Indonesia*; Rhino ARIEFANSYAH, *University of Indonesia, Indonesia*; Hendra Kurniawan MAURY, *University*

of Cenderawasih, Indonesia; Zulfikar Ali AKBAR, Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB), Indonesia and Sari RAMADHAN, Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB), Indonesia
Stories of Community Resilience: Seeing Beyond the Success and Failure of Community-Based Conservation in Indonesia

DISRUPTED PAPERS:

JS-68.6 David CHAMPAGNE, University of British Columbia, Canada

Looking through Fiery Futures: Disputed Governments of Forest Fires, Heatwaves and Climate Adaptation on Canada's West Coast

JS-68.7 Jingxuan Yi, Central China Normal University, China; Guanghuai ZHENG, Central China Normal University, China and Yean WANG, Beijing Normal University, China
Icing on the Cake: How Governance Absorption and Accountability Promote the Durability of Nonprofits

JS-68.8 Winifredo DAGLI, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines
'Central' and 'Peripheral' Adaptation Pathways of Entangled Agrifood Systems Transformations

JS-68.9 Andrea LAMPIS, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil; Ebba BRINK, Centre for Sustainability Studies (LUCSUS), Lund University, Sweden; Amaya CARRASCO-TORRONTGUEI, Food Systems and Agroecology Livelihoods Collaborative, College of Agriculture and Life Sciences, University of Vermont, Burlington, Vermont, United States of America, Ecuador; Agni Hévea dos SANTOS, Palmares Orgânico, Maricá, RJ, Brazil / ou Núcleo Interdisciplinar de Pesquisas de Paisagens (NIPP), Universidade Federal Fluminense, Niterói, RJ, Brazil, Brazil; Estuardo SOLÓRZANO-LEMUS, Centre for Conservation Studies (CECON/USAC), Faculty of Chemical Sciences and Pharmacy, National University of San Carlos, Guatemala City, Guatemala, Guatemala and Cláudia VÁSQUEZ-ARANGO, Environmental consultant and alumni Universidad de Los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia, Colombia
Reparation Ecology and Climate Risk in Latin-America: Experiences from Four Countries

JS-68.10 Victoria SANAGUSTIN-FONS, University of Zaragoza, Spain
The Role of Social Economy Organizations Promoting Intergenerational Dialogue and Intangible Heritage in Europe for Achieving Social Sustainability. a Study Case

JS-68.11 Iris BALSAMO, --, Argentina
Cross-Funding for Production Structure By Abundance Perspective. a Tool for Organizations

JS-68.12 Victor NOMBERTO BAZAN, Colegio de Sociólogos del Peru, Peru
Cero Emisiones Al 2050

JS-69 Can the new be Born? Critical theory in times of interregnum. Part i

Committees: RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis, RC16 Sociological Theory

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Craig BROWNE, The University of Sydney, Australia and Arthur BUENO, University of Frankfurt, Germany

Chair: Spyros GANGAS, DERE- The American College of Greece, Greece

AUTHORSHIP PAPERS:

JS-69.1 Craig BROWNE, The University of Sydney, Australia
Capitalist Modernity in Transition: Metamorphoses of Heteronomous Dependency and Autonomy

JS-69.2 Arthur BUENO, University of Frankfurt, Germany
The Standpoint of the Proletariat Today

JS-69.3 Frank WELZ, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Critical Theory As Historical Practice

JS-69.4 Gregor BONGAERTS, University Duisburg-Essen, Germany
The Production of Fake Maturity

JS-69.5 Kokichi SHOJI, University of Tokyo, Japan
Sociological Ways to Create a Human Society on Networked Contacts and Harmony with the Planet

JS-70 Diversities Bodies, Violence and Human Rights in the 21st Century: the Gender and Racism issues

Committees: RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences, TG11 Violence and Society

Location: M16 (Crown)

Session organizer: Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, University of Brasilia, Brazil

Chair: Somdatta MUKHERJEE, Department of Sociology Sister Nivedita University, Kolkata, India., India

Co-Chair: Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, University of Brasilia, Brazil

AUTHORSHIP PAPERS:

JS-70.2 Abdelfattah EZZINE, Institut des Etudes Africaines, Euroméditerranéennes et Ibéroaméricaines, Morocco
L'éducation Dans Une Société Plurielle Education in a Plural Society

JS-70.3 Leticia SILVA, Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil; Nárgila Mara da Silva BENTO, University of Brasília, Brazil; Ester Geraldo CAMPELO TORRES, University of Brasília, Brazil and Natalia MENDONCA, Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil
The Existing Relationship between Embodiment and Bodily Practices in the Brazilian Cientific Literature

JS-70.4 Dandara SOARES, UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL FLUMINENSE, Brazil
Movements of Mothers of State Violence Victims Against Public Security Policy of State of Rio De Janeiro 2007-2022

JS-71 Doing Research on Young People with Young People: Co-Productions, Co-Authoring and Collaborations

Committees: RC34 Sociology of Youth, RC18 Political Sociology

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Sarah PICKARD, Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3, France and Dena ARYA, Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom

Chair: Rob WATTS, RMIT University, Australia

Co-Chair: Cécile VAN DE VELDE, Université de Montréal, Canada

Discussant: Ilaria PITTI, University of Bologna, Italy

AUTHORSHIP PAPERS:

JS-71.1 Amanda THIRD, Western Sydney University, Australia; Philippa COLLIN, Young and Resilient Research Centre, Australia; Edmee KENNY, Centre for Multicultural Youth, Australia; Louisa WELLAND, Western Sydney University,

Australia and Komal GREWAL, *Centre for Multicultural Youth, Australia*
What Is Co-Research Anyway? Advancing Theory and Practice

JS-71.2 Eddy DAVIS RAE, *Office of the Children's Commissioner, New Zealand* and Bronwyn WOOD, *Thorndon, New Zealand*
Creating Participatory Space: Sustaining Collective and Intergenerational Youth Participation through YPAR

JS-71.3 Dena ARYA, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*
The Role of Intersectional Inequalities in Shaping Young People's Environmental Action in the UK

JS-71.4 Eve MAYES, *Deakin University, Australia*; Natasha ABHAYAWICKRAMA, *Deakin University, Australia*; Sophie CHIEW, *Deakin University, Australia*; Netta MAIAVA, *Deakin University, Australia* and Danielle VILLAFANA, *Deakin University, Australia*
Co-Researching Young People's Multiple Climate Justice Activisms: Ethical, Methodological and Political Questions

JS-71.5 Harriet ROWLEY, *Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom*
Exploring the Potential and Limitations of Co-Produced Research Using Film: A Comparison of Two Participatory Projects in Manchester with Young People.

DiSt RiBUT ED PAPERS:

JS-71.6 Alison BAKER, *Victoria University, Australia*; Christopher PHUNG, *Victoria University, Australia* and Madelena REHOREK, *Victoria University, Australia*
Resonant Voices: Building Solidarities with Youth People through Creative Activist Knowledges

JS-71.7 Bhavna SOOD, *Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV College for Women, Chandigarh, India, India*
"Lifestyles of Gen Z: A Co-Production and a Collaboration with Young People"

JS-72 Everyday Practices of 'othering': ongoing Developments. Part iii

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity, RC25 Language and Society

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Co-Chair: Catharina PEECK-HO, *Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany*

AUT HoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-72.1 Elisabeth TUIDER, *Universitat Kassel, Germany* and Tina SPIES, *Professor of Sociology at Univ. of Kiel, Germany*
Intersectional-Decolonial Subjectivation Research: Analyzing Othering and Counter-Positions in Postmigrant Societies

JS-72.2 Hans VOGT, *German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Germany*
Institutional Racism between Medical Education and Medical Practice in Germany: A Participatory Explorative Analysis

JS-72.3 Tuhin ROY, *Sociology Discipline, Khulna University, Bangladesh*; Md kamrul HASAN, *Bangladesh Institute of Social Research Trust, Bangladesh*; M. M. Abdullah SONY, *University of Debrecen, Hungary*; Md. Habibur RAHMAN, *Khulna University, Bangladesh* and Shima CHOWDHURY, *National University, Bangladesh*
"We Want to Get Back Our Normal Life": Social Integration and Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh

JS-72.4 Ingrid BOSELDAL, *Department of Educational Sciences, Lund University, Sweden*
Who and What Am I – Intercountry Adoptees As Inappropriate/d Others

JS-72.5 Bhawesh PANT, *TATA INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, India*
Everyday Denial and Reconstruction of Social Identity: Anecdotes from Raji's Lived- World

JS-72.6 Cary WU, *York University, Canada* and Ann KIM, *York University, Canada*
Who Believes There Is Anti-Asian Discrimination?

JS-73 Femmes Migrantes Sur Le Marché Du travail Subalterne/Migrant Women in the Subaltern Labor Market

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration, RC30 Sociology of Work

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Abdoul-Malik AHMAD, *CNRS - LEST-UMR 7317, France* and Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*

Chair: Laura OSO CASAS, *Universidade da Coruña, Spain*

AUT HoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-73.1 Marion BRETEAU, *American University of Kuwait, Kuwait*
Foreign Domestic Workers' Digital Practices in the Gulf States: Tiktok, Agency, and Creative Forms of Resistance

JS-73.3 Laura WIESBOECK, *Institute for Advanced Studies, Austria*
Female Domestic Cleaners in the Gig-Economy: Status Construction on the Informal Labour Market

JS-73.4 Naoko SUNAI, *Tokyo Gakugei University, Japan*
War Generation Mothers and Doi Moi Kids: Analysis of Migration with the Perspective of Gender, Capital, and Age

JS-73.5 Sally OGOE, *University of Manitoba, Canada*
Measuring Success: Predictors of Successful Economic Integration of Resettled Female Refugees.

JS-74 People-Centric Governance, Society, and Sustainable Development

Committees: WG05 Famine and Society, RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session organizers: Mahamuni THAMILARASAN, *University of Madras, India* and Jagdish Chander MEHTA, *D.A.V. College, Chandigarh (India), India*

Chair: Shruti TAMBE, *Savitribai Phule Pune University, India*

Co-Chair: Achalie KUMARAGE, *The Australian National University, Australia*

Discussants: Perna GAUTAM, *Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai, India* and Tika GAUTAM, *Tribhuvan University, Nepal*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-74.1 Maria FREGIDOU-MALAMA, *Department of Business and Economic Studies, Faculty of Education and Business Studies, University of Gävle, Sweden* and Agneta SUNDSTRÖM, *Department of Business and Economic Studies, Faculty of Education and Business Studies, University of Gävle, Sweden*
Cooperative Identity and Corporate Social Responsibility: Regional Cooperatives in Sweden

JS-74.2 Joseph Benhar RAJAN, *Executive President, India* and Biju S K BIJU S K, *Government College, India*
People Centric Governance : A Comparative Analysis of Tqm in Kerala and Batho Pele in South Africa

JS-74.3 Sunil GOVINNAGE, *Independent scholar, Australia*
Aragalaya: The Struggle of People in Sri Lanka

JS-74.4 Sumanth HIREMATH, *Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, India*
Empowering Women through Entrepreneurship: Seclusion to Inclusion

JS-75 the Algorithmic turn in Visual Studies

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology, RC57 Visual Sociology

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session organizers: Regev NATHANSOHN, *Sapir College, Israel* and Gary BRATCHFORD, *The University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom*

Chair: Bartosz SLOSARSKI, *University of Warsaw, Poland*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-75.1 Carolina CAMBRE, *Concordia University, Canada* and Christine LAVRENCE, *King's University College at Western University, Canada*
Algorithmic Sociality: "They Feed You Stuff"

JS-75.2 Tommaso DURANTE, *The University of Melbourne, Australia*
The Algorithm and the Making of the Global Imaginary

JS-75.3 Regev NATHANSOHN, *Sapir College, Israel*
Sensitive Content: The Genealogy of Algorithmic Aura in Visual Culture

JS-75.4 Matthias SOMMER, *Chemnitz University of Technology, Germany*
Smart Photos: On Personalized Images in Algorithmic Situations

JS-76 the Criminalization of Struggles for Rights, Democratic Regression, and Legal Mobilisation. Part i

Committees: RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements, RC12 Sociology of Law

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Marie-Christine DORAN, *University of Ottawa, Canada*; Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Carolina VESTENA, *University of Kassel, Germany*

Chairs: Marie-Christine DORAN, *University of Ottawa, Canada* and Joao VELLOSO, *University of Ottawa, Canada*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-76.1 Ricardo PENAFIEL, *Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada*
"La Protesta Es Un Derecho / Pero No La Violencia": Criminalización De La Democracia En Las Américas y Respuestas Dialógicas

JS-76.2 Camille DENICOURT-FAUVEL, *Observatory Violence, Criminalization and Democracy, Canada*
Democratic Regression in Brazil: How Transitional Impunity Fueled State Violence Targeting Human Rights Defenders

JS-76.3 Hugo ROJAS, *Alberto Hurtado University and Millennium Research Institute on Violence and Democracy, Chile*
Towards Comprehensive Reparation for Victims of Police Violence during the Chilean Social Uprising in 2019: Lessons and Proposals from the Theory and Practice of Transitional Justice

JS-76.4 Debora MACIEL, *Universidade Federal de Sao Paulo, Brazil* and Marta MACHADO, *Brazilian Center of Analysis and Planning - Cebrap, Brazil*
Political Repression and Human Rights Mobilization in Brazil: Competitive Diffusion of Protest Control Repertoires

JS-76.5 Mianzhi CAO, *Frankfurt University, Germany*
A Neoliberal Handle: Legality and Courts in the Struggle for Human Rights in Hong Kong

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-76.6 Piotr KULAS, *Uniwersytet Warszawski, Poland*
Recognition Gaps in East-Central European Society. Distribution of (Dis)Respect and Its Role in Struggles for Human Rights and Cultural Worth.

17:30 - 19:20

JS-77 Accountability and Sustainable transitions: toward an integrated Analysis of Sociopolitical and Ecological Risks. Part ii

Committees: TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty, RC17 Sociology of Organization, RC24 Environment and Society, RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA*; Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Rolf LIDSKOG, *Orebro University, Sweden*

Chairs: Rolf LIDSKOG, *Orebro University, Sweden*; Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA* and Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

JS-78 Bodies, Emotions and Social interaction. Part i

Committees: RC54 The Body in the Social Sciences, WG08 Society and Emotions

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session organizer: Somdatta MUKHERJEE, *Sister Nivedita University, India, India*

Chair: Monica MESQUITA, *Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal*

Co-Chair: Craig COOK, *Woodstock School, India*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-78.1 Adriana GARCIA ANDRADE, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana, Mexico*
Emotional Bodies in Synchrony. Sociology in Dialogue with Social Neuroscience: A Review of the Literature in Social Neuroscience.

JS-78.2 Marci COTTINGHAM, *Kenyon College, USA*
Neo-Emotions As Cultural Practices: What Can the Sociology of Emotion Learn from Compersion, Doom-Scrolling, and Black Joy?

JS-78.3 Anabela PEREIRA, *CIES-ISCTE, IUL, Lisboa, Portugal*
Bridging the Divide between the Body and Environment: The Emotionally Embedded Cognition Hypothesis

JS-78.4 Christopher WINTER, *Victoria University, Australia*
Embodied Emotions in a Lone Actor Terrorist Attack: The Lindt Cafe Siege

JS-78.5 Miriam DILLON, *University of Queensland, Australia*; Jenny SETCHELL, *School of Health and Rehabilitation, The University of Queensland, Australia*; Maxi MICIAK, *University of Alberta, Canada*; Peter WINDOW, *Royal Brisbane and Women's Hospital, Australia* and Rebecca OLSON, *School of Social Science, The University of Queensland, Australia*
Distress in Physiotherapy Low Back PAIN Care: A Socio-Relational Exploration

JS-78.6 Annette MICHELSEN LA COUR, *University of Southern Denmark, Denmark*
Like a Winter without Christmas. a Study of the Emotions, Interaction Rituals and Youth Culture Following the Cancellation of the Roskilde Festival, an Iconic Danish Music Festival.

JS-79 Can the new be Born? Critical theory in times of interregnum. Part ii

Committees: RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis, RC16 Sociological Theory

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Arthur BUENO, *University of Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Craig BROWNE, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-79.1 Ichiro OKANO, *Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Japan*
Differentiation or Centralization?: An Attempt at Unifying the Two Sociological Viewpoints on Modernity

JS-79.2 Jiri SUBRT, *Charles University, Czech Republic*
Progress, Utopia, Imagination and Ideology

JS-79.3 James SANTOS, *Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil*
Genealogy As Immanent Critique of Forms of Life

JS-79.4 Dmitry IVANOV, *St. Petersburg state university, Russian Federation*
Herbert Marcuse's Dialectic of Modernity in the Perspective of Post-Virtualization

JS-80 Language and immigrant Generations: new Entanglements.

Committees: RC25 Language and Society, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Amado ALARCON ALARCON, *University Rovira i Virgili, Spain*; Cecilio LAPRESTA-REY, *University of Lleida, Spain* and Roland TERBORG, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*

Chair: Amado ALARCON ALARCON, *University Rovira i Virgili, Spain*

Co-Chair: Cecilio LAPRESTA-REY, *University of Lleida, Spain*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-80.1 Valentine IBEKA, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Education-for-Immigration, Language and the Orchestration of the Migrant Habitus: Exploring the Narratives of International Graduates in Denmark and New Zealand

JS-80.2 Iskra PAVEZ, *Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins, Chile*; Juan ORTIZ, *Universidad Las Américas, Chile*; Pablo MARDONES, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile*; Valeria ACUÑA, *Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins, Chile*; Jendery JALDÍN, *Universidad Arturo Prat, Chile*; Sius-Geng SALINAS, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile* and Iciar DUFRAIX, *Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile*
Unaccompanied Migrant Children and Adolescents in Chile

JS-80.3 Tricia OKADA, *Tamagawa University, Japan*
The Accent That We Speak: Examining Identities of Filipino English Language Teachers in Japan

JS-80.4 Dong DONG, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Elena NICHINI, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Saba ASIM, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Zhengwei HUANG, *The Chinese University of Hong Kong, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, Hong Kong*
Reproducing Information Disparity and Health Inequity Via Risk Communication during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Qualitative Study on South Asian Migrants in Hong Kong

JS-81 Music and Society: identities, Resistances and Politics through Musical Production. Part i

Committees: RC37 Sociology of Arts, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC14 Sociology of Communication, Knowledge and Culture

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Omar CERRILLO, *ITESM, Mexico*

Chair: Musa YUSUPOV, *Chechen State University, Russian Federation*

Panelist: Manan DESAI, *University of Michigan, USA*

Discussant: Ryan MARTIN, *University of New South Wales, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-81.1 Albeniz EZME GURLEK, *Ahi Evran University, Turkey*
Sulukule on a Journey from Preserving a Musical Heritage to Protecting a Place with Music: Auto-Ethnographic Views

JS-81.2 Joseph GREENWOOD, *University of Kurdistan Hewlêr, Iraq*; Ana Cristina MARQUES, *University of Kurdistan Hewlêr, Iraq* and Vienna SALAM, *University of Kurdistan Hewlêr, Iraq*
Songs and Performance of Kurdish Identity

JS-81.3 Manan DESAI, *University of Michigan, USA*
Imperial Vinyl: Race, the Cold War, and the Sound of U.S. Empire

JS-81.4 Ryan MARTIN, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Two Mechanisms for Musical Improvisation's Political Impacts: Disruption and the Expression of Public Opinion

JS-81.5 Shiene KIRIYA, *University of Tokyo, Japan*
Songs As Music and Songs As Sounds in Urban Plaza: Focusing on the Anti-War Folk-Singing Gathering in Tokyo in 1969

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-81.6 Hannah FAIRLAMB, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Grassroots Gender Equality Interventions and DIY Music in Australia

JS-82 Professional transformations in Public Sector/Social Services Management: trends and Challenges – between Managerial ‘Governmentality’ and Authoritarian Governance?

Committees: RC52 *Sociology of Professional Groups*, RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy*

Language: French

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Susana PENALVA, *Cons. Nac. Investigaciones Cient. y Tec. (CONICET), Argentina*

Chair: Lara MAESTRIPIERI, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Italy*

Discussants: Arianna GATTA, *University of Queensland, Italy* and Koichi HIRAOKA, *Tokyo Online University, Japan*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-82.1 Giuseppe DE LUCA PICIONE, *University of Naples ‘Federico II’, Italy*; Lucia FORTINI, *University of Naples ‘Federico II’, Italy* and Domenico TREZZA, *University of Naples ‘Federico II’, Italy*
Welfare in Italian Regions between Fragmentation and Management. Emerging Governance Models

JS-82.2 Federica GRAZIANO, *Università della Calabria, Italy*
Controlling the Poor

JS-82.3 Susana PENALVA, *Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Argentina*
Politics and Professions in Public Management of Social Policy – between Inequalities Regulation and Authoritarian ‘Governmentality’? (Política y profesiones en la gestión pública de la política social – ¿Entre regulación de las desigualdades y “gubernamentalidad managerial”?)

JS-82.4 Mingzi MA, *School of Sociology, Central China Normal University, China*; Yean WANG, *Beijing Normal University, China* and Ou WANG, *School of Sociology, Central China Normal University, China*
“Being Red but Not Professional”: Professional Autonomy and the Construction of State Hegemony.

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-83.1 Spyros GANGAS, *DEREE-The American College of Greece, Greece*
Critical Theory’s Unforgetfulness: Human Essentialism Reconstructed in the Capability Approach

JS-83.2 Alvaro MALAINA, *University Complutense of Madrid, Spain*
The Implications of the Ontological Turn in Sociological Theory: A Necessary Debate

JS-83.3 João Mauro CARVALHO, *NA, Brazil* and Milton LAHUERTA, *UNESP - FCL/Ar, Brazil*
Critical Theory before a New Structural Change of the Public Sphere: Digital Social Media between Democracy and Economic Rationality

JS-83.4 Enzo COLOMBO, *Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy* and Paola REBUGHINI, *Milan University, Italy*
Individualism and Critical Theory: Rethinking Critical Potential in an Individualized Social Environment

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-83.5 Esther OLIVER, *University of Barcelona, Spain* and Mar JOANPERE, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Reconnaissance and Measurement of Sociology’s Social Improvements

JS-84 Citizenship and inequality

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration*, RC05 *Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Ana VELITCHKOVA, *University of Mississippi, USA*

Chairs: Paromita SANYAL, *Florida State University, USA* and Nicole SATHERLEY, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*

AUt Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-84.1 Omid ASAYESH, *University of Calgary, Canada*
Homo Emigraturus: A New Social Category Beyond Migrant and Non-Migrant? a Particular Focus on the Case of Iran

JS-84.2 Shelene GOMES, *The University of the West Indies, St Augustine, Trinidad and Tobago*
Competing Nationalisms: Venezuelans and Spanish-Speakers in Postcolonial Trinidad and Tobago

JS-84.3 Catriona STEVENS, *School of Arts and Humanities, Edith Cowan University, Australia*
Homeland Socio-Spatial Class, Differential Subnational Memberships, and the Strategic Citizenship Choices of Chinese Labour Migrants in Australia

JS-84.4 David GOUARD, *University of Toulouse, France*
Inequalities in the Electoral Registration of the Non National EU Citizens Living in France

JS-84.5 Ulrike M VIETEN, *Queen’s University Belfast, United Kingdom*
Liquid Citizenship and the Post-Migration Condition

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-84.6 Philip YANG, *POB 425887, USA* and Wai-cheong TAM, *Texas Woman’s University, USA*
Global Rise in Dual Citizenship

JS-84.7 Hideki TARUMOTO, *Waseda University, Japan*
Migrant Citizenship and Inequality in East Asia

Thursday 29 June

08:30 - 10:20

JS-83 Can the new be Born? Critical theory in times of interregnum. Part iii

Committees: RC16 *Sociological Theory*, RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Arthur BUENO, *University of Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Arthur BUENO, *University of Frankfurt, Germany*

JS-85 Crisis and State Capacities 1: Crises and Challenges

Committees: RC17 Sociology of Organization, RC18 Political Sociology

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Alan SCOTT, University of New England, Australia and Stephanie ALENDIA, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile

Chairs: Alan SCOTT, University of New England, Australia and Stephanie ALENDIA, Universidad Andres Bello, Chile

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-85.1 Sighard NECKEL, University of Hamburg, Germany
Tackling the Climate Crisis: Infrastructure, Foundational Economy, and the State

JS-85.2 Gregorius SAHDAN, STPMD "APMD", Indonesia
Bureaucratic Government in Overcoming the Covid-19 Pandemic in Yogyakarta

JS-85.3 Claire BAKER, University of New England, Australia
The Pendulum Swings? Crisis and the Role of the State in Australia

JS-85.4 Michelle Fei-yu HSIEH, Academia Sinica, Taiwan
Revamping the PPE Supply Chain: The Taiwanese State's Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-86 New Urban Mobilizations and Solidarities - Theoretical and Empirical Perspectives

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development, RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Pierre HAMEL, Université de Montréal, Canada and Anna DOMARADZKA, University of Warsaw, Poland

Chairs: Pierre HAMEL, Université de Montréal, Canada and Anna DOMARADZKA, University of Warsaw, Poland

Co-Chair: Shruti TAMBE, Savitribai Phule Pune University, India

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-86.1 Maria da Gloria GOHN, University of Campinas, Brazil
Urban Activism in Brazil Today: How Do Movements, Collectives and Civil Organizations in Solidarity Networks?

JS-86.2 Yasemin BAHCEKAPILI, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, Turkey; Murat Cemal YALÇINTAN, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, Turkey and Fuat ERCAN, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, Turkey
Analyzing Urban Activism within the Context of the Right to the City for All: An Ethnographic Research on Prince Islands, Istanbul

JS-86.3 Alan MABIN, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa
Citizens in a World of Recomposition: The Popular and New Social Movements in Capital City Regions

JS-86.4 Valesca LIMA, Dublin City University, Ireland
The Politics of Knowledge Production - Translocal Learning in Housing Struggles

JS-86.5 Asato SAITO, Yokohama National University, Japan
Localism and Urban Social Movement: A Case Study of Queen's Park Community Council in London

JS-86.6 Hideaki SASAJIMA, Sumiyoshi-ku, Japan
Alternative Space Movements in the Global Sixties: Comparative Urban Sociological Studies of London, Tokyo and New York.

JS-87 Transforming traditional Knowledge System of Mountains: A Threat to Sustainability

Committees: WG05 Famine and Society, RC24 Environment and Society

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Mohinder Kumar SLARIYA, Department of Higher Education, India

Chair: Satish SHARMA, HIMACHAL PRADESH UNIVERSITY, India

Co-Chair: Bali BAHADUR, Central University of Punjab, India

Panelists: Jagsir SINGH, University College, India; Dr. lakhwinder SINGH, Northern Regional Language Centre Patiala India, India and Gandhar SINGH, Northern Regional Language Centre, Patiala, India, India

Discussants: Dr. Mangal HASAN, Northern Regional Language Centre, Patiala, India (NRLCPI), India and Parmpreet Singh SIDHU, Punjabi University Patiala 147002, India

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-87.1 Kashmir KASHYAP, Government P.G. College, India
Forest Fire in Himachal Pradesh: An Environmental Review

JS-87.2 Lakhvir SINGH, PUNJABI UNIVERSITY PATIALA, PUNJAB (INDIA), India and Haresh KUMAR, CEVA, Panghi, Himachal Pradesh, India
Displacement and Rehabilitation: A Case of Hydro Power Projects in Mountainous Areas of Himachal Pradesh

JS-87.3 Peter Dichunlung RWANGMEI, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India and Munmum JHA, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India
Trans-Asian Railway: Hopes and Threats for the Traditional Society of the Mountainous Tribal Belt of Northeast India

JS-87.4 Haresh KUMAR, CEVA, Panghi, Himachal Pradesh, India; Charanjiv SAROA, Punjabi University, Patiala, India and Harpreet SINGH, Punjabi University, Patiala, India
Upliftment of Displaced People: An Examination of the Role of Government and NGOs at Hydro Power Projects in Mountains of Himachal Pradesh

JS-88 Women in an Occupational Gender Segregation Global Labor Market

Committees: RC30 Sociology of Work, RC32 Women, Gender and Society

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Melissa DE MATTOS PIMENTA, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil and Eva BÉRMUDEZ FIGUEROA, Universidad de Cádiz, Spain

Chair: Empar AGUADO, Universitat de València, Spain

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-88.1 Lyndall STRAZDINS, Australian National University, Australia; Tinh DOAN, Australian National University, Australia; Liana LEACH, Australian National University, Australia; Matthias POLLMANN-SCHULT, Faculty of Humanities, Social Science & Education, Magdeburg University, Germany and Till KAISER, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany
Hour-Glass Ceilings: Long Hour Limits to Employment Equality in Germany and Australia

JS-88.2 Adwoa BOBIE, University of Ghana, Ghana
The Mama in the Garage: The Positionality of Female Artistes in the Creative Industry in West Africa.

JS-88.3 Wataru YOSHIDA, IPSS, Japan
Trickle-Down Effect or Vice Versa? Examining the Effect of Female Managers in Japanese Firms, 2008-2016

JS-88.4 Miguel SERNA FORCHERI, *Universidad de la República, Uruguay*
Gender Inequalities at the Top of Political and Economic Power in Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Mexico and Uruguay

JS-88.5 Donna BRIDGES, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*; Elizabeth WULFF, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*; Larissa BAMBERRY, *Charles Sturt University, Australia* and Branka KRIVOKAPIC-SKOKO, *Charles Sturt University, Australia*
Gender Segregation in the Skilled Trades in Rural Australia: Using Bourdieusian Theory to Understand the Barriers

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-88.6 Ronit KARK, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel* and Ruth BLATT, *Bar Ilan University, Israel*
Leading in a Hyper-Masculine Organization: The Gendered Leadership Selection Paradox

JS-88.7 Montserrat SIMO-SOLSONA, *University of Barcelona (Gran Via Corts Catalanes, 585, 08007 Barcelona), Spain*; Laura SUAREZ GRIMALT, *UNIVERSITY OF A CORUÑA, Spain* and Andres COCO-PRIETO, *University of Barcelona, Spain*
Paro Oculito y Género En Europa: Una Cuestión De Doble Invisibilidad

JS-88.8 Sheree GREGORY, *Western Sydney University, Australia*
Succession Planning and the 'Glass Ceiling' in Australian Universities

10:30 - 12:20

JS-89 **Childhoods at the Crossection of Disasters**

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood*, RC39 *Sociology of Disasters*

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey* and Maureen FORDHAM, *UCL, United Kingdom*

Co-chairs: Ilknur ONER, *Firat University, Turkey* and Maureen FORDHAM, *UCL, United Kingdom*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-89.1 Briony TOWERS, *Leadrrr, Australia*; Erica KULIGOWSKI, *RMIT University, Australia* and Billy HAWORTH, *Leadrrr, Australia*
Student Voice, Influence and Leadership in School Emergency Management: An Action Research Case Study from Victoria, Australia

JS-89.2 Alison LLOYD WILLIAMS, *University of Hull, United Kingdom* and Katie PARSONS, *University of Hull, United Kingdom*
From 'Flood Stories' to 'Flood Actors': Children As Change Agents in Disaster Risk Education

JS-89.3 Fiona MACDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*; Leo BORTOLOTTI, *Youth Affairs Council Victoria, Australia*; Sneha CHALLA, *Youth Affairs Council Victoria, Australia*; Carla HALL, *Youth Affairs Council Victoria, Australia*; Emily KIRTON, *Youth Affairs Council Victoria, Australia*; Derm RYAN, *Youth Affairs Council Victoria, Australia* and Brett WOODS, *Victoria University, Australia*
Children and Young People As Agents of Change in Disasters: Flipping the Risk and Vulnerability Discourse to Enable a Capability Narrative

JS-89.4 Lisa GIBBS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Jane NURSEY, *Phoenix Australia: Centre for Posttraumatic Mental Health, Australia*; Ruth WRAITH, *Child Trauma Psychology Consultant, Australia* and Katitza MARINKOVIC CHAVEZ, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Long Term Academic Impacts after Disaster

JS-90 **Extending Critical Approaches to Agtech and Foodtech: Dialoguing insights from the insides and o utsides of technology Design Projects**

Committees: RC40 *Sociology of Agriculture and Food*, TG10 *Digital Sociology*

Location: CCH3 (Crown)

Session organizers: Karly BURCH, *University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Katharine LEGUN, *Wageningen University, Netherlands*

Chair: Tatiana KARABCHUK, *UAE University, United Arab Emirates*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-90.1 Maaz GARDEZI, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Bhavna JOSHI, *Virginia Tech, USA*; Pablo CARCAMO, *Virginia Tech, USA* and Edward PRUTZER, *Virginia Tech, USA*
"Has Anyone Ever Innovated Responsibly?" Social Scientists' Participation in Responsible Co-Design of Digital Farming Tools

JS-90.2 Kirsten AYRIS, *University of Reading, United Kingdom*; Alice MAUCLINE, *University of Reading, United Kingdom* and David Christian ROSE, *Cranfield University, United Kingdom*
Participatory Approaches for Inclusive Agtech Development: Investigating Innovation in the UK Agricultural Robotics Sector

JS-90.3 Mariana HASE UETA, *Technische Universität Dresden, Germany* and Frank I MÜLLER, *Center for Urban Studies, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands*
Food Technopolitical Innovation and the Geographies of Inequality

JS-90.4 Matt COMI, *Marshfield Clinic Research Institute, USA*; Florence BECOT, *Marshfield Clinic Research Institute, USA* and Casper BENDIXSEN, *National Farm Medicine Center, Marshfield Research Institute, USA*
Agtech and the Future of Farmwork: Insights on Labor and Equity in Agricultural Innovation

JS-90.5 Lara ROEVEN, *Cornell University, USA*; Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA*; Phoebe SENGER, *Cornell University, USA*; Jen LIU, *Cornell University, USA*; Gloire RUBAMBIZA, *Cornell University, USA*; Donny PERSAUD, *Cornell University, USA* and Hakim WEATHERSPOON, *Cornell University, USA*
Hiding Technical Complexity or Erasing Social and Ecological Difference? Abstraction in the Design of a Data Infrastructure for Digital Agriculture.

JS-90.6 Karly BURCH, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Katharine LEGUN, *Wageningen University, Netherlands* and Carolina CAMACHO VILLA, *Lincoln University, United Kingdom*
What Is the Role of Social Scientists in the Design of New Agtech?

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-90.7 Karaitiana TAIURU, *Taiuru & Associates Ltd, New Zealand*; Susanna FINLAY-SMITS, *AgResearch, New Zealand* and Karly BURCH, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Realising the Promises of Big Data in Agriculture through a Māori Data Sovereignty Approach

JS-90.8 Jeanne OUI, *IRISSO, Paris, France* and Steven WOLF, *Cornell University, USA*
Tracing Grain Digitally from Farms to Markets. Promises, Trials, and Lessons for Technological Design

JS-91 Family Structure and Social Stratification in transformation. Part i

Committees: RC06 Family Research, RC28 Social Stratification

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Institute of Campeche, Mexico* and Delfino VARGAS, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Yan XIA, *University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA*

Panelist: Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Institute of Campeche, Mexico*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-91.1 WU HANIA, *Department of sociology, Fudan University, China*
Parental Absence during Childhood and Intergenerational Income Mobility in China

JS-91.2 Jenny RINALLO, *LEST – Aix Marseille University, France*
Forming One's Own Family in Times of Labour Market Uncertainty and Dependency from the Parents: A Comparison between French and Italian Young Adults

JS-91.3 Andrea TARTAKOWSKY, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*; Susan HARKNESS, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom* and Esther DERMOTT, *University of Bristol, United Kingdom*
The Intra-Couple Wealth Gap in the UK: A Longitudinal Perspective

JS-91.4 Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Institute of Campeche, Mexico* and Delfino VARGAS-CHANES, *Facultad de Economía UNAM, Mexico*
Inequalities in Life and Job Satisfaction? a Parallel Longitudinal Analysis of China, 2010-2018

JS-91.5 Doudou YAN, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation* and Anna BAGIROVA, *Ural Federal University, Russian Federation*
Intergenerational Relations in Chinese Families of Former Left-behind Children

DiSt RiBUT ED PAPERS:

JS-91.6 Sunyu HAM, *KIHASA, Republic of Korea*
The Interplay between Family Structure and Income Inequality: Consequences of Unequal Chances of Marriage and Childbirth in Korea

JS-91.7 Jin JIANG, *Hong Kong Baptist University, Hong Kong*
Partially Patriarchy? Coresidence of Young Adults with Their Parents in the Least Affordable City

JS-92 indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations

Committees: RC31 Sociology of Migration, RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Rochelle COTE, *Memorial University, Canada*

Co-Chair: Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-92.1 Margaret WALTER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations

JS-92.2 Rochelle COTE, *Memorial University, Canada*
Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations - Presenter 4

JS-92.3 Michelle EVANS, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations - Presenter 5

JS-92.4 Lara GREAVES, *iNZight Analytics Ltd, New Zealand*
Indigenous Peoples, Mobility, and Migrant/Settler Relations - Presenter 6

JS-93 La Lucha Contra Los Extractivismos En América Latina y El Futuro De La Región | Struggle Against Extractivism in Latin America and the Future of the Region

Committees: RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change, RC07 Futures Research

Language: Spanish

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Ligia TAVERA FENOLLOSA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico*

Chair: Nelson ARTEAGA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-93.1 Lorena TORRES BERNARDINO, *TRIANGLE UMR 5206 / SCIENCES PO LYON, France*
Movimientos Sociales Contra El Extractivismo Hídrico: Coaliciones Multinivel En Los Conflictos Por El Agua En México

JS-93.2 Luis ruben GONZALEZ MARQUEZ, *University of California, Merced, USA*
"the Dam Only Brought Us Bitterness". Extractivism, Authoritarian Development and the Conflict-Repression Nexus in Central America

JS-93.3 Carlos MARTINEZ, *Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico*
Por Qué Los Movimientos Contra Los Proyectos Mineros En México Emplean Estrategias De Movilización Legal

JS-93.4 Rafael SCHOEGLER, *University of Graz, Austria*; Christina KORAK, *University of Graz, Austria* and Eduardo PICHILINGUE RAMOS, *Cuencas Sagradas, Peru*
Translation and Non-Translation As Forms of Indigenous Resistance

JS-93.5 Ligia TAVERA FENOLLOSA, *Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Mexico*
Legal Mobilization Against Extractivism in Mexico: A Comparative Analysis

JS-93.6 Camila PONCE LARA, *Philipps Universität Marburg, Germany*
New Deal or Green Extractivism: The Ups and Downs of the Petro and Boric Governments Regarding the Model.

JS-94 Religion and Science

Committees: RC22 Sociology of Religion, RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Hossein GODAZGAR, *University of Warwick, United Kingdom*

Chair: Rafael CAZARIN DE BRITO, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, South Africa*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-94.1 Blessing EMMANUEL, *University of Georgia, USA*
Critical Analysis of Malinowski's Socio-Anthropological Perspective to 'Science' and 'Religion': Implications for 21st-Century Health Care Best Practices.

JS-94.2 Adrian ROSENFELDT, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Bringing Religion and Science Back Down to Earth in the New Millennium

JS-94.3 Ryan CRAGUN, *University of Tampa, USA* and Bethany GULL, *University of Utah, USA*
God Is the Ultimate Scientist: Lds Conceptualizations of Science

JS-94.4 Kristina KOVALSKAYA, *Groupe Sociétés, Religions, Laïcités, France*
Destinies of Nuclear Orthodoxy: Religious Expertise on Scientific Issues in Russia

JS-94.5 Patricio OLIVA, *Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Avi ASTOR, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Cyberreligiosity in Young Catholics: Integration or Overcoming of the Digital?

JS-95 The Potential of Food Movements and Intersectional Food Inequalities

Committees: RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements*, RC40 *Sociology of Agriculture and Food*

Location: P3 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Renata MOTTA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

Chair: Marco Antonio TEIXEIRA, *Heidelberg University, Germany*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-95.1 Charles LEVKOE, *Lakehead University, Canada* and Amanda WILSON, *Saint Paul University, Canada*
Introspecting Food Movements in Canada: Unpacking Tensions Towards Justice and Sustainability

JS-95.2 Camille FREEMAN, *University of Queensland, Australia* and Kiah SMITH, *U. Queensland, Australia*
Towards a Framework for Scaling-up Civic Food: Lessons from Coalition Building in Australia

JS-95.3 Andrew BENNIE, *Sociology Department, Wits University, South Africa*
"Food Movements Unite!": Food Sovereignty, Inequality and the Contours of Organising from Below in the South African Food System

JS-95.4 Sayamol CHAROENRATANA, *Chulalongkorn University, Thailand* and Chohnapa ANUKUL, *Chulalongkorn University Social Research Institute, Thailand*
Linking Farmers Food Sovereignty with Consumers Food Justice: Case Study of Farmers' Markets in Thailand

JS-96 Traditional Water Cultures and the Modern Life

Committees: RC24 *Environment and Society*, RC03 *Community Research*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Abbas FAGHII KHORASANI, *University of Tehran, Iran*

Chair: Anjali YADAV, *Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-96.1 Farhat NAZ, *Indian Institute of Technology Jodhpur, India* and George K.J. GEORGE, *School of Liberal Arts, Indian Institute of Technology Jodhpur, India, India*
Traditional Water Wisdom and Water Management: A Viewpoint from Thar Desert, Rajasthan, India

JS-96.2 Vibha ARORA, *IIT Delhi, India*
Fusion of Tradition and Modernity in India's Riverscapes

JS-96.3 Ritu SHARMA, *University of Delhi, India*
Socio-Cultural Study of Water and Women in Rajasthan

JS-96.4 Ana LARA HEYNS, *Monash University, Australia*
Walking with Water: A Relational and Respectful Design to Water Planning in the City.

JS-96.5 Pearl PUWURAYIRE, *Brandenburg University of Technology, Germany*
Analysing the Intersection of Formal and Informal Water Actors As a Socio-Material Practices

15:30 - 17:20

JS-97 Alternative Food Futures: Connecting Research with Citizen Politics ii

Committees: RC40 *Sociology of Agriculture and Food*, RC07 *Futures Research*

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Kiah SMITH, *U. Queensland, Australia* and Alana MANN, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Chair: Kiah SMITH, *U. Queensland, Australia*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-97.1 Joanna HORTON, *University of Queensland, Australia*
Civil Society Power and Participation in the UN Food Systems Summit

JS-97.2 Qian ZHANG, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Anti-Productivism: A Rural-Initiated Alternative to Productivist Agriculture

JS-97.3 Mariana HASE UETA, *Technische Universität Dresden, Germany*
From Scarcity Memories Towards Alternative Futures: Intergenerational Dialogues in the Global South

JS-98 Challenges and Opportunities in Measuring Violence

Committees: TG11 *Violence and Society*, RC55 *Social Indicators*

Location: M12 (Crown)

Session Organizer: Oliver NAHKUR, *University of Tartu, Estonia*

Chair: Sylvia WALBY, *Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-98.1 Oliver NAHKUR, *University of Tartu, Estonia* and Rein TAAGEPERA, *School of Social Sciences, University of California, Irvine, USA*
Lead and Lag Times of Countries in a Gentler World

JS-98.2 Mare AINSAAR, *University of Tartu, Estonia*; Ave ROOTS, *University of Tartu, Estonia*; Kadri SOO, *University of Tartu, Estonia* and Jana BRUNS, *Statistics Estonia, Estonia*
Survey Method's Impact on Sexual Violence Indicators

JS-98.3 Christopher WINTER, *Victoria University, Australia*
Measuring Lone Actor Terrorism: Insights from the Lone Actor Terrorism Micro-Sociological Database

JS-98.4 Cynthia COOK, *Creighton University, USA* and Kelechi KALU, *University of California at Riverside, USA*
The Social Determinants of Peace and Stability and Sub-Saharan Africa

JS-98.5 Carlos PERIS CASTIGLIONI, *Montevideo entre Oliva y, Paraguay* and Marcelo MORICONI, *Instituto Universitario de Lisboa (ISCTE-IUL), Portugal*
Cultivating Cannabis in a Paraguayan Nature Reserve: Incentives and Moral Justification for Breaking the Law

JS-99 Crossing Borders – Shifting orders? intersectional Perspectives on the Ukrainian War and the Reorganization of European Border Spaces

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Co-Chair: Elisabeth TUIDER, *Universitat Kassel, Germany*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-99.1 Maria MAYERCHYK, *University of Greifswald temporary, Ukraine*
Welcomed and Othered: Ukrainian War Refugees Seeking Jobs in Western Europe

JS-99.2 Olga PLAKHOTNIK, *University of Greifswald temporary, Ukraine*
Racial Politics and Necropolitics of the War

JS-99.3 Anna AMELINA, *BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany* and Jana SCHAEFER, *BTU Cottbus, Germany*
Gendered Violence in the Name of Imperial Memories: Renegotiation of Social Membership of Mobile Ukrainian Citizens in Germany and the Russian Federation

JS-99.4 Manuela BOATCA, *Freiburg University, Germany*
Unequal Citizenships: Between Solidarity Norms and the Regulation of Social Mobility

JS-99.5 Saara KOIKKALAINEN, *University of Eastern Finland, Finland*
Volunteerism and Citizenship in the Context of the War in Ukraine

JS-100 Family Structure and Social Stratification in transformation. Part ii

Committees: RC06 Family Research, RC28 Social Stratification

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Instituto Campechano, Mexico* and Delfino VARGAS, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Chair: Delfino VARGAS, *National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico*

Co-Chair: Lukasz CZARNECKI, *Pedagogical University of Cracow, Poland*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-100.1 Natalie NITSCHKE, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany*; Alessandra TRIMARCHI, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Marika JALOVAARA, *University of Turku, Finland*
The Power of Two: Second Birth Rate Differences between Couples with Homogamous and Heterogamous Educational Pairings

JS-100.2 Andres CASTRO, *Centro de Estudios Demograficos, Spain*; Mariona LOZANO, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain* and Carlos RUIZ-RAMOS, *Center for Demographic Studies, Spain*
Social Configurations of Inequality and Family Formation Trajectories in Contemporary Spain

JS-100.3 Tugce BEYCAN, *Centre Maurice Halbwachs (ENS/EHESS/CNRS/PSL), Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France* and Serge PAUGAM, *Centre Maurice Halbwachs (EHESS/ENS/CNRS/PSL), Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France*
Lineal Bond Dynamics By Capabilities, Social Class, and Ethnicity Aspects in Mexico

JS-100.4 Wei-Jun Jean YEUNG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore* and Senhu WANG, *National University of Singapore, Singapore*
Family Ideals/Goals across Cultural and Socioeconomic Groups: A Factorial Survey Experiment in Singapore

JS-100.5 Pragna RUGUNANAN, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Celine MEYERS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*
Transnational Family Practices Among Zimbabwean Women Migrants in South Africa

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-100.6 Melek KIRTIL, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
The Impact of Family Structure and Affluence on Children's Behavioral Outcomes

JS-100.7 Sunil JOHNSON, *KNM Govt College Kanjiramkulam, India* and Rajan KOYU, *SREE NEELAKANTA GOVERNMENT SANSKRIT COLLEGE, PATTAMBI, KERALA, INDIA, India*
Concept of Fatherhood in Polyandry a Case Study of Family Structure and Gender Relations Among the Thityyas of Malabar, South India

JS-100.8 Shuang QIU, *Keele University, United Kingdom*
Gendered Lives in LAT Relationships: Exploring Agency from a Relational Perspective

JS-101 Language on Health Under Co ViD-19 Pandemic. Part i

Committees: RC25 Language and Society, RC15 Sociology of Health

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan* and Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*

Chair: Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-101.1 Win-ping KUO, *Chinese Culture University, Taiwan* and Sumei WANG, *National Chengchi University, Taiwan*
Social Representation of Pandemic: Collocational Network and Keyword Analysis of Media Reports and Public Discussion on COVID-19

JS-101.2 Paul KELAITA, *Deakin University, Australia*; Kiran PIENAAR, *Deakin University, Australia*; Jaya KEANEY, *University of Melbourne, Australia*; Dean MURPHY, *Kirby Institute, UNSW, Australia*; Catherine BENNETT, *Deakin University, Australia* and Hassan VALLY, *Deakin University, Australia*

Pandemic Policing and the Construction of Publics: An Analysis of COVID-19 Lockdowns in Public Housing

JS-101.3 Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*
COVID-19 Beyond the Metaphor of War

JS-101.4 Ben LYALL, *Monash University, Australia*
'Find Your Pandemic Flow': Corporate Blogs in the Liminal Space between Health and Wellness

JS-102 Mobilizing Emotions by Social Movements and in Contemporary Humanitarian Effort

Committees: WG08 Society and Emotions, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Davide NICOLOSI, *University of Catania, Italy* and Gada MAHROUSE, *Concordia University, Canada*

Chair: Helena FLAM, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-102.1 Inga KORALEWSKA, *Australian National University, Australia*
Emotions and Autonomous Health Movements: Lessons from Abortion Self-Help Collectives in Europe.

JS-102.2 Ruthie GINSBURG, *Beit Berl College, Israel*
Kites on Fire: Disobedience Objects on the Fence

JS-102.3 Mariam KALANDADZE, *Central European University, Austria*
"from Georgian People": Compassion As Moral Obligation and Humanitarian Aid for Ukraine

JS-102.4 Idayane SOARES, *Freie Universität Berlin, Germany*
Anxiety and Inequalities: A Case Study with the Brazilian Mutual-Aid Group Neurotics Anonymous

JS-102.5 Maria MAIRANO, *CIC-UNLAM; UBA, Argentina*
Emociones En Torno a La Alimentación En Comedores y Merenderos Comunitarios, La Matanza y Ciudad De Buenos Aires

JS-103 Theories of Practice: New Perspectives in Urban Theory and Research

Committees: RC03 Community Research, RC16 Sociological Theory

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Natalia MARTINI, *Jagiellonian University, Poland* and Karol KURNICKI, *Lancaster University, United Kingdom*

Chair: Natalia MARTINI, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-103.1 Bhavna MIDDHA, *RMIT University, Australia* and Ralph HORNE, *RMIT University, Australia*
Apartments As Excluded and Arhythmic Spaces in the Urban Waste Regime

JS-103.2 Marta KLEKOTKO, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
Urban Community As Meta-Practice

JS-104 Whistleblowing and Social Justice

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology, RC17 Sociology of Organization

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizer: Tina UYS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Chair: David DU TOIT, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-104.1 Kezia BATISAI, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Chenai CHIKOTO, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Whistleblower or Informer? Exploring the Reporting of Migrants to Dudula Movement and Other Relevant Authorities By South African Citizens

JS-104.2 Anne OBLING, *The Royal Danish Defence College, Denmark* and Thomas LOPDRUP-HJORTH, *Copenhagen Business School, Denmark*

Blowing the Whistle in National Security and Defence Organizations: Navigating the Tensions between Transparency and Secrecy

JS-104.3 Ugljesa RADULOVIC, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Tina UYS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

Paying the Ultimate Price: The Death of Whistleblower Protection

JS-104.4 Pamela FORWARD, *Whistleblowing Canada Research Society, Canada*

Organizational Culture and Whistleblowing: The Invisible Forces Driving Reprisals

JS-104.5 Wim VANDEKERCKHOVE, *EDHEC Business School, France*

Role-Prescribed Whistleblowing and Social Injustice.

17:30 - 19:20

JS-105 Building Local Participatory Democracies in the Era of Threatened National Democracies and Resurgent Authoritarianism.

Committees: RC46 Clinical Sociology, RC18 Political Sociology

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Suava ZBIERSKI-SALAMEH, *Haverford Institute, USA*

Chair: David DU TOIT, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-105.1 Anthony KAZIBONI, *University of Johannesburg (UJ), South Africa*
Disengaged Citizenship in Post-Apartheid: A Case of Madibeng Hydropolitics

JS-105.2 Iolanda BIANCHI, *University of Antwerp, Belgium*
Community Co-Production and the Common Beyond Self-Government: The Case of the Patrimoni Ciutadà in Barcelona.

JS-105.3 Shilpa KRISHNAN, *Indian Institute of Technology, Guwhatti, India*
Democratic Environmental Governance, Fisherfolk Communities and the State: A Case of Vizhinjam International Seaport in Kerala

JS-105.4 Marina PERA, *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain*
Building Local Participatory Democracies through Social Infrastructure: The Case of Civic Management Facilities in Barcelona

JS-105.5 Suava ZBIERSKI-SALAMEH, *Haverford Institute, USA*
Post-Socialist Urban-Periphery Development Towards Construction of Alternative City Center: Combining Deliberative and Design Intervention in the Rural County in the Western Poland

JS-106 Climate Change, Poverty and inequality in Globalizing World: Changing Socio-Economic, Environmental Fabric of Human Settlements, neglect of Human Rights and Marginalization of the Poor

Committees: WG05 *Famine and Society*, TG03 *Human Rights and Global Justice*

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Manoj Kumar TEOTIA, *Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development, India* and Namita GUPTA, *Centre for Human Rights and Duties, Panjab University, Chandigarh (India), India*

Chair: Rani MEHTA, *Panjab University, India, India*

Co-Chair: Jagdish Chander MEHTA, *D.A.V. College, Chandigarh (India), India*

Panelists: Minakshi RANA, *MCM DAV, India* and Rimma AKHMETIANOVA, *Institute for Strategic Studies of the Republic of Bashkortostan, Russian Federation*

Discussant: Kashmir KASHYAP, *Government P.G. College, India*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-106.1 Manish K. VERMA, *Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India*
Environment, Development and Sustainability in India

JS-106.2 Eduardo ALMEIDA, *Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain*
Weaponized Development and the Deterritorialization on Indigenous Peoples in Mexico

JS-106.3 Shweta PHULWARI, *Indira Gandhi National Open University, India*
Climate Change and Poverty in India: Reinforcement of Marginalization

JS-106.4 Ramesh KHANAL, *Saraswati Multiple Campus, Nepal*
The Contribution of Nepal's Tourism Workers and Industry to Promoting Responsible Travel

JS-107 Education, Solidarity and Engagement: the Study of Morals and Emotions in Altruistic Educational Experiences

Committees: RC04 *Sociology of Education*, WG08 *Society and Emotions*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Sebastian FUENTES, *CONICET/FLACSO-UNTREF, Argentina* and Mariana NOBILE, *FLACSO Argentina - CONICET / FaHCE - UNLP, Argentina*

Chair: Jekatyerina DUNAJEVA, *Public Policy & Management Inst, Lithuania, Hungary*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-107.1 Nikhil PANDEY, *Mahatma Gandhi Central University, Bihar, India*
Role of Social Capital in Shaping the Learning Experiences of University Students in India: A Case Study of Postgraduate Students of Banaras Hindu University

JS-107.2 Hany ZAYED, *University of Illinois - Urbana Champaign, USA*
'We Are Not Cheating. We Are Helping Each Other out': Cheating, Deviance and Resistance in Egyptian Secondary Education

JS-107.3 Mimar RAMIS SALAS, *University of Barcelona, Spain* and Tinka SCHUBERT, *Institute for Applied Research and Project Support, Germany*
Zero Violence Braves Club, Preventing Violence in Educational Centres

JS-107.4 Simone MEUCCI, *UFPR, Brazil*
"Citizenship Learning" in Brazil: Justifications in Favor of Human Rights, Religious Education, Philosophy and Sociology at Schools (1987-2006)

JS-107.5 Alan MARVELL, *University of Gloucestershire, United Kingdom* and David SIMM, *Bath Spa University, United Kingdom*
Promoting Education, Solidarity and Engagement through International Fieldwork: Facilitating Emotional Responses to Enhance Transformative Learning.

JS-108 Migration and Ageing

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration*, RC11 *Sociology of Ageing*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia* and Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

Chair: Raelene WILDING, *La Trobe University, Australia*

Co-Chair: Myra HAMILTON, *The University of Sydney, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-108.1 Mihaela NEDELCO, *University of Neuchâtel, Institut of Sociology, Switzerland* and Malika WYSS, *University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland*
Transnational Grandparenting Challenged By the Covid-19 Pandemic: Frustration Experiences and Digitally Mediated Coping Strategies

JS-108.2 Rizza Kaye CASES, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
Mobilities and Future Imaginaries of Older Filipino Workers in the Care Sectors of New York and London

JS-108.3 Heidi HETZ, *University of South Australia, Australia* and David RADFORD, *University of South Australia, Australia*
"Because of My Age, I Keep Getting Rejected, Because I'm Too Old to Work There" Unpacking the Complexity of the Lives of Older Hazara Afghani Humanitarian Migrants in a Small Australian Rural Township

JS-108.4 Loretta BALDASSAR, *Edith Cowan University (ECU), Australia*
Digital Kinning and Digital Homing: The Role of Digital Care Labour

JS-109 Organizing through Standards and Value Hierarchies

Committees: RC40 Sociology of Agriculture and Food, RC17 Sociology of Organization

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Allison LOCONTO, *Université Gustave Eiffel, France* and Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*

Chairs: Allison LOCONTO, *Université Gustave Eiffel, France* and Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-109.1 Allison LOCONTO, *Université Gustave Eiffel, France*
Sustainability Standards As Spaces for (Bio)Diversity

JS-109.2 Nikolai SIIMES, *University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Emma L. SHARP, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
The Role of Scalar Standards in Qualifying Wines: An Antipodean Study of Biodynamic Wine Values and Valuation.

JS-109.3 Sohini BHATTACHARJEE, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*
On Paper and on Land: The 'organic' Standard and Organic Farmers of Delhi Ncr

JS-109.4 Romain BLANCANEUX, *Kyoto University, France*; Hart FEUER, *Kyoto University, Japan* and Daniel MONTERESCU, *Central European University, Austria*
Seasonality As Productive Fiction: Reordering Value(s) in Novel Ecological and Temporal Representations of Geographical Indication Products in Japan

JS-109.5 Marie-Christine RENARD, *Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, Mexico* and Graciela RASGADO, *Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, Mexico*
Making Standards for Cocoa Excellence: The Cocoaqualitystandards.Org

JS-109.6 Rachel RECKINGER, *University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg*
Values-Based Territorial Food Networks (VTFN): Qualifying Sustainable and Ethical Transitions of Alternative Food Networks (AFN)

DiStRiButed PAPERS:

JS-109.7 Nadine ARNOLD, *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands* and Christopher DORN, *Universität Bielefeld, Germany*
The Other Side of Values: Observing Wastes in Organizational Contexts

JS-109.8 Adrienne HAWLEY, *South East Technological University, USA*
Making Sex Boring: Organising Relationships through Standardisation

JS-110 Spatial Scales and the Analysis of Biographies and Family (Hi)Stories

Committees: RC38 Biography and Society, RC21 Regional and Urban Development

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Eva BAHL, *University of Goettingen, Germany*; Johannes BECKER, *University of Leipzig, Germany* and Nicole WITTE, *University of Goettingen - Center of Methods in Social Sciences, Germany*

Chair: Johannes BECKER, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-110.1 Goda DAMASEVICIUTE, *Vilnius university, Lithuania*
Childhood in Post-Soviet Lithuania: Precarious Places and Sour Encounters

JS-110.2 Geetika ANAND, *University of Cape Town, South Africa*
Practicing in Cities Against the Backdrop of the Nation and the Self: Auto/Biographies of Urban Practitioners from South Africa

JS-110.3 Rama DEVI, *KREA University, India*
Mapping Socio-Economic Mobility and Urban Inequalities through Spatial Histories and Biographies: Trajectories of Dalit Life in a Metropolitan City, Delhi

JS-110.4 Felipe LINK, *Pontificia Univ Catolica Chile, Chile*
Scales of Sociability: Towards New Forms of Segregation of Social Ties in Urban Space

JS-111 The Language of Risk. Part I

Committees: TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty, RC25 Language and Society

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*

Chair: Maria Grazia GALANTINO, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*

AUthoRS AND PAPERS:

JS-111.1 Fiorenza DERIU, *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*
The Manifold Narratives of the Russian-Ukraine War, and the Primary Components of Their Latent Structure in the Italian Public Debate

JS-111.2 Chandrabali DUTTA, *HIRALAL MAZUMDAR MEMORIAL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, India*
Language, Risk and Protests: The Case of Cab and NRC in India

JS-111.3 Magdalena GIL, *P. Universidad Catolica de Chile, Chile*
The Language of Risk and Responsibility: The Case of the 2010 Chilean Earthquake.

JS-111.4 Stephanie CASSILDE, *Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Belgium*
Sanctions and the Framework of Homeless People: An Analysis of Anticipated or Proven Risks for the "Accueilpagnement" ("welcare") System

DiStRiButed PAPERS:

JS-111.5 Miyako KIMURA, *St. Marianna University School of Medicine, Japan*
Fear of Transmission of the COVID-19: Voices from Mothers of Young Children in Japan

JS-112 To Participate or Not to Participate? Social Movements 4.0 and the Return of Dichotomies

Committees: RC10 Participation, Organizational Democracy and Self-Management, RC34 Sociology of Youth, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Michela FREDDANO, *INVALSI, Italy*; Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom* and Maurizio MERICO, *University of Salerno, Italy*

Chairs: Dasarath CHETTY, *Durban University of Technology, South Africa* and Maurizio MERICO, *University of Salerno, Italy*

Co-Chair: Camilo TAMAYO GOMEZ, *The University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-112.1 Sheetal BHOOLA, *The University of Zululand, South Africa, South Africa*
The Importance of Impact Evaluations of Corporate Social Responsibility Programs and Government Food and Nutrition Programs for South African Children.

JS-112.2 Frank REICHERT, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Anna Julia FIEDLER, *The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Sympathetic but Inactive? – Explaining Youth Non-Participation in Social Movements

JS-112.3 Tova BENSKI, *College of Management Academic Studies, Israel*
The Return of the Maternal Element to Women's Peace Mobilizations in Israel

JS-112.4 Ana ANDREU PEREZ, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*; Raúl LUCENA MARTÍNEZ, *Universidad de Granada, Spain*; Eva CATANO GARCÍA, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*; Ruben MARTIN GIMENO, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain* and Tristán PERTÍÑEZ BLASCO, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*
La Visión Actual De La Sociedad Andaluza Por El Futuro De Europa: El Marco De Las Políticas Europeas Dirigidas a Sus Regiones

JS-113 Uses and Misuses of Arts and Culture in Community and Urban Development ii

Committees: RC03 Community Research, RC37 Sociology of Arts

Location: M2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Terry Nichols CLARK, *University of Chicago, USA* and Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada*

Chair: Hyesun JEONG, *University of Cincinnati, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-113.1 Jake SALLAWAY-COSTELLO, *University of Nottingham, United Kingdom*
Artistic 'Lines of Flight' for Food Security: A New Materialist Appraisal of the Birmingham Creative Class in Community Food Support

JS-113.2 Matt PATTERSON, *University of Calgary, Canada*
Cultural Planning in North American Chinatowns

JS-113.3 Heide IMAI, *Hosei, Japan*
The Liminality of Subculture Spaces: Uncertainty, Community and New Social Divides in Post-Covid Tokyo

JS-113.4 Manish KUMAR, *Mahatma Gandhi Central University, Bihar, India*
Understanding Environmental Conservation through the Lens of Myths, Beliefs and Practices : A Case Study from the Mithila Region in Bihar.

JS-113.5 Doel JAIKISHEN, *Youth for Unity and Voluntary Action, India*
Asserting Youth Identities and Mainstreaming Urban Poor Neighbourhoods: How a Festival Is Using Arts and Culture for Narrative Change

Friday 30 June

08:30 - 10:20

JS-114 Black Lives and the new Wave of Antiracist Mobilization within and across World Regions

Committees: RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements, RC38 Biography and Society

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Nicole DOERR, *University of Copenhagen, Denmark* and Sabrina ZAJAK, *German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Berlin & Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany*

Chair: Eren YETKIN, *Koblenz University of Applied Sciences, Germany*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-114.1 Sabrina ZAJAK, *German Center for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Berlin & Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany* and Jill PÖGGEL, *German Center of Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM), Germany*
Waves of Anti-Racist Mobilization and Challenges to Racial Capitalism Since the 1980 until Today

JS-114.3 Eija RANTA, *University of Helsinki, Finland*
Emerging Anti-Racism Activism and Discourses of Racism in Times of Political Polarization in Bolivia

JS-114.4 Selvaraj VELAYUTHAM, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Chand SOMAIAH, *Yale-NUS College, Singapore*
@Minority Voices: Racialised Communicative Labour and Anti-Racism in Singapore

JS-115 CoViD-19: Patterns in Domestic Military operations

Committees: RC01 Armed Forces and Conflict Resolution, RC39 Sociology of Disasters

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizers: Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada* and Lindy HEINECKEN, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*

Chair: Cornelis KOONINGS, *University of Utrecht, Netherlands*

Panelists: Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada* and Lindy HEINECKEN, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-115.1 Tyler WENTZELL, *Canadian Forces College, Canada*
Built to Scale? the Canadian Armed Forces' Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-115.2 Maria Sabrina Erica CARLOS, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines* and Leslie ADVINCULA-LOPEZ, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*
The Recrafting of CIVIL-Military Relations during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Insights from a Naval Operating Base in the Philippines

JS-115.3 Mario Joyo AGUJA, *Mindanao State University-General Santos City, Philippines*
The Philippine Military during the Covid 19 Pandemic: Perspectives, Roles and Challenges

JS-115.4 Richard IROANYA, *University of Namibia, Namibia*
Military Deployment in Times of Crises: The Namibian Experience with COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-115.5 Lindy HEINECKEN, *Stellenbosch University, South Africa*
South Africa: Domestic Operations and the Military Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-115.6 Christian LEUPRECHT, *Royal Military College of Canada, Canada*
Domestic Military Deployments: Canada

JS-115.7 Veronica AZZI, *FGV CPDOC, Brazil* and Celso CASTRO, *Fundação Getulio Vargas, Brazil*
COVID-19 and Comparative Domestic Military Deployments: The Case of Brazil

JS-116 inclusive Education, Knowledge Co-Production, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education, RC03 Community Research

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Sin Yi CHEUNG, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom* and Rachel FREEMAN, *University of Namibia, Namibia*

Chair: Hany ZAYED, *University of Illinois - Urbana Champaign, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-116.1 Sudarat MUSIKAWONG, *Institute for Population, Thailand*; tammy Ko ROBINSON, *Hanyang University, Republic of Korea*; Teeranong SAKULSRI, *Mahidol University, Thailand*; Pichaiwat SAENGRAPAN, *Chulalongkorn University, Thailand*; Adisorn KERDMONGKOL, *Migrant Working Group- Thailand, Thailand* and Sirijit SUNANTA, *Mahidol University, Thailand*
Transversals in Migrant Workers Rights: Mahidol Migration Center's Social Lab, Policy Dialogues, and Alternative Politics

JS-116.2 Hulda WEHMANN, *Federal University of ABC, Brazil*
The Democratic Co-Production of the City As an Academic Activity: Learning through Experience in Communities in the Southern Region of the City of São Paulo – Brazil

JS-116.3 Ada FREYTES FREY, *Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda/Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche, Argentina* and Adriana ARROYO ORTEGA, *MINCIENCIAS, Colombia*
Knowledge Co-Production between University Research Teams and High School Teachers: Educational Inclusion, Peace Building and Citizenship in Secondary Schools in Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires and Medellin.

JS-116.4 Salvador VIDAL-ORTIZ, *American University, USA*
The Bachillerato Popular Travesti/Trans Mocha Celis: Collaborative Knowledge-Making

DiStRiButed PAPERS:

JS-116.5 Roberta RICUCCI, *Univ. degli studi di Torino, Italy*; Lena DE BOTTON, *University of Barcelona, Spain* and Roger CAMPDEPADROS, *Universitat de Girona, Spain*
Integrating Immigrant Students and Increasing Local Students' Acceptance in Europe through the Buddy System and the Dialogic Learning

JS-116.6 Asrafi AKRAM, *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Bangladesh* and

Mohammad HASAN, *Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Bangladesh*
Functional Toilet for Menstruating Adolescent Girls: A Study on Northern Bangladesh

JS-117 international Political Economy of Digital Platforms: Sovereignty and Infrastructural Power

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society, RC23 Sociology of Science and Technology

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: June WANG, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Julia TOMASSETTI, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*

Chair: Julia TOMASSETTI, *City University of Hong Kong, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-117.1 Karolina MIKOLAJEWSKA-ZAJAC, *University of Queensland, Australia*
An Ecosystemic Perspective on the Growth of Airbnb

JS-117.2 Olivier JUTEL, *University of Otago, New Zealand*
Platform Governance and the Hybrid War Industrial Complex

JS-117.3 Liu CAO, *Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University, China*
Wanghong Urbanism and Its Politics of (re)Making the Place through New Urban Aestheticisation

JS-117.4 Anne KOVALAINEN, *University of Turku, Finland* and Seppo POUTANEN, *University of Turku, Finland*
Platformization As a New Social Order

JS-117.5 Kb HEYLEN, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Australia's News Media Bargaining Code: A Case Study in Digital Platform Sovereignty

JS-117.6 June WANG, *City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
Constructing the Value Chain of the Creator Economy in China

Discussion

JS-118 Language on Health Under COVID-19 Pandemic. Part ii

Committees: RC25 Language and Society, RC15 Sociology of Health

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Keiji FUJIYOSHI, *Otemon Gakuin University, Japan* and Miwako HOSODA, *Seisa University, Japan*

Chair: Mark SEILHAMER, *National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-118.1 Raphaella DWIANTO, *Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia*
From 'God the Almighty' to 'Remember Mom's Words': Negotiating Language during COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-118.2 Miyako KIMURA, *St. Marianna University School of Medicine, Japan*
Key Person Who Influenced Behavior of Mothers with Young Children during the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-118.3 Valeriya VASILKOVA, *Saint Petersburg State University, Russian Federation, Russian Federation* and

Natalia LEGOSTAEVA, *St. Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*

Linguistic and Communicative Strategies of COVID-Trolling in the Russian Social Network "Vkontakte"

JS-118.4 Nadezhda GEORGIEVA-STANKOVA, *Trakia University, Bulgaria*

Discursive Dimensions of Media Representation of Roma Identity and the Ghetto in the Context of Covid-19

JS-118.5 Chandrabali DUTTA, HIRALAL MAZUMDAR
MEMORIAL COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, India

COVID-19, Media Representations and Dismal Health-Care in India: A Sociological Analysis

JS-118.6 Keiko NISHIMURA, *Sophia University, Japan*
Language and Representation of Health, Science, and Credibility in COVID-19 Pandemic: Analysis of COVID-19-Themed Manga

JS-119 Persistence and Change: Collaborative, Conceptual and Contextual Global Understandings of Gender-Based and Intersectional Violence

Committees: TG11 *Violence and Society*, RC32 *Women, Gender and Society*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Margaret ABRAHAM, *Hofstra University, USA* and Stefani VASIL, *Monash University, Australia*

Chair: Marie SEGRAVE, *Monash Gender and Family Violence Prevention Centre and Monash Migration and Inclusion Centre, Monash University, Australia, Australia*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-119.1 Valentine MOGHADAM, *Northeastern University, USA* and Omid GHADERZADEH, *University of Kurdistan, Iran*

Scales of Violence: Iranian Kurdistan in Context

JS-119.2 Evangelia TASTSOGLU, *Saint Mary's University, Canada* and Jane FREEDMAN, *Université Paris 8, France*

The Gbv-MIG Project: A Collaborative, Conceptual and Contextual Global Understanding of Gender-Based and Intersectional Violence

JS-119.3 Manali DESAI, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*; Kammila NAIDOO, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*; Nandini GOOPTU, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*; Lyn OSSOME, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa* and Sanjay SRIVASTAVA, *SOAS, University of London, United Kingdom*

Gendered Violence and Urban Transformation in India and South Africa

JS-119.4 Margaret ABRAHAM, *Hofstra University, USA* and Stefani VASIL, *Monash University, Australia*

Migrant Women, Domestic Violence, and the State: A Comparative, Intersectional Analysis of the United States of America and Australia

JS-119.5 Marlise MATOS ALMEIDA, *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil*

Violence Against Women and the Layers of Racist and Cissexist Patriarchal Junction: A Decolonial Reading

10:30 - 12:20

JS-120 Bodies, Emotions and Social interaction. Part ii

Committees: RC54 *The Body in the Social Sciences*, WG08 *Society and Emotions*

Location: M6 (Crown)

Session organizer: Leticia SILVA, *Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil*

Chair: Leticia SILVA, *Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Brazil*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-120.1 Dietmar WETZEL, *MSH Medical School, Hamburg & University of Basel, Switzerland*

Affective Resonance and Conflict in the Context of Bodily Social Interactions

JS-120.2 Dulce FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, *University of Brasilia, Brazil*

For the Humanization of Bodies: A Reflection from David Le Breton and Tim Ingold

JS-120.3 Rui GOMES, *University of Coimbra, Centre for Social Studies, Portugal*

Body and Risks

JS-120.4 Sarah MACLEAN, *La Trobe University, Australia*
Drinking Alcohol at Home Feels Different to Drinking in Public Places

JS-120.5 Sanjana TEWARI, *University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy*

Dancing with Differences: Case of Kathak Dance in London

JS-120.6 Atufah NISHAT, *Centre for Studies in Social Sciences Calcutta, India*

Sleeping Bodies As Protesting Bodies

JS-121 Combating Homelessness in Welfare State Regimes: A new Paradigm Shift in Local Social Policy?

Committees: RC18 *Political Sociology*, RC19 *Poverty, Social Welfare and Social Policy*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Frank SOWA, *Nuremberg Institute of Technology Georg Simon Ohm, Germany* and Marco HEINRICH, *Nuremberg Institute of Technology Georg Simon Ohm, Germany*

Chair: Alexandra KAASCH, *Bielefeld University, Germany*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-121.1 Elena BRUSHINSKI, *Carl von Ossietzky University Oldenburg, Germany*

The Discomfort at the Edge of the Sidewalk: Homelessness As a Social Phenomenon between Stigmatization and Social Invisibility

JS-121.2 Ke-hsien HUANG, *National Taiwan University, Sociology Department, Taiwan* and Yi-ching HUANG, *Sociology Department, National Taiwan University, Taiwan*
Caring for the Homeless, Caring for Oneself: Innovative Practices and Reflexivity of New-Type Workers for the Homeless in Taipei

JS-121.3 Christopher HERRING, *UCLA, USA*
Complaint-Oriented "Services": Shelters As Tools of Criminalizing Homelessness

JS-121.4 Mehmet ali AKYURT, *Istanbul University, Turkey* and Melike halide EKINCI, *Istanbul University, Turkey*
The Role of Social Networks in Escaping Homelessness: A Qualitative Study on Former Homeless Men in Istanbul

JS-121.5 Teresa CONSOLI, *University of Catania, Italy* and Antonella MEO, *University of Torino, Italy*
Homelessness in Italy. Housing Led Policies between Rhetoric and Welfare Reformation

JS-122 Community Influences on Lifestyles and Health

Committees: RC03 Community Research, RC15 Sociology of Health

Location: 212 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Angel ZAPATA MOYA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain* and Cristina MATEOS MORA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*

Chair: Angel ZAPATA MOYA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*

Co-Chair: Cristina MATEOS MORA, *Pablo de Olavide University, Spain*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-122.1 Jesus RIVERA-NAVARRO, *University of Salamanca, Spain*; Raquel VIDAL BLANCO, *Salamanca University. Department of Sociology, Spain*; Ignacio GONZALEZ SALGADO, *Salamanca University. Department of Sociology, Spain* and Guadalupe RAMOS-TRUCHERO, *University of Valladolid, Spain*
Food Environmental and Inequalities. Determinants in Adolescent Food Consumption in Spain

JS-122.2 Camila RONDEROS, *Fundación Keralty, Colombia*
Proyecto a-Guajira: Promoviendo La Salud En La Alta Guajira

JS-122.3 Tadaaki FUJITANI, *Soai University, Japan*
Influence of Place Memories on People's Lives

JS-122.4 Daniel DOHAN, *University of California San Francisco, USA*; Melissa MA, *University of California San Francisco, USA*; Alma HERNANDEZ, *University of California San Francisco, USA*; Stephen ZAMARRIPA, *University of California San Francisco, USA* and Corey ABRAMSON, *University of Arizona, USA*
Comparative Ethnography to Understand Experiences of Aging and Cognitive Decline in Diverse US Communities

JS-122.5 Sophie LEWIS, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Maja MOENSTED, *University of Sydney, Australia*; Karen WILLIS, *Melbourne Health, Australia*; Leslie DUBBIN, *University of California, San Francisco, USA* and Lorraine SMITH, *University of Sydney, Australia*
Sense of Place, Space and Loneliness for People Living with Chronic Conditions

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-122.6 Patricia RUIZ-ANGEL, *Universidad Pablo de Olavide (Sevilla), Spain* and Ruiz Repullo, Carmen RUIZ REPULLO, *Universidad de Jaén, Spain*
Digitized Cultural Practices in Two Different Territorial Areas: Spain and Andalusia in the Period 2006-2022.

JS-122.7 Raimundo RAIMUNDO PAULINO SILVA, *University of São Paulo, Brazil* and Samuel ROSA, *Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil*
Impacts of the Pandemic and Housing Conditions: A Sociological Study with Residents of the North and South Area of Natal-Brazil

JS-123 Educational Migration in the Post-Pandemic World: Exploring Continuities and Discontinuities

Committees: RC04 Sociology of Education, RC31 Sociology of Migration

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Hiroki IGARASHI, *Chiba University, Japan* and Hiro SAITO, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Chair: Hiroki IGARASHI, *Chiba University, Japan*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-123.1 Douglas TRELFA, *Tamagawa University, College of Arts and Sciences, Japan*; Aki YAMADA, *Tamagawa University, College of Arts and Sciences, Japan* and Yuichiro KOYAMA, *Tamagawa University, College of Arts and Sciences, Japan*
Global Mobility Aspirations and Orientation Among Students at a Private Japanese University

JS-123.2 Yasmin ORTIGA, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Flexible Universities, Unlikely Destinations: Coping with Uncertainty at the Periphery of International Higher Education

JS-123.3 Varsha JOSHI, *International Institute of migration and development, India* and Rohit IRUDAYARAJAN, *International Institute of migration and development, India*
Experience of Indian Students Abroad: Victims of Recruitment Agency Frauds.

JS-123.4 Charles ADEYANJU, *University of Prince Edward Island, Canada*
COVID-19 and Nigerian Migration to Canada for Higher Education

JS-123.5 Elisabeth SCHILLING, *FHöV NRW, Germany*
Young Refugees and Their Education in the Post-Pandemic World

DiSt RiBUt ED PAPERS:

JS-123.6 Oral ROBINSON, *University of British Columbia, Canada*
Doing Care: The Role of Social Networks in Promoting International Students Migration

JS-123.7 Milos DEBNAR, *Ryukoku University, Japan*; Wolfram MANZENREITER, *University of Vienna, Austria* and Christopher KUMMER, *University of Vienna, Austria*
Motivations for Study Abroad Among Central European Students of East Asian Studies amidst the Fading out Pandemic

JS-124 indigenous Sociology, indigenous Lifeworlds

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity, RC20 Comparative Sociology

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Tahu KUKUTAI, *The University of Waikato, New Zealand* and Margaret WALTER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Chair: Margaret WALTER, *University of Tasmania, Australia*

Co-Chair: Tahu KUKUTAI, *The University of Waikato, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-124.1 Yvonne SHERWOOD, *University of Toronto, Mississauga, Canada* and Michelle JACOB, *University of Oregon, USA*
Indigenous Womxn's Embodied Theory and Praxis

JS-124.2 Robert HENRY, *University of Saskatchewan, Canada*
Settler Colonialism's Code of the Streets: Street Violence, Street Gangs, and Supporting the Indigenous Body As Violent

JS-124.3 Huw PEACOCK, *University of Tasmania, Australia* and Michael GUERZONI, *University of Tasmania, Australia*
Kids Feeling Good about Being Indigenous at School and Its Link to Heightened Educational Aspirations

JS-124.4 Arapera BLANK-PENETITO, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Naomi FUAMATU, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Tamasailau SUAALII-SAUNI, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*; Juan TAURI, *University of Auckland, New Zealand* and Robert WEBB, *University of Auckland, New Zealand*
Māori Rangatahi, Samoan Talavou and Youth Justice in Aotearoa New Zealand

JS-124.5 Allison RAMIREZ, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*
Race and Indigeneity: Accounting for Kinship in Racial Boundaries

JS-125 Linking Ages - Pathways to Cross-Fertilizing the Fields of Age and Childhood Studies

Committees: RC53 *Sociology of Childhood*, RC11 *Sociology of Aging*

Location: 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Lucia RABELLO DE CASTRO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Valeria LLOBET, *CONICET / UNSAM, Argentina* and Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Anna URBANIAK, *NUI Galway, Austria*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-125.1 Anne RAMOS, *University of Fribourg, Switzerland* and Insa FOOKEN, *University of Siegen, Germany*
Age(ism), Adultcentrism or Generational Ordering? Linking Childhood and Ageing Research

JS-125.2 Milena FELDMANN, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*; Karla WAZINSKI, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany* and Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*
Linking Ages in Academic Research: Making Material-Discursive Age Boundaries through Studying Bodies and Spaces in Early and Late Adulthood

JS-125.3 Clary KREKULA, *Linnaeus University, Sweden*
The Biosocial Construction of Age: On the Political Use of Age in Age Determination of Asylum Seekers and in Healthcare Prioritization during the Covid 19 Pandemic

JS-125.4 Ginte MARTINKENE, *Klaipeda university, Lithuania*
Bridging Transnational Life Experiences: From Childhood to Adulthood

JS-125.5 Irina KRETSEK, *Saint-Petersburg State University, Russian Federation*
"It Is so Difficult to be a Younger Sibling All the Time": Younger / Elder Relations As a Biological Fact and Social Construction

JS-125.6 Marc SZYDLIK, *University of Zurich, Department of Sociology, Switzerland*; Bettina ISENGARD, *University of Zurich, Department of Sociology, Switzerland* and Ronny KÖNIG, *University of Zurich, Department of Sociology, Switzerland*
Childhood and Aging: Connecting Generations

JS-126 Mental Health and Risk

Committees: RC49 *Mental Health and Illness*, TG04 *Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*

Location: 210 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Jeremy DIXON, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*

Chair: Jeremy DIXON, *University of Bath, United Kingdom*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-126.1 Silvia KRUMM, *Ulm University, Germany*
Gender and Violence in the Psychiatric Context

JS-126.2 Piyush PUSHKAR, *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*
The Role of Shame in Forensic Psychiatric Assessment and Treatment

JS-126.3 Maryam MEHRABI, *Alzahra university, Iran* and Maryam Ghazinejad MARYAM GHAZINEJAD, *Faculty member of the Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social and Economic Sciences, Al-Zahra University, Tehran, Iran*
Conceptual Investigation of the Social Acceptability of Drug Use Disorders Services in the Primary Health Care System from the Iranian Client's Perspective

JS-126.4 Kitty LASSINANTTI, *Malardalen University, Sweden* and Anna-lena ALMQVIST, *Malardalen University, Sweden*
Out-of-Home Care of Young People with 'Complex Needs'. A Parental Perspective on Risk Management

JS-127 Thinking through and Beyond Capitalism after the Great Reset

Committees: RC02 *Economy and Society*, RC16 *Sociological Theory*

Location: CCH2 (Crown)

Session organizer: Hiro SAITO, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

Chair: Hiro SAITO, *University of Tokyo, Japan*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-127.1 Alwyn LIM, *Singapore Management University, Singapore*
Accelerationism: Capitalism Beyond the Great Reset

JS-127.2 Svetlana KIRDINA-CHANDLER, *Institute of Economics, Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation*
The Formation of a Bipolar World with a New Anti-Capitalist Coalition?

JS-127.3 Carlos PALACIOS, *Macquarie University, Australia*
The Test for "Post-Neoliberal" Governance: Harnessing Human Value with Residual Competition

JS-127.4 Christian GIRARD, *The University of the South Pacific, Fiji*
Social Entrepreneurship and Social Business: Foundations for the 'Great Reset' or Canary in the Coal Mine?

15:30 - 17:20

JS-128 Approaching Planetary Youth Research**Committees:** WG01 *Sociology of Local-Global Relations*, RC34 *Sociology of Youth***Location:** 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizers:** Sofia LAINE, *The Finnish Youth Research Network, Finland* and Kari SAARI, *Juvenia – youth research and development centre, Finland***Chair:** Sofia LAINE, *The Finnish Youth Research Network, Finland***AU THORS AND PAPERS:****JS-128.1** Wendi LI, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Global Youth Climate Activism and Planetary Citizenship in Times of Crisis: A Global North and South Comparative Perspective**JS-128.2** Rachel ZHOU, *McMaster University, Canada*
Moving Toward a Generational Conversation on Transplanetary Connectivity: A Case of Collective Reading By Global Youth on Reddit**JS-128.3** Hart FEUER, *Kyoto University, Japan*
Youth Food Literacy for Global Health and Ecology: Building Food System Awareness and Action**JS-128.4** Syafiqah ABDUL RAHIM, *Malaysian Youth Council, Malaysia*
Nature School Pedagogy in Re-Imagining Sustainable Future of Young People in Malaysia**JS-128.5** Mathias ALBERT, *Bielefeld University, Germany*
What Would a Planetary Youth Study Look like? the Challenges of Overcoming Methodological Nationalism**JS-129 Brokering novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: innovation and Dynamism****Committees:** RC02 *Economy and Society*, RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis***Location:** P1 (Crown)**Session organizer:** Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA***Chair:** Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA***AU THORS AND PAPERS:****JS-129.1** Dana KORNBERG, *UC-Santa Barbara, USA*
Transactional Pathways**JS-129.2** Dustin STOLTZ, *Lehigh University, USA*
Theorizing Imaginative Labor**JS-129.3** Po-Fang TSAI, *National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan*
Einverständnis: A Neglected Concept in the Tradition and Field of Economy and Society**JS-129.4** Arnaud SALES, *Université de Montréal, Canada*
Innovative Corporate Networks and Dynamic Reticular Structures*Discussion***JS-130 Complexity in the Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe (ii)****Committees:** RC51 *Sociocybernetics*, RC18 *Political Sociology*, RC31 *Sociology of Migration***Location:** 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizers:** Patricia Eugenia ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, *Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain* and Murat AKTAS, *Mus Alparslan University, Turkey***Chair:** Juan Carlos BARRON-PASTOR, *CISAN UNAM, Mexico***Co-Chair:** Fabio GIGLIETTO, *Università di Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy***AU THORS AND PAPERS:****JS-130.1** Rafael BOCKER ZAVARO, *Rovira i Virgili University, Spain*
Populism: Political Concept and Phenomenon**JS-130.2** Andrea MACCARINI, *University of Padova, Italy*
The Clash within Civilizations? a Cultural Sociology of Populism**JS-130.3** Felicien FAURY, *Paris Dauphine University, France* and Elisa BELLE, *Sciences Po CEE, France*
Going Local, Going Mainstream? an Ethnography of Two Cities Governed By the French Rassemblement National**JS-130.4** Maria TORRES, *Universidade de Coimbra, Brazil*
A Populist Contitucionalism As a Challenge for 21st Century Democracy'S: An Analysis of Hungary Under the Orbán Regime**JS-131 Emotions and Environmental Activism****Committees:** RC47 *Social Classes and Social Movements*, WG08 *Society and Emotions***Location:** 204 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizers:** Roger PATULNY, *University of Wollongong, Australia*; Rebecca OLSON, *University of Queensland, Australia* and Jordan MCKENZIE, *University of Wollongong, Australia***Chair:** Roger PATULNY, *University of Wollongong, Australia***Co-chairs:** Camila PONCE LARA, *Philipps Universität Marburg, Germany* and Pedro LISDERO, *CIECS (CONICET y UNC) / UNVM / CIES, Argentina***AU THORS AND PAPERS:****JS-131.1** Victoria D'HERS, *CONICET-IIGG, Argentina*
Catharsis and Politics. Art and Cultural Movements Responding to Climate Crisis**JS-131.2** Jesse CARLSON, *Acadia University, Canada*
Look up: Popular Culture, Public Feelings, and Social Theories of Climate Change Activism**JS-131.3** Rebecca OLSON, *School of Social Science, The University of Queensland, Australia*; Alberto BELLOCCHI, *Faculty of Education, Queensland University of Technology, Australia* and Jordan MCKENZIE, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
Holding and Harnessing Distress: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Emotions in Australian News Reporting on Climate Change and Climate Anxiety**JS-131.4** Joseph edward ALEGADO, *Australian National University Crawford School of Public Policy, Australia*
Unpacking Philippines' Zero Waste Community Sites As a Pathway for Degrowth in the Global South

JS-132 **the Prospects of a Pluriversal transition to a Post-Capitalist, Post-Carbon Future**

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: S A Hamed HOSSEINI, School of Humanities, Creative Industries and Social Sciences, Australia and Barry GILLS, University of Helsinki, Finland

Chair: S A Hamed HOSSEINI, School of Humanities, Creative Industries and Social Sciences, Australia

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-132.1 Damien KRICHEWSKY, University of Bonn, Germany
Pushing Pluriversal Transformation through the Cracks of 'Sustainable Development': An Emancipatory Journey in the Worlds of Access & Benefit-Sharing

JS-132.2 Anja HABERSANG, University of Kassel, Germany
Tackling Terricidal and Not (only) Climate Change – a Pluriversal Perspective on the Global and Multifaceted Crisis of Capitalist Modernity

JS-132.3 Eija RANTA, University of Helsinki, Finland
Reforming and Resisting Development: The History and the Present of Development Alternatives

JS-132.4 S A Hamed HOSSEINI, School of Humanities, Creative Industries and Social Sciences, Australia and Barry GILLS, University of Helsinki, Finland
Redefining Value: Toward a Normative Value Theory As an Integrative Platform for Transformative Praxes

JS-133 **Understanding the Entanglements of Urban Disasters**

Committees: RC21 Regional and Urban Development, RC43 Housing and Built Environment, RC39 Sociology of Disasters

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Sonia ROITMAN, The University of Queensland, Australia and Flavio DE SOUZA, Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil

Chairs: Sonia ROITMAN, The University of Queensland, Australia and Flavio DE SOUZA, Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil

Discussant: Emma PORIO, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-133.1 Michele COMPANION, University of Colorado-Colorado Springs, USA
"Building Resilience through Greening the Urban Landscape in Kyoto, Japan"

JS-133.2 David KING, James Cook University, Australia
Climate Change Adaptation in Australia from a Professional Planning Perspective

JS-133.3 Jia ZHANG, Tsinghua University, China and Fei WANG, Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School, China
Resilient Communities Evaluation

JS-133.4 Fuminori KAWAMI, Doshisha University, Japan
Inequality of Housing Recovery after Great East Japan Earthquake Disaster

JS-133.5 Sanjukta BHADURI, SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE, India
Disaster and Climate Change Affected Persons in Cities

17:30 - 19:20

JS-134 **(Re)turning to Urban (new) normality**

Committees: RC03 Community Research, RC21 Regional and Urban Development

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Marta KLEKOTKO, Jagiellonian University, Poland; Marta SMAGACZ-POZIEMSKA, Jagiellonian University, Poland and Natalia MARTINI, Jagiellonian University, Poland

Chair: Marta KLEKOTKO, Jagiellonian University, Poland

Co-Chair: Natalia MARTINI, Jagiellonian University, Poland

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-134.1 Sybille FRANK, Technical University Darmstadt, Germany and Georg KRAJEWSKY, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany
Unsettling the Heritage of Urbanity: Urbanism and Urban Space in (Post-)Pandemic Times

JS-134.2 Macarena IBARRA, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile and Felipe LINK, Pontificia Univ Católica Chile, Chile
Planning for Post-Pandemic Neighborhoods of Metropolitan Cities. the Case of Santiago De Chile.

JS-134.3 Zeynep ATAS, Mardin Artuklu University Department of Architecture, Turkey and Yuvacan ATMACA, Mardin Artuklu University Department of Architecture, Turkey
New Strategies for Urban Development after Covid-19

JS-134.4 Alberto LUSOLI, Digital Democracies Institute, Simon Fraser University, Italy
The Impact of Remote Work on U.S. Rural Regions and Second-Tier Cities during the COVID-19 Pandemic

JS-134.5 Albeniz EZME GURLEK, Ahi Evran University, Turkey
Changing Demand for a City to Live in the Pandemic: Kırşehir and Istanbul As a Comparison of a Metropolis and a Country

JS-135 **Brokering novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Relational and Cultural Analysis**

Committees: RC35 Conceptual and Terminological Analysis, RC02 Economy and Society

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Dustin STOLTZ, Lehigh University, USA

Chair: Dustin STOLTZ, Lehigh University, USA

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-135.1 Ekaterina SVETLOVA, University of Twente, Netherlands
Methodological Relationalism

JS-135.2 Jordi MUNDÓ, University of Barcelona, Spain
Fiduciary Relationships

JS-135.3 Aaron PITLUCK, Illinois State University, USA
Conflicts of Interest

JS-135.4 Tom DUTERME, *University of Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium* and Jean DE MUNCK, *University of Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium*
The Semiosis and the Market: What Peirce Can Learn to Economic Sociology

JS-135.5 Xiangyu MA, *University of Chicago, USA*
Tastes and Complex Tastes.

Discussion

JS-136 Knowledge Co-Production, Communities, Social Justice and Human Rights

Committees: RC09 *Social Transformations and Sociology of Development*, RC15 *Sociology of Health*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Sin Yi CHEUNG, *Cardiff University, United Kingdom* and Rachel FREEMAN, *University of Namibia, Namibia*

Chair: Brian DILL, *University of Illinois, USA*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-136.1 Branwen PEDDI, *Ghent University, Belgium* and Joost DESSEIN, *Ghent University, Belgium*
Mobilising Academic, Indigenous and Local Knowledge for Inclusive Agricultural Development: A Case Study in the Upper East Region of Ghana

JS-136.2 Kien NGUYEN-TRUNG, *Monash University, Australia*
Navigate the Complexity of Climate Adaptation Co-Design Process: Reflections on Knowledge Co-Production

JS-136.3 Marzell GRAY, *University of Minnesota Duluth, USA*; Linda GIBSON, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*; Damilola OMODARA, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*; Michael BROWN, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*; Natewinde SAWADOGO, *Thomas Sankara University, Burkina Faso* and David MUSOKE, *Makerere University, Uganda*
Using a Collaborative Online International Learning Approach to Apply Social Theories to Global Health and Development Issues

JS-136.4 Sally BASHFORD-SQUIRES, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom*; Michael BROWN, *Nottingham Trent University, United Kingdom* and Grace LUBEGA, *Makerere University, Uganda*
Researchers from a Minority World Working in a Majority World Setting: Prioritising Indigenous Knowledge When Working with Ugandan Communities

JS-136.5 Elena NICHINI, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Saba ASIM, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*; Yan ZENG, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong* and Faustina YIP, *JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong*
"I Need to be Heard": Community Based Participatory Action Research to Explore South Asian Women's Health Experiences in Hong Kong

JS-136.6 Àlex BOSÓ, *Ciemat, Spain*; Jaime GARRIDO, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile*; Ignacio RODRÍGUEZ, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile* and Luz Karime SÁNCHEZ-GALVIS, *Universidad de la Frontera, Chile*
Exploring Role-Playing As a Tool for Involving Citizens in Air Pollution Mitigation Urban Policies

JS-137 The Rise of the Far Right and Populist Movements in Europe

Committees: RC31 *Sociology of Migration*, RC18 *Political Sociology*, RC51 *Sociocybernetics*

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Murat AKTAS, *Mus Alparslan University, Turkey*

Chair: Jennifer CLARK, *South Texas College, USA*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-137.1 Pamela Irving JACKSON, *Rhode Island College, USA* and Peter DOERSCHLER, *Bloomsburg University of Pennsylvania, USA*
What Drives Support for Authoritarian Populist Parties in Eastern and Central Europe?

JS-137.2 Marta KOLCZYNSKA, *Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland* and Ireneusz SADOWSKI, *Institute of Political Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*
Through Partisan Lenses. How Political Trust and Policy Assessment Changed Under the Law and Justice Rule in Poland

JS-137.3 Mirko BRAACK, *Research Institute Social Cohesion (Forschungsinstitut Gesellschaftlicher Zusammenhalt), Germany*; Melanie DIETZ, *Research Institute Social Cohesion, Section Frankfurt am Main, Germany* and Sigrid ROSSTEUTSCHER, *Research Institute Social Cohesion, Section Frankfurt am Main, Germany*
How Do Competing Gender Ideologies Impact Voters in Germany?

JS-137.4 Michal NAWROCKI, *Faculty of Sociology, University of Warsaw, Poland*
Exploring Populist Epistemologies: Knowledge Practices of Law and Justice's (PiS) Supporters

Saturday 1 July

08:30 - 10:20

JS-138 Brokering novel Concepts into Economic Sociology: Societal Variation, Entrepreneurship

Committees: RC35 *Conceptual and Terminological Analysis*, RC02 *Economy and Society*

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Alexander EBNER, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Chair: Aaron PITLUCK, *Illinois State University, USA*

AU THORS AND PAPERS:

JS-138.1 Yuhao LIAO, *University of California-Riverside, USA* and Christopher CHASE-DUNN, *University of California-Riverside, USA*
Deglobalization: Conceptual Issues and Long-Term Global Social Change

JS-138.2 Mayya SHMIDT, *Uppsala University, Sweden*
On the Concept of Sharing

JS-138.3 Quentin SCHNAPPER, *LaSSP, France*
From Family Businesses to "Houses": Virtues of an Old-Fashioned Anthropological Concept to the Study of Entrepreneurship

JS-138.4 Lewei HUANG, *The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong*; Chenyun GUO, *Sun Yat-sen University, China* and Zijie SONG, *Sun Yat-sen University, China*
Relational Mobility and Entrepreneurship

Discussion

JS-139 Racial Capitalisms, Spatial Productions

Committees: RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity, RC02 Economy and Society

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Nicole TRUJILLO-PAGAN, *Wayne State University, USA*

Chair: Matthew WAYMOUTH, *iNZight Analytics, New Zealand*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-139.1 Kasey HENRICKS, *University of Tennessee at Knoxville, USA* and Diego TABOADA, *University of Tennessee at Knoxville, USA*
A City so Cold: Winter Parking on the Streets of Segrenomics

JS-139.2 Jiyoung KIM, *IDHE.S-Nanterre, France*
The Coloniality of Spatial Production : Gentrification in Canal Saint-Martin Neighbourhood in Paris

JS-139.3 Jessica TERRUHN, *University of Waikato, New Zealand*
Rethinking Residential Segregation through an Anti-Racist Lens

10:30 - 12:20

JS-140 Digital Urbanism

Committees: TG10 Digital Sociology, RC21 Regional and Urban Development

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Regev NATHANSOHN, *Sapir College, Israel*; Miguel Angel MARTINEZ LOPEZ, *University of Uppsala, Sweden* and Talja BLOKLAND, *Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany*

Chair: Talja BLOKLAND, *Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-140.1 Kasey HENRICKS, *University of Tennessee at Knoxville, USA* and Ruben ORTIZ, *Center for Policing Equity, USA*
The Irrelevance of Innocence: Ethnoracial Context, Occupational Differences in Policing, and Tickets Issued in Error

JS-140.2 Josephine SEAH, *University of Cambridge, United Kingdom*
Gaming Gamification: (Not) Walking with Singapore's National Steps Challenge

JS-140.3 Gerald AHABWE, *Makerere University, Uganda*; Dauda DAUDA WAISWA BATEGA, *Makerere University, Uganda* and Achilles SSEWAYA, *Makerere University, Uganda*
Social Construction of Prepayment in Water Service Provision in Uganda.

JS-140.4 Danielle CHEVALIER, *Leiden Law School, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Netherlands*
From Skate Zone to Tiktok: How Social Media Affects the Production of Public Space.

JS-141 Future Visions, Strategies, and Contentious Politics. Part i

Committees: RC07 Futures Research, RC47 Social Classes and Social Movements, RC48 Social Movements, Collective Actions and Social Change

Location: 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*

Chair: Markus S. SCHULZ, *Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Germany*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-141.1 Paolo GERBAUDO, *Industries Department, United Kingdom*
Social Movements in Times of Ecological Risk Social Implosion

JS-141.2 Nataliya VELIKAYA, *Institute of Social and Political Research of Russian Academy of Science, Russian Federation*
Alternatives to the Future Development of the Country from Russians' Point of View As a Factor in the Political System Transformation.

JS-141.3 Geci KARURI-SEBINA, *Wits School of Governance, South Africa*; Robin BOURGEOIS, *CIRAD, France* and Eva Kwamou FEUKEU, *Lancaster University, United Kingdom*
The Future As a Public Good

JS-141.4 Jordan MCKENZIE, *University of Wollongong, Australia*
A Sociology of the Future?

JS-141.5 Maximilian WECKEMANN, *Berlin Social Science Center (WZB), Germany*
Polarising the Future, Mobilising 'the People' - the Temporal Structure of Querdenker Future Horizons

JS-142 Participation Chances, inequality and Risks of Exclusion in Prolonged Working Lives in Europe

Committees: RC11 Sociology of Aging, RC30 Sociology of Work

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizer: Andreas MOTEL-KLINGEBIEL, *Linköping University, Sweden*

Chair: Anna WANKA, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

Panelists: Andreas MOTEL-KLINGEBIEL, *Linköping University, Sweden*; Wiebke SCHMITZ, *Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, Germany*; Nehle PENNING, *TU Dortmund University, Germany*; Gulin OYLU, *Linköping University, Sweden*; Jolanta PEREK-BIALAS, *Jagiellonian University, Poland* and Rachel CROSSDALE, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*

AU t Ho RS An D PAPERS:

JS-142.1 Rachel CROSSDALE, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*; Liam FOSTER, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom* and Alan WALKER, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
Dynamics of an Extended Working Lives Policy Agenda and Life Course Focussed Policies: A Four-Country Comparison of Macro-Social and Political Economic Change on Late Working Life Exclusion and Inequality

JS-142.2 Gulin OYLU, *Linköping University, Sweden*; Sussane KELFVE, *Linköping University, Sweden* and Andreas MOTEL-KLINGEBIEL, *Linköping University, Sweden*
Part of the Problem or Part of the Solution: The Ambiguous Contribution of Companies and Branches to Inequality and Exclusion from Late Work in Sweden

JS-142.3 Wiebke SCHMITZ, *Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, Germany*
How Does the Covid-19 Pandemic Affect Late Working Life? European Employment Trajectories from 2011 to 2021

JS-142.4 Jolanta PEREK-BIALAS, *Jagiellonian University Krakow, Poland*; Anna URBANIAK, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*; Natalia KRYGOWSKA-NOWAK, *Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland* and Maria VARLAMOVA, *Jagiellonian University Krakow, Poland*
Extending Working Life in Poland: Supportive and (Un) Supportive Solutions Implemented By Employers Towards Older Workers

JS-142.5 Nehle PENNING, *TU Dortmund University, Germany*; Rachel CROSSDALE, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom* and Monika REICHERT, *TU Dortmund University, Germany*
Inequalities in Lifelong Learning throughout the Life Course – Results from a Qualitative Study from Four European Countries

JS-143 tax Policies and tax optimization Practices

Committees: RC02 Economy and Society, RC12 Sociology of Law

Location: P1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Mailys GANTOIS-MALDAGUE, *Université Paris 1 - Panthéon Sorbonne, France* and Antoine VION, *University of Nantes, France*

Chair: Dennis MCNAMARA, 3700 O St NW, USA

AUT HORS AND PAPERS:

JS-143.1 Mailys GANTOIS-MALDAGUE, *Université Paris 1 - Panthéon Sorbonne, France*
Employer tax optimization strategies and practices. An ethnographic eye from the solicitor job

JS-143.2 Antoine VION, *University of Nantes, France* and Mailys GANTOIS-MALDAGUE, *Université Paris 1 - Panthéon Sorbonne, France*
Enrich the sociology of tax evasion. Preponderance of British Virgin Islands in the architecture of offshore financial circuits extracts from data leakage

JS-143.3 Alice KROZER, *El Colegio de México, Mexico*; Natalia TORRES, *Colmex, Mexico*; Raymundo CAMPOS, *Colmex, Mexico* and Aurora RAMÍREZ, *Colmex, Mexico*
Governing Inequality: Tax Perceptions, Redistributive Preferences and Expectations Towards the State Among the Political Elite in Mexico

JS-143.4 Marie QUARREY, *University of Geneva, Switzerland*
Border Optimisation. Issues and Genesis of the Social Construction of Tax Optimisation Practices at the Franco-Swiss Border By Professionals

JS-143.5 Florencia Fu-Chuan HUANG, *Graduate Institute of Latin American Studies, Taiwan*
Debt, Loan and National Development in 21st Century Argentina: Fiscal Social Contract Approach

Discussion

JS-144 Women Entrepreneurs on the African Continent and Beyond

Committees: RC09 Social Transformations and Sociology of Development, RC02 Economy and Society

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2 LiRIS EA 7481, France* and Dorina ROSCA, *The American University of Moldova, Moldova*

Chair: Dieter NEUBERT, *University of Bayreuth, Germany*

AUT HORS AND PAPERS:

JS-144.1 Ulrike SCHUERKENS, *Université Rennes 2 LiRIS EA 7481, France* and Seydi Ababacar DIENG, *Université Cheikh Anta Diop, Dakar, Senegal*
Women Entrepreneurs in Senegal

JS-144.2 Paul DIEDHIOU, *Rennes 2 et UCAD, Senegal*
La Multinationale « Auchan » Au Sénégal : Une Source d'Approvisionnement Pour Les Femmes Vendeuses d'Étalage à Mbour (Thiès)

JS-144.3 Moustapha SEYE, *LARTES-IFAN/Université Cheikh Anta Diop De Dakar, Senegal*
Femmes Entrepreneures Et Logiques Entrepreneuriales Dans Le Secteur Informel Au Sénégal

JS-144.4 Sutawan SATJASOMBOON, *Maejo University, Thailand*; Pusanisa THECHATAKERNG, *Meajo University, Thailand* and Pheeraya WONGSARANUCHIT, *Meajo University, Thailand*
The Challenges of Young Female Social Entrepreneurs after Covid 19: A Case Study of Mueang Pon Village, Mae Hong Son, Thailand

12:30 - 14:20

JS-145 Environment and Work: Links and threats

Committees: RC30 Sociology of Work, RC24 Environment and Society

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada*

Chair: Elizabeth HUMPHRYS, *University of Technology Sydney, Australia*

AUT HORS AND PAPERS:

JS-145.1 Jai COOPER, *University of Newcastle, Australia*
'How Did Us Cutting Down Trees Fight Climate Change?' - Environmental Workfare and Disillusion

JS-145.2 Maria Eugenia LONGO, *INRS, Canada* and Stéphanie BEXIGA, *INRS / Chaire-réseau de recherche sur la jeunesse du Québec, Canada*
Green Jobs for Young People: Policies and Controversies

JS-145.3 Patrick LUCAS, *UNSW, Australia*
Re-Thinking Biodiversity Conservation Work on Agricultural Land

JS-145.4 Marco ALBERIO, *Università di Bologna, Italy*
In Search for Profit and Environmental Protection. a Possible Combination? the Fisheries Sector in Québec

JS-145.5 Orin LOCKYER, *BRANZ, New Zealand*
Transitioning to Sustainable Practices in the Development of Apprentices in the Construction Sector in a Time of Emergency.

JS-146 Gendered intergenerational Experiences of Social Mobility in Migration**Committees:** RC32 Women, Gender and Society, RC38 Biography and Society**Location:** 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizers:** Ursula APITZSCH, Goethe University, Germany; Manashi RAY, West Virginia State University, USA and Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, Institute for Social Research at Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany**Chair:** Ursula APITZSCH, Goethe University, Germany**AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:****JS-146.2** Laeek SIDDIQUI, International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai, India and Namrata SHOKEEN, Monk Prayogshala, India
Intergenerational Mobility in Education Among Women: A Micro-Level Study from Weavers' Community of Varanasi, India**JS-146.3** Minna-Kristiina RUOKONEN-ENGLER, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Climbing up Together? Intergenerational, Gendered Negotiations of Upward Social Mobility in Migrant Families**JS-146.4** Sandla NOMVETE, Nelson Mandela University, South Africa
Understanding the Agency of Women, Power Shifts in Migrant Households in Mpondoland and How That Begets Continued Migrant Labour By Men to the Mines.**JS-147 Historical Sociology of organizations. Part ii****Committees:** RC56 Historical Sociology, RC17 Sociology of Organization**Location:** M4 (Crown)**Session organizers:** Robert VAN KRIEKEN, University of Sydney, Australia and Stewart CLEGG, UTS, Australia**AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:****JS-147.1** Jualynne DODSON, Michigan State University, USA
Church Building in the African Diaspora: Oriente Cuba**JS-147.2** Emrah YILDIZ, ankara haci bayram veli university, Turkey
Experts Isomorphism: Institutional Transformation in Turkey, 1950-1960**JS-147.3** Yoshinori KASAI, Keio University, Japan
Voluntary Association As a Predecessor of Resident Self-Governing Bodies in Japan**JS-148 Language on/of Youth Under COVID-19 Pandemic****Committees:** RC25 Language and Society, RC34 Sociology of Youth**Location:** P1 (Crown)**Session organizers:** Keiji FUJIYOSHI, Otemon Gakuin University, Japan and Asami SENOO, Otemon Gakuin University, Japan**Chair:** Asami SENOO, Ritsumeikan University, Japan**AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:****JS-148.1** Helena HELVE, Tampere University, Finland
Hermeneutic-Phenomenological Research on Young People's Individual Experiences of the COVID-19 Pandemic and Their Thoughts about Future**JS-148.2** Anna ODROWAZ-COATES, Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland and Urszula MARKOWSKA-MANISTA, University of Warsaw, Poland
COVID-19 Pandemic Situation Experienced By Polish Youths in Light of the Participatory Research Approaches**JS-148.3** Josiane MARTIN-O'BRIEN, International University of Monaco (IUM), Monaco
What Young People Say about Meeting New Friends during 2021 Pandemic**JS-148.4** Gatitu KIGURU, Kenyatta University, Kenya and Purity NTHIGA, KENYATTA UNIVERSITY, Kenya
In Campus Away from Campus: Perspectives on Learning during COVID-19 from Students in a Kenyan University**JS-149 Political Economy and Violence: the implications of taking Violence Seriously for theories of Hegemonic and Counter-Hegemonic Forces****Committees:** RC02 Economy and Society, TG11 Violence and Society**Location:** 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizer:** Heidi GOTTFRIED, Wayne State University, USA**Chair:** Heidi GOTTFRIED, Wayne State University, USA**Discussants:** William CARROLL, University of Victoria, Canada and Margaret ABRAHAM, Hofstra University, USA**AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:****JS-149.1** Sylvia WALBY, Royal Holloway, University of London, United Kingdom
Political Economy and Violence: The Implications of Taking Violence Seriously for Theories of Hegemonic and Counter-Hegemonic Forces

14:30 - 16:20

JS-150 Female Employment, Gender Equality and Women Empowerment across the Globe**Committees:** RC32 Women, Gender and Society, RC20 Comparative Sociology**Location:** 105 (Melbourne Convention Centre)**Session organizers:** Tatiana KARABCHUK, United Arab Emirates University, United Arab Emirates; Natalia SOBOLEVA, National Research University Higher School of Economics, Russian Federation and Malina VOICU, GESIS Leibniz Institute for Social Sciences, Germany**Co-Chair:** Tatiana KARABCHUK, UAE University, United Arab Emirates**AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:****JS-150.1** Amy RAUB, WORLD Policy Analysis Center, University of California Los Angeles, USA
Understanding How Laws and Policies Contribute to the Economic Gender Gap in 193 Countries**JS-150.2** Neeru GUPTA, University of New Brunswick, Canada and Sarah BALCOM, University of New Brunswick, Canada
Gender Occupational Segregation and Wage Gaps in the Policy Research Workforce: A Neglected Dimension to Developing Gender-Responsive Policies

JS-150.3 Brett WOODS, *Victoria University, Australia*; Ruth LISTON, *Victoria University, Australia*; Tim CORNEY, *Victoria University, Australia* and Fiona MACDONALD, *Victoria University, Australia*
Tackling Inequality in Construction Trades Training through Gender Transformative Pedagogy

JS-150.4 Sneha KADYAN, *OP Jindal Global University, Jindal Global Business School, India*
The Impact of COVID-19 on Garment Workers in India: Recovery with Women Empowering Alternative Models, Fair Trade

JS-150.5 Carolina COIMBRA VIEIRA, *Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Germany* and Marisa VASCONCELOS, *IBM Brazil, Brazil*
Contrasting Global Gender Gaps in STEM Using Facebook Data and Offline Indicators

JS-150.6 Frances Michelle NUBLA, *Ateneo de Naga University, Philippines*
Barriers to Women's Economic Participation: The Case of a Small Island Community in the Philippines

DiSt RiBUT ED PAPERS:

JS-150.7 Illescas Estévez, Eladia ILLESCAS, *Universidad de Malaga, Spain*; Ruben MARTIN GIMENO, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*; Eva CATAÑO GARCÍA, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*; Raúl LUCENA MARTÍNEZ, *Universidad de Granada, Spain*; Ana ANDREU PEREZ, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain* and Tristán PERTÍÑEZ BLASCO, *Fundación Pública Centro de Estudios Andaluces, Spain*
¿Cómo Perciben Las Mujeres Su Papel En La Sociedad? Retos De Futuro De Las Mujeres Del Sur De Europa

JS-151 Organising Precarity and inequality in the Gig Economy

Committees: RC17 *Sociology of Organization*, RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

Location: CCH1 (Crown)

Session organizers: Norbert EBERT, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Selvaraj VELAYUTHAM, *Macquarie University, Australia*

Chair: Selvaraj VELAYUTHAM, *Macquarie University, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-151.1 Tiago VIEIRA, *European University Institute, Italy*
More Than a Gig: Algorithmic Management and Human Authority in Salaried Platform Work - Implications for the Future of Employment

JS-151.2 Youngrong LEE, *University of Toronto, Canada*
The Contested Making of Gig Workers: A Comparative Study of Global Capital and Organized Labour in the Gig Economy in Seoul and Toronto

JS-151.3 Macarena BONHOMME, *Universidad Autónoma de Chile, Chile* and Funda USTEK-SPILDA, *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*
Making the Commoditized Worker: Work Precarity and the Acts of Resistance of Migrant Workers in the Gig Economy in Chile

JS-151.4 Adarsh KUMAR, *Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Germany*
Migrant Workers of Colour in Platform Economy: A Case of Uber in the United Kingdom

JS-151.5 Norbert EBERT, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Amanda WISE, *Macquarie University, Australia*; Shaun WILSON, *Macquarie University, Australia* and Nicholas HARRIGAN, *Macquarie University, Australia*
Gig Economy, Migration Status and Precarious Work

JS-152 Religion As an instrument of Rooting for the Liquid identity of Migrants Part 2

Committees: RC22 *Sociology of Religion*, RC31 *Sociology of Migration*

Location: 106 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizers: Letizia CARRERA, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy* and Paolo CONTINI, *University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy*

Chair: William CALVO-QUIROS, *American Culture and Latina/o Studies | University of Michigan, USA*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-152.1 Anisha DATTA, *Western University, Canada* and Indranil CHAKRABORTY, *Concordia University, Canada*
Migrants and Religious Identity in Canada: A Critical Examination of the Canadian Hindu Diaspora's Media

JS-152.2 Kristina KOVALSKAYA, *Groupe Sociétés, Religions, Laïcités, France*
Post-Soviet Muslims in Europe: Recycling the National into the Religious?

JS-152.3 Sandra PERTEK, *University of Birmingham, United Kingdom*
Adapted Religious Coping: Strategies and Effects in Experiences of Gender-Based Violence and Forced Displacement

JS-152.4 Kenneth VAUGHAN, *University of Central Oklahoma, USA*
Religion and Attitudes Toward Migrants: Understanding the Role of National Religious Contexts

JS-153 The Language of Risk. Part ii

Committees: TG04 *Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty*, RC25 *Language and Society*

Location: 203 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session organizer: Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

Chair: Jens ZINN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*

AUthoRS AnD PAPERS:

JS-153.1 Martin FRENCH, *Concordia University, Sociology & Anthropology, Canada*; Pierre-Olivier JOURDENNAIS, *Concordia University, Canada*; Patrizia VILLOTTI, *Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada* and Eva MONSON, *Université de Sherbrooke, Canada*
The Risks of Gambling Studies: A Critical Analysis

JS-153.2 Chabel KHAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia*
Policing the (risky) Family: Examining Mass Media Representations of Risk As Sites of Social Control

JS-153.3 Evelyn KISEMBE, *Moi University, Kenya* and Sarah NAKHONE, *Moi University, Kenya*
Medicine, Language and Risk Concealment: A Linguistic Analysis of Patient Information Leaflets in Kenya.

JS-153.4 Vanessa MCDERMOTT, *University of New South Wales, Australia*
Risk-Shifting in the Time of COVID-19: The Australian Federal Government Response and Support for Family Day Care Providers

JS-154 trade Unions Under Authoritarianism in the Global South**Committees:** RC30 *Sociology of Work*, RC44 *Labor Movements***Location:** P1 (Crown)**Session organizers:** Isil ERDINC, *Universite libre de Bruxelles, Belgium* and Atakan CIFTCI, *Bogazici University, Turkey***Chair:** Joerg NOWAK, *Universidade de Brasilia, Brazil***AU t H o R S A n D P A P E R S:**

JS-154.1 Carolina VESTENA, *Institute for Development and Peace, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany*
Labour and Socioeconomic Conflicts Under an Authoritarian Project: A Case Study on the Textile and Coffee Production Chains in Brazil

JS-154.2 Jose RAMALHO, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*; Tarik HAMDAN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil* and Leonardo AUCAR, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*
Trade Unions Under Attack: Labor Reforms and the Dismantling of Social Rights in Brazil

JS-154.3 Alpkam BIRELMA, *Ozyegin University, Turkey*
Struggle between Growing Labor Militancy and Authoritarianism: The Case of Turkey

JS-154.4 Benjamin VELASCO, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines*
Laboring Under Authoritarianism and the Pandemic: Workers' Repression and Resistance in the Philippines, Myanmar, Hong Kong and Indonesia

JS-154.5 Achalie KUMARAGE, *School of Regulation and Global Governance, Australian National University, Australia*
Labour Regulation in Global Apparel Supply Chains: Collective Voice in the Place of Collective Bargaining?

JS-154.6 Mrinmoy MAJUMDER, *UCA, United Kingdom*
The Historical Legacy of Trade Unions in India

Associations of Sociology

Monday 26 June

15:30 - 17:20

857 Health and Well-being of Individuals in East Asia: Changes from 2010 through 2021

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Noriko IWAI, *JGSS Research Center, Osaka University of Commerce, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

857.1 Jae-Mahn SHIM, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*; Jibum KIM, *Sungkyunkwan University, Republic of Korea* and Heijin OH, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*
Interplays of Subjective Health, Objective Health, and Health Beliefs in Korea

857.2 Chyi-in WU, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan* and Yi-fu CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*
The Impact of Social Capital upon Health and Well-Being of Individuals in Taiwan: Changes from 2010 through 2021

857.3 Satomi YOSHINO, *JGSS Research Center, Osaka University of Commerce, Japan*; Noriko IWAI, *JGSS Research Center, Osaka University of Commerce, Japan* and Takayuki SASAKI, *Osaka University of Commerce, Japan*
Social Exclusion and Well-Being of Older Persons in Japan: Comparison between 2010 and 2021

857.4 Weidong WANG, *Renmin University of China, China* and Yisong HU, *Renmin University of China, China*
Effect of the COVID-19 Epidemic on Body Mass Index: A Natural Experiment Result Based on the Wuhan Lockdown

Tuesday 27 June

15:30 - 17:20

858 Looking Back to Move Forward: European Sociological Legacy Revisited

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Maria Carmela AGODI, *University of Naples Federico II, Italy* and Teresa SORDE-MARTI, *Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

858.1 Ligia FERRO, *Associação Portuguesa de Sociologia, Portugal*
Beyond Borders: The Contribution of European Sociology to Approaching Migrations and Cultural Diversity

858.2 Piotr SZTOMPKA, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*
European Sociological Theory Thirty Years Later

858.3 Frank WELZ, *University of Innsbruck, Austria*
European Sociology: Cognitive Promises and Institutional Realities

858.4 Marta SOLER GALLART, *Universidad de Barcelona, Spain*
Turning Dialogic: The Role of European Sociology in Breaching the Gap between Science and Society

Wednesday 28 June

15:30 - 17:20

859 Pacific Indigenous Sociology

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Debra CABRERA, *University of Guam, Guam*

ROUNDTABLES:

The Indigenous Educational Experience

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

859.1 Kirk JOHNSON, *University of Guam, Guam*
Teaching and Learning in Micronesia: Exploring Island Centered Pedagogy through the Lens of Island Wisdom

859.2 Carol SIMPSON-WARNER, *University of Guam, Guam*; Christopher GARCIA-SANTOS, *University of Guam, Guam*; Teresita PEREZ, *University of Guam, Guam* and Sharleen SANTOS-BAMBA, *University of Guam, Guam*
Weaving Community in the Classroom: Co-Teaching for Community Building in Pacific Island Higher Education

Cultural Shifts

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

859.3 Josiah MESNGON, *University of Guam, Guam*
Changing Tides: A Look into Shifting Cultural Trends in Micronesia

859.4 Ulysses STORY, *University of Guam, Guam*
Indigenous Neighborhoods in the 21st Century: Food As a Connection to Culture and Community

Guåhan Women

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

859.5 Briante BARRETTO, *University of Guam, Guam* and Anesha IGNACIO, *University of Guam, Guam*
Gender Role Expectations and Family Life Satisfaction Among Guåhan Women

859.6 Chelsea GONZALES, *University of Guam, Guam*; Nicole MARIN, *University of Guam, Guam*; Debra CABRERA, *University of Guam, Guam* and Haley CARREON, *University of Guam, Guam*
Generational and Ethnic Differences in Fear of Victimization Among Guåhan Women

Indigenous Experience with Social Challenges

ROUNDTABLE AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

859.7 Rochelle ALVIZ, *University of Guam, Guam*
Social Construction of Mental Illness in Micronesia

859.8 Annie Fay CAMACHO, *University of Guam, Guam*
Charting the Fortitude of Traditional Seafaring in Micronesia

859.9 Anesha IGNACIO, *University of Guam, Guam*
CHamoru Attitudes on Native Language and Culture

859.10 Aira Kristine HERMOSURA, *University of Guam, Guam*
Diabetes and Cultural Lifestyles of Micronesian Ethnicities in Guam

Thursday 29 June

15:30 - 17:20

860 The Restoration of Justice and Human Rights

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Dong Hoon SEOL, *Jeonbuk National University, Republic of Korea*Chair: Hyun-Chin LIM, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*Co-Chair: Jin Kyu LEE, *Committee for the Five Northern Korean Provinces, and Korea University, Republic of Korea*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

860.1 Il Joon CHUNG, *Korea University, Republic of Korea*
Does Judicialization of Politics Promote Justice? Displacement of South Korean Politics

860.2 Suk-ki KONG, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*
Reclaiming Democratic Citizenship Against Algocracy in the Pandemic Era

860.3 Hyomin PARK, *University of Seoul, Republic of Korea* and Wonho JANG, *University of Seoul, Republic of Korea*
The Effect of Uncertainty on Justice Evaluations

860.4 Chunwoong PARK, *Jeonbuk National University, Republic of Korea*
Developmental Mind in Post-Colonial Cold War South Korea, 1960-1980s

860.5 Joon HAN, *Yonsei University, Republic of Korea*
Human Rights Situation in South Korea: Results from National Social Surveys

860.6 Dong Hoon SEOL, *Jeonbuk National University, Republic of Korea* and Taeseok JEONG, *Jeonbuk National University, Republic of Korea*
Social Identities and Mutual Perceptions of the Two Types Migrants Created By the Division System of Korean Peninsula

861 The Toolkit of Emerging Autocrats. Part I

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Cecilia MENJIVAR, *University of California Los Angeles, USA* and Deisy DEL REAL, *University of Southern California, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

861.1 Michael KENNEDY, *Brown University, USA*
Autocracies in Practice: Historical Legacies, Cultural Articulations and Violence Among Putin, Trump, Orban and Their Kin in Democracies' Assaults

861.2 Basia VUCIC, *Maria Grzegorzewska University, Poland*
How to Destroy an Empire - By Herbert Hoover & Friends

861.3 Gabriela FRIED AMILIVIA, *California State University Los Angeles, USA*
Infamous Confessions: Perpetrators and Right-Wing Discourse in the 50th Anniversary of the Civic-Military Dictatorship in Uruguay (1973-2023)

861.4 Eric BROWN, *University of Missouri, USA*
Trumpism As Fascism: New Politics of White Supremacy and Authoritarianism

Friday 30 June

15:30 - 17:20

862 Recovery, Resilience, and Regeneration beyond Disasters

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Koichi HASEGAWA, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

862.1 Noriko IWAI, *JGSS Research Center, Osaka University of Commerce, Japan* and Kuniaki SHISHIDO, *Osaka University of Commerce, Japan*

Has Japan's Resilience Enhanced through Repeated Disasters? Based on Japanese General Social Surveys (JGSS) and a Survey Conducted in Coastal Areas Affected By the Great East Japan Earthquake

862.2 Ryosuke TAKAKI, *Shokei Gakuin University, Japan* and Saori KAWAZOE, *Toyo University, Japan*
Reconstruction Process and the Problems on Evacuation Area in Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Accidents

862.3 Keiko IKEDA, *Shizuoka University, Japan*
Women and Community Disaster Resilience in Post-3.11 Japan

862.4 Takashi TSUJI, *National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan* and Yoshihiko KURODA, *Sugiyama Jogakuen University, Japan*
The Reconstruction Process and the Function of Community Resilience in Tsunami-Affected Areas of the Great East Japan Earthquake: The Case of Onagawa Town

898 The Toolkit of Emerging Autocrats. Part II

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Cecilia MENJIVAR, *University of California Los Angeles, USA* and Deisy DEL REAL, *University of Southern California, USA*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

897.1 Heba KHALIL, *Nebraska Wesleyan University, USA*
"This Country Has Laws": Rule of Law As a Tool of Entrenching Autocracy

897.2 Kennedy chi-pan WONG, *University of Southern California, USA*
Counter-Movements, Surveillance, and Assaults: Mobilizing Pro-Regime Diasporas As Non-State Agents of Transnational Repression

897.3 Luiza DE ABREU MONETTI, *University of California, Los Angeles, USA*
Father Knows Best: Delegitimizing the Press As a Political Strategy in Bolsonaro's Brazil

897.4 Xiaoxu YANG, *Louisiana State University, USA*
Legitimacy through Nationalism: The Evidence for the Retreat of Democracy from China

Professional Development

Monday 26 June

19:30 - 20:50

863 Getting Active with the United Nations

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Jan Marie FRITZ, *Univ. of Cincinnati and Univ. of Johannesburg, USA*

Panelists: Rosemary BARBERET, *John Jay College of Criminal Justice, CUNY, USA*; Allison LOCONTO, *Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE), France*; Lucie VIDOVICOVA, *Masaryk University, Czech Republic*; Michele FORD, *The University of Sydney, Australia*; Rhoda REDDOCK, *The University of the West Indies, Trinidad and Tobago* and Michael SAKS, *University of Suffolk, United Kingdom*

864 Turning Research into Publications in Sociology Journals

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Karim MURJI, *University of West London, United Kingdom* and Sarah NEAL, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*

Chairs: Karim MURJI, *University of West London, United Kingdom* and Sarah NEAL, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*

Tuesday 27 June

19:30 - 20:50

865 How to get into the international publication game if you are a scholar from the Global South

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

Chair: Eloisa MARTIN, *Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

866 In Conversation with Senior Sociologists: Making Connections, Bridging Generations

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Melbourne Room (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Filomin GUTIERREZ, *University of the Philippines Diliman, Philippines* and Chih-Jou Jay CHEN, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

Co-Chair: Elina OINAS, *University of Helsinki, Finland*

Panelists: Stephane DUFOIX, *University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France*; Michael BURAWOY, *University of California, USA*; Wan-Chi CHEN, *National Taipei University, Taiwan*; Siri HETTIGE, *University of Colombo, Sri Lanka*; Mohammed BAMYEH, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*; Raewyn CONNELL, *University of Sydney, Australia* and Margaret ABRAHAM, *Hofstra University, USA*

Discussants: Fumiya UCHIKOSHI, *Princeton University, USA*; Chungse JUNG, *SUNY Cortland, USA*; Yingjian LIANG, *Indiana University, USA*; Federico Maria JELO DI LENTINI,

University of Catania, Italy; Karmvir PADDA, University of Waterloo, Canada; Vaclav MASEK, Center for Advanced Genocide Research, Guatemala; Diego MAGGI, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; Bruno Henrique BARBOSA, Department of Sociology - Federal University of Sao Carlos (UFSCar - Brazil), Brazil; Sana AHMAD, WZB Social Science Center Berlin, Germany; Rahat SHAH, Institute of Sociology, Goethe university Frankfurt, Germany, Germany; Fareed KAVIANI, Monash University, Australia; Maria Virginia NESSI, IIGG-UBA/CONICET, Argentina; Katja STREHLE, Western Sydney University, Australia; Michelle KING, Queensland University of Technology, Australia; Heijin OH, Korea University, Republic of Korea; Xiaomin CAI, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; John Rey CODILLA, Davao Oriental State University, Philippines; Omid ASAYESH, University of Calgary, Canada; Xiangyu MA, University of Chicago, USA; Malgorzata GAWRONSKA, Uniwersytet Warszawski, Poland; Shilpa KRISHNAN, Indian Institute of Technology, Guwhatti, India; Hossein HAMDIEH, Humboldt University of Berlin, Germany; Mariana HASE UETA, University of Campinas, Brazil; Sandeepan TRIPATHY, National University of Singapore, Singapore; Sara MEJIA MUNOZ, The University of Queensland, Australia; Carmela FERRARA, University of Naples Federico II, Italy; Sandhya AS, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany; Subhaschandra MALLED, Gulbarga university, India; Ouafae ELARABI, Université Abdelmalek Essadi Tétouan, Morocco; Nishi FRANCIS, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, India; Daniel GUIGUI, University College Dublin, Ireland; Yvan YONAH, Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong; Shiene KIRIYA, University of Tokyo, Japan; Jowita RADZINSKA, SWPS University, Poland; Janina SUPPERS, University of Waikato, Germany; Julia LAUREAU, Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium; Yanwen WANG, National University of Singapore, Singapore; Masum BILLAH, Department of Sociology, East West University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; Kiran BEDI, Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana, India; M. M. Abdullah SONY, University of Debrecen, Hungary; Rachel ROWE, University of New South Wales, Australia; Zhaolun FAN, Tsinghua University, China; Liam MCLOUGHLIN, University of Technology Sydney, Australia and Khushboo DUTTA, BBAU, Lucknow, India

ROUNDTABLES:**Table A: Margaret Abraham**

Chair: Margaret ABRAHAM, Hofstra University, USA

Table B: Michael Burawoy

Chair: Michael BURAWOY, University of California, USA

Table C: Siri HETTIGE

Chair: Siri HETTIGE, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

Table D: Raewyn CONNELL

Chair: Raewyn CONNELL, University of Sydney, Australia

Table E: Wan-Chi CHEN

Chair: Wan-Chi CHEN, National Taipei University, Taiwan

Table F: Stephane DUFOIX

Chair: Stephane DUFOIX, University of Paris Nanterre, and Institut universitaire de France, France

Table G: Mohammed BAMYEH

Chair: Mohammed BAMYEH, University of Pittsburgh, USA

867 Public Sociology: Writing for Publics

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Gisela REDONDO-SAMA, Rovira i Virgili University, Spain and Breno BRINGEL, State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Chairs: Gisela REDONDO-SAMA, Rovira i Virgili University, Spain and Breno BRINGEL, State University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Wednesday 28 June

19:30 - 20:50

868 Principles Supporting Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in the ISA

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Debra DAVIDSON, University of Alberta, Canada

Chair: Debra DAVIDSON, University of Alberta, Canada

869 The backstage of Journal Editing and How to be a good reviewer

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Gabriel KESSLER, Universidad Nacional de La Plata-Conicet, Argentina and Juan PIOVANI, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina

Chairs: Gabriel KESSLER, Universidad Nacional de La Plata-Conicet, Argentina and Juan PIOVANI, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina

870 What Editors Look for In a Book Manuscript and How to Prepare Your Proposal

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain

Chair: Chaime MARCUELLO SERVOS, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain

Thursday 29 June

19:30 - 20:50

871 Doing Sociology Writing Workshop

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Rituparna PATGIRI, Indraprastha College for Women (IPCW), India; Maitrayee CHAUDHURI, Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), India and Deepali DUNGUNG, Ranchi University, India

Chairs: Rituparna PATGIRI, Indraprastha College for Women (IPCW), India; Maitrayee CHAUDHURI, Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), India and Deepali DUNGUNG, Ranchi University, India

872 How to Write a Book Review and Why It Is Important for Early-Career Scholars

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 3 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Junpeng LI, *Central China Normal University, China*

Chair: Junpeng LI, *Central China Normal University, China*

Friday 30 June

19:30 - 20:50

873 Managing Everyday Life as a Research-Focused Academic

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Sandra TORRES, *Uppsala University, Sweden*

874 Practicing Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in ISA Research Committees, Working Groups, and Thematic Groups

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Tina UYS, *University of Johannesburg, South Africa* and Laurence LAROCHELLE, *University of Sorbonne Nouvelle Paris III, France*

Chair: Debra DAVIDSON, *University of Alberta, Canada*

Author Meets Critics

Monday 26 June

17:30 - 19:20

875 Critical Engagement with Public Sociology: A Perspective from the Global South edited by **Andries Bezuidenhout, Sonwabile Mswana, Karl Von Holdt**

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Rhoda REDDOCK, *The University of the West Indies, Trinidad and Tobago*

Panelists: Karl VON HOLDT, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*; Andries BEZUIDENHOUT, *University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa*; Sonwabile MNWANA, *Rhodes University, South Africa*; Nandini SUNDAR, *University of Delhi, India* and Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

876 The Gift Paradigm: A Short Introduction to the Anti-Utilitarian Movement in the Social Sciences by **Alain Caillé**

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 217 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Chih-Jou Jay CHEN, *Academia Sinica, Taiwan*

Panelists: Alain CAILLÉ, *Université de Paris X Nanterre, France*; Craig CALHOUN, *Berggruen Centre, USA*; Farhad KHOSROKHAVAR, *EHEES, France* and Ilana SILBER, *Bar-Ilan University, Israel*

Tuesday 27 June

17:30 - 19:20

877 Diaspora as Translation and Decolonisation by **Ipek Demir**

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 207 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Laura OSO CASAS, *Universidad de Coruña, Spain*

Panelists: Ipek DEMIR, *University of Leeds, United Kingdom*; Helma LUTZ, *Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*; Aleksandra LEWICKI, *University of Sussex, United Kingdom* and Manuela BOATCA, *Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany*

Wednesday 28 June

17:30 - 19:20

878 Aesthetico-Cultural Cosmopolitanism and French Youth: The Taste of the World by **Vincenzo**

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Chair: Mounir SAIDANI, *Centre d'Études et de Recherches Économiques et Sociales, Tunisia*

Panelists: Vincenzo CICCHELLI, *Université Paris Cité - Ceped, France*; Sylvie OCTOBRE, *DEPS, France*; Victor ROUDOMETOF, *University of Cyprus POB 20537, Cyprus*; Dan WOODMAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Ian WOODWARD, *Syddansk Universitet, Denmark*

879 **Refuge beyond Reach: How Rich Democracies Repel Asylum Seekers by David Scott FitzGerald**

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: David FITZGERALD, *University of California San Diego, USA*

Chair: Jan Marie FRITZ, *Univ. of Cincinnati and Univ. of Johannesburg, USA*

Panelists: David FITZGERALD, *University of California San Diego, USA*; Paula BANJERJEE, *Calcutta Research Group, India*; Claire LOUGHNAN, *University of Melbourne, Australia* and Susan BANKI, *University of Sydney, Australia*

ISA Former Presidents

Wednesday 28 June

15:30 - 17:30

880 Former ISA Presidents Session: History of ISA and its twenty World Congresses of Sociology

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: Plenary 2 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Gisèle SAPIRO, *Ecole des hautes études en sciences sociales and CNRS, France*

Chair: Sari HANAFI, *American University of Beirut, Lebanon*

Panelists: Michael BURAWOY, *University of California, USA*; Margaret ABRAHAM, *Hofstra University, USA*; Piotr SZTOMPKA, *Jagiellonian University, Poland*; Michel WIEVIORKA, *Fondation Maison des Sciences de l'Homme, France*; Alberto MARTINELLI, *University of Milano, Italy*; Tom DWYER, *University of Campinas, Brazil* and T.K. OOMMEN, *Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

880.1 Gisèle SAPIRO, *Ecole des hautes études en sciences sociales and CNRS, France*
The Changing Role and Morphology of the ISA in Light of Its Congresses

880.2 Tom DWYER, *University of Campinas, Brazil*
Step by Step – ISA'S Last Quarter Century in Context

Ad Hoc Sessions

Monday 26 June

17:30 - 19:20

881 Atmospheres of the infra-ordinary

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizers: Andrea BRIGHENTI, *University of Trento, Italy* and Alice BROMBIN, *University of Trento, Italy*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

881.1 Lorenzo SABETTA, *Sapienza-University of Rome, Italy*
The Infra-Ordinary as a Privilege?

881.2 Mattias KARRHOLM, *Department of Architecture and Built Environment, Lund University, Sweden* and Fredrik TORISSON, *Department of Architecture and Built Environment, Lund University, Sweden*
The Infraordinary Life of Researchers: Meeting Places and Scientific Culture in the University-City of Lund, Sweden.

881.3 Federico LA BRUNA, *Università degli Studi di Milano and Università degli Studi di Torino, Italy*
Atmospheres of Distance. a Comparative Ethnography of Social Distancing between the Public Transport Systems of Milan and Amsterdam

Wednesday 28 June

17:30 - 19:20

882 Neighbour Culture Around the World: Challenges and Opportunities

Language: English, French, Spanish

Session Organizers: Margret KUSENBACH, *University of South Florida, USA* and Lynda CHESHIRE, *University of Queensland, Australia*

Chair: Lynda CHESHIRE, *University of Queensland, Australia*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

882.1 Sarah NEAL, *University of Sheffield, United Kingdom*
More Than Just Good Friends: Rethinking Neighbours in Contexts of Urban Multiculture

882.2 Talja BLOKLAND, *Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany*
Morals of Mothering As Neighbour Culture: Inclusions and Exclusions Among Women with Dependent Children in Berlin, Germany

882.3 Hone Mandefro BELAYE, *Concordia University, Canada*
Change and Continuities in Neighbour Relationships in Newly Emerging Condominium Neighbourhoods in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

882.4 Maria-Luisa MENDEZ, *Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile*
The Ordinary and the Exceptional of Neighbourhoods and Neighbour Culture

Thursday 29 June

17:30 - 19:20

883 Teaching the Sociology of Climate Change across the Sociology Curriculum

Location: 209 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Andrew SZASZ, *University of California, Santa Cruz, United States*

AUTHORS AND PAPERS:

883.1 Farhat NAZ, *Indian Institute of Technology Jodhpur, India*
Teaching Climate Change Course in an Engineering Institute

883.2 Shaikh Mohammad KAIS, *University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh*
Global Warming at the Margin: A Study of the Sociology of Climate Change in Bangladesh

883.2 Shaikh Mohammad KAIS, *University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh*
Global Warming at the Margin: A Study of the Sociology of Climate Change in Bangladesh

883.3 Emma PORIO, *Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines*
Teaching Sociology of Climate across the Curriculum: The Case of the Master of Disaster Risk and Resilience (MDRR) in Ateneo De Manila University, Philippines

883.4 Joy SEMIEN, *Texas A & M, United States*
Best Practices for Building Capacity within Environmental Justice Communities

883.5 Catherine Mei Ling WONG, *University of Amsterdam, Netherlands*
A Reflection on Teaching Environmental Sociology Using Amsterdam As a Living Lab

Friday 30 June

17:30 - 19:20

884 What Makes a Global Intellectual? The Joyful Seriousness of Robert Bellah

Language: English, French, Spanish

Location: 208 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Session Organizer: Armando SALVATORE, *McGill University, Canada*

Chair: Jeremy SMITH, *Federation University Australia, Australia*

Panelists: Mohammed BAMYEH, *University of Pittsburgh, USA*; Matteo BORTOLINI, *University of Padua, Italy, Italy*; Armando SALVATORE, *McGill University, Canada* and Kieko OBUSE, *Kobe City University of Foreign Studies, Japan*

ISA Administrative Meetings

Friday 23 June

09:00 - 19:30

885 ISA Executive Committee Meeting. Part I

Location: (University of Melbourne)

Saturday 24 June

09:30 - 19:30

886 ISA Executive Committee Meeting. Part II

Location: 218 (Melbourne Convention Center)

Sunday 25 June

10:30 - 12:30

887 Research Council. Business Meeting

Location: M12 (Crown)

14:00 - 16:00

888 Council of National Associations. Business Meeting

Location: M12 (Crown)

Monday 26 June

21:00 - 23:00

889 Candidates election speeches

Location: Plenary 1 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Wednesday 28 June

21:00 - 23:00

890 Assembly of Councils. Elections

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Thursday 29 June

17:30 - 19:30

891 Council of National Associations. Elections

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

21:00 - 23:00

892 Research Council. Elections

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

17:30 - 19:20

893 Training session RC/WG/TG officers

Location: 104 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Saturday 1 July

10:30 - 12:30

894 New Executive Committee meeting

Location: 216 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

12:30 - 14:00

895 Induction session new EC officers

Location: 103 (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Social Events

Sunday 25 June

20:15 - 22:30

896 Welcome Reception

Location: Main Foyer (Melbourne Convention Centre)

Friday 30 June

21:00 - 23:00

897 Farewell Party

Location: Conference Hall 1 (Crown, Level 2)

Program Coordinators

List of Program Coordinators:
Alphabetical and by Committee

Alphabetical

A

ABDULLAH, Noorman — **TG07**
ABREU, Alice — **RC23**
ADAMS, Tracey — **RC52**
ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, Patricia
Eugenia — **RC51**
ALVARADO MENDOZA, Arturo
— **RC29**
ANSON, Ofra — **RC41**
ARAGONA, Biagio — **RC33**
ASHEULOVA, Nadia — **RC23**

B

BAIMURZINA, Guzel — **RC30**
BAJARD, Flora — **RC30**
BALDASSAR, Loretta — **RC31**
BARBOSA NEVES, Barbara — **RC06**
BARROS, Nelson — **RC15**
BASS, Loretta — **TG03**
BECKER, Johannes — **RC38**
BENSKI, Tova — **RC48**
BHOOLA, Sheetal — **RC10**
BIANCHI, Alison — **RC42**
BOATCA, Manuela — **RC56**
BOESE, Martina — **RC05**

BRATCHFORD, Gary — **RC57**
BREZNAU, Nate — **RC20**
BRINGEL, Breno — **RC47**
BROWNE, Craig — **RC16**
BUENO, Arthur — **RC35**

C

CARLAND, Susan — **RC22**
CASSILDE, Stephanie — **RC25**
CASTRO, Celso — **RC01**
CHAUDHURY, Sukant — **RC13**
CHESTERS, Jennifer — **RC55**
CHETTY, Dasarath — **RC10**
COMI, Matt — **RC40**
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- RC02** —PITLUCK, Aaron
- RC03** —MATEOS MORA, Cristina; ZAPATA MOYA, Angel; KLEKOTKO, Marta; ZAAIMAN, Johan
- RC04** —VRYONIDES, Marios; ESSACK, Shaheeda
- RC05** —SPORLE, Andrew; COTE, Rochelle; LUTZ, Helma; BOESE, Martina; TAZREITER, Claudia
- RC06** —CZARNECKI, Lukasz; BARBOSA NEVES, Barbara
- RC07** —SOORYAMOORTHY, Radhamany
- RC08** —MAYSTOROVICH CHULIO, Natalia
- RC09** —SCHUERKENS, Ulrike; KHONDKER, Habibul
- RC10** —CHETTY, Dasarath; BHOOLA, Sheetal; FREDDANO, Michela
- RC11** —HAMILTON, Myra; WANKA, Anna
- RC12** —HOLDER, Robyn; WEBLEY, Lisa
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- RC14** —CONSTANTOPOULOU, Christiana
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- RC17** —GROTHER-HAMMER, Michael; VAN KRIEKEN, Robert
- RC18** —TOKUMITSU, Naoko; RODRIGUEZ BLANCO, Maricel
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- RC27** —SAM, Michael; MCLACHLAN, Fiona; JACKSON, Steven; SPAALJ, Ramon; MCDONALD, Brent; DAWSON, Marcelle
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- RC46** —UYS, Tina
- RC47** —BRINGEL, Breno; TAMBE, Shruti; ZAJAK, Sabrina; FADAEE, Simin
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- RC51** —ALMAGUER-KALIXTO, Patricia Eugenia
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- RC54** —FILGUEIRA DE ALMEIDA, Dulce; COOK, Craig
- RC55** —CHESTERS, Jennifer
- RC56** —BOATCA, Manuela; DOLAN, Paddy
- RC57** —PAUWELS, Luc; BRATCHFORD, Gary
- TG03** —BASS, Loretta
- TG04** —ZINN, Jens
- TG07** —ABDULLAH, Noorman; LOW, Kelvin; PATERSON, Mark
- TG09** —LYON, Katherine; TEZLI, Annette
- TG10** —NATHANSOHN, Regev; MARTON, Attila
- TG11** —WALBY, Sylvia; DAWSON, Myrna
- WG01** —VELIKAYA, Nataliya
- WG05** —RAJAN, Joseph Benhar; TEOTIA, Manoj Kumar
- WG06** —EASTWOOD, Lauren; SUAREZ-DELUCCHI, Adriana
- WG08** —NOBILE, Mariana; FLAM, Helena

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